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Book of Abstracts

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A NanoTR Panel:

Defense Innovation Through Nanotechnology: Industry Leaders Perspective!

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Preface

We are pleased to present the book of abstracts for the 19th International Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Conference (NanoTR-19), held at the METU Culture and Convention Center, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Türkiye, from August 27–29, 2025.

Since 2004, the NanoTR conference series has evolved from a national gathering into a premier global platform for nanoscience and nanotechnology advancement. NanoTR-19 brings together 785 registered participants, including 58 international attendees from 26 countries, comprising 212 academicians, 102 industry representatives, and 471 students. The conference features over 535 scientific presentations supported by more than 20 sponsors.

We are honored to feature four distinguished plenary speakers: Kourosch Kalantar-Zadeh (University of Sydney), Utkan Demirci (Stanford University), Michael Naguib (Tulane University), and Francesco Bonaccorso (Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia), alongside 32 invited speakers who provide valuable perspectives on fundamental and applied nanoscience.

A significant highlight is our dedicated panel on "Defense Innovation Through Nanotechnology: Industry Leaders Perspective," moderated by Cenk Aktaş and featuring prominent defense industry leaders including Mehmet Erim İnal, Hakan Aydemir, Rabia Günay, Fatih Say, Fatih Oral, and Olcay Elmalı Meço. This panel emphasizes the strategic role of nanoscience in addressing technological challenges and highlights the importance of academia-industry collaboration.

NanoTR-19 introduces enhanced features including dedicated symposia on Defense Applications & Materials Engineering, an Enhanced Industry-Academia Partnership Track, and an Innovation Showcase for nanotechnology companies to present cutting-edge solutions. These initiatives strengthen connections between research breakthroughs and practical implementation.

The conference's strength lies in uniting leading academics, early-career researchers, industry representatives, and students. We are particularly pleased with the strong participation of undergraduate and young researchers, ensuring NanoTR remains a hub for fostering the next generation of scientists.

We extend our gratitude to all participants, speakers, sponsors, and organizing committee members. Special thanks to Middle East Technical University for providing excellent facilities at the METU Culture and Convention Center.

We are confident that the discussions and collaborations during these three days will strengthen our scientific community and inspire new directions in nanoscience and nanotechnology research. This book of abstracts serves as a valuable resource and testament to the vibrant state of our field.

Warm regards,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee

Prof. Dr. H. Emrah ÜNALAN
Co-chair

Prof. Dr. Ali ÇIRPAN
Co-chair

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Batur ERCAN
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The industrial applications of 2D materials

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We will present our industrial strategy to scale up the production of 2D materials.^[1-3] The extensive use of 2D materials in various applications requires scalable, reliable, and inexpensive production processes,^[1-8] involving a balance between final product quality and ease of fabrication. We will demonstrate the efficiency of the manufacturing of high-quality 2D materials by wet-jet milling^[3] and the path towards industrial production.

Afterward, we will provide an overview on key applications of the as produced 2D materials. We will show how the production of 2D materials in liquid phase by wet-jet milling^[3] represents a powerful pathway towards the development of 2D materials-based next-generation devices, offering massive integration flexibility compared to other production methods. We will present insights in some applications.^[4-10]

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Flexible Printed Photodetectors: From Graphene Hybrids to Sustainable Electronics

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The evolution of flexible and sustainable electronics has paved the way for innovative solutions in wearable, textile-integrated, and biodegradable systems. In this talk, I will present our latest advances in printed optoelectronics, focusing on scalable strategies to integrate low-dimensional materials such as graphene, perovskites, and black phosphorus onto unconventional substrates.

I will showcase our high-performance graphene–perovskite fibre photodetectors, which exhibit remarkable responsivity ($\sim 22 \text{ kA W}^{-1}$) at a bias voltage of only 1 V, fast response times ($\sim 9 \text{ ms}$), and mechanical durability under bending and washing, demonstrating their strong potential for wearable and healthcare applications. Additionally, I will discuss our recent printed-lithography platform for paper-based photodetectors, achieving record-high responsivity ($\sim 82,000 \text{ A W}^{-1}$ at 520 nm with a bias of less than 1 V) through the integration of CVD graphene and perovskite quantum dots. This scalable, low-cost method avoids conventional cleanroom processes and aligns with the vision of environmentally friendly, large-area electronics.

As part of the talk, I will also highlight our emerging work on sustainable and ingestible electronics, underscoring new directions in transient and biocompatible sensing platforms for smart health monitoring.

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Engineered Electrocatalysts for PEM Fuel Cells and Electrolyzers: Graphene-Supported Pt for ORR Cathodes and Transition Metal Incorporated Iridium Oxides for OER Anodes

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Hydrogen energy systems, encompassing polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) fuel cells and electrolyzers, are essential for decarbonizing transportation and industrial sectors. Fuel cells electrochemically convert hydrogen to electricity, while electrolyzers use renewable electricity to produce green hydrogen via water splitting. The advancement of high activity, durable and cost-effective electrocatalysts for both systems represents a critical frontier. The oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at fuel cell cathodes and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) at electrolyzer anodes suffer from high kinetic barriers and overpotentials, catalyst degradation in acidic media, and high costs. While Pt-based materials remain the gold standard for cathodic ORR applications due to their exceptional activity and selectivity, metal oxide systems, particularly iridium (Ir) based compounds, dominate anodic OER catalysis in acidic environments. However, the high cost and scarcity of these noble metals present significant barriers to widespread commercialization. We engineered graphene-supported Pt nanoparticles as catalysts leveraging graphene's exceptional electrical conductivity, high surface area, and electrochemical stability to enhance Pt utilization efficiency and activity through optimized charge transfer kinetics^{1,2}. We employed various graphene supports including graphene nanoplatelets, reduced graphene oxide (rGO), functionalized graphenes, and graphene-based hybrids and demonstrated enhanced catalytic activity, reduced Pt loading and superior fuel cell performance^{1,2}. Moreover, we developed a novel photocatalytic deposition methodology, utilizing transition metal ions as both hole scavengers and surface modifiers for rGO, offering a precise control over Pt nanoparticle nucleation and growth^{3,4}. Further ORR enhancement was realized by integrating cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanorods and CeO₂/N-doped rGO composites, resulting in a significant reduction in Pt loading while maintaining or exceeding performance benchmarks⁵. For anodic OER in acidic PEM electrolyzers, we addressed the cost and scarcity of iridium oxide (IrO₂) through transition metal incorporation which significantly alters the distribution of electronic charge, affecting both the thermodynamic and kinetic characteristics of the OER. Doping IrO₂ with Ni or Co reduces activation energies, increases the exothermic behavior of the reactions, and boosts the overall catalytic performance. Our study focused on transition metal-incorporated IrO₂ catalysts synthesized via the sol-gel method. We demonstrated that incorporation of Mn, Ti, Ni reduced precious metal loading by 20% while enhancing OER activity in acidic media. Moreover, the integration of anodized TiO₂ nanotube arrays on Ti mesh substrates provided high-surface-area supports that further enhanced catalyst stability and activity. Our study confirms that advanced graphene architectures and transition metal-doped IrO₂ systems enable activity, stability and cost improvements essential for scalable PEM hydrogen technologies.

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Keyword: fuel cell, electrolyzer, electrocatalyst, ORR OER

Polycationic guanidine cyclodextrin nanoparticles for dual-targeted cancer treatment and combating drug resistance

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For the past several years, our research group have significantly advanced the field of cyclodextrin-based nanoparticle systems for addressing cancer therapy challenges—namely targeted delivery and drug resistance. Initially, we demonstrated that **polycationic amphiphilic cyclodextrin (PC-CD)** nanoparticles, formed via self-assembly, achieve high loading of anticancer agents like paclitaxel, exhibit controlled release, favorable biocompatibility, and enhanced cytotoxicity compared to free drug. These formulations penetrated MCF-7 tumor spheroids more deeply and achieved earlier antitumor onset in animal models, with reduced off-target organ accumulation. It was further shown that **blank polycationic cyclodextrin nanoparticles**—even without drug loading—displayed intrinsic anticancer activity, inducing apoptosis, downregulating P-glycoprotein, and restoring chemosensitivity in hepatocellular carcinoma spheroids.

Building on this, **Demirtürk and Bilensoy** engineered **dual-targeted cyclodextrin nanoparticles** conjugated with **rituximab (anti-CD20)** alongside encapsulated chemotherapeutics, aimed at overcoming drug resistance in **Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL)**. These guanidine-modified amphiphilic cyclodextrin (ACD) and polymeric cyclodextrin (PCD) nanoparticles were optimized to remain under 200 nm, stable in biological fluids, and demonstrated minimal hemolytic or complement-activating toxicity. In 2D and 3D lymphoma cell models, rituximab-conjugated, drug-loaded ACD nanoparticles yielded the greatest reduction in viability—statistically superior to free drug formulations ($p < 0.05$), via rituximab-dependent cytotoxicity. Importantly, in vivo studies in BALB/c mice established promising pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, safety, and antitumor efficacy: the rituximab-targeted, multidrug-loaded nanoparticles produced significant tumor suppression and showed potential to overcome R-CHOP therapy resistance even without corticosteroids.

Collectively, our findings support a **dual-targeting nanoparticle strategy** for cancer treatment: combining **passive tumor accumulation (EPR effect)**, **active targeting via polycationic surface groups and antibody conjugation**, and the ability to bypass drug resistance mechanisms. This multifunctional cyclodextrin platform offers a compelling paradigm to improve efficacy, limit toxicity, and tackle resistance across tumor types and delivery routes.

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Responsive Liquid Crystal-Aqueous Interfaces Reporting Mechanical and Chemical Changes

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The long-range orientational ordering and the sensitivity of the liquid crystal (LCs) interfaces against external stimuli offer opportunities towards new-generation sensing platforms. We investigate the structures and structural transitions in LCs induced by mechanical and chemical changes occurring at their interfaces with aqueous phases. We employ LC-aqueous interfaces formed by (i) emulsification of thermotropic LCs in aqueous phases, (ii) supporting LCs in microwells, and (iii) stabilization of LC-aqueous interfaces (virtual walls) by the preferential wetting of the two phases on a heterogeneous interface with distinct hydrophilic and hydrophobic functionalization. Our studies to date revealed that (i) LCs are responsive against mechanical shear and interfacial alignment conditions in microfluidics that result in easily observable optical changes, (ii) LCs respond to the fusion of the vesicles formed by phospholipids, which provide information about the mechanical properties of the vesicles, (iii) LCs can report aqueous phase reactions with no significant influence on the reaction kinetics. These results demonstrated that the LC-aqueous soft interfaced platforms present a promising candidate for future high-throughput sensing platforms.

Liquid Metal Colloids – A Unique Class Of Catalysts Towards Sustainability

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RMIT University

Liquid metals are an emerging class of compounds that are liquid close to room temperature yet exhibit metallic conductivity. Liquid metals have found application in the design of flexible and reconfigurable electronics and more recently emerged as a platform for the synthesis of nano-structures as well as a unique class of catalysts that is extraordinarily resilient towards deactivation. In comparison to other liquids such as covalent solvents and ionic liquids, comparatively little is known about the chemistry that occurs inside molten metals. This talk covers the emerging picture of liquid metal chemistry and will report our most recent results for solid-metal-in-liquid-metal colloidal systems. This talk will also draw on our recent results in the area of CO₂ reduction to graphene, liquid metal electrocatalysts and NH₃ synthesis.

Keyword: *Liquid Metal, Gallium, Fuel Cell, Ammonia*

Rational design of anode materials for practical Na-ion batteries

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Sodium-ion batteries (NIBs) have recently attracted growing interest, owing to the abundance and wide distribution of sodium resources, along with advantages such as low cost, improved safety, and excellent low-temperature performance. These features make them particularly promising for applications in large-scale energy storage. Despite significant progress in fundamental research and industrial development, practical NIBs currently achieve energy densities of around 120–150 Wh/kg, which remain lower than those of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). To bridge this gap, the development of high-capacity electrode materials is considered a crucial challenge. In this presentation, key application-oriented fundamental aspects of anode electrodes will be discussed. Special emphasis will be placed on synthesis strategies for stable and high-performance alloy/carbon anode materials, along with insights into structural evolution, interfacial properties, and sodium storage mechanisms.

This work is funded by the European Union (TwinBat- 101159770).

Oxford-UMAT: An Efficient and User-Friendly Crystal Plasticity Framework for Micro/Nanomechanics of Crystalline Solids

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Crystal plasticity-based finite elements has been used a numerical tool to incorporate crystallographic anisotropy to the models for more accurate prediction of the stress states. We have developed OXFORD-UMAT a crystal plasticity solver that has unique capabilities. The framework is equipped with two different solvers as backup of each other to deal with convergence problems associated with non-linear crystal plasticity problems including nanoindentation to microcantilever beam bending. The length scale dependence is incorporated using a new geometrically-necessary dislocation density (GND) based method and a unique backstress model for kinematic hardening . Material library contains a variety of materials with different crystal structure including the effects of irradiation. The framework is equipped with cohesive element library to deal with grain boundary or interface related fracture phenomena. The code is in the form of user material subroutine that works in a finite element software. The framework unlocks limitless possibilities for advanced constitutive model development, empowering users with the freedom to select their preferred numerical solver and customize material models.

Keyword: *crystal plasticity, nanomechanics, crystalline solids*

Engineering Supramolecular Bioactive Nanobiomaterials: Emerging Strategies for Tissue Regeneration and Translational Biomaterials

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Supramolecular nanobiomaterials represent a versatile platform for the design of next-generation regenerative therapies. Two distinct strategies have been developed to construct bioactive supramolecular systems with applicability in both soft and hard tissue engineering.

The first approach involves the use of synthetic peptide amphiphiles as modular building blocks. These amphiphilic molecules incorporate bioactive motifs—such as osteoinductive, neuroinductive, or angiogenic sequences—that self-assemble and interact with oppositely charged biopolymers through electrostatic forces. The resulting nanocomposite hydrogels exhibit tunable mechanical and biological properties suitable for bone regeneration, neural repair, and vascular tissue engineering. Their hierarchical architecture and biomimetic functionality enable enhanced cellular response and matrix remodeling.

The second approach leverages decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM) as a naturally derived scaffold for supramolecular organization. Organic components of dECM can act as templates for the nucleation of inorganic nanostructures, including fluoroapatite, thereby facilitating biomimetic mineralization. This strategy enables the creation of hybrid organic–inorganic materials with structural and compositional features resembling native bone and dental tissues. Such constructs offer improved bioactivity and integration potential in tissue-specific repair models.

Together, these methodologies illustrate the potential of supramolecular design in engineering functional biomaterials that integrate synthetic precision with biological complexity. The convergence of bottom-up molecular assembly and top-down bioinspiration offers a powerful toolkit for advancing translational outcomes in tissue regeneration.

Keyword: *Supramolecular Chemistry, Biomaterials, Peptide Nanofibres, Tissue Engineering*

Disposable sensors for next-generation diagnostics

Can Dincer *

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Disposable sensors are affordable and easy-to-use sensing devices for short-term or single-shot measurements. Over the last decade, they have become increasingly important for various applications, including from environmental, forensic, pharmaceutical, agricultural, and food monitoring to diagnostics, especially the point-of-care testing and wearables. In this talk, a broad spectrum of different biosensing approaches for next-generation on-site testing will be presented: (i) Multiplexed on-site therapeutic drug monitoring of antibiotics from invasive and non-invasive samples toward personalized antibiotherapy, (ii) CRISPR-powered electrochemical biosensors for nucleic-acid-amplification-free, simultaneous and on-site detection of multiple RNAs and other biomolecules for COVID-19 management, (iii) wearable microfluidic immunosensing devices for lab-on-a-bird applications and beyond, (iv) low-cost electrochemical paper-based wearable sensors that can be integrated to any type of facemask for wearable and continuous monitoring of breath biochemistry and/or testing of the infectious diseases such as coronaviruses from exhaled breath, and (v) light-controlled dynamic bioassays using optogenetic switches (OptoAssays) for wash- and pump-free point-of-care diagnostics.

Keyword: *Synthetic Biology, Microfluidics, Wearables, Multiplexed sensors*

Cellulose Photonics: Structuring Light with Bio-Based Liquid Crystals

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Cellulose photonics is an emerging field at the intersection of soft matter physics, optics, and sustainable materials science. It explores how cellulose-based materials, both colloidal and polymeric, can be structured across multiple length scales to manipulate light through interference and birefringence, producing vibrant structural colours without pigments. These photonic effects arise from the self-assembly of cellulose into cholesteric liquid crystalline phases and the light interference from the helicoidal architectures with periodicities in the visible range, offering a biodegradable and scalable alternative to conventional colour forming mechanisms.

Figure 1. a) Illustration of the 3d printing of the functionalised HPC mesophases with b) uniform structurally coloured filaments and c) the second-degree microstructural hierarchy induced by the shear forces through the 3d processing

In this talk, I will explore how we use cellulose-based systems to create colourful, functional materials through evaporation-driven self-assembly, 3D printing, and soft confinement. I will first introduce our work on cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), which form **left-handed** cholesteric mesophases in highly concentrated aqueous suspensions which can be retained in film form upon drying. I will discuss how the droplet drying process governs the final structure, and how mass transport, concentration gradients, and particle flow influence the self-assembly, pattern formation and the optical response [1-3].

I will also introduce our work on hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC), a water-soluble derivative of cellulose that forms **right-handed** cholesteric phases [4]. I will show how HPC serves as a model system for mechanochromic, printable, and edible photonic materials. I'll present examples where we exploit flow-induced alignment through 3d printing, elastomeric confinement, and doctor blading to induce hierarchical ordering, enabling stretchable colour sensors and angle-independent optical effects [5-7].

Together, these examples demonstrate how cellulose photonics can bridge precision ordering and scalable processing. From droplet assembly to stretchable sensors and printed microstructures, our work charts a path toward environmentally responsible optical materials capable of responding to touch, flow, and form.

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Very-Large-Scale Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces for Dynamic Control of Terahertz and Millimetre Waves

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Unlocking the potential of terahertz (THz) and millimeter (mm) waves for next generation communications and imaging applications requires reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) with programmable elements that can manipulate the waves in real-time. Realization of this technology has been hindered by the lack of efficient THz electro-optical materials and scalable THz semiconductor platform. Here, by merging graphene-based THz modulators and the thin-film transistor (TFT) technology, we demonstrate very-large-scale (>300000 pixels) spatial light modulator with individually addressable subwavelength pixels. We demonstrate electronically programmable reflection and transmission patterns of THz light over a large area with unprecedented levels of uniformity and reproducibility. To highlight the potential of these devices, we demonstrate a single pixel mm-wave camera capable of imaging metallic objects. Furthermore, we demonstrate dynamic beam steering with reconfigurable direction pattern. We anticipate that these results will provide realistic pathways to structure THz waves for applications in non-invasive THz imaging and next generation THz communications.

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Keyword: *graphene, terahertz*

From Nanosizing to Nanoconfinement - Materials Design Strategies Battery Electrodes

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Layered and two-dimensional materials can undergo electrochemically-induced intercalation reactions, where a chemical species is inserted between the layers without causing major structural changes to the host material. These materials are of particular interest for modern rechargeable batteries like the lithium-ion battery, where they serve as electrode materials to reversibly host the charge carrying ions in their interlayer space. To maximize charge storage performance, researchers typically optimize the chemical composition and/or morphology of the electrode materials. Here, the goals are to (1) increase the number of ions that can be stored reversibly in the host lattice (maximize energy) and to (2) increase the rate at which ions can be (de)intercalated (maximize power).

Nanosizing of electrode materials can lead to an increased specific surface area and thus, to improved kinetics of the electrochemical intercalation reaction due to reduced ion diffusion lengths. However, challenges associated with nanosized electrode materials are a reduced density and an increasing influence of parasitic reactions at the electrochemical interface.

The impact of nanoconfinement effects within electrode materials on electrochemical intercalation reactions is distinctly different from nanosizing effects, and is currently poorly understood. In my research group, model nanoconfinement materials are synthesized to elucidate the impact of nanoconfinement properties like interlayer distance and interlayer chemical environment on intercalation reactions.

In this contribution, I will introduce our efforts on understanding nanoconfinement-driven changes in ion intercalation properties and mechanisms using a series of model host materials with well-defined nanoconfinement properties.[1,2] This includes our recent discovery that there is a geometrical threshold of the interlayer spacing of bilayered V₂O₅ host materials above which the intercalation of partially solvated Li⁺ becomes evident.[1] Mechanistic understanding is achieved by my team's broad analytical toolkit to unambiguously identify electrochemical charge storage mechanisms, including electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), operando X-ray diffraction (XRD), electrochemical dilatometry (ECD) and electrochemical crystal quartz microbalance (EQCM).

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Keyword: *Electrochemical energy storage, Ion intercalation, Nanoconfinement effects, Interlayer spacing*

GaN Photonic Devices for Near-Eye Immersive Displays

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Emerging near-eye display technologies, such as holographic displays that use artificial intelligence (AI) to process data, recognize patterns, and make real-time decisions, require ultra-compact, high-performance light sources to project digital content onto the real world. This talk explores Gallium Nitride (GaN)-based visible light emitters, focusing on novel Horizontal-Cavity Surface-Emitting Superluminescent Diodes (SLDs). These devices leverage a single-mode, GaN ridge waveguide design with a 45° total internal reflector (TIR) to redirect emission outward while suppressing optical feedback, enabling partially coherent, broadband light ideal for reducing speckle and coherent light related artifacts in holography. We compare SLDs with laser diodes (LDs) and microLEDs in terms of image quality, power efficiency, and integration into AI-enabled glasses, where small eye-box size, form factor and power constraints pose significant challenges. The presentation will also highlight key performance metrics, including optical power, efficiency, and reliability. From a manufacturing perspective, we will examine chip-scale integration strategies, flip-chip bonding, heterogeneous & monolithic integration via transfer printing, and their compatibility with existing fabrication ecosystems. The advantages and limitations of each, including optical complexity, will be discussed, emphasizing the potential of GaN-based SLDs in next-generation immersive display systems.

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Keyword: *Horizontal-Cavity SLDs, Chip-scale integration, Speckle reduction, Near-eye displays*

Multifunctional Hybrid Nanomaterials for Integrated Opto-Electrochemical Biosensing in Health Status and Food Quality Monitoring

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Recent advances in nanomaterials and nanotechnology have opened new directions in creating innovative technologies for the architecture of advanced sensing systems for health monitoring and food contamination detection. In our work, versatile and efficient biosensing opto-electrochemical platforms were developed using carbon-based structures like polyhydroxylated fullerene (Fullerenol-FL), single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), often combined with metallic nanoparticles (e.g. platinum, gold) and the redox mediator Prussian blue (PB) for health status and food quality monitoring.

To enable the early and reliable detection of a wide range of analytes—from clinically relevant biomarkers to food safety indicators—specific aptasensors and enzyme-based biosensors were strategically integrated into miniaturized and portable bioanalytical platforms. A multiplex, flexible, wearable and portable patch based on novel FL-PB-Hydrogel nanomaterial was developed for simultaneous detection of glucose, lactate and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) from sweat. Cortisol was determined by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using a specific aptamer covalently bound to FL-modified sensors.

Miniaturized electrochemical biosensors were also designed for the sensitive detection of putrescine and histamine using SWCNT-PB and SWCNT-PtNPs nanocomposites. Monoamine and diamine oxidases were entrapped in sol-gel and chitosan matrices to build the biorecognition layer.

Electrochemical characterization confirmed high electrocatalytic activity toward H₂O₂, a key enzymatic reaction product. The excellent conductivity and structural properties of Fullerenol-based materials enhanced analytical performance, enabling selective detection of glucose and lactate, with sensitivities of 8.67 and 25.55 mA·M⁻¹·cm⁻², respectively.

The aptasensors developed by using AuNPs and specific aptamers for histamine and histidine were integrated in portable miniaturized opto-electrochemical tool allowing the sensitive and specific detection of histamine and histidine by EIS and electrochemiluminescence (ECL). The ECL determinations were performed in a solution containing 100 mM luminol and the co-reactant H₂O₂, after incubation with different concentrations of biogenic amines. For the EIS measurements, the value of the charge transfer resistance increases with the concentration of biogenic amine from 0.1 to 5 ng/mL, and at concentrations higher than 10 ng/mL a saturation of the signal was observed due to the "hook" effect.

It is important to note that the developed biosensors have also been used for the successful detection of histamine and putrescine in fish, chicken, cheese, sausages and beer, acting as spoilage indicators. The biosensors demonstrated sensitivity values of 6.25 and 153.7 mA·M⁻¹·cm⁻² for histamine and putrescine, respectively.

Overall, the systems we have developed offer versatile platforms capable of detecting multiple compounds in diverse fields - including medical diagnostics, environmental monitoring and food safety. Their portability, sensitivity and adaptability make them strong candidates for real-time, non-invasive applications that can contribute to improving quality of life and public health.

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Keyword: *Fullerenol, wearable patch, sweat, food safety*

Engineering the Invisible: The Next Frontier in Medicine and Biology

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The future of biology and medicine is being meticulously reshaped at the intersection of engineering, nanotechnology, chemistry, and materials science. Over the past decade, rapid progress in micro- and nanoscale technologies—alongside transformative advances in biomedical engineering—has sparked a wave of disruptive innovations aimed at resolving pressing challenges and longstanding unmet needs in the life sciences. Bridging the divide between engineering principles and biomedical applications necessitates the development of transformative platforms and next-generation methodologies. These span a wide array of technologies, including advanced biosensing systems, synthetic and polymeric receptors, microneedle-based therapeutics, extracellular vesicle (EV) engineering, and lab-on-a-chip devices. In this talk, Dr. Fatih Inci presents cutting-edge micro- and nanoscale platforms developed in his laboratory, engineered for the precise manipulation of biomolecules—such as proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids—as well as cells, pathogens, and EVs, which were once dismissed as biological noise. These platforms serve as practical, high-impact tools that address real-world challenges in diagnostics and therapeutics, contributing meaningfully to the advancement of human health. By integrating cellular engineering with multifunctional nanotechnological modalities, Dr. Inci's work yields highly sensitive, user-centric diagnostic and therapeutic solutions. These systems enable early detection of cancers, rapid identification of biomarkers for both acute and chronic diseases. Incorporating miniaturized, portable devices capable of real-time disease monitoring, his technologies place powerful diagnostic capabilities in the hands of individuals—ushering in a new era of personalized, precision healthcare. Through a deeply interdisciplinary approach, Dr. Inci and his team are redefining the landscape of biomedical innovation, pioneering technologies that challenge convention and expand the frontiers of personalized medicine.

Structuring of Hierarchical Porous Materials for Efficient CO₂ Capture Applications

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The structuring of advanced porous materials into application-specific shapes is critical to achieve high performance in energy and environmental technologies, including gas separation, air filtration, and energy conversion and storage. In this work, we present the development and structuring of hierarchical porous sorbents for CO₂ capture in key applications, such as biogas upgrading, post-combustion capture, and Direct Air Capture (DAC).

Separation processes based on Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) and Thermal Swing Adsorption (TSA) require sorbents with tailored porosity, morphology, and thermal properties. Different structuring strategies for zeolites and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) [1–3] have been evaluated, including shear granulation to prepare hierarchical porous granules and electrospinning to produce composite nanofibers. The impact of materials design and the structure of the sorbents on CO₂ uptake, selectivity, mass transfer kinetics, and thermal conductivity are analyzed to guide the optimization of the sorbents for implementation in specific applications.

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Keyword: *Carbon Capture, Porous Materials, Processing, Sorbents*

Functional Materials for Sensor Applications

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Sensitive, selective, low cost and practical analyte determination is one of the important research topics. For this purpose, studies on the development of different techniques are continuing and the studies carried out are quite promising. It is known that chemical sensors, which are effective and powerful analytical tools, have replaced classical methods. These analytical tools not only perform efficacious determination but also provide some advantages due to their suitability for on-site analysis. Chemical sensing enables the determination of an analyte through chemical information with the help of a sensing material and a transducer. The choice of materials used in sensing is the most important criterion for this potent performance. With the help of material chemistry and nanotechnology, different types of functional or functionalized materials are used for sensor applications. These include various materials such as metallic-based nanoparticles, carbon-based structures, polymeric structures, nanocellulose, dendrimers, and quantum dots [1-4]. In this context, the main theme of this presentation talks about nano or micromaterials (polymeric structures, metallic-based particles, carbon-based materials) related sensor studies that have the potential for use in the biomedical field. Among these sensing applications, electrochemical sensors and micro/nanomotor based recognition strategies will be summarized. These studies cover the preparation of functional electrodes and micro/nanomotors, their characterization steps and their use in the detection of nucleic acid, anticancer drug, DNA damage, amino acid, and cancer biomarker detection. Cancer cell line recognition will also be discussed.

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Keyword: *Chemical sensor, Electrochemical sensing, Micro/nanomotor*

The Synergy of Perovskite and 2D Materials: Enabling Sustainable Photovoltaics and Responsible Electronics

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The relentless pursuit of sustainable energy solutions and advanced electronics for applications like the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and ubiquitous sensing necessitates continuous innovation in materials science. This presentation highlights our group's recent breakthroughs in solution-processed advanced materials, emphasizing their transformative potential in high-performance photovoltaics, flexible electronics, and neuromorphic computing.

In photovoltaics, our research significantly advances perovskite solar cell (PSC) technology towards enhanced performance, stability, and scalability. A cornerstone is the successful integration and long-term outdoor assessment of large-area graphene-perovskite solar panels in a solar farm [1], with ongoing detailed investigations into degradation mechanisms, dark storage recovery, and visual defects under real-world conditions [2]. We are actively pushing the boundaries of upscaling, transitioning from small modules to large 0.73 m² panels [3]. Fundamental is our meticulous control over perovskite film properties via strategies like antisolvent engineering to manage crystallization, strain, and defects [4]. We have also demonstrated improved stability and efficiency in inverted PSC architectures through innovative interface modifications of charge transport layers, for example, by using azulene-pyridine molecules [5] or by engineering the perovskite/electron-transporting layer interface with transition metal chalcogenides [6] effective in boosting operational stability and enabling printable PSCs.

Concurrently, our group is pioneering flexible and printable electronics, with a strong focus on perovskite-based resistive switching memories (memristors) for neuromorphic computing. We have developed mixed-halide perovskite memristors exhibiting gate-tunable functionalities at low electric fields [7]. Enhancing device durability is key, achieved via innovative mixed-dimensional perfluoroarene perovskite heterostructures [8]. Our commitment to sustainability is reflected in the development of mixed-halide perovskite memristors utilizing self-assembled monolayers as bottom contacts [9]. A significant stride towards practical neuromorphic systems is our work on lead-free inorganic cesium-bismuth iodide perovskite memristors, which demonstrate threshold resistive switching suitable for neuron emulation [10]. Beyond perovskites, our exploration extends to other promising 2D materials, such as piezo-phototronic In₂Se₃ nanosheets for multifunctional printable sensing and spray-coated transition metal dichalcogenides [11].

This presentation will synthesize these interconnected research avenues, illustrating how strategic materials design and solution processing are paving the way for scalable, sustainable, and high-performance technologies crucial for the future of energy and computing.

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Keyword: *photovoltaics, memristors, 2d materials*

Actionable Quantum Digital Twin Creation for Quantum Control in Self-Driven Autonomous Material and Device Acceleration Platforms (AMADAP)

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Quantum Control Theory (QCT) is the interdisciplinary scientific and engineering field focused on the active steering of the dynamics of a quantum mechanical system toward a desired outcome. It is a part of the "second quantum revolution," which treats quantum effects such as superposition and entanglement as resources to be harnessed for practical applications, with applications in computing, sensing, chemistry, and communication. QCT seeks to answer the problem of designing external stimuli to manipulate its Hamiltonian and guide its state evolution with high fidelity and resilience to noise.

Autonomous Material and Device Acceleration Platform (AMADAP) is a holistic, self-driven laboratory concept aimed at accelerating the discovery and development of new functional materials, particularly for emerging photovoltaic (solar cell) technologies. These systems combine robotic synthesis and characterization of materials with AI-driven data analysis. They both rapidly explore and discover new materials, moving away from traditional trial-and-error methods, and optimize the manufacturing process by streamlining the production steps.

In this work I will talk about our progress towards using AiiDA as an orchestrator to create Shadow Hamiltonians as cost Hamiltonians of the optimal solution of the target quantum system to be manufactured, and the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) as an open-loop "bang-bang" quantum control mechanism. The data collected both by experiments and traditional simulations are exposed using MCP to an AI-model, which in turn infers the components of the both cost and mixer Hamiltonians, and performs further simulations/ suggests experiments if needed.

This approach will not only enable the autonomous discovery of promising quantum effects such as quantum scars in nanomaterials, but also provide a precious alternative to np-complete hard multivariate optimization problem encountered in AMADAP platforms, as a quantum-inspired or pure hybrid HPC-QPU (Quantum Processor Unit) solution in which the problem becomes solvable.

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Keyword: QCT, AMADAP, HPC+QPU, AI

Interface Engineering for Optical Physically Unclonable Functions

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Security layers based on physically unclonable functions (PUFs) have recently attracted significant interest for use in authentication applications. Anti-counterfeiting technologies, for example, are in urgent need to prevent counterfeit products and infringement of intellectual property, which constitute a significant threat to national security, world economy and human health. In addition to their significance for anti-counterfeiting, PUFs are becoming essential in authentication of individuals and data security, driven by the rapid digitization of the world. At the core of the PUF concept is the replacement of one-way mathematical functions used in modern cryptography with a physical system. The most important advantage of PUFs is the unique and unclonable response generated by a stochastic physical process in response to a challenge. Since their initial discovery, optical PUFs have stood out for their high encoding capacity and uniqueness based on light-matter interactions.

In this talk, I will present recent advances in interface engineering at the microscopic and nanoscopic length scales for generating optical PUFs. Our research focuses on controlling the physicochemical properties of interfaces with stochastic processes and obtaining security layers with unique optical responses. One approach we have introduced to the literature in the fabrication of stochastic interfaces is dewetting instabilities in nanoscopic films. With this approach, we have shown that polymers,[1] organic semiconductors,[2] quantum dots, graphene,[3] biomolecules, and metallic thin films can be arranged into random structures with optical responses depending on solid surface boundary conditions and form multilayer PUF-based security layers. Surface energy patterns defined by printing and lithography processes offer routes to hybrid encoding based on deterministic and stochastic components [4]. Dewetting instability induced self-assembly of designed organic building blocks into microscopic one-dimensional features represents an emerging class of encoding, which we refer to as molecular PUFs. We have very recently demonstrated stochastic orientational encoding approach using a facile ambient-atmosphere solution processing of a molecular thin film based on the rod-shaped organic molecule [5]. Artificial colorization coupled with random crystallization and convolutional neural network algorithms enabled ultrahigh encoding capacities in a bright field resolvable optical PUF composed of a single-material.

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Keyword: *Nanostructured surfaces, Optical encoding, Advanced materials, Wettability*

Solvation-dictating Additives for Advanced Rechargeable Batteries

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Anion shuttle batteries (ASBs) represent a promising next-generation energy storage technology that simultaneously utilizes both cation and anion intercalation [1]. By enabling high-voltage operation and fast charge-discharge kinetics, ASBs offer a compelling alternative to conventional lithium-ion systems. Their ability to use abundant carbonaceous materials and low-cost salts enhances cost-effectiveness and sustainability. Moreover, the absence of transition metals reduces environmental impact and facilitates recycling. Previous efforts have been primarily devoted to solving the anion-storage-derived issues such as large volume expansion of graphite cathode upon anion and unknown chemistry in anion-dictated electrolyte design [2]. Electrolytes for ASBs in particular, have been utilized as the same combination in the typical lithium-ion batteries where LiPF_6 salt and carbonate solvents. However, the typical operation of ASBs requires high voltage beyond the electrochemical stable window of the above electrolytes and high lithium cation transference number (not considering the counterpart, i.e. anion) across the electrolyte medium. Therefore, this calls for a rational electrolyte design to boost the anion mobility as well as the overall electrochemical stability.

Here, we report rationally designed electrolytes that modulate the solvation structure of electrolytes to extend the battery lifetime by more than a thousand cycles and enhance the rate capability. This study presents a nanomaterial-engineered electrolyte strategy to address ionic transport imbalance in sodium-based ASBs [3]. By incorporating functionalized nano-graphene oxides (NGOs) into a low-concentration carbonate-based electrolyte, we construct a dual-ionic weakly solvating electrolyte (DWSE) capable of simultaneously modulating the solvation environments of both Na^+ and PF_6^- ions. Two types of surface-functionalized NGOs—carboxylic acid (CNG) and ethylenediamine (ENG)—enable precise control over ionic coordination dynamics. DFT calculations and 2D NMR spectroscopy reveal distinct ion–nanomaterial interactions that weaken solvent–ion associations without promoting aggregation. DWSE not only facilitates balanced ion transport but also induces the formation of NaF-rich interphases, leading to enhanced interfacial stability on both graphite cathodes and Na metal anodes. As a result, the DWSE-enabled DIB achieves high-rate capability (82.0 mAh g^{-1} at 50 C) and remarkable cycling longevity (>1500 cycles at 10 C). Importantly, this electrolyte design suppresses solvent co-intercalation and structural degradation of graphite through selective modulation of nanoscopic solvation shells. These findings demonstrate how nanoscale functional materials can be strategically deployed within bulk electrolyte formulations to unlock dual-ion charge transport and interfacial stability, advancing the frontier of nanoscience-guided energy storage technologies.

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Keyword: *nano-graphene oxides, additives, electrolytes, anion shuttle batteries*

Next-Generation Multiplexed Diagnostics: Nanotechnology-Driven Interfaces for Biosensing, Imaging, and Point-of-Care Applications

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The race in the development of new nanotechnology-based materials has been in constant increase. The applications of nanoparticles and nanocomposites for different applications such as biosensors and drug delivery systems are an important category that needs continuous development. Biosensors have many fields where they shine especially in the development of point of care (PoC) tools based on electrochemical or paper-based materials for the detection of small molecules such as illicit drugs or virus particles. On-site detection lowers the burden on test centers due to their selectivity and sensitivity, fast turnaround, low price, and because they don't need trained staff. The development of biosensors is also associated with many tools such as smartphone that can facilitate readout through special applications and color-assisted analysis. These makes the process of using biosensor more accessible to the population. In this presentation, we will share our recent findings in the development of nanoparticles-based biosensors for the detection of biomolecules as well as other target molecules using paper-based biosensors and electrochemical biosensors. Various nanoparticles (NPs) such as magnetic, gold and polymeric structures loaded were used to produce satisfying signals and colors that can compete with the traditional known sensing methods. These techniques were combined with smartphones to analyze colors and electrical signals through available and in-house developed applications. Additionally, our team explored the development of various PoC model prototypes such as wearable watches for the detection illicit drugs.

On the other hand, our advances in the development of drug delivery systems using various types of nanocarriers for the detection and treatment of various diseases are presented. Our findings demonstrate the importance of such structures for the personalized and specific delivery of particular molecules to their targets with lower levels of toxicity and enhanced effect compared to traditional therapy approaches. These nanocarriers provides an important advantage through their flexibility and tunability allowing the preparation of interesting structures that can be used for both therapy and diagnostics (theranostics). The current presentation highlights the importance of nanomaterials development for future applications in the biomedical field.

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Keyword: *Functional Nanoplatforms, Point-of-Care Test Systems, Biosensors*

Overcoming Challenges in Modelling Surface Reactions in Computational Materials Science

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Although understanding reactions at the atomistic level is exceedingly important, they present a multitude of challenges to the computational materials science community. A reaction is typically viewed as a process that follows the minimum-energy path connecting two local minima on the potential energy surface of a system. The reaction rate is then determined by the energy difference between the highest point on this path and the energy of the reactants. While simple to state, calculating reaction paths is notoriously difficult. Accurate methods such as density functional theory (DFT) are time-consuming, whereas efficient methods such as reactive empirical potentials must be developed separately for each system. At present, there is great interest in addressing challenges related to identifying transition states, developing accurate reactive empirical potentials, and many other topics. In recent years, our group has approached this problem from several directions. In this talk, I will present both our past and ongoing work. After a brief background section, I will discuss our published results on CH₄ pyrolysis in molten metals, highlighting our novel analysis techniques. I will then describe our current efforts in generating reactive potentials using machine learning, and conclude with our recent work on magnetic nanoclusters in collaboration with Dr. Doğan Kaya. All of these topics, and more, will be presented in posters and oral contributions by members of our group throughout the conference.

Green Solvents in Organic Semiconductors: A New Molecular Engineering Frontier

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Over the past two centuries, advancements in chemistry and materials science have driven the development of modern functional materials, with π -conjugated molecules emerging as a compelling class for next-generation (opto)electronics. These molecules exhibit exceptional potential as semiconductors in organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) and as interfacial or surface layers in optoelectronic devices, such as organic photovoltaics and light-emitting diodes/transistors. Their unique features distinguish them from traditional inorganic semiconductors and metals, positioning them as critical components for applications like flexible electronics and wearable sensors. The adoption of green solvents in solution-based fabrication of semiconductor thin-films is increasingly vital to meet evolving regulatory mandates and enable sustainable commercialization of (opto)electronic devices. However, the limited availability of green solvent-processed molecular thin-films that perform effectively under ambient conditions underscores a critical need for further research.

In this talk, I will present recent advances in our research group in the development of structural engineering and device fabrication strategies for solubilizing high-mobility semiconductors that enables green-solvent processing for eco-friendly, sustainable device fabrication and unique molecular properties. Our research focuses on designing and building state-of-the-art, high-performance organic optoelectronic materials for next-generation optoelectronic devices. The p- and n-channel OFETs show charge carrier mobilities as high as $2.0 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ ($I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}} \approx 10^6\text{-}10^8$), which are among the highest OFET performances reported under ambient conditions from a green solvent. Hansen Solubility Parameters (HSP) analysis, combined with Scatchard-Hildebrand regular solution theory and single-crystal packing analysis, elucidates this exceptional solubility and reveals unique relationships between molecular structure, interaction energy densities, cohesive energetics, and solute-solvent distances (R_d). An optimal solute–green solvent interaction distance in HSP space proves critical for green solvent-processed thin film properties. This asymmetric functionalization approach developed in our lab, with the demonstrated unique solubility insights, provides a foundation for designing green-solvent-processable π -conjugated systems, potentially advancing innovation in sustainable (opto)electronics and bioelectronics.

Acknowledgement

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Keyword: *Organic Semiconductors, Organic Field-Effect Transistors (OFETs), Green Solvent, Solution Processing*

Converging Biointelligence with Artificial Intelligence for Multifunctional Nanostructured Surfaces

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In nature, due to evolutionary pressures, organisms have developed potent defense molecules. Unfortunately, some of these molecules are in plants, some in fungi, and some in animals. The concept of bio||intelligence is based on harnessing these molecules using machine learning to develop multifunctional microstructures based on biopolymers. This talk will cover the use of bio||intelligence in the context of infection prevention, particularly nosocomial and medical device-related infections, with specific examples of advanced woundcare systems and orthopaedic implants. IT will also cover the development of nanoscale coatings within the framework of the Safe and Sustainable by design approach. The use of such methodologies for development of nanoscale advanced textile coatings will be demonstrated. Finally, as such approaches are based on completely new nanoscale structures, the development of automated testing methods within the context of One Health (Simultaneous consideration of human, animal health and environmental impact) in the context of an ongoing Horizon Europe project (Toxbox) will be demonstrated.

Keyword: *biomaterials, Nanocoatings, Antimicrobial, Machine Learning*

Controlled Charge Flow in Nanoconfined Iontronics

Di Wei *

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Controlled charge flow is fundamental to many areas of science and technology, serving as charge carriers of energy and information, and probes of material properties and reaction kinetics. In nanoscale systems, particularly those with confinement below 2 nm, classical continuum theories, such as the Navier–Stokes, Kelvin, and Hertz–Knudsen equations, begin to fail, and a range of non-classical ionic phenomena emerge, including electrical double layer (EDL) overlap, ionic Coulomb blockade, and ultra-low resistance ion transport.

Figure: Controlled Charge Flow in Nanoconfined Iontronics via EDL Regulation

Nanoconfined iontronics, which harnesses ions as charge carriers, offers a promising platform to manipulate charge flux, enabling tunable directionality and magnitude of ionic currents in ways reminiscent of biological neural signaling. In this talk, Wei will present recent advances from his group in the design and understanding of nanoconfined iontronic systems, highlighting their potential in energy, information, and probing chemical reaction kinetics.

Composite Membranes, “PGM-Free” Electrocatalysts and Catalyst Layers for Fuel Cells and Electrolyzers

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Hydrogen technologies are increasingly central to global energy discussions as countries strive to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. As a clean fuel, feedstock, and energy carrier, hydrogen plays a pivotal role in addressing climate change, energy security, and sustainability. Electrolyzers, enable green hydrogen production, while fuel cells efficiently convert it into electricity, making both technologies central to the clean energy transition. Membranes and electrodes are critical components in both fuel cells and electrolyzers, and their performance directly impacts the efficiency, durability, and cost of these systems. However, significant material-based challenges must be addressed to enable their widespread deployment.

To address the need for more active and cost-effective materials, novel strategies were developed for the design and synthesis of electrocatalysts, electrodes, and polymer electrolyte membranes for application in fuel cells and electrolyzers. Initially, advanced composite membranes were fabricated using sol-gel synthesis and electrospinning technique to achieve controlled swelling behavior, enhanced ionic conductivity, improved mechanical strength, and overall superior fuel cell performance [1]. Secondly, platinum group metal (PGM)-free electrocatalysts, applicable to both fuel cells and electrolyzers, were synthesized via a meticulously synthesized through multi-step pyrolysis and calcination process. This approach facilitated precise modulation of the catalyst composition and optimized the exposure of catalytically active sites [2]. Finally, “PGM-free” catalyst layers were fabricated via electrospinning, ensuring homogeneous dispersion of electrocatalysts and an optimized electrode microstructure, thereby improving the performance and durability of fuel cells.

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Keyword: *PGM-free catalyst layer, polymer electrolyte membrane, fuel cells, electrolyzers*

Looking Inside: Multiscale Diffraction Imaging from Millimeters to Nanometers

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Macroscopic properties of advanced materials are governed by hierarchically-organized structures such as grains, subgrains, dislocations, and phase domains, spanning nanometers to millimeters. Understanding their dynamic interactions is key to property control and multiscale model validation. Dark Field X-ray Microscopy (DFXM) is a synchrotron-based diffraction imaging technique that enables non-destructive, three-dimensional mapping of orientation and strain in bulk materials, with submicron spatial and microstrain-level angular resolution. Using an objective lens to magnify diffracted X-rays, DFXM delivers full-field imaging of individual grains with high temporal resolution, enabling in situ studies of grain growth, dislocation dynamics, recovery, and recrystallization. Recent methodological advances have integrated DFXM with upstream grain mapping techniques such as 3DXRD, DCT, and labDCT, enabling seamless, multiscale targeting without dismantling the sample. At the ESRF, the upgraded ID03 beamline, part of the EBSL2 program, now supports both monochromatic and pink-beam modes, enhancing time-resolved and multimodal capabilities. We demonstrate the potential of this approach through recent studies on metal alloys and semiconductors, highlighting how DFXM, combined with grain mapping, reveals new insights into structure–property relationships across length and time scales.

Overcoming the Barriers of Brain Cancer Treatment: Realization of NIR Absorbing and Low Mw Photodynamic Therapy Agents

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Cancer remains the second foremost cause of mortality worldwide, claiming approximately 10 million lives in 2020. Over the past decades, remarkable strides have been made in improving 5-year survival rates for several malignancies—most notably prostate cancer, exceeding 90% in 24 countries, and breast cancer, reaching 85% in 25 nations. This narrative diverges for brain cancer, where survival rates remain dismally low at merely 30–40% across 20 countries and these figures have shown negligible improvement over the past decade in majority of regions. A high prevalence of surgically inoperable brain tumors, a restricted arsenal of drugs capable of traversing the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and the absence of effective, targeted therapeutic strategies are the leading causes for this grim picture.

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) emerges as a compelling candidate to address these unmet needs, offering the promise of precision, efficacy, and minimal invasiveness. Nevertheless, its success in brain oncology hinges on the development of photosensitizers that simultaneously possess strong near-infrared (NIR) absorption for deep-tissue penetration, high singlet oxygen quantum yields, and—critically for BBB penetration—low molecular weights.

Here, main discussion will be focused on our endeavors toward engineering next-generation fluorophores that reconcile two seemingly paradoxical attributes: strong NIR absorption and low molecular weights. We have demonstrated that dual “single-atom” modifications of fluorescein or rhodamine-based scaffolds operate synergistically to achieve red-shifts beyond 650 nm while maintaining low molecular weights. Building on this platform, I will detail the transformation of these chromophores into potent PDT agents, along with our design of reaction-triggered caging strategies tailored to enzymes upregulated in brain tumors. The discussion will highlight the photophysical properties and noteworthy in vitro performance of several PDT agents developed in our group. Finally, I will reflect on key lessons learned and outline our vision for advancing toward truly transformative therapeutic modalities for brain cancer.

MEMS Based Fully Implantable Cochlear Implants

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Cochlear implants have transformed the lives of individuals with severe to profound hearing loss; however, current devices still face significant challenges related to bulkiness, external hardware dependency, and limited long-term reliability. The FLAMENCO project addresses these limitations by pioneering a fully implantable cochlear implant system based on MEMS technologies.

This talk will present the design and development of a new class of microscale acoustic transducers that eliminate the need for external microphones, enabling seamless integration within the middle ear. The project also introduces piezoelectric energy harvesting modules and ultra-low-power signal processing electronics that together overcome the power constraints of fully implantable systems. Biocompatibility, wireless communication, and chronic implantation strategies are further explored to ensure clinical viability.

By combining innovations in MEMS-based sensing, power management, and system integration, the FLAMENCO project demonstrates a pathway toward the next generation of cochlear implants—devices that are not only invisible and unobtrusive, but also capable of providing naturalistic hearing experiences and improved quality of life for patients.

Small Angle X-ray and Neutron Scattering as Complementary Tools for Advanced Nanostructural Characterization of Silica Aero/Xerogels

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Silica-based aero- and xerogels, derived via sol–gel processes, are distinguished by their highly open mesoporous networks, low bulk density, high specific surface area, and tunable surface chemistry—properties that make them excellent candidates for adsorption-driven separation processes in environmental and energy-related applications [1,2]. However, their performance is strongly governed by subtle variations in nanostructure stemming from precursor chemistry, synthesis conditions, functional group incorporation, and drying protocols [3]. In this study, we highlight the use of Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS) and Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) as complementary, non-invasive tools for probing the intricate nanostructure of functionalized silica aero/xerogels. The scattering results, correlating with nitrogen sorption data and electron microscopy imaging, provide quantitative insights into pore size distributions, fractal dimensions, and morphological heterogeneity. Multiscale structural characterization enables a comprehensive understanding of structure–function relationships, guiding the rational design and optimization of silica-based adsorbents for the high-efficiency removal of various emerging contaminants from wastewater.

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Keyword: *Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS), Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS), silica aero-/xerogels, Nanostructural characterization*

Manipulation of Monomers toward Programmable Porous Organic Polymers for Iodine Capture

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Nuclear energy offers a high energy density and low carbon dioxide emission; however, its broader utilization is hampered by the production of radioactive iodine species, which present significant environmental and health risks. Therefore, the development of high-performance adsorbent materials for the removal of iodine from air and water is essential for realizing nuclear energy as a cleaner and more sustainable energy source. Recently, porous organic polymers have been utilized as promising adsorbent materials for iodine capture applications. However, the research on polymeric adsorbents for iodine capture remains in its infancy, facing challenges in achieving high iodine uptake capacities in vapor and aqueous phases as well as ensuring a long recycle life. Thus, the design of novel polymeric adsorbent materials for iodine capture is of significant interest [1,2]. In this talk, I will introduce new types of chemistry that evidently have a remarkable impact on several crucial factors in iodine capture, including control over textural properties and iodine adsorption performance in both gas-phase and aqueous solution, while offering a long recycling life without sacrificing removal efficiency. Additionally, I will discuss how detailed mechanistic studies pave the way for the understanding of the iodine adsorption mechanism, identifying the adsorption sites and emphasizing the role of textural properties in enhancing iodine capture performance.

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Keyword: *polymeric frameworks, porous organic polymers, iodine capture, environmental remediation*

Morphology Development of Hierarchical Vaterite Structures

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Vaterite, an anhydrous polymorph of calcium carbonate, is found in biominerals and has applications in a variety of fields. Vaterite particles are often found as polycrystalline structures with complex, hierarchical morphologies, which are of interest both due to the superior mechanical properties of naturally occurring layered materials, such as nacre, and the obscurity of their formation mechanism. The hierarchical organization of vaterite microstructures have so far been explained either by supersaturation-controlled kinetic roughening and interface instability or particle attachment.[1, 2] Although detailed analyses of vaterite growth revealed certain aspects of their morphology development, contradicting hypotheses prevail due to the non-exclusivity of the experimental methods that depend solely on observation of final particle morphologies and/or lack quantitative data on (time-dependent) supersaturation profile.

In order to advance our understanding of the formation pathways of hierarchical vaterite structures and identify the regulating parameters of the crystallization process, we have performed seeded growth experiments at controlled supersaturation and carried out detailed 2D and 3D analyses of the particles. The experiments were conducted over a supersaturation range of 1.5-5 with respect to vaterite, and a temperature range of 10 to 60 °C. The constant composition experiments revealed the significant dependence of growth mode on the temperature and supersaturation. Coherent X-ray diffraction imaging (CXDI) combined with wide-angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) was employed to resolve the internal architecture of particles at a 9.5 nanometer resolution. Together with scanning precession electron diffraction (SPED), these tools provided insights into crystal orientation. Our findings reveal that spherulitic vaterite seeds consist of biaxially oriented crystallites, and subsequent growth layers generally adhere to this underlying arrangement. The layered growth arises from a combination of anisotropic growth rates and spatial constraints. These results establish a strong correlation between particle morphology, crystal texture, and the thermodynamic and kinetic factors governing crystallization within the framework of classical crystal growth theory.

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Keyword: *crystal growth, crystal morphology, CXDI, SPED*

Ultrafast Laser Synthesis of Zeolites

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Research demonstrates that zeolite nucleation and growth can be controlled by fine-tuning chemical composition, temperature, and pressure, resulting in structures with diverse porosities and functionalities. Nevertheless, current energy delivery methods lack the finesse required to operate on the femto- and picosecond timescales of silica polymerization and depolymerization, limiting their ability to direct synthesis with high precision. To overcome this limitation, we introduce an ultrafast laser synthesis technique capable of delivering energy at these timescales with unprecedented spatiotemporal precision. Unlike conventional or emerging approaches, this method bypasses the need for specific temperature and pressure settings, as nucleation and growth are governed by dynamic phenomena arising from nonlinear light-matter interactions, such as convective flows, cavitation bubbles, plasma formation, and shock waves. These processes can be initiated, paused, and resumed within fractions of a second, effectively “freezing” structures at any stage of self-assembly. Using this approach, we trace the entire nucleation and growth pathway of laser-synthesized TPA-silicate-1 zeolites from early oligomer formation to fully developed crystals. The unprecedented spatiotemporal control of this technique unlocks new avenues for manipulating reaction pathways and exploring the vast configurational space of zeolites.

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Keyword: *ultrafast laser synthesis, zeolites, nucleation and growth, nonlinear light-matter interactions*

Advances in the Detection of Chemical Warfare Agents, Drugs and Explosives Using Raman Technology

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The TacticID family of products identifies unknown substances in the tactical operations of first responders, security operations, HazMat teams, and military first defenders. TacticID instruments are rugged and field-ready. They reduce risk and help manage uncertainty and response time without compromising the sample's integrity or the evidence chain.

The Metrohm TacticID-1064 ST uses <see-through> technology to measure samples inside bottles, envelopes, and even dense chemical storage containers. A unique data analysis algorithm quickly identifies and separates the container signature from the sample, accurately identifying both in seconds. Measure through packaging to avoid direct contact with the sample

• Actionable results display with comprehensive safety information • Extensive and customizable libraries • Advanced optical design and powerful data tools deliver fast results

The ergonomic design and compact size make it ideal for use in the field. A large, responsive touchscreen makes operation easy, even when working in protective gear. Color-coded results display illicit materials, suspected precursors and cutting agents, and chemical safety information so appropriate action can be taken.

Keyword: *HandheldRaman, RamanSpectroscopy, MetrohmRaman, Defense, Security, SeeThrough, NonHazardous, FirstDefenders*

Fabrication of Specialty Optical Fibers for Defense Applications including nanoparticle-doped active material preparation

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We will present recent results of the specialty optical fibers fabricated on a mass scale for the defense industry. The designed and fabricated specialty fibers include active Yb-doped fibers and polarization-maintaining fibers. The fibers were tested geometrically, mechanically, and optically. Active fibers were also tested using a kW-class master oscillator power amplifier (MOPA) system. Approaches for having high-beam quality using new generations of active fibers, including ultra-low NA fiber and pedestal layer fabrication, will be discussed. Different types of polarization-maintaining fibers will be presented, such as typical Panda-type fibers and biaxial PM fiber. A new approach in the fabrication of active and passive fibers containing nanoparticle-doped core regions will also be presented.

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Ali Karatutlu, Elif Yapar Yıldırım, Esra Kendir, Yakup Midilli, Samet Akçimen, Bülend Ortaç Fabrication of Biaxial Polarization-Maintaining Optical Fiber with Ultra-Low Bending-Dependent Polarization Extinction Ratio Deterioration Optical Fiber Technology Volume 69, March 2022, 1028362022 DOI: 10.1016/j.yofte.2022.102836

Esra Kendir Tekgul, Yakup Midilli, Huseyin Can Çamiçi, Elif Yapar Yıldırım, Ali Karatutlu and Bülend Ortaç Effects of Gamma Radiation on Yb-doped Al-P-Silicate Optical Fibers Applied Physics B: Lasers and Optics 128, 170 (2022) DOI: 10.1007/s00340-022-07891-y

Keyword: Active fiber, polarization-maintaining, fiber laser, kW-class

Investigation of Radar Absorption Performance of Magnetic Nanoparticles in Epoxy Matrix

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Stealth technology has been one of the crucial requirements for military vehicles such as aircrafts or naval ships. The radar absorbing material used in these vehicles absorb low frequencies, radio waves, microwaves also infrared waves. The material should have the tendency to reduce the reflection of the electromagnetic waves in order to make the vehicles invisible [1]. Radar Cross Section (RCS) is a characteristic of an object's ability to reflect growth waves in specific directions and it is an important factor in radar detection. RCS is influenced by the object's shape, material, orientation relative to the radar and the intensity of the radar signal. The most common methods of reducing RCS are shape modification and Radar Absorption Material (RAM) applications. RAMs are categorized as magnetic and dielectric absorbing materials. For absorption of radiation, magnetic losses (μ'') and dielectric losses (ϵ'') are required [2]. Magnetic materials are well-suited for comparison with dielectric technologies due to their ability to operate over a wide frequency range, dual absorption options (dielectric and magnetic), high impedance matching ability [3]. Magnetite (Fe_3O_4), which has remarkable properties such as high field irreversibility, high saturation field, superparamagnetism [4], large surface area, high chemical reactivity and magnetic dipole interaction [5] was synthesized using the co-precipitation method in this study. To protect the magnetic properties of the magnetic nanoparticles and prevent oxidation and aggregation, the Fe_3O_4 was coated with SiO_2 using the Stöber method to obtain a core-shell structure. Since ZnO provides strong electromagnetic wave absorption and a wide band gap when integrated with magnetic materials, and since this integration causes an increase in material interface polarisation, dielectric properties and magnetic loss, ZnO was added to the core-shell structure to form a core-shell-shell structure. The effects of layering, the coating thickness of the magnetic nanoparticles, and the epoxy/magnetic nanoparticle mass ratio on the radar absorption performance of the $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@/\text{SiO}_2@/\text{ZnO}$ structure were investigated.

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Keyword: *Stealth, Radar Absorbing Material, Magnetic Nanoparticles, Epoxy*

Fe₃O₄@C Core-Shell Particle Synthesis for X-Band Electromagnetic Wave Absorption to Reduce Radar Visibility

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Electromagnetic (EM) wave-absorbing materials have received significant attention due to their critical role in stealth technology, where reducing radar cross-section is essential. In this study, flower-like Fe₃O₄@C (iron oxide coated with carbon) core-shell particles were synthesized via a solvothermal method designed to enhance dielectric and magnetic loss mechanisms. Structural and morphological characterizations were performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis, confirming the magnetite phase and characteristic core-shell morphology. For electromagnetic measurements, the particles were uniformly dispersed in paraffin wax at a loading of 50 wt.% to form composite samples suitable for waveguide testing. Using a WR90 waveguide and a vector network analyzer (VNA), the electromagnetic parameters were measured across the X-band frequency range (8–12 GHz). The complex permittivity and permeability were extracted using a modified Nicholson-Ross-Weir algorithm, providing insights into the material's impedance matching and attenuation characteristics. Obtained electromagnetic properties were used to define a custom frequency dependent material in ANSYS HFSS software and subjected to wave guide simulation to validate the obtained parameters. The composite exhibited a minimum reflection loss of –3.61 dB at 11.6 GHz with a sample thickness of 4 mm, corresponding to an absorption of approximately 52.2% of the incident electromagnetic energy. The results highlight the potential of Fe₃O₄@C core-shell structures as lightweight, tunable microwave absorbers. Future optimization strategies may involve tailoring the carbon shell thickness and introducing dielectric silica coating to broaden the effective absorption bandwidth.

Keyword: radar absorbing materials, nano-technology, stealth

Development of Graphene-Reinforced Polyurethane Conductive Coating for Electromagnetic Interference Shielding

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The reduction of electromagnetic interference is critical in a variety of technology areas, including aerospace applications. In this regard, conductive coatings stand out as structures capable of directing the transmission or reflection of electromagnetic waves at specified frequency ranges.

Due to their lightweight nature, durability, and ability to cover a large frequency range, graphene-reinforced conductive coatings present a substantial alternative to traditional metal-based coatings. A wide range of C-based nanoparticle types and their metal equivalents were studied to better understand the relationship between material composition and conductivity. Graphene and copper were integrated into the coating structure to examine their effects on electrical conductivity and electromagnetic shielding efficacy. Moreover, these surfaces were accurately etched with a variety of geometric patterns designed for responding to specific frequency ranges using high-resolution laser ablation. This technique facilitated accurate adjustment of the pattern parameters to achieve the specified electromagnetic shielding performance. Experimental measurements and electromagnetic simulations were utilized to characterize the coatings and patterns. The results demonstrated a significant level of concordance with Graphene filler, suggesting that the surfaces can be adjusted to be both reflecting and selective at the specified frequencies.

This study demonstrates that graphene-reinforced coatings and their patterned designs offer effective and adaptable solutions for electromagnetic shielding applications.

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- G. Jena, J. Philip, "A review on recent advances in graphene oxide-based composite coatings for anticorrosion applications", *Prog. Org. Coat.*, vol. 173, p.107208,2022.

Keyword: *Graphane nanoparticle, Laser Ablation, EMI Shielding*

Achieving Superior Microwave Absorption in the X-Band with TiO₂@NiCo₂O₄ Heterostructures

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The increasing use of electronic devices that emit electromagnetic radiation has raised concerns regarding their potential impact on human health and the malfunction of sensitive electronic components. At the same time, EM waves, particularly in the microwave range, are purposefully employed in military technologies such as radar systems for object detection. Therefore, considering both the risks and the potential applications, this situation has brought attention to the urgent need for materials capable of effectively absorbing microwave energy. In response, microwave absorbing materials (MAMs) have gained increasing attention for their potential in both civilian and defense applications. Moreover, the pursuit of absorbers that are lightweight, thin, and highly efficient has driven the development of advanced heterostructure materials with tailored electromagnetic properties. To address this need, research has focused on developing lightweight, thin, and efficient absorbers, resulting in advanced hetero-structured materials. In this study, heterojunctions composed of NiCo₂O₄ nanoneedles decorated on TiO₂ nanofibers was synthesized and investigated for its microwave absorption properties. The heterojunctions were achieved via electrospinning, followed by hydrothermal growth of the NiCo₂O₄ nanoneedles and subsequent crystallization heat treatment. The characterization onto crystal structure confirmed that while TiO₂ crystallized into a dual-phase structure containing 58.2% anatase and 41.8% rutile, the NiCo₂O₄ phase exhibited a spinel structure. Morphological examinations indicated that the fiber morphology remained intact after hydrothermal and additional crystallization heat treatments and the surfaces of the fibers were uniformly coated with densely packed, needle-like features resembling honeybee legs. Furthermore, HRTEM results revealed clear physical contact and well-defined interfaces between the two phases. Magnetic measurements showed ferrimagnetic behavior for heterojunctions with a saturation magnetization of 1.98 emu/g. Microwave absorption characterization demonstrated that the heterojunction exhibited a minimum reflection loss of -21.30 dB at 9.35 GHz (4 mm thickness), with an effective absorption bandwidth (EAB) of 4.27 GHz. These results confirm that the synthesized TiO₂@NiCo₂O₄ heterostructures are promising candidates for high-performance microwave absorption, particularly in the X-band frequency range.

Keyword: Heterostructure, Microwave absorbers, Nickel cobaltite, Radar

Development of Smart Nanoparticles for Cancer Gene Therapy

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Triple Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) is an aggressive subtype of breast cancer with limited treatment options and a high risk of recurrence. Despite advancements in chemotherapy, targeted molecular therapies remain insufficient due to the heterogeneity and resistance profile of TNBC. In this context, gene therapy has emerged as a promising approach to address unmet therapeutic needs by silencing key oncogenic pathways or restoring tumor suppressor activity. However, the successful clinical translation of gene therapy is hindered by the lack of safe and efficient delivery systems capable of protecting and transporting gene editing tools into tumor cells.

To overcome these barriers, we developed a novel polymer-based nanocarrier system tailored for the delivery of siRNA, miRNA, and CRISPR-Cas9 plasmids. We engineered a well-defined copolymer, poly[hexyl methacrylate-co-2-(dimethylamino) ethyl methacrylate-co-trimethylaminoethyl methacrylate iodide], and a PEG heteroarm beta-cyclodextrin (βCD) core star copolymer to achieve high stability, target specificity, and endosomal escape.

Our platform successfully delivered LC3-targeting siRNA to TNBC cells, leading to significant inhibition of autophagy and enhanced anticancer activity both in vitro and in vivo. In a parallel approach, delivery of tumor-suppressive miR-186 effectively suppressed TNBC cell proliferation and migration in a 3D tumor spheroid model, further validating its potential for translational relevance. Moreover, we demonstrated the potential of our system to deliver CRISPR-Cas9 pDNA targeting the MUC1 oncogene, resulting in substantial gene knockout efficiency and impaired tumor cell viability.

These findings highlight the versatility and efficacy of our polymeric nanocarriers in mediating the delivery of diverse nucleic acid therapeutics. Our strategy not only addresses the current limitations of gene therapy delivery in TNBC but also opens avenues for personalized nanomedicine in oncology.

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Keyword: *gene delivery, siRNA, miRNA, CRISPR Cas9 pDNA*

Cellulase-Triggered Drug Release from Doxorubicin Integrated Cellulose Nanoparticles: A Novel Approach for Targeted Cancer Therapy

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Advancements in cancer treatment strategies have highlighted the critical need for targeted drug release technologies to mitigate the harsh side effects of conventional chemotherapy. Doxorubicin (Dox), a widely used and effective chemotherapeutic agent, unfortunately, leads to severe short- and long-term complications. This study introduces a novel targeted drug delivery system that ingeniously combines cellulose nanoparticles (CNPs) with bacterial cellulase enzyme. The cellulase was partially isolated from *Acinetobacter pittii* ROBY and *Ruminococcus flavefaciens* strain 17 bacteria. Subsequent analysis using a DNS enzyme activity assay revealed higher enzyme activity in acidic conditions for enzymes isolated from both strains. This characteristic is particularly advantageous due to the acidic nature of the tumor microenvironment, which can facilitate preferential drug release at the disease site. To develop the drug carriers, Dox-loaded CNPs were synthesized by dissolving microcrystalline cellulose in a NaOH-thiourea-urea complex system, providing the effective integration of Dox within the nanoparticulate structure. Preliminary investigations on bacterial models demonstrated this delivery system's potential: bacteria readily utilized non-drug-loaded CNPs as a sole carbon source, while the release of Dox from Dox-loaded CNPs significantly reduced bacterial cell viability due to its inherent cytotoxicity. Cell culture studies are currently underway to further validate this triggered release approach. These studies include controls lacking bacterial cellulase to confirm that drug release is specifically and exclusively triggered by the enzyme's presence. Preliminary results from these investigations demonstrate considerable promise for this innovative approach for targeted drug delivery in cancer therapy.

Keyword: *Doxorubicin, Targeted Drug Delivery, Cellulose Nanoparticles, Cancer Therapy*

Dual-function Apoferritin Nanocages: Transferrin Receptor-1 Targeted Theranostics for Glioblastoma Treatment & Imaging

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Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) remains a clinical challenge due to resistance to treatments and restrictive barriers such as the blood brain barrier (BBB). Median survival, with standard of clinical care remains ~16 months, thus, there is a need for new targeted therapeutic approaches. Among drug delivery systems, apoferritin (AFt) holds promise as a candidate for improving delivery to the brain by exploiting overexpression of transferrin receptor 1 (TfR1) on GBM and BBB endothelial cells. Herein, we developed a dual function theranostic platform based on horse spleen AFt nanocages co-encapsulating temozolomide (TMZ) and lead sulfide quantum dots (PbS QDs), termed AFt-PbS-TMZ. AFt-PbS-TMZ (12.1 ± 0.6 nm with high resolution transmission microscopy) demonstrated high encapsulation efficiencies (74.4 ± 11.25 for TMZ, one QD for each cage) and pH-dependent TMZ release (70% at pH 5.5, 33% at pH 7.4; 24 h at 37°C). In in vitro two-dimensional (2D) cultures, presto blue (PB) assay results demonstrated enhanced inhibitory effects with lower IC₅₀ values (3.5 ± 0.1 μM for U373M, 8.5 ± 0.7 μM for U373V, 10.9 ± 2.7 μM for U87MG) for GBM cells, whereas non-cancerous MRC-5 fibroblasts and human astrocytes exhibited IC₅₀ > 30 μM (p < 0.001) six days post-treatment, demonstrating GBM selectivity correlating with significantly higher (p < 0.05) TfR1 expression in GBM cells, confirmed by western blot and flow cytometry methods. In in vitro three-dimensional (3D) cultures, AFt-PbS-TMZ leveraged AFt's co-delivery advantages to achieve enhanced inhibition; IC₅₀ 5 ± 0.5 μM, with significantly (p < 0.0001) reduced spheroid volume over six days. In addition, deep tissue photoluminescence (PL) studies confirmed PbS QDs signalling in U87MG spheroid cultures post-treatment with AFt-PbS-TMZ for six days. These findings highlight the potential of AFt-PbS-TMZ as a TfR1 targeted theranostic agent, combining GBM therapy and imaging abilities in single platform (Nanoscale Advances, 2025).

References:

Nanoscale Advances,2025

Keyword: apoferritin; glioblastoma; temozolomide; lead sulfide quantum dots

Supramolecular Complexation of Ethyl 3,4-Dihydroxybenzoate with β -Cyclodextrin: A Potential Antioxidant Therapy

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Ethyl 3,4-dihydroxybenzoate (EDHB) is a phenolic compound known for its strong antioxidant [1], antimicrobial [2], neuroprotective [3], and cardioprotective properties [4]. However, its low aqueous solubility significantly limits its bioavailability and clinical applicability [5]. Supramolecular complexation with cyclodextrins offers a promising strategy to overcome such limitations by improving solubility, stability, and functional performance. This study focuses on the formation and characterization of inclusion complexes of EDHB with β -cyclodextrin (β -CD), aiming to enhance EDHB's solubility, physicochemical stability, and antioxidant activity through a supramolecular encapsulation approach. Inclusion complexes of EDHB and β -CD were prepared in a 1:1 molar ratio through solvent evaporation method. The complexation process and stoichiometry were evaluated by phase solubility analysis and confirmed via MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. The loading capacity and inclusion ratio of EDHB within the β -CD cavity were calculated. Structural characterization of the complexes was performed using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), while morphological analysis was carried out using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The stability of the complexes under varying pH and thermal conditions was also investigated to assess their potential for pharmaceutical applications. The antioxidant activity of the complexes was assessed via the DPPH radical scavenging assay, while their biocompatibility was determined using MTT assays on CRL-2097 healthy human dermal fibroblast cells. By applying a supramolecular approach, the formation of EDHB/ β -CD complexes successfully addressed the solubility-related limitations of EDHB and enhanced its pharmaceutical functionality. Moreover, the complexes demonstrated the ability to retain structural integrity under physiological and processing conditions, supporting their potential for use in antioxidant therapies and other biomedical applications.

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Keyword: antioxidant activity, β -cyclodextrin, ethyl 3,4-dihydroxybenzoate, inclusion complex

3D Network Architecture of MXene and Graphene With Anti-Microbial Properties

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The rise and re-emergence of infectious diseases are causing millions of deaths around the globe every year, while standard antimicrobial therapies are losing the battle against an increasing number of bacterial infections. 2D materials, specifically graphene oxide (GO) and MXenes are hydrophilic, have a high surface-to-volume ratio and various surface functionalities, and exhibit antibacterial properties. However, the sheets tend to aggregate, which diminishes the intrinsic properties. Functionalization of the sheets is an efficient way to prevent aggregation. In this work, we designed a 3D network of GO and MXene by crosslinking the sheets with N, N-bis(propyltriethoxysilyl)carbamide (bis-urea). Ag NPs were grown between the sheets by in situ reduction of AgNO₃ using bis-urea. This crosslinker plays three roles: 1- increasing the d-spacing of graphene sheets and decreasing aggregation, 2- reducing the Ag ions, and 3- providing a platform from which the Ag NPs will grow to a 2D sheet. SEM images and EDS showed the GO and MXene sheets and Ag NPs. XRD patterns confirmed the formation of Ag NPs exhibiting peaks corresponding to (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes at 38.2°, 44.4°, 64.6°, and 77.7°, respectively, for GO/Bis-urea/Ag and at 38.0°, 44.2°, 64.4°, and 77.3°, respectively, for MXene/bis-urea/Ag. Comparative antibacterial studies using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), and colony forming unit assay (CFU) were performed.

Keyword: *graphene oxide, MXene, Silver nanoparticles, Antibacterial properties*

From MAX to MXene: Decoding the etching protocols behind 2D MXene formation

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MXenes, a group of 2D materials with layers of transition metal carbides/nitrides/borides, hold significant potential in energy storage, catalysis, and a wide range of applications. Synthesis of MXenes typically involves etching A-layer atoms from MAX phases using acid, alkali, or molten salt etchants, however the atomistic mechanisms behind these processes are not fully understood. We used ab-initio calculations to explore the thermodynamic drive and defect formation energies for 11 MAX phases; Ti₂AlC, Ti₃AlC₂, Ti₂AlN, Ti₄AlN₃, Ta₂AlC, Ta₄AlC₃, Cr₂AlC, V₂AlC, V₄AlC₃, Nb₂AlC and Nb₄AlC₃. Contrary to conventional wisdom, we find that the etching mechanism is not limited by thermodynamic feasibility, and that the inability to synthesize many compositions is due to kinetic constraints. We synthesized Ti₃C₂T_x, V₂CT_x, and Nb₂CT_x to demonstrate the validity of our computational model in predicting etching rate trends and the applicability of defect engineering approach for development of etching protocols in the broader MXene compositional phase space. Hence, creating a blueprint for accelerated and commercial scalability of MXene synthesis.

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Keyword: MXene, MAX, etching mechanism, kinetics

Investigation of Interactions Between DNA and Some Transition Metals / Urea N-GQDs Nanocomposites

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Graphene-based materials serve as prospective foundational elements for future nanodevices, attributed to their exceptional electrical, thermal, and mechanical characteristics, with their chemical stability¹⁻⁴. Graphene quantum dots (GQDs) not only confer substantial benefits in biological applications due to the presence of hydroxyl and carboxyl groups in their structure but also exhibit water solubility⁵. The water solubility of GQDs is solely attributable to their carbon content, a critical attribute that contributes to the biocompatibility of these nanoparticles. Currently, the investigation of biocompatible multifunctional nanoparticles has gained significant importance.

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) inherently comprises nucleobases together with several phosphate, nitrogen, and oxygen atoms. These features enable interactions with metal cations. The investigation of anticancer medications that target DNA and novel compounds capable of interacting with DNA has become essential for the development of drugs applicable in chemotherapy. The UV-Visible Spectroscopy approach can also be employed to examine drug-DNA interactions. Moreover, DNA cleavage activity can be examined by hydrolytic and oxidative pathways, respectively, in the absence and presence of an oxidising agent.

In this study, some transition metal doped urea N-GQDs were prepared and their structures were characterized using UV-Vis Spectroscopy, FTIR, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Their interactions with pBR322 plasmid DNA were then investigated by UV-Vis Spectroscopy and agarose gel electrophoresis. A blue shift of 1-13 nm and 1-15 nm was found due to the interaction between metal-doped N-GQDs and CT-DNA. In addition, electrostatic binding of metal N-GQDs nanocomposites with DNA and hyperchromosity of 7-61 and 5-62% were observed. Metal N-GQDs nanocomposites were found to denature DNA both hydrolytically and oxidatively. These metal-doped N-GQDs capable of strong interactions with DNA are expected to be classified as potential pharmaceuticals.

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Keyword: *Metal-Doped Graphene Quantum Dots, DNA Cleavage Activity, DNA Binding Activity*

Tea Waste-Derived Carbon Materials with Reduced CO₂ Footprint

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The global priority for sustainability in waste management has gained significant attention in converting agricultural residues into valuable materials. Among various biomass waste types, tea waste is produced in large quantities worldwide and is often discarded or incinerated, leading to environmental pollution and resource inefficiencies. In this study, tea waste is converted into a carbon structure via a novel upcycling method, flash pyrolysis, by addressing both waste valorization and sustainable material development. The conducted process not only provides an alternative to conventional fossil-based carbon sources but also reduces reliance on energy-intensive production methods typically associated with carbon nanomaterial fabrication. The obtained carbon structure from tea waste is thoroughly examined by comprehensive characterization techniques such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Furthermore, a consequential life cycle assessment (LCA) was performed in order to evaluate the environmental impacts, with a specific focus on global warming potential (GWP), of the obtained carbon material sourcing from tea waste. The analysis results revealed a substantial reduction in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and overall environmental impacts compared to conventional carbon production methods, highlighting the potential of tea waste-derived carbon as a sustainable alternative. By integrating waste reduction, resource efficiency, and advanced material development, the current study demonstrates the feasibility and environmental benefits of converting tea waste into functional carbon nanostructures as a scalable and eco-friendly solution.

Keyword: tea waste, recycling, carbon, life cycle assessment

Manganese-Based Redox Flow Battery Performance Enhancements via Electrochemically Modified Electrodes with Carbon Nanomaterial Catalysts

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This study investigates the performance of a vanadium/manganese redox flow battery (V/Mn RFB), a hydrogen/manganese redox flow battery (H/Mn RFB) and a iron/manganese RFB (Fe/Mn RFB), employing carbon nanomaterial fabrics (CNFs) prepared through electrospinning followed by carbonization. In addition, some CNFs were prepared via electrophoretic deposition (EPD) to compare their performances with their electrospun counterparts. Noteworthy advancements are observed in both systems upon coupling CNFs with thermally treated graphite felt (GF) electrodes. Nearly doubled peak power density and 50% higher capacity utilization over 150 charge/discharge cycles at 75 mA cm^{-2} are achieved for the V/Mn RFB with the incorporation of CNFs alongside graphite felt as catalysts. Both H/Mn and Fe/Mn RFBs demonstrated notable enhancements too, achieving more than 100 cycles at a current density of 80 mA cm^{-2} , with high efficiencies (85%) and electrolyte utilization (79%) when CNFs are used in combination with graphite cloths, papers and felts. These advancements may facilitate pilot-scale testing and integration of the Mn-based RFBs for the employment in the renewable energy storage sector and grid-balancing studies.

Keyword: *Electrospinning, Carbon nanomaterial fabric, Redox flow battery, Nanomaterial catalysts*

Integration of Graphene Nanoparticles for Next-Generation Automotive Applications

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Elastomeric materials, especially EPDM-based rubber, are crucial in the automotive industry due to their flexibility, durability and excellent resistance to weathering, ozone, and heat. Continual improvement of rubber composites is key to producing better products. Traditionally, materials like carbon black and silica were used as reinforcing materials; however, nanoparticles are emerging an innovative alternative.

This study investigates the integration of graphene nanoparticles into EPDM rubber. For this aim, graphene/EPDM samples with varying ratios were prepared and subjected to comprehensive rheological characterization (evaluating viscosity and cure behavior) and mechanical testing (including tensile strength, modulus, and elongation at break). Graphene dispersion within the rubber matrix was optimized through experimental trials, enabling a precise evaluation of its effects on the composite's mechanical and physical properties.

This study compares two distinct mixing methods to identify the optimal processing route for achieving uniform graphene dispersion. The findings revealed that the dispersion of graphene nanoparticles led to significant improvements in tensile strength, elasticity, viscosity, and curing properties, even at low concentrations. The addition of Graphene nanoparticles decreased the viscosity. However, improved elasticity, higher density, and enhanced dynamic performance were achieved. The study concludes by examining potential applications of graphene-modified EPDM rubber formula in automotive sealing systems, highlighting the impact of graphene-based materials on advancing rubber composite technologies for next-generation vehicles.

Keyword: *Rubber, EPDM, Graphene*

Electrocatalytic Urea Oxidation Properties of Layered 2D Nickel Diselenides

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Hydrogen production is gaining increasing interest as a clean and sustainable alternative to the rapidly depleting fossil fuels. Water electrolysis, powered by renewable energy sources, produces high-purity hydrogen gas at the cathode and oxygen gas at the anode through a green approach. This process requires a theoretical thermodynamic cell voltage of 1.23 V to split water into hydrogen and oxygen at room temperature. However, the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) typically demands higher voltages, often above 1.5 V, due to slower reaction kinetics compared to hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Alternatively, using water that contains organic compounds, such as urea, for electrolysis can enable lower theoretical voltages (around 0.37 V) and offer a more cost-effective method for clean energy production [1]. Nickel-based catalysts, which are predominantly designed in the form of nanoparticles and nanorods, have been reported to be highly active in the urea oxidation reaction (UOR) and are more cost-effective than traditional high-cost water oxidation catalysts made from ruthenium and iridium [2]. Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have recently emerged promising candidates for UOR due to their tunable catalytic properties [3]. However, research on the UOR activity of these electrocatalysts is limited. In this study, novel two-dimensional (2D) nickel diselenide (NiSe₂) electrocatalyst materials were synthesized in thin films and layered flakes using a combination of chemical vapor deposition and thermal evaporation methods. A variety of spectroscopy and imaging characterization methods confirmed the formation of NiSe₂ materials. These materials were then studied for their application in the electrochemical urea oxidation reaction within a 0.1 M KOH alkaline water medium containing 0.33 M urea. Techniques such as cyclic voltammetry, linear sweep voltammetry, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy were employed for this investigation. The electrochemical OER activities were also evaluated in the 0.1 M KOH alkaline medium, which is competitive with the UOR, and were compared to the UOR activities. The results showed that 2D NiSe₂ electrocatalyst materials exhibited higher UOR activity and faster reaction kinetics compared to the OER. Additionally, the impact of the diverse morphologies of the 2D NiSe₂ materials on UOR kinetics was further assessed and compared with those of commercial OER/UOR catalysts. This study was supported by TÜBİTAK's 1001 Scientific and Technological Research Projects Funding Program under grant number 123M385.

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Keyword: 2D materials, Electrochemical urea oxidation, Nickel diselenides

Sulfonated Poly(Arylene Ether)s/Sol-Gel Hybrid Polymer Composite Membranes for New Generation Fuel Cell Applications

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The increasing global demand for energy is driving the advancement of innovative technologies that offer high performance, cost-effectiveness, and broad availability. Electrochemical energy systems have garnered considerable attention for their potential to mitigate environmental pollution and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. A key challenge in the development of next-generation electrochemical systems lies in addressing the high costs associated with two critical components: non-fluorinated membranes and platinum-free catalyst alternatives. Enhancing the chemical stability of non-fluorinated membranes (NFMs) and improving their electrochemical performance—particularly under demanding operational conditions—are essential for the realization of robust, durable, and economically viable energy conversion and storage technologies.

This study investigates the development of non-fluorinated sulfonated polyether ether ketone (SPEEK)-based membranes incorporating sol-gel hybrid polymeric structures for fuel cell applications. The resulting hybrid membranes demonstrated significantly enhanced proton conductivity, reaching values up to 258 mS/cm with silica gel (SG) content in the range of 5–15%. Furthermore, accelerated Fenton tests revealed improved chemical stability relative to pristine SPEEK membranes, confirming the enhanced durability and operational resilience of the hybrid structures. These findings underscore the potential of sol-gel-modified SPEEK membranes for use in fuel cells and hybrid energy storage systems, contributing to the broader goal of developing efficient, reliable, and sustainable electrochemical energy technologies.

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Keyword: Non-Flourinated Membranes (NFMs), SPEEK, conductivity, Fuel cell, sol-gel, Regenerated fuel cell, sustainability, nanomaterial, integrated hybrid systems, energy

High-Entropy Sulfides as Advanced Electrocatalysts: Design, Synthesis, and Electrochemical Performance

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High-entropy sulfides (HESs) have recently emerged as a novel class of functional materials, extending the concept of high-entropy alloys (HEAs) into the realm of chalcogenide chemistry. By incorporating five or more metallic elements in near-equimolar ratios within a sulfide framework, these materials achieve high configurational entropy, which thermodynamically stabilizes solid-solution phases and promotes unique physicochemical properties not attainable in conventional binary or ternary systems. This project explores the design, synthesis, and electrochemical characterization of selected HES compositions for catalytic applications [1-3]. Specifically, we investigate three formulations: $(\text{FeNiCoCrMn})\text{S}_2$, $(\text{FeNiCoCuTi})\text{S}_2$, and $(\text{FeNiCo}_{0.35}\text{CrMn})\text{S}_2$, all of which combine multiple transition metals with sulfur to form structurally robust and chemically versatile compounds. These compositions were chosen to probe the effects of elemental diversity, electron configuration, and valence synergy on catalytic activity and electrochemical stability. The materials were synthesized via conventional solid-state methods and evaluated using a three-electrode electrochemical system in alkaline medium. Key techniques included cyclic voltammetry (CV) to explore redox activity and surface response, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) to assess catalytic onset potentials and current densities, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to probe charge-transfer resistance and interface behavior. The electrochemical results demonstrated that the multi-metal sulfide systems exhibited enhanced catalytic features compared to conventional single-metal or binary sulfides. In particular, the $(\text{FeNiCoCrMn})\text{S}_2$ sample showed a notably low charge-transfer resistance and a high redox current, indicating rapid electron kinetics and abundant active sites. The enhanced performance is attributed to the combined effects of redox-active transition metals that dynamically influence the electronic structure, along with a high degree of surface heterogeneity that promotes diverse adsorption pathways, and the potential formation of sulfur vacancies, which introduce defect sites serving as catalytically active centers. Overall, this project highlights the promise of high-entropy sulfide systems as tunable, stable, and efficient electrocatalysts. Beyond performance metrics, it contributes to the broader understanding of how entropy-driven phase stabilization and compositional design strategies can be leveraged to engineer materials with targeted functionality.

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Keyword: *High-Entropy Sulfides (HESs), Electrocatalysis, Metal-Air Batteries*

Catalyst-Assisted Growth of Ultrathin Mo₂C MXene Films via CVD Using Au, Cu, and In Nanolayers for Catalytic and Electronic Applications

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Molybdenum carbide (Mo₂C) MXenes have gained significant attention as two-dimensional materials with exceptional electrical conductivity, thermal stability, and catalytic activity, making them strong candidates for energy storage, electrocatalysis, and next-generation electronic devices. In this study, we report the controlled synthesis of ultrathin Mo₂C films via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on molybdenum foil substrates pre-coated with nanometer-scale catalytic layers of Au, Cu, and In (≤ 10 nm). These ultrathin catalytic films play a critical role in modulating the nucleation density, growth kinetics, and final morphology of Mo₂C. Cu-assisted growth enabled tunable film thickness from ~ 7 nm to over 100 nm by adjusting CH₄ flow and Cu/Mo ratios, in agreement with carbon supersaturation-driven vertical growth mechanisms. In contrast, In catalysis enabled Mo₂C growth at lower temperatures (~ 1000 °C), producing highly crystalline orthorhombic structures with improved transferability due to In's low melting point and easy etching. Moreover, noble metal catalysts such as Au not only enhanced surface reactions but also acted as diffusion barriers, promoting the formation of highly uniform Mo₂C domains as thin as 2–10 nm [1,2,3].

Comprehensive structural and compositional characterizations confirmed the high quality of the synthesized films. This work underscores the potential of ultrathin catalyst-assisted CVD strategies for scalable and tunable synthesis of Mo₂C MXenes, offering promising prospects for catalytic and nanoelectronic applications.

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Keyword: Mo₂C, MXene, CVD, Ultrathin catalyst films, Au, Cu, In, 2D materials, catalysis

A Smart Polymeric Drug Delivery Approach for Cancer: POEGMA-CYS-DOX Conjugate

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Polymer-drug conjugates confer a promising strategy in cancer chemotherapy due to their enhanced circulation time, improved solubility effects and pharmacokinetic characteristics while minimizing systemic toxicity [1]. Glutathione (GSH)-sensitive drug delivery systems provide a controlled drug release by remaining intact during circulation but cleaving within cancer cells due to their high GSH levels [2]. These systems can control drug release by enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing off-target toxicity [3]. By this motivation, our project aims to passively target cancer cells by GSH-sensitive polymeric conjugates. Poly(oligo(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate) (POEGMA) is a highly hydrophilic, biocompatible polymer consisting of a hyperbranched structure. In this study, multifunctional POEGMA was first synthesized by RAFT polymerization [4], and characterized by FT-IR and ¹H-NMR. Then, it was modified with cystamine molecule containing a disulfide bond by EDC/NHS coupling reaction. Following this, modified POEGMA-CYS was conjugated to Doxorubicin (DOX) via Schiff base reaction. The conjugation reaction was confirmed by FT-IR and ¹H-NMR characterizations. The amount of DOX conjugation was estimated by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Next step of our study is an in vitro evaluation of POEGMA-CYS-DOX conjugate efficiency in MDA-MB-231 triple negative breast cancer cells. As a result, GSH-sensitive polymeric conjugates offer a passively targeted delivery, enhancing cellular uptake, thereby enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing off-target effects.

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Keyword: GSH-responsive, polymeric conjugate, POEGMA, RAFT

Design, Synthesis, Characterization, and Biological Evaluation of Cobalt-Ferrite Nanoparticles for Biomedical Applications

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Cobalt-Ferrite nanoparticles (CF NPs) are increasingly used in biomedical diagnostics and therapeutic applications because of their unique magnetic properties and biocompatibility. The strong tendency of agglomeration of metallic nanoparticles during synthesis has adverse impacts on their size and stability, therefore restricting biomedical utility of the final nano-enabled products. Among different techniques available for the synthesis of CF NPs, co-precipitation stands out for its simplicity, but careful screening of reaction conditions is required to obtain the desired material properties. Here, Plackett-Burman design was employed to investigate the effects of reaction conditions on the particle size and distribution of bare and oleic acid (OA)-coated CF NPs. Two bare and OA-coated CF NP samples, selected based on polydispersity index and particle size, were characterized for morphology, elemental composition, thermal stability, and optical and magnetic properties, using TEM, XRD, FTIR, TGA, UV-Vis, and VSM. The highest saturation magnetization value (~44 emu/g) was observed for bare CF NPs of smaller sizes. The coating of NP surfaces with OA caused a slight decrease in magnetic properties. The MTT assay was used to determine the viability of A549 cells treated with increasing concentrations of bare and OA-coated CF NPs for 24, 48, 48 and 72 hours. None of the tested samples showed significant cytotoxicity at the concentrations tested, except for the bare CF NPs, which reduced cell viability to approximately 50% following 72-hour exposure at 100 µg/mL. Following incubation in a cell culture medium for 48 hours, the proteins bound to the surface of CF NPs were analyzed using SDS-PAGE. The most abundant proteins observed across most samples were bovine serum albumin, apolipoprotein A-I and fibronectin. Our results indicated that OA-coating did not alter protein interactions of CF NPs, slightly improved aggregation behavior and reduced cytotoxicity, without significantly compromising the magnetic properties.

Keyword: *cobalt ferrite nanoparticles, co-precipitation, parameter screening, cytotoxicity*

Developing a Stable and Responsive Aqueous-Interfaced Liquid Crystal Microfluidic Sensing Platform

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The responsive soft interfaces of liquid crystals (LCs) and aqueous phases represent an efficient advancement in fundamental and applied research fields, by offering great potential for innovative applications including sensing and diagnostics, release and material synthesis. The employed stagnant LC systems possess limitations in their use in continuous, automated and high-throughput applications. Our new microfluidic platform, in which stable LC flow is maintained while in contact with aqueous phases, provides a novel solution for those limitations. The LC-aqueous soft interface was defined by the preferential wetting of distinct phases at chemically heterogeneous microchannel interfaces, creating simultaneous multiphase flow. The results show that the LC-aqueous soft interfaces remained stable up to 40 mbar of pressure difference across the interfaces while continuing to exhibit responsive characteristics. The stability was valid for both low and high flow velocities, which directly impacted the LC alignment, in the flow configurations as co-current and counter-current. Furthermore, the shear induced from both bulk phases affected the LC configuration near the soft aqueous interface, and this shear effect modulated the strain mechanism of LC mesogens at this responsive interface. The responsiveness was also apparent for both homogeneous and heterogeneous interfacial adsorbates. In addition to these results, we improved the stability of the system by changing surface wetting properties by chemical modification. This enabled a considerable enhancement in the durability of microchannels over time, by also providing antifouling surface properties. Considering the surface wetting of LC, the pressure limits for a stable multiphase flow in our LC flow platforms were calculated using a modified Laplace pressure expression, and the calculated values matched the experimental results significantly. The simplicity of the construction and operation of the soft-interface LC flow system, its responsive properties, and the long-time stability meets the fundamental needs of tailorable, continuous, automated, high-throughput analysis platforms.

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Keyword: *Liquid crystals, Soft interfaces, Microfluidics, Shear*

Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS)-Based Nanobiosensor for Rapid and Sensitive Detection of Circulating Tumor DNA (ctDNA)

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This novel work aims to develop an innovative analytical system for the rapid, cost-effective, and highly sensitive detection of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) as an alternative to traditional invasive biopsies [1]. The system integrates Ligase Chain Reaction (LCR) and Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) techniques for use in cancer diagnosis. LCR offers high specificity and sensitivity by amplifying circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) [2,3], while surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) enhances the detection sensitivity for low concentrations of ctDNA molecules through the enhancement of Raman scattering signals [4].

The work involves designing and synthesizing primers targeting the KRAS mutation, performing LCR amplification, validating the amplification via gel electrophoresis, and conducting surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) analysis. Particularly, SERS chips were utilized, which employ surfaces coated with gold nanoclusters to amplify Raman signals. These chips are crucial for the sensitive and specific detection of ctDNA, playing a vital role in analyzing cancer biomarkers.

The design and fabrication of these SERS chips, including the coating of surfaces with gold nanoclusters to achieve optimal signal conditions, was carried out in collaboration with the National Electronics and Computer Technology Center (NECTEC) in Thailand [5]. This innovative approach promises high accuracy and rapid results in cancer diagnosis, significantly improving clinical applications by enabling early and effective treatment for patients. Consequently, this project aims to develop a revolutionary technology with the potential to transform cancer diagnostics.

The methodology includes a multi-phase process: LCR-based amplification of ctDNA using mutation-specific primers, verification through gel electrophoresis, and final detection via SERS using thiolated SERS chips. Selectivity experiments with single- and four-base mutation controls confirmed the discriminatory power of the system. Additionally, the system's sensitivity was validated using varying target concentrations of ctDNA. Based on Raman spectra, the detection limit was determined to be approximately 10 pM, as SERS signals were distinguishable at and above this concentration, while signals at 1 pM approached the noise level. The method reliably distinguished between wild-type and mutant sequences at this detection threshold, demonstrating high selectivity and minimal cross-reactivity even at low ctDNA levels.

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Keyword: SERS, ctDNA, SERS chip, KRAS mutation

Chitosan-Grafted Folic Acid Decorated One-Dimensional GONS: A Cytocompatible Drug Cargo for Targeted Co-Delivery of Anticancer Agents

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In conventional chemotherapy, cancer cells can become highly resilient due to a phenomenon known as multi-drug resistance (MDR). The co-delivery of chemotherapeutic agents assisted with novel nanocarrier-based targeted DDS may counter the MDR issues and subsequently improve their therapeutic efficacy. In line with this, the present work deals with the development of 1D graphene oxide nanoscrolls (GONS)-based nano delivery system for co-delivery of chemosensitizer along with the chemotherapeutic agent. Herein, the 1D GONS nanocarrier was initially functionalized with chitosan (CS) biopolymer and folic acid (FA) to further enhance their biocompatibility and target-specific co-delivery. The resultant GONS-CS-FA (GCF) nanocarriers were co-loaded with doxorubicin (DOX) and caffeic acid (CA) at different weight proportions with respect to nanocarrier and drug composition. The optimum loading efficiency of 51.14 ± 1.47 % (DOX) and 49.70 ± 1.19 % (CA) was observed for GCF: drug ratio of 2.5 with drug composition of 1:1. In vitro release at pH 5 yielded ~83 % DOX and 75 % CA, compared to ~71 % DOX and 61 % CA at pH 7.4 over 7 days, suggesting a higher and more targeted drug release in the cancer microenvironment. Cytotoxicity tests revealed selective apoptosis in cancer cells (A549) while maintaining cytocompatibility with normal cells (HEK293).

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Keyword: Graphene oxide nanoscrolls (GONS), Chitosan, Targeted dual DDS, 1D nanocarrier

Simulation-Based Analysis of the Optical Properties of Silver Nanowires for Photonic Applications

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Understanding the optical properties of one-dimensional (1D) nanostructures, such as silver nanowires (AgNWs), is critical for advancing their applications in plasmonics, photonics, and sensing [1]. In this study, we investigate the optical properties of AgNWs using the COMSOL Multiphysics Wave Optics module under continuous-wave illumination in the visible to near-infrared spectrum. This method enables efficient modeling of wave propagation along high-aspect-ratio geometries by resolving the slowly varying field envelope instead of the full electromagnetic wave, significantly reducing computational cost without compromising accuracy in directional excitation scenarios.

3D models of silver nanowires were developed to match experimental observations, in which AgNWs with an average diameter of 80 nm and a length of 10 μm were synthesized according to our previous work [2]. Their cross-sectional geometries are varied as circular, pentagonal, and decahedral, to compare the effect of geometry on the optical profile. The far-field optical responses are simulated using perfectly matched layers (PMLs) and scattering boundary conditions. Absorption and scattering behaviors are evaluated across a wavelength range of 300 to 900 nm and compared with UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopic measurements obtained from experimentally synthesized colloidal AgNWs. This combined computational–experimental study demonstrates the effectiveness of envelope-based simulations in guiding the design of nanophotonic structures and offers deeper insights into the resonant optical behavior of metallic nanowires under directional light excitation.

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Keyword: *silver nanowires, optical simulation, absorption cross section*

Phase Stabilization and Structural Ordering Control in van der Waals Layered Sb-Doped Bi₂Te₃ Thin Films Grown by Molecular Beam Epitaxy

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Controlling the structural phase of Bi₂Te₃-based topological materials remains challenging due to complex non-equilibrium growth dynamics and the likelihood of secondary phase formation. This work explores the structural tuning of Sb-doped Bi₂Te₃ thin films grown on c-plane sapphire substrates via molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), with emphasis on adjusting van der Waals (vdW) gaps through compositional and kinetic parameters.

By optimizing the Sb-to-Bi flux ratio, substrate temperature, and growth rate, we achieved excellent crystalline uniformity and controlled microstructural phases. Structural analysis using high-resolution X-ray diffraction (XRD), reciprocal space mapping, and X-ray reflectivity (XRR) revealed Kiessig fringes and interface roughness below one quintuple layer indicating high crystalline quality and strong substrate-film coherency. The films ranged in thickness from 3 to 45 nm. XRD patterns showed that Sb incorporation suppresses a secondary phase indexed by the (015) reflection, typically observed in undoped Bi₂Te₃, enhancing phase purity and lattice regularity.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) revealed a transition in growth mode: low growth rates (< 0.5 QL/min) resulted in smooth, two-dimensional terraces, whereas higher rates led to three-dimensional island morphologies. This behavior aligns with adatom kinetic models, where low flux favors lateral diffusion and layer-by-layer growth (rms roughness < 0.3 nm), while high flux promotes vertical agglomeration.

A key outcome of the study is the Sb-dependent modification of the vdW gap in Bi₂Te₃. Raman spectroscopy of samples with varying Sb levels exhibited four distinct phonon modes typical of rhombohedral symmetry: the A(1,1g) interlayer breathing mode (~65 cm⁻¹), E(g) in-plane Bi-Te stretching (~107 cm⁻¹), A(2,1g) Te(2)-Bi mode (~130 cm⁻¹), and A(3,1g) Te(1) out-of-plane vibration (~155 cm⁻¹). A frequency downshift in the E(g) mode was observed with decreasing Sb, consistent with lattice expansion. Notably, the A(3,1g) Te(1) mode shifted by ~20 cm⁻¹ at low Sb concentrations, suggesting significant modifications in out-of-plane bonding and vdW gap configuration. While the precise atomic rearrangement remains undetermined, the spectroscopic data imply potential Bi-rich inclusions or stacking deviations within the layered Bi-Te framework. These structural transformations validated by XRD, Raman, and AFM are associated with narrower vdW gaps and increased interlayer coupling.

In summary, Sb doping allows systematic control of structural ordering in vdW-layered Bi₂Te₃ films. Raman phonon modes serve as sensitive indicators of interlayer evolution, and integrating compositional and kinetic tuning via MBE provides a robust platform for engineering topological chalcogenide materials.

Keyword: *Synthesis & Processing/Deposition/molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), Composition & Microstructure/Near Surface Techniques/Raman spectroscopy, Composition & Microstructure/Near Surface Techniques/x-ray reflectivity*

Experimental and Theoretical Insights on Seed-Layer-Driven Stabilization of Hexagonal Kagome FeGe via Molecular Beam Epitaxy.

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FeGe-based compounds are drawing growing interest as platforms for topological spintronic devices, due to their ability to host exotic magnetic phenomena—including skyrmions, flat bands, and van Hove singularities—when stabilized in a hexagonal kagome lattice. While the kagome phase is metastable compared to the thermodynamically preferred cubic B20 structure, it holds significant promise for realizing magnetic topological semimetals and probing correlated electron behavior. Nonetheless, thin-film stabilization of this phase remains challenging due to competing growth dynamics and sensitive interface conditions.

In this work, we demonstrate a reproducible strategy for stabilizing the hexagonal kagome FeGe phase on Si(111) substrates using molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) with metallic seed layers. Our deposition process utilized e-beam evaporation for Fe and a K-cell for Ge, with optimization efforts focused on achieving near-stoichiometric 1:1 Fe:Ge ratios. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed minimal elemental clustering and stoichiometry control under these optimized conditions.

To explore interfacial effects, we systematically varied Fe seed layer thickness from 0 to 6 nm while maintaining constant growth parameters. Initial X-ray diffraction (XRD) results showed dominant B20 signatures. However, upon increasing seed layer thickness, B20 reflections weakened while new diffraction features emerged, consistent with the hexagonal P6/mmm kagome phase. Films grown with 2–3 nm thick seed layers displayed sharp FeGe(111) peaks and well-defined Kiessig fringes in both grazing incidence and high-angle scans. These ~9 nm thick films also exhibited XRD peak shifts, suggesting compressive strain arising from lattice mismatch and interfacial interactions.

Magnetic characterization via vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM) revealed room-temperature ferromagnetism, with coercive fields between 50 and 100 Oe. Magnetic signatures were strongly correlated with both crystal structure and composition. First-principles calculations using spin-polarized DFT with PBE+U and spin-orbit coupling (SOC) predicted an antiferromagnetic ground state in zero field for the P6/mmm phase. The electronic band structure exhibited kagome-related features such as flat bands and van Hove singularities near the Fermi level. SOC-induced gaps at symmetry-protected crossings pointed to potential nontrivial topology.

By coupling structural and magnetic data with theory across seed layer variants, we show that interface engineering could enable the stabilization of a topological kagome phase in FeGe. This approach lays the groundwork for integrating magnetic kagome materials into silicon-based spintronic and neuromorphic systems.

Keyword: *Composition & Microstructure/Features/quantum surface, Synthesis & Processing/Deposition/molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), Performance/Functionality/ferromagnetic.*

Structural and Growth Characteristics of Electrochemically Formed Zinc Hydroxycarbonate Nanowires

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The anodization of zinc has primarily been investigated for the production of zinc-based nanowires intended for subsequent conversion into zinc oxide nanowire arrays. In most studies, these zinc-based nanowires are merely treated as precursor phases, while the key aspects such as their growth mechanisms, crystalline structure, and their dimension-controlled growth remain underexplored. Advancing fundamental insights into this process could broaden the scope of zinc anodization toward refined and sustainable processing strategies for advanced applications, including the development of zinc-based coatings for enhanced corrosion resistance and antibacterial properties.

To this end, this study addressed several key unknowns regarding the structural characteristics of electrochemically grown zinc-based nanowires and investigated the mechanisms governing the growth of the nanostructured anodic film. XRD analysis suggests that the previously unindexed zinc hydroxycarbonate phase is a variant that exhibits turbostratic disorder, distinct from the well-characterized phases such as hydrozincite ($Zn_5(CO_3)_2(OH)_6$). This distinction was further supported by a comparative analysis of vibrational spectra. Based on these findings, a crystalline structure is proposed for the nanowire growth.

Furthermore, the nanowire dimensions were tailored by leveraging the interplay between two critical anodization parameters: electrolyte concentration and applied potential difference. The mechanism enabling such dimensional control was discussed in the context of crystal growth via particle attachment. The stages of nanowire growth through this pathway were further elucidated using SEM imaging at sequential time intervals, accompanied by parallel analysis of changes in current behavior during anodization.

Lastly, the zinc-based anodic film was evaluated for its antibacterial potential. Bacterial assays demonstrated significant bactericidal activity of the nanostructured zinc hydroxycarbonate film against both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* strains.

Collectively, the results presented here offer insights into the electrochemical formation of zinc-based nanostructures and may support future efforts to refine this sustainable production method. The findings are relevant for applications in environmental, biomedical, and electronic technologies.

Keyword: *Anodization, Nanowires, Electrochemical Nucleation and Growth, Zinc*

Structural Stability of Carbon-Based Supports During Nano-Metal Impregnation

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Dry impregnation, also known as pore filling or incipient wetness, is the most straightforward, cost-effective, and widely used method for preparing supported metal catalysts. This process involves dissolving a specified quantity of metal precursor in water, which is then introduced to an oxide or carbon support in an amount enough to completely saturate the pore volume of the support. The thick slurry is desiccated and then heated in a reducing atmosphere to convert the metal to its elemental form. This technique requires no filtering, eradicates metal waste, and produces an exact metal loading. The selection of support material used in this procedure is critically significant. [1] During the reduction of metal nanoparticles from their ionic state to their metallic state, the structure of the supporting material must stay intact.

Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is a thermochemical conversion process whereby moist biomass is exposed to moderate temperatures (often 180–250 °C) and autogenous pressure inside a sealed aqueous environment, yielding a carbon-rich solid product referred to as hydrochar. [2] Hydrochar derived from the hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) method has distinct and beneficial characteristics in comparison to biochars generated by traditional pyrolysis. These characteristics render it especially appropriate for applications like metal nanoparticle support, adsorbent materials, and catalyst support. Nonetheless, a significant limitation of the solid product derived from hydrothermal carbonization is its intrinsically restricted pore volume and surface area. This constraint may be mitigated by substituting water with an ionic liquid in the carbonization process - termed ionothermal carbonization - which presents a potential approach to improving the textural characteristics of the resultant carbon material. [3]

These carbonaceous structures, named ionochars, also possess diverse functional groups on their surfaces. Structural alterations may transpire in ionochars used as support materials for metal loading during the reduction of metal ions. The structural stability of ionochars loaded with nickel nanoparticles during the reduction of nickel ions has been examined by different characterization methods, and the impact on metal dispersion has been analyzed.

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Keyword: *dry impregnation, nano-sized metal immobilization, carbon-based materials*

Synthesis and Characterization of PEDOT Nanoparticles

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Interest in conducting polymers is increasing day by day. The biggest advantage of conducting polymers is that their physicochemical properties can be tuned by changing parameters during synthesis. (Fanzio et al., 2017). The role of conducting polymers in composite materials is to provide electrical conductivity. They form active regions in the composite material that respond to electrical stimuli. In new technologies, it is observed that conducting polymer nanoparticles are beginning to replace inorganic nanoreinforcement material in nanocomposites. Agglomeration, the most important limiting factor of inorganic reinforcements, is eliminated in new generation organic-based composites. EDOT is a thiophene derivative ($C_2H_4O_2C_4H_2S$) and has high conductivity compared to other thiophene derivatives. It also has high charge mobility which can produce fast electrochemical kinetics (Abdah et al., 2017). In this study, PEDOT nanoparticles were synthesized from EDOT monomers by two-surfactant oxidative emulsion polymerization technique. One aqueous phase and one organic phase solutions are prepared independently of each other with separate surfactants. The first surfactant poly (4-styrenesulfonic acid-co-maleic acid) (PSS-co-MA) sodium salt is used to form the aqueous phase and the other surfactant dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid and EDOT monomer together form the organic phase. PEDOT NPs are obtained after oxidative emulsion polymerization initiated with iron (III) chloride. Emulsion polymerization for the preparation of NPs is an efficient method to obtain NPs that are easily scalable, comparatively fast and with a uniform colloidal morphology. The resulting colloidal PEDOT NP solutions are stable for a long time, which gives them an advantage over other conductive nanopolymers in laboratory studies. Dynamic light scattering and zeta potential analysis were performed to verify the size and zeta potential of the obtained nanoparticles. According to these analyses, an average particle size of around 60 nm and a zeta potential of -35 mV were measured. The results of morphological analysis also confirmed that the size of the spherical PEDOT nanoparticles was <100 nm. This nanomaterial can be applied in a wide range of applications from biotechnology to energy systems, from imaging to cancer treatment, both as a part of electro-signal responsive skeletal systems and as the nanomaterial itself. With this specificity, it is promising for future studies.

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Keyword: PEDOT Nanoparticles, Emulsion Polymerization, Dynamic Light Scattering

Effect of Electrolyte Type on Charge Storage Mechanism and Cycling Stability of V₂O₅-Based Electrodes

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Vanadium pentoxide (V₂O₅) has attracted significant attention as a promising electrode material for supercapacitor applications due to its high theoretical capacitance, layered crystal structure, and redox-active nature. However, its practical application is often limited by poor electrical conductivity and moderate cycling stability, which are strongly influenced by the choice of electrolyte. In this study, we present a comprehensive investigation into the effects of various electrolyte systems—including aqueous, organic, and hybrid electrolytes—on the electrochemical performance of V₂O₅-based electrodes.

V₂O₅ electrodes were synthesized via a sol-gel route and subjected to structural and morphological characterizations using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Electrochemical evaluations were carried out using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in different electrolytes such as 1 M Na₂SO₄ (aqueous), 1 M KOH and ZnSO₄ in key performance parameters such as specific capacitance, energy density, power density, and long-term cycling stability were comparatively analyzed.

The results indicate that the type of electrolyte significantly influences both the ionic conductivity and the interfacial characteristics between the electrode and electrolyte. Moreover, it plays a key role in determining the dominant charge storage mechanism, whether it is primarily electrical double-layer capacitance, pseudocapacitance, or a synergistic combination of both. One electrolyte system demonstrated superior ionic mobility and higher specific capacitance at relatively low operating voltages, making it favorable for rapid charge-discharge applications. In contrast, the other system allowed for a wider electrochemical stability window, thereby enabling higher energy storage capacity, although often at the expense of ionic transport rate. Additionally, a third, semi-solid electrolyte type was observed to offer a compromise between electrochemical performance and mechanical integrity, which may be advantageous for emerging flexible or solid-state supercapacitor technologies.

This study provides insights into the electrolyte-dependent charge storage behavior of V₂O₅ electrodes, which is essential for optimizing next-generation energy storage devices. The findings also highlight the importance of tailoring electrolyte properties to achieve enhanced cycling life and operational efficiency in practical supercapacitor systems.

Keyword: Energy

In-Situ-Assembled Polyaniline Frameworks on Reduced Graphene Oxide Toward High-Performance Energy-Storage Materials

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PANI exhibited considerable potential in the conversion and storage of energy systems because of its high elasticity, large specific capacitance, multiple oxidation states, and relatively inexpensive. Unfortunately, PANI's poor stability restricts its usage. The coupling of PANI and other active materials has the potential to overcome PANI's inherent limitations. Here, we successfully synthesized reduced graphene oxide (rGO) that was utilized as a carbon substrate for in situ chemical polymerization of PANI at different operating temperatures [0°C, room temperature (RT), and 50°C]. The fabricated PANI-RT/rGO nanocomposite showed a high porosity with a high surface area, acting as an ion diffusion pathway. The estimated electrochemical results of the prepared electrodes, PANI-RT, PANI-50, PANI-0, and PANI RT/rGO electrodes at an applied current of 2 A g⁻¹ are 832 F g⁻¹ (418 C g⁻¹), 256 F g⁻¹ (128 C g⁻¹), 224 F g⁻¹ (112 C g⁻¹), and 1056 F g⁻¹ (528 C g⁻¹), respectively. The capacitance of the PANI-RT/rGO electrode is much larger than that of the others, and rGO incorporation demonstrates a key factor in improving the electrochemical storage capability. Furthermore, the device is stable, keeping 90 % of its original capacity following 3 K charge/discharge repeated runs at 5 A g⁻¹.

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Keyword: Polyaniline, Reduced graphene oxide, Supercapacitor, Energy storage

Impact of Structural Phase on Charge Storage Behavior in Multi-Metallic High Entropy Oxides

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Supercapacitors are charge storage devices with higher power density and lower energy density compared to batteries. The main working principle of supercapacitor electrodes is that decreasing the distance between the electrode and ionic species covered on the surface to the angstrom level maximizes the capacity up to the F/g scale. There are three kinds of supercapacitor electrodes based on their charge storage mechanisms: electrical double-layer capacitor (EDLC), pseudocapacitor, and battery-type. EDLCs store charges electrostatically, pseudocapacitors store charges mostly through surface redox reactions, and battery-type electrodes rely mostly on bulk redox reactions. High entropy oxides (HEO) are used as electrode materials for pseudocapacitor applications. In this study, two HEOs were synthesized with the same multi-metallic composition and different crystal structures to investigate capacitive behavior. Electrochemical characterizations of the materials were done using three-electrode experiments of cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Test results revealed that the rock-salt structure (HEO-RS) exhibited a mostly capacitive mechanism relying on surface redox reactions; on the other hand, the spinel structure (HEO-SP) resulted in a mostly battery-type charge storage mechanism. This difference in charge storage mechanisms can be attributed to the higher oxygen vacancy content of HEO-SP, which enhances the diffusion of O^{2-} ions into the bulk, as in battery-type electrodes. Both electrode materials retained 60% of their initial capacity at the end of the 1000th cycle at a current density of 2 A/g.

Keyword: *High Entropy Oxide, Supercapacitors, Crystal Structure, Pseudocapacitors*

Sustainable Synthesis of Ni(OH)₂/Activated Carbon Nanocomposite from Waste Biomass for High-Performance Supercapacitor Electrodes

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Developing low-cost, high-efficiency electrode materials is essential for advancing supercapacitor applications. This study explores the synthesis of a nickel hydroxide (Ni(OH)₂) composite enhanced with activated carbon (AC) obtained from waste biomass for use as a supercapacitor electrode. The activated carbon was produced through pyrolysis and chemical activation, providing an eco-friendly and economical carbon source. The Ni(OH)₂/AC composite was prepared using a microwave-assisted hydrothermal technique, ensuring effective integration between Ni(OH)₂ nanostructures and the porous carbon network. The material was analyzed using XRD, SEM, BET, Raman, and XPS to examine its crystallinity, morphology, porosity, and surface chemistry. Electrochemical tests, including cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), revealed a higher specific capacitance, better rate performance, and enhanced cycling stability compared to pure Ni(OH)₂. The combination of Ni(OH)₂ (contributing pseudocapacitance) and waste-derived AC (providing conductivity and surface area) resulted in superior energy storage performance. This research highlights a sustainable method for fabricating high-performance supercapacitor electrodes by repurposing waste materials, offering both environmental and economic advantages.

Keyword: Supercapacitor, Nickel hydroxide, Activated carbon, Waste biomass

Robust Conductivity in Nanostructured and Strained Goldene: In-sights from First-Principles Studies

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One of the principal challenges in flexible and stretchable electronics is identifying materials that maintain high electrical conductivity under mechanical deformations. Low-dimensional materials like graphene offer substantial benefits due to their mechanical robustness and inherent high conductivity. However, their electrical performance is significantly compromised by mechanical stresses and structural defects such as vacancies and dislocations. Here, we study the effects of structural defects and mechanical deformations on the electronic transport properties of goldene [1], a single layer of hexagonally arranged gold atoms, to explore its potential for flexible electronics. Our quantum transport calculations reveal that goldene maintains its conductivity effectively, exhibiting only a 1.7% reduction in conductance under a tensile strain of 5%. Additionally, the introduction of single and divacancy defects results in conductance reductions of only 2% and 3%, respectively. Most importantly, goldene's conductivity remains robust under both bending and twisting, distinguishing it from graphene and positioning it as an outstanding candidate for flexible nanoelectronics [2].

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Keyword: *Goldene, electronic transport, flexibility, nanoelectronics*

Phototherapies for Cancer and Bacterial Infections

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The increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens and the challenges associated with conventional cancer treatments necessitate innovative therapeutic strategies. Among emerging approaches, phototherapies, specifically photodynamic therapy (PDT) and photothermal therapy (PTT), have shown significant promise due to their spatiotemporal selectivity and synergistic effects when combined. This work presents two distinct, yet thematically linked, applications of dual PDT/PTT using superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) functionalized with photosensitizers for the treatment of cancer and bacterial infections. In the context of bacterial biofilms, a major contributor to antimicrobial resistance, we demonstrate a rationally engineered nanopatform comprising aminolevulinic acid (ALA)-loaded polyacrylic acid-coated SPIONs (ALA/PAA-SPIONs). Under combined 640 nm (PDT) and 808 nm (PTT) laser irradiation, this system achieved complete eradication of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and significant reduction of *Staphylococcus epidermidis* biofilms. Notably, biofilm reductions reached up to 13-log with increasing Fe and ALA concentrations, supported by comprehensive modeling of temperature dynamics and irradiation dose response. In parallel, a cancer phototherapy strategy using indocyanine green (ICG)-loaded APTMS-coated SPIONs (ICG-APTMS@SPIONs) was explored. The nanoparticles exhibited high photothermal conversion efficiency and photostability, facilitating near-complete ablation of MCF7 and HT29 cancer cells upon NIR laser exposure at safe intensities. The dual therapeutic mechanism leveraged both ROS generation and mild hyperthermia, leading to over 90% cell death at ICG doses as low as 5 µg/mL, without harming surrounding healthy tissues. Together, these studies underscore the versatility of SPION-based dual phototherapies as powerful tools against antibiotic-resistant infections and cancer. By optimizing nanoparticle composition, photosensitizer loading, and irradiation protocols, phototherapies can achieve high therapeutic efficacy with minimal side effects. Future developments may include in vivo validation and the integration of diagnostic imaging for theranostic applications.

Keyword: photothermal therapy, photodynamic therapy, cancer, bacterial infections

Evaluating Melittin-Loaded Niosomes for Drug Delivery Across a Human Blood-Brain Barrier Model

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The blood-brain barrier (BBB) is a highly selective physiological interface that safeguards the central nervous system but poses a major challenge for the delivery of therapeutics to the brain. In this study, we developed and characterized melittin-loaded niosomal nanoparticles as a potential platform for targeted drug delivery across the BBB, with implications for glioblastoma threatment. Niosomes are self-assembling vesicular carriers composed of non-ionic surfactants and cholesterol. They represent a more stable, scalable and cost-effective alternative to liposomes.^{1,2} In our system, the niosomes were engineered to encapsulate melittin –an amphiphilic peptide derived from honeybee venom, known for its anticancer activity and membrane-disrupting properties.³ Comprehensive physicochemical characterization was performed using dynamic light scattering (DLS), nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The optimal niosomal formulation, comprising Span 60, Tween 60, and cholesterol in a 0.5:0.5:1 molar ratio, exhibited an average particle size of 131.67 ± 1.95 nm, a polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.211 ± 0.02 , and a zeta potential of -29.3 ± 0.82 mV. To assess cytocompatibility and therapeutic potential, cytotoxicity assays were conducted using free melittin, scrambled melittin, and melittin-loaded niosomes on iPSC-derived brain microvascular endothelial cells (iBMECs), primary human pericytes, astrocytes, and U87 glioblastoma cells at 24, 48 and 72-hour time points. Furthermore, the ability of melittin-loaded niosomes to transiently and reversibly permeabilize the BBB was evaluated in human cell-based models under both static (BBB-transwell) and dynamic (BBB-on-a-chip model, 100 μ L/h flow rate) conditions. Permeability assays demonstrated reversible disruption of BBB integrity, confirming the system's capacity to facilitate transport across the barrier. These findings support the potential of melittin-loaded niosomes as a versatile and effective platform for enhancing drug delivery to the brain, particularly in the context of glioblastoma and other neurological disorders

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Keyword: *Niosome, Melittin, Drug Delivery, Encapsulation*

hiPSCs-Derived In Vitro Models of the Blood-Brain Barrier for Studying Nanoparticle Transport

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The primary barrier restricting access to the central nervous system (CNS) is the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Its properties differ in the presence of neurological diseases. This restriction and diversity of features remain a significant challenge in most CNS-related studies investigating nanoparticle (NP) delivery to the brain for a particular purpose, like glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) therapy. For these studies, maintaining BBB's integrity and studying its characterization is crucial at first glance. Although decades have been devoted to better understanding and mimicking the BBB via several in vitro BBB models, the variability of BBB data and the lack of personalized in vitro BBB modeling for NP transport have been presented. Herein, our study approach is to exploit human-induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) to create a perfect human BBB model in vitro. In our study, hiPSCs were transduced from peripheral blood mononuclear cells of one healthy human and successfully differentiated into brain microvascular endothelial cells (BMECs). More importantly, for the first time, a relatively novel NP, titanium carbide/oxide (Ti₃C₂T_x) MXene quantum dots (MQDs), was tested for its delivery across the hiPSCs-derived BBB model and its uptake by brain tumors needed for treating GBM. Our experimental results found that the hiPSCs-derived model resembled in vivo BBB more than the model with hCMEC/D3 cell lines, and it expressed several BBB genes essential for the brain endothelium. Accordingly, 10-fold higher occludin gene expression in the model with hiPSCs-derived BMECs than that of immortalized BMEC lines was found, indicating better BBB integrity. Moreover, in our transport-related studies, Ti₃C₂T_x MQDs were tracked by their auto-fluorescence, and the percentage of fluorescence by tumor cells in our MQD-treated model was 2-fold higher than in the untreated model, showing MQD transport across the BBB and detection inside the brain tumor cells. Therefore, our study demonstrates the creation of well-developed BMECs, forming a protective membrane with the help of hiPSCs. It also emphasizes important points researchers consider in the BBB modeling for in vitro studies in neuro-nanotechnology. Finally, it offers a pivotal in vitro BBB model for personalized GBM therapy with MQDs and guides future studies in vivo.

Keyword: human induced pluripotent stem cells, blood-brain-barrier, nanoparticle transportation

Enhanced Anticancer Activity of Usnic Acid and Doxorubicin via Zein-Based Nanocarriers in Ovarian Cancer Cells

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Ovarian cancer is the most common gynaecological cancer and has the highest mortality rate. Ovarian tumours are among the more dangerous types of cancer due to their heterogeneous origin and different dissemination profile, and an effective treatment option has not yet been developed (1). Doxorubicin is a widely used chemotherapeutic agent, but it has several limitations, including low water solubility and off-target effects, as well as numerous side effects. It is therefore crucial to discover drug candidate molecules that are effective against chemotherapeutics. Usnic acid is a drug candidate which has demonstrated therapeutic efficacy against ovarian cancer; however, its hydrophobic structure limits its potential (2). Zein is a distinctive polymer with a unique protein composition and minimal water solubility (3). Its polymeric structure makes it a promising candidate for the encapsulation of hydrophobic molecules and combination drug therapy (4). The aim of this study was to use Zein (a plant protein), doxorubicin and usnic acid to create a safe and efficient drug delivery system on ovarian cancer. Thus, we developed a Zein nanocarrier system using an optimized solvent-antisolvent technique. In addition, the cytotoxicity activity of free drugs and nanocarrier systems was evaluated to determine the anti-proliferative effect profile in ovarian cancer OVCAR-3 cells. According to the data obtained from the study, Zein nanocarrier system was characterized by TEM analysis with dimensions ranging between 90-400 nm. Zein nanocarrier system was loaded with 200 µg/mL doxorubicin with 75% encapsulation efficiency and showed higher release profile with varying surface charge in acidic medium. In the cytotoxicity analysis with ovarian normal cell OSE, it was determined that Zein nanoparticles did not show cytotoxic effect with 80-90% viability up to 72 h. The IC₅₀ concentration of usnic acid molecule in OVCAR-3 cells was found to be 9.7 µg/mL, while it was 1.084 µg/mL in usnic acid loaded nanocarrier system. As a result of the anti-proliferative effect potential of doxorubicin and usnic acid loaded Zein nanocarrier structure on OVCAR-3 cells, IC₅₀ concentration was determined as 1.04 µg/mL. This study demonstrated that the zein-based nanocarrier system, which is loaded with both usnic acid and doxorubicin, exhibits a potent anti-proliferative effect on OVCAR-3 ovarian cancer cells. Significantly, the reduction in the IC₅₀ concentration of usnic acid following nanoformulation indicates the enhanced therapeutic efficacy of the delivery system. These results suggest that Zein nanocarriers could be an effective, targeted drug delivery platform for treating ovarian cancer.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: *Ovarian cancer, Zein nanoparticles, Doxorubicin, Usnic acid*

Comparative Evaluation of Biopolymer Coated Selenium Nanoparticles for Ferulic Acid Delivery in Triple Negative Breast Cancer

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Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) represents a clinically challenging and biologically aggressive subtype of breast cancer with limited therapeutic avenues due to the lack of well-defined molecular targets. The current study focuses on the development and comparative evaluation of ferulic acid-loaded selenium nanoparticles (FA-SeNPs) functionalized with two distinct biopolymers, alginate (Alg@FA-SeNPs) and chitosan (CS@FA-SeNPs), as potential nanocarrier systems for targeted TNBC therapy. Ferulic acid (FA), a naturally occurring phenolic compound, exhibits pro-apoptotic, antioxidant, and anti-metastatic properties; however, its clinical application is limited by poor water solubility, rapid metabolism, and low systemic bioavailability. Encapsulation of FA within selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs), known for their redox-active and anticancer properties, was employed to enhance its stability, cellular uptake, and sustained release. The resulting FA-SeNPs were further surface-coated with alginate and chitosan to assess the influence of surface chemistry on biological activity, cellular interactions, and gene-level responses in TNBC models.

In vitro cytotoxicity analysis performed on MDA-MB-231 cells revealed that Alg@FA-SeNPs exhibited significantly enhanced cytotoxic activity, with an IC₅₀ value of 103.6 µg/ml at 48 hours, compared to CS@FA-SeNPs (IC₅₀ = 178 µg/ml). Mechanistic insights obtained via quantitative gene expression profiling showed a notable upregulation of H2AX, a biomarker of DNA double-strand break-induced genotoxic stress, particularly in Alg@FA-SeNP-treated cells. Conversely, CS@FA-SeNPs induced a more pronounced downregulation of Bcl-2, suggesting an alternative apoptotic mechanism involving mitochondrial pathway regulation.

Physicochemical characterization of the nanocarriers revealed distinct differences based on surface modifications. Particle size analysis using SEM and distribution profiling showed that bare SeNPs had an average size of 119 nm, which increased to 261 nm for CS@FA-SeNPs and 218 nm for Alg@FA-SeNPs. XRD analysis indicated a predominantly amorphous structure. Zeta potential measurements revealed near-neutral surface charges for Alg@FA-SeNPs (-2.51 to -2.04 mV) and highly positive values for CS@FA-SeNPs (+23.9 to +24.5 mV), consistent with chitosan's cationic nature. Despite their strong positive charge, CS@FA-SeNPs showed greater aggregation, indicating that surface charge alone does not guarantee colloidal stability. This underscores the importance of surface modification in optimizing nanoparticle stability and drug delivery.

Overall, these results highlight the potential of biopolymer-coated FA-SeNPs, especially alginate-functionalized nanoparticles, as promising platforms for enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of hydrophobic drugs in TNBC treatment.

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Keyword: Alginate, Chitosan, Triple Negative Breast Cancer, Selenium Nanoparticle

Engineering Multifunctional Magnetic Nanoparticles for Theranostics and Beyond

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Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have become quite popular in biotechnology and biomedicine due to their unique physicochemical properties that enable simultaneous diagnostic and therapeutic applications. Their dual functionality has garnered significant attention, particularly in theragnostic approaches involving magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and magnetic hyperthermia (MHT). We achieved significant enhancements in MR imaging and thermal efficiency by carefully adjusting the synthesis parameters of iron oxide MNPs prepared with additional metal ions, such as Mn and Zn. Utilizing the heat-responsive gene delivery potential of these nanoparticles, we developed cancer-specific treatment approaches via the external heat-control of gene expression. Moreover, our findings indicated that polydopamine-coated MNPs exhibit selective affinity for cell types and trigger reactive oxygen species (ROS)-mediated cytotoxicity in neuroblastoma cells. We observed both localized and systemic therapeutic responses in tumor-bearing rat models following the targeted delivery of immunostimulatory nucleic acids via MNPs. These results underscore the potential of MNPs in modulating immune responses for effective cancer therapy. Additionally, we demonstrated that surface-functionalized MNPs enhance protein immobilization efficiency and secretion levels in microorganism-based recombinant protein production platforms. Our combined results have been presented in this work that provides an in-depth understanding of the surface modification techniques, synthesis approaches, and several biological applies of MNPs. It discusses the revolutionary effect of these nanoparticles as active therapeutic entities able to direct challenging biological processes as well as delivery vehicles or imaging agents. This study consequently emphasizes the important roles MNPs could play in developing the future scene of nanomedicine and nanobiotechnology.

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Keyword: *magnetic nanoparticles, theragnostic applications, Surface Functionalization, nanobiotechnology*

Establishing replacement cell-based assays for the sensitive detection of Botulinum Neurotoxins

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Botulinum neurotoxins (BoNTs), produced by *Clostridium botulinum*, are among the most potent bacterial toxins, capable of causing muscle paralysis and leading to botulism, a severe and potentially fatal neuromuscular disease. Despite their extreme toxicity, BoNTs are widely used in small, controlled doses for medical and cosmetic purposes. This dual nature highlights the need for highly sensitive detection methods to ensure accurate dose control, food safety, and biosecurity. The current gold standard for BoNT detection, the mouse bioassay, is expensive, time-consuming, and ethically problematic, as it causes significant animal suffering and death. Consequently, there is an urgent need to develop rapid, cost-effective, and sensitive alternative assays that comply with the 3Rs principles, replacement, reduction, and refinement of animal use in scientific research.

Since BoNTs specifically target neurons at the neuromuscular junction (NMJ), efforts to develop alternatives to animal-based assays have focused on human neuroblastoma cell lines. In 2012, Fernández-Salas et al. introduced the SiMa neuroblastoma cell line for BoNT/A detection, which was later expanded by Rust et al. (2017) with a one-step ELISA for BoNT/B using the same cell line. Building on these developments, we present a newly engineered neuroblastoma cell line, LAN-5, with enhanced sensitivity to BoNTs (Caliskan et al., 2024).

In this study, these neuroblastoma cell lines were characterized and tested for responsiveness to various BoNT serotypes. To further improve sensitivity, the BoNT receptor GT1b was incorporated into the assay, and a re-engineered LAN-5 cell line was genetically modified to express a fluorescent reporter fused with NanoLuc luciferase-SNAP25, and overexpress the SV2A, which is a specific receptor protein to BoNT/A. The modified cells were then exposed to different concentrations of BoNT serotypes, and their responsiveness was evaluated using both functional and morphological assays, demonstrating their potential as a robust, animal-free alternative for BoNT detection.

Our results show that both tested cell lines express the relevant receptor and target proteins associated with BoNTs, enabling them to detect multiple serotypes effectively. Notably, by incorporating a reporter system with SV2A overexpression, we achieved BoNT/A detection at concentrations as low as 10 femtomolar (fM) (0.12 MLD₅₀), a marked improvement in sensitivity over existing models. The genetic enhancements introduced into the engineered neuroblastoma cell line significantly increased its responsiveness to BoNT/A, establishing it as a powerful and reliable tool for toxin detection. This advancement not only improves assay performance but also offers a promising alternative to animal-based testing.

The successful development of this cell line represents a meaningful step toward more ethical, efficient, and scalable BoNT detection methods in line with modern scientific and regulatory standards.

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Keyword: *Botulinum neurotoxin, Cell-based assays, LAN-5 neuroblastoma cell line, Botulinum neurotoxin-sensitive cell line*

Protein Binding Affinities of Silica Nanoparticles and Carbon-Based Nanomaterials: A Spectroscopic and Total Dissolved Solids Approach

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The protein and antibody binding capacities of carbon nanotubes, carbon fibers, and silica nanoparticles, which are used especially in biosensor designs and even in drug delivery studies, are crucial for effective designs. In this study, three nanomaterials—**silica nanoparticles (SiNPs)**, **multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs)**, and **carbon fibers (CF)**—were evaluated for their bovine serum albumin (BSA) binding capacities.

Silica nanoparticles (SiNPs) were synthesized via a sol-gel method and exhibited a **spherical morphology** with a diameter ranging from **30 to 50 nm**, as confirmed by transmission electron microscopy. These nanoparticles had a **high surface area (100–500 m²/g)** and were **rich in silanol (Si–OH) and siloxane (Si–O–Si) groups**, which facilitate hydrogen bonding with proteins. Their **surface charge was negative** at physiological pH, with a zeta potential of approximately **–24 to –30 mV**, and they were found to be **highly hydrophilic and colloidally stable in PBS(1)**. **Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs)** were obtained from Nanografi (product code NGO1AM0109G5) and possessed an **outer diameter of 190–590 nm**, with a purity exceeding **96%**. These nanostructures featured **concentric graphene layers**, giving them a **hydrophobic and highly conductive surface**. While unmodified MWCNTs are typically inert, surface functionalization with polar groups (e.g., –COOH or –OH) can improve their dispersibility and protein interaction capacity(2). **Carbon fibers (CF)**, as characterized in the literature, have diameters of approximately 7–10 μm and consist primarily of **graphitic carbon**. Although less porous and with lower surface area compared to nanoparticles, carbon fibers can present **oxygen-containing functional groups** on their surface following oxidation, providing limited sites for biomolecular interaction. Their **hydrophobic nature and large diameter** distinguish them from nano-scaled materials, and they are generally **chemically stable and electrically conductive**.

For the protein adsorption assay, BSA (1 mg/mL) was incubated with each nanomaterial—functionalized carbon nanotubes (FCNT), non-functionalized carbon nanotubes (NFCNT), carbon fiber (CF), and silica nanoparticles (SiNP)—prepared at 1 mg/mL in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4). The mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 2 hours under gentle agitation, followed by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes. In parallel, **total dissolved solids (TDS)** were measured in the supernatants using a calibrated benchtop **conductivity/TDS meter** to assess the release of soluble ionic species and support adsorption-related changes in sample composition.

SiNPs resulted in the highest TDS value (**547 ppm**), suggesting both high ionic activity and surface interaction. FCNTs also showed elevated TDS (**399 ppm**), possibly reflecting surface functional group leaching, whereas CF and BSA control remained near baseline levels (**327–328 ppm**). In parallel, **silica nanoparticles (SiNPs)** exhibited the highest BSA adsorption, with a **2.74% decrease** in residual protein concentration, indicating strong surface-protein interaction likely driven by hydrogen bonding and high surface area(3). **ANOVA analysis revealed a statistically significant difference** between groups ($p < 0.02$), confirming material-specific variation in BSA adsorption.

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Keyword: Silica nanoparticles, Bovine serum albumin (BSA), Protein adsorption, Carbon nanotubes

Unraveling of Adverse Effect of Single-walled Carbon Nanotubes in vitro Using Proteomics Approach

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Carbon nanotubes exhibit remarkable properties including exceptional mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties with high chemical stability and adaptability, enable these materials bring groundbreaking advancements in different fields of science[1–5]. However, all these alluring wide range of applications have been hampered by their adverse effects. In this study, the nanotoxicity of SWCNTs have been investigated using breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7) and proteome landscape of MCF-7 cells after exposure to SWCNTs have been studied using Proteomics approach.

To begin with, MCF-7 cells were exposed to characterized and functionalized SWCNTs in three different groups and MTT cell proliferation assay have been performed for cytotoxicity of SWCNTs. In further steps, protein digests have been prepared according to optimized concentration in three groups. In the last step, different groups of digested protein samples have been analysed using nano-liquid chromatography mass-spectrometry (nLC-MS/MS) analysis and the changes of proteins after exposure to SWCNTs have been analysed using comparative analysis between control group and exposure groups. Through the above investigation, approximately 3500 unique protein groups were identified across all three experimental groups in which protein abundance change varying from 1.5 to 20-fold in experimental groups versus control group. There are 70 proteins have been found differentially regulated such as tendency of increase or decrease in their abundance when compare to control group. Among the differentially regulated proteins, approximately two-thirds exhibited increased abundance (upregulation), while one-third showed decreased abundance (downregulation) relative to the control group. Overall, from above studies a series of differentially regulated proteins associated with adverse effect of SWCNTs have been achieved in vitro. It will not only provide biological clues of regulation of protein function/activity and cytotoxic effect of SWCNTs but also pave the way for further study of cytotoxic effect of carbon-based nanomaterials in cellular level with different cell lines as well.

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Keyword: SWCNTs, MCF-7 cell line, Adverse effect, Proteomics

Engineered Nanomaterials for Neuromodulation and Single-Photon Technologies

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The flourishing fields of neuromodulation and quantum technologies critically rely on the precise engineering and integration of advanced nanomaterials.

Firstly, we address the challenge of vision restoration through advanced retinal prostheses. Retinal degeneration-related diseases pose a significant global health burden, and current treatments lack definitive efficacy. While optoelectronic biointerfaces offer promising solutions for partially restoring vision, optimizing their stimulation electrodes is paramount for safe and efficient neuronal activation. We focus on integrating sputtered iridium oxide film (SIROF), known for its exceptional biocompatibility and high pseudocapacitance due to reversible redox reactions, into our pixelated quantum dot and nanowire-based optoelectronic devices. Our work details the optimization of SIROF processing conditions, including sputtering parameters to precisely control film thickness, surface morphology, and elemental composition. Comprehensive characterization using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) shed light on the film properties, while cyclic voltammetry and electrophysiology (patch clamp) on SIROF-integrated active devices confirm the superior electrochemical and neurostimulation performance crucial for next-generation retinal implants.

Secondly, we explore the development of ultrafast, room-temperature near-infrared single-photon emitters, fundamental for scalable quantum technologies. Conventional epitaxial quantum dots (QDs) achieve high purity but are limited by cryogenic operating temperatures and lack silicon compatibility. Colloidal quantum dots (CQDs) offer room-temperature operation and facile integration, yet typically suffer from slow emission rates. To overcome this, we engineered a robust plasmonic nanoparticle-on-mirror (NPoM) nanocavity to significantly enhance the emission rate of single heavy-metal-free copper-doped InP/ZnSe CQDs. By sandwiching a monolayer of these CQDs between a bottom Au mirror and a top Au nanoparticle, we achieve extreme light confinement within a nanoscale gap. This plasmonic coupling leads to a remarkable Purcell enhancement factor of 10^6 , yielding sub-picosecond emission lifetimes. We observe pronounced exciton-plasmon coupling at room temperature, evidenced by characteristic splitting (90 meV) in both scattering and photoluminescence (PL) spectra, with strong NIR PL centered at 800 nm under 633 nm excitation. Our findings underscore the potential of InP-based CQDs as a viable platform for high-speed, room-temperature single-photon emission, paving the way for their integration into future quantum photonic circuits.

Collectively, these studies highlight the transformative potential of engineered nanomaterials, from optimizing bio-integrated interfaces for therapeutic applications to developing foundational components for quantum computing and communication, showcasing the breadth and impact of nanotechnology in addressing grand challenges.

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Keyword: *Bioelectronics, Optoelectronics, Colloidal Quantum Dots, Nanophotonics*

Beespenser Micro Dispensing Device and Ink Technologies

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Beespenser presents a novel micro-dispensing platform, Monobee, designed to address the growing demand for agile, cost-effective, and scalable fabrication methods in printed electronics. The system enables the direct deposition of functional inks onto a wide range of substrates, supporting both flexible and rigid circuit architectures. Unlike conventional cleanroom-dependent approaches, Monobee facilitates rapid prototyping and low-volume production in standard lab environments.

Our integrated solution combines customized ink formulations with precision hardware to optimize conductivity, adhesion, and printability. Specifically, we formulate silver nanoparticle inks and carbon-based conductive inks with tailored rheological properties to enhance performance in applications such as IoT devices, flexible sensors, and printed energy storage components. By eliminating the need for photolithography or etching, our method reduces material waste and accelerates design-to-device cycles.

Integration of advanced materials with precision micro-dispensing technologies can accelerate innovation in printed electronics. The proposed platform provides a modular and scalable alternative to traditional fabrication methods, reducing reliance on cleanroom infrastructure while maintaining high-resolution patterning and material compatibility. By bridging the gap between materials development and device prototyping, our approach facilitates accessible, rapid, and sustainable production pathways for emerging applications in next-generation electronics.

Keyword: *Micro-dispensing, conductive ink, printed electronics, flexible electronics*

Interatomic Potential Development for Bimetallic Nanoalloys Through Machine Learning

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Metallic nanoparticles such as Pt and Rh have an ever-increasing scientific attraction due to their high catalytic activity on a wide range of technological applications from fuel cells to dental alloys. However, some of the most important problems in the field of metallic nanoparticle catalysts are high cost, mining difficulties and insufficient raw material resources. Therefore, one of the basic solutions is that alloying them with cheaper metals which will not reduce their catalytic activity. In some cases, it is even possible to increase the catalytic activity by alloying due to the synergic effects depending on the metal selected.

Theoretical studies in metallic catalysis concentrate on the crystal structures and stabilities of catalyst nanoparticles and the reaction dynamics on them. In addition to the accuracy and precision limitations due to the selected method in theoretical studies, there exist also limitations such as temperature and entropic effects, which are not generally considered especially in quantum mechanical methods. Although such calculations can be made on device operating temperatures by using techniques based on molecular dynamics simulations, they have limitations especially for quantum mechanics level studies as these techniques require much larger system sizes and need very long simulation times. Therefore, systems in simulations for catalysis cannot reach experimental sizes and they are limited to ideal and ordered crystal structures. However, actual catalyst materials in experiments usually have defects and mixed phase structures. Although calculations for large systems can be reachable by techniques based on classical mechanics using force fields, the accuracy of these calculations are quite limited because they do not include electronic interactions. At this point, machine learning potentials such as GAP started to gain importance in literature due to their potential to generate the accuracy level of quantum mechanics-based techniques.

In this respect, the main goal is set to generate Gaussian Approximation Potential that has quantum mechanical accuracy using machine learning techniques for actual size nanoparticles of Pt-Cu and Au-Rh alloys. Thus, technologically important Pt-Cu and Au-Rh alloy nanoparticles are investigated first by quantum mechanical level molecular dynamics simulations and then the results are used as training set to develop machine learning type GAP potentials. The one-to-one energy and force comparison of DFT and GAP potentials gives good linear relationship both for training and validation sets. Moreover, the structural optimization results obtained from GAP potentials show very promising accuracy. Furthermore, the developed GAP potentials are showed to produce stable molecular dynamics simulations for larger systems that can not be dealt by quantum mechanical methods.

Keyword: *Machine learning, Gaussian approximation potential, density functional theory, bimetallic nanoparticles*

Molecularly Imprinted Polymer-based SPR Biosensor for Real-time Detection of Histamine in Food Safety Monitoring

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Histamine, a heterocyclic biogenic amine formed by the decarboxylation of L-histidine through amino acid decarboxylase activity, is the most abundant and toxic biogenic amine found in meat and fish products. It serves as a key indicator of food freshness and safety, particularly in protein-rich foods such as fish. Elevated histamine levels can cause foodborne intoxication, highlighting the need for effective monitoring throughout the food supply chain. However, conventional detection methods are often complex, time-consuming, and require extensive sample preparation.

In this study, a highly sensitive and selective surface plasmon resonance (SPR) biosensor was developed for the rapid and label-free detection of histamine. The sensor incorporates a molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) nanofilm as the recognition layer, synthesized via UV-induced photopolymerization using a vinyl imidazole–Cu(II) metal-chelate functional monomer. To evaluate imprinting efficiency, non-imprinted polymer (NIP) films were also prepared under identical conditions without the template molecule. SPR biosensor chips were characterized by contact angle measurements, atomic force microscopy (AFM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

The developed biosensor exhibited a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.057 mg/kg and a linear response range of 0.11–22.23 mg/kg within 8 minutes. The MIP-based SPR biosensor was successfully applied to fish samples, demonstrating its potential for real-time and on-site monitoring of food quality. This work presents a promising platform for selective histamine detection using metal-assisted molecular imprinting, offering a rapid, specific, and practical approach to enhance food safety monitoring.

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Keyword: *Foodborne Toxin, Histamine, Molecularly imprinted polymers, Surface plasmon resonance biosensors*

Gold-Decorated Iron Oxide Nanoplatfoms in Electrochemical Lateral Flow Assays for Improved SARS-CoV-2 IgG Detection

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Electrochemical lateral flow assays (LFAs) represent a promising advancement in point-of-care diagnostics, offering a synergistic combination of the simplicity and low cost of traditional lateral flow strips with the high sensitivity and quantitative capabilities of electrochemical detection. In these systems, biorecognition events occurring on the test line of the LFA strip are typically mediated by labeled nanoparticles. Instead of relying on visual colorimetric readouts, the accumulation of these labels at the detection zone is electrochemically quantified using integrated electrodes. This approach overcomes the limitations of visual interpretation, providing objective and potentially more sensitive results, making electrochemical LFAs attractive for a wide range of applications, including infectious disease diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and food safety testing.

In our novel works, we introduce a novel electrochemical LFA system for the enhanced detection of SARS-CoV-2 IgG. The system integrates custom-synthesized gold-decorated iron oxide nanoplatfoms, with and without PEG surface modification, with a custom-designed screen-printed electrode (SPE) to transduce the antigen-antibody binding event into a measurable electrochemical signal. This work details the preparation and characterization of novel nanoplatfoms based on iron oxide nanoparticles with and without surface modification using polyethylene glycol (PEG) and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). These nanoplatfoms were synthesized via a hydrothermal method and subsequently conjugated with carboxyl ferrocene (C-Fc) and spike protein for integration into an electrochemical LFA to detect SARS-CoV-2 IgG. Comprehensive material characterization using SEM, EDS, FTIR, and DLS confirmed the successful synthesis and functionalization of the nanostructures, revealing uniform particle size and distribution, particularly for the PEGylated and gold-decorated nanoplatfoms. Electrochemical characterization using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) demonstrated that the nanoplatfoms exhibited superior charge transfer properties and enhanced signal intensity. The integration of these nanoplatfoms with a custom-designed screen-printed electrode (SPE) in an LFA format allowed for sensitive electrochemical detection of IgG in various buffer conditions and serum samples. The ironoxide@PEG@AuNP-based electrochemical LFA showed improved analytical performance, including a lower detection limit, compared to traditional colorimetric LFAs. Furthermore, the system demonstrated reliable IgG detection in diluted serum samples, highlighting its potential for clinical diagnostic applications.

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Keyword: *Electrochemical Lateral Flow Assay, Gold Nanoparticles, Iron Oxide Nanoparticles, IgG Detection*

The Characterization of Immobilized Urease onto Modified Cellulose Nanocrystals

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Urease (EC 3.5.1.5) is an enzyme in the hydrolases class that catalyses the hydrolysis of one molecule of urea to release one molecule of carbon dioxide and two molecules of ammonia. Immobilized urease has potential applications in the removal of urea from blood or in the haemodialysis process, in the regeneration of synthetic dialysate solution; in biosensors for the determination of urea in blood, urine and wastewater; in the removal of urea from beverages in the food industry and in the conversion of urea in fertilizer wastewater (Alptekin, 2022). In this study, cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) were modified with glutaraldehyde (GA), 1,2-bis(3-aminopropylamino)ethane (1,2 BIS) and polyethyleneimine (PEI). Urease was immobilized on support modified with GA by covalent (IU_{CNC-GA}), and on supports modified with 1,2 BIS and PEI by ionic adsorption ($IU_{CNC-1,2BIS}$, $IU_{CNC-PEI}$). The characterization of immobilized urease preparations was performed. The optimum pH value was determined as 7.0, 7.5 and 7.0 for IU_{CNC-GA} , $IU_{CNC-1,2BIS}$ and $IU_{CNC-PEI}$, respectively. The optimum temperatures were determined as 50°C, 70°C and 70°C for IU_{CNC-GA} , $IU_{CNC-1,2BIS}$ and $IU_{CNC-PEI}$, respectively. When their thermal stabilities were examined, the all-immobilized urease preparations did not significantly lose their initial activities after 8 hours of incubation at 37°C. When the kinetic parameters were examined, the highest V_{max} and K_m values were found to be 140.8 IU/mg protein and 83.7 mM for $IU_{CNC-1,2BIS}$, respectively. The V_{max} value for free urease is 51.5 IU/mg protein and the K_m value is 2.7 mM (Alptekin 2019). The significant changes occurred in the kinetic parameters of urease after immobilization. The main reasons can be the conformational changes in the enzyme during immobilization and/or limitations in the approach of the substrate to the active site of the enzyme. As a result, the ureases immobilized on CNC with different modification methods show high thermal stabilities and when evaluated in terms of activity, they show the potential for use in wearable technologies in dialysate regeneration. In our further studies, the performance of immobilized urease preparations in batch and continuous reactor types will be examined.

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Keyword: Urease, Cellulose nanocrystals, immobilization, thermal stability

Development of Micro/Nanofluidic Technologies for Life Science Applications

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The field of microfluidics has rapidly evolved as a cornerstone technology in fluid physics and the life sciences, offering sophisticated methods for controlling and manipulating fluids at the microscale. This talk will delve into the development of advanced microfluidic systems with a focus on applications in fluid physics, microphysiological platforms, and life sciences. We will explore acoustofluidic techniques for enhanced flow control and mixing, utilizing acoustic waves to manipulate microflows efficiently, and droplet microfluidics, which enables high-throughput analysis and precise control over fluid partitioning, with significant implications for sample handling and reaction processes.

In addition, the integration of microwave sensors into microfluidic platforms offers heat-driven mixing and thermal actuation, providing novel avenues for temperature-controlled flow manipulation. The discussion will also extend to microphysiological systems, which replicate tissue and organ functions in vitro, facilitating research in drug testing and disease modeling. These platforms enhance our understanding of fluid dynamics under biologically relevant conditions, enabling detailed studies on cell and tissue interactions. Altogether, these advancements illustrate the powerful convergence of microfluidics, fluid physics and life sciences, with applications extending into biotechnology, regenerative medicine, and materials science.

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Keyword: *Micro/Nanofluidics, Biomaterials, Nanotechnology, Microphysiological Systems*

Nuclear Lamina Structure and Dynamics in Health and Disease

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Lamin proteins, integral components of the nuclear lamina, form a two-dimensional protein meshwork, maintaining the structural integrity and elasticity of the nucleus [3]. It consists primarily of lamin proteins—A/C-type and B-type—that form dynamic networks with distinct structural characteristics. 3D structured illumination microscopy (3D-SIM) reveals that B-type lamins form a loosely packed outer meshwork, with larger meshwork faces than the more uniform, denser A/C-type network [5].

The lamina meshwork can be disrupted in several diseases. An example is progeria (HGPS), where a single point mutation in the LMNA (A-type lamins) gene results in a reduced exchange between peripheral lamins and nucleoplasmic ones [1]. Mutated lamin A proteins (progerin) assemble into closely packed nematic phases at the nuclear periphery, in contrast to the relatively more randomly oriented isotropic microdomains in healthy cells [2]. Progerin also indirectly alters the B-type lamin meshwork, triggering further enlargement of mesh faces [4].

Despite these findings, the underlying molecular mechanisms that lead to such phase transitions and the strong peripheral association of lamin in diseases like progeria are still unclear. In this study, we present a coarse-grained molecular dynamics model to explore the kinetics and morphology of the nuclear lamina. We systematically manipulate lamin concentration, inter-lamin interactions, and lamin-nucleus associations. Our analyses can recapitulate the lamina's nematic phase formation in disease with increasing lamin concentration [2]. Furthermore, at lower inter-lamin attraction, lamins kinetically dissociate from the periphery, reminiscent of healthy nuclei. Our results also suggest that the ratio of lamin-lamin to lamin-nucleus interaction leads to a plethora of meshwork architecture with varying face size, shape, and edge characteristics.

Overall, our computational results provide insights into how altered lamin interactions could lead to morphological aberrations of the lamina in disease. These findings may inform future therapeutic strategies aimed at modulating lamin concentration and interactions. Future studies will extend this model to incorporate spatial chromatin organization, alongside lamin-chromatin interactions, to better capture disease-associated hallmarks and nuclear shape anomalies.

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Keyword: nucleus, lamina, disease, polymer modeling

Synthesis and Characterization of Silver Nanoparticles Obtained by Green Synthesis

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Today, the production of metal nanoparticles (metal-NP), which are widely used in many fields such as agriculture, biotechnology, catalysis, cosmetics, energy, electronics, mechanics, optics, pharmacy, sensor technologies, and textiles, is receiving increasing attention [1]. Advances in this field are accelerating with the adoption of environmentally friendly methods; researchers are exploring ways to produce metal-NPs using sustainable sources that are readily available in nature, rather than toxic substances, in line with green chemistry principles. Plant-based materials offer significant advantages for the biosynthesis of metal nanoparticles, as access to such biological sources is easy, economical, safe, and environmentally harmless. Additionally, the bioactive components contained in plants possess unique properties that support the formation of nanoparticles of various sizes and shapes, making them ideal synthesis tools [2].

Advances in nanotechnology have expanded the boundaries of materials science, and research on metal nanoparticles has increased significantly. In this context, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are among the most notable metallic nanostructures due to their high surface areas, optical properties, and antimicrobial activities [3]. It has been demonstrated that AgNPs interact with bacterial cell walls, disrupting membrane permeability, entering the cell and damaging DNA, and triggering the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). This enables them to be effective against antibiotic-resistant strains. Traditional chemical and physical synthesis methods for AgNPs have various environmental and biological limitations due to toxic chemicals and high energy requirements. Therefore, there has been an increasing shift toward sustainable and environmentally friendly methods in recent years. Green synthesis offers an important alternative in this context [4].

In addition to being costly and low in yield, the physicochemical methods used in metal-NP synthesis involve the use of toxic, environmentally harmful chemicals. As an alternative to these methods, the environmentally friendly green synthesis method has emerged in recent years, enabling nanoparticle synthesis using natural resources such as plants and microorganisms. Using this method, where phytochemicals and enzymes act as reducing and coating agents, nanoparticles can be synthesized without the use of toxic substances, and well-defined nanoparticles can be synthesized on a large scale while minimizing environmental impacts [5].

In this study, the seeds of the *Vitex agnus-castus* plant extract was used for the synthesis of AgNPs by green synthesis. In this context, the temperature, pH, synthesis time, and reducing agent concentration required for the synthesis of AgNP were optimized. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized using UV-Vis spectroscopy, SEM, FT-IR, and XRD.

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Keyword: *Green Synthesis, Vitex agnus-castus, Silver Nanoparticle*

Innovative Green Nanotechnology for Sustainable Food Packaging: A Biodegradable Approach Using *Helichrysum arenarium*-Derived ZnO Nanoparticles

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Food packaging is an essential component in preserving the quality and extending the shelf life of food products, while also preventing contamination. The widespread use of petroleum-based polymers in food packaging has raised serious environmental concerns due to their non-biodegradability and persistence in nature. In response, biodegradable biopolymers such as starch, polylactic acid (PLA), cellulose, and chitosan have emerged as eco-friendly alternatives. However, despite their renewable origin and compostability, these materials often suffer from poor mechanical strength, high moisture sensitivity, and lack of antimicrobial activity—limitations that restrict their broader application in food packaging. To overcome these deficiencies, the incorporation of functional nanomaterials into biopolymer matrices has emerged as a promising strategy. Among these, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) have attracted significant attention due to their unique physicochemical properties, including high surface area, UV-blocking capability, and pronounced antimicrobial activity against a broad spectrum of microorganisms. When embedded in biopolymer matrices, ZnO NPs not only reinforce mechanical and barrier properties but also impart active antimicrobial functionality, making the composite material suitable for intelligent and active packaging applications.

In this context, the present study aims to synthesize ZnO nanoparticles via an environmentally benign, green chemistry route using *Helichrysum arenarium* (dwarf everlast) leaf extract as a natural reducing and capping agent. Green synthesis eliminates the use of toxic solvents and harsh reducing agents typically involved in chemical and physical nanoparticle fabrication methods, thereby aligning with sustainability goals. The synthesized ZnO NPs were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), UV–Vis spectroscopy, and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) to determine their crystallinity, morphology, optical properties, and functional groups. The particles exhibited a hexagonal wurtzite structure with a narrow size distribution in the 50–80 nm range. Furthermore, the antimicrobial efficacy of the ZnO NPs was evaluated via the disk diffusion method against selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as a fungal species, at varying concentrations (100%, 75%, 50%, 25%). The nanoparticles demonstrated notable antimicrobial activity, underscoring their potential to inhibit microbial proliferation when integrated into packaging systems. The overarching objective of this study is to develop an advanced biodegradable packaging material by incorporating green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles into biopolymer matrices. The resulting nanocomposite aims to combine environmental sustainability with enhanced mechanical, barrier, and antimicrobial properties, contributing to safer and longer-lasting food preservation. The upcoming phase of the research will focus on the fabrication and evaluation of ZnO–biopolymer films under real storage conditions to assess their performance, stability, and biodegradability, thereby laying the groundwork for scalable, eco-friendly food packaging solutions.

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Keyword: Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles, Green Synthesis, Biodegradable Packaging, Antimicrobial Properties

Engineering the Nature of Rh Catalyst for Integrated CO₂ Capture and Utilization via Dry Reforming of Methane: Effect of CeO_x and FeO_x Promoters on HAP

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Integrated CO₂ capture and utilization (ICCU) provides a direct pathway to carbon-neutral fuels and chemicals by coupling CO₂ adsorption with catalytic conversion. Within this scheme, dry reforming of methane (DRM) offers a thermodynamically favorable route that converts CO₂ and CH₄ simultaneously into syngas (H₂/CO ≈ 1), the ideal feedstock for downstream processes such as Fischer–Tropsch synthesis [1,2]. Yet, even highly active rhodium (Rh) catalysts can deactivate under severe DRM conditions because of carbon deposition and particle sintering.

Here, first, a series of Rh catalysts were designed to investigate the effect of promoters (CeO_x, FeO_x) on DRM activity, stability, and carbon resistance. Hydroxyapatite (HAP) was used as the support material due to its high thermal stability, basic character, and oxygen vacancy-rich structure, which are known to enhance coke resistance and CO₂ activation [3,4].

DRM performance tests were conducted on Rh-based catalysts supported on HAP, and the effects of promoter addition were systematically evaluated to understand their role in improving redox properties and suppressing carbon deposition. Catalyst stability was assessed through time-on-stream (TOS) experiments. Post-reaction characterization of spent catalysts using TGA, Raman spectroscopy, and XPS revealed insights into the deactivation pathways and nature of possible coke species. Additionally, in-situ FTIR spectroscopy was performed on fresh catalysts under reaction conditions to identify surface intermediates and gain a deeper mechanistic understanding of the process.

Following performance tests, selected catalysts were physically mixed with CaO, a high-temperature CO₂ adsorbent, to produce dual-functional materials (DFMs) for an integrated CO₂ capture and dry reforming of methane (ICC-DRM) process. The adsorption–desorption behavior of CaO was investigated by temperature-programmed desorption (CO₂-TPD), providing insight into its capture capacity and regeneration potential. After initial screening of CO₂ adsorption and CH₄ conversion under ICC-DRM conditions, promising DFMs were subjected to cyclic testing to assess their long-term performance and resistance to deactivation over multiple cycles.

The results demonstrate that rational tuning of metal type and promoter selection can yield highly effective multifunctional materials for integrated carbon capture and utilization. This study provides insights for designing durable, coke-resistant DFMs for ICCU applications and contributes to the advancement of net-zero carbon technologies.

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Keyword: *Dry reforming of methane, dual-functional materials, hydroxyapatite (HAP), ICC-DRM*

Shear-Stable and Cytocompatible PDMS Surface Functionalization for Sustained Cell Adhesion in Microfluidic Organ-on-Chip Applications

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The inherent hydrophobicity of Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) poses significant challenges for its use in cell culture applications, particularly in organ-on-chip technology. This study presents a novel, versatile, and biocompatible surface treatment method for polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), designed to significantly improve its cytocompatibility and shear stability in organ-on-chip applications. Four tailored surface functionalization protocols were systematically explored using 3-(Trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate (TMSPMA), optimized to enhance wettability, surface roughness, and chemical functionality – leading to robust and sustained cell adhesion. The efficacy of these treatments was confirmed via comprehensive surface characterizations of contact angle measurements, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The changed hydrophilicity supported robust cell adhesion, proliferation and viability that were determined using three distinct human cell types: HUVECs, MCF-7, and Human-derived induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs). Importantly, our findings show that the treated PDMS supports long-term adhesion and proliferation under both static and dynamic microfluidic conditions, with minimal cell detachment even under flow rates corresponding to physiological shear stress (~1.5 dyne/cm²). Numerical simulations further validate the experimental flow conditions, strengthening the model's physiological relevance. This study underscores the effectiveness of TMSPMA treatment in improving PDMS compatibility for cell culture, offering an accessible, tunable, and scalable solution for researchers aiming to create more reliable and biologically relevant microfluidic systems.

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Keyword: *Microfluidic Systems, Organ-on-chip, Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), 3-(Trimethoxysilyl)propyl Methacrylate (TMSPMA)*

Synthesis and Characterization of Polymeric Nanocarriers from Renewable Resources for Cancer Therapy

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The increasing global burden of cancer and the inherent limitations of the classical chemotherapeutic approaches, like poor aqueous solubility, low bioavailability, or selective cytotoxicity, have further pushed the need for novel delivery systems. Many of these alternatives based on nanocarriers have environmental and biocompatibility issues as they make extensive use of synthetic petroleum-derived polymers and toxic organic solvents. This project followed an approach attempting to develop multifunctional nanogels coming from renewable resources for controlling the delivery of Doxorubicin, hence investigating both therapeutic and ecological limitations associated with present-day nanocarriers. It also intended to bridge the translational gap between stimuli-responsive polymeric systems and green chemistry into the evolution of circular biomedical nanotechnologies.

The experimental design included several optimization phases. Polymeric nanogels were prepared by UV-induced photopolymerization of methacrylated methyl ricinoleate, a castor oil-based monomer, and thus served as the hydrophobic plant-derived constituent. The backbone of the nanogel was formed from the thermo-responsive monomer N-isopropylacrylamide and the crosslinker N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide, whereas the pH-responsive and cationic character was imparted by either 2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate or (3-Acrylamidopropyl)trimethylammonium chloride. Formulation parameters involving monomer ratios, photoinitiator content, UV exposure duration, and surfactant concentration were optimized systematically in each phase. The generated nanogels were characterized by dynamic light scattering, zeta potential, Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy. The results demonstrated successful polymer network formation with tunable particle size and charge responding to temperature and pH changes.

The drug doxorubicin was loaded by the passive incubation into the nanogels, and the encapsulation integrity was validated by fluorescence measurements conducted in the assay which confirmed minimal quenching. Cytocompatibility testing in vitro using HUVEC cells demonstrated that the nanogels had no toxic effects up to 200 µg/mL. Moreover, nanogels demonstrated activities against Gram-positive organisms such as Bacillus subtilis and Enterococcus faecalis. Therefore, these findings indicated the development of a biocompatible, dual-responsive, and environmentally friendly nanocarrier system serving both for targeted drug delivery and antimicrobial action

Keyword: *Nanogels, Plant-based monomers, Photopolymerization, Dual-responsive systems*

Engineering Actuable Cell Culture Substrates with Embedded Nanoparticles for Probing Cellular Force Generation under Mechanical Stimulation

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Cells in their physiological environment are routinely exposed to various forms of external mechanical stimulation, arising from muscle movements, tissue deformations, and the flow of physiological fluids. Through a process central to the field of mechanobiology, cells sense and transduce the physical cues such as matrix stiffness, stretch, curvature, and shear stress into biochemical signals that regulate critical functions like differentiation, proliferation, and migration. Cells also actively generate forces for movement and remodeling their environment. This dynamic interplay between mechanical stimulation and cellular force generation is fundamental to tissue homeostasis and the progression of diseases like cancer [1]. Current in vitro approaches allow for applying physiologically relevant mechanical stimulation [2] or, separately, for measuring cellular force generation via techniques like traction force microscopy (TFM) [3]. However, systems that combine these two capabilities are notably lacking. Such integrated platforms are essential for fully elucidating cellular responses within mechanically active environments.

Here, we report on the development and characterization of a modular platform designed to address this need. The core of the system is a substrate with tunable stiffness (1 – 60 kPa) fabricated from PDMS blends, SLYGARD™ 527 and 184. We established a robust method for embedding fluorescent nanoparticles (NPs) within these substrates as fiducial markers for tracking substrate deformation, enabling 2D TFM. These substrates were configured as thin actuable membranes, that were then integrated with a PDMS pneumatic actuation layer and cell culture chambers fabricated from biocompatible resin using stereolithography 3D-printing. The modular nature of the platform enables later integration with microphysiological systems incorporating 3D culture and flow. The device's mechanical performance was characterized by quantifying strain fields with Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) and validated with COMSOL simulations. Initial tests with MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells confirmed the platform's biocompatibility and its capability to perform Fourier Transform Traction Cytometry (FTTC) analysis following mechanical stimulation.

This study establishes a successful methodology for fabricating and validating a modular integrated system for future dynamic mechanobiology studies where the complex interplay between external mechanical stimuli and cellular forces can be investigated in processes such as wound healing and cancer metastasis.

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Keyword: *Microfabrication, PDMS, Nanoparticle, Traction Force Microscopy*

Surface Structure Sensitivity of NO_x reduction on Well-Defined Cu₂O Nanocrystals

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The mechanistic understanding of NO_x decomposition over CuO_x-based catalysts remains a subject of significant interest due to their potential in low-temperature DeNO_x applications. In this study, we employ shape-defined Cu₂O nanocrystals as model catalysts to unravel facet-specific interactions governing NO_x adsorption and reduction. Shape-controlled Cu₂O nanocrystals with well-defined cubic and octahedral morphologies, preferentially exposing the {100} and {111} facets, respectively, were synthesized with high precision and employed as model systems to probe the facet-dependent nature of NO_x surface chemistry. To investigate the nature of surface-adsorbed species, in situ Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was utilized during the probe molecule adsorption experiments (NO_x, NO_x+H₂), enabling temperature-dependent and pressure-dependent analysis of surface intermediates. The morphology, crystallinity, and surface composition of the nanocrystals were comprehensively characterized using SEM, TEM, XRD, XPS, XANES, EXAFS, and ATR-IR. On {100}-terminated cubic nanocrystals, bridging and bidentate nitrate/nitrite species were predominantly formed, whereas {111}-terminated octahedral nanocrystals favored monodentate coordination modes. These differences are attributed to the variation in surface geometry and coordination environment: the {100} facets present high-coordination terrace sites conducive to polydentate binding, while the {111} facets are enriched with coordinatively unsaturated sites (e.g., kinks and edges), which stabilize low-coordination adsorbate configurations. Temperature-programmed desorption (TPD) experiments, combined with temperature-dependent in-situ FTIR spectroscopy conducted over the range of 50–700 °C, provided insight into the thermal behavior of adsorbed NO_x species and their decomposition pathways. The results revealed that NO_x intermediates on the {111} facets of octahedral Cu₂O nanocrystals exhibited greater thermal stability compared to those on the {100} facets of cubic nanocrystals, even though {100} surfaces are typically associated with stronger Cu–O bonding. This highlights the important influence of surface atomic structure and coordination on catalytic behavior. Interestingly, despite their weaker IR signals, octahedral Cu₂O released more NO_x during TPD, which is attributed to the smaller IR absorption cross-section of adsorbed NO_x species on octahedral Cu₂O as compared to that of the cubic Cu₂O nanocrystal model catalyst surface. These results collectively indicate that the adsorption modes, thermal stability, and decomposition dynamics of NO_x on Cu₂O nanocrystals are highly sensitive to the exposed crystallographic facets, underscoring the pivotal influence of surface structure in optimizing the selectivity and efficiency of Cu-based DeNO_x catalysts.

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Keyword: *In situ FTIR, DeNO_x, Cu₂O, Nanocrystals*

Hydrogen Production From Formic Acid Through N-Porous Carbon Supported Cu/Pd Nanoparticles

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With the depletion of fossil fuel reserves, the development of clean and sustainable alternative energy sources has become increasingly critical. Among these, hydrogen stands out as one of the most promising candidates to replace conventional non-renewable fuels. In the context of hydrogen generation from formic acid (FAD), palladium (Pd) nanoparticles, despite their high cost and reliance on noble metals, are commonly utilized due to their significant catalytic efficiency. To overcome the high cost and limited availability of noble metals, considerable efforts have been directed toward developing improved catalytic systems, such as Co/Pd-supported porous carbon [1] and ZrO₂/Pd-supported porous carbon [2].

Here we show that copper-promoted nitrogen-doped porous carbon can be utilized in the dehydrogenation of formic acid. ZIF-8 crystals, metal-organic framework (MOF) materials composed of 2-methylimidazole ligands coordinated with zinc cations, were synthesized and pyrolyzed at 900 °C under Ar environment to produce porous carbon. The direct carbonization of ZIF-8 crystals led to an increase in the active nitrogen content, the formation of porous carbon, and significant modifications to the pore structure and surface properties. Subsequently, various concentrations of copper and palladium nanoparticles were incorporated into the synthesized porous carbon structure. The catalysts have been analyzed using various characterization techniques, including SEM, XRD, FTIR, ICP-OES, and HR-TEM. The influence of different Pd and Cu concentrations on the turnover frequency (TOF) was systematically investigated. The resulting novel materials demonstrated remarkable TOF values up to 1176 h⁻¹ for the formic acid dehydrogenation at 60 °C. This study highlights that a satisfactory TOF value can be achieved using an alternative catalyst with reduced reliance on noble metals.

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Keyword: Hydrogen production, Formic Acid Decomposition, Copper, Porous Carbon

NiMoO₄-Supported Rhodium Nanoparticles for Efficient Hydrolysis of Ammonia Borane

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Herein, a series of Rhodium catalysts with varying Rh loadings (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 wt%) supported on NiMoO₄ were prepared for the catalytic hydrolysis of ammonia borane (AB). The Rh nanoparticles were deposited onto the NiMoO₄ surface via an impregnation–reduction method. Structural and morphological characteristics of the catalysts were investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), and elemental mapping. 4% Rh/NiMoO₄ catalyst (504.5 mL H₂/g_{cat}·min) has a higher H₂ generation rate (HGR) than other synthesized catalysts for the hydrolysis of AB. Furthermore, this catalyst demonstrated excellent recyclability, maintaining 100% H₂ selectivity even after five consecutive catalytic cycles.

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Keyword: Rh, NiMoO₄, Hydrogen Generation, Ammonia Borane

Nanostructured Architectures of Iron Oxide Cubes and Silver Nanowires for Improved Hyperthermia Performance

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Magnetic hyperthermia is a promising therapeutic approach where the heating efficiency of iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) plays a critical role. Enhancing this efficiency through the controlled assembly of IONPs into ordered nanostructures remains a key challenge, particularly for achieving one-dimensional (1D) arrangements such as chains or columns. In this study, silver nanowires were explored as anisotropic templates to guide the directional clustering of surface-functionalized IONPs. The resulting nanocomposites were characterized using alternating current magnetometry under varying magnetic field strengths (i.e., 12, 16, and 24 kA.m⁻¹) and frequencies (i.e., 110, 200, and 300 kHz). Preliminary findings indicate that the template-assisted clustering enhances the specific absorption rate at 24 kA.m⁻¹ magnetic field strength compared to individual IONPs at all studied frequencies by 16, 18, and 18% for 110, 200, and 300 kHz, respectively. Furthermore, dynamic hysteresis measurements suggest increased coercivity, supporting the presence of magnetic dipolar interactions among the assembled IONPs. This approach offers a potential route to improve the magnetic hyperthermia performance of iron oxide nanoparticles through controlled 1D assembly.

Keyword: *Iron oxide nanoparticles, Silver nanowires, Magnetic hyperthermia*

Important Process Parameters and Their Effects on the Reproducible Formation of 2D Mo₂C via CVD

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Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is a widely utilized technique for the synthesis of two-dimensional (2D) materials, offering advantages in controlling crystal quality, uniformity, and scalability. In the case of Mo₂C, CVD involves exposing a Mo/Cu bilayer to a methane (CH₄) atmosphere at elevated temperatures (T > 1080 °C). However, achieving reproducible growth remains a major challenge. Reports in the literature show significant variability in Mo₂C morphology, including differences in crystal shape (well-faceted vs. irregular), lateral dimensions, thickness, and purity.

In this study, we systematically investigate the influence of key processing parameters—including quartz tube and crucible contamination, Cu foil thickness, and the presence of graphene—on the morphology and quality of Mo₂C crystals. Experiments were conducted using both atmospheric pressure and low-pressure CVD systems to assess the effect of different environments on growth reproducibility.

Comprehensive characterization using optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Raman spectroscopy was performed to correlate growth conditions with resulting Mo₂C properties. The findings offer insight into critical factors influencing Mo₂C synthesis and provide guidelines for improving consistency and crystal quality in CVD-grown 2D Mo₂C.

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Keyword: *Molybdenum carbide, Copper, 2D Materials, CVD*

Synthesis of Graphene-Free Ultrathin Mo₂C

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Two-dimensional transition metal carbides (TMCs), particularly molybdenum carbide (Mo₂C), are promising for next-generation electronics and catalysis. However, Mo₂C synthesized via CVD often suffers from undesired graphene coverage, which hinders process control, limits performance, and necessitates additional post-processing to remove the graphene layer.

This study systematically investigates the role of graphene as a carbon source in Mo₂C growth via CVD. Three process routes were examined, with the most notable result achieved when graphene was used as the sole carbon source, eliminating methane. By annealing a Mo/Cu/graphene stack at 1100 °C, we demonstrate the complete transformation of graphene into ultrathin (~10 nm), large-area (up to 60 μm), well-faceted Mo₂C crystals. The process involves Mo diffusion through molten Cu and reaction with graphene via surface diffusion, resulting in the lateral growth of high-quality crystals with minimal impingement.

TEM, XRD, and Raman analyses confirm the orthorhombic structure of Mo₂C and the full consumption of graphene, yielding clean, graphene-free surfaces. This method presents a scalable, hydrocarbon-free pathway for synthesizing ultrathin TMCs with excellent crystallinity.

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Keyword: *Chemical Vapor Deposition, Molybdenum Carbide, Graphene, 2D Materials*

Nanostructured MOF-Aerogel Composite: A Promising Platform for Efficient CO₂ Removal

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Industrial sectors like cement, steel, and chemical production are among the leading contributors to global CO₂ emissions, which have reached a critical level of 36 gigatons annually. Metal Organic Framework Aerogel Composites (MOFACs) have emerged as promising candidates for gas adsorption applications, particularly for CO₂ capture. In this work, nanocomposites comprising calcium alginate aerogels and MIL-160(Al) (designated as AlgMIL160) with different MOF loadings of 25 wt% (AlgMIL160-3-1), 50 wt% (AlgMIL160-3-3), and 75 wt% (AlgMIL160-3-9) were synthesized via a sol-gel-assisted direct mixing approach followed by supercritical CO₂ drying.

Characterization techniques including gas sorption analysis, PXRD, FTIR, and SEM confirmed the successful integration of MIL-160(Al) into the alginate aerogel matrix while the crystalline structure of MOF remained intact. The CO₂ adsorption capabilities of these composites were assessed under both static and dynamic conditions. Static adsorption data were modeled using the Langmuir equation and Ideal Adsorbed Solution Theory (IAST), revealing that AlgMIL160 composites exhibit higher CO₂ uptake than their corresponding pristine MOF, demonstrating a synergistic interaction between the MOF particles and the aerogel matrix.

Additionally, the composites showed superior CO₂/N₂ selectivity at 25 °C and 1000 mbar when compared to the pure MOF. Dynamic adsorption tests using a 15% CO₂ / 85% N₂ gas mixture showed performance comparable to single-component adsorption, with only minor decreases due to competitive adsorption. These newly developed aerogel-MOF composites exhibit excellent potential for use in packed-bed adsorption systems, offering high CO₂ capture efficiency with minimal pressure drop.

Optimization of Soyasaponin-Carbon Quantum Dots as Naturally Derived and Cost-Effective Theranostic CQDs for Targeted Imaging of Cancer Cells

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Natural Carbon Quantum Dots (NACQDs) are a novel type of carbon-based material that has garnered significant interest due to their exceptional properties, including low toxicity, luminescence, photostability, nanoscale size, water solubility, biocompatibility, and cost-effectiveness. For the first time, isolated soyasaponin was attached to chitosan-biotin and utilized in the hydrothermal technique to induce the formation of carbon quantum dots. Dots were doped with bromine by using either 2-bromoresercinol or 4-bromoresercinol. The physical and chemical properties of soyasaponin carbon quantum dots have been systematically elucidated by numerous methods such as fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), atomic force microscopy (AFM), UV-Vis absorption, and fluorescence properties. The results proved the formation of carbon quantum dots with a rod-like shape as an innovative structure. The bromine-doped saponin CQDs exhibited unique fluorescent properties, which make them highly promising for biomedical applications. FTIR and XRD results clearly showed the successful conjugation of biotin units to carbon quantum dots during fabrication. CQDs structured from isolated soyasaponin, as a natural material, hold great potential towards the development of targeted imaging and therapeutic approaches.

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Keyword: *Quantum Dots, Soyasaponin, Biotin, Biomedical applications*

Development of an Incubator-Integrated Electrochemical System for Cell-Based Nanomedicine Research

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The high sensitivity, cost-effectiveness, and miniaturization potential of electrochemical techniques have positioned them as key tools in biological research (Maduraiveeran et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2020). Among these, screen-printed electrodes (SPEs) stand out as highly portable and adaptable platforms for real-time, cell-based analysis (Ahamed et al., 2021; Medina-Plaza et al., 2015). However, conventional electrochemical assays often expose cells to non-physiological environments—such as ambient temperature and atmospheric CO₂—which can compromise cell viability and measurement reliability (Cetin, 2023).

To address this limitation, we developed a fully integrated Incubator-Integrated Electrochemical Analysis Platform, enabling precise and reproducible electrochemical measurements of living cells under physiologically relevant conditions. The platform comprises four main modules: (i) a microfluidic system for controlled fluid handling, (ii) an incubation unit maintaining 37 °C and 5% CO₂, (iii) a measurement module incorporating SPEs and a portable potentiostat, and (iv) a custom-designed software interface for real-time data acquisition and device control. Additionally, we engineered a sample preparation apparatus to promote optimal cell adhesion onto SPE surfaces within standard incubators, without compromising electrode integrity. To validate the system, MCF-7 breast cancer cells were cultured on the electrode surface and analyzed using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV), and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV). The platform successfully differentiated cell densities and quantified the cytotoxic effects of paclitaxel (PTX), exhibiting a dose-dependent decline in cell viability. Confocal microscopy confirmed strong cell adhesion and well-organized cytoskeletal structures on the electrode surface. By maintaining incubator-like conditions throughout the entire assay, our system minimizes environmental artifacts and enhances biological relevance and reproducibility. This incubator-integrated electrochemical platform offers a robust, modular, and scalable solution for drug screening, cancer cell analysis, and emerging applications in personalized medicine and bioelectronic diagnostics.

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Keyword: : *Electrochemical analysis, Cell-based analysis, Incubator-integrated platform, Screen-printed electrodes (SPEs)*

Stretchable Electronic Substrates for Large Stroke Electrochemical Actuators

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New generation actuators, artificial muscles, gain importance thanks to the advancements in functional nanomaterials. Among them electrochemical actuators directly convert electrical energy into mechanical energy at low operation potentials which makes them promising candidate for biomedical devices and robotics. Electroactive polymers have been extensively studied as electrochemical actuator electrodes, however their low mechanical properties limit their usage. Alternatively, various nanomaterials (CNTs, graphene, MXene) have been used, however electrochemically generated strain is limited (<1%) [1]. To amplify the displacement, electroactive materials integrated onto flexible substrates (bimorph structure) where strain leads bending deformation depending on the active/passive layer thicknesses or modulus ratio. On the other hand, twisting nanomaterials such as CNT yarns leads much higher stroke performance [2], but exhibit high torsional stroke, while bimorph electrodes only show bending deformation.

Previously, we have shown that 1T phase molybdenum disulfide (1T MoS₂) is electroactive and outperforms most of the other materials [1]. Despite their strain performances are low (<1%), the displacement is amplified via bimorph actuator design and large bending degree was observed with Kapton film. Also, these bending beams attached to each other to produce an actuator in the form of elliptical spring by using the kirigami technique, and we showed that a high-stroke actuator by lifting 150 times its own weight to 15% of its own length. However, this approach limits its use as it is on a macro scale. Therefore, it is important to improve the stroke performance of actuators and develop new designs.

In this project, we use a novel approach to generate high stroke actuator by using low modulus flexible substrate (PDMS) and accordion type electrode design to miniaturized previously constructed spring actuator.[1] PDMS with wavy surface texture and spring shape flexible substrates were obtained by using molds with different wave sizes. In this way, it is aimed to produce surfaces with a wide spectrum of wavelength and amplitude. Then electroactive materials (chemically exfoliated MoS₂ nanosheets) were deposit on the inner surface of the wavy structures by drop casting. This approach enables to fabricate such artificial muscles through 3D printing. Eventually, accordion type electrodes were induced electrochemically and bending deformation is controlled in each wave and transformed to large stroke vertically. In this study, we manage to incorporate stretchable substrates used in electronics to generate high stroke electrochemical actuators.

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Keyword: *MoS₂ nanosheets, Electrochemical Actuators, Stretchable substrates*

Room Temperature Chemiresistive Ammonia Gas Sensing via Carbon Nanomaterial/Metal Oxide Heterostructure

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Ammonia is considered a breath biomarker which correlates with various diseases such as liver and kidney disorders, and developing a reliable, cost-efficient and highly sensitive ammonia sensor operable in low concentration regime is a great demand for the environment and human health.

ZnO-based materials have been widely used for the detection of ammonia for many years. Synthesizing ZnO using atomic layer deposition (ALD) offers significant advantages due to its ability to provide atomically controlled and uniform thin films [1]. Although ZnO-based materials are frequently used for ammonia sensing, their requirement for high operating temperatures is a major issue. However, achieving high sensing performance, preferably at room temperature, is challenging. In this context, modifying the electrical properties of ZnO-based materials has been shown to enhance sensor responses toward target gases at low operating temperatures [2]. Reduced graphene oxide (rGO), a carbon-based material with superior electrical conductivity, stands out as one of the most promising candidates for this purpose [3].

Sensor miniaturization remains a key challenge for the development of sensor device technology in the field of micro packaging and the possibility of low-cost mass fabrication. Conventionally, interdigital electrodes (IDEs) are deposited on a sensing layer, and then the sensor is heated by an external thermal source to obtain the operating temperature. However, a monolithic microfabricated sensor device consists of IDEs and a microheater itself which enables electronic control on the same chip [4].

Figure 1
(a) The schematic illustration and (b-d) optical microscope images of chemiresistive sensor chips

Figure 2
Sensor signals of rGO/ZnO heterostructure against ammonia in concentrations ranging from 11.6 ppm to 1.16 ppm

In this study, to fabricate the rGO/ZnO heterostructure based sensing layer, a combination of Hummer's method and ALD was used. Chemiresistive sensor chips (Figure 1) were fabricated by various micro electro-mechanical system (MEMs) techniques. The sensor was measured against ammonia over a wide concentration range at room temperature. According to sensor tests, a response of 3.28 was observed for 1.16 ppm ammonia with a clear signal (Figure 2). Moreover, the detection limit of the sensor was calculated as 10.5 ppb. All results suggest that the sensor is a promising candidate for real-time ammonia detection in various environments where a few ppm or ppb level monitoring is required, such as industrial safety, indoor air quality, environmental monitoring, and agricultural facilities.

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Keyword: Reduced Graphene Oxide, Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD), Ammonia Gas Sensor, Heterostructure

Parametric Study on Graphenated Carbon Nanotubes Fabricated by Single-Step Floating Catalyst Chemical Vapor Deposition

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Graphenated carbon nanotubes (g-CNTs) are emerging as a promising hybrid nanostructure that merges the high surface area and electrical conductivity of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) with the edge-rich characteristics of graphene foliates. This unique combination enhances electron transport, reactivity, and surface interaction, making g-CNTs ideal for advanced energy storage and catalytic applications. However, challenges in their synthesis—such as poor control over graphene foliate density, structural uniformity, and scalability—have limited their broader utilization. This work explores the fabrication of g-CNTs using a single-step floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition (FCCVD) method. Ethanol, ferrocene, and thiophene were used as the carbon source, catalyst, and promoter, respectively. The synthesis was carried out without a substrate, enabling the continuous spinning of g-CNT aerogels into cotton-like fibers suitable for scalable production. A systematic parametric study was conducted by varying the carbon injection rate (5–20 mL/h), hydrogen gas flow rate (200–300 sccm), and reaction temperature (1150–1250 °C). The morphology and structural quality of the resulting CNTs and g-CNTs were characterized via FESEM, HRTEM, Raman spectroscopy, and TGA. Results showed that at 1250 °C with 300 sccm hydrogen flow, g-CNTs with larger diameters (49.61 nm) and denser graphene foliates were obtained. Lower temperatures (1150 °C) yielded narrower CNTs (~24.63–24.81 nm) with fewer foliates unless the hydrogen flow was reduced, which extended the residence time and facilitated foliate formation. Similarly, a lower carbon feedstock rate (5 mL/h) led to more defect-rich structures, as indicated by higher I_D/I_G values in Raman spectra, suggesting increased graphene edge sites. The formation of g-CNTs was found to be highly sensitive to both thermal energy and carbon precursor availability. A growth mechanism was proposed where sidewall etching from hydrogen radicals and defect nucleation facilitated the deposition of graphene foliates on CNTs after a critical growth duration. Lower injection rates prolonged growth time in the reactor, enabling the gradual transformation of CNTs into g-CNTs with multilayer graphene extensions. In conclusion, the FCCVD method demonstrated effective control over the formation of graphenated carbon nanotubes by tuning process parameters. The ability to produce g-CNTs in cotton or film form without a substrate offers significant potential for industrial-scale fabrication of next-generation nanomaterials for energy and catalysis.

Keyword: Graphenated Carbon Nanotubes (g-CNTs), Floating Catalyst Chemical Vapor Deposition (FCCVD), Graphene Foliates

Photocatalytic Degradation of PET Microplastics in Aquatic Media by Magnetically Steerable ZnO-Based Nanoflower Micro-Rollers

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Microplastic pollution, particularly in aquatic ecosystems, poses an increasingly serious global threat. Although conventional filtration methods are effective in the short term, they are not sustainable in the long term. In contrast, in situ degradation methods, despite their operational challenges, offer significant potential for permanent remediation. This study presents the design, synthesis, and functional assessment of magnetically actuated micro-roller systems for degrading polyethylene terephthalate (PET) microplastics in aqueous environments. These microstructures feature an Fe₃O₄ magnetic core that enables motion to be guided by an external field and ZnO-based nanoflower surfaces that exhibit photocatalytic activity. Various ZnO nanoflower morphologies, including rod-like, needle-like, and plate-like structures, were synthesized to evaluate the effect of morphology on catalytic degradation performance.

Degradation experiments were conducted under 365 nm UV irradiation, and the photodegradation efficiency was assessed using high-resolution profilometry. Quantitative analysis of PET surface erosion, including topographical alterations such as depth, roughness, and wear volume, enabled precise monitoring of degradation kinetics. The results revealed that all nanoflower morphologies facilitated PET degradation within 24 hours, with distinct performance differences attributed to their structural characteristics.

This work demonstrates the feasibility of using magnetically navigable Fe₃O₄@ZnO micro-rollers for targeted microplastic remediation and highlights the important role of nanostructural morphology in determining photocatalytic efficiency. Integrating magnetic mobility and morphological tunability provides a promising approach for the scalable, controllable, and effective in situ degradation of persistent microplastic pollutants.

Keyword: *microplastic, micro roller, Photocatalytic degradation*

Magnetic Properties of Gold Surfaces with Adatoms: A DFT Study

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We perform theoretical calculations of spin and orbital magnetic moments on the metal surface of Au [111]. We employ a supercell approach and density functional theory to investigate gold surfaces in a slab configuration. We use a plane wave basis DFT package (VASP) in a 128-atom supercell and 20 Angstroms of vacuum. We hypothesize that a chiral molecule exhibits chiral polarizability and spin magnetic moment so that magnetic exchange interaction occurs between a chiral molecule and an adatom. To demonstrate this hypothesis, we have calculated the exchange energy between an adatom and D-alanine/Au(111) and L- alanine/Au(111) on the surface. We also calculate the orbital magnetic moment of adatoms on a noble metal surface and their exchange interaction with the chiral molecule.

Keyword: *Magnetic materials, chiral molecules*

Accelerating Materials Discovery: Crystal Structure Generation via customized Large Language Models

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Predicting the stable crystal structure of a material from its chemical composition is a fundamental challenge in materials science, often demanding extensive computational resources. Recent advancements in generative artificial intelligence, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), may offer a paradigm-shifting approach. Building upon foundational works like CrystaLLM and CrysText, this study investigates the efficacy and scalability of instruction tuning various LLMs for direct Crystallographic Information File (CIF) generation. We employed QLoRA, a parameter-efficient fine-tuning technique, to train different open-source LLMs, including Meta's Llama 3.1-8B and Llama 3.2-1B models, as well as the distilled DeepSeek model DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-1.5B and DeepSeek V2 Lite-12B. The models were fine-tuned on a comprehensive, custom dataset of 247,000+ known crystal structures from the OQMD database, with training conducted for one to three epochs. The task was formulated to generate the complete, lowest-energy CIF directly from a chemical formula prompt. Our results demonstrate that all fine-tuned models can generate crystallographically valid and high-fidelity CIFs. Evaluation on compositions from the training set shows near-perfect recall of structural parameters. More significantly, when prompted with previously unseen formulas, the models provide a considerably good starting base for generating plausible structures, accurately identifying space groups and closely approximating lattice parameters and atomic coordinates in line with experimental data. This indicates that a robust understanding of underlying physical constraints has been learned, rather than simple memorization. Our comparative analysis shows a strong correlation between number of model parameters and the fidelity of generated structures, with the Llama 3.1-8B model which contains 8 billion parameters achieving the highest generalizability. This work validates that QLoRA fine-tuning on a large-scale dataset is a highly effective and computationally efficient strategy for crystal structure prediction. It provides a rapid and scalable alternative to traditional methods, significantly accelerating the initial stages of materials discovery.

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Keyword: *Crystal Structure Prediction, Large Language Models, QLoRA Fine-Tuning, Generative AI*

MushMorph Micromotors: Synthesis and Characterization

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A micromotor is a miniature synthetic device that transforms available energy into mechanical motion. Based on the mechanism by which they achieve mobility, they can generally be categorized as either fuel-driven or fuel-free micromotors. Fuel-driven micromotors usually rely on the decomposition of a fuel, such as hydrogen peroxide and hydrazine. Fuel-free micromotors are activated by external forces like light, ultrasound, and acoustic, electric, or magnetic fields [1-2]. Magnetic micromotors have attracted significant attention in recent years, setting themselves apart from other micromotor designs. Though magnetic micromotors are synthesized in several physical structures [3-4], rethinking and refining the morphology of micromotors is becoming a crucial area of focus. In this study, we present the synthesis and characterization of MushMorph micromotors with cap-stem geometries mimicking fungal structures. Tubular MushMorph micromotors are synthesized using template-assisted electrochemical deposition into the pores of a polycarbonate membrane and constructed using gold (Au) and iron-nickel alloy (Fe-Ni). Optimization of electrodeposition conditions was carried out. The cap-stem geometries of the constructed micromotors were confirmed using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and elemental composition was validated with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The velocity profile of the MushMorph micromotors were created. This profile was studied in different environments.

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Keyword: *Micromotors, template-assisted deposition, electrochemical synthesis*

Influence of Mn_5Ge_3 Shell Thickness on the Structural and Magnetic Behavior of Ge-Based Core/Shell Nanowires

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One-dimensional (1D) nanowires (NWs) have attracted considerable attention due to their unique physical properties—such as enhanced surface-to-volume ratio, quantum confinement, and directional charge transport—which make them ideal for miniaturization, increased sensitivity, and improved performance in advanced spintronic applications. In particular, Mn_5Ge_3 is an important ferromagnetic material for magnetic nanowires due to its room-temperature ferromagnetism, compatibility with Ge and Si technologies, and tunable magnetic properties. Its ability to form high-quality interfaces with Ge makes it ideal for spintronic applications requiring efficient spin injection and stable magnetic behavior at the nanoscale. In this study, Ge/ Mn_5Ge_3 core-shell nanowire heterostructures were synthesized through a solid-phase epitaxial growth process, utilizing a combined approach of RF magnetron sputtering and molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) to ensure precise control over material composition and interface quality. The fabrication procedure consisted of the deposition of Mn onto uniformly aligned Ge nanowires, followed by a controlled thermal annealing process to promote the formation of a crystalline Mn_5Ge_3 shell through solid-phase reaction. Structural analysis performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed that the shell is primarily composed of Mn_5Ge_3 -phase crystalline clusters. The magnetic behavior of the Ge/ Mn_5Ge_3 nanowires was examined using Vibrating Sample Magnetometry (VSM) and X-band Ferromagnetic Resonance (FMR) techniques. The measurements revealed the presence of magnetic anisotropy, with the hard axis oriented along the longitudinal direction of the nanowires. Additionally, VSM-derived hysteresis loops demonstrated a clear linear correlation between both saturation magnetization and coercivity with respect to the Mn shell thickness, indicating the critical influence of geometric and interfacial parameters on the magnetic response. These results suggest that this heterostructure allows for tunable magnetic behavior through interface and shell-thickness engineering, making it a strong candidate for future spin-based devices.

Keyword: *ferromagnetic Mn_5Ge_3 clusters; core-shell heterostructures; magnetic anisotropy*

Controllable Porosity in Graphene-Polymer Nanocomposite Fiber for Wearable Applications

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Wearable electronics are transforming healthcare by enabling real-time, continuous monitoring through flexible, breathable materials. This study presents a scalable fabrication of conductive porous fibers using thermal-induced phase separation during thermal drawing. A homogeneous mixture of graphene nanoplatelets (Gr) and PVDF/PC within a SEBS cladding not only induces conductivity but also tunes the microstructure and mechanical behavior of the fibers. Increasing graphene content reduces particle size to the sub-micron scale at a Gr: PVDF ratio of 45:55 (Gr45), while electrical conductivity reaches percolation at Gr25 and stabilizes beyond Gr35.

The fibers were evaluated for multiparametric sensing, where Gr35 showed enhanced temperature sensitivity and Gr45 demonstrated higher pressure sensitivity. As a piezoresistive sensor, the fiber offered broad pressure range detection with high sensitivity and fast response. For temperature sensing, the fiber exhibited a strong negative temperature coefficient ($TCR = 0.558\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$), attributed to thermally activated tunneling and hopping across the graphene network, confirming suitability for skin-temperature monitoring.

The conductive porous core, usable as a freestanding electrode, exhibited low skin-electrode impedance and enabled clear ECG signal acquisition with well-resolved PQRST waveforms, rivaling commercial Ag/AgCl electrodes. This 3D interconnected nanocomposite fiber platform shows potential for diverse applications including biosensing, cell interfacing, and filtration systems.

Keyword: *Phase separation, Temperature, pressure and electrophysiology sensor, porous nanocomposite*

Synthesis, Characterization and Biological Activities of Nickel, Cerium and Tin Nanoparticles via Green Synthesis from Industrial Apple Wastes

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In this study, nickel, cerium, and tin nanoparticles were successfully synthesized utilizing industrial apple waste. The structural and morphological properties of the synthesized nanoparticles were characterized through SEM, EDX, XRD, Raman spectroscopy, and AFM analyses. Additionally, the antibacterial, antibiofilm, quorum sensing inhibition, and anticancer activities of the synthesized nanoparticles were investigated. The apple waste was extracted in 70% ethanol for 24 hours. Ultrasonic extraction and filtration were then performed. The substance was then subjected to liquid-liquid partitioning and extracted with ethyl acetate. Approximately 3 mg of the resulting extract was dissolved in distilled water, to which 20 mmol of metal salt was then added. The pH of the resulting mixture was adjusted to 12. The solution was then incubated at 90 °C for three hours. Once the solution had reached room temperature, it was subjected to three consecutive centrifugation cycles at 5,000 rpm. The resulting precipitate was then dried at 60°C [1, 2]. UV-visible spectrophotometer, Optical microscope, Raman spectroscopy, EDX, Atomic force microscopy and SEM were used to characterize the sample. In this study, the ethanol extract of industrial apple waste was found to have the highest phenolic substance content, and synthesis was carried out using this extract. Considering the UV-Visible spectroscopy analysis, nickel, cerium and tin nanoparticles gave peaks at 240 nm, 305 nm and 280 nm, respectively. When EDX analysis was examined, 75.42% nickel, 83.41% cerium and 77.50% tin were found by mass for nickel, cerium and tin nanoparticles, respectively. This high metal content indicates that green synthesis successfully reduces metal ions and the synthesized nanoparticles are of high purity. The remaining parts are elements originating from oxygen and bio coating. Raman spectra of all three nanoparticles are consistent with the literature. Especially the Raman peaks observed above 1000 cm⁻¹ can be said that apple waste acts as both a reductant and a coating during the synthesis of nanoparticles. The thickness measurements for nickel, cerium and tin nanoparticles were found to be approximately 60 nm, 50 nm and 90 nm, respectively. Nickel, cerium and tin nanoparticles act by targeting cellular structures, suppressing gene expression and disrupting intracellular signaling pathways. The most effective agent among the broad-spectrum agents was determined to be Ni NP, based on the results of the antibacterial, antibiofilm and anti-quorum detection activity tests. Ce NP and Sn NP, on the other hand, showed relatively weaker effects or no noticeable effect. Ni nanoparticles exhibited the greatest activity against A2780 ovarian cancer cells among all the tested cell lines.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: green synthesis, characterization, antibacterial activity, anticancer activity

Fiber-Shaped Zn-Ion Batteries with Laser-Cut MXene Nanocomposite Cathodes

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Zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) stand out as environmentally friendly, safe, and cost-effective candidates for advanced electrochemical energy storage systems. Their potential integration into flexible and wearable electronic devices offers a pathway to accelerate the adoption of next-generation technologies. The development of one-dimensional (1D) fiber-shaped electrodes represents a strategic approach to achieving high-performance ZIBs with enhanced energy density, extended cycling stability, and improved safety at low costs. Two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials, such as Ti_3C_2 MXenes, when structured into 1D macroscopic fibers, offer exceptional electrochemical performance and mechanical flexibility. In this study, a high-power nanosecond laser system was used to produce high-aspect-ratio 1D fibers from large-area thin film nanocomposites. We fabricated and characterized fiber-shaped ZIBs using Ti_3C_2 MXenes with various metal oxides as cathodes. These binder-free laser-cut cathodes exhibited a high specific capacity alongside excellent mechanical integrity. Our findings provide insights into the electrochemical and structural properties of MXene-metal oxide nanocomposite fibers, demonstrating their potential for scalable integration into flexible and sustainable energy storage systems.

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Keyword: *Energy storage, Zn-ion batteries, Fiber, MXene*

Current Matching and Operational Performance Optimization in Perovskite/silicon Tandem Solar Cells

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Metal halide perovskite materials have excellent characteristics such as solution processability, adjustable and complementary band gap with silicon for tandem solar cells. The high-quality perovskite film with low defect density improved the short-circuit current density and reduced the open-circuit voltage loss of the devices. The band gap of perovskite was optimized by adjusting the I/Br ratio, so that the short-circuit current density of the top and bottom cells of the tandem solar cell was matched, and the energy conversion efficiency of the tandem cell can be improved. Interference effect in transparent electrode was modulated to realize current matching in sub-cells. Curved heterojunctions were developed to extend optical path length and release film stress, improving weak-light conversion efficiency and thermal shock resistance. A low-temperature chemical vapor deposition was used for high-quality encapsulation films, enhancing device performance under harsh conditions.

References:

Current matching

Keyword: *Tandem solar cell, Current matching, Operational performance, Encapsulation*

Flax Seeds-Based Sustainable Electrolyte Providing High Interfacial Stability for Zinc Ion Batteries

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Rechargeable zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) have emerged as a promising option for future large-scale energy storage applications, experiencing substantial growth over the past decade. This growth can be attributed to their high capacity, the reversibility of the zinc metal anode, cost-effectiveness, enhanced safety, and environmental sustainability [1]. Nevertheless, traditional aqueous electrolytes in ZIBs encounter considerable challenges, including the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the formation of zinc dendrites, which undermine their cycling stability and safety. Such limitations demand the formulation of advanced electrolyte solutions to boost ZIB performance, concurrently prioritizing sustainability. The aqueous electrolyte represents a significant factor contributing to the constraints observed in ZIBs, serving as an excellent foundation for exploring potential solutions aimed at enhancing the stability of ZIBs. Natural materials and their derivatives, sourced from renewable and sustainable resources, may offer promising strategies to reduce both HER activity and dendrite formation [2]. In this study, a green and sustainable electrolyte derived from flax seeds (FS) is developed to enhance the electrochemical stability of zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs), thereby minimizing the presence of free water molecules and mitigating the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) as well as the formation of zinc dendrites. The obtained results confirm that the FS-based electrolyte contributes to enhanced electrochemical stability and improved performance of ZIBs. The FS-based electrolyte formulation in symmetrical Zn//Zn cells shows a remarkable cycle life of 3000 hours, significantly surpassing the longevity of aqueous electrolytes for ZIBs. The quinone structure within the FS-based electrolytes provides superior specific capacities for V₂O₅ cathodes in fully assembled cells.

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Keyword: *biomass electrolyte, natural solvent, interfacial stability, zinc ion batteries*

Laser-Carbonized HKUST-1 MOF as a Host Material for Anodeless Zinc-Ion Batteries

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The increasing global demand for sustainable and secure energy storage solutions has positioned aqueous zinc-ion batteries (AZIBs) as a promising candidate, thanks to their inherent safety, low cost, and environmental compatibility [1]. However, the practical adoption of AZIBs is significantly constrained by challenges associated with conventional zinc anodes, including dendrite formation and structural degradation, which compromise battery lifespan and reliability [2]. In this work, we present a novel approach that utilizes laser-assisted carbonization to fabricate a host material based on the HKUST-1 metal-organic framework (MOF). Through wet chemical synthesis, HKUST-1 MOF was directly grown on copper (Cu) substrates and subsequently carbonized using a nanosecond laser system under ambient conditions. The resulting porous carbon layer on the Cu substrate features a conductive, porous host material that eliminates the problems associated with the Zn metal anode, such as dendrites and H₂ gas formation. The fabricated Zn metal anode-free ZIBs demonstrated exceptional electrochemical performance, including enhanced rate capability, superior cycling stability, and robust dendrite suppression. Remarkably, these batteries retained 85% of their capacity after 1000 GCD cycles. The structural integrity and electrochemical performance of the designed anode-less ZIB will be presented, highlighting their scalability and potential as a transformative platform for next-generation sustainable AZIBs.

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Keyword: *Anode-less Zinc-Ion Batteries, HKUST-1, Laser Carbonization, Energy Storage*

Study of the Optical Properties of Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se Thin Films Grown by the Liquid Phase Epitaxy Method

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Gallium selenide (GaSe) thin films have garnered significant attention due to their promising optical characteristics [1], particularly for terahertz-frequency laser and optoelectronic applications [2]. However, structural defects—arising from weak van der Waals interactions between the layers in bulk crystals and during the thin-film growth process—can considerably impair their optical and electrical properties. To mitigate this issue, Ga atoms were partially substituted with boron to form Ga_{1-x}B_xSe ($x = 0.005$) solid solutions. These compounds were synthesized via the direct melting method, and single crystals were subsequently grown using the Bridgman technique. Thin films were then fabricated using the Liquid Phase Epitaxy (LPE) method [3], which is recognized as a cost-effective approach capable of minimizing defect formation compared to other deposition techniques.

In this study, the optical properties of Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se thin films were systematically investigated. Initially, bulk Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se crystals were synthesized and subsequently deposited onto appropriate substrates using LPE. The absorption coefficient as a function of photon energy was extracted from UV–Vis spectral measurements, revealing a high absorption coefficient and a direct allowed electronic transition. The optical band gap, determined via the Tauc plot method, was found to be 2.22 eV—wider than that of bulk Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se single crystals, which can be attributed to quantum confinement effects resulting from the reduced dimensionality of the thin film. These findings demonstrate the potential of Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se thin films for advanced optoelectronic applications

Fig.1. $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ curves for Ga_{0.995}Bo_{0.005}Se thin films

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Keyword: *Optical properties, Liquid Phase Epitaxy, the band gap of thin films*

Breaking the Boundaries of the Goldschmidt Tolerance Factor with Ethylammonium Lead Iodide Perovskite Nanocrystals

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We report the synthesis of ethylammonium lead iodide (EAPbI₃) colloidal nanocrystals as another member of the lead halide perovskites family. The insertion of an unusually large A-cation (274 pm in diameter) in the perovskite structure, hitherto considered unlikely due to the unfavorable Goldschmidt tolerance factor, results in a significantly larger lattice parameter compared to the Cs-, methylammonium- and formamidinium-based lead halide perovskite homologues. As a consequence, EAPbI₃ nanocrystals are highly unstable, evolving to a nonperovskite δ -EAPbI₃ polymorph within 1 day. Also, EAPbI₃ nanocrystals are very sensitive to electron irradiation and quickly degrade to PbI₂ upon exposure to the electron beam, following a mechanism similar to that of other hybrid lead iodide perovskites (although degradation can be reduced by partially replacing the EA⁺ ions with Cs⁺ ions). Interestingly, in some cases during this degradation the formation of an epitaxial interface between (EA_xCs_{1-x})PbI₃ and PbI₂ is observed. The photoluminescence emission of the EAPbI₃ perovskite nanocrystals, albeit being characterized by a low quantum yield (~1%), can be tuned in the 664–690 nm range by regulating their size during the synthesis. The emission efficiency can be improved upon partial alloying at the A site with Cs⁺ or formamidinium cations. Furthermore, the morphology of the EAPbI₃ nanocrystals can be chosen to be either nanocube or nanoplatelet, depending on the synthesis conditions.

Keyword: Halide perovskites, Nanocrystals, ethylammonium, Phase transformation

AgBiS₂ Nanocrystals with Improved Crystallinity via High-Temperature Synthesis

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The AgBiS₂ NCs have attracted significant attention as sustainable heavy metal-free NCs due to their superior features, such as high absorption coefficient ($\sim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), broad range of absorption in the visible-NIR region (400-1000 nm), non-toxic structure, and high stability[1]. Although the hot injection method is frequently used to synthesize AgBiS₂ NCs with high crystallinity, there is a high defect density on the surfaces of the NCs due to their binary cation composition structure[2]. Due to high defect density, charge transportation is hindered, trap states act as recombination centers, and the quantum efficiency decreases[3]. Another important property is monodispersity, which improves the photovoltaic efficiency by suppressing energetic disorder, minimizing recombination losses, and broadening the band tail[4]. The fundamental method to decrease the surface defect density is the design of core-shell nanostructures. The main problem is that conventional shell materials such as CdS, CdSe, ZnS, and ZnSe, etc., necessary high temperatures (>180°C) for the formation of the shell on the core surface, which causes the AgBiS₂ NCs to decompose or undergo crystal structural/morphological alteration[1]. Hence, it is very important to synthesize high-crystallinity AgBiS₂ NCs at elevated temperatures above 180°C by providing surface passivation, to ensure a narrow size distribution, and to synthesize core/shell nanostructures with more functional optical and electrical features.

In this research, highly crystalline AgBiS₂ nanocrystals (NCs) were successfully synthesized using a hot-injection approach at elevated temperatures reaching up to 285°C, employing trioctylphosphine (TOP) as a ligand for the first time. XRD analysis and TEM images demonstrated that the AgBiS₂ NCs synthesized at 285°C exhibit higher crystallinity and a significantly narrower size distribution compared to those produced via the traditional synthesis method. The existence of the TOP functional group was confirmed through quantitative NMR, FTIR, and XPS analyses. Furthermore, the effects of both growth temperature and time on the synthesis of AgBiS₂-TOP NCs were thoroughly examined. The structural, morphological, and optical characteristics of the NCs were characterized by high-resolution TEM, high-angle annular dark-field scanning TEM, and UV-vis-NIR absorption spectroscopy, respectively. This pioneering work utilizing TOP as a ligand paves the way for future studies focused on developing AgBiS₂-based core-shell nanostructures for next-generation optoelectronic devices, enabling the synthesis of highly crystalline, monodisperse NCs at high temperatures.

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Keyword: *Nanocrystals, I-V-VI, AgBiS₂, Trioctylphosphine*

Unraveling Structure-Functionality Relationships of Shape-Defined Cu₂O Nanocrystal Model Catalysts for Methanol Decomposition

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Methanol is a significant C1 chemical feedstock and energy carrier; however, mechanistic insights into its transformation over Cu-based catalysts are limited due to challenges related to material and pressure gaps. Shape-controlled Cu₂O nanocrystals provide a promising model system to explore structure-functionality relationships under practical conditions, narrowing the gap between fundamental studies and industrial applications. In this study, cubic and octahedral Cu₂O nanostructures were synthesized and thoroughly characterized using various analytical techniques, including SEM, XRD, XANES, EXAFS, ATR-IR, XPS, and H₂-TPR. Surface-active sites were analyzed via in-situ FTIR spectroscopy using CO as a probe molecule. The effect of crystal morphology on methanol decomposition was further examined through in-situ FTIR and temperature programmed desorption (TPD). A strong correlation between nanocrystal shape and catalytic performance was observed. Cubic Cu₂O (c-Cu₂O) exhibited highly reactive surface oxygen species, which facilitated the total oxidation of methanol and its intermediates, primarily producing CO₂ and H₂O. In contrast, octahedral Cu₂O (o-Cu₂O), characterized by lower surface reducibility, mainly promoted partial methanol dehydrogenation, generating CO and H₂. Notably, o-Cu₂O produced three times more CO than c-Cu₂O, while the CO₂ to CO product ratio in c-Cu₂O was about four times greater than that in o-Cu₂O, indicating a higher oxidation capability. The divergent oxidation pathways on c-Cu₂O and o-Cu₂O stem from differences in surface oxygen species, as revealed by H₂-TPR analysis. The c-Cu₂O surface features more reactive, weakly bound two coordinated oxygen (O_{2C}), enabling efficient oxidation at lower temperatures. In contrast, o-Cu₂O contains more stable, triply coordinated oxygen (O_{3C}), which limits oxygen reactivity and promotes partial oxidation routes. These findings emphasize the significant role of morphology in determining catalytic behavior, offering a strategy for tailoring methanol conversion by manipulating crystal shape.

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Keyword: *Methanol Decomposition, Model Catalysts, Structure-Functionality Relationships, Cu₂O*

Electroactive Aligned P3HB/PBA Nanofiber Matrices for Enhanced Skeletal Muscle Tissue Engineering

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Skeletal muscle tissue engineering aims to overcome the limitations of volumetric muscle loss by developing biomimetic scaffolds that can support myogenic regeneration. Nanostructured materials that emulate the morphological, mechanical, and electroactive properties of native muscle are essential for this purpose.

In this study, novel electrospun nanofiber matrices composed of poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (P3HB) blended with poly-β-alanine (PBA) were developed to replicate the anisotropic architecture and functional characteristics of skeletal muscle tissue. P3HB is a biocompatible piezoelectric biopolymer, while PBA contributes flexibility and protein-like features. Both random and aligned nanofiber matrices were fabricated by electrospinning; notably, the aligned fibers exhibited diameters near 900 nm and alignment closely mimicking native muscle tissue architecture.

Comprehensive physicochemical and structural characterizations were conducted. Microscopic imaging confirmed well-defined fiber morphology and precise alignment, while chemical and elemental analyses verified successful PBA incorporation. Thermal and structural studies revealed that blending with PBA reduced fiber crystallinity, enhanced thermal stability, and improved degradation behavior. Mechanical testing showed that aligned P3HB/PBA matrices possess high tensile strength (8.5 ± 1.8 MPa), strain to failure ($76.0 \pm 1.3\%$), and elastic modulus (378.2 ± 4.2 MPa), reflecting enhanced structural integrity and anisotropy comparable to native muscle. The d_{33} piezoelectric constant reached 5.3 pC/N in aligned matrices, indicating increased electroactivity.

In vitro cell culture using C2C12 mouse myoblasts over 21 days demonstrated that aligned P3HB/PBA matrices promote cell attachment, orientation, and fusion, with myoblasts forming organized multinucleated myotubes exhibiting dense microvilli. Gene expression analyses revealed approximately a 7-fold increase in myosin heavy chain (MHC) levels on aligned matrices compared to random ones, while marker analysis confirmed progression toward myogenic maturation.

This work represents a significant advancement in designing electroactive, nanostructured matrices for skeletal muscle engineering. The aligned P3HB/PBA nanofibers integrate morphological, mechanical, and piezoelectric cues to effectively enhance myogenic differentiation. Dynamic bioreactor testing of these matrices with combined mechanical and electrical stimulation has been conducted, and the outcomes will be communicated through academic channels.

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Keyword: *Nanofiber matrices, Piezoelectricity, Myogenic differentiation*

Investigation of Vascularization and Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Endothelial Cells on Antimicrobial Peptide-Loaded Electrospun PCL/COL Vascular Bed Scaffolds

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This study investigates the potential application of antimicrobial peptide (AMP)-enriched electrospun polycaprolactone/collagen (PCL/COL) scaffolds in constructing a vascular bed model that supports endothelial vascularization and modulates inflammatory responses. Electrospinning offers a highly tunable fabrication route for constructing fibrous matrices that closely emulate the morphology and dimensionality of the extracellular matrix (ECM), rendering it a compelling technique for tissue engineering applications. In particular, aligned electrospun fiber constructs serve as a promising platform for engineering biomimetic microenvironments. The incorporation of AMPs not only enhances the scaffold's resistance to microbial contamination but may also modulate cellular behaviors critical to vascular integration and immune balance [1-3]

Cylindrical, aligned AMP-loaded PCL/COL fiber scaffolds were fabricated and integrated into a custom-designed microfluidic system to simulate a dynamic vascular microenvironment. Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs), widely regarded for their physiological relevance in angiogenesis and vasculogenesis studies, were seeded onto these scaffolds. The study systematically evaluates endothelial adhesion, proliferation, viability, morphological adaptation, vascular network formation, and anti-inflammatory responses under flow-biomimicking conditions. [1-3]

The fiber morphology was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), revealing uniform alignment and nanoscale diameters. Chemical verification of AMP incorporation was conducted via Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR). Surface wettability and porosity were analyzed using contact angle measurements and swelling studies in PBS. Biodegradation kinetics were assessed through mass loss over time, and mechanical integrity was evaluated using uniaxial tensile testing at multiple degradation intervals. Biological performance was investigated through MTT viability assays, immunohistochemical staining of vascular markers (VEGFR), cytokine profiling, and apoptotic analyses (Calcein-AM/Ethidium homodimer-1). Results indicate that AMP incorporation contributes not only to microbial resistance but also enhances endothelial adhesion and morphogenesis while attenuating inflammatory signaling. [1-3]

This platform moves beyond static 2D cultures by providing a biomimetic and perfusable environment in which endothelial behavior can be studied with greater physiological relevance. Importantly, the integration of antimicrobial functionality addresses a critical need in preclinical model systems where sterility and immune regulation are pivotal. The system's modularity and translational design position it as a candidate for future vascularized organoid-on-a-chip models, advancing regenerative medicine and tissue-engineered disease modeling and offers a modular and translational approach for exploring cell-material interactions in complex microenvironments. [1-3]

This study is conducted under the auspices of the TUBITAK 1004 Programme and aims to advance the integration of nanofibrous biomaterials into next-generation in vitro vascular models.

Keyword: *Electrospinning, Antimicrobial Peptides, Endothelial Cells, Vascularization, Biomimetic Scaffolds, Organ-on-a-Chip*

Fabrication and in vitro Characterizations of Multifunctional Scaffold for Cardiac Patch Applications

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Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) continue to be the leading cause of mortality worldwide, with myocardial infarction (MI) alone affecting nearly half a million individuals each year [1,2]. MI occurs due to the blockage of coronary arteries, which leads to ischemia and subsequent death of cardiomyocytes. The resulting cellular damage triggers fibrotic remodelling and scar tissue formation, ultimately impairing the heart's synchronized contraction-relaxation function and potentially leading to heart failure [3,4]. Recently, cardiac patches have gained significant attention in the treatment of myocardial defects by providing mechanical support and delivering therapeutics at the site of injury. Herein, we developed a novel bilayered scaffold as a cardiac patch, consisting of a biologic-conductive first layer and a polymeric bioactive-degradable second layer. To fabricate the first layer, bovine pericardium was decellularized and its surface was coated with polyaniline (PANI) nanoparticles. The decellularization efficiency of the pericardium was evaluated histologically using hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) and diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) staining, and quantitatively by DNA assay. PANI nanoparticles were synthesized via oxidative polymerization, yielding particles with an average size of 104.94 ± 13.7 nm. The conductivity of the PANI-coated pericardium was measured as $9.093 \pm 8.6 \times 10^{-4}$ S/cm using the four-point probe method. For the second layer, membranes were fabricated using 15% (w/v, 9:1 ratio) poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid)/gelatin and incorporated with varying concentrations of VEGF (0.1, 0.5, and 1 µg/ml) and hawthorn extract (1%, 5%, 10%, and 15% w/v). These membranes exhibited fiber diameters ranging from 850 to 1200 nm and pore sizes between 14 and 20 µm. The controlled release of VEGF and hawthorn extract was studied, and complete release was achieved over 28 days. The anticoagulant activity of the hawthorn-containing membranes was evaluated via activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT). Each layer was characterized in vitro separately, and layers were integrated using a tissue glue. The bilayered cardiac patch demonstrated a tensile strength of 22.70 ± 6.33 MPa, an elongation of $53.58\% \pm 10.63$, and a Young's modulus of 0.67 ± 0.10 MPa. In addition, it exhibited good cell viability and cell adhesion with a cardiomyocyte cell line. The blood compatibility of the cardiac patch was determined by hemolysis ratio, measured as $0.421\% \pm 0.191$. The results suggest that the proposed bilayered scaffold is a promising candidate for cardiac patch applications.

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Keyword: *Cardiac patch, scaffold, decellularization, electrospinning*

Toward Sustainable Biomaterials: Methacrylated Quince Seed Mucilage for Tissue Engineering Applications

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The increasing demand for sustainable and functional biomaterials has led to the development of plant-based platforms with tunable structures and biointegration capacity [1][2]. In this study, quince seed mucilage (QSM), a polysaccharide-rich natural hydrocolloid, was chemically modified via methacrylation using methacrylic anhydride to introduce photo-crosslinkable vinyl groups [3][4]. Incorporation of the biocompatible photo-initiator Irgacure 2959 enabled UV-induced in situ photocuring to form structurally stable hydrogel networks [5]. Systematic adjustment of the methacrylation degree enables tuning of crosslink density, swelling behavior, and mechanical properties—critical parameters for scaffold performance in tissue engineering. The hydrogels are characterized using a range of analytical techniques, including FT-IR, ¹H-NMR spectroscopy, SEM, and micromechanical testing, to elucidate structure–property relationships. Preliminary findings indicate that methacrylated QSM hydrogels exhibit a well-defined interconnected porous architecture with tunable stiffness and hydrophilic properties. These features could support nutrient diffusion, cell adhesion, and tissue compatibility. Their structural features and plant-based origin indicate strong potential for use as bioresponsive scaffolds in regenerative applications. This work highlights a promising strategy for the development of sustainable, customizable biomaterials derived from agricultural waste. The photocrosslinkable and in situ formable nature of the material underscores its suitability for next-generation tissue scaffolds in regenerative medicine. We would like to acknowledge Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit for financial support (Project ID: FYL-2024-4958).

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Keyword: *Quince seed mucilage, Methacrylation, Hydrogel, Photo-crosslinking*

Impact of Device Geometry and Magnetic Properties on TDW and VDW Switching at Elevated Temperatures

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The domain wall (DW) random switching in planar magnetic nanowires is one of the crucial problems for storage data applications. Hence, a micromagnetic simulation was used to investigate the transverse domain wall (TDW) nucleation in the thinner and narrower nanomagnetic devices and the vortex domain wall (VDW) nucleation for the thicker and wider nanowires due to the device temperature. The TDW thermal creation was examined based on magnetic properties such as uniaxial magnetic anisotropy energy (K_u) and saturation magnetization (M_s). The thermal stability of TDW switching in nanowires is strongly dependent on the improvement of magnetic properties, whereas the TDW thermal nucleation decreases by increasing K_u or M_s . In addition, the TDW and VDW thermal creation in storage nanodevices such as nanowires could be controlled by nanowire geometry manipulation like width and thickness. Reducing the nanowire width or increasing its thickness helps both domain wall types (TDW and VDW) switch to be more stable against nanodevice temperature. TDW thermal switching was found to be stable under a device temperature of up to 500 K, which is higher than the room temperature. However, the VDW shows higher thermal stability switching reaches up to 900 K, which are good candidates for storage applications. Furthermore, the TDW dynamics in nanowires were affected by device temperature, whereas the TDW moves faster by increasing nanodevice temperature. All these findings will help to maintain the storage memory in nanodevices from failure due to device temperature.

Keyword: *micromagnetic simulation, DW thermal stability, magnetic domain wall*

First-Principles Investigation of Rashba Spin Splitting Induced by Sb substitutional Doping in Bi₂Te₃ and Bi₂Se₃

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Topological insulators (TIs) are quantum materials characterized by an insulating bulk and topologically protected, spin-polarized metallic surface states (TSSs), arising from strong spin-orbit coupling (SOC) and band inversion. Substitution of Bi with antimony (Sb) offers a promising route for tuning their electronic properties while maintaining structural stability. However, a complete picture of how topological and Rashba-type spin-split states evolve across the entire Sb substitution range remains incomplete.

In this work, we performed density functional theory (DFT) calculations including SOC to systematically investigate the structural, electronic, and topological properties of Sb-doped Bi₂Te₃ and Bi₂Se₃ thin films across the full composition range ($0 \leq x \leq 1$) using 5-quintuple-layer (QL) slabs. We identify 5QL as the critical thickness for the emergence of TSSs and observe that both in-plane and out-of-plane lattice parameters decrease nearly linearly with increasing Sb content, in agreement with Vegard's law. While band inversion persists throughout the full doping range, its magnitude weakens gradually at high Sb concentrations.

Our results show that Sb substitution induces non-monotonic changes in structural inversion asymmetry and spin-orbit interaction strength, particularly in the Te-based system. A pronounced Rashba splitting is observed in Bi₂Te₃ at $x = 0.6$, with a peak Rashba parameter $\alpha \approx 2.10$ eV·Å; surpassing many known Rashba-active materials while Bi₂Se₃ exhibits significantly weaker spin splitting. We further demonstrate that band inversion and helical spin-momentum locking persist across the full doping range, though their strength diminishes at high Sb concentrations. Orbital- and layer-resolved analyses confirm the surface-localized origin of these states, with negligible bulk contributions.

These results provide a comprehensive framework for Rashba and topological state engineering via compositional tuning. In particular, Sb-doped Bi₂Te₃ appears as a highly tunable platform for next-generation quantum and spintronic devices, including spin-orbit torque systems, spin field-effect transistors, and topological quantum computing architectures. The large and tunable Rashba coefficients suggest the feasibility of all-electric spin control without external magnetic fields.

Keyword: Density Functional Theory, Topological Insulator, Bi₂Te₃, Substitutional Doping

Ionic Motion Induced Phase Transitions in Low Dimensional Materials

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Bilkent Ulusal Nanoteknoloji Araştırma Merkezi - UNAM

Atoms in a crystal occupy fixed positions in the lattice. However, in certain materials, a subgroup of atoms forms a strong structure with an ion resting in quasi-stable positions in the lattice. These ions can move within the lattice under external stimuli, without destroying the host structure. Recently, we have introduced a class of single-crystalline ionic materials for the first time in the literature using the real-time chemical vapor deposition method. We have systematically studied their phase transitions induced by the ionic motion. Here, I am going to provide an overview of how to synthesize via chemical vapor deposition, study, and harness the unusual phase transitions in these ionic materials. I will particularly focus on how single-crystalline low-dimensional samples are crucial for the study of ionic motion-induced phase transitions. The materials I will be talking about are Cu_2Se , K , Na-MnO_2 , and K_xWO_3 in particular. I will illustrate their ionic motion induced phase transitions under electrical, optical, and thermal stimuli, and talk about their prospective applications in various fields.

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Keyword: *Ionic conductors, Phase transitions, Correlated materials, Memristors*

Simultaneous Damage Detection in Fiber-Reinforced Composites Using Electrically Conductive Hybrid Nanoparticles

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Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPCs) are widely used in aerospace structures, wind turbines, and electric vehicles due to their superior specific strength and stiffness compared to traditional materials. However, their vulnerability to damage under mechanical loading necessitates the utilization of structural health monitoring (SHM) methods to reduce the risk of catastrophic failure. Among these, electrical resistance change (ERC) measurement using conductive nanoparticles offers a reliable approach for simultaneous damage detection.

This study investigates the synergistic effect of hybrid conductive nanoparticles on the ERC sensitivity of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites under static tensile loading. The total nanoparticle concentration was maintained at 0.5 wt%, and combinations of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with either expanded graphite (EG) or carbon black (CB) were prepared in the following ratios: 0.4% CNT - 0.1% EG/CB, 0.3% CNT - 0.2% EG/CB, 0.2% CNT - 0.3% EG/CB, and 0.1% CNT - 0.4% EG/CB. The resulting nanocomposite resin was used in the fabrication of composite specimens by combining it with plain type glass fiber reinforcement material with an areal density of 200 g/m², using the hand lay-up and vacuum bagging methods. Tensile tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min on glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite specimens fabricated with the specified concentrations of nanoparticles. During the tests, changes in the electrical resistance of the structure were simultaneously recorded using a multimeter. According to the data obtained from the test results, in CNT/CB mixtures, it was observed that as the CNT content in the structure increased from 0.1% to 0.4%, the change in electrical resistance upon specimen failure decreased significantly from approximately 55% to 16%. Furthermore, this increase in CNT content led to an enhancement of the mechanical properties of the specimens by approximately 21%.

In addition, for CNT/EG mixtures, increasing the CNT content from 0.1% to 0.4% resulted in a decrease in electrical resistance change from 46% to 25% upon specimen failure. However, unlike the CNT/CB system, the same increase in CNT content was found to reduce the mechanical performance of the specimens by approximately 16%.

Keyword: *Damage Detection, Polymer Composites, Nanomaterials, CNT/CB/EG*

Twist Angle–Dependent Frictional Dynamics of Twisted Bilayer Graphene: A Nanotribological Perspective

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Nanotribology, the study of friction, wear, and lubrication at the nanoscale, plays a crucial role in advancing nanotechnology, materials science, and device engineering. At these scales, surface interactions dominate material behaviour, making tribological properties highly sensitive to atomic structure and interfacial phenomena. Recently, significant developments in two-dimensional (2D) materials, particularly systems with controlled twist angles, such as twisted bilayer graphene (t-BLG), have opened new avenues for nanotribological research. The unique structural and electronic characteristics induced by the twist angle in bilayer graphene provide a novel platform for investigating nanoscale friction and energy dissipation mechanisms with atomic precision.

In this study, the effect of moiré periodicity, emerging in twisted structures, particularly in bilayer graphene, on nanotribological characteristics has been investigated. In this context, the study results lie at the intersection of fundamental theories of dry friction at the nanoscale, two-dimensional materials, and twisted layered structures. Twisted bilayer graphenes with interlayer twist angles smaller than 10° were synthesized by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and employed as a nanomaterial. Nanotribological measurements were conducted under ambient conditions using an atomic force microscopy (AFM). The findings were compared with natural bilayer graphene, as a reference material. Frictional properties were investigated through AFM measurements, enabling the determination of friction coefficients. This study focuses on the tribological properties of twisted structures, with particular emphasis on t-BLG, and highlights the underlying mechanisms, current challenges, and future directions in the field.

Keyword: *Twisted bilayer graphene (t-BLG), Nanotribology, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Moiré patterns*

Investigation of the Effects of Defects Formed During the Synthesis on the Structural and Optical Properties of Y/B Co-Doped ZnO Nanoparticles

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Zn_{0.95-x}Y_xB_{0.05}O nanoparticles were synthesized using the sol-gel method by stoichiometrically varying the x values (x = 0.00, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05). The types and intensities of the defects formed during the synthesis process were investigated, and their effects on the structural and optical properties were examined. The structural properties of all Y/B co-doped ZnO nanoparticles were determined by X-ray diffraction and the presence of the hexagonal wurtzite structure was clearly confirmed. The surface morphology and elemental composition of the nanoparticles were revealed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), respectively. The optical properties of the nanoparticles were analyzed using ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy. The absorption spectra were used to calculate the energy band gap, and the refractive index was estimated using different models. The photoluminescence (PL) properties of Zn_{0.95-x}Y_xB_{0.05}O nanoparticles were employed to identify the types and intensities of structural defects [1–2]. The influence of defects formed during the sol-gel synthesis on the structural and optical properties of Y/B co-doped ZnO nanoparticles was demonstrated.

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Keyword: Nanoparticles, Sol-gel method, Optical properties, Photoluminescence

Optimizing Nanobody-Based Sandwich Electrochemical Immunosensors for Ultrasensitive Protein Detection

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Sandwich-type electrochemical immunosensors are widely recognized for their high specificity, sensitivity, and compatibility with miniaturized, point-of-care diagnostic platforms.^[1] By employing a dual-recognition format and enzymatic signal amplification, they enable robust detection of low-abundance biomarkers in complex samples. However, challenges such as non-specific adsorption, inconsistent surface functionalization, and suboptimal assay conditions can compromise reproducibility and sensitivity.^[2] These limitations highlight the need for systematic optimization strategies to realize the full potential of such biosensing platforms.

In this study, we present the development and optimization of sandwich electrochemical immunoassays for the detection of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), using nanobody/nanobody and nanobody/antibody recognition pairs, respectively. Our optimization strategy focused on three critical assay parameters. First, we compared gold electrode surface functionalization strategies: (i) covalent immobilization of the capture nanobody via a SpyTag-peptide system^[3] for oriented and stable attachment, and (ii) direct physisorption of the nanobody onto electrode surfaces. Second, we evaluated two target incubation methods: (i) pre-mixing the target with the horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated detection nanobody or antibody before application, and (ii) sequential addition of the target followed by the detection unit. Third, we investigated the impact of surface blocking by comparing signal outputs from unblocked electrodes versus those treated with bovine serum albumin (BSA) or casein. Electrochemical detection was carried out via amperometric measurements based on the enzymatic reaction of HRP with 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). In parallel, colorimetric measurements were also performed for the complementary assessment and validation of assay performance during the optimization process. The results demonstrate that all three parameters significantly affect signal intensity and background response, underscoring the importance of rational sensor design. Furthermore, the optimized immunoassay was integrated into an organic electrochemical transistor (OECT) platform to further enhance sensitivity and signal transduction^[4], demonstrating its adaptability for next-generation bioelectronic diagnostics.

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Keyword: *immunosensor, nanobody, sandwich-type, chronoamperometry*

Plasmon-Enhanced Detection Of Exosomes Via AuNDs-Based Electrochemical Immunosensor

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Exosomes are extracellular vesicles that contain proteins, sugars, and various other biomolecules either inside or embedded in their lipid bilayer membrane. They are secreted by both healthy and cancerous cells and are well known to aid the spread of cancer cells to other tissues by altering their microenvironment. This process is largely mediated by specific proteins present on the exosome membranes, which can be exploited for diagnostic purposes. CD63 is a protein whose elevated intracellular levels have been widely associated with certain types of cancer; it is also found embedded in the membranes of cancer-derived exosomes. As a cancer biomarker, the early detection of CD63 in human serum is crucial for timely diagnosis and intervention, which may significantly reduce mortality rates. In recent years, many types of biosensors have been developed to detect bioanalytes at trace levels in an attempt to predict diseases before they progress to more fatal stages, where they are typically diagnosed. Among various biosensor platforms, nanomaterial-based electrochemical immunosensors have emerged as prominent candidates due to their high sensitivity and specificity toward target molecules. Gold nanodendrimers (AuNDs), a distinct class of gold nanoparticles, are characterized by their optically active, branched architectures, which [provide] a substantially larger surface area compared to the more conventional, planar gold nanoparticles typically employed in electrochemical immunosensor design. Plasmon-enhanced electrochemistry (PEEC) integrates plasmonic nanostructures, such as AuNDs, with their electrocatalytic behavior under localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) conditions, defined as the collective and coherent oscillation of conduction electrons on the surface of metallic nanoparticles stimulated by an external electromagnetic field. By incorporating plasmonic nanomaterials into electrochemical sensors, PEEC enables enhanced catalytic activity and improved sensitivity under light excitation. In this study, we report an application of a chiral AuND-based plasmonic immunoassay platform for the enhanced electrochemical detection of the CD63 protein. Catalytic amplification was achieved via laser irradiation at a wavelength of 532 nm, which is close to LSPR band of AuNDs. A label-free electrochemical immunosensor was subsequently fabricated by covalently immobilizing monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) onto AuNDs-coated screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), facilitating the selective capture and trace-level detection of CD63-containing exosomes. The integration of plasmonic enhancement within the immunosensor architecture represents an innovative and adaptable strategy with significant promise for the development of next-generation electrochemical biosensors targeting clinically important biomarkers. This approach may be particularly valuable for early-stage cancer diagnostics, where the sensitive detection of low-abundance exosomal proteins is critically important.

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Keyword: *Gold Nanodendrimers, Electrochemistry, Biosensors, Exosomes*

Nanoparticle-Modified Electrochemical Immunosensor Platform for Cardiac Troponin Assay

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One of the most deadly diseases that occur in the heart and blood vessels is cardiovascular diseases. Due to their lethality, early diagnosis is of great importance. In the presence of any of these diseases, electrochemical methods stand out because of the rapid, easy, cheap and highly sensitive detection of cardiac biomarkers. One of the most important gold biomarkers of cardiovascular diseases is troponin I [1,2]. In this study, metal-based nanoparticles were used for the detection of cardiac troponin I to improve the electroanalytical performance of the sensing platform. Metallic nanoparticles are very useful materials used in the construction of beneficial immunosensors with their adjustable shape and morphology, effective surface area and advanced catalytic and chemical properties [3,4]. In this study, we synthesized sponge-like bimetallic-based nanoparticles consisting platinum (Pt) and nickel (Ni) to modify screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE). To ensure immobilization of the antibody onto this modified electrode, we incorporated gold nanoparticles into the structure using electrodeposition method. Characterization studies of the so-formed electrode were carried out with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The proposed electrode showed promising results for troponin I biomarker in terms of good sensitivity.

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Keyword: *Electrochemical cardiac troponin I determination, metal-based nanoparticles, immunosensor*

Screen Printed Electrodes Modified With Isoniazid Derived Gold Nanoparticles For The Simultaneous Determination Of Ascorbic Acid And Uric Acid

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In the current study, an electrochemical platform was fabricated using Isoniazid-derived gold nanoparticles (Isn-AuNPs) self-assembled on the surface of a screen-printed electrode for the simultaneous detection of uric acid (UA) and ascorbic acid (AA). Isoniazid is an antibacterial drug commonly used in the treatment of tuberculosis. The structure of isoniazid exhibits amine groups that are capable of attaching to the surface of AuNPs, and hence isoniazid can serve as a capping agent to stabilise AuNPs in aqueous medium. The Isn-AuNPs were characterised by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), FTIR spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis. The Isn-AuNPs modified screen printed electrode (SPE) demonstrated pronounced electrocatalytic activity as well as improved peak separation of around ~ 0.20 V for ascorbic acid and uric acid simultaneously in comparison to bare SPE that showed overlapped peaks for the two analytes. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was employed to characterize the surface of Isn-AuNPs modified SPE. Differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) was used to construct linear calibration plots in the concentration range of 10 μ M to 50 μ M for ascorbic acid and in the range of 3 μ M to 10 μ M for uric acid, and the detection limits were found to be 7 μ M and 1.6 μ M, respectively. The practical application of the proposed sensor was tested using real samples, yielding satisfactory recovery results.

Keyword: gold nanoparticles, Ascorbic acid, Uric acid, simultaneous determination

Impact of Electric Field and Charging on the Magnetic and Electronic Behaviors of 1D CrX₃ (X = Cl, Br, I) Single-Chains

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Throughout the study, the structural, magnetic, vibrational, and electronic properties of onedimensional (1D) CrX₃ (X = Cl, Br, I) single-chains (SCs) are investigated using density functional theory (DFT) based first-principles calculations. Geometric optimizations reveal that twodimensional (2D) CrX₃ single layers adopt an edge-sharing octahedral structure with ferromagnetic (FM) interaction. In contrast, 1D CrX₃ SCs maintain a face-sharing octahedral structure leading to an antiferromagnetic (AFM) interaction between the Cr atoms. Phonon band dispersions indicate the dynamical stability of CrX₃ SCs as free-standing structures whose Raman spectrum predicts four distinct peaks. Electronic band dispersions reveal the direct band gap nature of 1D SCs in contrast to the indirect band gap semiconducting 2D counterparts. The dimensional reduction from a 2D structure to the 1D SCs results in a significant decrease in the hole effective masses. Moreover, the 1D CrX₃ SCs are shown to exhibit a robust AFM ground state and a direct band gap under applied external electric field. Further analysis on the charging of 1D SCs reveals a magnetic phase transition from AFM to ferrimagnetic (FIM) after a critical level of electron injection. Overall, our findings reveal the robustness of 1D CrX₃ SCs under external electric field and demonstrate tunable magnetic phases through electron injection, showcasing their potential for optoelectronics.

Keyword: *one-dimensional nanochains, density functional theory*

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Time Dependency of Vibration Observables in Single-frequency AFM Operations

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Driving the micro-cantilever at the resonance frequency enhances sensitivity to tip-sample interaction forces in single-frequency AFM. Oscillation observables of AFM micro-cantilevers to Van der Waals forces vary with time at particular separation distances. Correspondingly, quantification of sensitivity to Van der Waals forces strongly depends on the selected time periods, which can be simply extracted from forced displacements. In the present study, oscillatory motions of the AFM micro-cantilevers with different elastic stiffness, effective masses, and tip radii are obtained for the fundamental eigenmode in monomodal operations using the lumped parameter model. It is observed that amplitude, phase shift, and frequency responses mostly exhibit similar behaviors in the time domain (19.0 – 19.4 ms) for different mechanical features of the micro-cantilever. The responses of the dynamic model are compared with the results in the literature, which are determined for an AFM micro-cantilever under different operating conditions. For instance, the amplitude of 9.05 nm at 19.02 ms and the phase shift of around 96 degrees at 19.08 ms are closer to the literature results, which are the amplitude of 9.9 nm and the phase shift of 90 degrees in the separation distance range of 1 - 5 nm, respectively. Therefore, the time dependency of vibration observables of micro-cantilevers under external forces is to be considered for enhanced sensitivity analysis.

Keyword: *Single-frequency AFM, Time-varying observables, Van der Waals forces*

A Nanostructured Gas Detector: nano-GEM

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Gas Electron Multipliers (GEMs) are essential tools in radiation detection technologies. While conventional GEMs offer high sensitivity and fast response, they suffer from limitations in structural precision, durability, and miniaturization. In this study, we propose a novel GEM design that uses anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) nano-tubes as a replacement for traditional GEM holes. AAO foils were fabricated through a controlled anodization process, resulting in highly uniform and vertically aligned nano-holes. Sputter coating was applied to both surfaces to form conductive layers while preserving hole openness. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis confirmed hole diameters around 100 nm, which are well-suited for gas gain and electron transport. A prototype detector was constructed using the AAO-based nano-GEM foil. The new design is expected to improve electric field uniformity, reduce discharge risk, and enable lower gas flow operation—offering both performance and economic advantages. Future work will focus on full electrical characterization, gas gain testing, and real-environment radiation exposure. This approach demonstrates the potential of nanotechnology in enhancing gaseous detector architectures and opens pathways for compact, low-cost, and durable radiation sensors across various applications.

Keyword: Gaseous Radiation Detectors, Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM), Anodic Aluminum Oxide (AAO)

Jones Matrix Analysis via a Polarization-Sensitive Sensor in Digital Holographic Microscopy

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Polarization-resolved quantitative phase imaging offers important insights for inspecting and characterizing the structural orientations and polarization dependent properties of anisotropic birefringent materials. Conventional imaging techniques fail to provide such insights, where they would be undetectable or distinguishable. In this study, two approaches for calculating full-field Jones matrix images based on the incident polarization orientations, are analyzed using a modified off-axis Mach-Zehnder interferometer, with a motorized half-wave plate and polarization sensitive CMOS sensor with micro polarizer arrays. The system was tested on anisotropic materials and biological samples to analyze and assess the accuracy of the polarimetric parameters, such as retardance and fast axis orientation, along with methods to further enhance the precision and accuracy of extracted Jones matrices. Those findings can be applied for a wide range of material science and biomedical imaging applications, allowing detailed visualization and understanding of the orientation of tissue and polymer microstructures.

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Keyword: *Polarization imaging, Digital Holographic Microscopy, Jones Matrix, Anisotropic Material Characterization*

Predictive Machine Learning Approach for Clarifying Composition-Band Gap Relationships in Two-Dimensional MXenes

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Two-dimensional (2D) transition metal carbides, nitrides carbonitrides and their hydroxide-terminated derivatives (MXenes) are a class of materials with the general formula $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, where 'M' is an early transition metal, 'X' is carbon or nitrogen, and 'T' represents surface functional groups. The extensive range of possible elemental combinations results in a wide variety of tunable material properties, leading to applications in fields such as energy storage, catalysis, and electronics. To accelerate the discovery of new MXenes, machine learning (ML) models are utilized to clarify complex composition-property relationships, thereby enabling the predictive design of materials tailored for specific applications. To enable data-driven discovery, we generate a computational library of 2430 terminated MXenes and use it to develop ML models with a diverse set of regression algorithms spanning kernel methods, tree-based ensembles and a multilayer perceptron (MLP) for predicting electronic band gaps (E_g). Therefore, we construct hexagonal $M_{n+1}C_n$ slabs ($n=1-3$; $M \in \{Ti, Zr, Hf, V, Nb, Ta, Cr, Mo, W\}$) with AB-stacked metal layers, carbon in octahedral sites decorating both surfaces using AdsorbateSiteFinder module in pymatgen alchemy either single-species full-coverage terminations $T \in \{O, S, Se, Te, F, Cl, Br, I, OH, NH\}$ or mixed O/F on hollow sites [1]. Symmetry-inequivalent arrangements are retained after structure matching via StructureMatcher via pymatgen alchemy [1]. All structures are relaxed using spin-polarized Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof with D3 dispersion in QuantumESPRESSO with a two-dimensional Coulomb cutoff [2]. Across ML models, Bagging algorithm gives the best predicting E_g ($R^2 \geq 0.95$) such as 0.53 eV for $Zr_4C_3(OH)_2$. These elemental-only models facilitate rapid, DFT-free assessment and produce prioritized list of MXene candidates for specific electronic applications.

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Keyword: *Mxenes, Machine learning, Band gap*

Advancing Hydrogen Permeation Testing: In Situ XRD Microscopy for Mapping Diffusivity and Concentration in Complex Microstructures

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Hydrogen uptake, diffusion, and permeation are critical factors in determining the performance and reliability of materials in demanding applications such as energy, aerospace, and structural engineering. Electrochemical hydrogen permeation testing is widely used to evaluate hydrogen diffusivity and permeability, but significant challenges remain regarding data interpretation, modelling accuracy, and experimental validation. One of the key difficulties is the complex nature of hydrogen transport, which is influenced by microstructural heterogeneities. For example, grain boundaries are often assumed to be fast diffusion pathways. Still, their exact role in hydrogen transport remains uncertain due to the lack of direct experimental evidence. Current techniques cannot unambiguously resolve whether hydrogen preferentially diffuses through grain boundaries (GBs), adding further complexity to the interpretation of permeation curves.

A significant limitation in hydrogen research is the lack of non-destructive techniques capable of directly visualising hydrogen distribution within a material's microstructure. While thermal desorption spectroscopy and nano-secondary ion mass spectrometry provide valuable insights into hydrogen content, they are inherently ex-situ, meaning that most hydrogen is lost before analysis. In situ techniques are required to accurately quantify hydrogen concentration and understand its distribution during active hydrogen charging.

To address these challenges, we introduce in-situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction (XRD) microscopy as a powerful tool to probe lattice strain with micrometre resolution and strain sensitivity of 1×10^{-5} . While this technique cannot directly track hydrogen diffusion along grain boundaries, it provides essential insights into hydrogen-affected regions within the lattice, enabling us to generate hydrogen concentration maps in real time. By correlating experimental lattice strain with hydrogen concentration using density functional theory (DFT), we establish a novel approach for quantifying hydrogen diffusivity in complex microstructures. Additionally, by scanning the material under simultaneous tensile strain and electrochemical hydrogen charging using high-energy synchrotron X-rays, we demonstrate how in situ XRD microscopy can serve as a complementary method to refine mathematical models of hydrogen transport. This approach advances our understanding of hydrogen-material interactions and helps overcome existing limitations in permeation testing.

Keyword: *Hydrogen Diffusion, Synchrotron XRD Microscopy, Density Functional Theory, Lattice Strain Mapping*

Electrochemical Performance of Hydrothermally Synthesized LaMnO₃ Nanostructures under Different Illumination Conditions for Supercapacitor Applications

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The development of high-performance electrode materials for next-generation supercapacitors is of critical importance in the context of sustainable energy storage technologies. In this study, LaMnO₃ nanostructures were synthesized via a hydrothermal route followed by sintering at 800 °C to enhance crystallinity. The structural and morphological properties were confirmed through X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). XRD analysis revealed that the synthesized material crystallized in the orthorhombic phase, while FT-IR confirmed characteristic La–O and Mn–O bonding vibrations.

Electrodes were fabricated by preparing a composite slurry composed of 85 wt% LaMnO₃, 10 wt% acetylene black, and 5 wt% PVDF, applied onto nickel foam and assembled into a symmetric supercapacitor cell using 2 M KOH as the electrolyte. Electrochemical performance was evaluated through cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using a Gamry Reference 3000 potentiostat. Measurements were performed under three illumination conditions: dark, white LED light, and UV light exposure.

At a scan rate of 100 mV/s, the specific capacitance of LaMnO₃ electrodes was determined to be 339 F/g (dark), 414 F/g (white light), and 391 F/g (UV light), indicating enhancements of 18.2% and 13.4% under white and UV illumination, respectively. These results highlight the photoresponsive nature of LaMnO₃ and suggest its potential for integration in light-assisted supercapacitor systems. The study provides valuable insights into the tunability of electrochemical performance under variable environmental conditions.

Keyword: nanoscience, energy storage, supercapacitor, photo supercapacitor

Electrochemical Performance of Chemically Exfoliated Borophene Nanosheets for Supercapacitor Applications

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Two-dimensional (2D) materials have attracted considerable interest in energy storage applications due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, tunable electronic structures, and exceptional mechanical and chemical properties. Among these, borophene – a monolayer of boron atoms – has recently emerged as a promising candidate for next-generation supercapacitor electrodes [1,2]. Borophene exhibits metallic conductivity, high mechanical flexibility, anisotropic properties, and tunable electronic characteristics, distinguishing it from conventional 2D materials such as graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides [3]. Theoretical studies have predicted that certain borophene phases can achieve ultrahigh ion storage capacities, with lithium storage capacities reaching up to 1720 mAh/g [4]. Furthermore, its compatibility with other conductive 2D materials makes it a suitable component for hybrid electrode structures. In this study, few-layer borophene was successfully synthesized through a modified Hummer's method involving chemical oxidation and exfoliation. Compared to high-vacuum CVD approaches, this technique offers a scalable, cost-effective, and chemically simple route for borophene production. The exfoliated borophene were characterized and integrated into supercapacitor electrodes. Comprehensive structural, morphological, and electrochemical characterizations were conducted to evaluate the quality and functionality of the synthesized material. The borophene-based electrodes exhibited promising supercapacitor performance in terms of specific capacitance, cycling stability, and energy-power density relationship, confirming their potential for high-performance energy storage applications.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: 2D materials, borophene, liquid-phase exfoliation, energy storage

Fabricating Flexible Conductive Mats Using a Lignin-Based Graphitic Ink

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Identifying novel applications for residual by-products from biomass-intensive industries is of paramount importance for advancing sustainable development and mitigating environmental impact. In this context, lignin—one of the most abundant and underutilized biopolymers—has attracted considerable attention for its potential in high-value applications [1,2]. Herein, the organosolv lignin with an average molecular weight of 3000–3500 Da, extracted from hazelnut shell biomass by Koruma Klor A.Ş., was transformed into its water-soluble form through carboxymethylation using chloroacetic acid as carboxylate group donor under alkaline conditions. The water-soluble carboxymethyl lignin (CML) was first used as a dispersant to prepare graphitic ink (Gt-ink), which was then coupled with polyethylene oxide (PEO) as a carrier polymer to fabricate flexible electrospun mats (CML-Gt-PEO) under optimized conditions. Scanning electron microscopy image of the CML-Gt-PEO mat demonstrated a high fiber network coated by graphitic particles. The mat with a thickness of 57 µm was electrically conductive (~2500 mS/cm) and mechanically stable with a Young's Modulus value of ~150 MPa. Produced CML-Gt mats can be used as conductive electrodes for various applications.

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Keyword: *Lignin, Biomass, Carboxymethyl lignin, Electrospinning*

Integrated Multifunctional Use of Magnetic Nanoparticles in Paper-based Diagnostic Tools: From Sample Enrichment to Sensing Interface Design

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Point-of-care (POC) diagnostics represent a transformative approach in rapid testing, combining portability, cost-effectiveness, and user-friendliness. Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have emerged as critical nanomaterials within such platforms, providing unique versatility¹. This work highlights three distinct POC applications where MNPs played pivotal roles in sample enrichment, signal probing and surface chemistry. Their multifunctionality enables their successful integration into sensing systems for various applications ranging from clinical diagnostics to environmental monitoring.

In the first application, MNPs served both as signal probes and as a sample preparation tool, enabling efficient visual detection and magnetic enrichment to eliminate matrix interferences from food samples. This MNP-based pre-enrichment strategy improved both sensitivity and specificity while reducing interference from complex matrices. The second application focused on diagnostics of abused drugs using a streptavidin-modified MNP-based electrochemical aptasensor for the simultaneous detection of methamphetamine and cocaine. Paper electrodes functionalized with aptamer–MNP complexes allowed for specific analyte capturing, achieving high sensitivity through differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and cyclic voltammetry (CV). In the final strategy, MNPs contribute to detection of multiple targets by providing multicolorimetric outputs alongside other nanoparticles. Hence, MNPs enabled enhanced visual distinction between analytes and broadened the system's multiplexing capacity.

Overall, MNPs stand out as versatile nanomaterials that significantly expand the functionality of POC systems. Their multi-purpose use in different assay types—optical, electrochemical, and multiplexed—demonstrates their adaptability and great potential on improving rapid diagnostics.

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Keyword: *Magnetic Nanoparticles, Lateral Flow Assays, Paper Diagnostics, Paper-based Electrochemical Biosensors*

Upcycling Beet Molasses into High-Performance Supercapacitors: A Nanocomposite of Activated Carbon-Mixed Phases MoS₂ for Sustainable Energy Storage.

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This work was driven by the growing need for sustainable and cost-effective energy storage solutions, especially in light of increasing global energy demands and environmental concerns. By utilizing sugar beet molasses, an abundant agricultural byproduct, as a carbon source, the study aims to transform waste into high-value energy materials. The general objective was to develop a high-performance supercapacitor electrode through the synergistic integration of porous activated carbon with mixed-phase MoS₂, thereby promoting environmental sustainability and advanced energy storage performance. In this study, sugar beet molasses, a form of agricultural waste, was initially transformed into biochar via a hydrothermal process. The resulting biochar was then chemically activated to yield highly porous activated carbon (AC) with a large surface area of 1443 m² g⁻¹. Ammonium tetrathiomolybdate (ATM) was the precursor for MoS₂, which was uniformly distributed across the AC surface. The MoS₂ formed consisted of a hybrid composition containing both the metallic 1T and the semiconducting 2H phases, offering substantial potential for advanced energy storage applications. Comprehensive analyses of the structural, morphological, physical, and electrochemical characteristics were conducted. When applied as an electrode material in supercapacitors, the AC-MoS₂ composite exhibited an impressive specific capacitance of 1873.9 F g⁻¹ (729.4 C g⁻¹) at a current density of 1 A g⁻¹. An asymmetric device (AC-MoS₂//AC) was assembled for practical evaluation using commercial activated carbon as the negative electrode and AC-MoS₂ as the positive electrode. This device delivered an outstanding energy density of 35.7 Wh kg⁻¹ and a power density of 1015 W kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹, with 100% coulombic efficiency and 88.6% capacity retention after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles.

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Keyword: Sugar beet molasses, Activated carbon, MoS₂, Supercapacitors

Fabrication of Novel Cu-embedded Core-shell Carbon Nanofibers with High Electrical Conductivity via Coaxial Electrospinning

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Electrospun carbon nanofibers (CNFs) possess a unique 1D structure (high alignment and high specific surface area) and controllable morphology (hollow, porous, and core-shell), which are extremely desirable in many applications, including composites, electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding, Li-ion batteries, supercapacitors, microwave absorption, sensors and fuel cells etc. However, the limitation of electrical conductivity has restricted their applications. The aim of this work is to fabricate a novel structure consisting of Cu-embedded core-shell carbon nanofibers with high electrical conductivity via a simple coaxial electrospinning method. The inner fluid is a composite of polyethylene oxide (PEO) and copper (II) acetate, whereas the outer fluid is polyacrylonitrile (PAN) solution. In this work, the effects of press on the structure and morphology of CNFs were investigated in detail to figure out the reasons behind the improvement of electrical conductivity. The as-spun nanofiber mat was pressed under various loads and then thermally stabilized at 280 °C and carbonized at 1000 °C to obtain a carbon nanofiber mat. Several techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy and four-point probe were carried out to investigate the structural, morphological and electrical properties of CNF samples. SEM and HRTEM images exhibit a hollow carbon nanofiber morphology with outer and inner diameters of about 500–600 nm and 340–360 nm, respectively. XRD data shows a decrease in the intensity of Cu₂O peaks and no change in the intensity of Cu peaks with increasing press. XPS and Raman spectroscopy results revealed that defects of graphite-like structure increase along with the amount of quaternary nitrogen (QN) while the press value increases. Based on results, the applied press on nanofibers slightly deforms the graphite-like framework and increases the defective structure of CNFs. The increase of these defects is accompanied by an enhancement of QN amount in CNFs, indicating that QN might exist in the graphite-like lattice (**Fig 1**). These effects become more pronounced with increasing press on nanofibers. The electrical conductivity of Cu-embedded coaxial CNFs significantly increases while the applied load gradually grows, reaching about 100.7 Scm⁻¹ at 5 tons. The quaternary nitrogen in the graphite layer generates an extra electron for the delocalized π -system, causing an increase in the vibration of π -system, thus improving the electrical conductivity.

Fig. 1. Graphical Abstract

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Keyword: Coaxial electrospinning, Carbon nanofibers, Electrical conductivity, Graphite-like structure

Electrodes for Multilayer MOF Supercapacitors Made With a Binder Based on Waste Polymers

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Supercapacitors are increasingly recognized as pivotal components in advanced energy systems, particularly in areas concerning efficient energy utilization, lossless energy transfer, and high-capacity, long-term energy storage. Sustained research into novel electrode materials is critical to further advancements in this field. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have garnered considerable attention as next-generation supercapacitor electrode materials. Their distinctive characteristics, including high surface areas and tunable pore sizes, position them as highly promising candidates for enhancing supercapacitor performance.

This study investigated a layered MOF-on-MOF (La-Fe-La) architecture in comparison to a pristine Lanthanum (La)-MOF structure, incorporating BDC (derived from waste polymers as binders). The objective was to elucidate the electrochemical performance disparities between these electrode configurations. Comprehensive electrochemical characterization was conducted using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Furthermore, the electrochemical stability of both electrodes was rigorously assessed over at least 5000 cycles. The results revealed a substantial enhancement in specific capacitance with the layered composite. The bare La-MOF exhibited a specific capacitance of 151.71 F/g at a current density of 1 A/g. In contrast, the layered composite, synthesized with FeCl₃, demonstrated a significantly higher specific capacitance of 311.73 F/g. Further material characterizations provided mechanistic insights into this enhanced performance. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images indicated that the layered structure of the composite facilitates a greater number of pathways for ion transfer, thereby promoting improved electrochemical kinetics. This hypothesis was corroborated by data from Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis, and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), collectively supporting the premise that the layered composite structure contributes to superior supercapacitor performance.

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Keyword: *supercapacitors, waste management, metal organic frameworks*

ZIF-8-Decorated Ferrocenyl Surfactant-Based Vesicles for Synergistic Therapeutic Applications

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In recent years, one of the most important issues in designing and preparing drug delivery systems is versatility, which includes providing synergistic therapeutic effects and sustainability. This study presents a multifunctional drug delivery system, Rhb@ZIF-8/PDA/AOT-Fc(C11), which has chemotherapeutic, chemodynamic, and photothermal effects. We created an effective therapeutic agent by combining metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and redox-active vesicles by using a ferrocene-containing surfactant. We utilized Zeolitic Imidazolate Framework-8 (ZIF-8) as a drug carrier due to its pH-sensitive, highly porous structure. We added a polydopamine (PDA) layer to ZIF-8 to provide photothermal therapy ability. Vesicles, which are well-known drug delivery structures, were chosen for the core of the system. Vesicles prepared using AOT-FcN⁺(CH₂CH₃)₃(CH₂)_nCH₃ (where n = 10) can be considered Fenton reaction agents due to the ferrocenyl surfactant used. We studied the properties of this multifunctional, multi-responsive system at different pH levels and under NIR laser irradiation and demonstrated its triple chemodynamic, photothermal, and chemotherapeutic effects.

Keyword: Zeolitic imidazolate framework-8, drug delivery systems, vesicle

Synthesis of Trehalose-Based Polyurethane Structures for Biomedical Applications and Investigation of Metformin Release Properties

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The design of advanced polymeric systems for controlled drug delivery is becoming increasingly important in biomedical research, with the aim of improving therapeutic efficacy while minimising side effects. In this context, polyurethanes (PUs) are a promising option due to their tunable physicochemical properties, excellent biocompatibility and structural flexibility. This study focuses on synthesising and characterising trehalose-based PU structures for use as sustained-release carriers for metformin, a first-line antidiabetic drug.

Three PU formulations were developed by incorporating different ratios of polyethylene glycol (PEG1500), β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and trehalose as polyol components. These were then reacted with hexamethylene diisocyanate under controlled conditions to produce the polymer systems MG-PU-001, MG-PU-002 and MG-PU-003. The synthesized materials were structurally confirmed via Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). They were also analysed for thermal stability using Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The surface morphology and porosity were evaluated using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and the crystallinity was assessed by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD).

Metformin was successfully loaded into the PU matrices and in vitro drug release studies were performed under simulated physiological conditions. The release profiles demonstrated sustained and controlled release over an extended period, with variation depending on the polyol composition. The demonstration of particularly promising results was shown by trehalose-based PU structures due to their favourable interaction with metformin and their porous network, which supports gradual drug diffusion.

In conclusion, the synthesized PU materials demonstrated excellent potential as biomedical carriers for sustained drug delivery. Their tunable structure, biocompatibility, and controlled release capabilities make them suitable candidates for further preclinical evaluation, especially in chronic disease management such as diabetes. This study contributes to the development of functional biomaterials that combine structural versatility with effective therapeutic performance.

Keyword: Polyurethane, Trehalose, β -Cyclodextrin, Metformin

Smart Nanocarriers for Cancers: Integrating Efficient Drug Synthesis for 3D Tumor Spheroid Models

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The evolution from conventional drug treatment to combination therapies, and switching to drug-carriers for enhanced drug availability has gained significant progression in cancer cure. However, restricted synthesis approaches still limit the easy yet efficient designing methods which provide maximum loading capacity into the carriers, thereby allowing enhanced bioavailability of the drug in the system. Moreover, advancing pre-clinical drug testing requires microphysiological systems (MPS) that accurately replicate human patho-physiology. Three-dimensional (3D) cell cultures, particularly multicellular tumor spheroids offer a transformative approach by mimicking the intricate tumor microenvironment, including cancer, immune, and stromal cell interactions within the extracellular matrix. However, the lack of high-throughput, physiologically relevant 3D models impedes progress in understanding therapeutic resistance and optimizing drug combinations. This study pioneers designing and hence offering a novel MPS platform integrating high-throughput 3D cancer spheroid models generation using customized modeling design. Once created, this model was further coupled with microfluidics on-chip protein-drug nanoconjugates production, enhancing both drug delivery precision and therapeutic efficacy. Our drug-nanoconjugates, personalized for single and multi-drug delivery, demonstrate superior targeting and safety profiles compared to conventional nanocarriers. Within the 3D-tumor microenvironment, these biomolecule-based nanocarriers significantly improve drug availability and efficacy. In physiologically relevant spheroid models, our nanoconjugates achieved a three-fold increase in intra-tumoral drug concentration, markedly suppressing tumor growth with a single-dose treatment. Compared to the clinically approved Doxil (liposomal Dox), our nanoconjugates extended median survival and exhibited lower toxicity at effective doses (3–5 μM) across diverse cancer cell lines. Our findings underscore the power of MPS-based approaches in revolutionizing drug discovery and personalized medicine. By bridging the gap between pre-clinical models and human disease biology, this platform offers a groundbreaking tool for developing next-generation cancer therapies. Thus, our findings underscore the power of integrating protein nanoconjugates with advanced 3D models to establish a new frontier in biomedical research and disease modeling, positioning this innovative system at the forefront of precision oncology

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Keyword: *Nanomedicine, Drug-nanoconjugates, 3D Spheroids, nanocarriers*

Nanomedicine Strategies for Synergistic Chemotherapy: Aprotinin as a Tumor-Selective Nano-Carrier for Valproic Acid Via Microfluidics

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Nanomedicine strategies leveraging bio-derived nano-carriers offer promising avenues for precision chemotherapy. Here, we introduce a microfluidics-assisted nano-bioconjugate platform that repurposes Aprotinin (Apr), a naturally occurring protein, as a tumor-selective nano-carrier for Valproic Acid (VPA), a histone deacetylase inhibitor with anticancer properties. The resulting Aprotinin-Valproic Acid (Apr-VPA) nanoconjugates were synthesized via a flow-controlled microfluidic process and characterized by spectroscopic and calorimetric analyses confirming stable binding. In vitro studies in 3D tumor spheroid models demonstrated dose-dependent inhibition of spheroid growth and viability, supporting the conjugate's therapeutic potential. Preliminary in vitro comparisons with healthy endothelial cells suggest selective cytotoxicity, warranting further investigation. The nanoconjugates also exhibited pH-responsive behavior under acidic conditions, indicating potential for environment-triggered drug release. These findings highlight the feasibility of using Aprotinin as a scalable protein-based nanocarrier for targeted cancer therapy and support its future development in advanced nanomedicine applications.

Keyword: *Nanomedicine, Nano-bioconjugates, Nano-carriers, Microfluidics synthesis*

International Requirements for Nanomaterials in Biomaterials and Medical Devices: EN ISO 10993-22

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ISO 10993-22 defines the basic standards for the assessment of biocompatibility of medical devices, especially those containing nanomaterials. Biocompatibility is a critical parameter for the safety and effectiveness of medical devices that come into direct contact with the human body. The ISO 10993 series generally outlines the preclinical test methodologies required to assess whether medical devices cause adverse biological reactions. These methodologies are of even greater importance for nano-enabled medical products, especially considering the unique physicochemical properties and increased biological interaction potential of nanomaterials (Szymanski et al., 2025).

Medical devices containing nanomaterials present significant regulatory challenges compared to traditional materials. The nano-size, large surface area, and special surface properties of these devices can cause unpredictable biological responses and therefore require additional safety tests prescribed by ISO standards (Gaur et al., 2020). In this context, biocompatibility assessments in line with ISO 10993-22 can be performed at early stages of the product development process, allowing the reduction of risks that may arise from biological interactions and the fulfillment of regulatory requirements (Szymanski et al., 2025).

In particular, the global trend towards in vitro testing methodologies replacing animal experiments further highlights the role of ISO guidelines in the modern medical device safety framework (Frisch et al., 2023). The development and adoption of standards such as ISO 10993-22 enables the systematic assessment of the safety of nanotechnology-based medical devices. Such standards contribute to the harmonization of regulatory frameworks with technological developments by providing a structured approach under headings such as material selection, manufacturing processes and potential toxicological risks.

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Keyword: *nanomaterial, medical device, biocompatibility, regulation*

IL-13R α 2 Receptor Targeting with Molecularly Imprinted Polymers as Promising Therapy for Diffuse Intrinsic Pontine Glioma

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We report the synthesis, characterization and validation of nanosized molecularly imprinted polymers with peptide epitopes (nanoMIPs) designed to selectively target the interleukin-13 receptor subunit alpha-2 (IL-13R α 2), which is overexpressed in diffuse midline gliomas (DMGs) (1-3). We identified key binding sequences on IL-13R α 2 using epitope mapping and defined sequences, which led to the development of nanoMIPs targeting the D1, D2, and D3 domains of the receptor protein (4-5). The nanoMIPs were characterized for their stability in various media, binding affinity to the IL-13R α 2 protein, and cellular uptake in different cell lines.

Our results showed that three specific nanoMIPs, targeting different motifs of the IL-13R α 2 receptor, significantly decreased cell viability in glioma cell lines (HSJD-DIPG-007 and SU-DIPG-36) by up to 40%, while not affecting the non-tumour MO3.13 cell line. These nanoMIPs were effectively internalized into glioma cells due to their selective molecular recognition properties, whereas they were not taken up by IL-13R α 2-deficient control cells.

Western blot analysis revealed that these three nanoMIPs reduced the phosphorylation of three key pathways involved in cell survival: ERK1/2, AKT, and STAT3. Additionally, Caspase 3/7 assays confirmed that these nanoMIPs rapidly induced apoptosis in glioma cells. Overall, our findings demonstrate that nanoMIP-4 (targeting D1), nanoMIP-6 (targeting D3), and nanoMIP-8 (also targeting D3) serve as targeted therapeutics for IL-13R α 2-expressing gliomas. This offers a promising molecularly imprinted platform for the development of further targeted therapies blocking affecting receptor activities without toxic drug molecules in oncology applications.

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Keyword: synthetic antibody nanoparticles, molecularly imprinted polymers, diffuse midline gliomas, cancer cell apoptosis

Limiting Moisture and Oxygen Ingress in Quantum Dot Films via Isotropic Encapsulation

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The long-term stability of quantum dot (QD) color converters remains a major obstacle in their integration into advanced display technologies, including mini- and microLEDs where exposure to ambient conditions is intensified due to high edge-area-to-volume ratios. Traditional thin-film encapsulation approaches often fail to prevent lateral ingress of moisture and oxygen, which leads to optical degradation over time.

In this work, we present a novel strategy that addresses this critical limitation by using isotropic encapsulation of QDs through maskless digital light processing (DLP) lithography. Our approach involves embedding methacrylate-functionalized CdSe/CdS@SiO₂ QDs into a commercially available UV-curable resin, resulting in a photopolymerizable QD-resin. This formulation allows for precise, additive manufacturing of QD-loaded 3D structures, which we refer to as “QD pockets”—monolithic heterostructures in which the active QD core is encapsulated seamlessly from all sides.

We demonstrate the fabrication of QD pockets with micrometer-level resolution, high spatial fidelity, and flexible geometries directly onto substrates using a custom DLP setup. Our optical and morphological analyses confirm that QDs are uniformly dispersed, exhibit strong photoluminescence retention, and show low variability across large-area arrays. Crucially, the continuous resin shell formed around each QD core acts as a barrier against the lateral diffusion of oxygen and water vapor, effectively mitigating edge ingress that often plagues conventional designs.

This method provides a scalable and versatile route for both simultaneous QD patterning and protection, making it compatible with complex display architectures and transfer printing techniques. Additionally, it offers a framework for further enhancement by integrating advanced barrier materials into the outer shell. As display technologies push toward higher resolution and reliability, our isotropic encapsulation strategy represents a significant advancement in ensuring the environmental stability of QD-based components.

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Keyword: *semiconductor nanocrystals, surface chemistry, QD-LED, 3D printing*

Polymer: Metal Oxide Composite Materials for Detection of Ionizing Radiation

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The applicability of organic semiconductors in radiation detectors has gained increasing attention due to their compatibility with low-cost manufacturing processes, suitability for large-area applications, and mechanical flexibility. In this context, P3HT based structures functionalized with ZnO nanoparticles present promising candidates in terms of both sensitivity and ease of fabrication. These materials hold significant potential for the development of high-performance and cost-effective X-ray detectors, particularly in fields such as healthcare, security, and industry.

This study explores the use of organic semiconductors for X-ray detection by incorporating zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles into a poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) matrix to form composite active layers. ZnO nanoparticles were selected due to their high electron mobility, wide bandgap, and thermal stability. They were synthesized using the sol-gel method and incorporated into P3HT at different doping ratios (1:0.25, 1:0.5, and 1:0.75). Two distinct device architectures were fabricated and tested: resistive type devices with interdigitated electrodes IDT/P3HT:ZnO and diode type devices with the configuration indium tin oxide ITO/ZnO/P3HT:ZnO/Graphite.

The effect of ZnO nanoparticle concentration on device performance was systematically evaluated. It was observed that increasing the ZnO content improved electron transport and enhanced sensitivity to X-rays. The best results were obtained with the ITO/ZnO/P3HT:ZnO/Graphite device containing a 1:0.75 P3HT:ZnO ratio, which exhibited the highest sensitivity (0.79 $\mu\text{Gy/s}$) and the fastest response time. Electrical characterization demonstrated significant variations in current response under different X-ray doses, confirming the active role of ZnO nanoparticles in the detection mechanism. This study was supported by TÜBİTAK, project number: 123F131.

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Keyword: *Organic semiconductor, X-ray detection, Organic X-ray detector, ZnO Nanoparticles*

Multifunctional, Biocompatible Hybrid Surface Coatings Combining Antibacterial, Superhydrophobic and Fluorescent Applications

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Hybrid inorganic organic material concept plays a bold role for multifunctional materials combining different features on one platform. Once varying properties coexist without canceling each other on one matrix, a new type of supermaterial can be formed. Within this concept it was shown that inorganic organic surface coatings can be embedded together by silver nanoparticles and Si QD's for symbiotic antibacterial character and UV excited visible light fluorescent features. Additionally fluorosilane material can be coupled with this prepolymeric structure to add the superhydrophobic feature showing water contact angles around 120 providing self cleaning features. Optical properties of the components and the final material were investigated by UV-Vis spectroscopy and PL analysis. Atomic investigations and structural variations were detected by XPS, SEM and EDX atomic mapping method correcting the atomic entities inside the coating. Surface features were tracked by FT-IR and statistical analysis of the QD's and nanoparticles were conducted. Multifunctional final materials showed antibacterial property against to E. coli and S.Aureus, exhibit self cleaning feature with high surface contact angle and visible light fluorescence due to the Si QD incorporation into the sol-gel produced nanocomposite hybrid structure.

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Keyword: *Multifunctional material, sol-gel, nanoparticle, quantum dot, nanocomposite*

Fabrication of Mechanically Strong and Electrically Conductive Nanocomposites by Integration of Graphene to Carbon Fiber Reinforced-ABS Copolymer

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Polymeric materials reinforced with carbonaceous additives have been studied intensively in the transportation field, including electrostatic coatings, trims, indoor and outdoor composite parts. Herein, graphene (GR) was integrated into short carbon fiber (CF) acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer (ABS) via melt-blending process. Composite samples were produced with component amounts of 20 wt.% CF besides 0.1, 0.5, and 1.0 wt.% of GR. Tensile, impact, hardness, and wear tests, conductive atomic force microscopy (AFM), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA), melt flow index test (MFI), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis were utilized to characterize mechanical, electrical, thermo-mechanical, thermal, melt-flow, and structural behaviors of ABS-based composites, respectively.

The mechanical test data of composites revealed that GR additions led to a remarkable increase in tensile strength and impact resistance for CF-reinforced ABS composites. The wear resistance behavior of composites was enhanced with GR inclusion due to the layered geometry of graphene. Composites involving GR additive yielded lower MFI values compared to ABS and CF-reinforced ABS. However, the variation of MFI was found to be in a narrow range, which means ABS/CF+GR nanocomposites can be used as 3D filament material for additive manufacturing applications. The formation of the conductive path into the ABS/CF composite structure was established thanks to the integration of GR nanoparticles. The synergistic interactions between GR nano pellets and CF were confirmed by electrical conductivity findings. Composites filled with 0.5% GR exhibited the highest nanomechanical performance according to the Young's modulus mapping data of the AFM study. SEM micrographs of composites visualized the homogeneous dispersion morphology of GR phase into the ABS matrix. Since the integration of GR nanoparticles improved the examined behaviors of composites, the ABS/CF+GR ternary composite system can be preferred in various fields where high performance is required.

Keyword: Graphene, Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene, Nanocomposites, Polymeric composites

Dual Detection Systems Using Electrochemical Enzyme Based Nanobiosensors

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Electrochemical enzyme-based biosensors are one of the most widespread and commercially effective biosensors. In the design of enzyme-based biosensors, enzyme immobilization has been shown to be an effective method to avoid the disadvantages of using free enzymes, thus improving the productivity and cost efficiency of the manufacturing process¹. Immobilized enzymes offer great potential for developing sensors that can detect and characterize their respective targets. It is anticipated that substrate/analyte molecules will migrate from the medium to the immobilized enzymes in enzymatic biosensors. Enzyme inhibition by drugs is crucial for therapeutic interventions and regulating biochemical processes. It allows precise control of metabolic pathways, preventing overactivity or imbalance. Targeted inhibition can mitigate disease progression, offering effective treatments for various conditions. Understanding and manipulating enzyme inhibition aids in developing pharmaceuticals with enhanced efficacy and reduced side effects. Enzyme inhibition is integral to enzyme-based biosensors, influencing their sensitivity and selectivity. By strategically inhibiting or modulating specific enzymes, biosensors can detect and quantify target molecules with precision². This synergy enables the development of biosensing platforms for diverse applications, including medical diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and food safety, enhancing analytical capabilities. Tyrosinase is a key enzyme in melanin synthesis, catalyzing the conversion of tyrosine to melanin. It plays a crucial role in skin pigmentation and is a target for cosmetic research. Its inhibition by several drugs was followed using novel electrochemical enzyme-based biosensors, and factors affecting the enzyme inhibition process were optimized. It is believed that these studies will shed light on the discovery of new drugs.

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Keyword: *Electrochemistry, Enzyme, Tyrosinase, Biosensor*

Recombinant Production of H6 scFv Antibody for Nanoparticle Conjugation

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The COVID-19 pandemic has once again underscored the critical importance of rapid and sensitive viral diagnostics. Emerging and region-specific viral diseases continue to pose public health challenges and are expected to do so in the future. Consequently, molecular diagnostic techniques are widely employed to identify causative agents. However, these methods are often time-consuming and require professional expertise, placing them at a disadvantage compared to techniques that detect viral surface antigens or antigenic fragments. Direct viral detection typically relies on antibodies or aptamers specific to viral antigens. These antibodies are generally produced via hybridoma technology and are commercially available as full-length immunoglobulins, which entails considerable cost and time. In contrast, single-chain variable fragment (scFv) antibodies offer significant potential in diagnostic applications due to their rapid and cost-effective production, as well as their high sensitivity. In this study, an scFv specific to the SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid (N) protein, which has high conservation, strong immunogenicity, and abundance in clinical samples, was recombinantly produced, and its potential for conjugation with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) was investigated. AuNPs were synthesized chemically and employed as labeling agents in scFv conjugation studies. Results showed that high-yield recombinant production of the H6 scFv was obtained and conjugated with AuNPs. As a future plan, diagnostic platforms such as ELISA, lateral flow assay or dot blot assay will be prepared and integrated with scFv as a rapid diagnostic tool for viral detection.

This project was supported by the Scientific Research Projects (BAP, TDK-2024-3601).

Keyword: SARS-COV-2, gold nanoparticles, scFv, rapid diagnosis

Development of Immunomagnetic Nanoparticle and pH Indicator Based Colorimetric Nanobiosensors and Investigation of Their Use in the Determination of Cytokeratin 18

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Bladder cancer is the tenth most common cancer worldwide and the second most common tumour of the urogenital tract after prostate cancer. Bladder cancers are typically non-muscle invasive (NMCCs), while around one third are muscle-invasive or metastatic. Cystoscopy and cytological examination of urine are the gold standard methods for diagnosing bladder cancer and monitoring non-muscle invasive bladder cancers (NMCCs). These methods are currently used for the primary diagnosis of bladder cancer and the follow-up of non-muscle invasive bladder cancers. However, due to the disadvantages and costs of these methods, faster, simpler, more cost-effective diagnostic methods are being sought, with urine biomarkers emerging as an alternative. Cytokeratins (CK) are biomarkers thought to be present in higher quantities in the urine of bladder cancer patients and can be measured using various techniques. CK8 and CK18 can be quantitatively detected in urine using monoclonal antibodies. Although various studies using commercial kits developed for measuring these CKs have been performed, their sensitivity is very limited.

Over the past decade, innovative diagnostic test platforms based on nanomaterials have been developed to measure biomolecules and cells with high sensitivity, enabling early disease detection. Nanoparticles, nanotubes and nanowires are among the most rapidly developing products of nanotechnology and exhibit ideal properties for many new diagnostic testing platforms for biomedical applications.

Some of the biomarkers used for this purpose, known as the 'cytokeratins' (cytokeratins 8, 18 and 19), are found in increased amounts in the urine of people with bladder cancer. Cytokeratin 8 and 18 can be detected quantitatively in urine using monoclonal antibodies. The main objective of the proposed project is to develop a nano-biosensor based on immunomagnetic nanoparticles and a natural pH indicator that can rapidly and sensitively detect CK18 from CK groups, and to perform delta E (ΔE) and RGB analysis with digital process imaging software to semi-quantitatively support these colorimetric results. The planned goals are to prepare larger budget projects with the obtained results and design them for clinical use, in order to achieve the aim of the proposed project.

Keyword: bladder cancer, cytokeratin, nanoparticle, pH indicator, colorimetric sensor

Label-Free SPR Biosensor with Molecular Imprinting for Early Cancer Marker Detection

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Neuron-specific enolase (NSE) is a key biomarker used in the diagnosis and monitoring of neuroendocrine tumors and neurological disorders. However, current diagnostic methods are often limited by high cost, low sensitivity, and invasive sampling procedures. To overcome these limitations, we propose the development of a novel, highly specific biosensor platform that combines **Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR)** with **Molecularly Imprinted Polymer (MIP)** technology for the detection of NSE in biological fluids.

This study focuses on constructing a synthetic recognition surface capable of selectively binding NSE molecules using a MIP layer formed directly on the SPR sensor chip. The imprinting process is carried out via UV-initiated polymerization using a carefully optimized composition of functional monomers, crosslinkers, and solvents. Characterization studies, including atomic force microscopy (AFM), contact angle measurements, and spectroscopic ellipsometry, confirm the uniformity and functionality of the imprinted surface. Following template removal, the resulting biosensor enables label-free, real-time, and non-invasive detection of NSE with high affinity and selectivity.

Preliminary tests using artificial plasma have demonstrated the sensor's strong binding kinetics, high reproducibility, and excellent selectivity against interfering biomolecules. The proposed biosensor is designed to be cost-effective and aims to support earlier diagnosis and clinical decision-making in cancer treatment. Furthermore, it presents a promising alternative to antibody-based assays, reducing dependence on biological reagents and cold chain logistics.

This research offers significant potential for advancing diagnostic strategies, particularly in resource-limited settings, and contributes to the development of locally engineered biomedical technologies. The integration of MIP and SPR in this context provides a robust platform for the detection of other clinically relevant biomarkers in future applications.

Keyword: *Cancer Biomarker, Surface Plasmon Resonance Sensor, Molecularly Imprinted Polymer, Early Diagnosis*

Acetone-derived polymers for use as electroactive components in lithium–sulfur battery applications

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Acetone-derived carbonyl–sulfur polymers are presented as a novel class of electroactive materials for application in lithium–sulfur (Li–S) batteries. These materials are synthesized through a one-step thermal reaction between elemental sulfur and acetone, the simplest and most accessible ketone. The resulting polymers possess abundant carbonyl functionalities and covalently bonded sulfur units integrated into the polymer backbone.

This study is significant in that it utilizes elemental sulfur, a low-cost and abundant by-product of petroleum refining, and acetone, an inexpensive solvent and chemical feedstock, to create functional materials. To our knowledge, this represents the first report of a carbonyl–sulfur polymer derived directly from acetone, forming a covalently cross-linked structure without relying on traditional inverse vulcanization or vinyl monomer systems. This synthetic route marks a substantial departure from conventional sulfur–polymer chemistries [1].

A systematic investigation of reactant ratios was conducted to identify conditions that yield fully polymerized, homogeneous materials. Structural and chemical characterizations using Field-Emission SEM, XRD, DTA-TG, XPS, Raman, and FTIR confirm polymer formation in a specific formulation, with evidence of chemically embedded sulfur and redox-active carbonyl groups. The polymers are found to be soluble in liquid electrolytes, a challenge addressed through thin separator coatings, which provide effective immobilization.

When implemented as cathode components in Li–S cells, these separator-coated polymer systems ($1.1\text{--}1.3\text{ mg cm}^{-2}$) exhibit an initial discharge capacity of $\sim 750\text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ at 0.1C and show promising cycling stability. Electrochemical behavior characterized by cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic cycling reveals stable sulfur redox kinetics, attributable to the chemically active backbone.

To further probe redox side reactions, potentiostatic shuttle current measurements were performed by holding the cell at 2.28 V. Unlike classical polysulfide shuttling, where the current stabilizes over time, we observed a steadily increasing positive current, indicating a previously unreported side reaction associated with the polymer. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) revealed dynamic resistance changes across states of charge, further supporting the presence of complex redox or interfacial behavior.

Overall, this work introduces acetone-derived sulfur–carbonyl polymers that can participate in redox activity. Their low-cost synthesis, processability, and electrochemical performance position them as promising candidates for future multifunctional cathode designs in Li–S battery technologies.

This research was supported by Yildiz Technical University (FBA-2024-6061).

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Keyword: sulfur, polymer, lithium-sulfur battery, energy storage

Enhancing the Stability of Carbon-Based Gas Diffusion Electrodes in Metal-Air Batteries via Chemical Vapor Deposition

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Recently, metal-air batteries (MABs) have attracted considerable interest due to high theoretical energy densities ($763\text{--}3458\text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$) in a wide range of applications, such as electric vehicles and stationary power plants [1]. To achieve this high theoretical energy density, it is critical to improve the stability and electrocatalytic activity of gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) used in MABs. The performance of GDEs is dependent on the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) that occur during charging and discharging, respectively. Carbon-based materials are commonly used in GDEs to enhance electrocatalytic activity due to their advantages, such as high electrical conductivity, lightness, affordability, and abundance [2]. However, when alkaline liquid electrolytes, which are widely preferred in MABs due to their high ionic conductivity, come into contact with carbon at high potentials, issues such as corrosion during the OER and structural degradation during long charge–discharge cycles arise. These problems threaten the stability of GDEs [3]. To draw on the advantages of carbon while maintaining stability, studies in the literature aim to modify the structure of carbon materials to preserve stability [2,4]. The original aspect of this study is the synthesis of thin polymer films at the electrolyte-catalyst interface with nanometric thicknesses that do not create high resistance but provide GDE stability. Polymers can be directly coated onto the catalyst surface without the use of solvents via Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD). This eliminates the negative effects that solvents could have on the catalyst. In this study, cross-linked ultra-thin copolymers containing functional groups such as epoxy and hydroxyl were synthesized via CVD to preserve GDE stability.

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Keyword: *Gas Diffusion Electrode (GDE), Carbon materials, Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)*

BiSn Core-Shell Particles as Novel Photothermal Agents for Efficient Solar Water Evaporation

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Solar evaporation offers a promising pathway, wherein sunlight is converted into thermal energy to facilitate water evaporation using photothermal materials. In this study, Bismuth–Tin (BiSn) core–shell particles—derived from liquid metals—were introduced as a novel solar absorber. These particles exhibit newly discovered photothermal properties¹, combining broadband solar absorption with efficient heat conversion, enabled by their thermally conductive metallic core, a defect-rich oxide shell, and the core-shell structure.

BiSn particles were embedded into cellulose-based substrates to fabricate solar absorber layers, ensuring both water transport and long-term evaporation stability. The performance was evaluated under varying environmental conditions, with rates reaching up to 1.5 kg/m²-h, approaching the theoretical upper limit for 2D absorber designs. Compared to uncontrolled evaporation in ambient conditions, this system boosted the evaporation rate by 3.3 times.

A comprehensive evaluation was conducted on system reusability across 15 cycles, the impact of particle size on performance, and applicability in saltwater. Beyond thermal performance, the study highlights the oxide surface's ability to facilitate intermediate water formation—contributing to reduced vaporization enthalpy—and the antifouling behavior and functionalizability of the BiSn particle's surface. Moreover, Bi and Sn are abundant and the synthesis conditions of BiSn particles are versatile². Considering the global scale of the water scarcity problem, these particles place themselves as a strong candidate to be used in real-life applications.

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Keyword: *Solar evaporation, photothermal materials, BiSn core-shell particles, broadband light absorption*

Next-Generation Polymer Gel Electrolytes for Flexible Energy Storage: Design, Characterization, and Application in EDLCs

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This study focuses on the development of next-generation polymer gel electrolytes that feature flexible structures, high ionic conductivity, and strong electrochemical stability, aiming to advance energy storage systems. Crosslinked hydrogels were synthesized via redox-initiated polymerization of acrylamide (AAm) and N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAAm) using a Ce(IV)/mercaptosuccinic acid initiator [1–2]. The resulting hydrogels were modified with varying amounts of poly(vinylsulfonic acid sodium salt) (PVSANa) and different concentrations of the surfactant Tricaprylmethylammonium Chloride (Aliquat 336), along with nano-sized additives to enhance ion transport and structural uniformity, forming semi-interpenetrating polymer networks (semi-IPNs) [3–4].

The hydrogels obtained were systematically characterized in terms of ionic conductivity, mechanical flexibility, and supercapacitor performance. Characterizations were carried out using symmetric EDLC (electrochemical double-layer capacitor) devices with graphite electrodes, following the methodologies described by Wang et al. [5].

In this study, for the first time, these innovative modified hydrogels demonstrate great potential as flexible solid-state electrolytes for supercapacitors and batteries, due to their enhanced capacitance and mechanical compatibility. They hold promise for flexible energy storage materials and electronic applications.

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Keyword: Energy storage materials, Flexible polymer gel electrolytes, Poly(vinylsulfonic acid sodium salt), Aliquat 336

Enhanced Phosphate Removal Using Zr-UiO-66 Nanoparticles Prepared by Microfluidic Synthesis over a Macro-Static Approach

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Increase in phosphate concentration of both underground and surface waters due to uncontrolled domestic wastewater and agricultural practices is detrimental for plant and animal life [1]. Some materials have previously been used to adsorb phosphorus from water. Mei et al. [2] have tested sand, iron powder, and aluminum powder and obtained the highest adsorption rate for sand with 2.9163 mg/g. He et al. [3] studied zeolites for phosphate removal and showed a significantly enhanced adsorption capacity of 17.2 mg/g for lanthanum-incorporated porous zeolite. Metal organic framework (MOF) structures, created from inorganic ions with organic connectors, have emerged as a class of materials with adaptable structure, flexible functionality, variable composition, and high porosity [4]. This study investigates the potential of zirconium (Zr)-based UiO-66 MOF nanoparticles for phosphate removal from water. Zr-UiO-66 nanoparticles that are synthesized via the solvothermal method utilizing droplet-based microfluidics and the conventional macro-static route, are comparatively analyzed. Particles produced using the same precursor solution recipe via micro-fluidic and macro-static methods are evaluated for their adsorption capacity. The research simulates removal of phosphate from polluted water by adding MOF nanoparticles to solutions with known phosphate concentrations. Adsorption kinetics and capacity are determined by monitoring the phosphate concentration change over time. Adsorption kinetics followed a pseudo-second-order model and the Freundlich isotherm provided a better fit to the equilibrium data. Thermodynamic analysis indicated a spontaneous physisorption process. Comparative adsorption studies showed that Zr-UiO-66 nanoparticles synthesized via the microfluidic route demonstrated slightly enhanced phosphate removal efficiency. This is attributed to the XRD and SEM characterization results revealing that micro-fluidically synthesized Zr-UiO-66 nanoparticles exhibited smaller crystallites and higher crystallinity compared to those from the macro-static route. This work highlights the potential of microfluidic synthesis for producing MOF nanoparticles with improved properties for environmental applications. This study is supported by TUBITAK through 1001 project (220M002) and BİDEB2209-A project (1919B012310536), and Hacettepe University BAP project (FHD-2024-20812).

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Keyword: Phosphate removal, Metal-organic framework (MOF), Droplet-based microfluidics, Zr-UiO-66

Multilayer Coating Architecture on Transparent PMMA Substrates with Integrated ESD Protection and Optical Transmittance

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Transparent polymer materials such as polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) are widely used in aerospace transparencies due to their lightweight nature and high optical properties. However, to meet the challenging demands of modern platforms (particularly regarding electromagnetic, electrostatic, optic, mechanic and environmental) these substrates often require the application of multifunctional and multilayer coatings. Previous studies have examined electrical or optical coatings separately, while limited attention has been given to their combined behavior in multilayer systems.

In this study, a multilayer coating system, consisting of transparent conductive oxide (ZTO/Ag/ZTO) thin film and waterborne polyurethane coating doped with indium tin oxide (ITO) nanoparticles, was developed and applied onto PMMA substrates via magnetron sputtering and flow coating, respectively. The effect of nanoparticle concentration and coating thickness on the optical and ESD properties of the multilayer system was systematically investigated. While the thin film stack primarily serves for electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding and low radar observability, the polyurethane topcoat enhances surface durability against abrasion and environmental conditions. This multilayer configuration achieves high optical clarity while meeting functional requirements for electrostatic discharge (ESD) protection and environmental resistance in aerospace transparencies.

Our results demonstrate that while increased ITO content enhances ESD properties, it also affects optical transmittance and haze. Similarly, the thickness of the topcoat has a significant effect on light transmission and haze, as well as on the coating's electrical breakdown voltage. These findings indicate the need to carefully balance and optimize both the nanoparticle concentration and coating thickness to meet the specific demands of the application, ensuring an effective compromise between optical clarity and electrical protection.

This study offers experimental findings about the design trade-offs between optical properties and ESD performance in aerospace transparency systems.

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Keyword: *transparent, canopy, electrostatic discharge, multilayer coating*

First-Principles Investigation of PEAI Salt-Induced Surface Passivation in FAPbI₃ Perovskites for Solar Cell Applications

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Perovskite materials have attracted significant attention in photovoltaic technologies due to their low-cost fabrication techniques and outstanding optoelectronic properties. However, their performance and stability are often limited by surface defects and environmental factors. Phenylethyl ammonium iodide (PEAI) salts have been shown to effectively passivate surface defects in perovskite layers. Additionally, the hydrophobic organic units in PEAIs enhance the material's resistance to oxygen and moisture, contributing to improved environmental stability.

In this study, we perform first-principles calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) to investigate the role of PEAIs containing different functional groups: Set 1, Set 2, Set 3, and Set 4 in surface passivation of formamidinium lead iodide (FAPbI₃) perovskites. The total energy calculations were carried out within a plane-wave, density functional theory (DFT) framework using Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package (VASP). All the first-principles calculations, the structural, electronic, and adsorption properties of perovskite systems are obtained using generalized gradient approximation (GGA) and Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) for the exchange-correlation potential. The calculated binding energies and partial (Bader) charges for different PEAIs orientations adsorbed on FAPbI₃ surfaces revealed orientation- and defect-dependent trends. The binding energies were calculated as approximately -5 eV and -4 eV for pristine and defected perovskite systems, respectively. In general, the calculated binding energies are quite high, indicating that the salts exhibit strong interactions with the perovskite surface. The results of the partial charge analysis indicate that a significant charge transfer occurs upon the binding of the salts to the perovskite surface. Significant charge redistribution occurred on iodide (I) and lead (Pb) atoms, with an average gain of ~-5.5 eV upon iodide binding. This suggests that the iodides strongly interact with the salts and contribute to the stabilization of the surface. Overall, our findings demonstrate the critical role of PEAIs-induced surface passivation in enhancing the stability and performance of FAPbI₃-based perovskite solar cells and offer valuable insights for the design of future high-efficiency photovoltaic devices. Our results demonstrate that PEAIs effectively reduces surface trap states by passivating undercoordinated Pb and I atoms, thereby suppressing non-radiative recombination pathways. Moreover, the hydrophobic phenylethyl group further improves environmental resilience by limiting moisture ingress. These findings offer atomistic insights into defect passivation mechanisms and highlight the potential of PEAIs surface engineering to enhance the efficiency and long-term stability of perovskite solar cells.

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Keyword: Perovskite, DFT, first-principles, solar cells

Strain Effects on Perovskite CsSiF₃ Solar Cell

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Addressing this increasing need sustainably necessitates a shift toward renewable energy sources. Over the past decade, halide perovskites have garnered significant interest in the field of photovoltaics due to their adjustable bandgap, strong light-harvesting ability, high charge carrier mobility, low recombination losses, and the advantage of low-cost solution-based fabrication. By refining the perovskite composition, controlling crystal nucleation and growth processes, and optimizing the solar cell's layered architecture, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) has improved dramatically. Strain engineering, widely recognized in semiconductor physics, offers a powerful means of tuning optoelectronic characteristics. However, the influence of strain on halide perovskites, especially regarding their photovoltaic potential, remains a subject of ongoing research. In this context, we performed first-principles calculations to examine how strain, ranging from -5% (compressive) to +5% (tensile), affects the structural, electronic, elastic, and optical behavior of CsSiF₃. Our results confirm that CsSiF₃ is both thermodynamically and mechanically stable across this strain range, as evidenced by negative formation enthalpy values extending up to +5% strain. This study introduces CsSiF₃ as a novel, silicon-based halide perovskite absorber and evaluates its application in a solar cell structure consisting of FTO/ Cd_{0.5}Zn_{0.5}S / CsSiF₃ / MoO₃ / Au. Using SCAPS-1D simulations, we conducted a detailed performance analysis of the absorber along with its electron transport layer (ETL) and hole transport layer (HTL). The ETL and HTL materials are critical in charge extraction and minimizing recombination losses. Band structure calculations reveal that CsSiF₃ possesses a direct bandgap of approximately 1.244 eV, which is ideal for efficient solar energy absorption. The total density of states (TDOS) and charge density difference maps highlight the pivotal role of silicon atoms in facilitating charge distribution and light interaction within the material. Our simulations indicate that the application of +4% tensile strain yields the most favorable performance, resulting in a power conversion efficiency of 27.23%, an open-circuit voltage (Voc) of 0.778 V, a short-circuit current density (Jsc) of 41.19 mA/cm², and a fill factor (FF) of 84.85%. These results demonstrate that tensile strain significantly enhances the photovoltaic properties of CsSiF₃, positioning it as a strong candidate for future lead-free perovskite solar cell technologies.

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Keyword: DFT, SCAPS-1D, solar cells, perovskite

Investigation of the Interlayer and Doping Role of Graphene in Cu_2SnS_3 Based Thin Films

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The increasing global population leads to rising energy consumption, creating a pressing need for alternative and sustainable energy sources. In this context, thin film based solar absorber materials have garnered significant attention due to their environmental benefits and energy conversion potential. Among them, particularly Cu_2SnS_3 (CTS), have emerged as promising candidates owing to their non-toxicity, abundance, ease of synthesis, and cost-effectiveness. Furthermore, CTS exhibits p-type semiconducting behavior with high absorption coefficients ($>10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), making it suitable for photovoltaic applications[1]. However, despite various optimization efforts, achieving the desired efficiency in CTS-based absorber layers remains challenging[2]. Recent studies suggest that incorporating graphene-based materials can enhance the performance of absorber layers by improving charge transport and reducing interface defects[3,4].

In this study, the effects of integrating a single-layer graphene (grown by chemical vapor deposition) as an interlayer, along with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) doping, on the structural, optical, electrical, and morphological properties of CTS thin films were investigated. CTS films were deposited on graphene-coated glass substrates via spin coating and subsequently sulfurized at 500°C for 5 minutes. rGO was added at concentrations of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2% to evaluate its effect on film properties. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) confirmed a Cu-poor composition in all samples. XRD and Raman analyses showed that the CTS films crystallized in a monoclinic phase, with reduced secondary phases (e.g., Sn_2S_3 , Cu_2S) observed in graphene-integrated samples. The incorporation of graphene and rGO significantly enhanced crystallinity and grain growth, as confirmed by SEM. Ellipsometric measurements revealed improved optical properties in samples containing graphene, while Hall effect analysis indicated enhanced electrical conductivity with rGO doping, attributed to its high carrier mobility. The graphene interlayer also contributed to a smoother film surface and more uniform grain distribution. In conclusion, the integration of graphene as an interlayer and the controlled addition of rGO effectively improved the structural, electrical, and optical performance of CTS thin films. These enhancements suggest that graphene-assisted CTS structures hold strong potential as absorber layers for next-generation solar cell applications.

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Keyword: *Cu_2SnS_3 Thin film, Spin Coating, Single layer-graphene, rGO doped-CTS*

A Hybrid Approach to Scalable Perovskite Solar Cells: Combining Evaporation and Slot-Die Coating for Efficient Large-Area Devices

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The development of scalable and reproducible fabrication methods is essential for the commercialization of perovskite solar cells (PSCs). In this work, we demonstrate a hybrid deposition strategy combining thermal evaporation of inorganic precursors with slot-die coating of organic components to fabricate PSCs in an inverted architecture. This approach enables material-efficient and scalable film formation while maintaining decent device performance without relying on spin-coating. Devices with active areas ranging from 0.25 to 1 cm² exhibited power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) up to 18.4%, with open-circuit voltages exceeding 1.08 V and short-circuit currents above 21 mA/cm². While performance variation is observed across larger areas, this method offers a promising pathway for the industrial-scale production of PSCs aimed at indoor energy harvesting and building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) applications.

Keyword: *Perovskites, Slot-die coating, Hybrid Evaporation-Solution Method*

Fabrication and Characterization of Photodetectors Based on P3HT:Perylenediimide:PCBM Active Layer

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Due to their lightweight nature, low production costs, and ease of integration with flexible substrates, organic photodetectors (OPDs) are particularly appealing for next-generation optoelectronic applications [1]. Binary bulk heterojunction (b-BHJ) structures are commonly utilized in organic optoelectronic devices, including organic photovoltaics (OPVs) and OPDs. However, the limited spectral response of these structures results in only partial absorption of the incoming spectrum by the active layer, thereby constraining overall device performance [2]. Consequently, b-BHJ architectures face challenges in meeting the demands for high-efficiency OPVs and broadband OPDs. Extending the spectral response of the active layer remains a crucial challenge in advancing organic optoelectronic technologies [3].

In this study, we investigated the impact of incorporating a synthesized perylenediimide derivative into a commercial blend of P3HT and PCBM, resulting in a ternary bulk heterojunction (t-BHJ) active layer. The combination of P3HT, the perylene derivative, and PCBM was designed to leverage the strong hole and electron transport properties of the commercial materials while expanding the spectral range with the perylene derivative, thus achieving a broadband response and benefiting from its high absorption coefficient in the visible region [4]. The OPD was fabricated using a conventional ITO/PEDOT:PSS/Active Layer/Al device structure with 7 mm² active area, and device characteristic measurements were done in an inert atmosphere under illumination from a solar simulator with 25 mW/cm² optical power. For the 1:0.25:0.5 weight ratio combination of P3HT:Perylene:PCBM, the average performance of three OPDs fabricated on the same substrate, measured under -1 V bias using a source measurement unit (SMU), resulted in a photocurrent density of approximately 5 mA/cm² and a dark current density of 0.25 mA/cm². In comparison, the reference device with a 1:0.5 P3HT:PCBM binary blend had ~4.5 mA/cm² and ~0.7 mA/cm² photocurrent and dark current density with respectively. The introduction of the perylene derivative into the active layer led to a ~18% increase in Responsivity and ~93% improvement in Detectivity relative to the reference device.

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Keyword: Organic Photodetectors (OPDs), Ternary Bulk Heterojunction (t-BHJ), Perylenediimide Derivative, Visible Light Detection

TADF OLEDs from Phenoxazine, Phenothiazine, and Phenoselenium-Based Small Molecules

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Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) are solid-state devices with lots of advantages, such as low power consumption, wide viewing angles, fast response times, and high brightness values¹. With thermally activated delayed fluorescent (TADF) OLEDs, theoretically, 100% external quantum efficiency and 100% exciton utilization efficiency can be obtained by an eco-friendly method without heavy-metal atoms². In this study, small molecules based on phenoxazine, phenothiazine, and phenoselenium were synthesized, and they were used as emitter materials in thermally activated delayed fluorescent organic light-emitting diodes (TADF OLEDs). These units were used as donor units, while the triazine unit was used as an acceptor in small molecules³. The aim of the study is to investigate the effect of different heteroatoms on the donor unit by the substitution of O, S, and Se atoms on it. Synthesized TADF emitters were characterized optically by using photoluminescence spectroscopy and UV-Vis spectroscopy. The cyclic voltammetry technique was used to get information about the electrochemical properties of TADF emitters. To investigate the OLED device performances of TADF emitters, OLED devices of these molecules were fabricated, and performance parameters such as the luminance, turn-on voltage, current efficiency, and CIE_{x,y} color coordinates were determined. In OLED devices of these emitters, mCP was used as a host material, and light-emitting small molecules were doped into the mCP layer by the co-evaporation process. The best device had a light-emitting layer with the phenoxazine-moiety, whose device performance was superior with a maximum luminance of 15088 cd/m², CIE_{x,y} color coordinates of (0.49,0.46), a maximum current density of 78.8 cd/A, and a turn-on voltage of 5.2 V.

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Keyword: OLED, TADF, phenothiazine, solid-state

Conducting Polymer/ Holey Super Graphene Nanocomposite as Next-Generation Material for Electrochromic Device Application

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In recent years, the field of conducting polymer-based nanocomposite materials has witnessed significant and exciting advancements. Among these, the design of conducting polymer/holey graphene (CP/HG) nanocomposites stands at the forefront of cutting-edge materials science. The combination of conducting polymers (CPs) with holey graphene (HG) has emerged as a powerful strategy for creating materials with enhanced properties [1]. The synergistic interactions between HG and CPs impart unique structural and functional characteristics to the resulting composites, making them highly attractive as electrode materials for electrochromic devices (ECDs).

In this study, we present the synthesis and comprehensive characterization of a novel holey super graphene (HSG)/CP nanocomposite designed for application in electrochromic devices. One of the key components of the composite is synthesized 2,5-di(2-thienyl)pyrrole derivative monomer (coded as Star-DTP), which features a three-dimensional star-shaped molecular architecture [2]. The molecular structure of the monomer was confirmed through spectroscopic techniques, including ¹H and ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), and UV-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy. The optical and electrical properties of the HSG-based nanocomposite films were evaluated and compared to those of the homopolymer (pStar-DTP). Through these comparative studies, the optimum feed ratio of HSG in the composite was determined. The structural and morphological characterizations of the nanocomposite synthesized at this optimal ratio were carried out using FT-IR and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The device demonstrated good electrochromic behavior, suggesting the strong potential of these materials in next-generation applications such as smart windows.

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Keyword: *conducting polymer, holey super graphene, nanocomposite, electrochromic device*

Synthesis and Optoelectronic Characterizations of Rare-Earth-Metal Complexes for White Organic Light Emitting Diode Applications

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Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) have revolutionized display and lighting technologies, offering remarkable flexibility and vibrant emission properties. Among them, white OLEDs (WOLEDs) are particularly significant because of their essential role in solid-state lighting and modern display systems. In recent years, a major focus of research has been the development of single-molecule emissive layers, which simplify fabrication and reduce production costs. In this study, six novel rare-earth complexes containing terbium (Tb) and europium (Eu) were synthesized as potential WOLED emitters. These complexes exhibit multicomponent emission arising from both the organic ligands and the metal centers. Their structures were confirmed using infrared (IR) spectroscopy and further supported by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Optical band gaps and highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energy levels were determined through UV-Vis absorption and cyclic voltammetry, yielding consistent values of roughly 3.10 eV for the band gap, -5.95 eV for the HOMO, and -2.85 eV for the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). Thermal stability was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Among the optoelectronic characterizations, a WOLED was fabricated with the ITO/HAT CN/TAPC/EML/TPBi/LiF/Al device architecture, in which the Tb-(L2)3 complex served as the emissive layer. The device demonstrated a low turn-on voltage of 2.94 V, a high maximum luminance of 12,159 cd·m⁻², and an external quantum efficiency (EQE) of 0.65%. To further characterize the synthesized rare-earth-metal complexes, host-guest type active layer coating strategy will be applied with the same device architecture.

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Keyword: Rare-earth-metal complex, multicomponent emission, WOLED, single-molecule emissive layer

In vitro Biocompatibility Investigation of Femtosecond Laser Surface Modified - High Entropy TiTaHfNbZr Alloy for Orthopedic Applications

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For biomedical alloys used as orthopedic implant materials, osseointegration; which can be defined as the structural bonding of the implant material with the surrounding bone tissue, is a crucial property for the success of the implant. In order to achieve better osseointegration, novel biomedical alloys as well as new surface treatment methods are being developed. Among the novel alloys, TiTaHfNbZr; which belongs to the class of high entropy alloys with superior mechanical properties is biomedically promising as well since its elemental content is biocompatible. In terms of the novel surface modification methods applied to biomedical alloys, femtosecond laser surface treatment stands out as an effective method for enabling controllable patterns of homogeneous topography, while not causing problems such as melting and phase transformation due to their short-term interaction with the material. Moreover, in the literature there aren't any studies focusing on the utility of high entropy alloys for biomedical applications, through modifying their surface with laser processing methods. With this motivation, the current study aims to investigate the utility of TiTaHfNbZr, an already promising biomedical alloy, as a novel orthopedic implant material with improved osseointegration and biocompatibility through controlled surface modification with femtosecond laser. For this purpose, the surface of the novel TiTaHfNbZr alloy was processed with a femtosecond laser in order to obtain surfaces with different topographic properties. Following the thorough characterization of the topography and properties of the newly formed surfaces, their biocompatibilities were analyzed via in vitro experiments, which put forward the importance of the micro and nano surface topography characteristics on cellular response. Overall, the findings of this study are expected to contribute to the development of novel biomedical alloys with improved surface properties for better osseointegration.

Keyword: *osseointegration, laser surface processing, high entropy alloy, biomedical alloys for implants*

Hydrophilic Sol-Gel TiO₂ Coating on Procaine-Loaded Injector Needle for Painless Clinical Treatments

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Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) coatings have been interested in biomedical science, since they have attracting properties like biocompatibility, porosity, and semiconducting feature. Since the pores on the surface of TiO₂ allow to capture of the drug solution, drug release can be controlled safely. Therefore, more voids and more hydrophilic surfaces are required to take more drug solutions. One way to attain hydrophilicity is to illuminate surfaces that of been coated by ultraviolet (UV) light and create electron (e⁻) - hole (h⁺) pairs. In the controlled drug release studies, TiO₂ coatings can offer demandable solutions for painless injection for those who have to take medicine through the injection frequently. In this study, TiO₂ was prepared via the sol-gel method with Titanium tetra isopropoxide (TTIP) precursor in alcohol solvent for pH 3, 4, and 5 values. The prepared solution was dip coated on 316 L stainless steel substrates and injectors. Following these steps, samples were calcinated at various temperatures (100°C, 300°C, 500°C, 700°C) to complete fabrication. The structural, physical, and chemical composition, wettability, and drug-release properties of TiO₂-coated samples were evaluated. Contact angle values affirmed that high calcination temperatures and ultraviolet (UV)-light irradiation improved the hydrophilicity of the samples (qqv. 26°±5° at 700°C for pH 4). Procaine, a short-time period ester type local anaesthetic, was chosen as a model drug. Increased calcination temperature and hydrophilicity enhanced the released drug amount due to nanopore formation. Drug release studies were carried out using Franz diffusion cells at 36.5°C to mimic human body. The highest amount of drug (90 %) for 45 sec injection time was observed in samples at 500°C calcinated. This study shed light on how TiO₂ coating can be successfully utilized for clinical applications in the future.

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Keyword: Drug release, Hydrophilic surface, Painless treatment, Sol-gel method

Enhancing Dental Implant Osseointegration and Stability with Bioactive Injectable Nanofiber Interfaces

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Achieving rapid and stable osseointegration remains a critical challenge in dental implantology, particularly in compromised bone conditions. Conventional surface coatings are prone to delamination during implantation, generating debris and compromising long-term outcomes. We developed a **needle-injectable, multifunctional peptide amphiphile (PA) nanofiber interface** to address these limitations. This interface, injected into the osteotomy site prior to implant placement, rapidly fills micro- and nanogaps and forms a bioactive extracellular matrix-mimetic environment. The PA formulation integrates DGEA-PA (osteogenesis), Dopa-PA (adhesion and mineralization), GL13K-PA (antimicrobial), and EEE-PA (mineralization). In vitro, **mesenchymal stromal cells** cultured on nanofiber-treated surfaces exhibited upregulated osteogenic markers (RUNX2, osteopontin, osteocalcin) and enhanced mineralization. In a **rabbit femoral defect model**, nanofiber-applied implants achieved **58.7% bone-to-implant contact** and **51.8% bone volume-to-total volume** at 6 weeks, significantly outperforming SLA-treated controls. Biomechanical testing revealed superior stability (reverse torque resistance of 19.1 N·cm). Moreover, GL13K-PA reduced bacterial adhesion, offering protection against peri-implant infections. These findings establish the potential of injectable PA nanofibers to enhance implant stability and integration, particularly in patients with compromised bone healing capacity. **Ongoing studies aim to translate this approach to sheep models as a precursor to clinical application.**

Keyword: *Dental implants, osseointegration, peptide nanofibers, bone regeneration*

MXF Encapsulated Liposomes Enriched Alginate Hydrogel Coatings for Drug Delivery by Using Two Different Routes: Micropipetting and TMJ Device Techniques

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Several studies conducted over the last few years have extensively investigated the use of liposomal nanoparticles in drug delivery. Liposomes are tiny vesicular structures typically composed of an aqueous core enclosed by one or more concentric phospholipid bilayers. Their size generally ranges from approximately 10 nm to 1 µm, depending on the preparation method and formulation parameters. Due to their unique characteristics, they are capable of encapsulating both hydrophilic and hydrophobic therapeutic agents[1]. Liposomal encapsulation of drug molecules offers protection against enzymatic degradation in the physiological environment, leading to improved systemic stability. Although liposomes are successful in delivering drugs to targeted sites, their limited stability can hinder sustained efficacy. A promising approach to overcome this limitation is the use of nanocomposite hydrogel systems, which are obtained by incorporating liposomes into hydrogel matrices. These composite systems have been shown to prolong drug release compared to either component alone. Additionally, they enhance liposome stability and extend the half-life of drug while maintaining its bioactivity[2].

This study presented to obtain moxifloxacin (MXF) encapsulated liposomes enriched alginate nanocomposite hydrogel coatings via two different deposition ways: (1) the micropipetting and (2) the T-shaped microfluidic junction (TMJ) device technique. Initially, MXF and soy lecithin (SL) were sonicated in to different ratios, SL:MXF:1:1 and SL:MXF:2:1, using probe sonicator to form MXF-encapsulated liposomes. Then, resultant samples were freeze-dried using a lyophilizer for 24 hours and characterization was performed to determine their structural, morphological and MXF release behaviour. To form coating solution, the liposomes achieved were then mixed with an alginate polymer solution. Subsequently, the coating solution prepared was applied to the polymeric substrate using two different methods: micropipetting and TMJ device techniques.

Structural and physical characterizations were performed on the synthesized MXF-encapsulated liposome-enriched alginate nanocomposite hydrogel coatings. Drug release performance from the nanocomposite hydrogels was evaluated by varying processing parameters such as hydrogel production method, polymer solution and crosslinker solution concentrations, coating substrate. The results demonstrate that the hydrogel produced by the TMJ method provides better prolonged and controlled drug release. Thus, MXF-encapsulated liposome-enriched alginate nanocomposite hydrogel structures produced via the TMJ device technique have demonstrated strong potential for use in antimicrobial treatment after cataract surgery. In addition, the potential applicability of the formulation in biomedical and ocular drug delivery systems can be evaluated.

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Keyword: liposome, T-shaped microfluidic junction device, hydrogels, controlled drug delivery

Optoelectronic Response of PAAm/GO Composite Hydrogels in Black Sea Seawater and Their Potential for Infrared Signature Reducer Marine Coatings

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This study analyzes the physical and optoelectronic behavior of PAAm(Polyacrylamide)-GO (Graphene oxide) -based gels containing different ratios of GO in Black Sea seawater. The materials were prepared with GO contents of 107 µl, 143 µl, 200 µl, and 250 µl evaluated in three different states: pre-diffusion, post-diffusion, and post-release. Thanks to the pyranine additive, the dispersion of the gels in seawater was measured under visible light and infrared region using UV/VIS spectroscopy and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, and the absorbances and real dielectric constants in the visible region and infrared region were calculated from raw data. In the analysis performed using the absorbance data, the effect of high GO content on light absorption and optical transmittance was investigated. The results obtained demonstrate the potential use of these composite gels in military ship coatings in terms of infrared visibility in marine environments. In this context, PAAm/GO gels have been discussed for use in IR-absorbing marine coatings due to their functional optical behavior.

Keyword: *PAAm/GO hydrogel; GO nanocomposite; UV-vis spectroscopy; Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy; real dielectric constant; infrared signature; marine coatings; Black Sea seawater*

Advances in 3D Printing by Two-Photon Polymerization

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Two-photon polymerization (2PP) can be used to directly print complex micro- and mesoscale 3D structures with sub-micrometer features. These structures can be transparent and have either optically smooth or deliberately structured surfaces. After a brief introduction to this key enabling technology, I will present our recent developments in additive manufacturing with examples from application areas such as micro-optics, photonic integrated circuit packaging and life sciences.

In recent years, we have made significant advancements in 2PP, including Two-Photon Grayscale Lithography (2GL) [1], 3D printing by 2GL [2] and Aligned 2-Photon Lithography (A2PL) [3].

2GL overcomes the fundamental trade-off in 3D printing, between printing speed and surface quality, by dynamically modulating the laser power, and thus, the size of the exposed volume pixel or "voxel". This capability has been applied to the creation of optically smooth surfaces for 2.5D structures and master molds. We recently introduced 3D printing by 2GL, which enables the fabrication of truly 3D structures with optical-quality surfaces for micro-optics applications.

With A2PL, it is possible to print 3D micro-optical components onto pre-structured surfaces, such as within microfluidic channels or on photonic integrated circuits and fibers. The components are printed with sub-micron positioning accuracy.

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Keyword: 3D printing, Polymer, Micro-optics, Photonics

Production and Performance Evaluation of Magnetorheological Grease With Iron Oxide–Aluminum Oxide

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PETROL OFİSİ A.Ş.

Magnetorheological (MR) materials are a class of smart materials that have rheological properties that can be reversibly and rapidly controlled by external magnetic field applications (i.e. under a magnetic field). Area of use; The area of use of MR fluids has generally been on vibration dampers, shock absorbers, clutches, brakes and engine bearings. Etc.

The study of rheological properties such as shear and yield stress of MR fluids has become an important design factor in the applications of MR fluids. Temperature is a parameter that affects the rheological properties of MR grease materials. (It affects apparent viscosity and yield stress.)

To improve wear resistance, load carrying capacity and rheological properties of magnetorheological greases we have been investigated the effect of iron oxide and aluminum oxied nanoparticles.

Penetration, Four Ball Wear Scar, Four Ball Weld Load, Droppin point, Water Spray, Water Washout and rheometer analyzes were made.

Keyword: *Grease, Nanoparticles, Magnetorheological*

Innovative Industrial Applications of Eco-Friendly Nanomaterials for Carbon Capture and Water Purification

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Nanografi offers sustainable industrial solutions through advanced nanomaterials developed with a focus on environmentally friendly technologies. Its product portfolio includes graphene, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), quantum dots, and functional metal oxide nanoparticles. These materials deliver high performance in the fields of energy, environment, and defense industries. Their exceptional properties—such as high surface area, electrical conductivity, and chemical durability—enhance efficiency in a wide range of applications.

As a result of our advanced technologies and collaborations with academicians and institutions, Nanografi launched the **GreenGraphene** project, focusing on the environmentally friendly production of graphene.

The **GreenGraphene** project is an initiative supported by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 program and has been recognized with a prestigious award. Developed with a vision of environmental sustainability, GreenGraphene is a special graphene series produced using eco-friendly methods. With its low carbon footprint, GreenGraphene offers effective solutions in **carbon capture, water purification, energy storage systems, and environmental remediation technologies**. With these properties, GreenGraphene not only enhances environmentally conscious performance in industrial applications but also contributes to the green transition.

Keyword: *water purification, carbon capture, graphene, energy*

A Simple-by-Design Approach for Vesicle-to-Cubosome Transformation Using Omega-3 PUFA Monoacylglycerols

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In addition to liposomes, micelles, and solid lipid nanoparticles, there is a growing interest in the development of drug nanocarriers based on lyotropic non-lamellar liquid crystalline (LLC) nanoparticles (including cubosomes and hexosomes)[1]. These nanoparticles with unique internal architectural repertoires are attractive for encapsulating hydrophilic, amphiphilic, and poorly water-soluble drugs. In this contribution, we aim at introducing structurally tunable and pH-sensitive nano-self-assemblies (including cubosomes, Figure 1) from binary mixtures of phosphatidylglycerol (DOPG) and docosahexaenoic acid (MAG-DHA). The latter is a new amphiphilic and biocompatible lipid with health-promoting effects and potential therapeutic uses in various disorders (including cancer and cardiovascular diseases). It tends to display an inverse hexagonal (H_2) phase on exposure to excess water.

Here, we show that its partial replacement with DOPG can be utilized to produce stabilizer-free and apolar solvent modifier-free liquid crystalline nano-self-assemblies. We also report on the biophysical characterization of these nanoparticles through use of nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA), synchrotron small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), and cryo-transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM). In addition to the pH-responsivity, we describe the structural transformations and alterations in size and morphological features of DOPG/MAG-DHA nano-self-assemblies on varying lipid composition and increasing temperature.

Considering the health-promoting effects of MAG-DHA and its potential therapeutic uses in various disorders, DOPG/MAG-DHA lamellar and non-lamellar liquid crystalline nanoparticles are attractive for use in the development of multifunctional nanocarriers for combinatorial delivery of drugs (or nucleic acids) and DHA.

Figure 1. Cryo-TEM micrograph of DOPG/MAG-DHA nanodispersion. Cubosomes in coexistence with vesicles are detected.

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Keyword: *Cubosomes, Cryo-TEM, Omega-3 fatty acid monoacylglycerol, SAXS*

Design of Hyaluronic Acid Nanocapsules for pH-Responsive Drug Delivery in Cancer Therapy

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Despite advancements in drug delivery systems, the development of an efficient nanocarrier platform remains a significant challenge, particularly in optimizing controlled release mechanisms and improving therapeutic performance. In this study, hyaluronic acid nanocapsules (HANCs) were synthesized via a polyaddition reaction in an inverse miniemulsion method. The formulation was optimized for the encapsulation of doxorubicin (DOX) through conducting physicochemical and morphological characterizations for various nanocapsule formulations. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) revealed a distinct hollow core-shell capsule morphology of the synthesized nanocapsules. Moreover, a stability study was performed on the selected formulation, which maintained its integrity for over 100 days. Successful DOX encapsulation was achieved, and the drug release behavior was evaluated under pH conditions mimicking tumor (pH 6.5) and physiological (pH 7.4) environments. A markedly higher DOX release was observed at pH 6.5, whereas drug leakage at pH 7.4 was effectively restricted, as intended. Additionally, the cytotoxicity and anticancer activity of both DOX-loaded and drug-free HANCs were assessed using cell viability assays on L929 mouse fibroblast and MCF-7 human breast cancer cell lines. DOX-loaded HANCs induced significantly greater cytotoxic effects in cancer cells compared to healthy cells, with the most pronounced difference observed at 72 hours post-treatment. These findings suggest that the developed HANCs represent a promising pH-responsive drug delivery platform with potential for targeted cancer therapy.

Keyword: *pH-responsive, doxorubicin delivery, hyaluronic acid nanocapsule, anticancer activity*

Development of Antifouling Thin Films for the Prevention of Staphylococcus epidermidis

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Catheters have become one of the most widely used medical devices over the years due to their ease of application in various systems, including the cardiac system, peripheral tissues, and urinary tract. Among the different types, urinary catheters stand out, as they are utilized both preoperatively for the administration of medication and postoperatively for urine drainage. However, these advantages are accompanied by drawbacks such as the development of infections and associated discomfort. One of the main reasons for this is the frequent contact of catheters with bacteria, particularly in the urinary system. The most commonly encountered microorganism in such cases is Staphylococcus epidermidis. S. epidermidis, a Gram-positive bacterium with a prevalence ranging from 0.2% to 4.0%, is particularly challenging to eliminate from the urinary system due to its resistance to both the host immune response and antibiotic treatment. The primary objective of this study was to develop a protective thin film layer on urinary catheter surfaces to prevent S. epidermidis colonization. Within this scope, polyethylene glycol (PEG) was selected as the coating material due to its proven biocompatibility and antifouling properties. The thin film was deposited using the Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (PECVD) technique, which offers several advantages including high deposition efficiency, uniform surface coverage, minimal chemical consumption, compatibility with complex geometries, and contamination-free coatings. In this process, PEG was introduced in vapor form and treated with plasma energy. Upon interaction with ionized plasma particles, the PEG molecules were excited to higher energy states, resulting in the formation of a uniform nanometer-scale thin film on the surfaces. The synthesized thin films were characterized using FTIR and XPS analyses. Subsequent to the coating and characterization process, the antifouling performance of the catheters was evaluated against S. epidermidis. Microbiological analyses demonstrated that PEG-coated surfaces inhibited biofilm development by approximately 90% over a period of 30 days. Furthermore, potential cytotoxic effects of the coatings were assessed using mouse fibroblast cells, yielding a cell viability of 109%, indicating no cytotoxic response. In conclusion, the results confirmed that PEG-based thin film coatings are effective in repelling bacterial colonization and maintaining their protective function for up to 30 days.

Keyword: Thin film, Antifouling, Biofilm Formation, Chemical Vapor Deposition

Thin Film Development for Root Canal Treatment Applications

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The mouth is one of the primary entry points for microorganisms, where they can live and spread to other parts of the body. Teeth, with their nerves and blood supply, provide a favorable environment for bacterial colonization. Over time, if proper precautions are not taken, bacteria can easily adhere to tooth surfaces, leading to plaque formation. Gradually, they invade deeper structures, penetrate the root canals, and cause tooth decay. In terms of treatment, the most effective approach is the removal of the infected tissue. At this point, root canal treatment becomes essential, as it involves removing the living blood and nerve tissues, along with the decayed portions of the tooth, while preserving the healthy parts. The cleaned canals are then filled with adhesives and gutta-percha. In this way, patients can continue using their natural teeth without the need for implants. However, in some cases, bacteria are difficult to eradicate completely and may repopulate any openings they find, leading to secondary infections. Re-infection occurs when the main filling material, gutta-percha, loses its integrity, and the adhesive cements begin to degrade, causing gutta-percha to detach from the tooth structure. The reappearance of infection necessitates a repeat of the root canal treatment. This is often due to the survival of bacteria that are already resistant to most medications and disinfectants. Therefore, the main aim of this study was to develop antibacterial surface coatings for gutta-percha. To achieve this, triclosan (TCS) was selected as the material due to its proven antibacterial and antifungal properties and its widespread use in dental applications. In the study, thin films were synthesized using the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method with pressure range between 100 - 120 mTorr. The vaporized chemicals were applied to ionized gutta-percha surfaces, where film formation occurred. Following polymerization, the films were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. FT-IR analysis confirmed the polymeric structure of the films such as main functional groups of benzene rings were preserved while polymerization took place from -C-Cl, -C-N, -C=N and -OH groups. Bacterial colony analysis demonstrated their antibacterial effectiveness over 15 days. The thin films significantly reduced the number of live bacterial colonies on the gutta-percha surfaces, achieving an inhibition rate of 91.23–99.86% from day 1 to day 15 compared to reference uncoated gutta perchas.

Keyword: *Thin film coating, E. coli, S. epidermidis, Antibacterial surface*

Investigation of Layer-Dependent Adhesion Energy and Surface Uniformity in 2D Perovskite Nanofilms

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Ensuring uniform and continuous coverage of two-dimensional (2D) materials on solid surfaces is essential for their reliable integration into electronic, optoelectronic, and sensing devices. Inhomogeneous coatings can lead to spatial variations in conductivity, charge transport, and interfacial contact, ultimately degrading device performance. While techniques such as the Langmuir–Blodgett (LB) method enable precise nanosheet deposition, the number of coating layers significantly influences surface topography and uniformity. Additionally, the nanoscale adhesion between 2D coatings and external materials is often affected by thickness-related surface properties. However, there is still a lack of systematic experimental studies exploring how the number of 2D layers influences both adhesion behavior and surface uniformity. Although previous studies have primarily focused on graphene [1], and to a lesser extent on other systems such as MXenes [2], no experimental data exist on how adhesion behavior varies with layer number in perovskite-based 2D materials. In this study, $\text{Ca}_2\text{NaNb}_4\text{O}_{13}^-$ perovskite nanosheets were fabricated via chemical exfoliation method using tetrabutylammonium (TBA) and deposited onto Si substrates via the LB method. To reduce organic residues and enhance coating purity, UV irradiation was applied for 24 and 48 hours [3]. Adhesion energies between a bare Si probe and two- and five-layer coatings were measured using atomic force microscopy (AFM)-based force spectroscopy. Analysis of 96 force curves obtained from two samples from each condition showed that both surface roughness and adhesion energy decreased with increasing layer number. After 24 hours of UV treatment, the root mean square roughness and adhesion energy of the five-layer coating decreased by approximately 2-fold and 50-fold, respectively. This pronounced reduction in adhesion energy may indicate more complete removal of residual TBA in the multilayer nanofilms. Ongoing analysis of 48-hour UV-treated samples aims to further clarify the relationship between coating thickness, surface quality, and adhesion behavior.

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Keyword: 2D Materials, Perovskite Nanosheets, Atomic Force Microscopy, Adhesion Energy

Effect Of Counterions On Electric Field Stimuli Response Of Organoboron-Based Polyelectrolytes

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Organoboron-based polymers have attracted significant attention due to electron deficiency of boron created by empty p-atomic orbitals. Additionally, negatively charged organoboron-based polymers provide highly chemically, electrochemically, and thermally stable structures thanks to the electron deficient nature of boron atom. This study introduced dielectric and electrorheological properties of organoboron-based polyelectrolytes to the literature. Nanosized organoboron-based polyelectrolyte systems namely: polymeric lithium tartaric acid borate (Poly-LiTB) and polymeric sodium tartaric acid borate (Poly-NaTB) were synthesized and characterized via ¹H-NMR, ATR-FTIR and SEM-EDX analyses. Electrical conductivity of Poly-LiTB ($\sigma = 1.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) was detected to be higher than Poly-NaTB ($\sigma = 1.6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) that may be attributed to the smaller size and higher ionic mobility of Li^+ counterion. Moreover, effect of counter ions on electric field responses were investigated by comparing dielectric and electrorheological properties of Poly-LiTB and Poly-NaTB dispersions prepared in an insulating silicon oil medium. At 20 wt.% concentration, higher polarizability was calculated for Poly-LiTB/SO ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.6$) than Poly-NaTB/SO ($\Delta\epsilon = 1.35$). In accordance with the electrical conductivity and dielectric results, better ER performance were observed for Poly-LiTB/SO ($\tau_y = 265 \text{ Pa}$, $\text{ER}_{\text{eff}} = 87$, $G' = 80 \text{ kPa}$ at 10 Hz, $\tau_c = 98 \text{ Pa}$ and recovery% = 68 under $E = 2.0 \text{ kV mm}^{-1}$) than Poly-NaTB/SO ($\tau_y = 195 \text{ Pa}$, $\text{ER}_{\text{eff}} = 38$, $G' = 42 \text{ kPa}$ at 10 Hz, $\tau_c = 42 \text{ Pa}$ and recovery% = 67 under $E = 2.0 \text{ kV mm}^{-1}$). The best activity was detected for the organoboron-based polyelectrolyte containing Li^+ counterion due to its smaller ionic radius and higher ionic mobility.

Figure 1. Electrorheological time dependent response of Poly-LiTB/SO and Poly-NaTB/SO dispersions.

Keyword: counterion, polyelectrolyte, dielectric, electrorheology

All-in-One Fiber-Based Thermally Drawn Piezo-Triboelectric Hybrid Nanogenerator for Wearable Energy Harvesting and Real-Time Sensing

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The advancement of self-powered wearable technologies relies mainly on the development of high-performance energy harvesting and sensing systems. Combining piezoelectric and triboelectric mechanisms in a hybrid structure presents a promising approach to enhance the power output of nanogenerators. This work demonstrates a thermally drawn, fiber-based piezoelectric–triboelectric hybrid nanogenerator (PT-HNG) integrated with different graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) ratios for energy harvesting and real-time wearable sensing. At a GNP loading of 5 wt%, the hybrid fiber shows a 114% increase in open-circuit voltage and a 164.9% increase in short-circuit current compared to pristine PVDF fibers without GNPs. This enhancement is attributed to improved dielectric properties and charge transfer efficiency resulting from interfacial polarization between PVDF and GNPs. The device delivers a peak power output of 21 μW at a load resistance of 5 $\text{M}\Omega$, corresponding to a power density of 266.27 mW m^{-2} over a 0.79 cm^2 area. The fabricated fiber sensor retains stable electrical output after 7,500 tapping cycles and demonstrates excellent flexibility for integration into textiles. Additionally, the fiber can detect biomechanical signals during motion, making it particularly suitable for fitness monitoring applications and enabling wireless, battery-free operation.

Keyword: *Wearable Electronics, Hybrid Nanogenerator, Self Powered Sensing, Smart Textiles*

Photoluminescent PVP Nanofibers Filled With Pyrene-Grafted Polypyrrole Nanoparticles

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This study presents the fabrication and characterization of photoluminescent pyrene-grafted polypyrrole (p-PPy)/polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) nanofibers. Polymer nanofibers possess a high surface area, excellent flexibility, and tunable functional properties, making them highly attractive for a broad range of applications. In recent years, they have gained significant attention in fields such as sensors, photonics, optoelectronics, and tissue engineering. Among the various fabrication techniques, electrospinning stands out due to its simplicity, scalability, and ability to produce nanofibers with a high surface area-to-volume ratio. This study focuses on the synthesis of photoluminescent p-PPy nanoparticles and their incorporation into PVP to produce nanofibers by electrospinning. p-PPy nanoparticles were synthesized by surfactant-assisted oxidative polymerization with two different concentrations of pyrene (3 mg and 5 mg). Solutions of 20% (wt.%) of PVP in DMF were prepared, and 3% (wt.% of polymer) pyrene-grafted polypyrrole nanoparticles were added. The solutions prepared were electrospun with a high voltage of 17.5 kV, a tip-to-collector distance of 15 cm, and a flow rate of 0.25 mL/h. SEM images show that the incorporation of p-PPy nanoparticles significantly affected the nanofiber structure and led to a decrease in nanofiber diameter. The average diameters were measured to be 373 nm for unfilled PVP fibers, 176 nm for p-PPy/PVP-filled fibers containing 3 mg pyrene, and 172 nm for p-PPy/PVP-filled samples containing 5 mg pyrene, indicating that the filler content has a direct effect on the fiber thickness. The optical properties were characterized by UV-vis and fluorescence spectroscopy. The absorption spectra showed a peak around 345 nm, and this peak decreased with increasing p-PPy nanoparticle concentration, indicating that nanoparticle incorporation affects the light absorption. In contrast, the fluorescence spectra exhibited emission peaks at 445 nm and additional bands extending into the visible region. Notably, the fluorescence emission intensity increased with higher p-PPy concentrations, and these optical shifts may be important for applications requiring tunable fluorescence response depending on the filler content. The ability to tailor the fluorescence and absorbance of the produced nanofibers by adjusting the p-PPy concentration may be applied in advanced optical devices, sensors, and photonic systems.

Keyword: *Electrospinning, Polypyrrole, Pyrene, Polyvinylpyrrolidone*

High-Performance PSU/h-BN Composite Films for Thermal Management in Electronics

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Modern electronic devices' continuous miniaturization, integration, and performance enhancement have led to a substantial increase in heat generation, making thermal management a crucial design concern. Excessive thermal accumulation can significantly degrade the performance of electronic devices, reduce operational reliability, and cause permanent damage or burnout. In general, the performance of electronic devices drops by 10% with every increase in temperature by 2°C. There is a growing demand for advanced thermal management materials that offer high thermal conductivity, lightweight properties, low fabrication cost, and compatibility with compact architectures of devices. Developing efficient electronic packaging that effectively dissipates heat is essential for maintaining stability, longevity, and optimal performance of the next-generation electronic systems [1, 2]. Polymer-based composites can satisfy all these requirements, especially for military and aerospace applications. These composites have the advantages of both polymers' excellent adhesion, easy processing, and light weight, as well as the selected filler's peculiar characteristics [3]. Strategic design for polymer-based composites includes the polymer matrix, additive, and method choices and considers the polymer-additive interactions [4]. In this study, polysulfone (PSU) was chosen as the polymer matrix due to its excellent thermal stability, mechanical strength, chemical resistance, flame retardancy, and resistance to radiation. As a filler material, hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) offers high intrinsic thermal conductivity (~ 400 W/mK), and a wide bandgap (~ 5.97 eV), making hBN electrically insulative and optically transparent [5]. The PSU-hBN composite films were prepared using the solution mixing method. Three different PSU concentrations (15wt%, 20wt%, 25wt%) and four hBN concentrations (5wt%, 10wt%, 15wt%, 25wt%) were investigated. The dispersion of hBN particles through the PSU matrix is a major point for enhancing thermal conductivity since uniformity leads to less phonon scattering and higher thermal conductivity. In addition, the specific surface area of the hBN particles also notably affects the thermal conductivity of the composite. Without any modification, the 10wt% hBN doped 25wt% PSU film showed the highest thermal conductivity with 0.66 W/mK by 230% enhancement compared to pristine PSU.

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Keyword: *thermal management, high-performance composite, polysulfone (PSU), hexagonal boron nitride (hBN)*

Tuning the Architecture of Electrospun PCL/Chitosan/nHAp Scaffolds for Bone Regeneration: A Design of Experiments Study

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Bone tissue engineering requires scaffolds that not only support cellular infiltration and tissue regeneration but also possess suitable mechanical strength, porosity, and bioactivity. Electrospun nanofibrous mats have shown significant promise in this field due to their structural similarity to the natural extracellular matrix (ECM). This study aims to design and optimize bioactive electrospun scaffolds composed of polycaprolactone (PCL), chitosan (CS), and nano-hydroxyapatite (nHAp), for enhanced bone regeneration. The primary goal was to understand the influence of composition on key scaffold characteristics, particularly fiber morphology, porosity, and potential for cell infiltration, which are critical factors in successful bone regeneration.

To systematically explore the effects of composition on scaffold quality, we employed a Box-Behnken Design (BBD) within the Design of Experiments (DOE) framework. The independent variables selected were the PCL/CS blend ratio, total polymer concentration, and nHAp content. This factorial approach allowed for the evaluation of main and interaction effects while reducing the number of required experiments. Electrospinning solutions were prepared by dissolving PCL, chitosan and nHAp in a constant formic acid/acetic acid solvent blend.

Nanofiber diameters ranged from 80 to 180 nm, porosity from 33% to 42%, and pore diameters from 0.38 to 0.57 μm , indicating highly porous structures suitable for nutrient diffusion and cell migration. Additional evaluations included mechanical testing (tensile strength) and qualitative assessments of nHAp dispersion using SEM-EDS mapping. These parameters are critical to predicting the scaffold's ability to withstand physiological conditions and to support osteogenic differentiation in future biological evaluations. The scaffold without nHAp (PCL/CS = 8:2, 6% w/v) exhibited the highest tensile strength (UTS = 8.49 MPa) and 38.7% porosity, ideal for load-bearing applications. The best-performing nHAp-loaded scaffold (same ratio, 20% nHAp) maintained good porosity (34%) with a UTS of 2.04 MPa, highlighting its osteoconductive potential.

In addition to earlier research on soft tissue binary polymer systems, this work presents a triphasic scaffold specifically designed for bone restoration. The uniform integration of ceramic and polymer is made possible by the direct electrospinning of nHAp instead of post-processing. This approach offers a tunable platform for developing next-generation nanofibrous scaffolds with controllable mechanical and bioactive profiles, suitable for future 3D tissue-engineered bone constructs.

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Keyword: *Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds, Bone tissue engineering, Design of Experiments (DOE)*

Microfabrication of Nanocrystal Photovoltaic Array for Photostimulation of Neurons

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The fabrication of multi-layered patterned films is crucial for enhancing the functionality and efficiency of next-generation quantum dot (QD) optoelectronic devices. Various high-resolution QD display patterning techniques, including transfer printing, direct photolithography, ink-jet printing, and contact patterning, have been demonstrated. However, they present limitations for patterning multilayered device architectures. To address these challenges, we present inductively coupled plasma dry etching following traditional photolithography. This approach eliminates the need for repetitive patterning process while overcoming the scalability constraints and enabling anisotropic features. We demonstrate the capabilities of this method through the microfabrication of high-fidelity nanocrystal-based photodiode arrays, achieving circular features with a radius down to 5 μm and complex star-shaped pixels, indicating the potential of the methodology. For the p-i-n diode structure, ZnO sol-gel is utilized as the electron transport layer, AgBiS₂ nanocrystals serve as the intrinsic layer, which is selected for their biocompatibility and broad spectral absorption, and P3HT (Poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diy)) functions as the hole transport layer. To increase the effectiveness of the photostimulation, a PEDOT:PSS pseudocapacitive ultrathin layer is incorporated. These microfabricated devices generate spatially selective and reversible high photoresponses within the artificial biological medium, within ocular safety limits. To further demonstrate their optoelectronic capabilities as a biointerface, rat cardiomyocyte explanted tissues are seeded onto the devices, and their beating activity is recorded under 620nm light illumination. Overall results reveal that microfabricated devices can increase the number of cardiomyocyte beats by more than 50%, revealing their significant potential for a multisite photostimulation platform as a pacemaker.

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Keyword: Microfabrication, Quantum dot, Photostimulation, Bioelectronic

MicroMetaSense: Coupling Plasmonic Metasurfaces with Fluorescence for Enhanced Detection of Microplastics in Real Samples

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A variety of analytical techniques have been used to investigate microplastics (MPs), which are commonly found at hazardous levels across a wide range of environments, from water bodies to consumable goods. However, existing methods often fall short when it comes to detecting MPs of very small sizes (1 to 5 μm for microplastics and below 1 μm for nanoplastics) due to their limited sensitivity. This creates a clear need for more advanced approaches with enhanced detection capabilities and lower limits of quantification. In this study, we present MicroMetaSense, a comprehensive detection platform that leverages the phenomenon of metal enhanced fluorescence (MEF) to identify a wide range of MP sizes and types, including poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), with a sensitivity reaching as low as 183 to 205 femtograms. The method was validated using real world samples including tap water, lake water, and artificial ocean water, demonstrating its practical applicability. To achieve accurate nanoscale size distribution, MPs are first processed via an on chip ultrafiltration technique and then stained with Nile Red dye. These are subsequently analyzed using fluorescence microscopy on both standard glass substrates and the MicroMetaSense metasurface. By integrating a custom designed metasurface, the system significantly amplifies fluorescence signals via the MEF effect, yielding a 36.56 fold enhancement in MP detection compared to conventional glass substrate. This low cost (2 dollars), time efficient (under 30 minutes), and ultra sensitive approach not only improves detection accuracy in laboratory conditions but also proves effective in analyzing complex environmental samples. As such, it represents a significant advancement over traditional MP detection methodologies.

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Keyword: *Microplastics, Nanoplastics, Plasmonic Metasurfaces, Metal-Enhances Fluorescence*

Surface Mechanics Engineering with Graded Biocomposite Films: Interplay of Layer Architecture and Force Regimes

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The mechanical behavior of biocompatible polymer nanocomposites was systematically investigated as a function of nanofiller type, particle distribution, and applied force regime. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)-based coatings reinforced with spherical nano silica (NS) and tubular halloysite nanotubes (HNT) were fabricated via spin coating and tested using colloidal probe microscopy (CPM, μN -scale) and instrumented indentation (mN-scale). A strong force-dependent mechanical response was recorded, with **elastic moduli in the MPa range under CPM and GPa range under nanoindentation**, highlighting the influence of polymer chain mobility and localized nanoparticle accumulation. Classical reinforcement models underestimated the observed stiffness, indicating deviation due to real-world stress localization effects.

To explore mechanical enhancement through structural design, both **gradient** and **reverse-gradient** architectures with spatially varying HNT concentrations (e.g., 5–15–30 wt% vs. 30–15–5 wt%) were constructed. While gradient coatings facilitated smoother stress transitions, **reverse-gradient coatings—featuring stiffer sublayers adjacent to the compliant substrate—demonstrated significantly improved surface properties**. A surface modulus as high as **2.92 GPa** was achieved in 30 μm thick reverse-gradient systems, **nearly an order of magnitude higher than their gradient counterparts (0.33 GPa)** at equivalent thickness. **Notably, the reverse-gradient design strategy remains largely unexplored in the literature**, despite its capacity to amplify load transfer toward the surface and mitigate compliance mismatch.

These results underscore that mechanical performance in polymer nanocomposites is not intrinsic, but rather an emergent outcome of multi-length-scale design, filler topology, and testing conditions. The study establishes a new conceptual and experimental framework for stiffness engineering at soft interfaces, paving the way for next-generation coatings in biomedical devices, wearable electronics, and flexible substrates requiring controlled compliance and mechanical durability.

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Keyword: *Nanocomposite film, Gradient composite, nanoindentation, atomic force microscopy*

Exploiting Layer-Dependent Quenching from Unclonable Adlayers of 2D Materials for Advanced Hybrid Optical Authentication

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The escalating demand for robust anti-counterfeiting solutions necessitates security tags that are simultaneously verifiable and physically unclonable. While conventional identifiers (e.g., barcodes) are easily replicated, purely stochastic Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs)^[1] often lack the deterministic features required for efficient authentication. Hybrid cryptographic platforms integrating both paradigms face a critical challenge: the foundational material must exhibit unique, fingerprint-like responses to stimuli, enabling multilayered security.^[2]

Herein, it is discovered that incidental island-like adlayer formations, typically deemed undesirable in 2D material synthesis, can be harnessed as an ideal platform for PUF applications. A new type of security system is presented that uses a random pattern of multilayer graphene (MLG) islands with different sizes and thicknesses, built on a single-layer graphene (SLG) base.

The core of this study lies in exploiting the fluorescence quenching mechanism in a previously unexplored manner. In the fabrication phase, uncontrolled adlayer growth is intentionally triggered to create this physically unclonable surface. The fabricated, physically unclonable graphene surface is coated with fluorophore thin films, transforming it into a nanoscale canvas with spatially variant quenching efficiencies. The local layer number of the graphene adlayers directly modulates the Förster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) rate, converting the random physical topography into a high-resolution, analog fluorescence intensity map. This mechanism generates an information-rich optical fingerprint where each grayscale level corresponds to a specific local layer count, a concept not previously exploited for cryptographic purposes.

It is demonstrated that this layer-dependent quenching mechanism holds the potential to create a powerful optical PUF with an unprecedented encoding capacity. Furthermore, graphene's chemically inert yet layer-tunable properties provide additional cryptographic security layers. By subsequently patterning these stochastic surfaces into deterministic micro-barcode formats using conventional photolithography, hybrid labels that merge this advanced cryptographic complexity with conventionally readable functionality. The proposed approach thus redefines the application of graphene's fluorescence quenching from a simple binary switch to a high-density analog information carrier, establishing a new physical basis for the next generation of unclonable, multi-layered optical tags.

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Keyword: *Graphene, Fluorescence Quenching, Physically Unclonable Function (PUF), Anti-counterfeiting*

Development of Hyaluronic Acid-Enhanced Hydrogels Strengthened with Henna-Derived Carbon Quantum Dots for Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems

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In this study, hydrogel-based wound dressings were developed to enable the transdermal delivery of ibuprofen, and their swelling capacity, mechanical strength, and drug release profiles were optimized.

The hydrogels, which were examined for their drug release profiles, were synthesized using acrylamide (AAM) and N,N'-methylene bis(acrylamide) (MBAA) monomers through crosslinking polymerization in an acidic aqueous medium [1-3]. To enhance the swelling capacity and reduce the proportion of synthetic monomers, hyaluronic acid (HA) was incorporated into the structure. HA, with its high molecular weight, improved the swelling capacity by increasing the distance between crosslinks and supported controlled drug release [4].

Subsequently, carbon quantum dots (CQDs) derived from *Lawsonia inermis* (henna) were incorporated into the hydrogel matrix. Due to their small size and large surface area, CQDs enhanced skin permeability, enabling deeper penetration of drugs and ensuring controlled release. Microwave-assisted methods were employed for environmentally friendly and cost-effective production. The structural and morphological properties of the produced hydrogels were analyzed using FTIR, SEM, EDS, and UV-Vis spectroscopy techniques

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Keyword: *Hydrogel, Hyaluronic Acid, Carbon Quantum Dots, Swelling Capacity*

Nonlinear Light-Matter Interaction Mediated by Polaritons in 2D Systems

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Understanding the fundamental mechanisms governing the optical response in materials is crucial for designing systems with strong nonlinearities at reduced light intensity thresholds and for uncovering their potential applications. The emergence of pronounced photon-polariton interaction signatures in the linear optical spectrum of two-dimensional (2D) materials, attributed to the reduction in Coulomb screening and the amplification of quantum-confinement effects, has sparked active research into polaritonic effects in the nonlinear optical response of these materials [1,2]. In this talk, we will discuss several exemplary studies of the nonlinear response in 2D materials [3-5]. We introduce a specific collection of 2D materials, along with a range of excitation modes such as phonons, excitons, and plasmons, which provide a suitable arena for monitoring the interactions between light and matter. Using first-principles methods, including density functional theory (DFT) and post-DFT approaches (e.g., GW and Bethe-Salpeter-equation) we reveal the detailed electronic and vibrational properties of 2D materials and predict their optical response in the presence of polaritons. Then, solving the equation of motion either in the time domain or with perturbative approaches, we obtain the nonlinear susceptibilities associated with second- and third-harmonic generation. In brief, our work demonstrates that various types of polaritons exhibit a robust, optically and electrically controllable nonlinear response in 2D materials. These polaritons offer numerous applications across a wide range of optical spectra in both optoelectronics and quantum optics.

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Keyword: *nonlinear optics, polariton, 2D materials, ultrafast optics*

Photoluminescence of Gated Mixed-Dimensional Heterostructures

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Atomically thin two-dimensional (2D) semiconductors exhibit a rich array of novel physical phenomena. Mixed-dimensional 1D–2D heterostructures are particularly promising, as they can introduce unique electronic and optical properties by leveraging the interplay between different dimensionalities at their interfaces. Our group has recently demonstrated efficient exciton transfer and the formation of interlayer excitons in mixed-dimensional heterostructures composed of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and monolayer tungsten diselenide (WSe₂), enabled by band alignment engineering [1,2]. Additional degrees of freedom can be introduced into this system through doping and the application of external electric fields, offering further control over interfacial interactions in these 1D–2D systems.

Here, we will discuss the photoluminescence (PL) emission in WSe₂/CNT heterostructures under the application of back-gate voltage. Measurements are conducted on air-suspended WSe₂/CNT field-effect transistors. The field-effect device fabrication begins with the chemical vapor deposition growth of CNTs over the trenches with pre-deposited source and drain metal contacts. The mixed-dimensional heterostructure is formed by transferring an exfoliated WSe₂ flake on top of an air-suspended CNT using anthracene-assisted dry transfer method [3]. We performed photoluminescence excitation spectroscopy under different gate voltages. We investigated the vertical electric field dependence of PL emission under E₂₂ excitation of CNT and A-exciton resonance excitation of WSe₂. We clarified the role of metal contacts on the chirality dependence of band alignments.

Acknowledgments

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Keyword: *CNT, TMDC, Heterostructure, Photoluminescence*

DFT Investigation of the Effect of Electric Field on Electronic and Optical Properties of Graphene, Stanene, and Molybdenum Carbide Monolayers

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Two-dimensional (2D) materials such as graphene, stanene, and transition-metal carbides have drawn significant attention in nanotechnology and optics owing to their exceptional carrier mobility, high electrical and thermal conductivity, tunable band structure, and strong light–matter interactions. In this work, we employ first-principles density functional theory (DFT) to investigate how a static perpendicular electric field (E_z) modulates the electronic and optical properties of three representative monolayers, graphene, stanene, and Mo_2C , including band structure evolution, interband transitions, dipole moments, charge redistribution, static dielectric response and total energy. For graphene and Mo_2C contributions of van der Waals interactions are included; for stanene, spin-orbit coupling (SOC) is included. In all systems, even modest fields ($E_z \geq 0.3 \text{ V/\AA}$) induce a pronounced downward shift of the states in the conduction band (CB). States in the valence band (VB) in graphene and stanene move upward under E_z , while the bands in the VB of Mo_2C are comparatively insensitive to E_z . Pristine stanene has no band gap without SOC, but acquires a direct $\sim 0.08 \text{ eV}$ gap at the K-point when SOC is included. Increasing E_z continuously reduces this gap, closing its indirect Γ -point gap (0.27 eV) at 0.6 V/\AA and its direct K-point gap at 0.8 V/\AA , signaling a metallic transition under E_z . Moreover, graphene and Mo_2C maintain metallic character throughout, as confirmed by the static dielectric constants ($\epsilon(\omega \rightarrow 0)$) and charge-density difference ($\Delta\rho$) plots. In graphene, the anti-bonding σ^* band approaches and crosses below the Fermi level (E_F) for $E_z > 0.4 \text{ V/\AA}$, evidencing electric-field–induced n-type doping. Similarly, in single-layer stanene, s and p bands cross the Fermi level beyond 0.7 V/\AA , and in Mo_2C , bands corresponding to the s orbitals of Mo cross the Fermi level under the same field strength, both cases indicating tunable carrier concentration via perpendicular gating. Analysis of the imaginary part of the dielectric function reveals a newly observed $\sigma^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition under E_z , in addition to the four well-known electronic interband transitions of monolayer graphene, offering a means to control optical absorption spectra. $\Delta\rho$ data further indicate that 2D Mo_2C exhibits the largest out-of-plane polarizability and the most sensitive charge response to E_z , together with a high zero-field in-plane $\epsilon(\omega \rightarrow 0)$, making it the most readily tunable system among those studied. In 2D materials, E_z can be used to gate in-plane screening, especially for graphene since its in-plane $\epsilon(\omega \rightarrow 0)$ have negative values with increasing E_z which outlines strategies for controlling electronic and optical functionality of 2D materials in future device applications.

Keyword: *Perpendicular static electric field, 2D materials, density functional theory, electronic and optical properties*

Self-Organized 3D Graphene on SiC: Catalyst-Free Growth and Field Emission Behavior

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Carbon nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene are highly promising candidates for field electron emission due to their exceptional electrical properties and high aspect ratios, especially when vertically aligned. Although chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is a commonly used synthesis technique, it faces several limitations, including weak adhesion to the substrate, high contact resistance, catalyst contamination, and rapid degradation under high-power conditions.

This study investigates the field emission behavior of 3D-graphene structures synthesized on single-crystal SiC substrates via a catalyst-free vacuum decomposition method. This technique offers key advantages over CVD, enabling strong bonding between the emitter and the substrate while eliminating catalyst-related impurities. Nitrogen doping was also employed to further enhance the electrical conductivity of the 3D-graphene layers.

Structural and electronic characterizations using Raman spectroscopy and TEM confirmed the formation of 3D graphene networks. The highest field emission performance was achieved for nitrogen-doped samples grown on the Si-terminated face of SiC at 1700°C, exhibiting a low turn-on field of 2 V/ μm and a high current density of 333 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$.

These findings demonstrate that catalyst-free vacuum decomposition is a robust and scalable approach for producing high-performance 3D-graphene field emitters, offering significant potential for advanced vacuum electronic applications.

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Keyword: *Carbon nanostructures, Vacuum Decomposition, Field Emission*

Bioactive Electrospun PBAT/nano-SrB₄O₇ Nanofibers for Enhanced Osteogenesis: A Promising Nanobiomaterial for Implant Interfaces

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The success of orthopedic and dental implants greatly depends on the quality of bone-implant integration. Functional surface coatings using nanostructured bioactive materials offer a promising strategy to enhance osseointegration and reduce implant failure [1]. In this study, electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds based on poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) were functionalized with strontium tetraborate (SrB₄O₇) nanoparticles (nano-SrB₄O₇) to evaluate their potential as osteoinductive implant coatings.

SrB₄O₇ nanoparticles were synthesized by solid-state synthesis method with approximately 340 nm average diameter. PBAT/SrB₄O₇ nanofibers were fabricated via electrospinning with three different nano-SrB₄O₇ concentrations: 5%, 10%, and 15% (w/w). Morphological analysis using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed that the 10% (w/w) nano-SrB₄O₇-loaded PBAT nanofibers exhibited the most uniform and bead-free structure. SEM analysis revealed smooth and uniform fiber morphologies, with an average diameter of 900 nm for PBAT nanofibers and a reduced average diameter of 500 nm for nano-SrB₄O₇-loaded nanofibers, likely due to changes in solution conductivity and polymer-particle interactions. Higher or lower nano-SrB₄O₇ contents led to structural irregularities or reduced electrospinnability. Therefore, 10% (w/w) nano-SrB₄O₇ was selected as the optimal formulation for further biological evaluation.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed successful nanoparticle incorporation and structural integrity of the nanofibrous matrices. In vitro studies using MC3T3-E1 preosteoblastic cells showed that both PBAT and PBAT/nano-SrB₄O₇ nanofibers supported cell viability, as demonstrated by MTT assay results indicating comparable levels of metabolic activity. To assess osteogenic differentiation, Alizarin Red and Von Kossa staining were performed. Results demonstrated increased osteogenic differentiation and extracellular matrix mineralization in nano-SrB₄O₇-loaded PBAT nanofibers than unmodified PBAT, confirming their osteoinductive effect. These improvements are attributed to the synergistic release of strontium and borate ions, which stimulate osteoblast function and bone matrix formation.

The nanofibrous structure of PBAT provides a high surface area and biomimetic environment conducive to cell-material interactions, while nano-SrB₄O₇ contributes bioactive cues that promote osteoinduction. This dual-functional nanofiber system presents a promising strategy for biofunctional implant coatings that support bone regeneration. Combining the favorable nanofibrous architecture of PBAT with the bioactivity of nano-SrB₄O₇ offers a synergistic platform for bone tissue integration. The findings in this study suggest that PBAT/nano-SrB₄O₇ nanofibers represent a promising surface coating strategy for orthopedic and dental implants, with both biocompatibility and osteogenic potential.

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Keyword: PBAT, strontium tetraborate, nanofiber, implant interface

Atomistic Insights Into Transition Metal Phosphides for Nanoelectromechanical Switch Applications

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The continued miniaturization of transistors in integrated circuits (ICs) is approaching fundamental physical limits, as conventional solid-state transistors suffer from intrinsic leakage currents and large switching voltages that hinder further scaling and energy efficiency [1]. Nano-electro-mechanical systems (NEMS) switches offer a promising alternative by providing near-zero leakage and low-power switching through physical contact-based mechanisms. However, their widespread application is currently limited by challenges related to adhesion and tribopolymer formation at the contact interface under operational conditions [2,3].

In this study, we employ density functional theory (DFT) to investigate the potential of transition metal phosphides (TMPs) as contact materials for MEMS/NEMS switches. We focus on Ru₂P, RuP, Rh₂P, and TiP, evaluating their thermodynamic stability in oxidative environments and their resistance to tribopolymer formation under repeated mechanical contact in the presence of benzene as a background gas. Our results reveal that Ru₂P and Rh₂P demonstrate both chemical robustness and low susceptibility to friction-induced polymerization, making them strong candidates for reliable and energy-efficient NEMS switching [4].

This work highlights the critical role of atomic-scale theoretical modeling in guiding the selection of novel materials for next-generation low-power nanoelectronic devices, particularly under harsh conditions involving high stress, temperature, and chemical reactivity.

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Keyword: *Transition Metal Phosphides (TMPs), Nanoelectromechanical Systems (NEMS), Density Functional Theory (DFT), Tribopolymer Formation, Contact Materials*

Manufacturing of pH-Sensitive and Three-Layered Electrospun Nanofiber Mat for In Vitro Evaluations of Chronic Wounds

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Chronic wounds, affecting approximately 40 million individuals globally, pose significant challenges due to impaired healing processes, leading to infection and tissue loss. This study presents a new three-layer mat made of tiny fibers that helps heal chronic wounds by being sensitive to pH, fighting germs, and being safe for the body. The composite mat comprises an upper layer of poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/chitosan (PCL/CS) for structural integrity, a middle layer of polyvinylpyrrolidone/ciprofloxacin (PVP/CFX) for infection control, and a bottom layer of polyvinyl alcohol/sodium alginate/anthocyanins (PVA/NaAlg/AC) for pH-responsive wound monitoring. Fabricated via electrospinning at a flow rate of 0.1 ml/h and 18 kV, the mat achieves a uniform thickness of approximately 1 micrometer, ensuring optimal porosity and flexibility.

The PVA/NaAlg/AC layer leverages the hydrophilicity of PVA and pH-dependent color-changing properties of anthocyanins, enabling real-time wound status monitoring. The mat transitions from green in acidic chronic wound environments to red upon healing, indicating pH normalization. Characterization through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) confirmed the uniform and continuous morphology of PVA/NaAlg/AC, PVP/CFX, and PCL/CS nanofibers. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) verified the successful incorporation of anthocyanins, ciprofloxacin, and chitosan into their respective layers. Density-viscosity-pH analyses ensured material compatibility, while MTT cytotoxicity and scratch assays using CCD1072-Sk human skin fibroblast cells demonstrated high biocompatibility and wound closure efficacy of the ST-598 nanofiber variant (derived from ST-5, ST-8, and ST-9 compositions, which are compositions for three different layers). The pH-sensing response was rapid, reversible, and reproducible, underscoring its potential for clinical application.

The developed mat addresses critical challenges in chronic wound management by preventing infection through ciprofloxacin release, promoting tissue regeneration via biocompatible scaffolds, and enabling non-invasive healing assessment through pH sensitivity. In vitro analyses indicate that the ST-598 (which is the three-layered mat) nanofiber mat is a promising candidate for chronic wound dressings. Future research will focus on in vivo studies to validate pH sensitivity and therapeutic efficacy, alongside exploring commercial scalability. This innovative electrospun mat represents a significant advancement in non-cellular scaffold-based therapies, offering a multifunctional, cost-effective solution for chronic wound care.

Keyword: *nanofibers, electrospinning, pH sensors, nanocomposites*

Nondegradable Implantable Lignin-base Electrospun Patch for Hernia Repair

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Most commercial hernia meshes are non-degradable and provide long-term mechanical support, but they often lack bioactivity and can contribute to complications such as chronic inflammation and adhesion. To address these limitations, our research focuses on a double-layer electrospun hernia patch, in which a non-degradable base layer ensures permanent mechanical reinforcement while a degradable top layer supports initial tissue regeneration. Electrospun scaffolds closely mimic the structure of the extracellular matrix (ECM), making them ideal platforms for tissue engineering.

PTFE (polytetrafluoroethylene), widely used for its chemical inertness and mechanical strength, is blended with PCL (polycaprolactone) to improve electrospinnability and flexibility. Lignin, an eco-friendly, cost-effective natural polymer with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, is incorporated to enhance the biological functionality of the mesh surface. This non-degradable layer, composed of PTFE/PCL/lignin nanofibers. This layer is designed to remain permanently in the body, providing the necessary structural integrity to prevent hernia recurrence.

The non-degradable layer was fabricated using a binary solvent system of acetic acid and formic acid, with an optimized PTFE/PCL/lignin ratio to achieve uniform, bead-free nanofibers with favorable morphology and elasticity, enabling the structure to withstand physiological pressure. Structural characterization was conducted using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Mechanical testing (tensile strength and adhesion strength) demonstrated that the PTFE/PCL/lignin nanofibrous layer provides robust mechanical support, suitable for permanent implantation in hernia repair applications.

Cytocompatibility of the non-degradable layer was evaluated via MTT assay using L929 fibroblasts, confirming high cell viability across a range of extract concentrations. The incorporation of lignin imparts antimicrobial properties to the mesh surface.

This approach presents a bioactive, sustainable alternative to fully synthetic hernia meshes, with the potential for drug loading and integration into a multi-layered patch system. The non-degradable layer provides permanent mechanical support, complementing the degradable component of the double-layer hernia patch for advanced hernia repair.

Keyword: *Electrospun Nanofibrous Patch, Hernia Repair, Biocompatible Patch, Lignin*

Design and Controlled Release Profiles of PCL and PLGA-Based Dual Drug-Loaded Core-Shell Nanoparticles Containing Ginger and Turmeric Extracts

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The increasing complexity of diseases and the toxicity of some treatments highlight the need for new drug delivery strategies. Polymeric delivery platforms, valued for their biodegradability and biocompatibility, utilize natural polymers with inherent biological compatibility, though limited by batch-to-batch variability and possible immunogenic responses, while synthetic polymers offer advantages through their controlled and reproducible chemical structures. Among synthetic polymers, poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) are prominent in drug delivery systems due to their biocompatibility and controlled release properties.¹

The utilization of natural medicines has attracted considerable interest for many years, leading to more research focused on developing drug formulations with plant extracts that improve their bioavailability and effectiveness. In this regard, *Zingiber officinale* L. (ginger) and *Curcuma longa* L. (turmeric) have gained particular attention due to their well-documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Ginger is the rhizome of the plant, known primarily for phytochemicals such as gingerol and shogaol, which contribute to its therapeutic effects.² Similarly, turmeric is a yellow-orange root widely used as a spice and natural preservative, with traditional medicinal applications for various health conditions.³ Aim of this study, to improve the bioavailability and efficacy of these plant extracts through controlled and sustained release by incorporating turmeric aqueous extracts into a PLGA shell surrounding a ginger-loaded PCL core polymeric nanoparticle system, and to evaluate their in vitro release profiles under different pH conditions with a detailed analysis of the release mechanisms.

In this study, nanoparticles were synthesized using a double emulsion solvent evaporation method, featuring a PCL-based core loaded with ginger extract and a PLGA-based shell encapsulating turmeric extract. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) confirmed the core-shell structure and morphology, while UV-Vis spectroscopy verified the successful encapsulation of the extracts by detecting their absorption peaks. In vitro release studies were conducted at pH 5, 7.4, and 8 to simulate various physiological conditions. The results demonstrated a biphasic release pattern, characterized by an initial release phase attributed to the PLGA shell, followed by sustained release from the PCL core. This confirms the successful fabrication of a dual-release system with spatial and temporal control of drug distribution.

Based on our findings, it could be suggested that the dual-release nanoparticle system can modulate drug release in response to environmental pH changes, potentially enabling targeted and sustained delivery. This behavior suggests promising applications for site-specific therapies where pH variations are common.

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Keyword: *Zingiber officinale* L., *Curcuma longa* L., Dual Drug, Core-Shell Nanoparticles

Polymer Coatings for the Regulation of Drug Delivery from Surface Mesoporous Titania Capsules

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Targeted surface delivery and controlled release of the chemicals and biomolecules from encapsulated systems are gaining high interest due to the adaptation for biomedical applications such as drug delivery, tissue engineering, cell encapsulation, theranostics [1-3]. In our work formation of surface mesoporous titania capsules on titanium with controllable release behavior are proposed for use on titanium implanted devices. Surface capsules are designed on the basic of porous titania layer formed by sonochemical etching treatment. Adsorbed bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP-2) is used as an active chemical to encapsulate. Different polymer coatings are designed to control release behavior and 1) achieve prolonged release; 2-3) switch on/off release 3) change of surface hydrophilicity due to surface enzymatic reactions are the parameters that we concentrated. We are comparing different polymer coatings with low-permeable skin-like polypyrrole based coating. Structural characterization of mesoporous titania layer before and after polymer coatings formation is examined by using AFM, SEM, contact angle, impedance spectroscopic and photoelectrochemical measurements. It is shown that polypyrrole coated titania surfaces are biocompatible for MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells and durable to simulated body fluids. BMP-2 protein is released slowly from the polypyrrole coated titania surface when it is compared with the other polymer coatings on titania mesoporous layer.

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Keyword: *Titanium mesoporous surface, Bone morphogenic protein, Releasing, Polymer coating*

Embedded 3D Bioprinting for Vascularized Tissue Barriers

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Embedded 3D bioprinting is a powerful biofabrication technique for producing functional and vascularized tissue models. A critical factor in this process is selecting suitable biocompatible support bath that exhibits shear-thinning and self-healing properties to enable the deposition of vascular channels. (Lei et al., 2023). The support bath, then, needs to be stabilized to maintain the shape fidelity of the vascular channels. These models are flexible for the biofabrication of various tissue models and can be used for understanding the disease mechanism and development of treatment approaches. In this study, extrusion-based 3D bioprinting was utilized for the development of vascularized 3D tissue models. A vascularized model structure was digitally designed by CAD models and printed using a support bath composed of Gelatin Methacryloyl (GelMA) and Xanthan gum (XaG). A 20% Pluronic F127 (PF127) solution was used as a sacrificial ink to form internal channels. After printing, UV radiation was applied to stabilize the GelMA-XaG support matrix. The sacrificial PF127 ink was removed, creating open, perfusable channels that resemble vascular channels. These channels were later seeded with endothelial cells to mimic natural flow conditions. The support hydrogel was optimized for cell compatibility and mechanical stability, allowing the encapsulation and growth of cells. Live/dead assays, structural imaging tests confirmed the biocompatibility and fidelity of the printed constructs, and characterization, and mechanical tests confirmed the synthesis and mechanical behavior of the support. The GelMA hydrogel maintained structural stability and provided a supportive matrix for cell growth and interaction. Confocal microscopy images revealed well-defined endothelialized vascular channels. This method demonstrates strong potential for advancing 3D bioprinted platforms in neurovascular research and drug testing applications.

Keyword: *Embedded 3D Bioprinting, Vascular Model, Hydrogel Biomaterials, Biofabrication*

Anodization of Pure Iron: A Candidate Material for Bioresorbable Stent Applications

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Ischemic heart disease, primarily caused by arterial narrowing, remains the leading global cause of mortality. While angioplasty with stent implantation is a standard treatment, restenosis remains a significant limitation. Drug-eluting stents mitigate this issue by inhibiting neointimal hyperplasia but carry a higher risk of thrombosis. Bioresorbable stents (BRSs) offer a promising alternative by degrading overtime and reducing long-term complications. However, BRS development faces two key challenges: ensuring mechanical stability for 3–6 months with complete degradation within 12–24 months, and achieving high cyto- and hemocompatibility to support vascular healing while minimizing thrombosis and calcification.

Among the primary candidates for metallic BRSs, iron, magnesium, and zinc, each exhibit distinct advantages and limitations. Iron stands out due to its excellent mechanical strength, offering superior vessel support compared to magnesium and zinc. However, slow degradation rate of iron is a major challenge for its clinical use. To address this challenge, we aimed to enhance the biodegradation behavior of pure iron through anodization. For this purpose, anodization was applied as a surface modification technique to accelerate the corrosion process, thereby improving its potential for use in BRS applications.

In this study, pure iron samples were anodized under varying electrochemical conditions to fabricate nanotubular surface features. Depending on the applied anodization voltage, the diameter of the nanotubular structures ranged from approximately 30 nm to 120 nm, and the oxide layer thickness ranged from approximately 160 nm to 400 nm. The RMS roughness (Sq) of the anodized surfaces ranged from 7.8 nm to 25.0 nm, compared to the initial roughness of 15.2 nm for the as-received sample. To assess their degradation behavior, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and Tafel extrapolation analyses were performed in 1X simulated body fluid (SBF) at 37°C. The electrochemical responses varied depending on the applied anodization voltage, indicating that surface modification significantly influenced corrosion performance. Wettability was assessed by contact angle measurements, revealing a contact angle of approximately 115 ° for the anodized sample. Furthermore, cytotoxicity assays completed up to 5 days demonstrated that the anodized iron samples were non-toxic, supporting their potential suitability for BRS applications. These findings demonstrate that anodization is an effective strategy to tailor the surface properties and accelerate the degradation of pure iron, thereby enhancing its viability as a BRS material.

Acknowledgments

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Keyword: *pure iron, anodization, nanotube, bioresorbable stent*

Improving Antifungal and Mechanical Properties of PMMA Denture Base Using Modified Cellulose Nanocrystals

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Denture stomatitis, a prevalent oral inflammatory condition affecting over 50% of denture wearers, was primarily caused by fungal biofilm formation on denture surfaces, particularly by *Candida albicans*. This issue was especially significant among elderly and immunocompromised individuals, for whom maintaining denture hygiene was challenging. Conventional treatments, including hygiene practices and antifungal agents, showed limitations due to patient compliance, material degradation, and the emergence of antifungal resistance. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), commonly used for denture bases, exhibited surface roughness that promoted fungal adherence and had limited mechanical strength. Although metal oxide nanoparticles had been investigated for reinforcement and antifungal activity, their long-term toxicity remained a concern. In this study, PMMA denture bases were developed with improved antifungal resistance and mechanical strength by incorporating cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) conjugated with photosensitizer (PS) agents. These PS molecules, activated by light, acted as antifungal agents. The modified PMMA composites were chemically and mechanically characterized and were tested for their biocompatibility and antifungal efficacy, demonstrating potential for long-term oral health applications.

Keyword: Denture, antifungal, cellulose nanocrystal, photosensitizer

Fabrication and Comprehensive Characterization of Electrospun Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)/Poly(hydroxybutyrate) (PHB)/Silk fibroin (SF) Composite Nanofibers

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In this study, electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds composed of poly(lactic acid) (PLA), poly(hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), and silk fibroin (SF) were developed and characterized for potential use in tissue engineering applications. PLA was incorporated to provide mechanical and structural strength, PHB to improve biodegradability and biocompatibility, and silk fibroin to enhance mechanical stability and bioactivity of composite scaffolds. Morphological features of generated nanofibers were investigated with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and were observed as bead-free, homogeneously distributed, and continuous fiber networks. Chemical functionalities and heat characteristics were characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), respectively, which represent the effective integration of components and thermal stability of the architecture. Mechanical properties were demonstrated to show that the PLA:PHB:SF1 group had the highest tensile strength in the groups examined. Biocompatibility in vitro was tested against mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), and the PLA:PHB:SF1 scaffolds had the optimal cellular response with respect to adhesion and viability. These findings demonstrate that PLA/PHB/SF nanofiber scaffolds possess promising structural and biological properties, rendering them ideal candidates for applications in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine.

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Keyword: *nanofibers, silk fibroin, poly(hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), poly(lactic acid) (PLA)*

Multifunctional PdCo Nanoparticles: Synthesis and Structural Insights for Catalysis and Magnetism

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Noble metals such as Pt, Pd, Au, Ag, Rh, Ru, and Ir are widely recognized for their excellent electrical conductivity, high surface activity, and chemical stability, making them ideal candidates for electrocatalysis and photocatalysis [1]. However, the pursuit of next-generation functional materials demands systems that not only retain high catalytic performance but also offer greater cost-effectiveness, recyclability, environmental compatibility, and multifunctionality. Alloying noble metals with transition metals like Fe, Co, or Ni has emerged as an effective strategy to enhance catalytic efficiency while significantly lowering material costs [2]. Additionally, combining non-magnetic noble metals with ferromagnetic elements introduces strong spin-orbit coupling effects, which can increase magnetocrystalline anisotropy—an essential characteristic for applications in high-density magnetic storage, magnetic separation, biomedical diagnostics, and imaging technologies. In this study, we synthesized Pd–Co alloy nanoparticles (NPs) with varying stoichiometric ratios using a modified polyol process under an inert Ar atmosphere. Structural analysis via X-ray diffraction (XRD) combined with Rietveld refinement revealed the coexistence of face-centered cubic (fcc) and hexagonal close-packed (hcp) phases. Morphological characterization through transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed that the particles are uniformly distributed with an average size below 10 nm. Elemental analysis using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) confirmed the targeted composition and the absence of detectable impurities.

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Keyword: PdCo Nanoparticles, Modified Polyol Synthesis, Structural Characterization

Green Synthesis of Carbon Dots From Plant-Based Natural Sources: A Case Study On Nettle Leaves And Walnut Shells

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In recent years, carbon dots (CDs) have emerged as a prominent class of carbon-based nanomaterials within the fields of nanotechnology and materials science, owing to their tunable photoluminescent properties, high oxidative capacity, excellent biocompatibility, low cytotoxicity, and environmentally benign nature (Wang & Hu, 2014). The adoption of green chemistry principles in the synthesis of CDs promotes sustainable manufacturing practices by encouraging the use of renewable, naturally derived, and cost-effective carbon sources (Kuang et al., 2023).

In this study, CDs were synthesized through an environmentally friendly hydrothermal approach using two distinct low-waste biomass resources: nettle leaves (*Urtica dioica*) and walnut shells (*Juglans regia*). The use of such agricultural residues as precursors for fluorescent nanomaterials has been well-documented in literature, particularly for walnut shells which offer significant carbon content and structural suitability (Cheng et al., 2017). Additionally, a sonochemical synthesis route employing a probe-type ultrasonicator was explored as an alternative method, and its influence on synthesis duration and structural integrity was systematically evaluated (Lu & Zhou, 2019).

The CDs derived from both biomass precursors exhibited characteristic blue-green fluorescence emission upon excitation at approximately 255 nm, consistent with the optical profiles reported for other plant-based CDs (Sachdev & Gopinath, 2015). Furthermore, the resulting nanoparticles demonstrated high colloidal stability and negligible tendency for agglomeration, which aligns with previous findings on biomass-derived CDs (Kuang et al., 2023).

Comprehensive characterization of the synthesized CDs was conducted using a suite of analytical techniques, including UV-Vis spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and zeta potential analysis. Although the sonochemical method enabled a more rapid synthesis process (Lu & Zhou, 2019), the hydrothermal approach yielded superior results in terms of carbon dot production efficiency and optical performance, echoing trends observed in recent comparative studies on biomass-based synthesis techniques (Kuang et al., 2023).

This work presents a sustainable and environmentally responsible strategy for carbon dot synthesis, offering a comparative evaluation of hydrothermal and sonochemical methods utilizing natural biomass precursors.

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Keyword: Carbon Nanoparticles (CNP), Carbon Dots (CDs), Green Synthesis, Hydrothermal Method

Utilization of Turkish Fly Ash Sources as a candidate zeolite catalyst for partial oxidation of Methane to Methanol

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Catalytic Valorization of Turkish Fly Ash: Fe-Zeolite Design for Methane-to-Methanol Reaction

The transformation of fly ash into catalytic materials offers a promising route for sustainable waste valorization and methane activation. This study investigates Turkish Class F and Class C fly ash as precursors for the synthesis of Fe-zeolite catalysts aimed at the partial oxidation of methane to methanol (MTM). A multifunctional strategy involving oxalic acid was employed to recover iron and induce controlled dealumination, facilitating improvements in mesoporosity and iron site dispersion.

Fe(II) oxalate dihydrate was recovered through acid leaching using a mixture of HCl, H₂SO₄, and oxalic acid, followed by reduction with metallic iron, yielding salts with purities exceeding 98%. These salts were used for ion exchange into FAU- and CHA-type zeolites synthesized via fusion-assisted hydrothermal methods, utilizing NaOH and KOH, respectively. Post-synthesis modifications included water aging, NH₄⁺ exchange, Fe loading, and steam treatment under N₂/steam flow. A mild oxalic acid treatment was also applied in selected cases to further tailor the framework.

Both Fe-FAU and Fe-CHA samples retained high crystallinity following treatment. UV-Vis spectroscopy confirmed the presence of mononuclear Fe³⁺ species around 240 nm, attributed to catalytically relevant iron sites in both frameworks. In MTM reaction tests at 573 K, Fe-FAU samples exhibited consistent methanol productivities up to 151 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹, with reduced coke formation observed following dual steaming. Fe-K-CHA catalysts achieved methanol productivities as high as 310 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹. Moreover, the methanol selectivity reaching 32% under optimized exchange and post-aging conditions. Both catalyst systems suppressed the formation of higher hydrocarbons, favoring selective C₁ oxygenate production.

These results suggest that fly ash-derived zeolites can serve as effective supports for iron-based MTM catalysts. The dual functionality of oxalic acid in metal recovery and framework modification provides a simplified, template-free route for tuning zeolite properties. The compatibility of both FAU and CHA frameworks with this approach underscores its potential applicability in sustainable catalyst design.

Acknowledgments:

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Keyword: Fly ash, zeolite, Methane to Methanol, Fe recovery

Tailoring Particle Morphologies via Controlled Solidification of Liquid Metal Alloys

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Undercooled liquid metals have various potential applications including catalysis, sensors, and drug delivery, making their production and behavior subjects of scientific interest. In addition, they make an excellent model system to study solidification due to their constrained volume. The main steps in microstructure formation during solidification in alloys, which govern the resultant morphology, are nucleation and growth. Nucleation is a stochastic process, making it difficult to control in bulk materials; however, it can be influenced by introducing or removing catalytic sites that serve as initiation points for nucleation. Changing the energy barrier for nucleation, thus the kinetics of the solidification reactions, is a method readily employed in industrial processes to obtain desirable microstructures in metallurgical processes. In smaller scales, such as sub-micron and nanometers, this manipulation can be taken further, as individual nucleants can be isolated in particles produced from the bulk. This makes it possible to obtain individual particles with far less catalytic sites compared to bulk alloys, allowing observation and utilization of phenomena not possible in bulk alloys, such as undercooling values which are orders of magnitude greater. Highly undercooled alloy particles serve as an ideal baseline for further modification, making it possible to obtain distinct morphologies consistently in large batches by introducing catalytic sites and changing solidification conditions. Here we show that various phase distributions, non-trivial to produce in metallic particles, including Janus and tri-block Janus morphologies, can be produced in a large scale by changing their solidification pathways via purely physical methods. To achieve this, top-down approaches are used to modify the distribution and potency of catalytic sites contained inside the liquid particles produced from bulk alloys. In contrast to methods like deposition or chemical modification to produce such particles, which produce core-shell particles, the solidification route allows for uniform phase distribution across the entire core of the particles, resulting in more pronounced anisotropy. The resulting particle morphologies are thoroughly characterized. The exploration of the relation between various parameters, such as thermal history and atmospheric conditions, and the final particle morphology allows us to gather further insight into the mechanics of solidification in constrained volumes. This opens the pathway for further manipulations to obtain more unique structures.

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Keyword: *Liquid Metal Particles, Janus Particles, Nucleation And Growth, Phase Separation*

Halogen-Free Electrolytic Synthesis of LaB₆ in Molten Salts

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Rare-earth borides are attracting increasing attention as advanced materials due to their outstanding electronic, magnetic, and chemical properties. Among them, lanthanum hexaboride (LaB₆) stands out with its high electrical conductivity, ultra-low work function, and excellent thermal and chemical stability, making it a preferred material for thermionic emitter applications.

LaB₆ is traditionally synthesized through methods such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD), metallothermic reduction, and molten salt electrolysis. However, the metallothermic route typically results in low-purity products with undesired by-products, while CVD requires toxic gases, expensive equipment, and is not suitable for large-scale production. According to the literature, molten salt electrolysis generally involves the use of fluoride- or chloride-based electrolytes. While this system can produce high-purity LaB₆, it also generates hazardous gases such as Cl₂ and F₂ during the process, which pose serious environmental, health, and equipment-related risks.

To overcome these limitations, this study introduces a new halogen-free molten salt electrochemical method using borax (Na₂B₄O₇) and lanthanum oxide (La₂O₃) as precursors. The process was carried out at atmospheric pressure in a medium-frequency induction furnace. Graphite was used as the anode and titanium as the cathode. Boron and lanthanum ions were reduced separately but simultaneously in the electrolyte, leading to the formation of stoichiometric LaB₆ directly on the titanium surface. The resulting LaB₆ powder, after acid washing, was obtained with high purity.

This method offers notable advantages, including low cost, operational simplicity, a very short processing time, and environmental friendliness—representing significant progress in LaB₆ synthesis. Moreover, Turkey's globally leading boron reserves offer a strategic advantage for the sustainable production of boride-based advanced materials.

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Keyword: *Lanthanum Hexaboride, Molten Salt Electrolysis, Thermionic Emitter*

Preparation and Characterization of ZnO Nanoparticles for Voltammetric Detection of Antitussive agent

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In this study, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) were synthesized using the solvothermal synthesis technique at different times (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 hours, respectively). The morphological properties of the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were determined by high-resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) analysis, and their crystal structures were investigated by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis. These analyses provided detailed information about the sizes (30.2 nm) and shapes of ZnO nanoparticles, revealing the effects of synthesis time on their morphological properties [1]. Especially, XRD analysis played a crucial role in determining the crystal structure (hexagonal wurtzite) and degree of crystallinity of ZnO NPs, revealing how the crystal structure changed with different synthesis times [1]. In addition, the surface areas of the nanoparticles were measured using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis, thereby providing information about particle sizes. BET analysis has been used as an essential method, particularly in determining the porosity properties of nanoparticles, which provides a critical parameter affecting the material's potential in its applications. In the second stage of the study, the synthesized and characterized ZnO nanoparticles were used for surface modification for electrochemical sensor applications. In this stage, ZnO NPs were modified onto the glassy carbon electrode (GCE) surface and used as electrode material for the sensitive electrochemical detection of butamirate citrate (BC), a non-narcotic antitussive agent. The integration of ZnO NPs onto the GCE surface enhanced the electrochemical performance of the electrode, resulting in higher sensitivity and selectivity in the electrochemical detection of BC. It has been observed that this modification enables faster and more reliable detection of BC, thanks to effective electrochemical properties of ZnO NPs. The square wave voltammetry and stripping conditions parameters were both optimized. Using adsorptive stripping square wave voltammetry, the calibration curve was linear in the 4.00×10^{-8} - 4.00×10^{-5} M range. Using the developed voltammetric method and optimized parameters, the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) of BC were determined to be 6.31×10^{-8} and 1.91×10^{-7} , respectively. The proposed method was utilized to accurately and precisely measure the quantity of BC in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

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Keyword: *ZnO NP, Square wave voltammetry, butamirate citrate, glassy carbon electrode*

TEAM-NANO: Teaming for Excellence and Synergies in Micro/Nanofabrication and Flexible Electronics at SUNUM – Sabanci University Nanotechnology Research and Application Center

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The TEAM-NANO project (EU Grant #101136388), a strategic initiative supported by the European Union and Türkiye's Ministry of Industry and Technology, aims to establish the Sabanci University Nanotechnology Research and Application Center (SUNUM) as a globally recognized Turkish national Center of Excellence (CoE) in nanotechnology, micro/nano fabrication, and flexible electronics. Rooted in the principle of EU's HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-01: Teaming for Excellence, the project seeks to foster strong partnerships between SUNUM and two leading European CoEs: TU-Delft (Netherlands) and the University of Southampton (United Kingdom). These partnerships will contribute to a long-term transformation of Türkiye's Research, Development, and Innovation (R&D&I) ecosystem.

TEAM-NANO enhances SUNUM's R&D infrastructure and human capital, while advancing interdisciplinary research in fields such as wearable sensors, biosensors, MEMS/NEMS devices, and chip technologies. Through structured collaboration and capacity building, the project raises the scientific capabilities of both SUNUM's and Türkiye to international standards, facilitating mutual learning, best practice exchange, and cross-border innovation. It acts as a bridge between the Türkiye's and European research ecosystems.

Aligned with the objectives of European Research Area (ERA), TEAM-NANO promotes collaborative R&D, technology transfer, and active participation in EU research programs. It emphasizes innovation valorization, enabling SUNUM and its partners to translate research outputs into market-ready solutions that address global challenges in health, sustainability, and digitization.

The project actively engages Türkiye's industry and SMEs, supports policy alignment with EU priorities such as the Green Deal, and foster researcher mobility to strengthen the talent pipeline. TEAM-NANO generates impact across scientific excellence, economic development, societal benefit, and global visibility, catalyzing SUNUM's transformation into a world-class CoE.

Ultimately, TEAM-NANO bridges academia, industry, and society- both within Türkiye and across Europe- leaving a lasting legacy of inclusive innovation and deep integration with the ERA.

Keyword: *Micro-nanofabrication, Flexible electronics, Nanotechnology, MEMS/NEMS*

Plasmonic Nanopore Fabrication Using Capillary Force-Assisted Particle Assembly for Single-Molecule Sensing

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In this study, we present a microfabrication-compatible process for integrating nanoparticles onto plasmonic solid-state nanopores with well-defined geometries. Our focus is on nanoparticle trapping within nanoholes using a modified Capillary Force Assisted Particle Assembly (CFAPA) method. Conventional CFAPA methods often rely on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) masters arranged in predefined two-dimensional arrays, which enable geometry-induced trapping of nanoparticles and leverage surface lattice resonances (SLRs). However, these methods involve cumbersome soft lithography processes and extensive surface pretreatment. To address these challenges, we propose a combined approach that integrates solid-state nanopore arrays with CFAPA-based particle trapping. Capillarity-assisted particle deposition is carried out by a commercial controlled particle placement setup, operated under a chemical fume hood. In this method, a small droplet of aqueous Au Nano Particles (NPs) solution (150 nm in diameter) is dragged across the membrane range in an area of $500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}$ including the nanohole arrays with diameters of 190-200 nm. During the process the essential parameters of substrate temperature and velocity, height of the assembled layer, and contact angle are precisely controlled. This method facilitates efficient coupling of the electromagnetic field between the trapped particles and pore walls, leading to the generation of highly localized surface plasmons in a multiple-particles-in-pore (MPP) configuration. This configuration exhibits excellent Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) spectroscopy performance, enabling the sensitive detection of Poly-Arginine (Poly-Arg) molecules ranging from 50 to 150 amino acids (AA) in length, even at very low concentration of 1 nM. The proposed strategy offers robust, stable, scalable, and reusable substrates, paving the way for advanced applications such as single-molecule detection using SERS.

Keyword: *Plasmonic- Microfabrication- CFAPA- SERS*

E-Beam Lithography Process Calibration with Simulated SEM Images using Deep Learning

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Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) plays a crucial role in high-resolution nanofabrication, but its accuracy is highly affected by proximity effect caused by electron scattering and complex process effects, which arise from different fabrication steps such as resist development and etching. Electron scattering can be modelled by Monte-Carlo simulation, leading to a point-spread function (PSF) for the proximity effect correction (PEC). Due to the lack of a physics-based model for the resist development or etching, precise experimental calibration of process correction parameters is required. The state-of-the-art process calibration is based on SEM imaging and measuring critical dimensions (CDs) of about 50 lines in a calibration pattern after exposure, development and pattern transfer (etching or lift-off). This procedure uses only one-dimensional (1D) structures for calibration and can be improved in efficiency by using 2D calibration patterns, thereby reducing both the metrology effort and metrology-induced noise. This study investigates the application of machine learning techniques for image processing in EBL process calibration using only a minimum number of 2D SEM images.

We propose a smart 2D calibration pattern (see Fig. 1) designed to fit within the field of view (FOV) of a typical SEM. This compact design consists of a 7x7 array of dose-varied squares at the center and density variation in the surroundings to capture a wide variety of e-beam and process effects. It aims to provide enhanced accuracy for capturing 2D effects, and its compact form also allows seamless integration with machine learning models. Next, we employed a deep learning model to capture and map the image data to continuous correction parameters. The model was trained with a dataset of synthetic SEM generated images based on simulated data. Synthetic SEM images were generated with exposure parameters varied within physically relevant ranges. Simulation parameters were used as labels for the images during training.

We present a detailed discussion and evaluation of our trained model on simulated SEM images. Furthermore, we discuss its potential applicability to real SEM data, highlighting promising directions for future adaptation.

Figure 1. 2D calibration pattern (a) with 7x7 array of squares at the center (b) and different background densities in the surroundings (%0-%25-%50-%75-%100) (c).

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Keyword: *Electron Beam Lithography, Process Calibration, Deep Learning*

A Nanoenterprise Ecosystem Based on Academic Excellence and Collaboration for Rapid Test Kit Development

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Rapid advancements in technology require collaboration across diverse disciplines. At Ege University, we established a multidisciplinary nanostartup ecosystem by bringing together experts from biochemistry, bioengineering, mechanical engineering, medicine, and an industry partner. The initial product developed within this ecosystem is ErasenseDx Respira, a rapid antigen test kit designed for detecting RSV, Influenza B, Influenza A, and SARS-CoV-2 from nasal and nasopharyngeal swabs, suitable for both professional and home use.

For the design and validation of ErasenseDx Respira, analytical and clinical performance studies were performed. Analytical evaluations utilized bacterial and viral strains provided by ATCC and NIBSC. Detection limits were reported as 6.68×10^3 PFU/mL, 2.47×10^4 PFU/mL, 8.23×10^2 PFU/mL, and 27.43 IU/mL. for RSV, Influenza B, Influenza A and SARS-CoV-2, respectively. Cross-reactivity and interference analyses involving 18 common respiratory pathogens demonstrated no cross-reactivity or interference. Additionally, interference tests with common respiratory medications indicated no false results.

Following analytical validation, clinical studies involved 1,074 patients, among whom 25 were positive for RSV, 25 for Influenza B, 102 for Influenza A, and 109 for SARS-CoV-2. Clinical outcomes exhibited the following sensitivities and specificities:

SARS-CoV-2: Sensitivities were 95.41% (nasopharyngeal), 82.57% (nasal), and 87.10% (self-testing), with specificities of 99.06%, 99.38%, and 99.48%, respectively. **Influenza B:** Sensitivities were 88.00% (nasopharyngeal), 76.00% (nasal), and 70.00% (self-testing), with specificities of 99.91%, 99.34%, and 99.40%. **RSV:** Sensitivities were 84.00% (nasopharyngeal), 60.00% (nasal), and 64.29% (self-testing), with specificities of 99.24%, 99.33%, and 99.88%. **Influenza A:** Sensitivities were 82.35% (nasopharyngeal), 79.41% (nasal), and 79.45% (self-testing), with specificities of 99.49%, 98.67%, and 98.82%.

These results demonstrate that ErasenseDx Respira is a reliable and effective diagnostic tool for rapidly identifying multiple respiratory pathogens.

Keyword: Start-up, Rapid test, Industry, ErasenseDx Respira

Elastocapillary Effect on Bacterial Biofilms

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Bacterial biofilms use nanofilaments to shape their dispersive motility and colony morphology. This presentation explores how elastocapillary forces govern the self-organization and surface adhesion of filamentous *Bacillus subtilis* biofilms. We begin by modeling the interplay between capillary forces and elastic bending in growing bacterial filaments to predict folding and chaining behavior on hydrophobic (smooth) versus biologically adhesive substrates. Building on the hypothesis that conductive nanowires enhance surface anchoring, we derive stress and tension profiles using Newton's equations and energy minimization. Numerical simulations illustrate characteristic folding patterns and identify stability regimes as a function of filament stiffness and interfacial tension. Finally, we discuss implications for biofilm mechanics and propose circadian regulation of nanowire expression as a promising avenue for further study.

Keyword: *biofilm, nanofilament, computation, elastocapillary*

Dynamic Behaviour of Liquid-Liquid Interfaces and a Microfluidic Reservoir-on-a-Chip Micromodel Under Acoustic Fields

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Understanding the dynamics of immiscible fluid interfaces under acoustic fields is essential for advancing multiphase flow technologies, with implications across enhanced oil recovery (EOR), pharmaceutical formulations, chemical processing, and droplet-based microfluidics. In this study, we explore the spatiotemporal behavior of the oil–water interface within microfluidic channels subjected to traveling acoustic waves, both continuous and pulsatile. We observed that, in the absence of actuation (Acoustics OFF), the interface remains stationary, stabilized by surface tension and pressure differences. Upon acoustic activation (Acoustics ON), the interface undergoes immediate displacement driven by acoustic radiation forces, followed by dynamic stabilization. We further examined the role of interface curvature by comparing channel geometries of different widths. Results showed that narrower channels, with higher initial curvature, exhibited greater initial displacement and slower stabilization due to enhanced capillary resistance. This effect highlights the interplay between confinement, surface tension, and viscous drag in determining interface response. Pulsatile acoustic excitation at varying pulsation frequencies (0.1 Hz, 0.25 Hz, and 12 Hz) revealed frequency-dependent behaviors. At low frequencies, the interface displayed pronounced cycles of displacement, overshoot, and recovery—indicating strong inertial effects and full relaxation between cycles. At moderate frequencies, partial stabilization was observed within each cycle, while high-frequency actuation produced quasi-continuous interface motion with minimal overshoot, reflecting limited time for mechanical recovery. To evaluate the practical impact of these dynamics, we developed a microfluidic reservoir-on-a-chip micromodel that mimics the pore-scale geometry of natural oil-bearing formations. Under continuous acoustic actuation, oil recovery increased from ~41.7% (control) to ~65.3%, driven by interface oscillations that mobilized trapped oil and reactivated stagnant regions. Pulsatile regimes also yielded enhanced recovery, confirming the capacity of acoustic fields to overcome capillary barriers and promote redistribution. This study establishes a comprehensive framework for understanding and harnessing acoustically driven interfacial dynamics in confined systems. Our findings offer a tunable, non-invasive strategy for enhancing multiphase displacement processes in energy and microfluidic applications.

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Keyword: *Interface Instability, Fluid-Fluid Interfaces, Acoustofluidics, Reservoir-on-a-Chip*

Comparison of The Adsorption Preferences of CO₂, SO₂, and N₂ on HKUST-1 Surfaces – A DFT Study

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Excessive production of carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the main source of global warming and climate change. CO₂ capture from post-combustion is currently the primary source of carbon capture systems. Post-combustion flue gas mainly contains CO₂, O₂, H₂S, SO_x, NO_x, and large amounts of water vapor and N₂. Zeolites, carbonaceous materials, mesoporous silica materials and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are the most used adsorbents for physical adsorption of CO₂ [1]. HKUST-1, which is one of the most studied MOFs for CO₂ capture, consists of Cu₃(BTC)₂ units (BTC = 1,3,5-benzene tricarboxylate). The main structure consists of two metal centers (Cu²⁺) connected via four carboxylic groups belonging to the BTC linker molecules [2]. The objective of this work is to compare the adsorption preferences of CO₂, SO₂ and N₂ on the different HKUST-1 structures to investigate the effect of the single or bi-metallic structures on the adsorption performance of the mentioned molecules. The method employed in this study is wB97XD functional with 6-31G(d,p) basis set for O, C, H, S and N atoms and LanL2DZ for Fe and Cu atoms. Results show that physisorption of N₂ is not feasible with positive Gibbs Free Energy change. Although both CO₂ and SO₂ have negative and similar Gibbs Free Energy change on Cu-HKUST-1 and Fe-HKUST-1, FeCu-HKUST-1 structure is found to be selective for the adsorption of CO₂.

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Keyword: *HKUST-1, CO₂ adsorption, DFT*

Studying the Adsorption of Sodium Atoms on the surface of Magnesium oxide by Density Functional Theory

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In this study, we utilize Density Functional Theory (DFT) to calculate the adsorption energy of sodium atoms on magnesium oxide (MgO) surfaces. The calculations are performed using the Full Potential Linear Augmented Plane Wave method, including local orbitals, as implemented in WIEN2K. We investigate sodium adsorption on MgO surfaces along the [100], [110], and [111] crystallographic directions.

The optimized lattice constant used for constructing the slabs is the rock-salt optimized lattice constant of 8.045 atomic units (a.u.). The stability of each surface has been verified using the following converged input parameters: $R_{\text{mtKmax}} = 5$, $G_{\text{max}} = 20$, and a K-point sampling of the Brillouin zone with a grid of $4 \times 4 \times 2$, which results in 24 k-points for the slab calculations. A vacuum of 15 Å is maintained between the slabs in all simulations to prevent periodic interactions. Each slab is fully relaxed, with the bottom two layers held fixed during the relaxation process. After adding sodium atoms, the slabs are fully relaxed once more. The cohesive energy for sodium adsorption on the MgO surface along the [100] direction is stable, regardless of whether magnesium or oxygen atoms are present on the surface.

Keyword: *DFT, Sodium, Adsorption energy, Surface adsorption MgO*

First-Principles Investigation of Water Splitting on Cu₁₄Co₁₂Pt₁₂ Clusters: Electronic Structure and Catalytic Insights

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Understanding the atomistic mechanisms governing hydrogen evolution in water splitting is of great importance for efficient catalyst design. Due to the synergetic effects between Pt and Cu on water splitting, bimetallic Pt-Cu nanoclusters in alkaline media offer a promising platform for HER compared to the pure nanoclusters (Kaya et al., 2023). Building upon the alloying strategy, we present a detailed density functional theory (DFT) study of the HER-relevant water splitting process to elucidate the synergetic effects; and hence, tuning the catalytic activity for a more rational catalyst design. To unravel the catalytic activity at the atomic scale, we computed the d-band centers for various surface sites, providing a descriptor for hydrogen binding and catalytic behavior. Multiple adsorption configurations were evaluated to identify the most favorable H₂O adsorption sites, and corresponding adsorption energies were calculated. We further analyzed the projected density of states (PDOS) for both molecularly adsorbed H₂O and its dissociated products (OH + H) to assess charge redistribution and electronic hybridization upon adsorption. Finally, we determined the Gibbs free energy difference (ΔG) for the elementary water dissociation reaction (H₂O → OH + H), offering thermodynamic insight into the activation step of HER. The spin-polarized calculations capture the magnetic contributions of Co atoms and their influence on the electronic structure and reactivity of the cluster. This theoretical work contributes fundamental understanding toward the rational design of trimetallic HER catalysts for sustainable hydrogen production.

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Keyword: *Hydrogen evolution reactions, Water Splitting, Density Functional Theory, Trimetallic Clusters*

First-Principles Design of Altermagnetic Materials: RuO₂ as a Case Study

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This study explores the first principles design of materials with altermagnetic properties, a newly identified class of magnetic materials that exhibit characteristics distinct from conventional ferromagnetic (FM) and antiferromagnetic (AFM) materials. Unlike FM and AFM materials, altermagnets display collinear magnetic ordering while exhibiting phenomena such as the Anomalous Hall effect, large Spin Hall conductivity, and spin torque transfer, all without net magnetization. Additionally, they lack the drawbacks of stray fields or sensitivity to external magnetic fields while they can perform in higher frequencies as opposed to FM materials. Due to these advantages, they are ideal candidates for next-generation spintronic components, such as spin filters, memory devices, and logic circuits.

Building on the recently proposed spin-group formalism, this research aims to identify, analyze, and predict candidate altermagnetic materials using a systematic computational workflow. The study begins with RuO₂ as a primary subject due to its recently recognized—and still debated—altermagnetic behavior. Results have been obtained through ab initio calculations of structure optimization, magnetization, spin-polarized band structures, and Hall effect properties. For this aim, ground state Kohn-Sham calculations were used to generate data for Wannier function-based analysis of Berry curvature and Hall conductivities. Additionally, the effect of Hubbard-U correction on these properties is investigated. In the next step of this work, the effects of doping, strain, and stacking on the electronic properties of altermagnetic materials will be investigated. Eventually, the workflow of methods developed in this project will be utilized for newly proposed altermagnetic candidate materials.

Keyword: *altermagnetism, first-principles calculations, spintronics, Spin Hall conductivity*

High-Performance and Energy-Efficient Sub-5 nm 2D Double-Gate MOSFETs Based on SiAs Monolayers

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As the demand for high-performance (HP), energy-efficient transistors grows, traditional silicon-based metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) face significant scaling limitations. To overcome these challenges and sustain advancements in semiconductor technology, new materials, and device architectures are being explored. In this study, sub-5 nm double-gate (DG) MOSFETs based on two-dimensional (2D) SiAs are investigated using first-principles calculations and the Non-equilibrium Green's function (NEGF) formalism to assess their potential as a HP alternative. SiAs monolayers exhibit an indirect bandgap of 1.58 eV and demonstrate promising electronic properties. Key performance metrics such as the on/off current ratio (I_{on}/I_{off}), subthreshold swing (SS), gate capacitance (C_g), intrinsic delay time (τ), and power-delay product (PDP) are evaluated. Devices with 1 nm and 2 nm underlap (UL) structures show enhanced performance, achieving on-state current (I_{on}) values up to $1206 \mu A/\mu m^{-1}$, meeting the International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS) 2028 HP standards. The SS ranges from 112 to 142 mV/dec, and minimized τ and PDP indicate the suitability of SiAs transistors for ultra-scaled, energy-efficient applications. These results suggest that 2D SiAs transistors offer a promising solution to the scaling challenges of traditional MOSFET technologies with potential for future semiconductor innovations.

Keyword: *2D materials, Computational Nanoscience, MOSFET*

Electronic Transport Properties of Nearly Flat Bands in Biphenylene Networks

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Since the discovery of graphene, many graphene derivatives have been studied theoretically and some have been experimentally realized with advanced techniques. Among these, carbon biphenylene, which consists of periodically ordered 4-6-8 carbon rings and in which all carbons are three-fold coordinated, was successfully synthesized in 2021 by Fan et.al [1]. Among the most notable features of the carbon biphenylene network are its semiconducting behavior under tensile strain and the ability of various periodic table elements (e.g., from groups IV–IV, III–V, II, VI) to integrate into its structure in place of carbon [2,3]. The distinctive electronic band structures of two-dimensional anisotropic biphenylene structures have encouraged us to investigate their electronic transport properties. In this study, electron and hole mobilities of two-dimensional biphenylenes have been calculated by using both Deformation Potential Theory (DP) and Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE) methods. Resulting values show that there are significant differences between the mobilities obtained from DP theory and BTE, especially due to the nearly flat valence band characteristic of biphenylene structures.

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Keyword: 2D Materials, Density Functional Theory, Electronic Transport Properties

Single-step Supercapacitor Fabrication and Performance Evaluation on Graphenated Carbon Nanotube Cotton or Ni-foam

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The development of efficient, scalable, and cost-effective fabrication methods is essential for advance supercapacitor technologies, especially for integration into flexible, wearable, and on-chip energy storage systems. Traditional fabrication routes for supercapacitors often involve multiple discrete steps, including electrode synthesis, binder addition, slurry casting, and post-processing (heating etc.), which not only increase the complexity and cost of production but also introduce interfacial resistances, surface-to-volume ratio loss, conductivity loss and performance losses. Therefore, single-step supercapacitor fabrication methods have attracted increasing attention, due to enabling direct synthesizing or assembling the active electrode material onto the current collector or device structure in a single process.

In this study, we have investigated the integration of graphenated carbon nanotube (G-CNT) cotton and Ni-foam with transition metal sulfides either in 2D-forms (WS_2 and MoS_2) or in 3D forms Ni_3S_2 structures using various techniques, including radio frequency (RF) sputtering, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and wet chemical adsorption. RF sputtering enabled the formation of vertically aligned nano-wall structures of MoS_2 and WS_2 , significantly increasing the surface-to-volume ratio. This method has yielded specific capacitances of 98 mF/cm^2 for MoS_2 and 131 mF/cm^2 for WS_2 . Similarly, CVD produced vertical morphologies like those from sputtering except for being thinner structures, resulting in a specific capacitance of 132 mF/cm^2 for $MoS_2/G-CNT$ composites. For the wet chemical adsorption approach, G-CNT cotton was immersed in a sonicated isopropanol (IPA) solution of MoS_2 and allowed to soak until complete evaporation of the solvent, facilitating the infiltration of MoS_2 into the porous carbon matrix. After drying, this method achieved a maximum specific capacitance of 57 mF/cm^2 . Single-step sputtered Ni-foam/ Ni_3S_2 has shown 590 $mF cm^{-2}$ in specific capacitance at 1 $mA cm^{-2}$ an electrode form.

Keyword: supercapacitor, 2D materials, carbon materials

Photoluminescence Properties Of Carbon- And Silicon-Doped Point Defects In h-BN: A First-Principles DFT Study

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Defect engineering in two-dimensional hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) offers a versatile platform for integrated quantum photonic and spintronic devices due to its wide band gap, chemical inertness, and atomically flat lattice that supports isolated, atom-like emitters with minimal background fluorescence. We perform a first-principles DFT study of eight underexplored point defects, carbon- or silicon-doped separately at boron and nitrogen sites, each with and without a neighboring vacancy, in a $5 \times 5 \times 1$ h-BN supercell. All configurations exhibit negative formation energies (-1.081 to -0.907 eV) and maintain structural integrity during 10 ps of molecular dynamics at 300 K, confirming thermal stability. Spin-orbit-coupled band-structure calculations reveal defect-induced states that tune the intrinsic gap. In addition, constrained DFT (cDFT) is used to optimize excited-state geometries, and phonon calculations yield vibrational modes for extracting Huang–Rhys (HR) and Debye–Waller (DW) factors.

Optical metrics include zero-phonon-line wavelength (λ_{ZPL}), configuration-coordinate displacement (ΔQ), HR factors (electron–phonon coupling strength), and DW factors (ZPL coherence). Among carbon-doped defects, C_{2B} without vacancy delivers $\lambda_{ZPL} = 1622$ nm, $\Delta Q = 0.266$ Å, HR = 1.011, and DW = 0.364, ideal for telecom-band single-photon emission with minimal phonon sidebands. Introducing a neighboring nitrogen vacancy ($C_{2B}V_N$) raises HR to 8.51, lowers DW, degrades coherence, and activates a $1 \mu_B$ magnetic moment. Silicon-doped $Si_{2N}V_B$ combines $\lambda_{ZPL} = 1350$ nm, $\Delta Q = 0.342$ Å, HR = 1.322, and DW = 0.267 with a $1 \mu_B$ moment, offering both high optical coherence and spin functionality. By contrast, Si_{2B} and Si_{2N} without vacancies exhibit stronger phonon coupling and weaker coherence.

These atomically precise defect designs yield room-temperature-stable quantum emitters with narrow linewidths and tunable magnetic moments. In particular, C_{2B} centers provide telecom-compatible, high-coherence emission, while $Si_{2N}V_B$ defects integrate spin and photon degrees of freedom, making them promising candidates for on-chip quantum communication nodes, integrated photonic circuits, and hybrid spin–photon interfaces.

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Keyword: 2D Materials, Quantum Emitters, Photoluminescence, Density Functional Theory

Anodized Ti13Nb13Zr Alloy for Orthopedic Applications

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Titanium and its alloys are widely used in orthopedic applications due to their superior corrosion resistance and favorable mechanical properties. However, their bioinert nature necessitates additional surface modifications to enhance osseointegration and long-term implant stability [1]. Anodization is a promising surface modification approach that can improve cellular interactions of titanium (Ti) alloy surface by producing nanostructured topographies known to stimulate bone cell functions [2]. On the other hand, Ti13Nb13Zr is a dual-phase titanium alloy with a significantly lower elastic modulus than pure titanium and most other metallic materials used in orthopedics, thereby reducing the stress shielding effect. In this study, to enhance cellular interactions, oxide layers with two different morphologies were formed on the Ti13Nb13Zr alloy via anodization. Anodization was conducted in an ethylene glycol-based electrolyte containing fluoride ions and water. By altering anodization parameters (F^- concentration, water concentration, voltage and duration) two distinct surface morphologies featuring nano and sub-micron scale structures were obtained. Surface properties and biological interactions of the anodized Ti13Nb13Zr samples were characterized using SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy), XPS (X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy), TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy), AFM (Atomic Force Microscopy), and WCA (water contact angle) measurements. For cytocompatibility assessment, MC3T3-E1 (pre-osteoblastic cell line derived from mouse) viability was evaluated on the 1, 3, and 5 days using 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide (MTT) assay. Additionally, cells were stained with rhodamine and DAPI to image f-actin filaments and nuclei, respectively. The MTT assay results indicated that the anodized Ti13Nb13Zr samples having either surface morphology exhibited no cytotoxic effects towards MC3T3-E1 cells over 5 days of in vitro. Cell proliferation and spreading improved on the anodized surfaces compared to its non-anodized control. These findings collectively indicate that anodized Ti13Nb13Zr is a promising material for orthopedic applications.

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Keyword: Anodization, Orthopedics, Biocompatibility, Titanium Alloy

Development of Hyaluronic Acid-Coated/Curcumin-Loaded Polycaprolactone Membranes for Biofunctional Wound Dressing Applications

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Chronic wounds impose a significant global healthcare burden, necessitating the development of advanced wound dressings that are both biocompatible and biodegradable [1]. Among various options, polymer-based wound dressings, particularly those incorporating natural bioactive compounds, have gained increasing attention due to their ability to accelerate healing while minimizing adverse effects [2, 3]. In this study, poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), a biodegradable and biocompatible aliphatic polyester, was utilized to fabricate fibrous membranes via electrospinning. To enhance the wound healing functionality of the scaffolds, the nanofiber surfaces were further modified by dip-coating with 1 wt.% hyaluronic acid (HA), a naturally occurring glycosaminoglycan known for its role in tissue hydration and regeneration (PCL/HA). Additionally, curcumin (Cur), a polyphenolic compound with well-documented anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities, was incorporated into the PCL matrix to improve the overall bioactivity of the system (PCL-Cur). The morphology of the produced fibers was evaluated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), confirming the formation of uniform, bead-free nanofibers. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) analysis revealed an increase in surface roughness after curcumin incorporation, rising from 187 ± 36 nm to 245 ± 65 nm. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) verified the successful integration of both HA and Cur into the PCL structure. Water contact angle (WCA) measurements demonstrated that HA coating improved surface hydrophilicity. The measured WCA values were 136.0° , 125.4° , 82.1° , and 77.9° for PCL, PCL-Cur, PCL/HA, and PCL-Cur/HA membranes, respectively, indicating enhanced wettability, particularly in HA-coated samples. This study presents a straightforward yet effective approach for designing multifunctional nanofibrous scaffolds by integrating structural polymers, bioactive agents, and surface modifiers. The developed system exhibits promising characteristics for wound healing applications, including enhanced surface properties and biocompatibility.

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Keyword: Poly(ϵ -caprolactone), Curcumin, Hyaluronic Acid, Wound dressing

Lignin Nanoparticles From Food-Derived Waste For Sustainable Nanotherapeutics

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Converting food-derived organic waste into functional nanomaterials presents a promising approach for sustainable drug delivery technologies. In this study, lignin was extracted from commonly discarded materials such as used tea leaves and walnut shells. These sources were selected for their availability and potential as renewable sources for photodynamically active nanoparticles. Extraction was performed using source-specific soda pulping protocols in a hydrothermal autoclave at a constant solid-to-liquid ratio. The resulting lignin powders were characterized using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Nanoparticles were synthesized by nanoprecipitation at a fixed solvent-to-non-solvent ratio (S/NS: 1/5). Lignin from each source was dissolved in DMF at two concentrations (5 and 10 mg/mL) and injected into the non-solvent phase (1% PVA in 0.1 mM HCl) using a syringe pump at a constant rate to ensure reproducibility. Methylene blue (MB) was added to solvent phase (0.5 mg/mL) as a model photosensitizer to evaluate both drug loading capacity and photodynamic activity. Particle characterization included Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) for hydrodynamic size and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) for morphological analysis. Drug loading was quantified spectrophotometrically, and reactive oxygen species production was assessed indirectly by monitoring the absorbance change of a singlet oxygen quencher (DPBF). These preliminary findings support the potential of post-consumer biomass as a viable source for lignin-based nanocarriers with therapeutic applications. Overall, the study presents a simple and cost-effective strategy for integrating green nanotechnology with biomedical innovation, while contributing to waste valorization and environmental sustainability.

Keyword: *Lignin nanoparticles, Drug delivery, Photodynamic therapy*

Decoding the Nanoscale: The Role of SAXS in Modern Nanotechnology Research

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Xenocs provides state-of-the-art instrumentation for Small-Angle, Wide-Angle, and Ultra-Small-Angle X-ray scattering (SAXS, WAXS, and USAXS) enabling comprehensive structural characterization at the nanoscale. Our laboratory systems, ranging from compact vertical SAXS/WAXS systems to high-end modular beamline-grade instruments, integrate innovative hardware, powerful data analysis software (XSACT Pro), and versatile sample environments for in situ and operando studies.

This presentation will offer a concise overview of SAXS principles and capabilities, highlighting key strengths such as direct modeling of particle size and shape, as well as the analysis of complex, hierarchical structures. We will showcase recent developments such as automated detector positioning for simultaneous SWAXS, advanced imaging modules (InXight), and new approaches for time-resolved and phase-contrast imaging.

Through selected case studies, we will illustrate how SAXS enables breakthroughs in fields such as nanomaterials, pharmaceuticals, polymers, energy storage, and biostructural research. Examples include nanoparticle size distribution, pore analysis in carbon materials for sodium-ion batteries, and formulation optimization of mRNA-loaded lipid nanoparticles. Together, these applications demonstrate how SAXS provides unique insights into material structure, dynamics, and performance with minimal sample preparation and non-destructive analysis.

Keyword: SAXS, nanoscale, in situ, nanomaterials, polymers, pharmaceutical research, nanoparticles, characterization

Advancing Colloidal Optical Gain: Rational Design of Colloidal Quantum Well Heterostructures for Next-Generation Lasers

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Colloidal quantum wells (CQWs) are promising gain media for next-generation nanolasers owing to their exceptional optoelectronic features such as inherently weak Auger recombination, large absorption cross-section, low synthesis cost, and highly tunable optical properties. Still, commercialization of semiconductor nanocrystal based photonic devices face fundamental challenges intrinsic to confined semiconductors, which must be overcome through rational design and engineering of their advanced heterostructures. Here, we introduce several design strategies to address the hitherto limitations of CQWs as gain materials and implemented advanced synthetic methods to develop variety of rational heterostructures, allowing us to uncover detailed structure-property relationships. Our spectral and time-resolved gain measurements revealed the mechanisms governing their performance and directed iterative improvements to the CQW architecture. The outcome is a set of CQW heterostructures that simultaneously exhibit ultralow gain thresholds, very large material gain coefficients, and extended gain lifetimes—meeting every key criterion for high-quality gain media. We demonstrated proof-of-concept devices underlining these advancements including those in high-performance amplified spontaneous emission from solutions and whispering-gallery-mode lasing with record-low thresholds. Altogether, this research direction shows that such meticulously engineered CQW heterostructures serve as outstanding gain materials for future photonic devices.

Keyword: *colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals, colloidal quantum wells, optical gain, lasing*

Interface Design of Metal Oxide Nanoflower Spheres to Enhance the Thermal-Physical Properties of Molten Salts for Concentrated Solar Power Plants

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In recent years, the global demand for clean, sustainable, and efficient energy has increased significantly. To meet this need, investigating renewable and environmentally friendly energy sources are important. Concentrated solar power (CSP) plants have emerged as a promising solution. The performance of CSP systems is highly dependent on the thermal properties of the heat transfer fluids (HTFs) used. Recent studies have shown that nanoparticle enhanced molten salts are able to provide outstanding thermophysical properties, such as improved specific heat capacity, wider working temperature range, lower viscosity, and enhanced thermal stability. In this study, flower shaped manganese nanoparticles (FAMNP) were integrated into conventional molten salts (MS) to improve their thermal performance. These nanostructures were successfully synthesized with the desired morphology by two distinct approaches: direct growth on the salt surface and wet-chemical synthesis (Figure 1). FAMNP confirmed to be manganese oxide through X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis. A two-stage crystallization protocol was employed to ensure homogeneous distribution and stable integration of nanoparticles into the salt matrix. This study aims to reduce melting point, improve thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, and minimize nanoparticle aggregation. The crystalline structures of FAMNP/MS composites were characterized by X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). Following the first crystallization step, the specific heat capacity (C_p) was measured as $0.716 \text{ J/g}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ in the $140\text{--}230^\circ\text{C}$ range based on DSC analysis. Pure potassium nitrate has a melting point of 334°C and a decomposition temperature of 634°C . In contrast, the FAMNP/MS composite displayed a significantly decreased melting point of 131°C and a higher decomposition temperature of 686°C , according to DSC and TGA analysis. The reduced melting point helps to prevent pipe blockages caused by phase changes during temperature differences, while the elevated decomposition temperature allows a wider operating range. This wider thermal range results in increased sensible heat storage within the same system, eventually improving thermal efficiency. These improvements demonstrate that the FAMNP/MS composite offers significant advantages over conventional molten salts and holds great potential for advanced CSP applications.

Figure 1: High-resolution SEM images of pure MNO nanoparticles, a) produced with wet chemical synthesis b) produced with direct growth, c and d) SEM image of nanoparticles in the molten salt matrix

Keyword: Concentrated Solar Power Plants, Heat Transfer Fluids, Molten Salts, Crystallization

Laser-induced based microsupercapacitors

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The laser processing technique produces porous graphene, called laser-induced graphene (LIG), from materials such as polyimide, wood, lignin, and cellulose. In this way, technical challenges encountered in other graphene production methods—such as the use of toxic chemicals and the need for high temperatures—are eliminated. Furthermore, these graphene structures, which possess high conductivity and a large surface area, can be patterned onto a surface with high resolution and in the desired architecture. Such LIG structures can be utilized in electronics, sensors, actuators, and micro-energy storage devices. Despite these advantages, untreated LIG structures exhibit relatively low capacity values, which limits their application areas. Therefore, functional materials such as transition metal oxides and conductive polymers are coated onto the LIG surface to enhance supercapacitor performance. Additionally, before laser processing to obtain graphene, the surface can be treated with additives such as melamine or thiourea, enabling the production of N/S-doped graphene structures. N-doped graphene introduces electron-rich regions that improve charge transfer kinetics and pseudocapacitance, while S-doped graphene alters the electronic structure of the carbon lattice, increasing surface reactivity and conductivity. These doping configurations synergize with accumulated materials to enhance specific capacitance and electrochemical stability. As a new approach, studies are being conducted on simultaneous graphene/metal oxide production using polyamic acid resin mixed with metal salts. These developments enable LIG to become a scalable, multifunctional material for next-generation energy storage and sensor devices.

Keyword: *Laser induced graphene, Micro-supercapacitors, Electrodeposition, Surface Functionalization*

Influence of Halogen Substitution on the Performance of BDT-Based Donor Polymers in Organic Solar Cells

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Solar cells are devices that directly convert sunlight into electrical energy through the photoelectric effect. Organic solar cells (OSCs), in particular, have emerged as a promising photovoltaic technology due to their potential for lightweight, flexible devices and low-cost, large-scale production. Benzodithiophene (BDT)-based donor polymers are widely used in OSCs due to their strong light absorption, efficient charge transport, and structural tunability. Moreover, halogenation, especially fluorine and chlorine substitution, is a common approach to lowering the HOMO energy level and improving device performance. In this work, two novel BDT-based donor- π -acceptor type polymers with fluorine and chlorine substitution synthesized to investigate the impact of halogenation on photovoltaic performance. The polymers were characterized using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, and used in fabrication of both binary and ternary organic solar cells. The best device performances for both polymers were achieved with ternary organic solar cells fabricated with the device structure of ITO/PEDOT:PSS/Active layer/PDINN/Ag. The device fabricated with the chlorine-substituted polymer demonstrated a power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 12.82%, a short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) of 22.37 mA/cm², an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 0.85 V, and a fill factor (FF) of 67.43%.

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Keyword: *Halogenation, Benzodithiophene, Ternary OSCs, Organic photovoltaics*

Benzodithiophene Dione Based Polymers for Organic Solar Cell Applications

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In this study, electron deficient benzodithiophene dione (BDD) and electron rich benzothiophene (BDT) bearing two polymers P1 and P2 were synthesized. Polymers P1 and P2 have fluorine and chlorine atoms, respectively. Electronic and optical properties of the polymers were investigated. Effect of different halogens (F and Cl) on electronic properties and photovoltaic performance were examined. The HOMO and LUMO energy levels of P1 ($-5.64\text{ eV} / -3.68\text{ eV}$) and P2 ($-5.58\text{ eV} / -3.57\text{ eV}$) are well aligned with those of Y6, indicating their suitability for blending in a donor-acceptor system. Photovoltaic performances of P1 and P2 were investigated with the OSC architecture of ITO / SAM / polymer: Y6 / CIL / Ag. Organic solar cell device fabrications and characterizations were performed in nitrogen filled glove box system. J-V characterizations were carried out under illumination of AM 1.5G solar simulator.

P1 incorporated organic solar cells (OSCs) showed superior performance and had power conversion efficiency (PCE) value of 11.07 % with a V_{OC} value of 0.78V, a J_{SC} value of 20.27 mA/cm^2 and a fill factor of 0.70.

Keyword: *Organic solar cells, Polymer, non-fullerene acceptor*

Fluorene-Based Passivation Strategy for Enhancing the NiOx/Perovskite Interface in Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells

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Nickel oxide (NiOx) is widely employed as a hole transport layer (HTL) in inverted perovskite solar cells (PSCs) due to its favorable energy alignment. However, the presence of various nickel oxidation states—such as Ni(OH)₂ and Ni₂O₃—can degrade the perovskite layer and increase charge carrier recombination at the interface, limiting power conversion efficiency (PCE) and stability. To address these interfacial issues, this study introduces a novel fluorene-based passivation molecule, 2,7-di(10H-phenoxazin-10-yl)spiro[fluorene-9,2'-[1,3]dioxolane] (**FPO-O**), specifically designed for NiOx-based p-i-n PSCs.

 A diagram of a structure AI-generated content may be incorrect.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the **FPO-O**-modified PSC architecture.

FPO-O offers key advantages: it is cost-effective (≈ \$3/g), compatible with thermal evaporation, and exhibits favorable electronic properties. Structurally inspired by the DFH molecule¹, **FPO-O** features a more rigid design aimed at enhancing hole transfer and passivation efficiency. The phenoxazine moiety within **FPO-O** contributes to effective surface passivation by interacting with undercoordinated Pb²⁺ ions in the perovskite layer.

The study proceeds in three phases: synthesis and structural characterization of **FPO-O**, deposition on sputtered NiOx, and fabrication of PSCs to assess performance. Devices treated with **FPO-O** layers of varying thickness (0.5–1.5 nm) were evaluated through spectroscopic, electrical, and stability analyses. Results revealed that a 0.5 nm **FPO-O** layer led to optimal improvements in open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) and short-circuit current density (J_{SC}), increasing the PCE from 17.07% (reference) to 18.71%.

Moreover, thermal stability tests at 85 °C under nitrogen showed that the 0.5 nm **FPO-O** device retained 100% of its efficiency after 24 hours, outperforming both thicker **FPO-O** layers and the reference device. These findings highlight the potential of **FPO-O** as a scalable and effective passivation strategy to enhance both the efficiency and operational durability of inverted PSCs.

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Keyword: Perovskite Solar Cells, NiOx passivation, Evaporated passivation layer, Organic Small Molecule

Tailoring Charge Storage Properties of Polypyrrole via Rare-Earth Ion Engineering for High-Performance Supercapacitors

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This study explores the enhancement of supercapacitor performance through the incorporation of cerium ions into polypyrrole (PPy) nanofibers. The PPy and cerium-doped PPy (PPy:Ce) nanofibers were synthesized via in situ oxidative polymerization. Cerium ions were directly introduced into the polymer matrix, enabling redox modulation and structural tuning without forming a crystalline oxide phase. FTIR spectroscopy revealed vibrational shifts and band suppression associated with Ce–N coordination and structural distortions. EPR analysis confirmed an increased density of paramagnetic centers in PPy:Ce composites, indicating enhanced charge carrier availability and defect-induced conductivity. BET analysis showed that while cerium incorporation reduced surface area, it facilitated the formation of larger mesopores, improving ion accessibility and electrolyte interaction. Electrochemical tests conducted in a symmetric two-electrode setup demonstrated that the PPy:Ce5 composition exhibited superior performance, achieving a specific capacitance of 203 F g⁻¹ and an energy density of 21.3 Wh kg⁻¹. Dunn's analysis indicated a transition from capacitive to diffusion-controlled pseudocapacitive behavior upon cerium doping. These results highlight the critical role of rare-earth ion engineering in optimizing polymer-based electrodes for next-generation energy storage devices.

Keyword: *Polypyrrole, Rare-Earth Elements, Energy-storage system, Supercapacitor*

Electrochemical Detection of Levodropropizine Using TiO₂ Nanoparticles Synthesized via Solvothermal Method

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In this study, TiO₂ nanoparticles synthesized by the solvothermal synthesis technique were modified to the glassy carbon electrode (GCE) surface and used in sensitive electrochemical determination of Levodropropizine (LDP). LDP is a molecule with antitussive and antihistaminic properties and is widely used, especially in cold and flu treatment. Also used to treat allergic reactions, LDP's accurate and sensitive determination is of great importance in biomedical applications. Within the scope of the study, TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized by the solvothermal method, and various analytical techniques were used for their characterization. Morphological and structural properties of TiO₂ nanoparticles were examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), thus obtaining detailed information about the shape, size, and distribution of nanoparticles. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis determined the crystal structure of TiO₂ and confirmed that the particles have a pure TiO₂ structure. In addition, the surface areas of the nanoparticles were measured using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis to evaluate their suitability for electrochemical sensor applications. Modified GCE was used for the detection of LDP. The modification of TiO₂ nanoparticles to the GCE surface improved the electrochemical properties of the electrode, resulting in higher sensitivity and selectivity in the detection of LDP. In the modification process, carbon black (CB) was also used as a binder with TiO₂. CB created a synergistic effect with TiO₂ nanoparticles, increased the conductivity on the electrode surface, and further improved the electrochemical performance of the sensor. Electrochemical measurements were performed with different voltammetric techniques, such as Square Wave Voltammetry and Differential Pulse Voltammetry, and it was observed that the combination of TiO₂ nanoparticles with CB increased the analytical performance for LDP.

Keyword: *Voltammetry, Glassy carbon electrode, Levodropropizine, Nanoparticles*

Structural and Chemical Modification of h-BN, an electrochemical analysis

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Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN), known for its exceptional thermal and chemical stability, is traditionally limited by its insulating nature when applied in electrochemical energy storage. To overcome this limitation, we report the development of a hybrid electrode material composed of h-BN cores decorated with manganese-doped zinc oxide (Mn:ZnO) nanostructures, synthesized via a multi-step approach combining high-energy ball milling, chemical precipitation, and microwave-assisted hydrothermal treatment. This composite architecture integrates the high surface area and structural robustness of h-BN with the redox-active, semiconductive behavior of Mn:ZnO, enabling enhanced electrical conductivity and pseudocapacitive charge storage. The inclusion of Mn dopants into ZnO lattices introduces additional donor states and oxygen vacancies, which significantly improve electron mobility and electrochemical responsiveness. Structural and morphological characterization confirms the uniform dispersion of Mn:ZnO on h-BN surfaces, while electrochemical testing demonstrates high specific capacitance, excellent rate capability, and superior cycling stability. These findings underscore the potential of h-BN/Mn:ZnO composites as next-generation electrode materials for high-performance supercapacitors, where the synergy between defect engineering and hierarchical architecture plays a key role in optimizing both conductivity and capacitive behavior.

Keyword: *Nanomaterials, Characterization, Spectroscopy, Electrochemical performance*

Dose-Dependent Structural Evolution of GO/PVA/AgNWs Nanocomposites under Gamma Radiation

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The polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)-based matrix, which is incorporated into silver nanowires (AgNWs) and graphite oxide (GO), has attracted considerable research interest due to its promising physical properties and potential applications in optoelectronic devices. Due to their functional relevance, the study of the effects of ionizing radiation on these nanocomposites has become an increasingly important research focus. In this study, we analyze the effects of gamma radiation on the microstructure of GO/PVA/AgNW nanocomposites by analyzing dose-dependent structural changes using Raman spectroscopy (figure 1) [1]. To evaluate these effects, nanocomposites were exposed to three different gamma radiation doses: 8, 25, and 50 kGy. The Raman spectrum analysis revealed two characteristic peaks of the D and G bands, which correspond to the density of defects and graphic sequence. The intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) of these bands is a reliable indicator of structural disturbances within the composite. The lowest I_D/I_G values (1.02) were recorded in clean samples (non-irradiated), and the highest ratios (1.07) were shown in 8 kGy, indicating an increase in deficiency concentration. It is interesting to note that further exposure to higher doses (25 kGy and 50 kGy) resulted in a slight decrease in defects density, indicating a nonlinear tendency associated with possible nanostructure restructuring or partial self-healing mechanisms. Quantitative structural analysis was carried out with the Cancado and Lucchese models [2], estimating crystal size (L_a), average deviation space (L_D), and defect density. The shortest distance (22.88 nm) and highest defects concentration ($6.08 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) in 8kGy doses were observed, indicating significant structural degradation at this level of radiation. However, additional radiation appears to induce a partial stabilization of the nanostructure, perhaps due to the rearrangement or radiation effects in the matrix.

Overall, these results show that gamma radiation significantly alters the structural properties of GO/PVA/AgNWs nanocomposites depending on dose, but not linear. The ability to adjust defective structures by controlled radiation exposure offers promising opportunities for optimizing these materials for advanced applications in optical electronics and radiation sensitive technologies.

Figure 1. Raman spectra for GO/PVA/AgNWs nanocomposites: (A) Non-irradiated sample, (B) irradiated at 8 kGy, (C) irradiated at 25 kGy, (D) irradiated at 50 kGy

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Keyword: *nanocomposite, gamma radiation, structural disorder*

Characterization of Porins Isolated from *Acinetobacter Baumannii* by Single-Channel Electrophysiology

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As one of the primary health concerns, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) to many antibiotics is increasing due to the misuse of antibiotics. Parallel to this rise, there has been a significant decline in the development and discovery of new antibiotics. During antibiotic treatment, a comprehensive understanding of the resistance that bacteria develop against any antibiotic is necessary. Unlike classical methods used to understand resistance mechanisms, the electrophysiology technique is employed as an alternative and complementary approach to characterize a single bacterial porin channel (proteins with a nanochannel structure that control the passage of antibiotics, sulfur dioxide, and/or nutrients through the bacterial cell membrane) at the single-molecule detection level. *Acinetobacter Baumannii* (*A. Baumannii*), as a gram-negative bacteria, is one of the main causes of nosocomial infections and multiple drug resistance. In this study, different porins isolated from *A. Baumannii* were characterized single-molecule detection level by single-channel electrophysiology [1-3]. The permeability rates of antibiotics and molecules that permeate the cellular membrane using porins, and the identification of the changes in the permeability rates, were investigated. 0.5 M KCl solution buffered using 10 mM HEPES (pH=8.0) was used for single-channel electrophysiology measurements. OccAB1, OmpA, OmpW, and HMP-BA porins from bacterial strains of *A. Baumannii* were then inserted into a lipid bilayer, and the current-voltage curves were obtained by using electrical recordings through a pair of Ag/AgCl electrodes. It was attached to an Axon Instruments 200B amplifier, digitized by an Axon Digidata 1550B digitizer. The results were analyzed by ClampFit software. Thus, by working with porins of *A. Baumannii*, whilst casting light upon the problem of MDR to various antibiotics, also intends to provide the basic knowledge for research of the new antibiotics.

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Keyword: *Single-channel Electrophysiology, Porins, A. Baumannii, Antimicrobial Resistance*

Prediction of Gamma Radiation Shielding Properties Using Machine Learning Methods

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The widespread use of radiation in many areas, such as industry, medicine, agriculture and nuclear energy, poses significant risks to human health. Therefore, the need for effective shielding solutions is increasing day by day. In this context, the linear attenuation coefficient (LAC), which determines the effectiveness of materials against gamma rays, stands out as a critical parameter in environments operating with radiation. LAC is usually obtained through experimental studies or detailed Monte Carlo simulations; however, these methods can be time and cost-limiting. In this study, a dataset consisting of LAC values obtained from the NIST XCOM database and covering the energy range of 0.01–10 MeV was created [1,3,4], and this data was used to train machine learning models. The applied models include Support Vector Regression (SVR), Kernel Ridge Regression (KRR) and k-nearest Neighbor (k-NN) algorithms; the performance of the models was evaluated with MAE, MSE and R² metrics. The trained models were tested on Praseodymium Hexaboride (PrB₆) material. The estimation results show that machine learning methods provide an effective alternative for predicting LAC values [2] for new materials or materials with limited literature data. This way, the experimental load can be reduced, and significant time and cost savings can be achieved. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that machine learning is a powerful tool for accurately and rapidly estimating gamma radiation attenuation coefficients. This approach can provide scientific and industrial contributions to radiation-driven systems' design and optimization processes.

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Keyword: *Monte Carlo simulations, Machine Learning, the linear attenuation coefficient*

Machine Learning NEXAFS and XPS Spectra: From Excited-State Properties to Highly Accurate Molecular Structure Determination

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Core-electron spectroscopies, such as X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), are crucial for obtaining detailed information about the local geometric and chemical environments of absorbing atoms. XPS is based on the photoelectric effect, where electrons are emitted after interacting with X-ray photons. In XAS, the sample is exposed to monochromatic X-rays, leading to transitions to unoccupied virtual orbitals and the formation of a core-hole and particle state [1]. Despite the broader availability of tunable radiation sources like synchrotron light sources, interpreting Near Edge X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (NEXAFS) spectra remains challenging, requiring precise quantum mechanical calculations [2].

Machine learning (ML) methods offer a versatile and cost-effective solution for predicting spectroscopy data [3]. This work presents a novel ML-based methodology for predicting NEXAFS spectra from molecular structures (the direct problem) and inferring molecular structures from NEXAFS spectra (the reverse problem). In the study, K-edge and L-edge NEXAFS spectra for various molecules with different absorbing centers (C, O, F, B, S, and metals) are generated and used to train and validate ML models for achieving quantitative accuracy.

The methodology involves developing a comprehensive molecular database of XPS and NEXAFS spectra. Accurate NEXAFS spectra are calculated using Density Functional Theory-Transition Potential (DFT-TP) and Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT) [4]. For elements like Boron, where core-hole relaxation effects are particularly difficult to describe, explicit wave function methods are utilized. The Amsterdam Modeling Suite (AMS) facilitates DFT-TP and TDDFT calculations through its high-throughput workflow library, PLAMS [5]. Neural networks and kernel ridge regression are used to solve the direct problem, while classification methods such as random forests are applied to the reverse problem. This work has extensive applications in catalysis, drug design, and energy sectors.

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Keyword: Near Edge X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy, Machine Learning, Density Functional Theory

Coupled Nanofilaments Provide Computational Ability to Bacterial Biofilms

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Biological systems are distinguished by their capacity to process environmental information—a capability that can be construed as a form of intelligence. Much like neuronal networks in the brain, interacting bacterial populations in biofilm structures could also exhibit computational ability. In our recent work, we investigated this phenomenon by analyzing the complex wave patterns generated in bacterial biofilms. A bacterial biofilm, comprising millions of bacteria, produces metachronal waves and engages in non-reciprocal interactions that propagate information, enabling behaviors analogous to elementary logic operations and abstract reasoning. This presentation summarizes our experimental results, highlighting how coupled nanofilament interactions give rise to emergent biological intelligence. Our findings indicate that, by forming biofilms, bacterial colonies acquire computational abilities reminiscent of those seen in brain, thereby suggesting novel, bio-inspired pathways for advancing artificial intelligence in both biology and engineering.

Keyword: *Nanofilaments, Bacterial Biofilm, Computational Ability/Intelligence, Non-reciprocal Interactions*

Enhanced Foliar Adhesion and Micronutrient Delivery via Cationically-Modified Lignin-Based Microparticles

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The effectiveness of foliar fertilizers in agriculture depends largely on their ability to adhere to the leaf surface and facilitate nutrient uptake by the plant. Given that plant surfaces are typically negatively charged, it is hypothesized that carrier systems with a positive surface charge can establish stronger electrostatic interactions, enhancing adhesion and nutrient delivery. In this study, we aimed to develop lignin-based carrier systems with improved foliar performance through cationic modification. Lignin-based micro- and nanoparticles were synthesized to both control nutrient release and improve retention on leaf surface. The degree of cationization of modified lignin (C-Ligno) was tuned by varying the amount of functional groups introduced, as evidenced by shifts in zeta potential from -24.65 ± 3.42 mV (unmodified lignin) to 5.85 ± 1.20 mV, $+12.71 \pm 0.33$ mV, and $+24.14 \pm 0.95$ mV. This increase in positive charge promoted stronger electrostatic interaction with leaf surface, leading to improved foliar adhesion and nutrient delivery. Iron (Fe^{2+}) ions, as a micronutrient, were encapsulated within the lignin matrix using both solution-based and spray-drying processes, and the resulting particulate systems were characterized in detail. The adhesion capacity of these formulations was evaluated on live plant leaves and quantitatively analyzed by ICP-OES analysis. Results showed that cationic lignin derivatives exhibited significantly higher adhesion performance compared to the unmodified lignin controls. These findings confirm that cationic lignin structures enhanced electrostatic affinity to the leaf surface, improved micronutrient delivery efficiency, and offer promising potential of lignin-based biomaterials as sustainable and effective carrier systems in foliar fertilization.

This study was financially supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under 1004 program LignoNANO (Grant No. 22AG045).

Keyword: Lignin, Foliar Fertilizer, Micronutrient Carrier, Leaf Adhesion

Exploration of Liposomal Resiquimod Immunotherapy on a Novel Tumor-Microenvironment-on-Chip

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The heterogenous tumor microenvironment (TME) is typically wired by exhaustive interplays among cancer cells and diverse range of non-cancerous cells, with loads of soluble factors [1]. Macrophages, a predominant immune cell population in the TME, possessing a unique repolarization ability from pro-inflammatory M1 to anti-inflammatory M2 state. This ability influences the progression of neoplastic development from early TME formation stages, where macrophages interact with cancer cells and become polarized into a tumor-associated state. Tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs), displaying M2-like polarization, reshape the TME by promoting angiogenesis, supporting tumor growth while suppressing the immune response [2]. As much promising it may sound, repolarizing the M2-like state back to an M1-like state is challenging, with the not completely unveiled biology of TAMs. In result, many of such therapeutic approaches yield unsatisfactory outcomes. In this study we successfully developed a tumor-microenvironment-on-chip model including colorectal cancer spheroids in coculture with THP-1 derived macrophages to study the effect of paracrine molecules produced by macrophages on cancer spheroid behavior. Our analysis of the spheroid growth profile and EMT has revealed the prominent role of macrophages at the TME on altering the tumor dynamics. Macrophages in tumor-associated state were found to enhance the colorectal cancer spheroid growth, proliferation, and EMT. Whereas re-education of these macrophages by our synthesized resiquimod-loaded-lipid nanoparticles, to the M1-like state, has restrained the observed effects. The comprehensive findings from our engineered TME-on-chip model were in-line with our observations in culture environments outside of the microfluidic chip. These results confirm the effectiveness of our platform on elucidating the intricate communication between cancer cells and macrophages inside the TME and the critical role of immune cells manipulation on hindering the oncogenic progression. In general, this study underscores the potential usefulness of our platform for further immunotherapeutic agent discovery and screening, offering a physiologically relevant environment for further research efforts.

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Keyword: *Microfluidics, Organ-on-chip, Spheroid, Microphysiological Systems*

From Waste to Innovation: Development of Nanocomposite Materials Using Brick Powders

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Recent advances in nanotechnology have led to groundbreaking innovations in materials science and the construction industry. In particular, the growing demand for new materials with enhanced durability, lightweight properties, mechanical strength, and environmental sustainability has drawn increasing attention. In this context, the utilization of natural waste materials such as brick powders in the design of nanocomposites presents significant potential from both environmental and economic perspectives. Brick powders are cost-effective, abundant, recyclable materials that, when integrated with nanocomposites, can provide superior mechanical and functional performance. Moreover, the incorporation of different nanomaterials into clay-based composites has been shown to significantly influence their electromagnetic transmission characteristics [1] and enhance their ionizing radiation shielding capabilities, thereby expanding their applicability in advanced construction and protective material technologies [2,3].

In this study, brick powders with different nano-morphologies were combined with Ag, Co, and ZrO nanoparticles to synthesize various composites. The sonochemical method, a green synthesis approach, was employed in the fabrication process. The molecular and crystalline structures of the developed composites were characterized using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD), while their nanoscale structures and pore characteristics were investigated by Small Angle X-Ray Spectroscopy (SAXS). The radius of gyration values for nanocomposites containing 8% Ag, Co, and ZrO were calculated as 27.1 ± 0.5 nm, 26.8 ± 0.4 nm, and 23.6 ± 0.2 nm, respectively. Moreover, advanced structural analyses were performed using the SAXS analysis programs DAMMIN and DENSS to reconstruct ab initio three-dimensional (3D) electron density models. Based on these models, the nanocomposite with 8% Co-doped brick powder was predicted to exhibit the highest durability potential, owing to its most uniform pair-distance distribution function (PDDF) and compact structural configuration.

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Keyword: *Nanocomposite brick powder; Sonochemical synthesis; SAXS; Structural characterization; Green synthesis; Sustainable construction materials.*, **Acknowledgments:** *This research was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Unit of Yüksek İhtisas University*

Bacterial Self-Healing In Reactive MgO Cement (RMC) Based Mortars

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Micro-cracks severely limit the long-term durability of cementitious composites. Biogenic carbonate precipitation offers a promising self-healing mechanism for their repair. In this study, *Sporosarcina pasteurii*, an ureolytic bacterium known for its carbonate production, was utilized to enable self-healing in reactive MgO cement (RMC) mortars reinforced with 1.5 vol% polypropylene fiber. Bacterial cells were cultivated in a urea-corn steep liquor (UCSL), aerobically incubated with shaking at 30°C until reaching stationary phase, then collected via centrifugation, washed twice with phosphate buffer solution (PBS), and stored at 4°C until casting. 4×4×16 cm fiber-reinforced RMC mortar prisms, with and without the bacterial cells, were cast and cured for 28-day under moist conditions at 20% CO₂ concentration to promote cement hydration and carbonation. Controlled cracking was introduced on the prisms via three-point flexural testing, followed by 28 days of air curing during which a urea-containing nutrient solution was periodically applied to sustain bacterial viability. Crack healing was assessed on days 0, 14, and 28 using stereomicroscopy. Significant biogenic carbonate deposition was observed within the cracks of bacteria-containing samples, indicating successful microbial healing. This research demonstrates that integrating microbial action with RMC matrices offers a promising approach for enhancing their sustainability and durability.

Keyword: *Microbial self-healing, Reactive MgO cement (RMC), Biogenic carbonate deposition, Ureolytic Bacterium*

Flexible and Conductive Composite Ionogels for Human Motion Monitoring

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Flexible electronic devices, soft robotics, personalized e-health services, and soft, conductive materials for human-computer interaction have become essential technologies [1-2]. In recent years, research on soft and flexible hydrogel-based strain sensors for e-health applications has grown significantly, enabling the monitoring of human movements in real time [3-4]. However, a major limitation of hydrogel-based wearable sensors is the loss of signal detection and stability due to the freezing or evaporation of water under varying climatic conditions. To address this challenge, the development of ionogel systems using deep eutectic solvents (DES) has gained prominence in wearable sensor applications [5]. In this study, a stretchable, self-adhesive, and antifreezing conductive hydrogel featuring multiple interpenetrating networks and outstanding mechanical properties was synthesized for application in highly sensitive motion sensors. First, Laponite@Polyaniline (LAP@PANI) nanocomposites were synthesized as the electroactive component of the hydrogel system. Subsequently, flexible and conductive composite ionogels composed of polyacrylamide (PAAm), Gum Arabic (GA), and LAP@PANI were fabricated using a choline chloride/urea DES system. In this ionogel system, the DES imparts high mechanical strength and flexibility, along with excellent self-healing properties, through the formation of physical cross-links and hydrogen bonds within the network structure. The obtained ionogels exhibited biocompatibility and remarkable flexibility (2100%), tensile strength (73.6 kPa) and freezing tolerance (-20°C). This ionogel system effectively monitors various human motions, such as knee bending and extension, finger movement, and walking. These findings suggest that flexible DES-based ionogel strain sensors hold significant promise for advancing next-generation sensing technologies.

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Keyword: flexible strain sensor, ionogel, nanocomposite hydrogel, deep eutectic solvent

Post-Synthesis Nanoparticle Separations via Continuous Membrane Processes

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Post-synthesis processing of nanoparticles often requires purification, concentration and solvent exchange for stabilization or further functionalization. In lab scale these are typically done by centrifugation. Large-scale production of nanoparticles would benefit significantly from a continuous flow process, which is more practical and economical. Ultrafiltration and nanofiltration membranes, with pores down to 1 nm in diameter, emerge as promising separation agents for this purpose.

A major route in nanoparticle synthesis is the solvothermal method, which uses various solvents depending on the chemistry involved. Post-synthesis concentration, purification or solvent exchange using ultrafiltration or nanofiltration requires membranes that show stable performance in the solvent media. In this study, we demonstrate the performance of ultrafiltration membranes made of cellulose, a biopolymer that is inherently solvent-resistant due to extensive hydrogen bonding in its structure. Hydrophilic and hydrophobized silica nanoparticles suspended in isopropanol, ethanol, water and dimethylformamide are concentrated and continuously solvent-exchanged using these membranes. Material loss due to cake formation, or fouling, on the membrane is evaluated considering both flux decline during the process and nanoparticle recovery. Furthermore, the quality of recovered nanoparticles was assessed by the particle size after the process, indicating the presence or absence of agglomerates.

In nanoparticle concentration tests, it was observed that hydrophobized nanoparticles fouled the membranes significantly more than hydrophilic particles, attributed to larger attractive interactions between the hydrophobic surfaces in all solvents. Fouling by hydrophilic particles could be completely removed from the membrane surface by briefly stirring the filtration cell when dimethylformamide was the dispersing solvent, while a fraction of the cake remained on the surface with water and isopropanol. The recovered nanoparticles had the same particle size as those in the feed, implying a loose and easily dispersible cake layer in all three solvents. On the contrary, recovery of hydrophobized nanoparticles from isopropanol was complete, while it was lowest from dimethylformamide also showing significant agglomeration.

In a second application, continuous solvent exchange was done in a tangential-flow system starting from nanoparticle suspensions in isopropanol and gradually changing the solvent medium to ethanol, water or dimethylformamide in separate experiments. Analyzing the flow resistance during filtration using Darcy's law, taking into account the change in permeate viscosity as solvent composition varies, revealed that even at quite low tangential flow rates, the process can be operated without significant cake buildup on the membrane, thereby suggesting that ultrafiltration after nanoparticle synthesis is a viable option for continuous solvent exchange.

Keyword: *Membrane, Ultrafiltration, Continuous nanoparticle purification, Post-synthesis solvent exchange*

Experimental Investigation of Forced Convective Heat Transfer of Magnetic Nanofluid Under Different Magnetic Field Configurations and Volume Fractions

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Nanofluids can offer higher thermal conductivity compared to conventional heat transfer fluids. Ferrofluids, a subclass of nanofluids, are characterized by their magnetically responsive nanoparticles, which distinguish them from conventional nanofluids. When exposed to a magnetic field, metal oxide nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4 , Fe_2O_3) in ferrofluids become polarized and behave like nanoscale magnets. This unique behavior enables significant improvements in heat transfer performance through magnetically induced changes in their thermal and physical properties. Due to these features, ferrofluids have shown great potential in a variety of thermal management applications [1–5].

In this study, the forced convective heat transfer performance of water-based ferrofluids containing Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles at two different volume fractions (0.5% and 1%) was experimentally investigated in a circular stainless steel tube under the influence of a constant magnetic field. Permanent magnets generating a field strength of 700 G were placed along the flow path in two configurations (aligned and staggered) to evaluate the effect of magnetic field distribution. Experiments were carried out under constant heat flux conditions for Reynolds numbers ranging from 400 to 1000. In the study, the effect of different magnetic field distributions on heat transfer performance was investigated in detail, with particular attention to how this performance varies with nanoparticle concentration. For each case, local and average Nusselt numbers as well as pressure drops were measured. Furthermore, a Performance Evaluation Criterion (PEC) was employed to assess the overall efficiency of heat transfer enhancement relative to the pressure drop.

The results demonstrate that the application of a magnetic field significantly enhances the convective heat transfer performance of the ferrofluid. This enhancement is more pronounced at lower Reynolds numbers, higher nanoparticle concentrations, and under staggered magnet arrangements with stronger magnetic field gradients. The maximum improvements in local and average Nusselt numbers were recorded at $\text{Re} = 400$ for the 1% volume fraction under staggered magnet placement, with increases of 94.59% and 36.57%, respectively.

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Keyword: *Ferrofluid, heat transfer enhancement, experimental, magnetic nanofluid*

Multiscale Modeling of Deposit Control Mechanism by Dispersants and Detergents in the Lubricant Oil.

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Molecular modeling calculations can support and improve experimental results for the design of next-generation additives for lubricant oils. Control of insoluble sludge and soot nanoparticle aggregations in oil and on the engine surfaces is the most important key performance parameter for lubricant oil additives. General consensus about the mechanism of deposit build-up is the self-aggregation of nanosized insoluble structures. Dispersants and detergents are the major additives to prevent aggregation in lubricant formulations. Together with the base oil, they play a significant role to disperse and stabilize insoluble particles to control deposit formation. Multiscale modeling methods were performed to elucidate molecular mechanism of deposit control via polyisobutylene bis-succinimide (PIBSI) based dispersants and alkyl sulfonate based detergents by using density functional theory, molecular dynamics simulations and coarse-grained simulations. The aim of this study is to understand the role of different functional groups dispersants and detergents on the deposit control. It was demonstrated that the mechanism of deposit control by dispersants and detergents can be explained by the interactions between constituents such as hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic-hydrophilic interactions. We showed that nanoparticle aggregation is mitigated by intercalation of polar groups between the insoluble nanoparticles followed by the extension of hydrophobic tails into the oil phase that decreases coalesce further by forming a repulsive layer against the other nanoparticles.

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Özdemir, E.; Kan, E.; Guo, B.; Pashkovski, E.; Ağral, A.; Yildirim, E. Multiscale Modeling Approach to Understand Mechanism of Deposit Control by Sulfonate-Based Lubricant Detergents. *ACS Omega* 2024, 9, 38753–38768.

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Keyword: *molecular dynamics simulations, self-aggregation, detergent, dispersant*

Ab Initio Investigation of Magnetism and Band Gap Modulation in 2D SnTe Through Doping and Vacancy Control

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Using spin-polarized density functional theory (DFT) calculations, we performed a systematic first-principles exploration of pristine, vacancy-engineered and substitutionally doped SnTe monolayers. Formation and cohesive energy benchmarks confirm that the pristine γ and newly explored β' and hexagonal phases are energetically favourable, while phonon dispersions contain no imaginary modes, attesting to dynamical stability. They showed semiconducting nature with electronic band gaps in the range of 0.82 to 1.84 eV revealing HSE06 and spin-orbit coupling effect. The investigation systematically examined the impact of vacancy-type defects (V_{Sn} , V_{SnSn} , V_{Te} , V_{TeTe} , and V_{SnTe}) and substitutional doping with Bi, Sb, Mn, Ge, Cr, V, and Co at a concentration of 2.7% on the electronic band structure of monolayer SnTe. The results reveal that intrinsic vacancies preserve the non-magnetic ground state, whereas substitution with magnetic dopants; most notably Cr and Mn induces substantial localized magnetic moments, thereby driving a transition from a non-magnetic to a magnetic semiconducting phase. Substitutional magnetic doping instead of Sn, induced localized magnetic moments, 4.43, 3.62, 2.68 and 2.56 μB for Mn, Cr, V and Co, respectively. Further investigation indicates that the magnetization becomes stronger upon increasing the substitutional magnetic Cr doping instead of Te, with a total magnetic moment of up to 5.02 μB . The cohesive and doping energies confirm the thermodynamic stability of dopants within SnTe. In addition, the thermal stability of the doped systems at room temperature is also confirmed by ab initio molecular-dynamics (AIMD) simulations. This work expands the fundamental understanding of 2D SnTe and demonstrates how defect and substitutional doping strategies can be employed to engineer its multifunctional properties. The results not only provide insight into the underlying physics but also chart a pathway for the design of SnTe-based materials in emerging energy and information technologies.

Keyword: *Ab-initio calculations, 2D materials, Substitutional doping, Electronic Properties*

Correlated Magnetism And Topological Signatures In FeGe And Mn₃Ge Kagome Materials: A DFT+U Perspective

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In this study, we present a comprehensive theoretical investigation of the structural, electronic, and magnetic ground-state properties of FeGe and Mn₃Ge Kagome lattice systems using first-principles density functional theory (DFT). The Kagome lattice, known for hosting exotic quantum phenomena such as flat bands, Dirac fermions, and nontrivial topology, provides a promising platform for exploring correlated magnetism and spin-dependent transport. We first constructed periodic models of FeGe and Mn₃Ge Kagome structures and examine their magnetic configurations, including nonmagnetic (NM), ferromagnetic (FM), and antiferromagnetic (AFM) states. Total energy comparisons reveal that the FeGe Kagome system energetically favors the AFM ground state. Electronic band structure analyses, including spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effects, indicate the presence of near-flat bands around the Fermi level, along with multiple van Hove singularities. These features are expected to play a critical role in driving correlated electronic states.

To account for strong on-site Coulomb interactions in partially filled 3d orbitals of Fe, we incorporate the GGA+U formalism using a self-consistently determined Hubbard U parameter of 3.75 eV. The results suggest significant improvements in the accuracy of magnetic moment predictions and band gap estimates. Furthermore, we provide linear response analysis to validate the U value and emphasize its role in describing localized d-electron behavior.

Our findings establish that FeGe Kagome systems, when treated with appropriate correlation corrections, exhibit structurally robust and electronically intricate behavior conducive to magnetic frustration and quantum criticality. This work contributes essential insights into the quantum design of Kagome-based materials and lays the groundwork for experimental realizations targeting spintronic, topological, and strongly correlated applications.

Keyword: Kagome, Density Functional Theory, Magnetism, Spintronics

Solvent-Free Quantum Dots: Unlocking Solid-State Luminescence with Boron-Confined Carbon Nanostructures for Color-Tunable Optoelectronics

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Carbon quantum dots (CQDs) have garnered increasing attention as next-generation nanomaterials for optoelectronic applications due to their tunable photoluminescence, water solubility, and low toxicity. However, their practical integration into solid-state devices is limited by aggregation-induced quenching (AIQ) effects that compromise emission efficiency. In this study, we report a novel, vacuum-assisted, solvent-free synthesis strategy for the fabrication of boron-doped carbon quantum dots (B-CDs) using urea, trisodium citrate dihydrate, and boric acid precursors. This approach not only enhances precursor interaction in a confined foam-like matrix under vacuum but also stabilizes the emission properties of CDs in solid-state environments.

The synthesized B-CDs demonstrate bright green emission with a photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) of 22% in aqueous solution, which is preserved up to 18% in solid PVP-based thin films—a notable performance compared to undoped CDs, which exhibit no luminescence in the solid state. Optical characterizations reveal excitation-independent emission, a broad Stokes shift (~100 nm), and biexponential time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) decay behavior, indicating the presence of multiple recombination pathways and stable mid-gap radiative states.

B-CDs were integrated into color conversion LEDs using a simple drop-casting method, and the resulting films exhibited tunable CIE coordinates ranging from (0.28, 0.27) to (0.32, 0.47) depending on concentration. The photostability studies under continuous UV exposure (365 nm, 100 min) show that solid-state B-CDs retain over 93% of their PL intensity, highlighting their durability. Thermogravimetric analysis further confirms high thermal stability, with 94.89% of mass retained at 230 °C. These properties validate B-CDs as robust phosphors for solid-state lighting applications.

This work presents a scalable and environmentally friendly synthesis route that eliminates the need for toxic solvents while simultaneously enhancing the solid-state optical performance of CDs. The incorporation of boric acid as both dopant and structural matrix significantly suppresses AIQ and opens new avenues for the development of efficient, stable, and color-tunable luminescent films. The strategy demonstrated here may serve as a foundation for future integration of carbon-based nanomaterials in flexible displays, lighting systems, and anti-counterfeiting technologies.

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Keyword: *Carbon quantum dots (CQDs), Solid-state photoluminescence, Optoelectronic applications*

Electrodeposited and in Situ Carbon Quantum Dot Doped CdS Thin Films as Electron Transport Layers

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Cadmium sulfide (CdS) has emerged as a favorable alternative for commonly used zinc oxide (ZnO) electron transport material in high performance PbS quantum dot solar cells that suffers from inherent instability and energy level misalignment. Nevertheless, the techniques currently employed for the growth of CdS thin films offer only limited control over the resulting properties, including parameters such as thickness, morphology, and defect density. In this study, we demonstrate that the electrodeposition technique serves as an effective method for the deposition of CdS. The employment of this technique in conjunction with in situ carbon quantum dot (CQD) doping has been demonstrated to facilitate the formation of denser films, which exhibit enhanced surface uniformity, increased transparency, and prolonged excited state lifetimes. This technique, which is both cost-effective and suitable for large-scale implementation, enables precise and simultaneous control over thickness and charge carrier density. Consequently, a noteworthy efficiency of 7.47% was attained in CdS/PbS solar cells utilizing electrodeposited CdS, signifying a substantial advancement in the field. The in situ CQD doping strategy promotes faster exciton dissociation, more efficient interfacial charge transfer, and improved charge collection, attributed to the formation of a type-II heterojunction between CQDs and CdS. This technique represents a promising pathway toward further enhancement of solar cell performance.

Keyword: CdS, PbS quantum dots, electrodeposition, solar cells

Detection of Molecular Indicators with Nanofiber Composites Using Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering

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Nucleic acids are among the key biomarkers for disease monitoring, and their detection in cell-free biological fluids has gained interest due to their potential for non-invasive diagnostics [1,2]. Recently, nanobiosensors have gained a crucial role in prognostic and diagnostic strategies to detect and monitor diseases and infections with their ability to significantly enhance the selectivity and sensitivity [3,4]. In this study, we present surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) based biosensors for the detection of microRNA (miRNA) for laryngeal cancer in early stages using electrospun nanofibers. The biosensor consists of electrospun ϵ -caprolactam (CLA) and ϵ -caprolactone (CLO) nanofibers incorporated with in situ synthesized gold nanoparticles (AuNPs). As target, miRNA 223-3p was selected as a biomarker of laryngeal cancer, and selectivity of the biosensor was achieved with a molecular beacon that can hybridize with the target miRNA and also provide a signal from the conjugated Raman reporter. Due to the structure of the molecular beacon, in the presence of the target sequence, the signal obtained from the Raman reporter decreased, and this decrease was monitored for the detection of target miRNA. The designed SERS substrate provided homogenous signal distribution and significant signal enhancement (enhancement factor (EF) greater than 10^6). Target miRNA was detected up to fM levels due to this significant signal enhancement and good signal distribution. The specificity of the designed detection system was tested against a non-complementary miRNA, and it was observed that the designed system can provide a significant signal to the target miRNA, while a non-complementary miRNA could not provide any significant signal interference. Consequently, it was found that designed biosensors can detect miRNA 223-3p as a biomarker of laryngeal cancer with high selectivity and sensitivity. The obtained results showed that the designed SERS biosensor can be used for tracking and monitoring biomarkers for specific conditions, and possible applications for different markers, such as oligonucleotides.

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Keyword: Nanobiosensor, Surface enhanced Raman scattering, Gold nanoparticles, Nanofiber

A Living Material Platform for the Biomineralization of Biosilica

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Biomineralization by living organisms enables the synthesis of structurally and functionally diverse materials. Inspired by diatom biosilicification, we developed a synthetic biology-based bacterial platform capable of inducing silica precipitation through genetically encoded surface display of the R5 peptide, a well-known silica-nucleating motif derived from silaffins. Using the autotransporter antigen 43 (Ag43), R5 was fused to fluorescent proteins (sfGFP, YFP, and mCherry) and presented on the outer membrane of *Escherichia coli*. This system enabled both surface-bound and heat-triggered released forms of R5-fusion proteins, providing a tunable and purification-free method for biosilicification. We demonstrated that the engineered bacteria effectively nucleate silica nanoparticles both as intact cells and via released fusion proteins, confirmed by TEM, SEM, EDS, and confocal microscopy. Importantly, the silica aggregates formed by R5-fusion proteins enhanced extracellular calcium deposition in human dental pulp stem cells (hDPSCs), indicating osteogenic stimulation. These findings suggest that our living material platform offers a cost-effective and modular route to biofabricate silica-based materials for biomedical applications. This approach circumvents labor-intensive purification protocols, supports environmentally friendly processing, and may contribute to next-generation strategies in tissue engineering and regenerative endodontics.

Keyword: *synthetic biology, living materials, biomineralization, biosilicification*

Two-Dimensional 2γ -In₂Se₃ in Bilayer-Like Coloring Triangle Lattice: Mechanical, Electronic, Transport, and Photocatalytic Properties

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The discovery of two-dimensional (2D) materials derived from non-van der Waals (vdW) bulk counterparts has opened up a new era, drawing attention to the crystals composed of asymmetrically bonded vertical exotic layers. In this respect, γ -In₂Se₃, a promising material utilized in various applications, built with coloring triangle layers, emerges as a suitable candidate. Through first-principles calculations, we show that a novel 2D structure, the 2γ -In₂Se₃ monolayer, consisting of a bilayer-like coloring triangle lattice, can be exfoliated from bulk γ -In₂Se₃ with minimal external energy. The formation of this exotic 2D lattice is facilitated by sp³ hybrid bonds. Comprehensive phonon dispersion and finite-temperature molecular dynamics analyses confirm the thermodynamic stability of the 2γ -In₂Se₃ monolayer. The material exhibits an anisotropic mechanical response due to missing bonds at lattice sites, making it suitable for flexible nanoelectronic devices. It possesses semiconductor characteristics with an indirect band gap in the visible region. Analysis of band edge positions and charge carrier mobility suggests that the 2γ -In₂Se₃ monolayer is highly efficient for photocatalytic water-splitting applications.

Keyword: *ab-initio, semiconductors*

PNcsp: A Periodic Number-Based Crystal Structure Prediction Method Enhanced by Machine Learning

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The periodic number (PN) representation, originally conceptualized by Dmitri Mendeleev, offers a fundamental perspective on chemical similarity by aligning elemental properties with principal quantum numbers in their electronic configurations. This systematic arrangement provides enhanced insight into the relationships and trends among the elements. Building on this framework, we present a novel approach to prototype prediction using PN relationships to assess structural modifications and phase stability in unexplored chemical systems. Our PN-based crystal structure prediction (PNcsp) methodology systematically identifies the most probable structural prototypes for phases that lack experimentally resolved structures. By analyzing 59 equimolar chemical systems with ambiguous phase diagrams, PNcsp successfully predicted 93 candidate prototypes, 47 of which demonstrate mechanical and dynamic stability. Significantly, this approach revealed 19 entirely new and fully stable polymorphic phases —some exhibiting semiconducting properties— thereby expanding the known landscape of potential materials. Moreover, its applicability extends beyond equimolar systems to more complex multi-component chemistries, underscoring its versatility in structure prediction. Unlike complex models, the key strength of this methodology is its simplicity and transparency, rooted in the periodicity of chemical elements. Besides, by narrowing the phase space for stable structures, it not only enhances prediction accuracy but also reduces computational costs of identifying proper modifications. Importantly, the methodology is modular by design, enabling the seamless integration of modern machine learning tools into the evaluation pipeline. This optional enhancement allows for the elimination of redundant data and provides users with a more refined and manageable dataset, further accelerating the discovery process. The current implementation is fully compatible with several widely used deep neural network-based energy prediction models, including MEGNet and M3GNet. We are actively expanding the range of machine learning methods integrated into our framework to enhance its versatility and applicability. An open-source software implementation of our crystal structure prediction method is publicly available at <https://github.com/tccdem/PNcsp>.

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Keyword: *Crystal Structure Prediction, Computational Material Screening, Machine Learning*

Solvent Engineering for the Accelerated Solvothermal Synthesis of Reduced-Size V-MIL-47 MOF Nanocrystals

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Vanadium-based metal organic framework (MOF) V-MIL-47 exhibits enhanced adsorption capacity owing to its characteristic large pore sizes [1, 2] with applicability in catalytic reactions [3] and separation processes [4]. Synthesis of crystalline MIL-47 MOF structures is typically achieved through solvothermal methodologies [5]. Metal ions and organic ligands undergo self-assembly in the solution, forming clusters. The solvent system employed in the precursor solution plays a critical role in influencing the self-assembly and nucleation kinetics by controlling the solubility of the precursors, degree of supersaturation at a given temperature, and ionic diffusion rates. Dielectric constant, pH, polarity, boiling point, and viscosity, govern the rates of precursor dissolution and subsequent nuclei formation. This study aimed to reduce the synthesis time for the formation of V-MIL-47 structures while simultaneously achieving a reduction in particle size. Vanadium(IV)-oxide-sulfate-hydrate ($\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and terephthalic acid (H_2BDC) were employed as the metal salt and organic ligand at a molar ratio of 1:0.73 within a 5 mL precursor solution. Solvothermal synthesis was conducted utilizing various solvent systems, including *n,n*-dimethylformamide (DMF), *n*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), and mixtures of DMF with 15%v NMP, 80%v dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), 25%v ethylene glycol, and mixtures of NMP with 10, 20, 30, and 50%v glycerol across a range of temperatures and synthesis times.

Using DMF alone at 160 °C resulted with particle formation at 8 hours (319 ± 144 nm) and 16 hours (275 ± 76 nm), while NMP allowing for higher synthesis temperatures provided particles (133.5 ± 70 nm) at 250°C and a reduced time of 2 hours. This observation aligns with the established principle that the energy barrier for nucleation is inversely proportional to the synthesis temperature, thereby accelerating the nucleation process. To elevate the boiling point of the solvent DMF, it was combined with higher boiling point solvents. DMF-15%NMP slowed the nucleation down to 16 hours at 160 °C with delayed formation of smaller particles (89.3 ± 22 nm). This can be explained by the shorter molecular chain length of DMF compared to NMP, facilitating faster diffusion and self-assembly. The higher dielectric constant of NMP hinders nucleation by increasing electrostatic repulsion between precursor ions, while concurrently modulating the self-assembly process favoring nucleation. Using DMF and NMP in combination with ethylene glycol and glycerol did not yield detectable particle formation at 160°C, 230°C, and 250°C up to 16 hours.

Optimal solvothermal conditions were identified for the DMF-NMP solvent system at 160°C and 16 hours achieving V-MIL-47 particles with a uniform size of 89.3 ± 22 nm and crystallinity of 80.6%.

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Keyword: *Solvent system, Solvothermal synthesis, Vanadium-based-metal-organic-framework, Nanoparticle*

Effect Of Modulator Induced Defects On The Water Adsorption Behavior Of MOFs

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Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are a class of hybrid crystalline porous materials that consist of inorganic (nodes or clusters) and organic (linkers) moieties arranged in a 3D molecular framework [1]. MOFs possess very high surface areas, ultra-high porosities, design flexibility, and tunable chemistry, which make them ideal candidates for various potential applications, such as catalysis, clean energy, gas adsorption, and water adsorption [2]. UiO-66-Zr is an archetypal MOF comprising zirconium-based metal clusters connected by 1,4-benzodicyclohexane (H₂BDC) organic linker to form a 3D framework. MOFs generally have low thermal stability, but UiO-66-Zr is a unique type of MOF that has high thermal as well as chemical stability [3]. Defect engineering of UiO-66-Zr using acid modulators is a method to introduce structural imperfections (missing linkers or missing clusters) into the framework, allowing control over its porosity, surface area, and functionality, thus tuning the MOF for a specific application [4].

In this work, Defects were induced in the UiO-66-Zr structure, and their effect on the water adsorption behavior was studied. The introduction of defects led to enhanced water adsorption capacity, attributed to increased hydrophilicity and greater pore accessibility. Defects can be induced in the structure of UiO-66-Zr using acid modulators like HCl. HCl facilitates defect formation via two mechanisms [5]: by releasing protons (H⁺), it suppresses the deprotonation of the H₂BDC linker, preventing effective coordination with Zr⁴⁺ and resulting in missing linker defects; and (2) by providing chloride ions (Cl⁻), which compete with the linker for coordination with Zr⁴⁺ centers, disrupting complete node formation and inducing missing linker defects. These defects create open metal sites, which serve as primary nucleation sites for water molecules, subsequently enhancing pore filling of the UiO-66-Zr framework via van der Waals and hydrogen-bonding interactions. The defective UiO-66-Zr exhibited up to a 65% increase in water uptake at 25 °C and 35% relative humidity. Water Adsorption in MOFs has considerable significance because it can pave the way for various applications, such as atmospheric water harvesting, thermal management, humidity control, catalysis, and proton conductivity [2].

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Keyword: MOFs, defect engineering, UiO-66-Zr, water adsorption, modulator

Sustainable Zeolite Production via Solar Calcination of Kaolin and Halloysite: Structural Evolution, Phase Control, and CO₂ Adsorption Efficiency

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The production of zeolites from natural clays offers a promising route toward low-cost and sustainable adsorbent materials, especially for applications in carbon capture. However, conventional calcination processes used to activate kaolin and halloysite clays are highly energy-intensive and carbon-emitting. This thesis explores solar-driven calcination as an environmentally benign alternative for clay activation, aiming to reduce the carbon footprint of zeolite synthesis without compromising material performance. Kaolin and halloysite were subjected to concentrated solar thermal treatment at temperatures ranging from 700 °C to 1000 °C to induce structural transformations into amorphous metaforms and Al–Si spinel intermediates. The thermally activated products were then converted into LTA- and FAU-type zeolites via alkali hydrothermal synthesis. Phase evolution and porosity development were investigated using various characterization techniques. Special attention was given to kaolin, an abundant and low-cost clay that is extensively mined in Türkiye and offers strategic advantages for sustainable materials development. The influence of precursor type and calcination conditions on zeolite formation pathways was systematically evaluated. CO₂ adsorption capacities of the resulting zeolites were assessed at 25 °C and 1 bar using breakthrough and equilibrium measurements. Results demonstrate that solar-calcined clays yield zeolites with comparable crystallinity, surface area, and CO₂ uptake to those produced via conventional heating, while achieving significant reductions in thermal energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. This work validates solar calcination as a viable route for scalable zeolite production and supports the integration of clay-based zeolites into low-cost, low-carbon CO₂ capture technologies.

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Keyword: *Solar Calcination, Kaolin and Halloysite, Zeolite 4A and 13X, CO₂ Capture*

Ga-Assisted Direct Growth of Mo₂C Nanorods via CVD for Enhanced Hydrogen Evolution Catalysis

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The hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) is a key process in sustainable energy technologies, yet its reliance on platinum-based catalysts presents significant cost barriers. Molybdenum carbide (Mo₂C), with its platinum-like electronic structure, high electrical conductivity, and thermal stability, has emerged as a promising non-precious metal catalyst. Particularly, engineering Mo₂C into one-dimensional (1D) nanostructures, such as nanorods, can dramatically improve catalytic efficiency by increasing surface area, enhancing charge transport, and exposing abundant active sites.

In this study, we present a novel one-step chemical vapor deposition (CVD) strategy for the direct synthesis of Mo₂C nanorods. Gallium (Ga), deposited on Mo foil, acts as a transient liquid growth medium under CH₄ flow at temperatures above 900°C, enabling anisotropic and directional Mo₂C growth. Following synthesis, Ga is selectively etched, exposing well-defined, high-aspect-ratio Mo₂C nanorods. Their structure and crystallinity were confirmed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Raman spectroscopy, and X-ray diffraction (XRD), while their enhanced performance in the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) demonstrates the catalytic potential of this approach.

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Keyword: CVD, Nanorod, Molybdenum Carbide, Gallium

The Production of Different Carbon Nanomaterials During the Methane Catalytic Decomposition in the Microwave Assisted Reactor System.

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Methane decomposition is a promising pathway for hydrogen production that avoids CO₂ emissions while yielding valuable carbon nanomaterials. It is an endothermic process that occurs at high temperatures, such as around 1200 °C, can be carried out at lower temperatures in the presence of a catalyst [1].

Conventional heating is extensively utilized in literature as a heating method, however, microwave-based heating has been found to boost catalytic reaction rates and selectivity. Additionally, compared to conventional heating for chemical reactions, microwave heating offers several advantages, such as high heating power, volumetric and quick heating, contactless heating, easy drying or heating control, and smaller equipment sizes [2]. This study examines the catalytic performance of carbon supported nickel (Ni) activated catalyst with and without promoter (La and Pd) in a microwave-assisted reactor system. Moreover, the formation of different carbon nanostructures, such as carbon nanofibers, encapsulated carbon, carbon nanotubes, under the effect of microwave energy is investigated in comparison to conventionally heated system. Catalysts were prepared using the impregnation method, with improvements to ensure homogeneous metal distribution and minimize agglomeration, especially for high metal loadings (up to 50 wt%). The physical and structural properties of the synthesized catalysts were characterized using various techniques, such as Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) analysis, Nitrogen physisorption, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), Raman spectroscopy, Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The catalytic activities of the synthesized catalysts were evaluated under continuous flow conditions using a microwave generator provided by SAIREM. The carbon nanotube structures were observed besides the encapsulated carbon structures for lanthanum promoted catalysts whereas encapsulated carbon was seen for minor amount of La added catalyst as an indication of lower activity. Pd-modified catalysts demonstrated superior performance, retaining activity for up to 400 minutes under reaction conditions. Pd's ability to promote the growth of uniform carbon nanostructures, mitigate carbon agglomeration, and prevent sintering greatly enhanced catalytic efficiency.

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Keyword: methane decomposition, heterogeneous catalysts, hydrogen, nanomaterials

Solid State Synthesis of ZIF-67: Effect of Temperature on the Properties

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Zeolitic-imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs), which have been constituted by combining a metal source (Zn and Co) and an organic ligand (Imidazole), have emerged as a Metal-Organic Framework (MOF). Even if they resemble zeolites regarding their bond type and angle, ZIFs possess unique features such as high surface area and porosity, and thermal and chemical stability [1]. Thanks to these outstanding properties, ZIFs have been utilized in several applications such as the separation of binary gas mixtures and the adsorption of hazardous chemicals from water, such as PFAS [2-3]. ZIF-67, which is one of the ZIFs, has crystallinity, a high surface area (up to over 1700 m²/g), microporosity, and high affinity in catalytic reactions. Besides that, its properties can be improved by composting it with other materials such as carbon. Nowadays, green synthesis methods, avoiding the utilization of excess chemicals and energy, have gained popularity regarding global warming issues [1]. Within this regard, this study aimed to produce ZIF-67 by using solid-state synthesis. The procedure was applied in the same with Chaemchuen and co-workers' study via a slight modification [4]. In different, cobalt nitrate salt was used as a metal source, and static air for the synthesis atmosphere. Three different synthesis temperatures were tested at 200, 300, and 400 °C. The effect of temperature on the ZIF-67 properties was observed via XRD, SEM-EDX, and N₂ sorption analysis. The solid-state synthesis is crucial for ZIF synthesis since this method does not require to use of any solvent (water, methanol) and excess energy (ultrasonication, centrifugation, ball-milling). Besides that, the synthesis time is low compared to the conventional solvothermal method.

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Keyword: MOF, ZIF, green chemistry

Synthesis and Characterization of Mg-Al Layered Double Hydroxides by Co-Precipitation Method: Structural, Morphological and Spectroscopic

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Layered double hydroxides (LDHs) have recently received a lot of attention because of their distinctive layered structures, ion-exchange capabilities, and multifunctional features, which make them appropriate for a wide range of technical and environmental applications. Among these, Mg-Al-based LDHs stand out for their chemical stability, environmental compatibility, and inexpensive synthesis costs. In this study, Mg-Al LDH was successfully synthesized using the co-precipitation method under reflux circumstances at pH 10. The synthesized material's structural, morphological, and chemical properties were carefully examined utilizing XRD, SEM, EDX, and FTIR investigations. XRD data confirmed the development of a typical LDH structure with distinctive diffraction peaks, but small impurity signals showed that synthesis should be optimized. SEM investigation revealed slightly disordered sheet-like morphologies, which corroborated the structural abnormalities reported in XRD. EDX revealed the existence of essential elements (Mg, Al, O, and C), indicating that the LDH phase was successfully formed. Furthermore, FTIR spectra confirmed the structural integrity and functional groups of the produced material. The financial support by TUBITAK (Project Code: 223M389) is gratefully acknowledged.

Keyword: Layered Double Hydroxides, Mg-Al LDH, XRD, SEM

Biowaste-Derived Activated Carbon for Sustainable Applications: A Synergic Pathway Using Almond Shells and Modified Starch

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The global emphasis on sustainable carbon-based materials has accelerated interest in agricultural residues toward circular economy goals [1]. Within this framework, lignocellulosic and biopolymer-rich wastes are gaining attention as renewable feedstocks for the synthesis of functional carbon materials [2]. This approach not only mitigates biowaste accumulation but also contributes to circular economy principles by transforming low-value residues into high-performance materials [3].

This study demonstrates a synergic pathway strategy for synthesizing activated carbon (AC) from two distinct biowaste sources: almond shells (a lignocellulosic agro-waste) and bio-based modified starch (a renewable biopolymer). These abundant and underutilized feedstocks provide a sustainable platform for developing value-added carbon materials. The dual-precursor system was designed to evaluate the comparative efficacy of lignocellulosic versus polysaccharide-based materials with blends prepared at different mass ratios (1:1, 1:3, and 3:1) to investigate their influence on the physicochemical properties of the final product. For this purpose, the synthesis of biowaste-derived activated carbon (BAC) involved a three-step process: pre-carbonization (500 °C for 5 min), chemical activation by phosphoric acid (50°C for 12 h), and final carbonization processes (900 °C for 5 min) under an inert argon atmosphere that enhance its porosity and surface area.

Comprehensive characterization of the synthesized activated carbons was conducted using a suite of advanced techniques to elucidate their structural and morphological properties. XRD analysis was employed to investigate the crystalline/amorphous nature of the carbon materials. All samples displayed two broad peaks centered approximately at $2\theta=24-25^\circ$ and $2\theta=43-44^\circ$, which correspond to the (002) and (100) planes of graphitic carbon, respectively. Raman spectroscopy confirmed the presence of the D band ($1332-1343\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and G band ($1589-1592\text{ cm}^{-1}$), with I_D/I_G ratios (0.92-0.95) indicating moderate graphitization and significant defect density. All samples exhibited a moderate level of graphitic character with substantial defect density. Moreover, surface morphology and microstructural features of BAC materials by SEM analysis was revealed well-developed porous textures with surface irregularities, particularly in samples with higher almond shell content, which exhibited dense microporosity attributed to the lignocellulosic matrix.

These findings not only validate the potential of dual biowaste-derived precursors for producing biowaste-derived activated carbon but also pave the way for future research focused on application-specific optimization, scale-up processes, and integration into sustainable water treatment, energy storage, and environmental remediation systems.

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Keyword: *Activated carbon, renewable feedstocks, microporosity, sustainability*

Microwave Assisted One Step Synthesis of Hydrophilic Upconversion Nanoparticles

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Upconversion nanomaterials attract great attention in many areas such as biomedical imaging, photodynamic therapy, gas sensors, solar panels and anti-counterfeiting due to their ability to convert low-energy infrared light into high-energy visible or ultraviolet light. In this study, it was aimed to synthesize hydrophilic NaGdF₄:Yb³⁺:Er³⁺ upconversion nanoparticles with a rapid, single-step and environmentally friendly method. In microwave-assisted synthesis, lower energy is required compared to traditional methods. In addition, the method is not required inert gas and not lead to produce toxic by-products and wastes. This study is also important because the Gd³⁺ ions in the host crystal structure can be used as contrast agents in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) applications. As a result of the synthesis, hydrophilic nanoparticles coated with acetic acid (or cellulose) were obtained with a narrow particles size distribution. The structural properties of the synthesized nanoparticles were determined by XRD, SEM and DLS. Steady state luminescence, luminescence lifetime and power dependent luminescence properties of Er³⁺ ion were characterized using upconversion luminescence spectroscopy using 976 nm excitation light. It was determined that the obtained particles exhibited strong upconversion luminescence and high stability in aqueous media. The obtained results show that the microwave-assisted one-step method offers a rapid and efficient alternative for the production of hydrophilic upconversion nanoparticles.

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Keyword: *upconversion nanoparticle, hydrophilic, one step synthesis, upconversion luminescence*

Zinc Chalcogenide Shell Engineering for High-Efficiency Colloidal Nanoplatelet LEDs

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Colloidal quantum wells, also known as nanoplatelets (NPLs), are emerging as highly promising materials for light-emitting devices (LEDs) due to their narrow emission spectra and strong quantum confinement. However, most studied core/shell heterostructured NPLs rely on cadmium-based shells such as CdS, which are both toxic and offer suboptimal charge confinement. In this study, we present a novel synthetic approach to grow zinc chalcogenide shells on CdSe core NPLs, exploring various shell compositions.

We first synthesized CdSe/ZnSe core/shell NPLs, which exhibited red emission in the 615–630 nm range and photoluminescence quantum yields (PL-QYs) of 40–50%. Interestingly, reducing the lateral dimensions of the core led to narrower emission linewidths, reaching as low as 20 nm. To further enhance optical performance, a ZnS terminal shell layer was introduced, boosting the PL-QY to 80–90%.

Solution-processed LEDs were subsequently fabricated using both CdSe/ZnSe and CdSe/ZnSe/ZnS NPLs as the active emissive layers. The incorporation of the ZnS shell significantly enhanced device performance, increasing the external quantum efficiency (EQE) from 0.80% to 3.82% and improving the maximum brightness from 4479 to 6477 cd/m².

These results demonstrate the strong potential of zinc chalcogenide-based shell layers for developing environmentally friendlier and more efficient colloidal NPL-based LEDs.

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Keyword: *Colloidal Nanoplatelets, Solution-Processed LEDs, Core/Multi-shell Structures, Colloidal Quantum Wells*

Metallic Sponge-Like Structure Functionalized Electrodes for Amino Acid Detection

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Amino acids are important molecules in human physiology and biology, especially in biomedical research. Alterations in their concentrations are closely associated with the development of various metabolic and genetic disorders, emphasizing the need for precise and reliable monitoring with analytical techniques. Redox-active compound L-tryptophan is an essential amino acid that takes part in various biological processes in the human body and therefore the determination of L-tryptophan is extremely important. Carbon and metallic-based materials are commonly used in the modification of electrodes for the electrochemical determination of various analytes, due to improved electrochemical surface area and electron transfer rate, low cost, chemical stability, availability for precise and rapid detection [1-5]. In this study, platinum and iron (PtFe)-based sponge-like structures (NS) combined with carbon black (CB) were modified on screen printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) for tryptophan detection. The ratio of PtFe-CB and pH of the medium were optimized. Characterization studies were performed by cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Modification of the electrodes were also monitored with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). DPV was used in the determination studies and the detection limit was found to be 0,67µM.

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Keyword: *Electrochemistry, Sponge-like structure, L- tryptophan, Carbon and metallic-based material*

Copper Nanoparticles/Carbon Black Functionalized Electrodes for Tryptophan Detection

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Tryptophan is an amino acid that cannot be synthesized in the human body and therefore must be taken from external resources. Its deficiencies and excesses may cause various neurological and biological diseases. For this reason, detection of the tryptophan biomolecule has become an interesting and important subject in terms of sensor development. In this study, electrochemical preparation of copper nanoparticles (CuNPs)/carbon black (CB) modified pencil graphite electrodes (PGEs) were utilized to determine L-tryptophan. Copper is selected in the sensor design due to its natural abundance, low cost, and high conductivity, as well as its unique structural properties [1-5]. PGEs were firstly modified with CB and then this step was followed up by the electrochemical deposition of Cu-based nanoparticles via cyclic voltammetry (CV) to improve the electrochemical properties of the electrode, such as high electron transfer rate. Before the electroanalytical measurements performed by differential pulse voltammetry (DPV), parameters such as medium pH and cycles used in the CV method were optimized. For the electrochemical characterization studies, CV, DPV, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) techniques were used. Modification of the electrodes were also visualized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

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Keyword: *Carbon materials and Metallic-based structures, Copper nanoparticles, Electrochemistry, L-tryptophan*

Enhancement of the Antimicrobial Activity by Using Chitosan-Coated Green-Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles Against Gram-Negative Bacteria

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Recently, antimicrobials have shown resistance in clinical environments, including resistance against antibacterial drugs, such as *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. On the other hand, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) show a good strategy as an antibacterial due to their properties. In this study, we used green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from green tea as a reagent to increase the stability of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and coat them with chitosan and Gentamicin as a nanocomposite for enhancing antimicrobial activity against Gram-negative bacteria. The shape of silver nanoparticles was spherical-like, with an average size around 30-10nm and Z-potential -55.8 mV. This nanocomposite leads to a decrease in bacterial growth compared to Gentamicin alone. This nanocomposite leads to a synergistic effect with antibiotics. It provides a novel strategy to combat antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections

Keyword: *Green synthesis, Silver Nanoparticles, Antimicrobial Resistance*

Antimicrobial Activity of Chitosan-Coated, Green-Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles Against Gram-Negative Bacteria

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Recently, bacteria, such as *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, have shown resistance in clinical environments, including resistance against antibacterial drugs. Yet, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) show promising antimicrobial activity due to their superior properties. In this study, green synthesis of AgNPs was successfully achieved from green tea as a reducing reagent to increase the stability of AgNPs. Moreover, AgNPs were coated with chitosan and gentamicin to form a nanocomposite, which was endowed with antimicrobial activity against Gram-negative bacteria. The shape of silver nanoparticles was spherical-like, with an average size around 30-10 nm and Z-potential at -55.8 mV. The results showed that the nanocomposite has antimicrobial activity compared to AgNPs alone. In contrast, the nanocomposite did not show an improved antimicrobial activity compared to GENTA alone. The findings of this study provide a novel strategy to combat antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections.

Keyword: *Green Synthesis, Silver Nanoparticles, Nanocomposite, Antimicrobial Resistance*

Synthesis and Engineering of Redox-Active NanoMOFs For PDT: A Step Towards Light-Triggered Cancer Therapeutics

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Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a prospective cancer treatment due to its precision and minor side effects. However, two primary impediments frequently undermine its efficacy: high glutathione (GSH) concentrations, which aid cancer cells in neutralizing reactive oxygen species (ROS), and low oxygen levels in tumors (hypoxia). To overcome these challenges, our work focuses on designing nanoscale metal–organic frameworks (nanoMOFs) based on redox metals like copper (Cu²⁺) and bismuth (Bi³⁺), certainly known for their redox-driven catalytic activity. Such nanoMOFs may significantly promote deeper penetration of light while actively depleting GSH levels via redox cycling, impairing the antioxidant defenses of cancer cells. Herein, we have synthesized Cu and Bi-based nanoMOFs while adopting a synergistic platform that could have tumor-selective ROS diffusion, GSH scavenging, and catalytic ROS amplification even under hypoxic settings. To achieve regulated particle size, morphology, crystallinity, and improved dispersibility in aqueous environments, we have modified the nucleation process through nucleation time, solvent, pH, Temperature and capping agents. The resultant nMOFs demonstrated variable particle size from 50-120 nm via a controlled nucleation process. The structural, functional, and morphological characteristics of the resultant nMOFs were validated using FTIR, UV-Vis, XPS, PL, and Raman spectroscopy, followed by XRD, BET, and FESEM analyses. The results of the respective characterization techniques advocated the successful synthesis of the Cu and Bi-based nMOFs with improved surface and functional attributes, which are essential for triggering PDT pathways in biological settings. **Acknowledgement:** This publication was created by benefiting from the 2236-B Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Cofund Scholarship Programs Contribution Fund Program (TUBITAK project ID: 123C460) and Horizon Europe MSCA Cofund Postdoctoral Program (EU project ID: 101126492). The views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or TUBITAK. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

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Keyword: *Nano MOFs, Photodynamic Treatment (PDT), Synthesis and characterization, Cancer Therapeutics*

Seeded Droplet-Microfluidic Synthesis of V-MIL-47 for Accelerated Production

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Vanadium-based metal-organic framework V-MIL-47 exhibits significant potential across diverse applications, including catalysis [1], separation processes [2], gas storage [3], and drug delivery [4], attributed to its high surface-area-to-volume ratio, alongside utility in anticorrosion coatings [5] leveraging its inherent redox activity in corrosive media. While conventional countertop macroscale static MOF synthesis [6] in milliliter-volume autoclaves presents challenges in precisely controlling nucleation kinetics and resulting particle dimensions, droplet-based microfluidic systems, with their picoliter reactor volumes, have emerged as promising platforms for nanoparticle synthesis due to enhanced mass and heat transfer characteristics and facilitated homogeneous mixing and diffusion [7]. However, maintaining identical thermodynamic parameters, such as temperature and concentration, between milliliter autoclaves and picoliter droplet reactors does not ensure synchronous nucleation owing to disparate pressure regimes experienced by the liquid precursor solution: precursor solution-vapor interface versus precursor solution-oil interface, respectively. The constrained molecular interactions within the limited volume of picoliter droplets can further impede nucleation.

To address these limitations and achieve more controlled, rapid, and precise synthesis of V-MIL-47 nanoparticles, this study introduces a novel strategy of employing a seeded precursor solution for microfluidic synthesis. A flow-focusing microchannel device with a hydrodynamic diameter of 100 microns was used for continuous generation of monodisperse precursor droplets. Silicone oil and precursor solution were used as the continuous and dispersed phases, respectively. Continuous generation of 50-60 micron uniform precursor-solution droplets was achieved. To facilitate heterogeneous nucleation, precursor solution was combined with pre-synthesized V-MIL-47 seeds of various sizes, 136±18 and 1097±369, at 5 mg for 5 mL of solution.

For synthesis in the milliliter autoclave at 150°C and 2 hours, the cases of using no-seeds and 136 nm seeds resulted with amorphous particles, i.e. no V-MIL-47 production, whereas using 1097 nm seeds with the same recipe resulted with large, agglomerated V-MIL-47 particles. For synthesis in picoliter droplets at the same conditions, using seeds of 1097 nm resulted with V-MIL-47 particles of 67±14 nm in size. Our work demonstrated that using the seeding approach with the microfluidic route facilitated rapid nucleation with enhanced control over particle size and uniformity, effectively mitigating the aggregation observed in comparable conventional autoclave synthesis that yielded amorphous or agglomerated products under identical conditions.

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Keyword: *Metal organic framework (MOF), Seeded synthesis, Droplet based microfluidic, Nanoparticles*

Preparation of Nanoparticle-Immobilized Gold Surfaces for the Reversible Conjugation of Neurotensin Peptide

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Polymer coatings as thin films stand out as a commonly used strategy to modify biosensor surfaces for improving detection performance; however, nonspecific biomolecule interactions and the limited degree of ligand conjugation on the surface have necessitated the development of innovative methods for surface modification. To this end, methacrylated tethered telechelic polyethylene glycol (PEG-diMA) chains of three different molecular weights (2, 6, and 10 kDa) were synthesized herein and used for obtaining thiolated nanoparticles (NPs) upon adding excess amounts of a tetra-thiol crosslinker.[1] Characterized according to their size, surface charge, morphology, and thiol amounts, these nanoparticles were immobilized on gold surfaces that mimicked gold-coated mass sensor platforms. The PEG-based nanoparticles, prepared especially by PEG6K-diMA polymers, were shown to result in the preparation of a monolayer and smooth coating of 80–120 nm thickness. Cysteine-modified NTS(8–13) peptide (RRPYIL) was conjugated to thiolated NP with reversible disulfide bonds, and it was demonstrated that its cleavage with a reducing agent such as dithiothreitol (DTT) restores the NP-immobilized gold surface for at least two cycles. Together with its binding studies to NTSR2 antibodies, it was revealed that the peptide-conjugated NP-modified gold surface could be employed as a model for a reusable sensor surface for the detection of biomarkers of the same or different types.

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[1] Preparation of Nanoparticle-Immobilized Gold Surfaces for the Reversible Conjugation of Neurotensin Peptide. *Biomolecules* 2025, 15, 767.

Keyword: reactive nanoparticles, poly(ethylene glycol), surface modification, disulfide exchange reaction

A Solvent-Free Strategy for the Fabrication of Superhydrophobic Surfaces via Photochemical Activation

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One of the major obstacles to the widespread use of superhydrophobic coatings in practical applications is the reliance on conventional methods that involve multi-step, time-consuming chemical processes and expensive materials. In this study, we introduce a simple and solvent-free method that, for the first time, allows the direct grafting of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) in dry form onto metal oxide photocatalyst surfaces. Unlike conventional approaches that use liquid PDMS, our strategy utilizes free oligomers released from cured flexible PDMS to functionalize the metal oxide particles. This innovative technique enables effective PDMS grafting without the need for complex chemical reactions. The resulting superhydrophobic particles exhibited a high-water contact angle of 169° and a low sliding angle of 2°, indicating excellent water repellency. Furthermore, these functional powders demonstrated high photocatalytic activity, achieving 98% degradation efficiency of organic pollutants such as methylene blue under UV irradiation within just 30 minutes. These results demonstrate the potential of this environmentally friendly, scalable, and solvent-free process for the development of multifunctional nanomaterials, particularly for environmental applications such as water purification.

Keyword: PDMS, superhydrophobic, sustainability, photocatalysis

Physicochemical and Biological Evaluation of SPION-Loaded Hyaluronic Acid Nanocapsules for Biomedical Imaging

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Magnetic nanoparticles play an important role in the development of multifunctional nanocarrier systems that combine diagnosis and treatment. In this study, β -cyclodextrin-coated superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) were in situ encapsulated into hyaluronic acid nanocapsules (HANCs). HANCs were synthesized by polyaddition reaction in the inverse miniemulsion technique. To prepare two different magnetic formulations, 1 mg/mL and 2 mg/mL of SPIONs were added to the water phase during the synthesis. The prepared nanocapsules were imaged by Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) to examine their morphologies. Then, the presence and amount of SPIONs in the HANCs were quantitatively determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). In addition, the long-term stability of SPION-loaded HANCs (S-HANCs) was evaluated. Physiological stability was assessed by monitoring the colloidal characteristics of HANCs and S-HANCs in biologically relevant media (PBS, PBS containing 10% FBS, DMEM, and DMEM containing 10% FBS) at 37 °C for 120 hours. Time-dependent particle size and zeta potential changes were monitored by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and electrophoretic light scattering (ELS). In addition, the in vitro cytotoxicity of HANCs and S-HANCs on L929 cells for 24 and 48 hours was evaluated. The obtained results show that SPIONs were successfully encapsulated with HANCs. It was determined that this system remained stable in physiological environments and exhibited low cytotoxicity. In addition, the specific binding ability of HA to CD44 receptors supports the use of these HANCs structures as targeted nanocarriers in biomedical imaging applications.

Keyword: *superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, hyaluronic acid nanocarriers, stability, biomedical imaging*

Gd₂O₃-ZnO-AC Nanocomposite as an electrode material

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The growing demand for efficient and sustainable energy storage systems has intensified research into advanced electrode materials for supercapacitors. In this study, a novel ternary composite comprising **gadolinium oxide (Gd₂O₃)**, **zinc oxide (ZnO)**, and **activated carbon (AC)** was synthesized and evaluated for its electrochemical performance as a supercapacitor electrode. The activated carbon was derived from waste cigarette butts through pyrolysis followed by chemical activation, providing a high-surface-area matrix. ZnO and Gd₂O₃ nanoparticles were incorporated via a wet chemical co-precipitation route to enhance the pseudocapacitive behaviour and conductivity of the composite. The structural, morphological, and textural properties were characterized using EPR, XRD, SEM, BET, and FTIR techniques.

Electrochemical measurements conducted in a two-electrode setup using 1 M KOH as the electrolyte revealed that the Gd₂O₃-ZnO-AC composite exhibited excellent specific capacitance, superior rate capability, and enhanced cyclic stability compared to pristine AC and binary composites. The synergistic effect between the metal oxides and porous carbon framework contributed to improved charge storage through a combination of electrical double-layer capacitance and Faradaic redox reactions. The composite retained over 90% of its initial capacitance after 5000 cycles, demonstrating excellent stability. These findings highlight the potential of Gd₂O₃-ZnO-AC as a promising electrode material for high-performance supercapacitor applications.

Keyword: *gadolinium oxide, zinc oxide, activated carbon, supercapacitors*

Fabrication of Conjugated Organic Polymers through Monomer Modulation and Their Performances in Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries

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High energy demand results in a simultaneous need for energy storage, which is why lithium-ion batteries are commonly utilized. However, expensive/limited lithium resources and safety issues related to organic electrolytes have initiated the search for other possible anode materials.^[1] Considering the drawbacks of lithium-ion batteries, zinc is a promising candidate for next-generation batteries. It shows high compatibility with aqueous electrolytes, a high theoretical specific capacity of 820 mA h g⁻¹ and a low redox potential of -0.76 V vs SHE.^[2] However, the advantages of aqueous zinc-ion batteries (AZIBs) are hindered by the inorganic cathode materials, as these materials go through a significant lattice collapse and volumetric swelling with increased cycling, thus deteriorating the cycle stability and capacity of the battery.^[3] To overcome these challenges, quinone-rich redox-active organic materials that operate through reversible enolization/de-enolization processes can be employed to fabricate high-performance AZIBs.^[4] In this regard, conjugated organic polymers were synthesized using different quinone-containing monomers to investigate how the structural manipulation of these monomers impacts the electrochemical performance of AZIBs. These cathode materials' rate capabilities, specific capacities, and cycling stabilities were investigated to reveal the effect of monomer engineering, which resulted in alterations in the number of redox-active sites, conjugation, and structural features. Furthermore, the charge storage mechanism involving Zn²⁺/H⁺ co-insertion was elucidated in detail.

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Keyword: *conjugated organic polymers, monomer-engineering, aqueous zinc-ion batteries, cathode materials*

Synthesis and Characterization of Charged Porous Organic Polymers for CO₂ Utilization

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CO₂ capture and conversion technologies play a crucial role in mitigating the adverse environmental impacts of carbon emissions from the combustion of fossil fuels to meet the increasing energy demand, including global warming and sea level rise. The design and synthesis of porous organic polymers aiming to reduce excessive CO₂ emissions have garnered significant attention due to their superior properties, such as tunable pore sizes, good chemical stability, and easy functionalization.[1] In this study, charged porous organic polymers have been designed and synthesized to investigate their CO₂ uptake performance and catalytic activity for CO₂ conversion. These synthesized porous charged organic polymers have been utilized as an adsorbent and organocatalyst not only for capturing CO₂ but also for converting CO₂ to cyclic carbonates in the presence of related epoxides.

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Keyword: *porous organic polymers, charged polymers, CO₂ capture and conversion, cyclic carbonates*

Effects of Mixing Conditions and Additives on Precipitation and Stability of Amorphous Calcium Phosphate

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Calcium phosphate (CaP) mineralization has been under extensive research mostly due to CaP's biological relevance, as it constitutes the main mineral content in human bones and teeth^[1]. Although the formation mechanism of biological apatites is not yet fully understood due to the complexity of in vivo systems, in situ investigations of hydroxyapatite (HA) formation suggest a precursor-mediated pathway in which amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) is frequently involved^[2]. Beyond its biological role, ACP has attracted growing interest due to its versatile physicochemical properties and its ability to transform into various crystalline CaP phases, making it a valuable material for numerous applications^[3]. However, its inherent instability in aqueous environments, where it rapidly transforms into more stable phases, remains a major limitation^[4]. Therefore, stabilizing ACP is crucial for fully utilizing its transformation potential and functional versatility. In this work, we focus on the stabilization of ACP using titration experiments that enable simultaneous analysis of solution chemistry and solid-phase evolution. Three different titration setups were used, namely, titrating calcium solution to phosphate solution, vice versa, and both sources to a blank solution. In addition to the titration method, additive effects were investigated using citrate, known to prolong ACP stability and delay HA crystallization, and BSA, representing a bulk macromolecule with nonspecific interactions. During the experiments, in-situ pH profiles and Ca²⁺ ion activity were continuously monitored, while the collected precipitates at intermediate and final stages were characterized using XRD, Raman, FTIR, SEM, TEM, and TGA. The identity of the precipitating phases remained consistent across conditions, with ACP forming initially, followed by HA crystallization. However, the stability and lifetime of ACP were strongly influenced by both titration procedure and additive presence. Furthermore, ICP-OES and TGA analyses were performed to assess the Ca/P ratios and hydration levels of ACP under different experimental conditions. The findings offer valuable insight into ACP stabilization mechanisms and will inform future studies on controlled HA formation in synthetic environments.

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Keyword: *Amorphous calcium phosphate, Crystallization, Solution Chemistry*

The Modification of Partial Oxidation Based Magnetic Nanoparticles with Cyclodextrin and Application in Magnetic Hyperthermia

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Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles are one of the most preferred materials for nanotechnology-based applications due to their excellent magnetic properties along with extremely adequate biocompatibility. The efficient incorporation of magnetic nanoparticles to relevant applications relies on utilization of specific surface functionalization. The surface modification allows both the binding of niche molecules to the surface and enhance the colloidal stability. β -Cyclodextrin (β -CD) is a cyclic oligosaccharide consisting of both a hydrophilic outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity. The structural characteristics of this system facilitate the formation of complexes with a range of hydrophobic guest molecules, including drugs. These guest molecules can be encapsulated within the non-polar cavity of β -CD, thereby rendering β -CD a highly versatile platform for applications in the controlled release of drugs. Although, magnetic nanoparticles are shown to be modified with several molecules for biomedical applications, the surface functionalization of relatively larger and unconventional partial oxidation based magnetic nanoparticles with β -CD has not been studied extensively. Consequently, the objective of this study was to synthesize magnetic nanoparticles in the presence of β -CD possessing adequate colloidal stability in aqueous medium and subsequently analyze its potential in hyperthermia applications via studying the local temperature enhancements at varying concentrations, magnetic field strengths and frequencies. The results demonstrated that the magnetic nanoparticles synthesized using the partial oxidation method exhibited an average size of 27 nm and a saturation magnetization of 48.4 emu/g. Furthermore, the obtained nanoparticles exhibited sufficient colloidal stability and morphological changes after modification with β -CD. In addition, hyperthermia analyses conducted in the presence of an alternating magnetic field have indicated that local temperatures increased in conjunction with concentration, magnetic field strength, and frequency. The findings demonstrate the preliminary possibility of magnetic nanoparticles modified with β -CD and synthesized using the partial oxidation method for utilization in both drug delivery and hyperthermia applications.

Keyword: *Magnetic nanoparticles, Cyclodextrin, Hyperthermia*

Benzoxazine-Based Networks for Iodine Removal from Water and Air

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Radioactive isotopes of iodine are generated as a fission side-product during the production of nuclear energy, presenting a significant hazard in the reprocessing of nuclear fuel. ^[1] To address this issue, various types of adsorbent materials have been developed, including various organic materials. Among these organic materials, porous organic networks have attracted remarkable attention due to their stability in aqueous media and synthetic versatility. ^[2] In this context, benzoxazine-based porous organic networks were synthesized, and derivatives of these networks were also prepared by the thermal ring opening of benzoxazine linkages. The iodine adsorption capacity of these resultant intrinsically porous benzoxazine organic networks was investigated under both aqueous and vapor conditions. Additionally, the structure-property relationships governing iodine adsorption were investigated using both experimental and theoretical approaches.

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Keyword: *organic networks, benzoxazines, iodine capture, porous materials*

Functional Heteroatom Rich Porous Organic Polymers for Efficient Iodine and CO₂ Capture

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As the global energy demand continues to rise, there has been a tremendous increase in the levels of atmospheric CO₂ due to the reliance on fossil fuels to meet energy needs. The increasing levels of atmospheric CO₂, an important contributor to global warming, have become a significant environmental concern. [1] While nuclear energy can be seen as a low CO₂ emission alternative, it also generates hazardous radioactive species, such as iodine isotopes (¹²⁹I, ¹³¹I), which have become a serious problem for health and the environment [2]. As a result, research into environmental remediation has gained considerable attention in recent years to capture iodine and CO₂ from the atmosphere. In this study, functional heteroatom-rich porous organic polymers were synthesized with the aim of enhancing the uptake capacity of both iodine and CO₂. Throughout the design process, structure-activity relationships were carefully evaluated to optimize the sorption processes. [3] Various analytical techniques (FTIR, NMR, TGA, Raman, XRD, etc.) have been employed to characterize the materials, confirming their chemical structure, porosity, and thermal stability. The synthesized polymers exhibited a high uptake capacity for both iodine and CO₂, highlighting the impact of molecular design on uptake efficiency.

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Keyword: *porous organic polymers, iodine capture, CO₂ capture, environmental remediation*

Nanoporous Palladium-Gold Alloy Films for Hydrogen Detection

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Hydrogen, one of the renewable energy sources, has many areas of use in the industry such as petrochemical, chemistry, food, semiconductor technology, fuel cell technology, and aerospace[1,2]. The detection of hydrogen is vital because human senses cannot perceive hydrogen and hydrogen is the lightest element, non-odorless, toxic, colorless, tasteless, flammable and flammable-explosive when found between 4% and 75% in environment. Commonly used hydrogen sensor platforms can be mainly classified into nine types depending physico-chemical principles such as electrochemical, resistor based, catalytic, work function based, thermal conductivity, optical, acoustic, mechanical, and magnetic in various reviews[3-5]. We focused on the metallic resistive-type H₂ sensor that is a part of a resistor-based H₂ sensor.

This study presents the preparation of palladium – gold (Pd-Au) alloy thin films onto anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) with varying thicknesses from 5 nm to 50 nm by using the DC magnetron co-sputtering method and investigation of their resistive hydrogen sensing properties depending on annealing, film thickness, concentration and temperature. The synthesis of anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) nanotubes with an average pore diameter of less than 120 nm served as the template for the fabrication of nanoporous Pd-Au films using an anodization method. This was achieved by applying a voltage of 60 V in 0.4 M of a phosphoric acid solution at 20 °C. From the structural analysis, EDX and XPS results is revealed that the Pd/Au ratio of the deposited films was about 30/70 at.%. The hydrogen sensing mechanism and the sensor performance of Pd-Au alloy thin films will be discussed in detail.

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Keyword: palladium, gold, PdAu alloy, DC sputtering

Synthesis of Bovine Serum Albumin-Based Nanoparticles Using Full Factorial Design of Experiments

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This study investigates the synthesis of albumin-based nanocarriers using the inverse miniemulsion method with interfacial polyaddition reaction. The evaluation of formulation parameters on the performance of carriers is a pivotal point in the design of drug delivery systems. The optimization is carried out with a full factorial experimental design approach, and the effect of formulation factors such as emulsifier amount, crosslinker amount, and co-emulsifier usage on particle size and stability is compared. In the study, a systematic optimization strategy is presented to obtain controlled-sized and stable nanoparticle dispersions. Further analyses reveal that parameters such as the type of surfactants in the redispersion step play a decisive role in the physicochemical and morphological properties of nanoparticles. A novel use of co-emulsifier in the continuous oil phase, and alternative nonionic surfactants in the final aqueous dispersions, provides important information on particle stability and cell viability. This comprehensive study highlights the design of albumin-based nanocarriers and their relevant applications in delivery systems.

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Keyword: *bovine serum albumin, inverse miniemulsion method, interfacial polyaddition reaction, design of experiments*

Fabrication of Strain-Engineered Carbon Nanotube Microstructures

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Scalable nanofabrication is essential for the development of multifunctional and complex surfaces, with critical applications in tissue engineering, dynamic interfaces, lab-on-a-chip systems, biomedical devices, and advanced microelectromechanical systems (MEMS). Despite the demand for precise control at the micron scale, fabricating such structures remains challenging. Existing top-down methods—such as stereolithography, multiphoton lithography, and focused ion beam techniques—are effective for producing random architectures or master templates, but are not well suited for creating large-scale, arrayed microstructures. In this context, bottom-up approaches like self-assembly offer a promising route for scalable nanostructure fabrication. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), in particular, are ideal candidates due to their ability to be grown vertically from catalyst-patterned substrates. Photolithographic patterning defines the horizontal geometry, while vertical CNT growth completes the 3D structure. However, traditional CNT synthesis typically results in planar arrays, as CNT forests grow perpendicular to the substrate with mutual support from adjacent nanotubes—limiting the formation of non-planar or curved geometries. To address this, we developed a new method to control CNT forest growth rates by varying the thickness of the catalyst layer. CNTs grown on thinner or thicker catalyst films exhibit different growth rates, leading to height differentials between adjacent regions. When regions with different catalyst thicknesses are patterned side by side, the faster-growing CNTs mechanically influence their slower-growing neighbors, inducing bending and curvature due to differential growth. This interaction enables the fabrication of curved, non-planar, and even re-entrant CNT microstructures. Furthermore, we demonstrated that the radius of curvature can be finely tuned by adjusting synthesis parameters such as gas flow rate, growth time, and temperature—enabling scalable, deterministic control over the final geometry. As a proof of concept, we fabricated anisotropic wetting surfaces that direct water flow along desired paths using these curved CNT microstructures.

Keyword: *Carbon Nanotube, Nano Fabrication, Anisotropic Surfaces*

Synthesis of Molecularly Imprinted Polymer Modified SiO₂ Particles for Extracellular Vesicles Isolation via Janus Micromotors

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Cervical cancer remains a prevalent gynecological malignancy with significant global health implications. Although human papillomavirus (HPV) infection is a well-established etiological factor, the precise molecular mechanisms driving HPV-induced carcinogenesis are not fully elucidated. Recent evidence highlights the critical role of extracellular vesicles (EVs) in cancer progression, particularly as mediators of intercellular communication. These nanoscale vesicles, which are abundantly present in biological fluids, carry bioactive molecules that modulate tumor microenvironments and metastatic processes. Given their diagnostic accessibility, EVs have emerged as promising targets for liquid biopsy-based strategies in cervical cancer management. To address the need for high-specificity EV isolation techniques, this study leverages molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs)—synthetic recognition elements that mimic the "lock-and-key" binding mechanism of natural antibodies. MIPs offer distinct advantages over biological receptors, including enhanced stability, cost-effectiveness, and customizable selectivity toward template molecules. Here, we report the synthesis of EV-imprinted MIPs conjugated to silica (SiO₂) microspheres, fabricated via a modified Stöber method. Subsequent functionalization with (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) and N-γ-maleimidobutyryloxy succinimide ester (GMBS) enabled MIP modification, as confirmed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) through characteristic C1s, N1s, and S2s peaks. To further enhance EV capture efficiency, these MIP-modified SiO₂ microspheres will be engineered into Janus micromotors—anisotropic particles inspired by the two-faced Roman God Janus. Janus particles exhibit chemically or morphologically asymmetric surfaces, a property exploited here to confer autonomous motion. Specifically, platinum (Pt) will be deposited on one hemisphere of the SiO₂ microspheres via atomic layer deposition (ALD), creating a catalytic interface for self-propulsion.

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Keyword: *Extracellular Vesicles, Janus Particle, Micromotor, Molecularly Imprinted Polymers*

Modulating Titanium Incorporation into Silicalite-1 via Ultrafast Laser Synthesis

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Titanium Silicalite-1 zeolite (TS-1) is a microporous titanium-containing crystal and is of particular interest due to its unique redox properties, hydrophobicity, and framework-incorporated titanium sites. It is one of the most widely studied zeolites due to its vast catalytic and photocatalytic abilities. These characteristics, however, are limited to the amount of titanium that can be substituted in the zeolite framework. Considerable amounts of research have been conducted to investigate the theoretical limit of titanium amount that can be substituted, and experimental methods to achieve the theoretical maximum. Experimental limit is considered as around 2.5 per unit cell of silicalite-1 structure, and several papers have reported a tendency of increasing titanium parallel with reaction temperature. The conventional hydrothermal synthesis of TS-1 remains energy-intensive and time-consuming, and higher reaction temperatures lead to higher number of defects. To overcome these constraints, we propose an ultrafast laser synthesis method that delivers energy with precise spatiotemporal resolution on femto- to picosecond timescales. Ultrafast pulses thereby allow us to bypass the need for external heating, and enable real-time control over the silica polymerization, nucleation and growth processes. The method utilizes multiphoton absorption within a confined region of the precursor suspension and creates microreactor with local high temperature and pressure (10^5 K and 20 kBar), where titanium and silica containing oligomers can form zeolite crystals under dynamic laser-induced flow conditions. This environment accelerates nucleation and growth, and produce zeolite crystals with superior product quality in terms of uniform particle size, crystallinity and number of defects. Initial trials with TS-1 and other zeolite syntheses have shown a huge reduction in synthesis times to several hours from that typically lasting several days. The TS-1 crystals synthesized via ultrafast laser synthesis method have been characterized by comprehensive analysis tools such as SEM, XRD, ICP-OES, FTIR, UV-Visible, UV-Raman spectroscopy. In addition, the substitution has been tested by photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue by comparing hydrothermal and laser-synthesized TS-1. Ultimately, this research lays the groundwork for a new class of rapid, tunable, and scalable synthetic strategies for high-value zeolitic materials like TS-1, with broad implications for catalysis, environmental remediation, and advanced materials design.

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Keyword: *ultrafast laser, zeolites, light-matter interaction, titanium silicalite-1*

Two Salt-Surfactant Mesophases: Synthesis of Mesoporous MgM₂O₄ (M=Mn, Fe and Co) Electrodes and Their Electrochemical Properties

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Mesoporous magnesium metal oxides (MgM₂O₄, M=Mn(II), Fe(III) and Co(II)) have been synthesized using transition metal nitrate salts ([Mn(H₂O)₄(NO₃)₂], Co(H₂O)₆(NO₃)₂, and [Fe(H₂O)₉(NO₃)₃]), two surfactants; hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), oligo(ethylene oxide) in water and ethanol by employing the molten salt-assisted self-assembly (MASA) approach [1]. Clear solutions of the two salts-two surfactants are prepared and spreaded over various substrates to evaporate the solvent that ensures the formation of a lyotropic liquid crystalline phase (LLC). The gel-LLC coatings are calcined at elevated temperatures to obtain mesoporous MgM₂O₄ thin films. The samples are analyzed using ATR-FTIR, XRD, POM, and SEM. Furthermore, the solutions are also coated over fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) glass substrate and calcined in order to obtain porous electrodes for studying their electrochemical properties by cyclic voltammogram (CV), multi-step chronopotentiometry and amperometry (MCP and MCA) and galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) measurements.

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Keyword: *Mesoporous Materials, Lyotropic Liquid Crystalline Mesophase, Mesoporous Thin Film, Magnesium Metal Oxides*

Reduced Graphene Oxide-Driven Fluorescence Modulation in Aptamer-Based PTH Detection Biosensor Systems

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Reduced graphene oxide (rGO), a partially restored form of graphene oxide, has emerged as a highly promising nanomaterial in the field of biosensing due to its exceptional electrical conductivity, high surface-to-volume ratio, and rich surface chemistry. These properties make rGO particularly suitable for interactions with nucleic acids such as aptamers via π - π stacking and hydrogen bonding, thus this component is very important for on off signal mechanism based biosensors. In the present study, rGO served as a key component in a fluorescence-based aptasensor for the detection of parathormone (PTH). When the 6-FAM-labeled aptamer was adsorbed onto the rGO surface in the absence of PTH, the fluorescence signal was efficiently quenched due to Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET) between the fluorophore and rGO—establishing a "signal OFF" state. However, upon introduction of the target PTH molecule, the aptamer underwent a conformational change to bind its specific epitope on PTH, thereby desorbing from the rGO surface and restoring the fluorescence signal—resulting in a "signal ON" state.

This switchable fluorescence behavior forms the foundation of a highly sensitive detection mechanism, enabling real-time monitoring of PTH concentrations with remarkable specificity and minimal background interference. Compared to traditional techniques such as ELISA or radioimmunoassay, this rGO-based platform offers faster turnaround, reduced reagent consumption, and comparable—if not superior—limits of detection. In this study, the developed sensor demonstrated a detection limit as low as 50 pg/mL for PTH, showcasing the potential of rGO as an indispensable nanomaterial for next-generation, low-cost, and highly responsive biosensors in clinical diagnostics. Real serum samples testing gave us comparable results making this experiment a reliable sensing system.

Keyword: *Reduced Graphene Oxide, PTH, biosensors, aptamer*

Synthesis And Characterization of VS₂ Nanoparticles Via One-Step Hydrothermal Method: Optimization of Process Parameters and Material Properties

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Vanadium disulfide (VS₂), a layered transition metal dichalcogenide, has emerged as a promising material for applications in catalysis, energy storage, and electronics due to its unique structural and electronic properties. In this study, we present a one-step hydrothermal synthesis route for synthesising VS₂ nanoparticles, offering a simple, scalable, and environmentally friendly approach without the need for post-synthesis treatments. Key process parameters—including temperature, reaction time, and precursor concentration—were systematically optimized to control nanoparticle morphology, size distribution, crystallinity, and phase purity. Comprehensive characterization techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning and transmission electron microscopy (SEM/TEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy, confirmed the formation of highly crystalline, uniformly dispersed VS₂ nanostructures with tunable surface properties. Our findings demonstrate that precise tuning of hydrothermal conditions significantly influences the structural and functional properties of VS₂, paving the way for its tailored use in next-generation catalytic and energy-related applications.

Keyword: Nanostructures, Hydrothermal Synthesis, Vanadium disulfide (VS₂), Transition Metal Dichalcogenides (TMDs)

First-Principles Insights into Phenylethylammonium-Based Salts Interactions in FAPbI₃ Perovskite for Indoor Applications of Perovskite Solar Cells

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Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have emerged as promising candidates for next-generation indoor photovoltaic applications due to their superior light-harvesting capabilities under low-light conditions. However, their performance and long-term stability remain key challenges, particularly in environments with variable humidity and oxygen exposure.

This study covers a wide range of surface passivators based on phenylethylammonium (PEA) salts, where the benzene ring is functionalized with different types of hydrophobic groups (fluorine (F), chlorine (Cl), bromine (Br), trifluoromethyl (CF₃), methyl (CH₃)). We employ first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations to investigate the interactions of PEA-based mono-ammonium (x-X-PEAI (x: o, m, p; X: F, Cl, Br), F₂-PEAI, (CF₃)₂-PEAI, (CH₃)₂-PEAI, F₄-PEAI, (CH₃)₄-PEAI) salts and di-ammonium (F₂-P(EAI)₂, (CF₃)₂-P(EAI)₂, (CH₃)₂-P(EAI)₂, (CH₃)₄-P(EAI)₂, F₄-P(EAI)₂) salts with the formamidinium lead iodide (FAPbI₃) perovskite surface to investigate the role of PEA-containing different functional groups surface passivation of FAPbI₃ perovskite. The total energy calculations were carried out within a plane-wave, DFT framework using Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package (VASP) for solving the resulting Kohn-Sham equation. All the first-principles calculations, the structural, electronic, and adsorption properties of perovskite systems are obtained using generalized gradient approximation (GGA) and Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) for the exchange-correlation potential. The binding energies were calculated as -5.05 eV, -5.08 eV, -5.07 eV and -5.03 eV, -4.81 eV, -5.09 eV for o-, m-, p-Cl-PEAI and o-, m-, p-Br-PEAI with perovskite systems, respectively. Our results reveal that PEA-based salts contribute significantly to surface defect passivation and structural stabilization by forming favorable ionic and hydrogen-bonding interactions at the perovskite interface. These interactions are shown to reduce trap states and improve the electronic structure, potentially enhancing device performance under indoor lighting. The insights gained from this work offer a theoretical foundation for the rational design of indoor perovskite solar energy systems involving the use of aromatic ammonium salts as additive materials within the perovskite structure.

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Keyword: perovskite solar cells (PSCs), phenylethylammonium salts, DFT, first principles

Simulation-Based Optimization of Non-toxic CuSbSe₂ Thin-Film Solar Cells Using SCAPS-1D

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Advancements in solar technology, such as the development of non-toxic materials and efficient absorber layers, enhance the viability of solar cells as a key component in the transition to a more sustainable energy future. In this context, thin film solar cells emerge as a crucial innovation, offering a lightweight and flexible solution that maximizes the benefits of solar energy while further enhancing the efficiency and accessibility of renewable power generation. The importance of non-toxic, earth-abundant materials in the development of thin film solar cells cannot be overstated, as they not only promote environmental sustainability but also ensure the widespread accessibility and efficiency of renewable energy solutions.

The escalating and ever-increasing demand for materials that are not only sustainable but also non-toxic in the realm of photovoltaic technologies has, in turn, resulted in a significant surge of interest surrounding the compound known as CuSbSe₂, which is commonly abbreviated as CAsE, as it serves as an ideal absorber layer owing to its remarkably optimal direct bandgap that measures approximately 1.1 eV, its impressively high absorption coefficient that exceeds 10^5 cm^{-1} , and its unique composition that consists of elements which are both abundantly available in the earth's crust and are considered to be environmentally benign and safe for use

In this study, we conduct a theoretical examination of the efficacy of CAsE-based thin-film solar cells utilizing SCAPS-1D, with the objective of substituting the traditional CdS buffer layer with environmentally benign alternatives. Three distinct buffering materials—SnS₂, ZnSe, and ZnSnO—were systematically assessed within the device architecture designated as SLG/Mo/CuSbSe₂/Buffer (X)/ZnO/ZnO:Al/Pt. The characteristics of each layer, including parameters such as thickness, bandgap, electron affinity, and doping concentration, were meticulously selected in accordance with existing scholarly literature. The simulation focused on evaluating interfacial band alignment, charge carrier dynamics, and recombination effects to determine the most promising buffer configuration.

Simulation results reveal that all three buffer materials—SnS₂, ZnSe, and ZnSnO—exhibit compatible band alignment and significant potential to reduce interfacial recombination. These findings support the replacement of CdS with environmentally benign alternatives and contribute to the development of sustainable thin-film solar technologies. Further optimization and analysis of these buffer materials could lead to even greater enhancements in the efficiency and sustainability of CuSbSe₂ thin-film solar cells.

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Keyword: *CuSbSe₂, Non-Toxic Materials, Thin-Film Solar Cells, SCAPS-1D*

Molecular Command over Interfaces: Toward Long-Life Inverted PSCs with Scalable Organic Salts

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As global energy demand rises and climate change accelerates, the need for clean and sustainable energy sources is more urgent than ever. Among renewables, solar energy stands out as an abundant and widely available option. Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have emerged as promising candidates for next-generation photovoltaics due to their high power conversion efficiency and low fabrication costs. However, interfacial instability remains a major bottleneck to their long-term performance.

In this study, we present a novel and scalable three-step synthesis method for phenylethylammonium iodide (PEAI)-based organic salts, specifically designed for interfacial passivation through 2D layer formation. This remarkable method enables high-yield production with structural diversity and commercialization potential. The synthesized salts were systematically tested at either the electron or hole transport interfaces in both normal (n-i-p) and inverted (p-i-n) device architectures, yielding promising results. While initial characterization concentrated on these single-interface configurations, the long-term goal is to implement dual-side passivation in inverted (p-i-n) cells, where interfacial degradation is more severe and directly impacts device stability. Structure-performance relationship analyses allowed us to identify the most promising candidates for future dual-interface applications on cells and mini-modules with an architecture: Glass/ITO/NiO_x/X-EDG-PEAI/Perovskite/Y-EWG-PEAI/C60/BCP/Cu.

This work presents a new molecular design platform for interfacial engineering and lays the foundation for tailored stability enhancement strategies in inverted PSCs.

Keyword: Perovskite Solar Cells, Molecular Design, Dual-Interface Engineering, Phenylethylammonium Iodide

Imidazole-Substituted Phthalocyanine as an Efficient Bifunctional Passivating Agent for Perovskite Solar Cells

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Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) are considered promising candidates for next-generation photovoltaics due to their high power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) exceeding 25%, but their long-term operational stability remains insufficient to compete with conventional silicon-based solar cells.¹ Defects originating from both intrinsic and extrinsic sources in the ABX₃ perovskite structure negatively affect device stability and limit photovoltaic performance.² In this work, we present a novel defect passivation strategy in PSCs using phthalocyanine (Pc) derivatives carrying positively charged imidazolium cations and various counter anions (I⁻, TFSI⁻, BF₄⁻, and PF₆⁻). The incorporation of Pc dopants into PSCs has played an important role in both photovoltaic performance and device durability. It has been demonstrated that structural defects can be passivated, solubility can be increased, perovskite/charge transfer layer interfaces can be created, and energy levels can be improved by using Pc-derived passivating agents. In particular, ZnPc-BF₄⁻ offers a power conversion efficiency (PCE) exceeding 22% and exhibits superior stability under continuous illumination and thermal stress. This work highlights the ability of special PC-based additives as an effective route to highly efficient and stable perovskite devices.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Keyword: *Phthalocyanine, Perovskite solar cells, Defect passivation, Imidazolium*

Investigation of Recombination Losses and Edge Passivation in Divided Silicon Solar Cells Using Organic Molecules

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In photovoltaic manufacturing, silicon solar cells are frequently divided either to create half-cut cells that enhance module performance or to produce smaller units for space-constrained and custom applications. However, cutting the cells exposes new edge surfaces that are prone to carrier recombination. Although these edge-induced losses have minimal impact on the open-circuit voltage (Voc), they can noticeably reduce the fill factor (FF), which is a critical parameter directly linked to the maximum power output of the device. Restoring performance losses caused by edge recombination is essential for maintaining the efficiency of advanced cell and module architectures.

Our study began with Nafion, a well-known cationic polymer previously reported in the literature to yield promising results for edge passivation in silicon-based devices. This initial success motivated the investigation of alternative organic materials with the potential for improved performance and simplified processes. In this study, we present a simple and scalable edge passivation strategy using organic molecules applied through low-temperature, solution-based processes.

Hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS), 9-decen-1-ol, hydrocinnamic acid, and 9,10-phenanthrenequinone (PQ) were evaluated across various concentrations and solvents. Among these, only PQ, when dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF) and followed by mild thermal annealing, exhibited statistically significant passivation effects. On the day of passivation, PQ-treated samples achieved an average increase of **4 mV** in Voc, **1.69%** in pseudo fill factor, and **0.59%** in pseudo efficiency, with the improvements clearly exceeding the experimental error margin.

Compared to Nafion, PQ provided greater performance improvements and more consistent results, with uniformly positive effects observed across all tested samples. While Nafion-treated devices exhibited higher variability, PQ demonstrated superior reproducibility and a more controllable passivation effect. Over a 10-day ambient storage period, PQ-passivated samples showed only a mild decline, maintaining a **2 mV** improvement in open-circuit voltage, **1.34%** in pseudo fill factor and **0.43%** in pseudo efficiency by day 10, confirming its long-term potential.

These findings introduce a promising direction for edge-specific surface engineering in silicon photovoltaics. The approach combines measurable performance recovery with environmentally friendly and manufacturing-compatible processing. Future work will focus on enhancing long-term stability and expanding the library of organic molecules suitable for edge passivation.

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Keyword: silicon solar cell, edge passivation, organic molecules

Bandgap Tuning in Perovskite Solar Cells Using Self-Assembled Monolayers

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In the global pursuit of climate neutrality, drastically reducing greenhouse gas emissions has become a critical priority. Renewable energy technologies, particularly photovoltaic (PV) systems, play a pivotal role in this transition¹. Among emerging PV technologies, perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have garnered considerable attention due to their exceptional optoelectronic properties and tunable bandgaps, ranging from 1.25 eV to over 3.0 eV, enabled by their versatile ABX₃ crystal structure. However, tuning the bandgap to meet specific application requirements introduces challenges at the device interface, often necessitating careful optimization of charge transport layers to mitigate recombination losses and maintain high open circuit voltages².

A promising approach to address these challenges involves the application of functionalized self-assembled monolayers (SAMs), which can form chemically bonded, uniform interfacial layers that stabilize the perovskite surface, suppress phase segregation, and enhance charge extraction³. In this work, PSCs with three distinct bandgaps 1.55 eV, 1.62 eV, and 1.73 eV were systematically fabricated and studied. By incorporating the SAM molecules as a passivator interface layer, significant improvements in device performance were achieved. Notably, the highest power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 22.5% was achieved with the 1.55 eV bandgap device, exhibiting a V_{oc} of 1.15 V and a fill factor (FF) of 85.3%. The 1.61 eV configuration also demonstrated excellent performance, reaching a PCE of 21.0% with balanced photovoltaic parameters. For the wider bandgap device (1.73 eV), the introduction of SAMs led to a significant improvement in open-circuit voltage, increasing from 1.12 V to 1.28 V, underscoring the effectiveness of SAM-assisted interface engineering, particularly in mitigating voltage losses in high-bandgap PSCs.

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Keyword: Solar Cell, Perovskite, SAM

Electrochemical Performance of PEDOT/Carbon Fabric Electrodes Enhanced with Cobalt Doping and Bio-derived Quantum Dots for Wearable Electronics

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High energy density, fast charge-discharge capability, long cycle life, environmental friendliness, and safety are crucial factors for the effective use of energy storage systems. The polymer poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT), commonly used in wearable energy storage materials, exhibits limited performance due to its low energy density in small portable forms [1-2]. The primary causes of low capacity are inadequate surface properties and the inability to fully express theoretical capacity values. To overcome these performance limitations, it is necessary to improve the morphological and chemical properties of the electrode material [3-4].

In this study, PEDOT polymer was synthesized on the surface of carbon fabric electrodes using a hydrothermal synthesis method. The polymer was optimized by adding cobalt salts in different ratios, achieving the highest discharge time. Additionally, carbon quantum dots produced from tomatoes were used, and the contribution ratio was optimized to enhance the material's conductivity, surface area, and electrochemical stability. The electrochemical performance of the produced fabric electrodes was evaluated using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Structural and morphological characterizations were conducted using FTIR, SEM, and UV-Vis spectrophotometry. By considering the low cost of the single-step manufacturing process, waste utilization, and performing reactions in a water-based environment, materials that can offer long-term and sustainable solutions were designed for wearable electronics.

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Keyword: *Wearable Supercapacitor, Flexible Energy Storage, PEDOT, Carbon Quantum Dot*

Electronics Assembly for Low-Temperature Flexible and Stretchable Electronics

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Despite significant progress in printed electronics, traditional electronic assembly remains indispensable, particularly where high-resolution features are required. While silicon-based chips can achieve features as small as 2 nm, most printed electronics are limited to resolutions above 1 μm . Consequently, there is a continued need to adapt electronic assembly methods to new, unconventional substrates, including flexible films, paper, stretchable fabrics, and heat-shrinkable foils.

In these emerging applications, electronic assemblies must withstand not only mechanical stresses such as shear, but also dynamic deformations like bending, stretching, shrinking, and creasing — and in some use cases, even washing. Many of the flexible substrates used in these applications are thermally sensitive, requiring curing temperatures well below 120°C, often under 90°C or even 50°C.

At the same time, sustainability is becoming increasingly important. In disposable printed electronics, such as smart packaging or telemedicine devices, materials must be compatible with low-temperature processes while allowing for biodegradability or recyclability. This calls for innovative conductive materials, adhesives, and interconnection methods.

While recent research has made progress in flexible and stretchable electronic assembly, challenges remain in cost-efficiency, scalability, and integration with conventional manufacturing. This presentation will explore current techniques, assess their limitations, and highlight future directions in sustainable, low-temperature assembly for next-generation electronics, illustrated with both commercial and original (proprietary) solutions.

Keyword: *Printed Electronics, Flexible electronics, Low-Temperature Assembly, Conductive Adhesives*

Lactic Acid-Modified Chitosan Gel Electrodes for Flexible Capacitive Sensors

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Chitosan-based gel electrodes offer a sustainable and biocompatible alternative for the development of flexible capacitive sensors. In this study, chitosan films were prepared using lactic acid as both a solvent and functional modifier, enabling the formation of soft, ionically conductive structures suitable for parallel-plate sensor configurations. By tuning the lactic acid content, the electroactive behavior of the films was adjusted without the need for synthetic additives or toxic salts.

These films were successfully integrated into a basic capacitive sensing setup, where their dielectric response under ambient conditions demonstrated compatibility with low-frequency, low-power sensing applications. The combination of natural polymer chemistry, ease of processing, and tunable performance positions this approach as a promising platform for wearable electronics and environmentally friendly sensor technologies.

Keyword: *Chitosan, Flexible Sensors, Capacitive Sensing*

Electrically Conductive MXene and Carbon Nanotube Integrated Conductive Polymeric Fibers for Flexible Electronics

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Conductive fibers are essential for next-generation flexible electronics and wearable devices due to their combination of electrical conductivity and mechanical flexibility. This study compares the performance of MXene and carbon nanotube (CNT) integrated polymer fibers with MXene/CNT as the conductive core and SEBS as the outer layer. Results show that increasing fiber diameter reduces conductivity in both materials, the conductivity of MXene fibers drops below 8 S/m above 350 μm in diameter, while that of CNT fibers drops below 75 S/m above 450 μm in diameter. Notably, at a fiber diameter of 279 μm , MXene-based fibers exhibit a conductivity of 27 S/m, whereas CNT-based fibers demonstrate a significantly higher conductivity of 94 S/m at a nearly similar diameter of 284 μm . Resistance increases with fiber length for both MXene (279 μm fiber diameter) and CNT (284 μm fiber diameter) fibers emphasizing the reliance on structural parameters. Thus, smaller core sizes improve conductivity by enhancing nanoparticle alignment and minimizing porosity. CNT fibers exhibit superior electron transport, attributed to their high aspect ratio, strong interconnectivity, and stable conductive pathways. The findings emphasize the applicability of CNT-based fibers for high-performance, miniaturized wearable devices that require consistent electrical output.

Keyword: Carbon Nanotube (CNT), MXene, Conductivity

Highly Stretchable Magnetic Composite Fibers With Desirable Magnetic Properties

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Soft magnetic actuators exhibiting excellent stretchability and magnetic responsiveness are crucial for advancing next-generation wearable and biomedical robotic systems. Here, we introduce a highly stretchable, magnetic composite fiber produced by a thermal drawing technique. The fiber has a diameter of around 1 mm, has neodymium-iron-boron (NdFeB) magnetic material up to 70 wt%. Fiber exhibits an elongation capability of up to 300%, ensuring superior mechanical compliance. Moreover, a magnetic field of up to 55 Gauss can be generated by the fiber when stimulated with a magnetic field for a duration of 10 minutes. The fiber's exceptional stretchability and high magnetic content make it a promising material for soft robotic actuation. The fiber's reactivity to magnetic stimuli also makes it a promising platform for future soft systems with applications in biomedical research, such as wearable sensors that can detect biomechanical signals and surgical equipment that is magnetically guided.

Keyword: *Robotic actuation, Magnetoelastic, Thermal Drawing, Wearable*

Smart Insoles For Real-Time Gait Cycle Analysis

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Human movements often contain subtle clues that may indicate the presence of certain diseases, as some medical conditions can cause alterations in normal movement patterns. Therefore, accurate analyzing human motion provides an opportunity to detect such anomalies and potentially enables early diagnosis. Although there are already several devices for these purposes one of the main disadvantages of these systems is their lack of mobility. This work addresses the problem and demonstrates a wearable sensor design that provides mobility and takes accurate measurements of pressure distribution across the insole. In the design process a wearable sensor system is designed, with a PCB unit for maintenance of the connection between the mobile application and the sensors. A mobile application is developed for visualization, storage and documentation of data. Smart insoles are compared simultaneously with a gold-standard system and test results showed that cycle and sentence times measured with wearable sensors shows less than %3 error for each cycle and stance times. However, due to noise in the sensor data the error for more sensitive measurements such as single support, double support, and swing time reached up to %20. Additionally, smart insoles can measure pressure distribution within the foot that cannot be provided by the reference device.

Keyword: *Wearable Sensors, Human Motion Analysis, Smart Insoles, Gait Analysis*

diMe-O9, P1-COOH, O9 Carboranethiol SAMs on Au and Ag surfaces, and their computational adsorption study on Au and Ag nanocluster surfaces

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We will present a study of the adsorption mechanism of carborane-thiol molecules on Au nanoclusters surface using density functional theory (DFT). We will investigate the adsorption behavior and dipol-dipol lateral interactions of diMe-O9 (Dimethyleted o-Carborane-9-thiol), Carboxylated p-Carborane-1-thiol (P1-COOH), and O9 (o-carborane-9-thiol) carboranethiol self-assembled monolayers on template-stripped Au films (TSAu) using contact angle measurements (CAs), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) techniques. Our results show that the adsorption of carborane-thiol molecules on Au nanoclusters is a complex process that is influenced by the size and shape of the nanoclusters, the surface chemistry of the nanoclusters, and the molecular structure of the carborane-thiol molecules. We believe that our study provides new insights into the adsorption mechanism of carborane-thiol molecules on Au nanoclusters, and that this information could be used to design new materials with enhanced properties. This work was supported by TÜBİTAK Grant no. 120N628.

Keyword: *Self Assembled Monolayer, Carboranethiol, Template Stripped Gold Film, Template Stripped Silver Film*

Comparing The Performance of Used and Non-Used Electrodes Offers an Alternative Viewpoint on Upcycling.

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Recycling has become a global necessity due to increasing environmental pollution and diminishing resources. In fact, very effective methods of dealing with wastes are being developed by following upcycling policies, which are less costly and more effective than processing and recycling wastes. Although upcycling is an important step for nature, when a conscious recycling policy is not followed, the operations carried out may have negative consequences.

In this context, based on the idea that the most important step in waste recycling policies is to recycle our own wastes, which is the most dominant point, it is thought that the cleaning and reuse of used nickel foams will be a positive step for nature. Since examining the environmental effects of this issue is out of our subject, it was examined whether upcycling would be an effective and wise step for us by looking at electrochemical characterizations. As a result of the measurements and characterizations, it was observed that the specific capacitance value for the Lanthanum-based MOF electrode components using clean nickel foam was calculated as 208.67 F/g at 1A/g, while this value was calculated as 186.4 F/g when the used and recleaned electrode was used. FESEM and XRD characterizations were also performed for both electrodes and this decrease in capacitance value was tried to be better understood.

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Keyword: *supercapacitors, waste management, nickel foam*

PEDOT Nanoparticles as a Component for Thermoelectric Devices

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Thermoelectric (TE) materials generate energy through the direct conversion between heat and electricity. Thermoelectric devices exhibit broad applications such as waste and low-grade heat harvesting, local cooling, sensing and wearable electronics (Fu et al., 2024). Recently, organic and reinforced composite TE materials have been developed together. Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) is possibly the most successful and frequently reported type among these newly developed components. This study aims to highlight recent advances in the synthesis, mechanism and applications of PEDOT-based TE composites. PEDOT has high structural stability, high optical transmittance (above 90%) over a wide spectral range (250 nm-800 nm) and high carrier mobility (Vosgueritchian et al., 2011; Nakano et al., 2008). The aim of the study is to synthesize organic conductive PEDOT nanoparticles for use in thermoelectric modules. In this way; the initial cost will be reduced, production will be accelerated (increasing supply) and demand will be increased by expanding its use. PEDOT NPs were synthesized and optimized from EDOT monomers by two surfactant oxidative emulsion polymerization technique. This technique provides an advantage in controlling nanoparticle size. Grain size and zeta potential measurements elucidated by Dynamic Light Scattering allow to control the kinetic activity in the TE regions to be targeted.

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Keyword: Thermoelectric, Conducting Polymers, PEDOT Nanoparticles

Electrochemical Synthesis and Surface Characterization of a Photoactive Carbazole–Azobenzene Based Conductive Polymer

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Conductive polymers offer a wide range of applications and significant potential in many innovative fields, such as sustainable and flexible electronics, smart material systems, controlled drug delivery devices, corrosion-resistant coating technologies, biosensor applications and supercapacitors [1][2]. Among conductive polymer types, redox and photosensitive materials exhibit distinct properties due to their rough surface and the resulting hydrophilic and hydrophobic characteristics. The combination of carbazole and azobenzene with alterations to the polymer surface has been demonstrated to result in the preparation of materials with divergent properties.

In this study the monomer AzoCz tetrakis(2-(9H-carbazol-9-yl)ethyl) 5,5'-(diazene-1,2-diyl)(E)-diisophthalate was synthesized by the reaction of the electroactive carbazole groups and photoactive azobenzene derivative. Electrochemical polymerization of the AzoCz was conducted in a three-electrode cell setup on the ITO working electrode with CV technique ranging from -0.5 to 1.5 V. Electrochemical and optical properties of the obtained conducting polymer (P(AzoCz)) were investigated. Spectroelectrochemical techniques were used to determine the band gap energies of the π - π^* transitions of the P(AzoCz). P(AzoCz) surface morphology was investigated by AFM, SEM analysis, and contact angle measurements.

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Keyword: Azobenzene, Carbazole, Functional Polymer, Electrochromic Materials, Thin Film

Azobenzen Fonksiyonlu Karbazol Tabanlı Çift Uyarana Duyarlı İletken Polimerlerin Elektrokimyasal ve Fotoaktif Davranışları

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İletken polimerler, π -konjuge yapıları sayesinde yarı iletken davranış gösterebilmekte ve çeşitli işlevsel gruplar ile modifiye edilerek uygulama alanları genişletilebilmektedir. Bu polimerlerin elektronik yapılarına yönelik modifikasyonlar, enerji depolama sistemlerinden optoelektronığe kadar pek çok alanda performans artışı sağlamaktadır. Karbazol türevleri, yüksek elektrooksidatif kararlılığa sahip olmaları nedeniyle iletken polimer tasarımlarında sıkça tercih edilmektedir. Azobenzen grupları ise, ışık ve elektrik alan gibi çevresel uyarılarla cis-trans izomerizasyon gösterebilmekte; bu özellik, polimer zincirinde fotomekanik ve fotoelektronik tepkimelerin kontrolüne olanak sunmaktadır[1]. Azobenzen içeren polimer sistemlerinde, potansiyel uyarım altında izomerizasyon kinetiğinin modifiye edilebildiği gösterilmiş olup, bu durum; yüzey yönelimli fotoahtarlama, yeniden yapılandırılabilir optik yüzeyler ve alan kontrollü fotoduyarlı sistemler için yeni uygulama alanları açmaktadır.

Yürütülen deneysel çalışma kapsamında, elektroaktif karbazol çekirdeği içeren yeni bir monomer tasarımı gerçekleştirilmiş ve bu monomer yapısına fotoaktif azobenzen grubu başarıyla bağlanmıştır. Böylece hem ışığa hem de potansiyel uyarana tepki verebilen çift fonksiyonlu bir yapı elde edilmiştir. Sentezlenen monomerin yapısal doğrulaması, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR ve FT-IR spektroskopik analizleri kullanılarak yapılmıştır. Monomerin elektropolimerizasyonu, dönüşümlü voltametri (CV) yöntemi ile gerçekleştirilmiş; elde edilen polimer filmlerin elektrokimyasal davranışları detaylı şekilde incelenmiştir. Polimerin yükseltgenme ve indirgenme özellikleri, elektroaktif karakteri hakkında bilgi sağlamıştır. Ayrıca spektroelettrokimyasal ölçümler ile polimerin elektrokromik yanıtı ve optik geçiş özellikleri değerlendirilmiştir. Fotoaktif azobenzen gruplarının yapıya entegre edilmesi sayesinde, polimerin potansiyel uygulaması altında cis-trans izomerizasyon davranışı göstermesi sağlanmıştır. +1.7 V ve -1.0 V potansiyeller uygulandığında yapının izomerik form değiştirdiği, UV-Vis spektroskopisi ile doğrulanmıştır. Bu izomerizasyon sürecine bağlı olarak, polimer yüzeyinin morfolojik özelliklerinde meydana gelen değişimler SEM, AFM ve temas açısı ölçümleri ile değerlendirilmiştir. ITO elektrot üzerine kaplanan polimerin, uygulanan potansiyele bağlı olarak yüzey yapısında ve ıslanabilirlik özelliklerinde önemli farklılıklar gösterdiği gözlemlenmiştir. Sonuç olarak, geliştirilen bu çift fonksiyonlu iletken polimerin, elektrokimyasal olarak kontrol edilebilir yapısı, akıllı yüzeyler, nanoelektronik aygıtlar ve elektro-optik sistemler gibi ileri teknoloji uygulamaları için dikkat çekici bir potansiyel ortaya koymaktadır.

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Keyword: Azobenzen, karbazol, ince film, elektroizomerizasyon

Gold Nanoparticle Modified Phytic Acid Supported Polyaniline-Based Platform for Electrochemical Detection of Cardiac Troponin I

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Electrochemical biosensors serve significant advantages over other sensor technologies and classical methods with their high sensitivity, reliability and ease of miniaturization. These features make these sensors an effective tool for the early diagnosis and monitoring of cardiovascular diseases which are one of the most common causes of death today. Early analysis of cardiac biomarkers contributes to reduction of mortality rates by providing early diagnosis [1,2]. In this work, a novel biosensor platform for the electrochemical detection of a cardiac biomarker, cardiac troponin I, was developed. The detection platform was prepared by electrochemical deposition of gold nanoparticles on a polymeric hydrogel film. Polyaniline was preferred as the conducting polymer in the platform and supramolecular complex formation was achieved by using phytic acid, which is known for its biocompatibility. Thanks to this complex structure, a hydrogel film with high antifouling properties was obtained [3]. Electrochemical deposition of gold nanoparticles on the film increased the sensor's surface reactivity and functionality. Thus, anti-troponin I antibodies were immobilized on the surface with high stability, enabling the selective detection of troponin I. Additionally, we characterized the developed immunosensor platform by using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

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Keyword: *Cardiac troponin I, electrochemical biosensor, immunosensor*

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes and graphene platelets are incorporated to enhance the mechanical properties of a carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy resin composite

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This study explores the enhancement of mechanical and thermal properties in carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composites through the integration of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) as hybrid nanofillers. Epoxy nanocomposites with varying MWCNT:GNP ratios (1:1, 1:3, 3:1) and filler contents (0.1–0.4 wt.%) were fabricated and systematically characterized. The optimal mechanical performance was observed at a MWCNT:GNP ratio of 1:3 with 0.3 wt.% total nanofiller, achieving a tensile strength of 75.1 MPa representing a 12% improvement over neat epoxy. Incorporation of these nanofillers in carbon fiber laminates further increased tensile strength and strain at break, though a reduction in elastic modulus was noted. Thermal analysis revealed significant increases in glass transition temperature, with the highest value reaching 114.67°C. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed that improved dispersion and reduced agglomeration of nanofillers contributed to the enhanced properties. The results demonstrate that even small additions of hybrid nanofillers can synergistically improve the performance of epoxy-based composites, providing insights for advanced material design in structural applications.

Keyword: Hybrid epoxy nanocomposites, nanofillers, graphene nanoplatelets, multi-walled carbon nanotubes

QCM Sensor Functionalized with Polymer Films and Nanostructures for Acetone Detection

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Gas sensors provide a unique, non-invasive method for identifying diseases and diagnosis. Diabetes is a significant and common health problem characterized by acetone (C₃H₆O) gas in the exhaled breath. The current diagnosis with blood test methods is invasive and needs to increase practicability and response performance. Polymer-based gas sensors received considerable attention in medical diagnostics after undergoing significant developments to improve their stability and selectivity.

In this study, we report the application of the conductive polymer Polypyrrole (PPy) as thin films to improve the sensitivity and selectivity of QCM Sensors.

Oxidative chemical vapor deposition (oCVD) was used to deposit PPy thin films. With precise control over the film's composition and thickness, this method delivers homogeneous, conformal coatings even on complicated structures.

We evaluated the sensor's sensitivity to acetone by injecting acetone in liquid form at predetermined concentrations and exposing the deposited layer to acetone vapor while maintaining regulated humidity and temperature. Detection capability, particularly at low concentrations was evaluated by recording the frequency changes in the QCM crystal by subjecting it to varying acetone concentrations up to 100 ppm.

This study demonstrates the QCM sensor system enhanced with PPy functional polymeric thin films for acetone detection. The measurements proposed by the sensor development methodology provide a sensitive, stable, and selective gas detection system, especially for detecting trace levels of acetone in various biomedical applications.

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Keyword: functionalized polymers, gas sensors, polymer nanostructures, qcm sensors

Tunable Actuation in Soft Robotics via Liquid–Gas Phase Transitions Induced by Light of Varying Wavelengths

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Soft robotics based on liquid–gas phase transitions offer a powerful framework for creating lightweight, flexible, and untethered systems capable of converting external stimuli into controlled mechanical motion. These systems leverage the volumetric expansion associated with the liquid–gas phase change to produce actuation, making them particularly attractive for applications in wearable devices, biomedical tools, and autonomous systems. Among various stimuli, light has emerged as a highly effective trigger due to its non-contact nature, high spatial resolution, and tunable energy input. Despite growing interest, most existing studies focus on single-parameter evaluations, often examining only one light source or solvent system. As a result, the complex interplay between light wavelength and solvent characteristics in driving liquid–gas transitions remains poorly understood. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these factors is critical for improving actuation performance, energy efficiency, and system durability in real-world applications. This study aims to address these gaps through a systematic investigation of multi-wavelength light sources and a range of organic solvents to optimize the behavior of photothermal actuators based on liquid–gas phase transitions.

Herein, we report on the design of light-driven polymeric actuators and investigate the effects of different light sources (IR, blue, red, and green LEDs) with varying wavelengths and solvents (ethanol, methanol, butanol, etc.) on phase-transition-based mechanical motion. While existing literature often focuses on studies using a single light source or solvent, this research offers a unique contribution in terms of multi-parameter analysis. The findings obtained may provide new insights into how mechanical motion can be optimized depending on the wavelength of light and the type of solvent, thereby guiding the design process of light-driven soft actuators. In addition, the combined evaluation of different parameters will provide important clues for improving the energy efficiency of photothermal actuators and developing their application areas.

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Keyword: *Actuator, Smart Materials, Soft Robotics, Phase-transition*

Preparation Of Coatings With Tunable Optical Properties Featuring UV Protection, Self-Cleaning, And Anti-Icing Characteristics

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Glass surfaces used in high-rise buildings provide important advantages such as aesthetic appeal and natural lighting. However, they also face several challenges, including intense sunlight exposure, surface contamination, and icing problems (1, 2). In this study, we developed a novel multifunctional coating system for glass surfaces that exhibits tunable optical properties, UV protection, self-cleaning, and anti-icing capabilities by integrating light-responsive spiropyran molecules with a slippery surface design. To achieve enhanced optical functionality, spiropyran was modified with acryloyl chloride to obtain a polymerizable monomer. The resulting photochromic polymer was synthesized and characterized by FTIR and ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. The coating was applied by spray-coating a solution containing the photochromic polymer, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), and silicone oil onto glass substrates. The optical transmittance of the coated surfaces was evaluated using UV-Vis spectroscopy, while surface wettability was determined through water contact angle measurements. To investigate chemical durability, coated samples were immersed in pure water, 1 M hydrochloric acid (HCl), 1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and ethanol for varying durations up to 10 hours. Additionally, UV stability was examined by exposing the samples to UV light ($\lambda = 365$ nm) for periods ranging from 60 to 600 minutes. The self-cleaning performance of the surfaces was evaluated using various types of common contaminants including dust, fruit juice, honey, ketchup, mayonnaise, and milk, and their removal was monitored. Anti-icing performance was tested by observing the freezing time of water droplets placed on the coated surfaces at -15 °C. Overall, the experimental results demonstrated that the developed multifunctional coating shows strong potential for smart and sustainable glass applications due to its integrated properties, including adjustable transparency, UV shielding, easy-cleaning, and ice-repellent performance.

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Keyword: *Smart Glass Coatings, UV Protection, Self-Cleaning, Tunable Optical Properties*

Improving Corn Starch-Based Biopolymers with Mg-Al LDH/Mxene Heterostructures for Advanced Food Packaging

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Natural biopolymers are necessary to reduce the negative effects of petroleum derivatives on the environment. These biopolymers provide a sustainable alternative to synthetic polymers made from fossil fuels because they can be produced from renewable materials such as bacteria, plants or algae. Natural biopolymers are very important in various applications, especially in the field of food packaging, as they can replace non-biodegradable plastics and have a lower carbon impact. As the world looks to reduce dependence on limited oil resources and grapple with the effects of plastic pollution, natural biopolymers may be a viable way to produce more environmentally friendly materials. For this reason, the usability of natural biopolymer is being investigated by scientists at full speed. Despite their many environmental advantages, there are significant barriers to widespread adoption of natural biopolymers over petroleum-derived polymers. To overcome these obstacles, the barrier, mechanical properties and stability of natural biopolymers need to be improved. Therefore, nowadays there is an increasing interest in improving the properties of natural biopolymers. The use of nanoparticles represents a groundbreaking approach to improve some properties of natural biopolymers. By incorporating nanoparticles such as clay, carbon nanotubes or metallic oxides into biopolymer matrices, mechanical properties, thermal stability and barrier properties are improved. These nanoparticles act as strengthening agents, creating a synergistic effect that significantly improves the overall performance of the biopolymer. Furthermore, the controlled distribution of nanoparticles within the biopolymer matrix can lead to a more homogeneous material, reducing possible inconsistencies in properties. The application of nanotechnology with natural biopolymers can increase competitiveness with petroleum-derived polymers and offer new possibilities for sustainable materials in a wide range of applications, from packaging to biomedical applications. In this study, polymer composite films were obtained by doping natural corn starch as biopolymer, with synthesized Mg-Al LDH/Mxene (2D/2D) heterostructures to improve their properties for use in food packaging. Several characterization methods, including XRD, SEM-EDX, TEM, and optical properties, were examined. The financial support by TUBITAK (Project Code: 223M389) is gratefully acknowledged.

Keyword: *polymer composite films, Mg-Al LDH, Mxene, corn starch*

Ag Nanoparticle Embedded Antibacterial, Fluorosilane Modified Hydrophobic, QD Modified Fluorescent Hybrid Multifunctional Nanocomposite Coating

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Widely known ORMOCER materials (hybrid polymers) is functional structures that combines brand new and improved properties for different applications providing new materials by tailoring the different requirements. Polymeric features and glass-ceramic like properties can be fused within a new material showing the advantages of organic polymers and ceramics. As one of the examples, ORMOCER coatings can be applied on to glass, metals, wood, and bio-based plastics, fibers like paper and textiles. Organically modified material concept therefore, interestingly play a platform role for additional functionalities coexisting together on these hybrid structures. By combining different features multifunctional nanomaterials which show hydrophobicity, antibacterial features, fluorescence, pH sensing properties, durability, controlled release can be brought together. Hence, these multifunctional hybrid coatings provide the formation of a new active coating structures by employing ORMOCERs as the matrix platform. In this way, a hybrid surface coating can simultaneously display fluorescence and provide color sensor properties, acts as antibacterial material with nanoparticles, shows self cleaning effect due to the long alkyl chains on the surface by controlled modification.

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Keyword: *multifunctional coating, sol-gel, hydrophobic, fluorescent coating*

Catalytic Application of Biopolymer-Encapsulated Ru and Pd Biohybrid Nanoparticles for Hydrogen Generation via Hydrolysis Reaction

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The advancement of technology, the escalation of industrial activities, and the rapid growth of the global population have collectively contributed to the accelerated depletion of fossil fuel resources and a concomitant increase in environmental pollution [1-2]. Consequently, recent scientific endeavors have increasingly focused on the exploration of alternative and renewable energy sources. Among these, hydrogen energy remains one of the least widely utilized, despite its significant potential. Hydrogen is regarded as a promising future energy carrier owing to its high energy density (142 MJ kg⁻¹), renewability, low cost, non-toxicity, and clean combustion characteristics. Rather than storing hydrogen in its gaseous form which poses safety concerns on demand hydrogen generation from chemical hydrogen storage materials such as ammonia borane (AB), formic acid, aqueous hydrazine, hydrazine borane, lithium borohydride, sodium borohydride, and diamine bisborane offers a safer and more practical alternative. These hydrogen storage compounds are therefore expected to play a critical role in meeting future industrial energy demands. The hydrolysis of these hydrogen storage compounds in aqueous media requires the use of effective catalyst systems [3-5]. In this study, a novel class of biohybrid Ru and Pd nanoparticles was synthesized via a cost-effective, environmentally benign, and single-step procedure. To prevent nanoparticle aggregation during synthesis, the Ru and Pd nanoparticles were stabilized using natural polymers agarose and gelatin. The resulting biohybrid nanoparticles were characterized using a range of spectroscopic and analytical techniques, including SEM, TEM, XRD, XPS, TGA, and FT-IR. These polymer-stabilized Ru and Pd nanoparticles were subsequently employed as catalysts in the hydrolysis reactions of amine borane-derived hydrogen storage materials for hydrogen generation. The study investigated key operational parameters, including hydrogen storage material concentration, temperature, catalyst loading, catalyst shelf-life, and the recyclability of the biohybrid catalysts. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis reactions were also determined. The findings demonstrated that Pd-based biohybrid nanoparticles exhibited superior catalytic activity and efficiency compared to their Ru-based nanoparticles.

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Keyword: Nanoparticle, Catalyst, Hydrogen

Synthesis and Electrochemical Evaluation of 2D Silicene for Supercapacitor Applications

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Two-dimensional (2D) silicene, a monoelemental material composed of silicon atoms arranged in a buckled hexagonal lattice, has attracted significant attention as a promising alternative to graphene due to its exceptional electronic and magnetic properties [1]. Despite its potential, studies on the integration of silicene into energy storage devices remain limited. Theoretical calculations have predicted that silicene can exhibit a specific capacitance as high as 1200 F g⁻¹, surpassing that of graphene (~500 F g⁻¹), along with advantageous features such as high surface area, mechanical flexibility, and rapid charge–discharge dynamics [2]. In addition to supercapacitor applications, silicene has also been investigated for lithium-ion batteries, hydrogen storage, chemical sensors, and nanoelectronic devices [3–5]. In this study, 2D silicene nanosheets were successfully synthesized via various wet-chemical exfoliation strategies, including acid-mediated topochemical transformation of CaSi₂ precursors. The structural and morphological properties of the resulting silicene were systematically characterized using XRD, FESEM, TEM, and XPS techniques. The accordion-like layered morphology and crystalline features observed in the optimized samples confirm the successful formation of few-layer silicene. Furthermore, the electrochemical performance of the silicene-based electrodes was evaluated, revealing capacitive behavior and promising cycle stability. These findings underscore the critical role of the synthesis route—particularly HCl-assisted topochemical conversion—in enabling the production of structurally and electrochemically viable silicene. This study offers valuable insights into the development of high-performance silicene-based materials for next-generation energy storage applications.

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Keyword: 2D materials, silicene, layered nanomaterials, energy storage

Development of a flexible lithium-ion battery and integration of a triboelectric nanogenerator for self-charging energy systems

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The growing demand for wearable electronics has highlighted the need for lightweight, flexible, and autonomous energy systems. Conventional lithium-ion batteries, though effective in energy density and stability, lack the mechanical adaptability and self-sufficiency required for next-generation wearable devices. To address these challenges, this study proposes the development of a self-charging energy platform that integrates a flexible lithium-ion battery with a triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG) into a unified, stretchable architecture. While TENGs and flexible batteries have been studied individually, their combination remains largely unexplored. The proposed system aims to achieve continuous energy harvesting, high cycling stability, and practical usability in wearable electronics.

The flexible battery is fabricated on elastomeric substrates, ensuring conformability and durability under motion. Nanostructured conductive coatings are used to enhance electrical conductivity while preserving stretchability. A custom-developed gel polymer electrolyte is used to replace conventional liquid electrolytes, offering improved safety, leakage resistance, and mechanical compatibility with flexible form factors. The electrolyte exhibits high ionic conductivity and strong interfacial adhesion to electrode layers, ensuring stable electrochemical performance under deformation. The battery design is optimized for stable operation under bending, stretching, and repetitive mechanical stress conditions typical of wearable applications.

Simultaneously, the TENG is fabricated using electrospun nanofiber layers with high triboelectric polarity. These high-surface-area membranes harvest biomechanical energy from movements like walking or fabric deformation. The system includes custom energy conditioning circuits to convert the pulsed AC output of the TENG into a regulated form suitable for real-time battery charging.

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Keyword: triboelectric, flexible batteries, electrospinning

Surface design of polymer-based triboelectric nanogenerators for biomedical applications

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In this study, surface designs for polymer-based triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) were developed for biomedical applications. TENGs are noteworthy as sustainable and renewable energy sources and can be used in various applications in the biomedical field. In this study, dielectric and conductive surfaces based on chitosan (CH), a biopolymer that is non-toxic to the human body, were created. The conductive surfaces were modified with reduced graphene oxide (rGO), while the dielectric surfaces were modified with graphene oxide (GO), magnetite (Fe_3O_4), and magnetite-graphene oxide (mGO) in different ratios. Additionally, comprehensive electrical measurements, including rectifier and amplifier circuits, were conducted to evaluate the performance of the TENG. These measurements examined changes in the output voltage of the TENG and evaluated its performance under various conditions. The components of the TENG were characterized using XRD analysis, and the surfaces were characterized with FTIR analysis. The electrical measurements indicated that TENGs with GO-doped CH ($V_{\text{max}} = 13.11$ mV) are suitable for applications with low mechanical impacts, such as respiratory monitoring, pulse monitoring, and nerve stimulation. On the other hand, TENGs with mGO 1:1-doped CH ($V_{\text{max}} = 63.31$ mV) were found to be suitable for applications involving high mechanical impacts, such as implantable pacemakers, smart sports applications, and monitoring human movement. The findings demonstrate the potential of TENGs as sustainable energy sources in biomedical devices.

Keyword: *Bioengineering, Biotechnology, Chemical Engineering*

High-Capacitance $\text{MCo}_3\text{S}_4/\text{Co}_3\text{S}_4$ Electrodes on RGH-Modified Nickel Foam

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The demand for sustainable energy storage and conversion technologies is growing rapidly. This situation stems from the global energy crisis and environmental problems caused by the continuous burning of fossil fuels. Therefore, the development of high-efficiency energy storage systems (ESS) for the effective use of reliable and environmentally friendly energy sources is the top priority. In this context, high-performance electrochemical energy storage devices are emerging as an important component of modern energy infrastructure and are attracting intense research interest in industrial circles [1-3]. The addition of various ions to regulate electron distribution and enhance the electrochemical activity of spinel cobalt sulfide (Co_3S_4) material is considered a promising strategy [4]. This study systematically investigates the effect of reduced graphene hydrogel (RGH) structures integrated into nickel foam (NF), a current collector with a high surface area, on the performance of supercapacitor (SC) devices. In the study, 2-methylimidazole was used to facilitate the self-growth of MCo_3S_4 (M: Ni, Cu, and Mn) nanostructures. The results obtained show that the specific capacitance (Cs) value of the $\text{NiCo}_3\text{S}_4/\text{Co}_3\text{S}_4/\text{RGH-NF}$ electrode is 4104 F/g when a scan rate of 5 mVs⁻¹ is used. In contrast, the Cs values of the $\text{CuCo}_3\text{S}_4/\text{Co}_3\text{S}_4/\text{RGH-NF}$ and $\text{MnCo}_3\text{S}_4/\text{Co}_3\text{S}_4/\text{RGH-NF}$ electrodes were 2913 F/g and 3321 F/g, respectively.

Adknowledge

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Keyword: Graphene, Thiospinel, Supercapacitor

Thermally Drawn PtFE-PVDF Nanocomposite Fibers for High-Performance Triboelectric Nanogenerators

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In the era of AI-driven technologies, the demand for autonomous, maintenance-free power sources in compact devices is growing rapidly. Triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) offer a compelling solution by enabling self-powered operation while simultaneously harvesting energy and sensing biomechanical signals. In this study, the scalable fabrication of flexible, fiber based TENGs is demonstrated using a thermal drawing process, where polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is blended with varying concentrations of perfluorinated polymer (PtFE) to enhance triboelectric performance. A conductive polyethylene (CPE) serves as the conductive core, and polycarbonate (PC) is used as a sacrificial outer layer during drawing process. Structural analysis confirms an increased fraction of electroactive β -phase in PtFE-modified PVDF, attributed to the strong electronegativity of fluorine atoms that promote dipole alignment along with making it more electronegative as compared to other positive triboelectric materials. Triboelectric output measurements show significant improvement with PtFE addition: the open-circuit voltage increases from 9.5 V (0% PtFE) to 11.3 V (1% PtFE) and 18.5 V (3% PtFE), corresponding to a 19% and 95% enhancement, respectively. Optimized fibers with 3% PtFE reinforcement further improved load performance, delivering a peak power of 10.03 μ W at 9 M Ω for the single fiber with a diameter of 300 μ m and length 40 mm. The output of the fibers is seen to stable up to 15000 cycles as measured. These findings validate the role of fluorinated additives in tailoring the dielectric, electronegativity and dipolar properties of PVDF to boost TENG performance. The mechanically robust and flexible fiber architecture is compatible with textile integration, enabling its use in wearable energy harvesting systems.

Keyword: PVDF, Triboelectric, Energy Harvesting, Thermally drawn fibers

Development of Sustainable Cathode Electrodes for Zinc-Air Batteries Using Metal Doping and Biomass-Derived Carbon Quantum Dots

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Turkey has set an ambitious goal to become a regional hub for battery production and innovation by 2030, with a strategic focus on alternative energy storage systems beyond conventional lithium-ion technologies. Among these alternatives, metal-air batteries have attracted significant attention due to their high theoretical energy density, environmental compatibility, and cost efficiency [1-2].

In this study, the development of high-performance and sustainable cathode electrodes for zinc-air batteries was investigated. Initially, graphite was electrochemically oxidized to graphene oxide via a chronoamperometric method in a sulfuric acid medium. During synthesis, various concentrations of zinc sulfate were introduced to simultaneously achieve metal doping. This process improved the electrical conductivity and prolonged the discharge duration, thereby enhancing the overall charge transport capability of the electrode material [3-5].

In the second phase, carbon quantum dots (CQDs) were synthesized from food waste, specifically lemon peels, as a sustainable carbon source. The CQDs were incorporated into the electrochemical synthesis medium at different ratios and anchored onto the surface of the metal-doped graphene oxide. Their influence on the electrochemical behavior of the electrodes was systematically evaluated. The best-performing electrodes were tested in 6 M KOH electrolyte.

Electrochemical performance was assessed using cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Structural and morphological characterizations were carried out via FTIR, SEM, and UV-Vis spectrophotometry. The findings demonstrate that biomass-derived CQDs and metal doping synergistically enhance the electrochemical properties of zinc-air battery electrodes, offering a promising route toward environmentally friendly and efficient energy storage systems.

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Keyword: *Zinc-air battery, Energy storage, Carbon quantum dots, Electrochemical synthesis*

Plant Extract-Based Integrated Microfluidic Platform for Cyclotide Isolation

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Microfluidic chips play a vital role in modern biotechnology research. They offer a promising, low-cost, and easy-to-implement platform for developing efficient separation methodologies. This study introduces a separation method utilizing two distinct microfluidic chip designs. Compact microfluidic systems offer key advantages in speed, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness [1, 2]. The first design features three inlets and employs an applied electric current to facilitate active separation based on molecular charge or mobility. In this configuration, the central inlet introduces a plant extract, while the side inlets supply reagents [3]. Various voltages were tested to determine optimal separation conditions. The second design utilizes a simpler configuration with two inlets and incorporates a PET membrane positioned between two separate channels. This allows passive separation through selective diffusion, eliminating the need for external forces. As a low-cost and straightforward option, this membrane-based chip is well-suited for small-scale laboratory applications. In this setup, a dilute acid solution, either hydrochloric acid or phosphoric acid, was introduced through the second inlet. Flow rates of 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and 2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ were tested. To evaluate the effectiveness of both designs, a plant extract from *Viola ignobilis*, collected in Iran's West Azerbaijan province, was used. The target compounds in this study were cyclotides, small, highly stable cyclic peptides with promising potential in biomedical applications [3, 4].

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Keyword: *microfluidic chip, seperation, cyclotide, Viola Ignobilis*

Comparative Study of Titanosilicate ETS-10 and Vanadosilicate AM-6 Zeolite Films Prepared via Secondary Growth for Humidity Sensing Applications

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Zeotype-based materials are increasingly investigated for humidity sensing due to their high surface area, ion-exchange capacity, and structural tunability. Tailoring these materials to enhance sensitivity across a broad range of humidity levels remains a key challenge (1). This study explores the use of secondary growth techniques to improve the structural integrity and durability of ETS-10 and AM-6 zeolite films. AM-6, a vanadosilicate, was synthesized by overgrowing on ETS-10 seed layers, introducing a Ti–O–V linkage within the Ti–O–Ti framework. Impedance spectroscopy confirmed that both ETS-10 and AM-6 films exhibited stable performance, with AM-6 demonstrating enhanced sensitivity at low relative humidity. The incorporation of vanadium species, coupled with secondary growth, contributed to improved long-term performance by reducing degradation and increasing signal reproducibility. These results demonstrate the potential of vanadium-modified zeotype architectures, grown via secondary techniques, for robust and reliable humidity sensing applications.

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Keyword: *Zeotypes, Humidity sensing, Secondary growth method, Molecular sieves*

Synthesis, Characterization, and Electrochemical Evaluation of Transition Metal-Based Catalysts for Water Splitting Applications

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The growing global interest in renewable energy is accelerating the pursuit of technologies that are both efficient and environmentally sustainable.⁽¹⁾ Electrochemical water splitting is a promising method for hydrogen production, in which the nano- and microstructures and surface area of catalysts play critical roles.⁽²⁾

This study focuses on the synthesis and structural characterization of transition metal-based catalysts as alternatives to expensive noble metals. Due to their lower cost, natural abundance, and favorable redox properties, transition metals such as Iron, Cobalt, and Nickel (Fe, Co, Ni) have emerged as attractive alternatives to noble metals like Ruthenium (Ru).⁽³⁾

The synthesized catalysts are analyzed using advanced techniques, including X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), and Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX). These techniques are used to reveal key structural features such as crystallinity, morphology, and elemental distribution, which directly influence the catalytic efficiency and stability of the materials under electrochemical conditions.

Their catalytic behavior toward electrochemical reactions was assessed for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in alkaline medium using a three-electrode setup, with the synthesized catalysts deposited onto a glassy carbon electrode (GCE). Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) and Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV) are employed to gain insights into the structure–activity relationships of the catalysts.

These outcomes emphasize the promising role of transition metal catalysts in replacing noble metals for sustainable hydrogen production via water splitting.⁽⁴⁾

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Keyword: *Transition Metal Catalysts, Electrochemical Water Splitting, Oxygen Evolution Reaction*

Synthesis and Characterization of Graphene Oxide/Metal Oxide Nanostructures and Study of Their Catalytic Activities for Water Splitting

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With the increasing demand for energy and the gradual decrease of fossil fuel resources, the need for cleaner and more sustainable alternatives has become pressing. Hydrogen is considered a promising energy carrier due to its high efficiency. Among various production methods, electrochemical water splitting is one of the most eco-friendly approaches, though its high energy requirement remains a challenge. Transition metal oxides such as NiMoO₄ [1] and CoMoO₄ [2] exhibit promising electrocatalytic behavior, especially when supported on graphene oxide (GO) due to their redox-active nature. The synergistic interaction between metal oxide phases [3] and the conductive GO [4] matrix enhances charge transport and increases the availability of active sites. As a result, these hybrid nanostructures deliver high catalytic efficiency and long-term stability under alkaline conditions, making them suitable for sustainable hydrogen production.[5]

In this study, GO-NiMoO₄, GO-CoMoO₄, and novel GO-CoMoO₄-NiMoO₄ hybrid nanostructures were synthesized via hydrothermal method. The materials were characterized using FT-IR, UV-Vis, XRD, SEM, EDX, TEM, XPS, ICP-OES, and BET analyses. Their electrocatalytic performance toward the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in alkaline medium was evaluated using a three-electrode system, where the synthesized materials were coated onto a glassy carbon electrode (GCE). Among the synthesized structures, the P-U-GO-CoMoO₄-NiMoO₄ (P: Precursors, U: Urea) hybrid exhibited the most promising performance, with an onset potential of 1.56 V vs. RHE, an overpotential of 550 mV at a current density of 10 mA/ cm², and a Tafel slope of 71.7 mV/ dec in 0.1 M KOH. The enhanced activity was attributed to the improved conductivity and redox-active surface sites offered by the combination of NiMoO₄ and CoMoO₄ on the GO matrix. The findings of this research highlight the potential of P-U-GO-CoMoO₄-NiMoO₄ as a low-cost and efficient electrocatalyst for water splitting applications, contributing to the advancement of sustainable hydrogen production technologies.

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Keyword: *Metal Oxide Nanoparticles, Graphene Oxide, Electrochemical Water Splitting, Hybrid Nanomaterials*

Protein Corona in Nanomedicine: Trojan Horse or Biological Barrier?

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The diagnostic and therapeutic innovations of nanomedical applications have ushered in a new transformative era in biomedical research, particularly through the development of targeted drug delivery systems. However, upon exposure to biological media, nanoparticles rapidly interact with biomolecules, most notably proteins, leading to the formation of a dynamic, protein-rich layer known as the protein corona. The composition and behaviour of the protein corona structure are governed by various factors, including the size, shape, surface chemistry, and charge of nanoparticles, as well as the biochemical complexity and protein content of the surrounding environment. This coating masks the synthetic nature of nanoparticles and endows them with a new “biological identity”, thereby playing a pivotal role in determining their cellular interactions and uptake, biodistribution, circulation lifetime, toxicity profile, immune response and therapeutic effects. In this context, the protein corona may act either as a biological barrier that induces undesired, non-specific interactions and impedes targeted delivery, or conversely, as a Trojan Horse that facilitates cellular uptake or immune evasion. Understanding the mechanistic underpinnings of protein corona formation and its dynamic evolution is thus essential for improving the biological predictability and translational success of nanomedical systems. This poster explores whether the protein corona represents a natural barrier or a modifiable design interface opportunity, emphasizing its dual role in modulating the efficacy and safety of nanocarrier-based therapeutics. It further outlines the strategic approaches to manipulate protein corona formation through nanoparticle surface engineering. Additionally, emerging paradigms are also highlighted that aim to transform the protein corona from a biological challenge into an integrative and functional design element in the rational development of next-generation nanomedicines.

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Keyword: *Protein Corona, Nanoparticles, Nanomedicine, Nanoparticle surface engineering*

Monodisperse Ultra-Thin Shell Double Emulsions via a Controlled Droplet Emulsification Method

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Ultrathin-shell double emulsions have emerged as highly promising microstructures for a wide range of applications in drug delivery, synthetic biology, and nanomaterial synthesis. Their unique architecture enables the encapsulation of sensitive chemical or biological species with high efficiency while maintaining a minimal barrier between the internal and external environments. The reduced shell thickness plays a key role in improving molecular transport, allowing for faster diffusion, more responsive release behavior, and increased interaction with the surrounding medium. These properties are particularly beneficial in systems requiring dynamic exchange, such as drug release, biochemical sensing, or artificial cell models.

In this study, we present a novel microfluidic approach for generating water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) double emulsions with ultrathin oil shells using a two-junction flow-focusing design that decouples droplet formation timing. Unlike conventional methods where the inner aqueous phase forms discrete droplets at the first junction, this technique maintains it as a continuous stream through precise flow rate control. This prevents premature breakup and allows the aqueous stream to reach the second junction, where it is encapsulated by the oil phase and pinched off into uniform double emulsions with submicron shell thickness. The resulting droplets exhibit high monodispersity, structural stability, and tunable shell thickness, offering enhanced control over emulsion architecture for applications in nanomedicine, synthetic cell engineering, and targeted delivery systems.

Keyword: *Microfluidics, Ultrathin-shell double emulsions, W/O/W emulsions, Droplet generation*

Synergistic Therapy of Pancreatic Cancer: Gold Nanoparticles Decorated FOLFIRINOX Loaded Liposomes

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Pancreatic cancer is predicted to be the second highest cause of cancer deaths by 2030, with a mortality rate of 98 % and a 5-year survival rate of only 4–8 %. FOLFIRINOX which consists of four main ingredients has shown superior efficacy in treating patients with pancreatic cancer compared to other agents and combinations. However, toxicities have prevented full-dose use of FOLFIRINOX. In this study, we present the design of a liposome nanosystem that enables the sequential release of a drug combination that is called FOLFIRINOX using lipid-based nanosystem synergistic chemo/photothermal therapy approaches. The co-eccentric liposome allowed us to locate the drug molecules in different locations giving us the flexibility to release them in a selected order.

Keyword: *Pancreatic cancer, Folfrinox, Vesicle*

Development and Characterization of Vitamin K3-Loaded Liposomes for Enhanced Treatment of Breast Cancer

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Breast cancer is among the most prevalent malignancies in women worldwide, with approximately 2.3 million new cases diagnosed annually. Although chemotherapy remains the first-line treatment, it is limited by significant adverse effects. Vitamin K, an essential micronutrient, has shown anticancer properties in various cell models. Menadione sodium bisulfite (Vitamin K3, VK3) is a hydrophilic synthetic vitamin K analog that exhibits potent anticancer activity against breast cancer cells by inducing reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation and mitochondrial damage.

To improve drug delivery and therapeutic efficacy, a novel PEGylated liposomal formulation of VK3 (L-VK3) composed of hydrogenated soy phosphatidylcholine (HSPC), cholesterol, and DSPE-PEG2000. L-VK3 was prepared by thin-film hydration with passive loading of VK3, achieving an encapsulation efficiency of $53.8 \pm 11.4\%$. For combination therapy, doxorubicin-loaded PEGylated liposomes (L-DOX) were prepared by thin-film hydration followed by active loading via an ammonium sulfate gradient, achieving an encapsulation efficiency of $96.2 \pm 1.1\%$. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) confirmed that both formulations were spherical with diameters of 128-150 nm. L-VK3 remained stable at 4°C for 45 days, and in vitro release studies demonstrated sustained release of VK3 from the liposomes.

In vitro cytotoxicity was evaluated using the MCF-7 human breast cancer cell line and L929 fibroblasts as a noncancerous control. Free VK3 was cytotoxic to both cell types. In contrast, L-VK3 showed reduced cytotoxicity in both MCF-7 and L929 cells relative to free VK3, consistent with its controlled release profile and suggesting enhanced selectivity for cancer cells. L-DOX demonstrated increased cytotoxicity against MCF-7 cells and decreased toxicity toward L929 cells compared to free DOX. Notably, sequential treatment (L-VK3 for 3 days followed by L-DOX for 3 days) significantly enhanced cytotoxicity in MCF-7 cells relative to single-liposome treatments. These findings indicate successful development of L-VK3 formulation and show that encapsulating VK3 in PEGylated liposomes shows potential in the treatment of breast cancer, and that sequential administration of VK3 followed by DOX may represent a promising therapeutic strategy for breast cancer.

Keyword: *Vitamin K3, Liposomes, Doxorubicin, Breast Cancer*

Eco-Friendly Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles from Rice Husk for Blood-Brain Barrier Penetration and Brain-Targeted Drug Delivery

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The blood-brain barrier (BBB) is a highly selective physiological barrier that restricts the delivery of therapeutic agents to the brain.^[1] Safely and environmentally friendly overcoming the BBB remains a major challenge in drug delivery systems.^[2] Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are promising candidates for overcoming the BBB and brain-targeted drug delivery due to their high surface area, tunable pore size, biocompatibility, ease of synthesis, and porous structure that enables controlled drug loading and release.^[3] In this study, rice husk, a biowaste, was used instead of toxic chemical silica sources used in conventional MSN synthesis. Moreover, by eliminating the environmentally harmful calcination step in silica extraction from biosources, RPMSNs (Rice Precipitated MSN) were synthesized in an ecofriendly, economical, and scalable manner by a green chemistry-based sol-gel method.^[4] Surface modifications were applied to RPMSNs to increase their functions and BBB permeability. As a result, four types of nanoparticles were synthesized: RPMSN, amine-modified RPMSN, carboxyl-modified RPMSN and PEG-modified RPMSN. The physicochemical properties of nanoparticles were successfully verified by FTIR, XRD, BET, TEM, Zeta potential, and TGA. MTT assay analyses were performed in the dose range of 0–200 µg/mL for the toxicity evaluation of the synthesized nanoparticles on HDF, HUVEC, and U87 cell lines. The results indicated the biosafety of RPMSN and amine-modified RPMSNs among all cell lines while carboxyl-modified RPMSNs and PEG-modified RPMSNs appeared to be safe at low concentrations. An in vitro BBB model was established on the Transwell system by seeding induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) derived brain microvessel endothelial cells (iBMECs) in the apical compartment and astrocytes and pericytes in the basolateral compartment to assess BBB permeability. Nanoparticles were applied to the Transwell system at a concentration of 70 µg/mL and incubated for 24 hours. To evaluate both the establishment and preservation of barrier integrity, apparent permeability (P_{app}) measurements were conducted before and after nanoparticle treatment. The data highlights that none of the nanoparticle groups disrupted the BBB integrity or significantly altered its permeability. As a result, RPMSN and PEG-modified RPMSN exhibited the highest permeation across the BBB model, indicating their strong potential as nanocarriers for brain-targeted drug delivery

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Keyword: *Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles, Green Chemistry, Blood-brain Barrier, Drug Delivery*

Development of Gene Therapy Nanoparticles for Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Therapy

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Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) is a stem cell malignancy caused by the Philadelphia chromosome, which generates the BCR-ABL fusion gene. This gene encodes a constitutively active tyrosine kinase, leading to uncontrolled myeloid cell proliferation. Eukaryotic elongation factor 2 kinase (eEF2K) plays a crucial role in cancer cell survival and drug resistance, making it a potential therapeutic target. In this study, we developed layer-by-layer (LbL) nanoparticles to deliver eEF2K siRNA to K562 cells, aiming to suppress EF2K expression and promote apoptosis. Hybrid nanoparticles were synthesized following our previously published protocol. The zeta potential of each layer was measured to monitor changes in surface charge, confirming successful layer deposition. The biological activity and cytotoxic effects of the nanoparticles were evaluated on K562 cells using the Resazurin assay to determine cell viability. Zeta potential measurements confirmed the successful assembly of nanoparticles. The hybrid nanoparticles had a zeta potential of -42.6 ± 0.6 mV. After PAH coating, the potential shifted to 51.6 ± 4.0 mV, indicating successful coating. eEF2K siRNA binding reduced the potential to 23.7 ± 4.2 mV, confirming attachment. Finally, PSS coating further decreased the zeta potential to -48.7 ± 1.3 mV, verifying successful deposition. In vitro molecular analysis is currently being conducted to evaluate the therapeutic effect of our engineered hybrid particles. The assembly of hybrid nanoparticles was confirmed by zeta potential measurements. The IC_{50} value of 86.1 ± 9.0 nM indicates high efficacy in reducing K562 cell viability, suggesting effective EF2K gene silencing. These findings demonstrate the potential of hybrid nanoparticles as a promising siRNA delivery platform for chronic myeloid leukemia treatment.

Keyword: Gene Therapy, Layer-by-Layer, Leukemia Cancer, eEF2K siRNA

Nano-Enabled Antimicrobial Strategy Against Oral Biofilms and *S. mutans*

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Streptococcus mutans is a major contributor to dental caries and biofilm formation in the oral cavity, leading to persistent infections that are challenging to eliminate with conventional antimicrobial treatments. Its ability to form robust biofilms on tooth surfaces enhances resistance to antimicrobial agents and hosts immune defenses, highlighting the need for novel therapeutic strategies. This study aims to evaluate the dual antimicrobial efficacy of Melittin-Micelle Complex (MMC) against *Streptococcus mutans*, focusing on its ability to inhibit planktonic bacterial growth and eradicate established biofilms. By comparing the activity of free melittin, micelle carriers, and the melittin-micelle formulation through MIC and MBEC assays, this study seeks to explore the potential of MMC as a novel therapeutic agent for oral infections and biofilm-related dental diseases. The study evaluated the antibacterial and anti-biofilm effects of melittin and MMC nanoparticles against *S. mutans* using MIC and MBEC assays. Significant inhibition of *Streptococcus mutans* growth was observed at concentrations above 32 µg/mL according to the MIC assay. Spot assay results confirmed these findings, showing visible bacterial colonies at concentrations ≤ 32 µg/mL and no visible colonies at 64 µg/mL and above, thus confirming the MIC value. Furthermore, the MBEC₅₀, representing the concentration required to eradicate 50% of the biofilm, was determined as 32 µg/mL. These results are consistent with previous assays and support the antimicrobial effectiveness of melittin nanoparticles against *S. mutans*. MMC shows promising potential for oral healthcare applications. Its antibacterial and anti-biofilm properties make it suitable for preventing and treating dental infections.

Keyword: Melittin-Micelle Complex, Antibacterial, Antibiofilm, *S. mutans*

Nanoformulated Melittin-Doxorubicin Cocktail in Polymeric Micelles for Enhanced Cytotoxicity in Triple-Negative Breast Cancer Cells

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Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer among women, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is particularly challenging with current treatments, often leading to high toxicity, drug resistance, and risks of metastasis. Melittin (Mel), a peptide derived from bee venom, makes up approximately 50% of the venom's dry weight and has significant biological and pharmacological activities, including anticancer effects. Despite its therapeutic potential, Mel's clinical use has been restricted due to its substantial hemolytic effects and non-specific cytotoxicity, which can damage healthy cells as well as cancer cells. To address these challenges, we have developed polymeric micelles for the delivery of melittin. By combining melittin with doxorubicin (Mel-DOX NPs), we aim to harness the synergistic effects of both agents to more effectively treat Triple-Negative Breast Cancer, enhancing therapeutic efficacy while minimizing side effects. In this study, a negatively charged copolymer, SPMA-co-PMMA, was used using RAFT polymerization. This copolymer was utilized to create micelles for the co-delivery of melittin and doxorubicin. The critical micelle concentration (CMC) was determined using Nile Red. Their impact and biocompatibility were evaluated through cell viability on MDA-MB-231, 4T1, and HEK-293 cell lines, and hemolysis assays. Additionally, the combination index was assessed using Compusyn. The results indicate that Mel-NPs have a size of 147.9 ± 10.3 nm, DOX-NPs measure 178.3 ± 7.1 nm, and Mel-DOX NPs are 180.1 ± 9.5 nm, whereas the empty micelles have a size of 125.6 ± 5 nm. The measured zeta potentials for the empty NPs, Mel-NPs, DOX-NPs, and Mel-DOX NPs are -31.3 ± 1.15 mV, -31.1 ± 1.48 mV, -20.6 ± 0.60 mV, and -19.6 ± 1.77 mV, respectively. The binding efficiencies of the developed Mel-DOX NPs are 96.02 ± 0.96 % and 71.98 ± 1.36 % for melittin and DOX, respectively. Both Empty NPs and Mel-NPs exhibited no hemolysis of red blood cells (RBCs), and there was no significant difference compared to the negative control (PBS). According to cell viability results, Mel-DOX NPs affected cell viability at lower doses in MDA and 4T1 cells compared to their free states and individual NP formulations, while higher doses were required in HEK cells. The CI was <0 , indicating that the melittin and doxorubicin combination has a synergistic effect on MDA-MB-231 and 4T1 cells. The developed polymeric micelles show strong potential for triple-negative breast cancer treatment by enhancing efficacy and minimizing side effects through the synergistic delivery of melittin and doxorubicin.

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Keyword: Melittin, Polymeric Micelles, Triple-Negative Breast Cancer, Synergic Effect

Engineering a Hybrid Nanoplatfom for Combined Therapeutic Delivery and Immune Activation

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The integration of nanotechnology with immunotherapy strategies presents new opportunities for effective cancer treatment. In this study, a multifunctional nanoplatfom was developed by combining bioactive flavonoid molecules with green-synthesized gold and silver-based nanoparticles. To enhance cellular uptake, the nanoparticle surfaces were functionalized with short cationic peptides known to facilitate endocytosis. Furthermore, the particles were cloaked with cancer cell-derived membrane vesicles to impart biomimetic properties, enabling homotypic targeting and presentation of tumor-associated antigens. This strategy not only improves the intracellular delivery of poorly soluble therapeutic agents but also contributes to immune activation through antigen mimicry. Preliminary physicochemical characterizations confirmed the stability, size distribution, and surface properties of the system. The designed platform offers dual functionality in delivering therapeutic molecules and stimulating immune responses, representing a promising approach for combined chemo-immunotherapy.

Keyword: Nano-vaccine, Cell Membrane Coating, Peptides, Drug-Loaded-Nanoparticles, Cancer Therapy.

Self-Organized Peptide Nanofibers for Treatment of Viral Infections

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The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic emphasized the need for quickly adaptive therapeutic approaches by demonstrating how fast viral evolution makes regular antiviral drugs ineffective. Using counterionic peptide amphiphiles (PAs) with different inhibitory effects, we created a multi-targeted peptide nanofiber (PNF) system in this work. In order to assess their efficacy against distinct SARS-CoV-2 variants, negatively charged PAs included a heparin-inspired peptide sequence that was created using heparin's known inhibitory properties in addition to a number of spacer sequences. From previously examined inhibitory sequences, positively charged PAs that allowed for the production of nanofibers were chosen. With differing degrees of efficacy, these PNF systems demonstrated strong inhibitory activity against both wild-type and mutant viruses, demonstrating the system's versatility. The PNF systems' inhibitory efficacy was assessed using a number of tests, such as 3D cell spheroid models and pseudovirus neutralization. These findings showed that the PNF systems may considerably lower viral entrance, with certain formulations showing almost 100% inhibition in the wild-type pseudovirus. The H2F PNF significantly reduced the viral entrance of the D614G mutant pseudoviruses by 81% for the mutant versions. Additionally, by blocking the cleavage of the spike protein via TMPRSS2, a critical step in viral entry, nafamostat (NFM) improved the inhibitory effects. Peptide nanofibers and nafamostat together offer a promising method for creating highly effective and versatile antiviral therapies that can adapt to the quickly changing SARS- CoV-2 and other viral pathogens.

Keyword: SARS-CoV-2, Nanopharmaceutics, Nanotechnology, Peptide Nanofibers

Antibacterial Efficacy of Ti₃C₂T_x and Nb₂CT_x MXenes Against Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Bacterial Strains

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Bacterial infections remain a pressing global health concern, with conventional antibiotic therapies increasingly compromised by the rapid rise of multidrug-resistant MDR pathogens. This escalating resistance crisis necessitates the exploration of alternative, non-antibiotic antimicrobial strategies. MXenes, a novel class of two-dimensional transition metal carbides, nitrides, and carbonitride, have emerged as promising candidates in nanomedicine due to their unique structural, electrical, and surface properties.

In this study, the antibacterial potential of two representative MXenes, Ti₃C₂T_x and Nb₂CT_x was investigated against Gram-negative Escherichia coli ATCC 25922 (E. coli) and Gram-positive Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 25923 (S. aureus) bacteria. Ti₃C₂T_x and Nb₂CT_x were synthesized via lithium fluoride and hydrochloride acid (LiF/HCl) assisted mild etching and hydrothermal etching methods, respectively. Structural and morphological characterizations were performed using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Particle size and zeta potential were measured using dynamic light scattering (DLS). The antibacterial activities of both samples at varying concentrations were determined by minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and colony formation unit (CFU) values.

The XRD patterns of both samples demonstrated typical diffraction peaks below 10° corresponding to the (0 0 2) plane of MXenes and the absence of residual peaks of MAX phases at around 39° after etching, confirming the successful transformation from MAX phases to MXene. SEM imaging and EDX revealed the layered nanosheet morphology and elemental composition consistent with MXene structures. Moreover, the average hydrodynamic diameters and zeta potentials were approximately 178 nm and -27 mV for Ti₃C₂T_x and 217 nm and -42 mV for Nb₂CT_x, respectively. Both MXenes exhibited significant dose-dependent antibacterial activity against E. coli and S. aureus, with Ti₃C₂T_x showing superior inhibitory effects, particularly against E. coli.

These findings highlight the antimicrobial efficacy of Ti₃C₂T_x and Nb₂CT_x as effective antibacterial agents against both E. coli and S. aureus bacteria, supporting the continued investigation of MXene-based nanomaterials as promising platforms for combating antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections in the context of advanced nanomedicine.

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Keyword: MXenes, Antibacterial agents, Nanomedicine, Multi-drug resistance

Enhancing Paclitaxel's Chemotherapeutic Potential with MOF-5 Nanocarriers: Superior Efficacy Across Breast Cancer Subtypes

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Breast cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths among women, with triple-negative subtypes presenting major challenges due to their aggressiveness and treatment resistance. Paclitaxel is a widely used chemotherapeutic that disrupts cell division by stabilizing microtubules, yet its efficacy is limited by poor solubility, systemic toxicity, and non-specific distribution. To overcome these issues, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have gained attention as nanocarriers, offering high surface area, tunable porosity, and biocompatibility. MOF-5 provides an efficient platform for paclitaxel loading, improving solubility, enabling controlled release, and enhancing tumour targeting. In this study, MOF-5 nanoparticles were synthesized via coordination of terephthalic acid (H₂BDC) with zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6H₂O) in DMF, using triethylamine (TEA) as a modulator.

Characterization of the nanoparticles using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) revealed uniformly distributed nanoparticles with 50 to 70 nm diameters. Paclitaxel was loaded into the MOF-5 structure at a concentration of 10 µM with approximately 70% encapsulation efficiency. To evaluate the therapeutic efficacy, the Paclitaxel-loaded MOF-5 nanoparticles were tested in MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell lines. In MCF-7 cells, the IC₅₀ value of free paclitaxel was 2.28 µM, while the paclitaxel-loaded MOF-5 nano formulation reduced the IC₅₀ value to 1.12 µM. An even more pronounced improvement was observed in the triple-negative MDA-MB-231 line. The initial IC₅₀ value was 3.64 µM and decreased to 20.3 nM following MOF-5 mediated delivery.

These results underline the potential of MOF-5 as a highly effective nanocarrier capable of enhancing drug potency, especially in aggressive breast cancer type. The observed improvements are likely linked to improved cellular uptake and sustained release kinetics. Overall, this study supports the continued development of MOF-based targeted drug delivery systems and provides a base for future translational applications.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: *Nanomedicine, Breast cancer, MOF-5 nanoparticles, Paclitaxel*

The Role of Acoustic Treatment in Zein Nanoencapsulation of Vitamin B12

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Vitamin B12 (cobalamin) is an essential water-soluble micronutrient involved in numerous physiological processes, including red blood cell formation and neurological function. However, its chemical instability under environmental stressors and low bioavailability necessitate protective delivery systems. Zein, a hydrophobic prolamine protein derived from corn, has emerged as a promising encapsulation matrix due to its biodegradability, biocompatibility, and unique solubility profile — being insoluble in gastric conditions but readily dissolving in the intestinal environment. This property enables zein-based carriers to provide targeted release of bioactives in the intestine, making it a suitable candidate for oral delivery of sensitive compounds like vitamin B12.

In the present study, vitamin B12 was nanoencapsulated within a zein matrix via ultrasonic cavitation, employing a sonochemistry-driven approach as an alternative to conventional encapsulation techniques such as electrospinning and electrospaying. The experimental design was developed based on parameters reported in the literature, with encapsulation efficiency evaluated under varying electrical current intensities (0.4 A, 0.8 A, 1.3 A, and 1.7 A). While power level, processing time, solvent ratio, and B12/zein ratios were held constant, the device power output was incrementally adjusted from 25% to 100%.

In contrast to prior studies, a sinusoidal waveform was utilized for acoustic energy application, enabling dynamic and continuous energy transfer to the cavitation process. The resulting nanocapsules were characterized using optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Among the tested conditions, the sample processed at 1.3 A exhibited optimal encapsulation performance, as evidenced by homogeneous surface morphology and reduced crystallinity. SEM analysis revealed uniform capsule structures, while XRD patterns indicated a suppression of the crystalline B12 phase and the predominance of an amorphous structure. These findings demonstrate the potential of sonochemical methods as an effective strategy for the nanoencapsulation of vitamin B12, particularly when intestinal-targeted delivery is desired.

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Keyword: *Sonochemistry, Ultrasonic Cavitation, Cyanocobalamin, Zein*

Nanocomposite Thin Film Based on Ru(II)-Complex and Polymeric Layer for Solid-State Sensing Surface

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Tris(2,2'-bipyridyl) ruthenium(II), $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, and 4-amino-3-hydroxynaphthalene sulfonic acid (AHNSA) were electrochemically polymerized from their aqueous solutions at a glassy carbon electrode (GCE) to create a composite electrochemiluminescence (ECL) sensor. The proposed one-step electrochemical fabrication of the composite film (Ru/PAHNSA/GCE) produces a stable and reactive luminescent material for quantifying chlorpheniramine maleate (CPM) in pharmaceutical formulations. The features and structure of the modified surface were examined using common testing methods like voltammetry, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The ECL intensity increases in a straight line with the amount of CPM from 0.2 to 32 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, with the lowest amount that can be detected being 0.023 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The sensor's performance was evaluated in the presence of interfering species and during the analysis of genuine samples under ideal conditions.

Keyword: *Solid-state surface, Ru(II)-Complex, Electrochemiluminescence*

Structural, Electronic, and Magnetic Properties of Altermagnetic MnTe

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Altermagnetism is a new form of unconventional magnetism characterized by its spin-rotation symmetry breaking with zero net magnetization, such as antiferromagnets. Despite the absence of net magnetization, altermagnets can also exhibit phenomena typically associated with ferromagnets, such as anomalous Hall conductivity (AHC), spin-dependent band structures, and spin Hall conductivity (SHC), therefore offering distinct advantages for spintronic applications such as efficient spin currents without stray magnetic fields. Among these materials, hexagonal MnTe has emerged as a strong material candidate due to its substantial spin-splitting. In this study, we first perform density functional theory calculations with Hubbard U corrections (DFT+U) to obtain the structural relaxation and the electronic band structure of MnTe. We use a plane wave-based DFT package (Quantum Espresso) with a Monkhorst-Pack grid for Brillouin zone integration for ground state charge densities, energies, and wavefunctions. Following first-principles calculations, we compute the maximally localized Wannier functions and proceed to evaluate the intrinsic AHC and SHC from the Kubo formula within the linear response approximation. We observe that the band structure exhibits momentum-dependent spin splitting without net magnetization, which is consistent with the altermagnetic nature of MnTe. We also find that increasing the Hubbard U leads to a progressive opening of the band gap, inducing a transition from metallic to semiconducting behavior. In addition, evaluation of the intrinsic AHC and SHC shows significantly high values, originating particularly from states located approximately 1.5 - 2 eV above and below the Fermi level, which contain Berry curvature “hot spots” with extremely large values. These findings support the classification of MnTe as an altermagnet and highlight its potential for spintronic platforms.

Keyword: *altermagnetism, spintronics, quantum materials*

Design of stimuli-responsive bioadhesives based on anchor peptides: Toward recyclable composite materials

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The low recycling rate of composite materials is one of the major challenges currently faced in waste management, due to the difficulty in separating and/or recovering their individual constituents. “Stimuli-responsive adhesives” can provide a new perspective that could offer a solution to this problem. Here, bio-based adhesives, which can be separated under a controlled trigger effect, were developed for PVC and aluminum foil sheets by using advanced protein engineering techniques. For this purpose, firstly, the surface-coating abilities of several wild-type and engineered anchor peptides (APs) on target surfaces were systematically evaluated. Owing to their potential for selective binding to polymers and proteins, these peptides present significant advantages for surface functionalization applications. For the APs exhibiting higher affinities, CBM3-AP (Carbohydrate-Binding Module Family 3-fused AP) constructs were produced via genetic fusion to be able to obtain more target-oriented and efficient interactions. Various glue formulations were then designed by combining these constructs with cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) to achieve high dry-bond strength and enhanced water resistance. The data obtained confirmed that, CBM3-AP and CNC interactions played a key role in improving adhesion properties and ensuring improved stability. Moreover, the selective on-demand debonding behavior of these samples under the pH trigger, occurring within feasible timeframes, was found to be highly promising. The results obtained in this study were thought to bring substantial contributions to the sustainability, waste management and circular economy applications.

Keyword: *Composite waste recyclability, stimuli-responsive adhesive, nanocellulose crystals (CNC), anchor peptides*

Immunomodulatory Effects of Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles in the Ehrlich Ascites Tumour Model

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Nanoparticles (NPs) can modulate the immune response by enhancing or suppressing it, depending on their physicochemical properties, surface reactivity, and the cellular microenvironment (1). In cancer research, NPs play a critical role in the reprogramming and modulation of the tumor microenvironment by influencing not only tumor cells but also the activity of immune cells and cytokine secretion (2).

In this study, the biological effects of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) NPs were investigated on ascites fluid cells derived from the intraperitoneal injection of Ehrlich Ascites Tumor (EAT) cells, originating from mammary adenocarcinoma, into Balb/C mice. TiO₂ NPs were characterized by UV-VIS spectrometry, DLS, Cryo-TEM, and EDX analyses. Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) oxidase activity and inflammatory cytokine levels were measured by flow cytometry in ascites fluid cells cultured for 24, 48, and 72 hours with TiO₂ NPs at concentrations of 0, 25, 50, 100, and 200 µg/mL.

Using flow cytometry gating techniques, it was determined that NADPH oxidase activity increased in peritoneal CD11b⁺ (neutrophil, monocyte, macrophage) cells isolated from ascites fluid. This increase was observed at all concentrations at 24 and 48 hours, and at 100 µg/mL and 200 µg/mL TiO₂ NP concentrations at 72 hours. In CD11b⁻ EAT cells, a significant increase in NADPH oxidase activity compared to the control group was observed at high concentrations (100 and 200 µg/mL) at 24 and 48 hours, and at 100 µg/mL at 72 hours. TiO₂ NPs were found to suppress antitumor IL-12 production in CD11b⁺ cells, while increasing IL-1β and immunosuppressive IL-10 levels. IL-1β peaked at 48 hours, IL-10 showed the highest increase at 24 hours and reached its maximum at 72 hours with 200 µg/mL. IL-12 suppression persisted up to 72 hours. In CD3⁺ T cells within the ascites fluid, IL-10 production peaked at 24 hours with 200 µg/mL TiO₂ NPs and declined over time. TNF-α production was significantly increased in the presence of TiO₂ NP at concentrations of 100 and 200 µg/mL at 24 hours, but this increase continued at 48 hours, although it decreased.

NADPH oxidases produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and studies have revealed that they promote protumorigenic processes through redox-dependent signaling pathways (3). TiO₂ NPs may increase ROS production via NADPH oxidase activating signaling in endothelial, immune and tumor cells, which supports angiogenesis, tumor growth and immunosuppression in EAT cells. They can modulate cytokine secretion in the tumor microenvironment by activating CD11b⁺ cells and directly interacting with T cells. The observed modulation of cytokine production in CD11b⁺ and CD3⁺ T cells suggests a potential immunomodulatory role for these nanoparticles in shaping a tumor-promoting inflammatory microenvironment.

This study was supported by Erciyes University BAP (Project No: TDK-2022-11610) and animal experiments were approved by the Erciyes University Local Ethics Committee.

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Keyword: *TiO₂ NPs, Immunomodulatory effects, NADPH oxidase, Cytokine*

Functionalization of CaCO₃ crystals as novel polyelectrolyte multilayer reservoir for drug delivery

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The properties of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) make it a great option for drug delivery, particularly for medicinal substances with short half-lives, poor stability, solubility, bioavailability, and distribution/penetration. The significant step in CaCO₃ fabrication is to obtain polyelectrolyte multilayered capsules. Isolated soysaponin-integrated CaCO₃ crystals were functionalized by chitosan/polyacrylic acid and polydopamine/hyaluronic acid as multilayers. Rose Bengal and camptothecin were integrated during fabrication separately and simultaneously. The characterization of CaCO₃ crystals was investigated by using SEM, FTIR, XRD, and zeta potential measurements. Results showed an assembled structure of CaCO₃ crystals with strong integration of Rose Bengal and camptothecin. CaCO₃ crystals removed by EDTA obtained good reservation for Rose Bengal and camptothecin. The structure raised the potential application in drug delivery.

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Keyword: CaCO₃, Soysaponin, reservation, Rose Bengal

Machine Learning Combined Label-free SERS for Investigation of Brucella Infected Body Fluids

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Brucella is a Gram-negative bacterium that causes brucellosis, a zoonotic disease. Rapid and accurate detection of Brucella is critical due to its impact on human and animal health, its economic consequences, and the necessity of controlling its transmission. Conventional diagnostic methods, including culture from blood or other body fluids, serological assays, and PCR, are widely used but have drawbacks. These include being time-consuming, costly, and dependent on specialized equipment and trained personnel, often within high-level biosafety environments. There is an urgent need to develop accelerated methods for the detection of the bacteria and to investigate the impact of bacteria on bodily fluids for efficient treatment. Surface-enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS), enhances the Raman scattering signal of molecules that are attached to nanostructured metallic surfaces, has become a promising method for rapidly and precisely identifying bacteria and studying bodily fluids such as blood, and cerebrospinal fluid. The combination of SERS with machine learning techniques enhances diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. Machine learning algorithms could examine intricate SERS spectrum data and accurately differentiate between samples. In this study, we investigated the potential of combining SERS with machine learning algorithms to analyze cerebrospinal fluid and blood serum samples infected with Brucella. Using silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) as the enhancing substrate, we acquired SERS spectra from both infected and non-infected samples [1,2]. Distinct spectral differences were observed between infected and non-infected fluids. Linear regression accurately classified cerebrospinal fluid and serum samples with 100% accuracy. Additionally, the t-SNE algorithm successfully distinguished serum samples infected with varying bacterial titers, achieving 92% accuracy. In conclusion, this approach demonstrates the promise of combining SERS with machine learning for rapid and precise detection of bacterial infections in bodily fluids.

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Keyword: *Brucella, brucellosis, Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS), machine learning*

Development of a Nanoparticle-Based Subunit Vaccine Against Epstein-Barr Virus: Comparative Formulation and In Vitro Evaluation

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Introduction:

Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV) is the first oncogenic virus, infecting nearly 90% of adults worldwide. As a member of the subfamily Gammaherpesvirinae of the family Herpesviridae, EBV tends to be asymptomatic during childhood but can cause infectious mononucleosis in adolescence or early adulthood. Once primary infection has occurred, the virus becomes latently established in B lymphocytes and can be reactivated during stress, immunosuppression states, and even due to certain pharmacological agents. It produces a broad range of clinical manifestations. Besides acute infections, EBV is also associated with numerous hematologic and epithelial malignancies (Hodgkin lymphoma, Burkitt lymphoma, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, EBV-associated gastric carcinoma) and autoimmune conditions such as systemic lupus erythematosus, Sjögren's syndrome and multiple sclerosis. In spite of extensive large-scale studies, no licensed vaccine exists to date.(1-5)

Aim: This study aimed to construct a nanoparticle-based vaccine candidate that would induce a strong immune response against EBV, through optimization of the lipid formulation and in vitro cytokine profile analysis.

Methods: Different liposomal subunit vaccine formulations containing recombinant gp350 antigen and the immunostimulatory adjuvant Monophosphoryl Lipid (MPL) were developed using various lipid compositions (including DOPC, DOPE, cholesterol, lecithin, and PEG-lipids). These formulations were evaluated for their physicochemical properties (particle size, polydispersity index, SPAN, zeta potential and encapsulation efficiency) and in vitro protein release profile. Cytotoxicity was evaluated in EBV-positive Burkitt lymphoma B cells (Daudi cell line), whereas immunogenicity was investigated in THP-1 monocyte-derived cells by evaluating cytokine response (TNF- α , IL-6, IL-10).

Results: Among the formulations developed, DOPC liposomal formulation had favorable physicochemical characteristics such as particle size <200 nm, polydispersity index <0.3, and encapsulation efficiency >90%. The formulation had zeta potential values, typical for good colloidal stability. Release studies in vitro confirmed sustained release of antigen. It indicated lower cytotoxicity levels than the positive control, suggesting a good safety profile in EBV-positive Daudi cells. The cytokine assays revealed significantly higher levels of TNF- α and IL-6, indicative of a Th1-biased immune response, especially at 24 and 48 hours post-incubation.

Conclusion: Parallel comparison of various liposomal formulations identified the DOPC-based system as a promising candidate for further development. Its favorable physicochemical stability, high capacity for encapsulation, and ability to induce a strong immune response in vitro are all optimal markers of its potential as a next-generation EBV subunit vaccine.

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Keyword: Epstein-Barr Virus, subunit vaccine, Liposome, Adjuvant

siRNA Loading Strategy to the Exosome

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Gene therapy is a new strategy that provides great benefits for various treatments. However, the problems experienced in the delivery of naked genetic material (oligonucleotide, siRNA, etc.) have led to the search for an effective strategy and have enabled the development of nanocarrier systems in the field of gene therapy. In general, nanocarrier systems & drug delivery systems designed to carry, distribute and release molecules with biological activity are based on nanotechnology. These nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems are described as promising strategies used to overcome technical, biological, and biopharmaceutical limitations; their advantages include the possibility of designing multifunctional drugs with high therapeutic efficacy thanks to the possibility of increasing selectivity and specificity towards cellular or molecular targets. In the presented study, it is aimed to develop a drug candidate for gene therapy by providing genetic material transport of exosomes with a nanobiotechnological approach and protecting the genetic material by providing escape from the immune system.

In the presented study, while developing the exosome isolation strategy, the effect of sucrose gradient on exosome isolation from blood was evaluated. The obtained exosomes were characterised by NTA, zeta potential, western blot, and electron microscopy. siRNA loading was performed as genetic material into exosomes. At this stage, siRNA loading analyses were performed using ultrasonic probes into exosomes. The effects of ultrasonic probe power, loading times, and siRNA concentrations on siRNA loading into exosomes were examined. Loaded siRNA efficiencies were shown by gel electrophoresis. The highest siRNA loading efficiency was achieved with 50% amplitude in 6 cycles, and the siRNA loading efficiency was found to be 30-35%.

As a result, it was determined that ultrasonic probe power and loading time were effective on loading efficiency in the siRNA loading strategy into exosomes; however, it was observed that the desired siRNA concentration level did not have a major effect on the efficiency.

Keyword: *exosome, exosome isolation, gene delivery, siRNA*

Stabilization of Antibody Fragments as Biorecognition Molecules on Gold Surfaces: Influenza A Diagnosis as a Model Study

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The design and fabrication of sensitive and selective detection platforms for viral infections remains a critical need in modern diagnostics. In this study, we present model systems for the Influenza A diagnosis, using antibody (Ab) fragments as the biorecognition part, instead of conventional full-length antibodies.

Therefore, only one-step surface modification is possible for the biomolecule stabilization on gold electrode surfaces. This design enables the easy formation of a well-oriented self-assembled monolayer on various Au-surfaces, improving both surface bio functionalization and analytical test performances. Both electrochemical and optical measurements confirmed the high selectivity and sensitivity for Influenza A, highlighting its potential use as robust diagnostic platform.

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Keyword: *Influenza A, Antibody Fragments, Electrochemical Biosensors, Self-Assembled Monolayers*

Synthesis and Use of Functional Carbon-Based Nanoparticles for Various Bio-Applications

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Carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) are highly promising nanomaterials due to their low toxicity, biocompatibility, and unique optical properties, rendering them exceptionally suitable for diverse biomedical applications.

This study investigates the various bio-applications of CNPs synthesized from *Mangifera indica* peels, a non-recyclable agricultural waste rich in phytochemicals and natural antioxidant properties. The resulting fluorescent nanoparticles were characterized by various methods. Strong fluorescence under UV light, which confirmed their promising optical characteristics.

After synthesis, these materials were also investigated in terms of their cell toxicity and imaging features as well as antioxidant properties, were then subjected to in vitro testing to assess their performance as cell imaging nanoproboscopes. Our preliminary data proved their successful use in in vitro cell applications that makes them an advanced diagnostic nanoplatforms.

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Keyword: Carbon nanomaterials, Cell imaging, Probe molecules

A Versatile Aptamer-Based Lateral Flow Assay Platform for Rapid Chikungunya Virus Detection

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In recent years, the development of rapid diagnostic kits and intensive research in this field to control the spread of viral diseases have led to significantly increasing interest in point-of-care tests (POCT), which is now considered one of the most promising diagnostic technologies of the future¹. Among POCT platforms, lateral flow assay (LFA), which is widely used in rapid diagnostic kits, provides various advantages such as easy accessibility, fast results, cost-effectiveness, producing a visible signal, and the ability to perform specific and sensitive detection even from small sample volumes (saliva, urine, nasopharyngeal swab, etc.)².

This study presents the development of an LFA-based diagnostic kit for the detection of Chikungunya virus (CHIKV), which is a mosquito-borne disease that causes joint pains, fever, nausea, and fatigue among those affected. Although CHIKV-related mortality is rare, the virus may cause severe neurological complications, increasing the demand for rapid and reliable detection methods³. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were used in the proposed system as colorimetric labels because of their characteristic dark red color, enabling easily visual detection. As the target recognition element, aptamers were used instead of traditional antibodies. An aptamer is a short, single-stranded synthetic DNA or RNA sequence that offers low production costs, high specificity toward target molecules, and enhanced stability under harsh environmental conditions⁴.

In this study, aptamer-functionalized AuNP-based LFA was demonstrated as an accessible, cost-effective, and user-friendly solution for CHIKV detection. Furthermore, the platform is easily adaptable to various analytes in future rapid test developments highlighting its potential for broader applications in the development of rapid in vitro diagnostic tests.

This work was supported by TUBITAK 2209-B - Industry Oriented Research Project Support Programme for Undergraduate Students.

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Keyword: *Lateral flow assay, Point of care system, Aptamer, Chikungunya virus*

Magnetic Pre-Enrichment and Protein G Assisted Design Strategy for High Sensitivity Lateral Flow Assay in Early Tuberculosis Diagnosis

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Tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the most critical global public health challenges, particularly in developing regions¹. Early detection is essential for effective disease control; however, current detection techniques are often slow, expensive, and dependent on well-resourced laboratory settings-limiting their applicability in rural and resource-constrained environments. The aim of this study was to develop a handheld, low-cost lateral flow assay (LFA) system for the detection of Culture Filtrate Protein-10 (CFP-10), a biomarker for early-stage tuberculosis. The proposed system integrates two innovative strategies to enhance analytical sensitivity: (i) magnetic pre-enrichment with carboxyl-functionalized magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) and (ii) antibody orientation control via Protein G.

In the experimental setup, CFP-10 protein was spiked into synthetic sputum samples to simulate early-phase infection conditions². MNPs were used to selectively capture the target protein, enabling sample enrichment and signal enhancement on the LFA strip. At the test line, protein G improved the efficiency of antigen-antibody binding by controlling the orientation of the antibody via Fc region binding³. LFA strips incorporating Protein G were compared to control strips in terms of signal intensity, specificity, and limit of detection (LOD). The results demonstrated that this LFA platform provided satisfactory analytical performance on synthetic sputum matrixes offering both field applicability and improved sensitivity. Furthermore, this technique has the potential for adaptation to other different protein-based biomarkers, highlighting its versatility in point-of-care diagnostics.

This work is carried out in the context of COST Action CA21164 ADVANCE-TB, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Keyword: *Tuberculosis, Lateral Flow Assay, Pre-Enrichment, Magnetic Nanoparticles*

Electrochemical Detection of Prilocaine Using POSS-TiO₂ Nanomaterial Modification: First Detection at Nanomolar Levels in Real Blood Samples and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms

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Prilocaine is a local anesthetic agent of the amide type, generally used in dentistry, surgery and dermatological procedures. Prilocaine, whose molecular formula is C₁₃H₂₀N₂O, consists of two main components, 2-propylamine and toluidine derivatives, and provides anesthesia by temporarily blocking nerve conduction. However, aromatic amines such as o-toluidine, which are formed during the metabolism of prilocaine, can increase methemoglobinemia, reduce oxygen carrying capacity, and lead to toxic effects at high doses. Therefore, the sensitive detection of prilocaine in biological fluids is of great importance for pharmacokinetic studies, toxicology, and forensic medicine. The detection of prilocaine in biological fluids is a critical requirement, especially for toxicological analyses, verification of pharmaceutical dosage forms, and abuse for doping purposes. Although traditional analysis methods provide high-sensitivity results, they usually use complex sample preparation processes and high-cost devices. At this point, electrochemical analyses stand out due to their advantages, including low cost, fast analysis time, and portability. Electrochemical techniques do not require sample pre-treatment and are environmentally friendly since they work based on the direct oxidation-reduction properties of analyzers. In this study, it was proposed to immobilize POSS-TiO₂ nanomaterial combination on the surface of glassy carbon electrode (GCE) for the detection of Prilocaine. The materials were characterized using various techniques, including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area analysis. TiO₂ nanoparticles increased the electrochemical sensitivity on the GCE surface with their high surface area, chemical stability and strong electron transfer properties. TiO₂ strengthened the interaction between the electrode and the analysis molecule, allowing high-sensitivity detection even at low concentrations. In addition, the semiconductor structure of TiO₂ increased the electrocatalytic activity by supporting fast electron transfer on the electrode surface. These properties offered significant advantages in the detection of pharmaceutical compounds such as Prilocaine. In addition, this study is the first to detect Prilocaine at the nanomolar level in real blood samples and in pharmaceutical dosage forms using adsorptive stripping voltammetry (AdSV). The immobilization of the POSS-TiO₂ combination on GCE provides a highly sensitive method for this detection, highlighting the usability of electrochemical sensors in pharmaceutical analysis, clinical toxicology, and forensic science investigations.

Keyword: Voltammetry, Glassy carbon electrode, Prilocaine, TiO₂ nanoparticles

Design and Development of a Wireless Portable Spectrophotometer Device for Rapid Measurement

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This thesis presents the design and development of a compact, cost-effective, modular, and portable spectrophotometric device tailored for the simultaneous detection and quantification of multiple metabolites associated with metabolic disorders, particularly diabetes mellitus and chronic kidney disease. Although considerable progress has been achieved in point-of-care diagnostic technologies and Lab-on-a-Chip platforms, the sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility of existing analytical methods remain inadequate for reliable clinical deployment. The proposed device leverages optoelectronic technologies to address these limitations by enabling rapid and accurate analysis of eight clinically relevant metabolites: glucose, urea, creatinine, sodium, chloride, calcium, bilirubin, and lactate, using minimal blood volume.

The analytical principle of the device is based on absorption spectroscopy, wherein the wavelength-dependent absorption characteristics of target analytes are measured. Central to the system is the Hamamatsu C12666MA spectral sensor, a CMOS-based linear photodiode array capable of acquiring absorption data across the 340–780 nm spectral range with a resolution of 15 nm. Illumination is provided by an array of high-intensity LEDs with discrete emission peaks at 405 nm, 460 nm, 505 nm, 515 nm, 530 nm, 565 nm, 580 nm, and 610 nm. The optical and electronic components are integrated into a sealed enclosure with dimensions of 40×40×20 cm, ensuring controlled environmental conditions and minimizing ambient light interference. Custom electronic circuitry has been designed and simulated to optimize LED driving and signal acquisition performance.

A bespoke graphical user interface, developed in Python, facilitates real-time data acquisition, calibration, noise reduction, and spectral visualization. Initial validation studies will be conducted using phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solutions spiked with known metabolite concentrations, followed by tests with synthetic blood matrices to emulate physiological conditions. Analytical performance parameters, including accuracy, precision, linearity, detection limit, and interference susceptibility—will be rigorously assessed to establish the system's reliability.

The resulting data will be benchmarked against conventional laboratory reference methods to evaluate clinical compatibility. By integrating miniaturized optoelectronic components with intelligent software, the proposed spectrophotometric system represents a novel diagnostic platform with potential applications in both clinical and home-based monitoring of metabolic disorders. This work was supported by the TÜBİTAK 1004 - Center of Excellence Support Program (Project No 22AG017).

Keyword: *Biosensor, Spectrophotometer, Point of Care Test, Diagnostic Device*

Chitosan-Functionalized Magnetic MIPs for Sensitive and Selective Detection of Ipratropium

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Ipratropium bromide is a quaternary ammonium anticholinergic agent commonly used as a bronchodilator in treating asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Due to its widespread therapeutic use, accurate monitoring of ipratropium levels is essential for dosage control, pharmaceutical quality assurance, and detecting potential drug residues in clinical or environmental samples. However, developing sensitive, selective, and rapid detection methods for ipratropium remains limited¹. In this study, a novel magnetic molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP)-based electrochemical sensor was developed for the selective detection of ipratropium. The sensor platform used manganese ferrite (MnFe_2O_4) nanoparticles as the magnetic core. These nanoparticles were first coated with a silica shell via tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), followed by surface functionalization with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) to introduce amino groups that enhance polymer adhesion. A molecularly imprinted chitosan layer was formed on the surface in the presence of ipratropium as the template molecule, and crosslinking was achieved using glutaraldehyde. After template removal, the resulting $\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4@/\text{SiO}_2\text{-APTES@MIP}$ particles were immobilized onto a screen-printed carbon electrode to fabricate the electrochemical sensor. The sensor's performance was evaluated using differential pulse voltammetry, focusing on parameters such as sensitivity, selectivity, linear range, and limit of detection. This approach successfully combined magnetic separation with biocompatible polymer chemistry, offering a promising tool for the targeted detection of ipratropium in complex matrices.

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Keyword: *Ipratropium detection, Magnetic MIPs, Chitosan-based sensor, Electrochemical sensing*

Portable Plasmonic Biosensor Platform for On-Site Diagnosis of Bacterial Infections Transmitted Sexually

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Sexually transmitted infections (STIs), particularly those caused by *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, continue to present major public health concerns due to their high prevalence and asymptomatic nature (Dalby & Stoner, 2022; Newman et al., 2015). Addressing the need for rapid, cost-effective, and point-of-care (PoC) diagnostics, we present a compact plasmonic biosensor kit designed for the simultaneous detection of *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* directly from urine samples (Cetin, 2023). The platform integrates a label-free plasmonic nanohole array with lens-free computational imaging, enabling detection through analysis of diffraction field images produced by bacterial binding events. In this platform, a microfluidic module integrated with a piezoelectric pump enables precise sample delivery onto a gold-coated nanohole chip functionalized with specific antibodies. The device architecture includes separate sensor regions for *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, along with control zones to minimize biological and optical noise. The imaging module, consisting of simple LED illumination and a CMOS camera, captures spatial intensity variations on the chip surface. A dedicated software suite supports image analysis, test execution, and overall hardware control.

The biosensor demonstrates highly sensitive detection capabilities for *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis*, comparable to or exceeding those of current molecular diagnostic techniques, without the need for complex instrumentation or sample pretreatment. Unlike conventional systems that rely on spectrometric readouts, this imaging-based approach enables simultaneous, high-throughput detection of multiple pathogens. Its lightweight, cost-effective design and elimination of optical labels make it particularly suitable for deployment in resource-limited settings. This presentation demonstrates the potential of our plasmonic platform as a transformative tool in PoC STI diagnostics, bridging the gap between laboratory-grade performance and on-site applicability.

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Keyword: *Plasmonic Biosensor, Label-free Detection, Point-of-Care Diagnostics, Sexually Transmitted Infections*

Fabrication of Label-Free, Highly Sensitive Hybrid Plasmonic Substrates Using Polymer Nanosphere Templates

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The self-assembly of polymer spheres at the air/water interface to form well-ordered structures has been the focus of significant research in recent years due to their simplicity and rapid adaptation to different fields [1]. The ability of the polymer spheres to self-assemble at the air/water interface results in a monolayer polymer sphere template [2]. This template can be easily transferred to the target surfaces to act as a mask, and the polymer spheres themselves can serve various purposes. This method offers a practical, cost-effective, and straightforward approach for masking and patterning on surfaces. The templates obtained with nanospheres also have a significant place in obtaining metallic patterns [3]. The simplicity and efficiency of the method are particularly advantageous in the context of obtaining plasmonic surfaces [4].

The integration of plasmonics and biosensing has precipitated a paradigm shift in domains such as medicine, diagnostics, and environmental monitoring, facilitating label-free sensing with unparalleled precision. In the domain of label-free biosensors, achieving uniform wide-area generation is imperative for ensuring robust detection signals [5]. We propose a hybrid plasmonic substrate by combining antenna and aperture responses through nanosphere lithography. The hybrid plasmonic design fulfills the criteria for an efficient label-free biosensor, including uniform large-scale production, a narrow spectral response, and strong local electromagnetic fields. The integration of antenna and aperture responses in a hybrid plasmonic substrate holds great promise for enhancing the capabilities of label-free biosensors and facilitating the development of sensitive and robust biosensor applications. The convergence of plasmonics and biosensing represents a paradigm shift in medicine, diagnostics, and environmental monitoring, paving the way for label-free sensing with unparalleled precision.

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Keyword: nanofabrication, plasmonics, self-assembly, nanospheres

Smart Near Field Communication (NFC) Nanosensor Empowered by Bi–Sn Core–Shell and Gold Nanoparticles for Ultrasensitive Detection of Cardiac Marker (cTnT)

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Particles formed from gallium-based room-temperature liquid metals, such as eutectic gallium–indium (EGaIn) and Galinstan, have garnered significant attention in biosensor studies due to their tunable surface and electrochemical characteristics^{1,2}. These particles retain high electrical conductivity and fluidic interface characteristics of their parent metals, while acquiring mechanical stability and processability appropriate for sensor fabrication. Liquid metal-derived bismuth tin (BiSn) core-shell particles have recently been recognized as a novel type of liquid metal particles, differentiated by their undercooled metal core and SnO-rich oxide shell and holding great promise in biosensor applications³. In addition, among the various nanomaterials used in biosensor construction, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have emerged as a particularly valuable tool⁴. Due to their unique physicochemical properties, including size-dependent optical behavior, excellent biocompatibility, and ease of functionalization, AuNPs serve as effective components in biosensing platforms. Their pronounced signal amplification capability and adaptability markedly enhance biosensor sensitivity and specificity⁵.

The majority of deaths from cardiovascular disease (CVD) are caused by acute myocardial infarction (AMI), sometimes referred to as a heart attack, which happens when a coronary artery suddenly becomes blocked by thrombus or embolization. Among them, troponin-T (cTnT), troponin-I (cTnI), and C-reactive protein (CRP) are recognized as important indicators⁶.

In recent years, nearfield communication (NFC) technology has become widely used in the field of electrochemical sensors due to its ability to facilitate wireless communication and data transfer at proximity. This technology gives consumers an effective way to collect and evaluate electrochemical data instantly by facilitating seamless data flow between sensors and mobile devices.

In this work, an affinity-based electrochemical biosensor for the detection of the cTnT was developed. The sensor surface was constructed by co-immobilizing BiSn core–shell particles and commercially available AuNPs onto an electrode. This modified surface was subsequently functionalized with cTnT aptamer using mercaptohexanol (MCH) as a linker. The performance of the developed biosensor was evaluated by detecting cTnT in human serum samples using an Android smartphone's data display and a small NFC reader, demonstrating its potential for clinical diagnostics.

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Keyword: BiSn core-shell particles, NFC-based biosensor, Electrochemical Sensor, Cardiac Marker

Multifunctional Peptide Nanofiber Coatings Enhance Bone Regeneration on Xenograft Materials

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Conventional bone graft materials used in dental and maxillofacial surgery often lack sufficient biological activity to promote robust bone regeneration. This study evaluates a **multifunctional peptide amphiphile (PA) nanofiber coating** strategy to enhance graft biofunctionality. PAs incorporating osteoinductive (DGEA), mineralization-promoting (EEE), adhesive (DOPA), and antimicrobial (GL13K) sequences were synthesized and self-assembled into extracellular matrix-mimetic nanofibers. These were used to functionalize **xenograft, allograft, and synthetic hydroxyapatite-based grafts**. In vitro, **human dental pulp stem cells** cultured on PA-functionalized grafts demonstrated significantly improved adhesion, viability, and upregulation of osteogenic markers (RUNX2, COL1A1, OPN). Enhanced alkaline phosphatase activity and mineralization were observed, particularly on PA-coated synthetic and allograft scaffolds. In vivo, in a **rabbit calvarial critical-sized defect model**, PA-coated xenografts and peptide nanofiber-only treatments resulted in significantly greater bone volume fraction, trabecular maturation, and defect integration compared to unmodified controls, as assessed by micro-CT and histology. These findings demonstrate that **bioactive peptide nanofiber coatings** can markedly improve the regenerative performance of clinically available grafts, offering a **minimally invasive, versatile approach** to enhance bone healing in dental and craniofacial applications.

Keyword: *Dental graft, Bone regeneration, Calvarial defect model, Peptide amphiphile*

Development and in vitro Analysis of Immunological Cell-Derived Nano Extracellular Vesicle Added Injectable Hydrogel

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Tissue engineering is a complex system that includes cells, signals, and scaffolds. This system means that cells are cultured in a three-dimensional scaffold that plays the role of ECM for cell growth (Eftekhari et al. 2020). Signals are used for cell growth and differentiation, resulting in greater cellular adhesion. Bones are responsible for providing mechanical support and protecting internal organs. They also form the body skeleton, which stores red and white blood cells and minerals. The completion of restoration of a damaged bone requires mechanical stability and the presence of periosteal cells and inflammatory cells at the defect site (Temenoff and Mikos 2000). The three key factors for bone reconstruction are to trigger calcification by cells and to synthesize the extracellular matrix. Enhanced and co-substituted hydroxyapatite is an alternative option to increase osteoconduction and osteogenesis. Hydrogels are nanoporous, three-dimensional networks that can absorb large amounts of water. Hydrogels are widely used for tissue engineering due to their similar structure to macromolecular-based components in the body (Temenoff and Mikos 2000).

In this study, it was aimed to develop a biodegradable and injectable hydrogel system with nanomaterial additives for use in bone tissue engineering and to evaluate the cellular effects of this system in the osteoimmune microenvironment in vitro. The developed system was prepared by adding biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP) to gelatin-based hydrogels and cross-linking with glutaraldehyde. The hydrogels were characterized by turbidimetric, UV-Vis absorbance, injectability, area scanning, homogeneity and ISO 10993-5 compatible cytotoxicity tests.

Within the scope of the study; extracellular vesicles (EVs) were isolated from M0 and M2 phenotype macrophages derived from THP-1 and U937 cell lines and characterized by dynamic light spectrophotometry (DLS) size analysis, BCA protein determination and polydispersity index analysis; it was determined that M2-derived EVs in particular had higher protein content and more regular distribution. EVs were applied to SAOS-2 osteoblast cells and their osteogenic activities were evaluated by ALP activity, Fluo 4 NW staining after 14 days, and calcification by Alizarin Red staining after 21 days. In addition, SAOS-2 osteoblast cells cultured with combined ceramic, EV-containing hydrogels were stained with Alizarin Red and Von Kossa after 28 days.

It was observed that the combination of EV and BCP increased osteoblastic activity. Especially the BCP-gel structures combined with M2-EV showed an enhancing effect on advanced osteoblastic differentiation. The findings indicated that the potential of these nanomaterial-containing hydrogels to be used minimally invasively is promising in terms of osteogenesis and immune-cell interaction modulation.

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Keyword: *nanomaterial, extracellular vesicle, hydrogel, bone tissue engineering*

Impact of Specific and Nonspecific Protein–Mineral Interactions on the Functional Performance of CaCO₃-Based Host Systems

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Proteins such as enzymes, antibodies, and regulatory biomolecules play essential roles in maintaining biological functions. Accordingly, a wide range of protein-based therapeutics is employed in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of diseases [1]. However, the structural and functional integrity of proteins is highly sensitive to environmental fluctuations, such as changes in temperature, pH, or ionic strength, which can lead to partial or complete loss of activity [2]. This inherent instability significantly limits their practical applications. One promising strategy to address these limitations involves the formation of protein-based biohybrids by integrating proteins with synthetic materials, thereby enhancing their stability and enabling new functionalities. These synthetic components ranging from organic and metal-organic to inorganic materials, can serve as protective matrices or delivery carriers. In particular, calcium carbonate has attracted considerable interest as an inorganic host due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and tunable physicochemical properties. Over the past two decades, calcium carbonate-based systems have been shown to improve the storage stability and therapeutic efficacy of protein drugs [3].

The complex and adaptable structure of calcium carbonate systems makes them useful for various biomedical applications, such as targeted and controlled drug delivery, biosensing, and tissue repair—especially when the role of the mineral host is considered in material design. In this study, protein loading and retention within calcium carbonate matrices are investigated as functions of mineral phase stability, porosity, and protein–mineral binding specificity. To this end, calcium carbonate hosts of either the vaterite or calcite polymorph, featuring hierarchical architectures, are examined. Hierarchical structures are fabricated by inducing the formation of a dense growth layer on spherulitic, porous vaterite seed particles. Protein incorporation is achieved via coprecipitation. Two model proteins are selected: bovine serum albumin (BSA), representing non-specific interactions with the mineral matrix, and fetuin-A, which exhibits specific affinity for calcium ions. Protein loading efficiency is quantified through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and the encapsulation performance is evaluated in relation to the physicochemical properties of the mineral hosts.

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Keyword: *drug delivery, vaterite, Protein–mineral interactions, Biohybrid materials*

Development of Nanocarrier Systems for Multiple Drug Delivery: Effective Brain Cancer Therapy

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Brain cancer remains one of the most challenging malignancies due to the blood-brain barrier and tumor heterogeneity. The objective of this study is to develop multicompartment nanocarrier systems loaded with anticancer agents, curcumin and doxorubicin, to enhance therapeutic efficacy against brain cancer. Nanocarrier systems were formulated using a combination of biocompatible polymers and surfactants to encapsulate both curcumin and doxorubicin simultaneously. The physicochemical properties of the nanocarriers were characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS), atomic force microscopy (AFM), zeta potential, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Entrapment efficiency values were evaluated using UV-vis spectrophotometry for each drug molecule. In vitro assays were conducted to assess the toxicity on fibroblast cell lines as well as the hemolytic activity of the nanocarriers. The developed multicomponent nanocarriers exhibited a uniform size distribution with a narrow polydispersity index, and high encapsulation efficiencies for both curcumin and doxorubicin (~70 for both). Controlled and sustained drug release profiles were observed over 72 hours. In vitro cytotoxicity studies confirmed the lack of toxicity of the samples towards both mice and human cells. Furthermore, it was found that the obtained nanocarriers have no toxicity and are suited for drug delivery applications. The findings of this study indicate that the developed multicomponent nanocarrier systems can effectively co-deliver curcumin and doxorubicin for applications in drug delivery. This approach may offer a promising strategy for future treatments of brain cancer.

Keyword: *brain cancer, nano carriers, controlled release*

Albumin-Hyaluronic Acid Coated Gold Nanorods as Targeted Photothermal Agents for Breast Cancer Therapy

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Gold nanoparticles (AuNRs) have gained prominence in cancer research due to their tunable optical properties, biocompatibility, and ease of synthesis. AuNRs are especially promising for photothermal therapy (PTT), a minimally invasive technique that converts light into heat to selectively kill cancer cells. AuNRs exhibit strong absorption in the near-infrared (NIR) region, allowing deep tissue penetration and localized heating. A common synthesis method for AuNRs uses cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as surfactant, which ensures shape control and stability but poses significant toxicity risks [1]. Various strategies have been explored to replace or coat CTAB to improve biocompatibility. One promising approach, recently developed by Zengin et al., involves a biopolymer coating that enhances stability and reduces toxicity [2]. Building on this, we have adapted the method using a conjugate of bovine serum albumin (BSA) [3] and hyaluronic acid (HA) to create a more targeted and biocompatible AuNR platform. BSA serves as a stabilizer, while HA targets CD44 receptors, which are overexpressed in many cancer types, including breast cancer. This dual-function coating aims to improve both colloidal stability and tumor-specific targeting, offering a safer and more effective alternative for PTT.

BSA-HA conjugate formation was induced via the Maillard reaction. Conjugates were prepared using various BSA-to-HA weight ratios and with different incubation times. They were then analyzed by sodium dodecyl-sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and the optimal parameters were selected accordingly. Subsequently, AuNRs were synthesized by the seed-mediated growth method and characterized by UV-visible absorption spectroscopy. Surface modification of AuNRs with BSA-HA conjugates was achieved successfully, indicated by zeta potential and the scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) images. Thus far, this study presents a promising PTT agent offering targeted delivery, enhanced biocompatibility, and therapeutic efficiency for potential application in breast cancer treatment.

Acknowledgements:

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Keyword: *photothermal therapy, nanotechnology, biomaterial, gold nanorods*

Scaffold Optimization of PBAT Nanofibers for Cardiac Patch Development: From Electrospinning to Cell Response

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Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds offer a biomimetic platform for soft tissue engineering applications. In this study, poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) nanofibrous matrices were fabricated under optimized electrospinning conditions using response surface methodology (RSM) to produce both random and highly aligned fiber topographies. The nanofibers were deposited onto solvent-casted PBAT and polycaprolactone (PCL) membranes to construct two-layered composite patches for cardiac tissue regeneration.

The influence of electrospinning parameters—including polymer concentration, flow rate, voltage, and tip-to-collector distance—on fiber diameter and alignment was systematically evaluated. Aligned nanofibers exhibited an average diameter of 417 ± 137 nm with 91% alignment within $\pm 10^\circ$, confirming successful process optimization. Mechanical testing revealed a two-fold increase in elastic modulus and ultimate tensile strength in aligned constructs compared to those in a random configuration. Surface roughness and fiber-membrane interactions varied depending on the membrane type, influencing fiber morphology and attachment.

Cytocompatibility was assessed using H9C2 cardiomyoblasts. MTT and SEM analyses demonstrated superior cell adhesion, proliferation, and surface coverage on aligned PBAT/PBAT patches, attributed to their enhanced topographical and mechanical properties. PCL membranes negatively affected fiber alignment and cellular response due to higher surface roughness and hydrophobicity.

The aim of this study was to develop an optimized, membrane-supported, nanofibrous PBAT-based scaffold that mimics the aligned anisotropic architecture of native cardiac tissue without relying on additional chemical modifications or bioactive agents.

This work contributes to the field of cardiac tissue engineering by presenting a biodegradable, mechanically tunable, and cytocompatible scaffold design that offers improved alignment, integration, and potential for applications.

This study was financially supported by Hacettepe University Research Fund (Project Number FDK–2020–18721).

Keyword: *PBAT nanofibers, Response surface methodology, H9C2 cells*

Effect Of Alloying Elements On Alkali And Heat Treatment Effectiveness In Conventional And Novel High-Entropy Titanium Alloys

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Titanium (Ti) and its alloys stand out among the metallic biomaterials due to their high specific strength, good corrosion resistance, and relatively similar mechanical properties to the bone tissue. Therefore, they are the best candidate for load-bearing implant applications. Nevertheless, their osseointegration ability needs to be enhanced, which is the direct structural and functional bonding between the implant material and the bone tissue. This can be achieved solely through surface modification techniques, without altering the bulk properties. Alkali and heat-treatment combinations are a simple and effective technique for enhancing the osseointegration of Ti and its alloys. Numerous studies have been published on alkali and heat-treatment of various Ti alloy systems. However, limited studies exist investigating the effect of alloying elements in this method. Within this scope, surface characteristics of alkali and heat-treated conventional and novel high-entropy Ti alloys were compared for the first time.

Alkali treatment (2M NaOH, 37 °C, 1 week) followed by heat treatment (600 °C, 1 hour) were applied to commercially pure titanium (CP-Ti), Ti-6Al-4V, Ti-6Al-7Nb, and high entropy TiTaHfNbZr alloy. Surface roughness was increased for all specimens after alkali and heat treatments, with the most prominent increase on TiTaHfNbZr alloy. This increase is attributed to loss of integrity in the alloy during heat treatment. Surface free energy and wettability were also increased for the alloys; however, a slight decrease was observed for the CP-Ti. EDX and XRD analyses confirmed that a sodium titanate ($\text{Na}_{0.99}\text{TiO}_2$) layer formed on the titanium surfaces following alkali and heat treatments. This layer was more evident on Ti-6Al-4V, while its formation was limited on Ti-6Al-7Nb and TiTaHfNbZr alloy surfaces. This limitation resulted from the niobium, zirconium, and hafnium oxides present on the alloy's surfaces, which hinder ionic exchange in the alkali environment. These results suggest that alloying elements significantly influence the effectiveness of the alkali treatment chemically and also physically by affecting the surface topography at the micro and nano level. The newly formed micro/nanoscale surface structures are expected to promote bioactivity.

Keyword: *Titanium alloys, high entropy alloys, alkali and heat treatment, sodium titanate*

Development of Smart Bioplastics Integrated with Multifunctional Nanomaterials

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The environmental and health implications of plastics have become a significant concern, as they are extensively used due to their durability, lightweight nature, and low production cost. Plastics' non-biodegradable nature and improper disposal lead to their long-term accumulation in ecosystems, particularly in oceans, posing a threat to wildlife through entanglement and ingestion.

The present study aimed to develop multifunctional bioplastics that are biodegradable, antibacterial, UV-resistant, and magnetically responsive by integrating the disciplines of biotechnology and nanotechnology. The bioplastic matrix was formulated using gelatin and pectin as base polymers, plasticized with glycerol and acetic acid to improve flexibility, mechanical strength, and chemical durability. These natural polymers were reinforced with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), zinc oxide (ZnO), titanium dioxide (TiO₂), and iron oxide (Fe₃O₄) synthesized via both chemical, co-precipitation [1], sol-gel method [2], and green synthesis techniques [3,4]. In particular, AgNPs were produced using hazelnut shell extract as a natural, eco-friendly reducing agent, enhancing the sustainability aspect of the material. Nanoparticles were incorporated into the polymer matrix using the ultrasonic dispersion and solvent casting method [5] to ensure homogeneous distribution. The final composite materials underwent extensive characterization using various techniques, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM), and UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-VIS). The mechanical, thermal, and antibacterial properties of the bioplastics were assessed through standardized analytical tests.

The integration of ZnO and TiO₂ not only improved UV resistance but also introduced photocatalytic activity, enabling the material to self-clean by breaking down organic pollutants on its surface. The AgNP-modified bioplastics exhibited enhanced antimicrobial activity, while Fe₃O₄ provided magnetic responsiveness for potential innovative applications. The bioplastics developed in this study outperform traditional bioplastics in terms of durability, functionality, and versatility, offering a safer and more hygienic alternative for industries such as food packaging and medical devices. These findings indicate a promising approach that opens pathways for future innovation by demonstrating the feasibility of combining natural polymers with multifunctional nanoparticles to create high-performance, smart bioplastics suitable for a wide range of applications.

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Keyword: *Bioplastics, Biomaterials, Biopolymers, Nanoparticles*

Evaluation of Artificial Intelligence Data for Formulation Development Studies

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Artificial intelligence (AI) has become one of the leading technologies that have transformed many processes, from scientific research to industrial applications, healthcare to education and production processes in recent years (1). With increased data processing capacity, advances in computing power, and the proliferation of big data sources, AI systems offer tools that optimize decision-making processes, have high predictive power, and increase efficiency (2).

Today, the pharmaceutical industry searches for more efficient and systematic drug discovery and development methods. The increasing number of low-solubility drugs is a major challenge, especially for oral formulation development. Current traditional pharmaceutical formulation development studies are largely based on trial-error study data, and this approach is time-consuming and costly. Therefore, it is extremely necessary to integrate developing technology and artificial intelligence applications into the pharmaceutical industry's progress and to develop innovative and efficient methods for formulation development.

In this study, self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) were constructed, which are frequently preferred for active substances with solubility problems, by **FormulationAI**. **FormulationAI** is a comprehensive web-based platform for in silico formulation design (3). **FormulationAI** keeps the most comprehensive data and artificial intelligence models up-to-date with accurate predictions and an easy-to-use interface. SEDD systems contain a dataset of 4495 formulation samples, including 15 types of oil, 10 types of surfactants, and 11 co-surfactants (3). It estimates the availability of the formulation under certain conditions.

SEDDSs, lipid-based systems, are stable thermodynamic drug delivery systems consisting of oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant that increase the solubility of active substances (4). The physicochemical properties of SEDDS are sensitive to various factors depending on their components (5). For the accuracy of the drug delivery system, parameters such as droplet size (DS), polydispersity index (PDI), hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB), self-emulsification time, and dispersibility must be optimum.

For systems created with **FormulationAI**, experimental studies investigated the parameters characterizing the system. The studies showed that as the SEDDS status is positive and the self-emulsification status approaches 1 (between 0 and 1), the characterization results are closer to the optimum (droplet size < 100 nm, PDI < 0.2, self-emulsification time < 2 min, HLB value approximately 13, dispersibility Grade A, self-emulsification area is larger). **FormulationAI** verifies the formulation consistency for the SEDD system, while the characterization studies have shown the program's data accuracy regarding formulation formation.

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Keyword: *Artificial intelligence, FormulationAI, formulation development*

Predictive Modeling for Controlling the Aspect Ratio of Silver Nanowires

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Silver nanowire (AgNW) networks exhibit high optical transmittance and low sheet resistance, making them suitable for smart windows, photovoltaics, electrochromic devices, and triboelectric nanogenerators. A key factor influencing their performance is the aspect ratio (length-to-diameter ratio), which directly affects the conductivity and efficiency of these networks. Although the polyol method is commonly employed for AgNW synthesis, precise control over the nanowire aspect ratio remains a significant challenge. This is due to the complex interplay of multiple synthesis parameters, including precursor type and concentration, reaction temperature, and reaction time. Conventional trial-and-error techniques often lack scalability and are inefficient in capturing these interdependencies. In this study, a data-driven approach was adopted to elucidate the relationships between synthesis conditions and the resulting aspect ratios of AgNWs. Machine learning (ML) techniques were applied to datasets compiled from high-impact, peer-reviewed publications to develop predictive models for aspect ratio. The models effectively captured the complex nature of the synthesis process, achieving predictive accuracy within the bounds of experimental variability. Furthermore, the analysis enabled the identification of optimal synthesis parameters that led to a fivefold increase in aspect ratio, underscoring the power of data-driven methods in enhancing synthesis outcomes. This research demonstrates how material informatics and predictive modeling enable process optimization and rational design of AgNWs for advanced electronic and photonic devices.

Keyword: *silver nanowires, polyol method, material informatics, machine learning*

Modeling Catalytic Pyrolysis of Methane on Ni(111) Surface Using a Reactive Neural Network Potential Approach

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Hydrogen production from methane is an important topic for the world as we aim for net-zero carbon emissions in the near future. A promising method of hydrogen production is catalytic methane pyrolysis[1]. Catalysts suitable for this process are required to make production feasible on a large scale, and the search for such catalysts is still ongoing. Molecular Dynamics (MD) is an effective computational tool for determining the most efficient catalysts and studying the reaction mechanisms. Although ab initio Molecular Dynamics (AIMD) methods offer good precision by incorporating quantum mechanical effects into the energy and force calculations, their scope is limited by high computational costs. Other methods, such as Reactive Force Fields (ReaxFF) [2], demand lower computational resources, but need to be parametrized in a system-specific manner requiring labor-intensive optimization. The rapidly advancing field of Machine Learning (ML) has enabled new approaches to reduce the computational demand of MD simulations while preserving the accuracy, such as Neural Network Potentials (NNPs). NNPs are developed with minimal manual intervention by training neural networks using a reliable dataset that contains atomic coordinates, forces, and energies in order to predict the forces and energies for given atomic coordinates.

The goal of our research is to develop a ready-to-use reactive NNP for methane pyrolysis on a Ni(111) surface. We have developed our dataset with a combination of data generated by AIMD and Metadynamics (MTD), covering temperatures from 300 K to 3000 K. While AIMD constructed the base of the dataset, MTD helped us sample rarely visited regions of the configuration space. We then tweaked and fine-tuned the state-of-the-art PaiNN model [3], and trained it on our dataset. At the later stages of our research, we plan to calculate reaction rates, radial distribution functions, and several other materials properties of Ni for the temperature range mentioned above. An analysis of the time and energy costs of the simulations will also be conducted.

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Keyword: *Molecular Dynamics, Heterogeneous Catalyst, Machine Learning, Neural Network Potentials*

AI-Driven Analysis of Organic Dye Adsorption and Synergistic Piezo-Photocatalytic Degradation Using MXene/MOF Nanocomposite

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In this study, we present a predominantly AI-driven analysis of Acid Red 88 (AR88) removal by a Ti₃C₂T_x MXene/ZIF-8 nanocomposite. The ZIF-8 and nanocomposite material were synthesised as in previous works [1-2], yielding a composite with a surface area of 1232 m².g⁻¹, a bandgap of 3.56 eV, and efficient charge separation (confirmed via BET, UV-Vis DRS, PL, XRD, and FTIR). Experimental tests demonstrated that AR88 adsorption followed pseudo-second-order kinetics and Langmuir isotherms, with standalone piezocatalysis and photocatalysis achieving ~96.3% and 96.6% degradation, respectively, within 60 minutes, and combined piezo-photocatalysis reaching 98.6% degradation.

Based on these results, we constructed a dataset of 82 observations with eight inputs involving initial dye concentration, solution pH, temperature, reaction time, and catalytic mode (dark, visible-light, piezocatalysis, photocatalysis, piezo-photocatalysis), and one numeric response (removal efficiency). We divide the data into training (80 %) and testing (20 %) subsets and apply 5-fold cross-validation on the training set for robust model development. Two ensemble algorithms, Random Forest and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), were implemented as in the literature [3] and extensively optimised. The Random Forest model was tuned by setting 500 trees, a node size of 1, and selecting the optimal mtry value near $\sqrt{8}$. For XGBoost, we optimised key parameters using grid search, including tree depth, learning rate, number of rounds, and sampling ratios.

On the held-out test set, the optimised Random Forest model achieved RMSE = 4.38 % and R² = 0.86, while XGBoost outperformed it with RMSE = 2.85 % and R² = 0.93. This study combines the synthesis and dye removal testing of a nanocomposite with a detailed machine learning workflow. The workflow includes dataset preparation, feature selection, model training, hyperparameter tuning, and model interpretation, forming a robust data-driven framework for designing and optimising advanced piezo-photocatalysts for sustainable wastewater treatment.

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Keyword: *Dye Removal, Machine Learning, MXene/MOF composite, Supervised Learning*

Accelerated Carbon Crystal Discovery with Generative AI

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Designing stable and realistic crystal structures remains a central challenge in materials science. This involves placing atoms not only in low-energy configurations but also in ways that satisfy chemical bonding preferences. In this work, we propose a generative model based on a variational autoencoder (VAE), trained on the Carbon-24 dataset, to generate novel carbon-based crystal structures. The model learns structural patterns from known materials and uses this knowledge to create diverse and physically plausible candidates. To further refine the generated structures before performing expensive DFT calculations, we use graph neural network models such as CHGNet, M3GNet, and Mattersim to relax atomic positions and predict their energies. In particular, CHGNet will be fine-tuned using the Carbon-24 dataset to better capture the energy landscape of carbon-rich materials. By combining deep generative models with fast graph-based relaxation, this approach aims to accelerate the discovery of stable and experimentally relevant crystal structures.

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Keyword: Carbon, machine learning, DFT

Electrochromism of Potentiostatically Electrodeposited WO₃ Thin Films

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Materials that are able to change their optical properties (transmission, reflection, and/or absorption), reversibly and persistently, as a response to an external electrical voltage are referred to as “electrochromic” [1]. WO₃ has wide interest in today’s smart windows technology for energy-efficient architecture due to high electrochromic efficiency and durability with large interstitial space volumes and fast ion diffusion pathways [2]. The coloration/bleaching process of amorphous WO₃ can occur upon electrochemical intercalation/deintercalation of cations and charge-balancing electrons into the conduction band through an outer circuit:

where M κ ⁺ is an ion of valency κ , e⁻ is the charge-compensating electron and x κ is the intercalation level for charge [3]. Simultaneous injection of an electron and of a charge-compensating cation cause a polaron absorption or a free carrier absorption. During coloration process, inserted ions break up the W-O bonds and then chemically bond with the lattice oxygens. The electrochromic performance of WO₃ strongly depend on the valency and the radius of intercalated ions [3]. For practical EC devices, monovalent species (typically light alkaline metallic ions, such as H⁺, Li⁺, Na⁺ or K⁺) with small ionic radius are preferred due to causing high charge density and in order to allow facile transport [3,4]. Especially, H⁺ and Li⁺ have the advantage of high ionic conductivity. Larger cation sizes cause the slow intercalation/de-intercalation kinetics [5].

Here, the WO₃ thin films were deposited by potentiostatically electrodeposition using Na₂WO₄·2H₂O with deionized water, H₂O₂ and HClO₄ electrolyte solution at -0.7 V versus Ag/AgCl. This study compared the electrochromic performance of WO₃ thin films deposited by in Li⁺ and H⁺ ions-based electrolytes. The bleached and colored transmission measurements were carried out after 50th CV and the change in charge density and coloration efficiency of the films were calculated depending on the number of cycles. Additionally, optical (UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer), morphological (SEM, EDX), and Mott-Schottky measurements were performed for the characterization the WO₃ films.

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Keyword: electrochromism, thin film, ion intercalation, WO₃

Synthesis, Characterization and Investigation of DNA Interactions of Hybrid Copper-Nanoflowers

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The quest for new substances has become imperative due to the impact of advancing technologies. Nanotechnology is primarily defined as the scientific discipline that investigates the synthesis of nanomaterials with dimensions between 1 and 100 nm, which exhibit distinct properties due to the manipulation of atoms and molecules, along with their applications¹. Nanoflowers are a kind of nanoparticles with enhanced capabilities that structurally resemble floral formations. The synthesis of nanoflowers involves the utilisation of biological materials as the organic component and metal ions as the inorganic component, resulting in "hybrid nanoflowers." The term hybrid denotes a material composed of organic and inorganic components that do not exist independently, yet exhibit novel features through synergistic interactions when combined. Owing to their surface and chemical interactions, these structures can occupy a more beneficial position across various fields, including medicine and engineering².

This study utilised seeds of Sorghum bicolor var. technicum (Körn) Stapf ex Holland as organic material. Nanoflowers were characterised using Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), thereby confirming their production. The interactions of nanoflowers with DNA were analysed to investigate their biological activities. The interactions between nanoflowers and DNA were examined through DNA binding with Calf-Thymus DNA and by assessing hydrolytic and oxidative DNA cleavage activities utilising pBR322 plasmid DNA. The results indicated that nanoflowers induced denaturation of pBR322 DNA.

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Keyword: Hybrid Copper-Nanoflowers, DNA Interactions, Sorghum bicolor var. technicum, Green Synthesis

Fabrication of Graphene Fiber Nonwoven Fabric Using a Wet-Fusing Strategy

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Graphene fiber fabrics are macroscopic graphene structures that exhibit excellent electrical conductivity, low density, high flexibility, and ease of functionalization [1-2]. The unique properties of graphene fiber fabrics make them good candidates for next-generation applications such as wearable smart textiles and flexible electronic devices [3-4]. Therefore, the straightforward fabrication of mechanically robust and flexible graphene fiber fabrics is of significant importance. The present study aims to fabricate nonwoven graphene fiber fabrics with good mechanical and electrical performance using a wet-fusing strategy and to evaluate the influence of the reduction step on the resulting properties. For this purpose, short fibers were generated from a 13 mg/mL aqueous graphene oxide dispersion via the wet-spinning method in a 2-propanol/ethyl acetate coagulation bath. The coagulated short fibers were collected by vacuum filtration and subsequently dried at 60 °C to produce graphene oxide fiber fabrics. The dried graphene oxide fiber fabrics were reduced to nonwoven graphene fiber fabrics using two different reducing agents: hydrazine monohydrate and hydroiodic acid. The fabricated nonwoven fabrics were characterized by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Furthermore, mechanical tests and electrical conductivity measurements of the graphene fiber fabrics were performed. Mechanical test results showed that the graphene fiber fabrics obtained using both reduction methods have high elongation. However, the graphene fiber fabrics reduced by hydroiodic acid are much stronger than those reduced with hydrazine monohydrate due to their much denser fiber structures. Notably, the electrical conductivity of the fabrics reduced with hydroiodic acid was approximately nine times higher than that of the hydrazine-reduced counterparts.

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Keyword: Graphene Fiber, Graphene Oxide, Graphene Fiber Fabric

Investigation of Valleytronic Properties of Infrared Interlayer Excitons in MoS₂/WSe₂ Van der Waals Heterostructures

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Van der Waals heterostructures based on transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) offer a tunable platform for investigating interfacial excitonic phenomena at the atomic scale. In particular, MoS₂/WSe₂ heterobilayers exhibit type-II band alignment, enabling the formation of interlayer excitons—electron-hole pairs spatially separated across adjacent monolayers. These excitons are characterized by near infrared emission, extended lifetimes, strong out-of-plane dipole moments, and valley-specific optical transitions.

One of the key motivations for studying this material system is that interlayer exciton emission appears near the O-band telecommunications range (~1260–1360 nm) and is spectrally tunable via external parameters such as electrostatic gating or interlayer alignment. This makes MoS₂/WSe₂ heterostructures highly relevant for the development of integrated optoelectronic and quantum photonic devices operating in telecom-compatible wavelengths.

In this work, we investigate the valleytronic properties of MoS₂/WSe₂ heterostructures with a focus on understanding how the moiré potential, introduced by lattice mismatch and rotational misalignment, affects exciton behavior. In particular, we explore the role of spatial trapping in shaping the excitonic landscape. Photoluminescence measurements under varied experimental conditions provide insights into interlayer coupling, recombination mechanisms, and the influence of structural parameters on optical performance.

Our findings contribute to the fundamental understanding of excitonic interactions in 2D layered materials and support the rational design of TMDC heterostructures for next-generation optoelectronic, valleytronic, and light-emitting technologies.

Keyword: *Tmdc, Heterostructure, Valleytronic, Exciton*

Water-Based and Biodegradable MXene–Alginate Systems for Transient Energy Storage: From Rheological Characteristics and Solid-State Electrolyte Optimization to Device Architecture

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This study presents a fully water-processable, biodegradable MXene–sodium alginate (SA) system tailored for transient and green electronics. MXenes, a family of two-dimensional transition metal carbides, offer high conductivity and charge storage capabilities, while SA is a naturally abundant, biocompatible polysaccharide derived from seaweed, known for its water solubility and gel-forming ability. The MXene–SA composite offers a safe and biodegradable materials platform by eliminating harmful solvents and additives. The formulation's rheological properties were systematically optimized by adjusting the solid content and MXene-to-SA ratio, achieving desirable viscosity and viscoelasticity for uniform film formation, electrical conductivity and mechanical stability. In the resulting symmetric capacitor architecture, both self-standing MXene films and MXene–SA composite structures were employed as electrode materials, while a Zn²⁺-crosslinked SA gel served as the solid polymer electrolyte (SPE). Zinc ions were selected for their low toxicity and ability to facilitate ionic transport within the gel matrix. The optimized device exhibited a specific capacitance of 40.6 F/g at 1 A/g and retained 91% of its capacity after 6000 cycles, demonstrating robust electrochemical performance. This work illustrates the integration of rheological tuning and electrolyte engineering to realize high-performance, biodegradable energy storage devices using water-based MXene–biopolymer composites.

Keyword: *mxene, energy storage, solid-state electrolyte*

Development of MEMS Gas Sensors Based on Fe-Doped Graphene and Graphene Derivatives

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Toxic gases found in mines, hospitals, laboratories, and spoiled food pose serious health and environmental risks, making their sensitive and reliable detection essential. This study investigates iron-doped graphene and its derivatives as gas sensors owing to their high surface area, conductivity, and strong gas interactions for detecting key toxic gases like ammonia (NH₃), ethanol (C₂H₅OH), and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) using Density Functional Theory (DFT) to help prevent potential hazards. All calculations performed using VASP in accordance with DFT principles. 4x4x1 supercell pure graphene (PG), single (SVG) and double vacancy (DVG) defective graphene and their graphene oxide structures (PGO, SVGGO, DVGO) were created and optimized, and the adsorption energies of the desired gases were calculated by doping iron (Fe) atoms on the surface of these structures. The adsorption energies of NH₃, C₂H₅OH, and H₂S on iron-doped graphene surfaces were calculated as follows: PGO-Fe (-1.69, -1.39, -3.25 eV), SVGGO-Fe (-1.32, -1.04, -0.98 eV), and DVGO-Fe (-0.80, -0.45, -1.18 eV), respectively. According to the obtained results, the electronic properties of these gases (PDOS electron state density, Bader charges, electron charge density differences) and selectivity were analyzed in detail. Compared to traditional sensors, MEMS-based gas sensors, offering low power consumption and fast response, are crucial for toxic gas detection. Therefore, this study focused on hybrid electrodes made with graphene and conductive polymers via microfabrication. Since the interactions of graphene with the desired gases will cause changes in its electrical properties, it will provide information about the type and concentration of the gas, especially with the effect of basic parameters such as resistance change. Based on the simulation results, the best performing surface designs will be subjected to experiments in the prepared test setup to evaluate the detection, selectivity and sensitivity of gases. In the light of the findings, this study aims to design and develop innovative gas sensors that enhance the detection performance of toxic gases, contributing to scientific and technological advancements in sensor technology. The results will contribute to the literature and offer practical benefits for industry.

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Keyword: MEMS sensor, Graphene, 2D Materials, DFT

Scalable Synthesis of Bulk and 2D TiS₂ for Energy Storage

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Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) are promising materials for energy-related applications due to their layered structures and electronic properties. In this study, a scalable synthesis route for bulk titanium disulfide (TiS₂) is developed using a solid-state reaction in sealed quartz tubes within a custom-designed furnace, achieving a batch production capacity of 50 grams in 18 hours. The obtained powders crystallized directly in the 1T phase. Exfoliation via organolithium treatment enabled the production of two-dimensional 1T-TiS₂ nanosheets with a yield of approximately 3 grams per batch. This approach provides an efficient pathway for producing both bulk and few-layer metallic TiS₂, which are particularly attractive for lithium-sulfur battery cathodes due to their high conductivity and polysulfide-trapping capabilities. Specific capacities reached up to 900 mAh/gS, indicating the effective utilization of TiS₂ in energy storage applications.

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Keyword: 2D Materials, Titanium Disulfide, Li-S Batteries, Energy Storage

Enhanced Electrochromic Properties of Ultrasonically Spray-Coated 2D TiO₂ for High Performance Electrochromic Devices

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Transition metal oxides with tunable optical properties are key materials for next-generation electrochromic devices (ECD). In this work, we present a new approach to fabricate 2D titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanosheet films for ECD applications via ultrasonic spray coating, a scalable and low-temperature deposition method. The TiO₂ nanostructures, fabricated through a hydrothermal route, are uniformly deposited onto indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass substrates, forming highly transparent and crack-free films with a well-defined 2D morphology. For the device fabrication, the 2D TiO₂ is used as the electrochromic cathode which is combined with a complementary NiO anodic layer. A gel polymer electrolyte composed of lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄) dissolved in propylene carbonate (PC) and solidified with PMMA is used as the electrolyte. This configuration enables efficient lithium-ion transport and enhances the overall mechanical stability of the device. The assembled electrochromic device shows a strong and reversible optical modulation between a transparent and blue state, with a sufficient transmittance change of around 30% at 650 nm and the device maintains over 74% of its initial optical contrast after 500 cycles. These results highlight the potential of combining 2D TiO₂ morphology with ultrasonic spray coating and a gel electrolyte to enable durable, fast-switching, and efficient electrochromic performance.

Keyword: 2D Materials, Electrochromic devices

DFT Investigation of H₂S Removal by Doped ZSM-5

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Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is generally generated from petroleum refining, natural gas processing, and coal gasification and the removal of H₂S from gas streams is crucial since it is a corrosive and highly toxic chemical. Zeolites have been extensively used to remove H₂S from the gas streams [1,2]. Metal oxide doped sorbents improve H₂S removal process [3]. This DFT study aims to compare the removal of H₂S via metal-oxide and mixed metal-oxide supported ZSM-5 clusters with high Si/Al ratio. The method employed in this study is wB97XD functional with LanL2DZ and 6-31 G(d,p) basis sets. Iron oxide was model as addition of Fe-O-Fe on the framework of ZSM-5 10-ring. Mixed metal oxide was model as replacing one of the iron atoms with manganese atom in form of Fe-O-Mn. Results showed that physisorption is possible on both structures with negative Gibbs Free Energy change and more favourable on the mixed oxide/zeolite structure (Fe-O-Mn/ZSM-5). However, chemisorption is more favorable on the iron oxide/zeolite structure with a lower energy barrier to break S-H bond. Energy barrier to break S-H bond on Fe-O-Fe/ZSM-5 and Fe-O-Mn/ZSM-5 clusters were found to be 4.31 kcal/mol and 6.43 kcal/mol, respectively. Complete conversion of H₂S to H₂ and elemental sulfur is suggested for better comparison.

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Keyword: *Hydrogen sulfide, Zeolite, ZSM-5, DFT*

Synthetic Approaches Toward Chlorophyll a and b in Artificial Photosynthesis

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Artificial photosynthesis is an emerging field aiming to convert solar energy into chemical fuels through biomimetic systems. A key challenge in this process is the development of effective light-harvesting units that mimic the spectral and functional properties of natural pigments. **Chlorophyll a and b**, the primary photoreceptors in natural photosynthesis, exhibit strong absorption in the visible spectrum and play a crucial role in solar energy capture and transfer. Therefore, their **synthetic analogues** are of great interest for designing efficient artificial photosynthetic systems. This study focuses on the **structural and photophysical properties of chlorophyll a and b**, and reviews the current methodologies used in their **biomimetic and total synthetic production**.

In conclusion, this work aims to provide a comprehensive overview of synthetic strategies for chlorophyll-based light-harvesting systems, offering insight into the rational design of next-generation pigments that combine **natural efficiency with enhanced chemical robustness** for artificial photosynthesis applications.

Keyword: *Artificial photosynthesis*

Synthesis, Characterization, and Thermal Analysis of Nano-Sized Oligomers Derived from Ampyrone and Vanillin

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In this study, the synthesis processes of nano-sized-oligomers containing hetero aromatic ampyrone and natural compound vanillin are discussed in detail. In addition, the focus is on the structural properties and thermal behavior of the synthesized nano-sized-oligomers. The findings were evaluated in terms of chemical characterization and thermal stability of the materials. An azo (AVAZ) compound was synthesized through a condensation reaction between ampyrone and vanillin. Two nano-sized oligomers, NSO-1 and NSO-2, of varying durations and sizes were produced by catalyzing the oxidation of this azo compound using hydrogen peroxide in the presence of horseradish peroxidase (HRP). The structures of the AVAZ compound and its nano-sized oligomers, NSO-1 and NSO-2, were analyzed using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR), UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis), and Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy ($^1\text{H-NMR}$). The molecular weights of the NSO-1 and NSO-2 nano-sized-oligomers were measured by Gel Permeability Chromatography. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to assess surface properties, and Thermogravimetric Analysis-Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA-DTA) was employed to determine thermal characteristics. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-DTA) indicated that the onset temperatures (T_{on}) were determined to be 245°C for AVAZ, 168°C for NSO-1, and 187°C for NSO-2. The residual mass at 1000°C was measured as 0% for AVAZ, 11.6% for NSO-1, and 25.4% for NSO-2.

Zeolite 13X: Surface Structure Effects On Small Organic Molecules Adsorption

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Zeolites are crystalline aluminosilicates with a nanoporous structure. They possess a high specific surface area and a regular system of channels and cavities. Due to these properties, zeolites are widely used as adsorbents, ion exchangers, and catalysts. Of particular interest are 13X-type zeolites, which are characterized by large pores and high adsorption capacity. Its pore diameter is 13 Å, while the diameter of the pore windows is 7.4 Å.

Study of adsorption thermal effects, specific surface area, and porous characteristics of zeolites is crucial for understanding the interaction mechanisms between the adsorbent and adsorbate molecules. The heat of adsorption reflects the interaction strength between the sorbate molecules and the active sites of the zeolite, and provides insight into the efficiency and selectivity of the adsorption process. Therefore, studying the adsorption characteristics of zeolites is a topical scientific challenge.

The novelty of the present study lies in examining the adsorption properties of a series of small organic molecules on zeolite 13X: dichloromethane, trichloromethane, tetrachloromethane, toluene, benzene, cyclohexane, pentane, hexane, and heptane, followed by analysis of the observed adsorption patterns.

Initially, the surface structure and elemental composition of the zeolite 13X sample were studied. From the nitrogen adsorption isotherm, the specific surface area was determined as 627 ± 19 m²/g and the pore volume as 0.271 ± 0.008 cm³/g. The asymmetry of the adsorption isotherm indicates the presence of pores of different sizes in the zeolite, which was attributed to the presence of different exchangeable cations within the framework. This was confirmed by X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF), revealing partial ion exchange of sodium ions by calcium ions.

Molecular dimensions of several chloromethanes were calculated, allowing the prediction of their retention behavior on zeolite 13X. A correlation was observed between the calculated molecular sizes and their experimentally measured adsorption.

The dependence of heat of adsorption on zeolite 13X on the nature of the organic sorbates (size, structure, polarizability, and dipole moment) was demonstrated.

Experimental heats of adsorption of the sorbates were compared with their heats of vaporization; the positive difference of the two values indicated energetically favorable interactions between the sorbates and the zeolite.

Energetic heterogeneity of the zeolite 13X surface was established based on the dependence of the heat of adsorption of dichloromethane on sorbate loading. The heat of adsorption increased as the loading decreased.

The contributions of dipole-dipole and dispersion interactions to the overall heat of adsorption were assessed.

Keyword: *Zeolite 13X, Adsorption, Adsorption heat*

Enhanced Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Removal via Crosslinked Electrospun PolyCyclodextrin/PolyBenzoxazine Fibrous Membrane

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Water pollution, driven by urbanization and industrialization, has led to the proliferation of persistent organic pollutants like polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), which are carcinogenic, mutagenic, and bioaccumulative [1]. Due to their chemical stability and low biodegradability, PAHs persist in aquatic environments and pose serious health and ecological risks [2]. Thus, the development of cost-effective, high-performance adsorbent materials is essential for their remediation.

Cyclodextrins (CDs), cyclic oligosaccharides with hydrophobic inner cavities and hydrophilic outer surfaces, are excellent candidates for environmental remediation due to their natural origin, non-toxicity, and ability to form host–guest inclusion complexes with organic molecules like PAHs [3]. However, their water solubility limits application in aqueous systems unless crosslinked [3]. Electrospinning of cyclodextrin-based nanofibers enables high surface area, porosity, and tunable surface chemistry—features beneficial for pollutant adsorption [4,5].

In this study, hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin (HP β CD), benzoxazine monomer (BA-a), and citric acid (CTR) were electrospun in dimethylformamide to produce uniform HP β CD15/BA-a fibrous membranes. Thermal crosslinking between 150–225 °C resulted in water-stable PolyHP β CD15/PolyBA-a membranes. Characterization was conducted via SEM, FTIR, and TGA to evaluate morphology, structural evolution, and thermal stability. The membranes were tested for adsorption of PAHs—fluoranthene, phenanthrene, and pyrene—at concentrations of 200, 400, and 600 ppb.

The crosslinked fibrous membranes demonstrated outstanding water stability and consistently achieved >80% removal efficiency for all PAHs tested. This study presents a sustainable approach to water purification by integrating cyclodextrin-based host–guest chemistry with electrospun fibrous architecture, offering a promising solution for environmental remediation challenges [6, 7].

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Keyword: *electrospinning, cyclodextrin, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, crosslinked fibrous membrane*

Synthesis and Purification of a Pro-Regenerative Drug

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While amphibians can spontaneously regenerate lost limbs, mammals typically develop scars at injury sites during the wound healing process. The Murphy Roths Large (MRL) mouse strain is an exceptional case among mammals, as it exhibits a spontaneous regenerative healing trait. Consequently, it serves as a valuable model for investigating proregenerative interventions in mammals. Recent research on adult MRL mice indicates that a crucial characteristic of their injury response is the sustained high levels of the transcription factor hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α (HIF-1 α) during the first few weeks after injury [1]. HIF-1 α regulates the expression of over 100 genes, including those involved in metabolism, angiogenesis, vasculogenesis, cell migration, and survival. Prolyl-4-hydroxylase (PHD) regulates HIF-1 α levels by hydroxylating proline residues, leading to its destruction via the ubiquitin–ligase complex. Under normoxic conditions, PHDs facilitate the degradation of HIF-1 α and function as a convenient regulatory point for HIF-1 α ; inhibition of PHDs results in the stabilization of HIF-1 α . In vitro experiments demonstrated that the PHD inhibitor 1,4-dihydrophenothroline-4-one-3-carboxylic acid (DPCA) can stabilize the constitutive expression of HIF-1 α protein [2,3]. Additionally, tissue regeneration similar to what is seen in MRL mice can be replicated in nonhealing mice through a 10-day delivery of DPCA using an injectable two-component polymer carrier. In this research, I will present DPCA synthesis and attach it to a hydrophilic poly(ethylene glycol) chain via an ester bond. We encountered some challenges in obtaining pure PEG-DPCA. After thorough investigation, we found a way to purify it. The polymeric pro-drug induced ear hole regeneration in adult nonhealing mice in vivo, suggesting that supramolecular polymer hydrogels are promising candidates for drug-triggered tissue regeneration [4].

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Keyword: *Drug synthesis, tissue regeneration, DPCA*

MOF-5-Derived Porous Carbon Zinc Anode Protection Layer for High Power Aqueous Zinc-Ion Batteries

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Aqueous zinc-ion batteries (ZIBs) have emerged as promising candidates for next-generation energy storage systems owing to their inherent safety, low cost, and environmental friendliness. However, the practical application of ZIBs remains limited due to the formation of zinc dendrites and parasitic side reactions during cycling, which degrade the anode performance and shorten the battery lifespan [1, 2]. In this study, we report a novel strategy for stabilizing zinc metal anodes by employing a porous carbon protection layer derived from the metal–organic framework (MOF-5) via laser-assisted carbonization. The porous carbon (c-MOF-5) serves as an ion sieve to modulate Zn^{2+} ion flux and suppress undesired reactions. The c-MOF-5/Zn anodes exhibit remarkable electrochemical stability, operating steadily for over 1000 hours at a current density of 10.0 mA cm^{-2} (10 mAh cm^{-2}), making them a promising candidate for high-power applications. The designed anodes are expected to advance the development of high-performance ZIBs, contributing to the realization of sustainable energy storage solutions for modern societal needs.

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Keyword: *Zinc-ion batteries, Laser carbonization, Metal-organic framework, Energy storage*

High-Performance Transparent Conductive ITO Coatings for Aerospace Transparencies via DC Magnetron Sputtering

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Indium tin oxide (ITO) thin films are widely used in the aerospace industry for applications requiring both high optical transmittance and electrical conductivity, such as EMI shielding, de-icing systems, and infrared control. In this study, ITO coatings were deposited on polycarbonate, acrylic, and glass-based aerospace transparencies using the DC magnetron sputtering method. The process parameters were optimized to achieve an optimum balance between visible light transmittance and sheet resistance (Rs), while ensuring adhesion performance suitable for aerospace conditions.

The optical properties were characterized using a UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer to determine the transmittance and reflection spectra in the visible and near-infrared regions. Electrical performance was evaluated by measuring the sheet resistance using the four-point probe method. Film thickness and refractive index were determined using profilometry and spectroscopic ellipsometry. The crystalline structure was analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), and the surface chemical composition was examined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

The results demonstrated that ITO films with high visible light transmittance and low sheet resistance were successfully produced. XRD patterns revealed a predominantly (222)-oriented crystalline structure, while XPS analysis confirmed that the coating possessed a stoichiometric ITO composition. These findings indicate that high-performance transparent conductive coatings can be produced on aerospace-grade polymeric and glass substrates through a controlled and scalable PVD sputtering process.

Keyword: *ITO Thin Films, DC Magnetron Sputtering, Transparent Conductive Coatings*

Active and passive tuning of a dipole decay rate at critical distances

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Plasmonic nanostructures provide electric field localization to be used as a fluorescence enhancement tool for the closely located fluorophores. However, metallic structures exhibit nonradiative energy transfer at close proximity, which suppresses the boost in the photoluminescence spectrum due to the inhomogeneous medium. Compensation to nonradiative losses is fundamentally restricted, therefore, defining the critical interparticle distances, where the fluorescence enhancement is detectable, holds utmost importance for device applications. In this work, the critical interparticle distances of a metal nanoparticle (MNP) and quantum emitters (QEs) are numerically identified with angstrom resolution by analyzing the interplay between quantum yield and non-radiative decay. By engaging a collimated light application on silver nanoparticle (AgNP) placed at a critical distance, an active fluorescence enhancement switch yielding an observable sevenfold increase in fluorescence intensity is simulated. The provided free space simulation includes the complete response of AgNP with retardation and higher order multi-polar effects, for which the previous analytical works fall short. While the model bridges the absorption and emission spectra via corresponding Stokes shift values and presents a general approach for the interaction of QEs and MNPs in the Rayleigh regime, it can be extended to the Mie regime for larger QEs and can be modified for a dielectric device environment.

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Keyword: *fluorescence enhancement, optical switching, quantum dots, emission*

Investigation of the Structural and Optical Properties of SiON Nanoparticles Produced From SiON Doped Si Thin Film Coated on Cu Wafer

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Nanoparticles have attracted great attention with the emergence of nanotechnology. For this reason, rapid nanoparticle synthesis methods and the variety of elements from which nanoparticles were synthesized have become more important. Earlier works on Silicon (Si) stimulated the progress in numerous Si-photonics devices [1]. Laser ablation method is a novel and environment-friendly nanoparticle synthesis technique. It has been observed that this method is frequently used in the production of materials at different scales, due to its applicability to the majority of elements and its suitability for the use of various types of lasers for different purposes during the process [2].

In this work, we synthesized silicon-oxynitride doped silicon thin film by using PE-CVD method using precursors SiH_4/N_2 (%2/%98) under a relatively low plasma power of 100 W with a radio frequency (RF) of 13.56 MHz under a vacuum of 10^{-5} mBar and fast cooled under an ambient atmosphere [1]. After production process, we performed laser ablation in distilled water by using high energy nanosecond pulsed laser ($\lambda=1064$ nm and pulse repetition rate of 1,5 kHz) to pure Cu plate and SiON doped Si on Cu plate. We obtained Cu nanoparticle solution and SiON doped Si nanoparticle solution. To determine optical and structural properties of resulting material we applied UV-Visible Spectroscopy, Photoluminescence (PL) Spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Raman Spectroscopy and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

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Keyword: Nanoparticle, Laser Ablation, Silicon-oxynitride

Data-Driven Insights into Titanium-Based Li-Ion Battery Materials and the Strategic Inclusion of TiS₂ for Cathode Development

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The development of high-performance cathode materials remains a critical challenge in advancing lithium-ion battery (LIB) technology for next-generation energy storage applications. Titanium-based compounds offer a promising route to safe, cobalt-free LIBs, but their electrochemical performance has historically lagged due to low voltages. This study employs a data-driven approach, leveraging high-throughput computational data of 165 Ti-containing compounds (~ 2200 data points retrieved from The Materials Project database and The Open Quantum Materials Database), to identify key descriptors and design rules for high-performance cathode materials, with particular emphasis on titanium disulfide (TiS₂) systems [1,2]. Through machine learning algorithms including Random Forest, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, and Logistic Regression, we systematically evaluated the electrochemical performance parameters of titanium-containing materials to uncover design guidelines for high-energy Ti-based cathodes. Our analysis reveals that average voltage contributes approximately 45% to the predicted gravimetric energy density, establishing voltage optimization as the most efficient pathway for enhancing Ti-based cathode performance. The TiS₂ family emerges as the most promising candidate for cathodes, demonstrating optimal balance between voltage (~2 V), capacity (~225 mAh g⁻¹), and structural stability (max delta volume, $\Delta V = 0.034-0.068$). Comparative analysis between titanium compounds with and without sulfur shows that sulfides enable higher average voltages (~2.1 V) compared to oxides (~1.6 V) due to the possibility of more covalent Ti-S bonding, while maintaining comparable volumetric energy densities. Decision tree analysis provides practical screening criteria for high-energy Ti compounds, establishing gravimetric capacity ≥ 150 mAh g⁻¹ as the primary gatekeeper, followed by voltage and volume expansion thresholds. These findings provide fundamental insights for rational design of titanium-based cathode materials and establish TiS₂ as a viable candidate for next-generation LIBs with enhanced energy density and cycling stability.

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Keyword: *Machine learning, Data mining, Lithium-ion batteries, Titanium disulfide*

Thermally and Optically Functionalized PVA Nanofibers: An Approach with Phase-Transition Oxides and Laser-Induced Synthesis of MOF Additives

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Electrospun polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) nanofibers are notable structures that can be integrated with functional materials, gaining new thermal and optical properties due to their high surface area and porosity [1]. In this study, it was aimed to increase the functionality of the fibers by integrating tungsten trioxide (WO₃), a well-documented transition metal oxide that exhibits structural phase transformation at low temperatures (transition from triclinic phase to monoclinic phase at approximately 17°C), and zinc-based metal-organic cage (Zn-MOF) components synthesized by a laser-based method into the PVA nanofiber matrix [2,3].

In the first stage of the study, WO₃ nanoparticles were added to the PVA solution at concentrations of 1%, 3%, and 5% by weight, prepared at 7.5% (w/v) in distilled water. The optimum parameters for electrospinning of the mixture were determined as 15 kV voltage, 15 cm tip-collector distance, and 0.2 mL/h flow rate. In the second stage, Zn-MOF structures were added to the PVA/WO₃ system at the same ratios, and nanofiber production was continued under the same conditions. Morphology of the resulting nanofibers was checked using SEM, and smooth, bead-free structures were observed. FTIR analyses confirmed the successful presence of WO₃ and Zn-MOF in the fiber structure. XPS analyses revealed the distribution of these components on the surface. The low-temperature phase transition of WO₃ and the effect of Zn-MOF on this behavior were investigated by DSC, and crystalline changes due to the phase transition were observed by XRD. Additionally, UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy evaluated optical absorption and emission properties in detail. This work combines the phase transition properties of WO₃ and the optical character of Zn-MOF in a single nanofiber platform, providing a new approach for developing multifunctional materials that can be used in smart textiles, sensors, and optoelectronics.

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Keyword: *Electrospun nanofibers, Thermal phase transition, Optical properties*

Tailoring Magnetic and Catalytic Properties of NiFe₂O₄ Nanoalloys via Controlled Sol-Gel Synthesis

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Nickel ferrite (NiFe₂O₄) nanoalloys were synthesized through a sol-gel technique to investigate their multifunctional capabilities, focusing on structural, magnetic and electrocatalytic properties [1, 2]. The crystalline phase and purity were confirmed by X-ray diffraction combined with Rietveld refinement, revealing a well-defined face-centered cubic spinel structure without secondary phases. The calcination temperature was found to critically influence the particle size and morphology, with higher temperatures producing smaller and more uniform crystallites, as observed by scanning electron microscopy. Magnetic characterization demonstrated soft ferromagnetic behavior of NiFe₂O₄ nanoalloys, with saturation magnetization values reaching up to 50 emu/g, which varied with particle size and calcination conditions. Electrocatalytic activity was assessed for the oxygen evolution reaction in 1 M KOH alkaline medium, where the sample calcined at 600 °C displayed the best performance. This sample exhibited a low onset potential of 1.52 V vs. RHE, an overpotential of 298 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², and a high peak current density, indicating its potential as an efficient and stable OER catalyst. This comprehensive study elucidates the relationship between synthesis parameters, particularly calcination temperature, and the resulting multifunctional properties of NiFe₂O₄ nanoalloys. The findings underscore the material's suitability for sustainable energy conversion processes and environmental remediation technologies, offering a promising platform for future development in catalysis and magnetic applications.

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Keyword: *Spinel Nickel ferrite, sol-gel, magnetic properties, oxygen evolution reaction*

Bimetallic PtNi PtCu, And NiCu Nanoparticles: Enhanced Hydrogen Evolution Reaction and Magnetic Performance

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Platinum-based nanoparticles (NPs) are widely recognized as benchmark electrocatalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) due to their excellent intrinsic activity, despite challenges associated with their high cost and limited abundance [1]. In this work, bifunctional bimetallic PtCu, PtNi, and NiCu NPs were synthesized via the polyol method to examine their electrocatalytic performance for the HER and their magnetic properties. Structural analysis using XRD and Rietveld refinement confirmed a face-centered cubic crystal structure with Fm-3m symmetry across all samples. SEM and TEM imaging revealed well-dispersed spherical NPs with average sizes ranging from 10.46 to 12.50 nm. Among the catalysts, Pt₂₈Ni₇₂ demonstrated superior HER performance with the lowest overpotential of -33 mV at -10 mA cm⁻² and a Tafel slope of 55 mV dec⁻¹, following a Volmer–Heyrovsky mechanism. Pt₂₅Cu₇₅ and Ni₂₇Cu₇₃ exhibited moderate activities, adhering to a Volmer–Tafel mechanism. Magnetic characterization indicated a ferromagnetic to paramagnetic transition in PtNi NPs with a notable coercivity of 672 Oe at 5 K, attributed to high Ni content. The multifunctionality of the PtNi catalyst, combining efficient electrocatalytic activity and magnetic recyclability, underscores its potential for applications in energy conversion and biomedicine, including MRI contrast agents and drug delivery systems.

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Keyword: *PtNi NPs, polyol method, HER, magnetic properties*

Biopolymer-Coated Gold Nanorods Engineered as Biorelevant Photothermal Agents

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Gold nanorods (AuNRs) are valuable metallic nanoparticles used in photothermal therapy (PTT) due to their tunable plasmonic characteristics, making them remarkable candidate for hyperthermia. However, their use in biological systems is restricted by cytotoxicity arising from the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), a common surfactant. Here, we aim to synthesize NIR-light absorbing AuNRs with aspect ratio (AR)>3.5 by seed-mediated growth technique adapted from Murphy^[1] and advance functionality of AuNR via improving biocompatibility by replacing CTAB, with BSA:Dextran and BSA:Guar Gum Maillard conjugates. Also, we aim to assess the heat generation ability of AuNRs by photoexcitation using an 808 nm continuous wave (CW) diode laser. Firstly, we tuned the optical properties by changing the silver nitrate concentration. AuNRs containing 0.1 M AgNO₃ (AuNR-10) are found as an optimum sample due to its AR (3.9), LSPR (795 nm), and clear rod-shaped morphology. Then, we replaced CTAB with biopolymer conjugates^[2], which were prepared via the Maillard reaction^[3]. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra showed that CTAB peaks of the biopolymer@AuNR eliminated while the OH and amide peaks which are characteristic peaks of biopolymer conjugates can be observed clearly. Electrophoretic light scattering (ELS) results indicated successful CTAB replacement with the zeta potential of CTAB@AuNR, BSA:Dext@AuNR, and BSA:GG@AuNR, determined as +26.8, -34.1, and -26.0 mV respectively. Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and UV-VIS spectra results showed that the nanorod morphology and optical characteristics are preserved in biopolymer@AuNR and they are intact for over 10 months. The cytotoxicity of CTAB@AuNR was below 20% for both L929 and MCF-7 cell lines at 200 µg/mL whereas cell viability remained above 70% in L929 cells treated with 1000 µg/mL biopolymer@AuNR. In this study, we significantly advanced the biocompatibility of AuNRs by coating them with biopolymer conjugates, while preserving their photothermal properties, thereby enabling their use at biologically relevant concentrations for PTT. Overall, this study offers a promising, non-toxic, and effective PTT agent for potential application in cancer treatment.

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Keyword: *gold nanorods, biopolymer, cytotoxicity, NIR light responsivity*

Ultrafast Laser Synthesis of Nanoporous Zeolite A

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Zeolite A (LTA), a nanoporous aluminosilicate, is the first commercially synthesized zeolite, which has properties like high porosity, high surface area, and high chemical and thermal stability. Due to these properties, zeolite A has been used in various industrial applications like CO₂ adsorption, wastewater treatments, biosensor applications etc. The conventional hydrothermal synthesis of zeolites offers benefits such as high-quality discrete crystals, ease of use, safety, and industrial scalability, it lacks precise control over nucleation and growth. Alternative methods have been developed for synthesizing zeolites and reducing the reaction time, but they all have limitations, such as defect formation, and safety issues related to the high-energy light source. A method that combines these advantages with the ability to produce defect-free crystals using low-energy photons within a short reaction time has not been developed yet. Here, we introduce a new synthesis method for the synthesis of nanoporous zeolite A by using ultrafast laser energy deposition. Utilizing a femtosecond laser at a wavelength of 1040 nm, we accelerated the formation of zeolite A crystals via multiphoton absorption and laser-induced convective flows.^[1] Through the controlled deposition of energy, this method achieves rapid crystallization of Zeolite A with high crystallinity (90-100%) and a narrower particle size distribution compared to the crystals synthesized via the conventional hydrothermal method. Comprehensive characterization techniques, including SEM, HR-TEM, SAED, XRD, and FTIR, confirmed the structural integrity and comparable quality of the laser-synthesized zeolites. Moreover, CO₂ adsorption capacity analysis was carried out to evaluate the gas capture performance and practical applicability of Zeolite A synthesized via the ultrafast laser synthesis method. The ultrafast laser synthesis method was successfully repeated over 70 times. This novel technique offers a rapid and scalable alternative for synthesizing zeolites with precise control over structural and functional properties.

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Keyword: *Zeolites, Ultrafast Lasers, Multiphoton absorption, CO₂ adsorption*

Synthesis and Characterization of Electroactive Vermiculite/Polypyrrole Nanocomposites for Dielectric Fluid Applications

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Vermiculite (VMT) is a naturally occurring clay mineral composed of hydrated magnesium aluminum silicate with a layered structure. Although VMT is an insulating material, this morphology provides a high surface-to-volume ratio, which enhances interfacial polarization, making VMT a promising candidate for dielectric applications. In this study, electrical properties of VMT was enhanced by preparing a nanocomposite with conductive polypyrrole (PPy). Layers of VMT were expanded and functionalized with PPy via in-situ polymerization. Structure of VMT/PPy nanocomposite was revealed by ATR-FTIR and XRD spectrometry. ATR-FTIR of VMT/PPy showed new methyl peaks around 2900 cm^{-1} indicating PPy formation. XRD diffractograms of VMT/PPy indicated successful polymerization of PPy on VMT via disappearance of VMT crystalline peaks. Layered structure of VMT and PPy presence for VMT/PPy nanocomposite were also approved by SEM images. Dielectric fluids were prepared by dispersing 1 wt.% of VMT and VMT/PPy particles in an insulating silicone oil (SO) medium. Dielectric properties were analysed by LCR meter, and dielectric constant (ϵ'), dielectric loss (ϵ''), and relaxation time (λ) of the dispersions were calculated by Cole-Cole model (Fig. 1). The higher $\Delta\epsilon' = 3 \times 10^{-2}$ and lower $\lambda = 5.8 \times 10^{-2}$ were detected for VMT/PPy/SO dispersion compared to VMT/SO ($\Delta\epsilon' = 2 \times 10^{-2}$ and $\lambda = 6.4 \times 10^{-2}$), and thus it was concluded that VMT/PPy nanocomposite is good candidates for future electroactive vibration damping studies.

Figure 1. Dielectric spectra of VMT/SO and VMT/PPy/SO dispersions (Solid lines are Cole-Cole fitted results).

Keyword: vermiculite, polypyrrole, nanocomposite, dielectric

Dexamethasone-Loaded PCL-Cholesterol Nanoparticles for Uveitis

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Uveitis is a non-bacterial inflammatory disease of the uveal tissue [1]. Uveitis is the third leading cause of vision loss worldwide, and in the young population is responsible for 5-20% of vision loss [2]. DEX is a glucocorticoid, and utilizing the treatment of uveitis. Multiple intra-vitreal injections are administered in the treatment of uveitis. Frequent injection has many handicaps, such as retinal detachment, cataracts. Therefore, to reduce the frequency, and the availability of drugs in the vitreous is essential for the treatment [3].

Therefore, the aim of the study, against uveitis, performance of preclinical studies of DEX loaded PCL-cholesterol blend particles. In the poster presentation, SEM, degradation, size-size distribution, and TGA studies of the particles were planned.

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Keyword: *Uveitis, nanoparticles, inflammations, dexamethasone*

Green Synthesis of Transition Metal Oxide Nanoparticles Using an Extract From *Brassica oleracea* as a Reducing Agent for Hyperthermia Application

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This study explores the biological synthesis and characterizations of silver (Ag), gold (Au), zinc (Zn), titanium (Ti), and iron oxide (FeO) nanoparticles (NPs) using *Brassica oleracea* (broccoli) extract as a sustainable, eco-friendly, and cost-effective reducing agent. NP solutions were prepared by combining metal precursors, which are silver nitrate, zinc acetate dihydrate, zinc nitrate hexahydrate, titanium (IV) isopropoxide, iron (III) chloride, and gold (III) chloride trihydrate, with 20 ml of broccoli extract, followed by magnetic stirring, centrifugation, and heat treatment. The resulting NPs were subjected to comprehensive physical, morphological, biological, and thermal analyses. Hyperthermia analysis was conducted on polydopamine (PDA)-coated metal oxide NPs under 470 nm blue-violet light to evaluate their heat conduction properties. Results from UV-visible spectroscopy revealed that 4 mM AuNPs exhibited superior morphological structure, UV absorption, hyperthermia performance, and cell viability (800 mg/L) compared to other NPs. While green synthesized NPs demonstrated high absorbance, excellent cell viability, and favorable nanostructure and size properties compared to those produced via conventional chemical and physical methods, their light-to-heat conversion efficiency was lower than reported in prior studies. PDA coating enhanced the heat absorption of metal oxide NPs, though insufficiently for effective photothermal therapy (PTT). Notably, AuNPs synthesized at 4 mM outperformed other NPs in hyperthermia, cell viability, and absorbance. To further enhance Au@PDA NPs for PTT, the incorporation of photosensitizers such as rose bengal is proposed. The study highlights the potential of green-synthesized NPs, particularly AuNPs, for biomedical applications, including drug delivery, imaging, and neurostimulation, owing to their biocompatibility, thermal properties, and sustainable production method

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Keyword: *thermotherapy, biological synthesis, noble metal nanoparticles, plant leaf extract*

Electrochromic Response of NiO Nanostructures for the Detection of Cu²⁺ Ions in Aqueous Media

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In this study, nickel oxide (NiO) nanostructures were synthesized using sol-gel and hydrothermal methods and systematically characterized to investigate their potential for detecting Cu²⁺, Co²⁺ and Fe²⁺ ions in aqueous solutions via electrochromic response. Structural properties were examined through X-ray diffraction (XRD), which confirmed the formation of a face-centered cubic (FCC) crystalline phase. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyses revealed a homogeneously distributed morphology, while optical properties were evaluated using UV-Vis spectrophotometry. The absorption coefficient was calculated from the UV-Vis spectra, and Tauc plots were employed to estimate the optical band gap energies. The band gaps were determined to be 3.3 eV for the sol-gel-derived NiO and 3.5 eV for the hydrothermally synthesized counterpart.

To assess electrochromic performance, the NiO nanostructures were deposited onto fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) glass substrates and tested in the presence of Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, and Fe²⁺ ions using galvanostatic techniques. Among these, Cu²⁺ ions induced the most prominent color change. Based on this observation, NiO nanostructures were subsequently integrated onto quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) sensors to evaluate their Cu²⁺ ion detection capability. Frequency shifts were recorded over time for five different Cu²⁺ concentrations. The hydrothermally synthesized NiO nanoparticles demonstrated enhanced sensing performance and a more pronounced electrochromic response compared to thin films prepared via the sol-gel method.

Keyword: *Electrochromism, NiO nanostructures, Heavy metal detection, QCM sensors*

Stability and Surface Modification of Iron Oxide Nanoparticles in Oil-Based Ferrofluids for Biomedical Applications

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Ferrofluids, combining magnetic and fluidic properties, find applications in sealing, lubrication, heavy metal adsorption, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), targeted drug delivery, hyperthermia, and biosensing. Stabilization of iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe_3O_4) within magnetic colloidal ferrofluids is critical for long-term functionality and biomedical safety.

In this study, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were synthesized via co-precipitation and surface-modified with (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES), stearic acid (C18:0), oleic acid (C18:1), and undecanoic acid (C11:0). Ferrofluids (0.5–5.0% w/v) were prepared in olive and sunflower oils, stored at +4°C, 25°C, and 40°C, and monitored over one month for stability through color changes and sedimentation. Nanoparticles were characterized pre- and post-modification using vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The displacement of the oil-based ferrofluid layer on a water phase in a two-phase system under a magnetic field (10–35 V, 1 Hz) was investigated at concentrations of 1%, 2%, and 5% (w/v), using sample volumes of 0.25, 0.5, and 1 mL placed 8 mm from the source.

Results revealed that pure Fe_3O_4 and fatty acid-coated nanoparticles sedimented in both oils from day one, while APTES-coated nanoparticles sedimented only in olive oil but remained stable in sunflower oil for 28 days. At 0.5–5.0% concentrations, APTES-coated nanoparticles showed no sedimentation for at least 7 days at 25°C and 37°C, and up to 28 days at +4°C. VSM analysis revealed that Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles possess a saturation magnetization of ≥ 60 emu/g. FTIR spectra verified fatty acid coatings via characteristic peaks at 2920 and 2850 cm^{-1} . TEM images showed average particle sizes of 10–13 nm. Ferrofluid displacement exhibited a linear relationship with voltage at 1% ($R^2 = 0.95$), near-linear at 2% ($R^2 = 0.90$), and strong linearity at 5% concentration ($R^2 = 0.99$). At 5% (w/v), displacement ranged between 0.41–2.35 mm for 0.25 mL (5–17.5 V), 0.44–3.17 mm for 0.5 mL (5–12.5 V), and 0.41–2.30 mm for 1.0 mL (5–20 V). Additionally, ferromagnetic ball formation exhibiting sink-and-rise behavior was observed at 5% (w/v) for 1 mL and 0.25 mL volumes at 22.5 V.

Ferromagnetic ball formation enables controlled and reversible motion under magnetic fields, which is essential for advanced biomedical applications. It allows precise actuation in guided drug delivery and injectable microactuators, offering improved targeting, reduced side effects, and minimally invasive treatment options. These features represent key advantages for next-generation medical technologies.

This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK, Grant No: 222M057) and the Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit of Hacettepe University (BAP, Project No: FHD-2024-21597). The authors gratefully acknowledge both institutions for their support.

Keyword: *Ferrofluid, Fe_3O_4 Nanoparticles, Surface Modification, Magnetic Actuation*

Synthesis and Characterization of Hydrochar/Conducting Polymer Biocomposite Particles

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In this study, hydrochar particles were obtained from dry pine cones in subcritical water environment by hydrothermal method to obtain hydrochar (HC) from plant sources. HC/PAni biocomposites were synthesized containing different percentages of conductive polymer (polyaniline (PAni)) (10%, 25% and 50%, g/g). Detailed structural, morphological, and thermal characterization of the synthesized HC/PAni biocomposites were carried out by FTIR, XRD, SEM/EDS, and TGA/DSC analyses. According to the characterization results, the successful formation of the composite structure was observed with the characteristic peaks of HC and PAni. SEM images showed that PAni coated the HC particles. According to the EDS results, the C ratio of HC (69%, g/g) decreased proportionally with the increasing PAni ratio in the composite structure (55%, g/g). Additionally, the increase in N content supports the presence of PAni. The conductivity value increased with increasing PAni ratio in the composite structure and is in the semiconductor range. The study will further investigate the colloidal (electrokinetic) properties and vibration damping (electrheological) behavior of the biocomposites under electric field strength.

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Keyword: *Hydrochar, Polyaniline, Biocomposite, Hydrothermal method*

Hansen Solubility Approach Toward Green Solvent Processing: N-Channel Organic Field-Effect Transistors in Ambient

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The adoption of green solvents is of utmost importance for the solution-based fabrication of semiconductor thin-films and for the commercialization of (opto)electronic devices, especially in response to evolving regulatory mandates for handling organic materials. Despite increasing interest in this area, the scarcity of green solvent-processed n-channel OFETs, especially functioning in ambient conditions, highlights the need for further research. In this study, we demonstrated the Hansen solubility approach to study the solubility behavior of an ambient-stable n-type semiconductor, 2,2'-(2,8-bis(3-dodecylthiophen-2-yl)indeno[1,2-b]fluorene-6,12-diylidene)dimalononitrile (**β,β' -C₁₂-TIFDMT**), and to analyze potential green solvents for thin-film processing. The Hansen solubility parameters were determined to be $\delta_D = 20.8 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$, $\delta_P = 5.8 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$, $\delta_H = 5.5 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$ with a radius (R_0) of $8.3 \text{ MPa}^{1/2}$. A green solvent screening analysis based on minimal distance constraint and quantitative sustainability score identified ethoxybenzene, anisole, 2-methylanisole, and 2-methyltetrahydrofuran as suitable green solvents (R_a 's = $5.17\text{-}7.93 \text{ MPa}^{1/2} < R_0$). A strong thermodynamic correlation was identified between the solubility and the semiconductor-solvent distance in the 3D Hansen solubility space, in which the maximum solubility limit could be estimated with the semiconductor's enthalpy of fusion (ΔH_{fus}) and melting temperature (T_{mp}). To the best of our knowledge, this relationship between maximum solubility limit and thermal properties is being established for the first time for an organic semiconductor. Bottom-gate/top-contact OFETs fabricated by spin-coating the semiconductor green solutions exhibited μ_e 's reaching to $\sim 0.2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ ($I_{\text{on}}/I_{\text{off}} \sim 10^6\text{-}10^7$ and $V_{\text{on}} \sim 0\text{-}5 \text{ V}$) in ambient. This device performance, to our knowledge, is the highest reported for an ambient-stable green solvent-processed n-channel OFET. Our HSP-based rational approach and unique findings presented in this study can shed a critical light on how green solvents can be efficiently incorporated in solution processing in organic (opto)electronics, and whether ambient-stable n-type semiconductors can continue to play an important role in green-OFETs.

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Keyword: *Organic Semiconductors, Organic Field Effect Transistors, Hansen Solubility Parameters, Green Chemistry,*

Synthesis and structural Characterization of InSb nanowires fabricated via Thermomechanical Nanomolding

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InSb nanowires were synthesized via thermomechanical nanomolding (TMNM) by applying a pressure of 400 MPa and a temperature of 450 °C for 1 hour, using anodized aluminum oxide (AAO) templates with a pore size of 110 nm. Field emission scanning microscopy (FESEM) revealed that the nanowires exhibited a high aspect ratio of approximately 80, corresponding to a length of 10 μm and a diameter of approximately 110 nm. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) confirmed that the nanowires consist solely of indium (In) and antimony (Sb), consistent with the stoichiometry of the InSb alloy. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis identified a zinc-blende crystal structure (JCPDS 06-0208), with a prominent peak corresponding to the (111) plane and no separate peaks for In and Sb observed.

Keyword: *InSb nanowires, Thermomechanical nanomolding (TMNM), High aspect ratio*

Bio-Based Carbon Dots: Valorization of Microalgal Residue into High-Value Nanomaterials

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Carbon dots (CDs) have emerged as promising members of the carbon-based nanomaterials family (nanocarbons) thanks to their appealing physicochemical and optical features that make them useful for a wide range of potential applications. Various techniques, such as microwave irradiation, hydrothermal treatment, and pyrolysis, have been investigated for CD synthesis, utilizing numerous types of carbon sources, both in the form of small organic molecules and waste materials. Aligned with the growing efforts aimed at addressing sustainability challenges in producing nanocarbons, bio-based waste materials stand out among carbon precursors. In this study, we employed the oil-extracted residue of a heterotrophic microalgal species, *Schizochytrium* sp. S31, which we exploit as a cellular system for producing the oil required for biodiesel synthesis. As the carbonization technique, we opted for microwave irradiation, which enables fast processing and provides uniform heating. After microwave-induced carbonization with or without added catalysts and multistage purification, we obtained blue- or red-emitting CDs. And notably, not only the emission profile but also the particle size of the resulting CDs showed dependence on the catalyst type (inorganic acid or ionic liquid). Thus, overall, we conducted preliminary studies on converting spent (oil-depleted) heterotrophic microalgae into a value-added product to help realize a practically zero-waste process for producing biodiesel.

Keyword: Carbonization, Biomass conversion, Microwave irradiation, Carbon nanodots

Ethanol-Mediated Tailoring of Photocatalytic NO_x Oxidation and Storage on Reducible Metal Oxides: Probing Molecular Basis of Reactivity

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To improve the photocatalytic oxidation and storage of NO_x (PHONOS) by TiO₂ under UVA light, a straightforward impregnation method using a monohydric alcohol was employed. This approach introduced structural defects and incorporated oxygen-containing species from ethanol (EtOH) into commercial P25 (TiO₂) through mild-temperature treatment. By varying the EtOH amount and calcination temperature, optimal conditions for partial reduction were identified. One-hour photocatalytic activity tests showed that catalyst color alone did not directly reflect performance, as measured by the DeNO_x Index. However, the sample treated at 150 °C with 3 mL of ethanol (TiO₂-EtOH-150) achieved the highest NO conversion and NO_x storage selectivity in the short-term PHONOS test.

Extended activity tests revealed that both untreated P25 and TiO₂-EtOH-150 suffered from gradual deactivation, primarily due to NO_x adsorption leading to surface poisoning and a decline in storage ability. Incorporating a basic metal oxide such as CaO significantly improved and prolonged NO_x storage efficiency, even after 15 hours of operation. Characterization using XRD, Raman, DR-UV-Vis, XPS, and valence band XPS confirmed defect formation and electronic alterations in the EtOH-modified samples. The unique surface chemistry and electronic structure of TiO₂-EtOH-150 were key contributors to its enhanced photocatalytic performance. In-situ EPR spectroscopy further revealed that UV-irradiated ethanol-treated TiO₂ samples, unlike untreated P25, displayed a strong EPR signal at $g \approx 1.99$ —an indicator of Ti³⁺ centers and oxygen vacancies.

Additionally, in-situ FTIR analysis verified that ethanol undergoes partial surface oxidation on TiO₂, forming acetaldehyde and acetate species. Acetaldehyde-related peaks vanished above 150 °C, while acetate accumulation persisted, indicating that acetaldehyde groups are likely involved in the enhanced reactivity observed at this temperature. Overall, this study demonstrates that introducing oxygenated surface groups through mild ethanol treatment is a simple yet effective strategy for boosting TiO₂-based NO_x photocatalysts.

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Keyword: *Photocatalysis, PHONOS, NO_x Storage, Reduced TiO₂*

Facet-Enriched TiO₂ Photocatalysts for Methanol Partial Oxidation to Formaldehyde

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Photocatalytic performances of anatase TiO₂ with {100}, {101}, and {001} facet-enriched nanocrystals for methanol partial oxidation to formaldehyde were investigated. Reaction parameters: pH (3, 7, and 11), gas flow (Ar, O₂) and gas flow rate with 200, 500, 1000, and 1500 sccm (two different procedures were performed: gas flow before UV+VIS irradiation and throughout the experiment), and temperature (13, 23, and 43 °C) were first optimized on Degussa P25 TiO₂ commercial photocatalyst. Maximum formaldehyde yield using P25 was achieved under basic conditions (pH = 11), with an O₂ flow rate of 1000 sccm (before irradiation), and at 43 °C under UV+VIS irradiation. These optimized conditions were subsequently applied to evaluate the photocatalytic performance of TiO₂-{100}/{101}/{001} nanocrystals, as mentioned earlier. Structural analysis via XRD and Raman spectroscopy confirmed successful facet engineering. HR-TEM images supported the highly single crystal nature of TiO₂-{100}, TiO₂-{101}, but it showed additional {100} facets for TiO₂-{001} due to higher surface energy of the TiO₂-{001} facets. Photocatalytic tests revealed that TiO₂-{100} and TiO₂-{101} exhibited superior activity compared to TiO₂-{001}. This reactivity trend was attributed to more favorable surface atomic configurations (lack of three-fold O species on TiO₂-{001}) and possibility of surface reconstruction on TiO₂-{001} evident by HR-TEM images. These results demonstrated that the photocatalytic methanol partial oxidation to formaldehyde is surface sensitive for anatase TiO₂.

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Keyword: Photocatalysis, Methanol partial oxidation, Formaldehyde, Facet-enriched TiO₂

ZnO Nanorod Arrays Hybridized with Amine-Modified Graphene Oxide for Photonic Application Platforms

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Zinc oxide (ZnO), with its wide bandgap (~3.37 eV), high transparency, and excellent electron mobility, is widely used in optoelectronic devices such as solar cells, photodetectors, and LEDs^{1,2}. One-dimensional ZnO nanostructures, especially nanorods (NRs), offer enhanced surface area and directional charge transport, improving device performance^{3,4}. Reduced and/or modified graphene oxide (mGO), with its absorption and tunable photoluminescence properties, is also promising for flexible electronics and hybrid nanostructures⁵.

In this study, a hybrid structure of ZnO NR/amine-mGO nanodot (ND) was fabricated and characterized. Vertically aligned ZnO NRs were synthesized on ITO substrates via chemical bath deposition, with tunable lengths (~1–2.5 µm) and diameters (62–131 nm). Oxygen plasma treatment enabled uniform alignment and minimized surface defects over a 400 µm² area, as confirmed by SEM and AFM. XRD and Raman analyses verified the wurtzite crystal structure. The NRs were hybridized with four mGO-NDs (dipropylamine, 2-ethylhexylamine, dihexylamine, dioctylamine), with hydrodynamic sizes of 20–90 nm (DLS). AFM and SEM confirmed conformal coating between rods, while XRD indicated preserved ZnO crystallinity. The hybrid structures exhibit promising optical and structural properties for use in optoelectronic and photocatalytic systems.

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Keyword: *Vertically Grown ZnO Nanorods, Modified Graphene Oxide, Chemical Bath Deposition*

Charging Behaviour of Surfactant-doped Emulsion Systems

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Micron and nanosized emulsions are essential in industries such as pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and food. This study investigates the formation and stability of spontaneously generated n-hexane/ethanol/water emulsions using various surfactants (CTAB, SDS, and Triton X-100). The effects of surfactant charge, concentration relative to the critical micelle concentration (CMC), and ethanol/surfactant ratios on droplet size and surface tension reduction were explored. Ionic surfactants, especially CTAB, provided stronger electrostatic stabilization compared to nonionic surfactants, which relied on steric effects. The most stable emulsions were achieved with CTAB at concentrations above the CMC and optimized ethanol ratios, resulting in narrow droplet size distributions. These findings support the use of low-energy emulsion systems in sustainable industrial applications.

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Keyword: *Droplet charge, Zeta potential, Droplet size, Spontaneous emulsions*

Surface modification of plasma-treated wool fabrics with zeolitic imidazolate frameworks

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Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), a newly developed crystalline materials with high porosity, have recently attracted growing research interest across academia and industry. These materials are primarily constructed via the self-assembly of metal ions with organic linkers. Thanks to their unique structural features, including large specific surface area, high porosity, tunable pore size and functionality, and outstanding adsorption behavior, they have found a wide variety of applications [1]. Recent studies have shown a significant interest in the integration of various MOFs into textile fabrics to lead to a range of beneficial outcomes [2]. Specifically, zeolitic imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs), which are formed through the tetrahedral coordination of transition metals (such as Zn^{2+} or Co^{2+}) with imidazolate ligands, have demonstrated significant potential for enhancing the functionalities of textile fabrics. In this study, ZIF-8 and ZIF-67 was in-situ synthesized on the wool fabric to enhance its surface and physical properties. Plasma treatment was employed on wool fabric to enhance the subsequent MOF crystal growth and surface modification. The surface morphology and wettability of functionalized wool fabrics were characterized by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) and water contact angle (WCA) measurement, respectively. FESEM images confirmed the uniform and dense formation of ZIF-8 and ZIF-67 crystals on the surface and within the fibrils of plasma-treated wool fabric (P-Wool). The WCA of wool-ZIF-8 and wool-ZIF-67 fabrics was significantly decreased from 140° to 5° and 143° to 5° , respectively, through the plasma pre-treatment. The air permeability of wool-ZIF-8 and wool-ZIF-67 fabrics was also measured and showed a slight decrease from 74 to 71 mL/s and 60 to 40 mL/s, respectively, with plasma pre-treatment, suggesting more deposition of MOF crystals with plasma modification. This confirmed the ability of the proposed process to improve the surface and structural properties of wool fiber with plasma treatment.

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Keyword: *Metal-organic framework, Plasma pre-treatment, Textile fabric, Surface modification.*

Development of Waste-Derived Zeolites for Efficient Fluoride Adsorption in Aqueous Systems

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Access to clean water is essential for human health, yet increasing pollution from industrial growth and population expansion continues to degrade water quality. Among various contaminants, fluoride poses a distinct challenge due to its dual nature as a beneficial trace element and a harmful pollutant at high concentrations. Effective fluoride removal is therefore critical for both water treatment and public health [1].

At the same time, managing industrial waste is key to environmental sustainability. The photovoltaic industry, for example, produces significant silicon waste (kerf loss) during wafer cutting. This study investigates the sustainable synthesis of zeolites from kerf loss, and fly ash as a waste valorization strategy [2].

The structural and electrokinetic properties of the synthesized zeolites were characterized, with particular focus on their zeta potential across different pH values and point of zero charge (pH_{pzc}). The relationship between these electrokinetic features and fluoride adsorption capacity was examined. Results demonstrate that waste-derived zeolites are effective fluoride adsorbents, offering a dual advantage of pollution mitigation and resource recovery.

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Keyword: *Waste Valorization, Wastewater Treatment, Fluoride Removal, Green Chemistry*

Influence of Rh Loading of Rh/Ce-HAP Single-Atom Catalysts on Ethanol and CO₂ Interactions: Oxidation vs. Decomposition Pathways

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The co-adsorption behavior of ethanol and CO₂ was systematically investigated on Rh single-atom catalysts (SACs) supported on ceria-promoted hydroxyapatite (Ce-HAP) with varying Rh loadings (0.2 and 2 wt%) to understand their relevance in ethanol dry reforming. A combination of in-situ FTIR, TPD, XANES/EXAFS, XPS, and TEM revealed that both catalysts predominantly featured isolated Rh species or sub-nanometric clusters, with negligible contribution from large Rh nanoparticles. The 0.2Rh/5Ce-HAP catalyst exhibited oxygen-rich Ce⁴⁺ domains that stabilized partially reduced Rh^{(3-x)+} sites, facilitating the formation of surface ethoxides, carbonates, and bicarbonates at 50 °C. Upon heating to 350 °C, these ethoxides were oxidized to acetate, consistent with a redox-active environment supported by ceria's oxygen storage capacity. In contrast, the 2Rh/5Ce-HAP catalyst, enriched in Ce³⁺, promoted direct ethoxide decomposition via C–C and C–H bond cleavage, leading to acetaldehyde, CO, and CH₄ formation. These differences were attributed to Rh–Ce interactions that altered Rh oxidation states with increasing Rh coverage, as confirmed by XPS shifts. TPD further revealed 5 times higher CH₄ evolution on 2Rh/5Ce-HAP, indicating enhanced decomposition and increased coke formation tendency. Despite lower total syngas (H₂/CO, 1:1) desorption, 0.2Rh/5Ce-HAP yielded higher H₂ and CO formation per Rh atom, reflecting superior atom economy. These findings highlight that Rh loading, even in SAC regimes, markedly affects redox behavior, intermediate stability, and catalytic pathways through changes in metal–support interactions.

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Keyword: *Single-atom catalysts, Rh, Ceria, in-situ FTIR spectroscopy*

How Single Atoms Keep Your Catalysts Alive: Effect Of Particle Size On Sulfur Poisoning and Regeneration of Rhodium Active Sites

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SO_x poisoning and regenerative capabilities of a Rh single atom catalyst (SAC) were investigated via in-situ FTIR spectroscopy and temperature programmed desorption (TPD) comparatively to that of a Rh nanoparticle catalyst on different ceria support materials. SO_x poisoning of the Rh single atom catalyst (i.e., 0.5 wt.%Rh/5 wt.%Ce/HAP, HAP: hydroxyapatite) with SO₂(g) + O₂(g) at 400 °C (P_{SO₂} + P_{O₂} = 2 Torr, P_{SO₂} : P_{O₂} = 1:10, exposure duration = 10 min) resulted in the formation of sulfates and sulfites. Consecutive regeneration of Rh/CeHAP SAC with H₂ revealed that Rh single atom sites could be readily regenerated under the currently used SO_x poisoning (P_{SO₂} = 2 Torr, 400 °C, 10 min) and regeneration (P_{H₂} = 10 Torr, 200 °C, 2 h) conditions meanwhile also causing Rh agglomeration to form small (presumably multi-atomic/oligomeric) Rh clusters. On the other hand, on the 0.5 wt.% Rh/CeO₂ catalyst which had dominantly large Rh nanoparticles as active sites along with a relatively smaller number Rh single atom minority sites, sulfur-poisoned large Rh nanoparticles were observed to be almost entirely inactive after the treatment with H₂; while Rh single atom minority sites were observed to be reactivated after the H₂ treatment under identical conditions. SO_x-TPD experiments indicated that sulfur-poisoned Rh/CeO₂ catalyst containing large Rh nanoparticles adsorbed significant amounts of sulfates and sulfites which desorbed mostly in the form of SO₂ (g) within 500-750 °C. On the other hand, sulfur-poisoned Rh/CeHAP SAC adsorbed a considerably smaller amount of sulfates/sulfites where sulfates/sulfites were found to adsorb on the Rh/CeHAP surface in a substantially stronger manner than that of Rh/CeO₂, evident by SO₂ desorption from sulfur-poisoned Rh/CeHAP SAC within 650-900 °C. Poor regeneration capability of sulfur-poisoned large Rh nanoparticles are attributed to the presence of a dense sulfate/sulfite multilayer precluding the transport and diffusion of hydrogen to the underlying Rh sites due to steric hindrance, while high regeneration efficiency of Rh single atom sites can be associated to the favorable accessibility of SAC sites to the adsorbed hydrogen.

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Keyword: *Single atom catalysts, Rhodium, SO_x poisoning, in-situ FTIR spectroscopy*

Tuning Structural Outcomes of Cation Exchange in Nanoplatelets via Anionic Crown Composition

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This study investigates the structural transformations of various cadmium selenide (CdSe)-based nanoplatelets (NPLs) upon cation exchange with lead (Pb). We synthesized several distinct NPL architectures, including pure CdSe, CdSe/CdS core/crown, and CdSe/CdSexTe1-x core/crown alloyed NPLs, to systematically evaluate the role of lattice strain and composition on the outcome of the exchange reaction. Upon exchanging cadmium with lead, distinct morphological changes were observed across the different nanoplatelet systems. Pure CdSe NPLs exhibited slight edge etching and minor structural deformation. In stark contrast, CdSe/CdS core/crown NPLs underwent catastrophic structural failure, with the entire nanoplatelet being ripped apart. Conversely, when CdSe/CdSexTe1-x core/crown alloyed NPLs were subjected to cation exchange, a clear trend of improved structural integrity was observed with increasing tellurium (Te) content, manifesting as a reduction in edge etching. Remarkably, in the case of pure CdSe/CdTe core/crown NPLs, the edges were perfectly preserved post-exchange; however, a distinct hole formed in the center of the nanoplatelet where the original CdSe core was located. We attribute the varying degrees of edge etching to the mitigation of lattice strain, as the incorporation of larger anions (Te) in the crown better accommodates the larger incoming Pb cations, thereby preserving the anion sublattice. The formation of a central hole in the CdSe/CdTe NPLs is ascribed to the nanoscale Kirkendall effect, likely arising from the disparity in the diffusion rates of cadmium in lead telluride (PbTe) and lead in cadmium selenide (CdSe). These findings provide valuable insights into the mechanisms governing cation exchange reactions in complex colloidal nanostructures and highlight the critical role of strain engineering in maintaining structural fidelity.

Keyword: *cation exchange, nanoplatelets*

Tunable Dielectric Behavior of Smart Hydrogels for Implantable pH Sensor Design

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Hydrogels, which are three-dimensional crosslinked polymeric networks capable of absorbing substantial amounts of water and can be engineered to exhibit pH-responsiveness and demonstrate high biocompatibility attributed to their low cytotoxicity. Their inherent properties, such as high water permeability, sensitivity to environmental stimuli, self-healing capability, mechanical flexibility, and soft tissue-like structure, make them highly suitable for a wide range of biomedical applications [1]. Beyond these advantages, pH-responsive hydrogels additionally offer electrical functionality through modification, enabling their integration into advanced technologies such as biosensors, bioelectronic devices, and soft robotic systems [2].

In this work, we explore the potential use of pH-responsive acrylic acid/acrylamide/N,N N-dimethylacrylamide/polyethylene glycol diacrylate (P(AAm-co-AAc-co-DMA-co-PEGDA)) hydrogels as pH-responsive resonators for wireless sensing applications in high-frequency bioelectronics. The effect of monomer ratio and gelation temperature on the frequency-dependent dielectric constant of hydrogels, which are synthesized via free radical polymerization, was investigated.

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Keyword: *pH responsive hydrogels, sensing*

Pseudomagnetic Field Induced Zeeman Splitting in 2D Van der Waals Heterostructures

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Two-dimensional (2D) van der Waals (vdW) transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have been extensively researched across various disciplines because of their outstanding mechanical, electronic, and optical properties. There has been considerable emphasis on investigating TMDCs for a range of applications, including optoelectronics, quantum information, and valleytronics¹. By vertically stacking different 2D materials using van der Waals interactions, a range of heterostructures and homostructures can be created². In heterostructures, electrons and holes bound by the Coulomb force can reside in different layers, forming interlayer excitons with exceptionally long lifetimes and permanent electric dipole moments. This interesting characteristic provides opportunities for exploring many-body effects³. In 2010, a strain-induced pseudomagnetic field greater than 300 T was demonstrated in graphene⁴. Theoretically, heterostrain can generate a pseudomagnetic field that causes electrons and holes to mimic the behaviour they would exhibit under an actual magnetic field⁵. In this study, we examined the photoluminescence emission of interlayer exciton of heterobilayer samples under an applied external magnetic field, observed valley polarization and antisymmetric Zeeman splitting at even zero tesla, and we calculated g factors \approx -20 and -17 for two different samples. This behavior is attributed to local strain that was imposed during the fabrication process, which created a pseudomagnetic field that caused the material to behave like a real magnetic field.

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Keyword: *Pseudo-magnetic field, Strain, Zeeman splitting, Interlayer excitons*

Designing Optically Addressable Spin Centers for Solid-State Quantum Technology: A First-Principles Approach

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Point defects in wide-band-gap semiconductors are promising candidates for optically addressable solid-state spin qubits. The benchmark example, the nitrogen-vacancy (NV) center in diamond, has demonstrated room-temperature coherence, optical readout, and quantum control. However, realizing NV-like behavior in more scalable or tunable host materials requires meeting a strict set of physical criteria - for both the host and the defect. The host must exhibit a sufficiently wide band gap, low spin-orbit coupling, and low natural abundance of nuclear spins, while offering high-quality crystal growth. The defect itself must support stable localized states, allow optical polarization and readout pathways, and exhibit deep levels isolated from host band edges to suppress decoherence.

In this work, we perform a first-principles screening of transition-metal-based defect complexes in wide band gap hosts. Specifically, we focus on substitutional defects M and nearest neighbor M-vacancy centers where M = Cu, Co, Ni, and Fe in two different host materials: ZnS and MgO. Using density functional theory, we characterize ground-state properties including formation energies, magnetic moments, charge-state stability, and defect-level positions. Particular focus is given to identifying charge-localized and spin-polarized in-gap states. We analyze both relaxed and unrelaxed structures across charge states to assess defect robustness. To address the well-known issue of band gap underestimation, we apply Hubbard correction parameters (PBE+U) where applicable. This framework is part of a broader search for deep-level color centers suitable for quantum information science and solid-state quantum sensing. Our findings serve to narrow the defect-host design space and identify promising candidates for host-defect pair for high-coherence spin centers with optically accessible transitions.

Keyword: *first-principles calculations, color centers, defect engineering*

Investigation of Nonlinear Optical Properties and Surface Behavior of Pristine and Zr-Doped ZnO Nanorods

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Among one-dimensional ZnO nanostructures, nanorods (NRs) are especially notable for their outstanding optical, electrical and piezoelectric properties [1]. When excited by a 532 nm laser, ZnO nanorods exhibit strong two-photon absorption and efficient second-harmonic generation, with significantly enhanced luminescence compared to their nanocrystalline counterparts. These characteristics make them strong candidates for applications in photonics and nonlinear optics.

In this study, ZnO seed layer was deposited on soda-lime glass and PDMS substrates via high-vacuum physical deposition (RF Magnetron sputtering) using a high-purity ZnO target at 60 W of power and for 9 min of deposition time. Al-doped ZnO (AZO) thin films were prepared using the same deposition method at 30 W of power for either 15 or 20 min of deposition time. Pristine and Zr-doped ZnO nanorods were prepared on the seed layer-coated substrates via a low-temperature hydrothermal synthesis method at 80°C for 3h. The linear optical properties and photoluminescence properties of pure and doped ZnO seed layers and nanorods were investigated. The optical band gap of the aluminum (Al) doped ZnO seed layer is 3.7 eV, while the optical band gap of the other samples varies between 3.0-3.3 eV. The reason for the change in the optical band gap may be the Burstein-Moss effect [2]. The nonlinear optical properties of pristine and Zr-doped ZnO nanorods were investigated by (nanosecond pulsed laser) OA Z scanning experiments at 532 nm wavelength. At this excitation wavelength energy corresponding to 2.33 eV, these experiments were performed at an INPUT power of 1 uJ for each nanostructure. ZnO nanorods have nonlinear optical properties, especially exhibiting two-photon absorption (TPA) mechanism. Zr doping increased the TPA effect by changing the free carrier density and defect levels. Using glass substrate instead of PDMS changed the transmittance and higher absorption effect was observed. Parameters such as morphological structure (nanorod vs. seed layer) and doping directly affected the NLO response of ZnO.

Fig.1 Open aperture (OA) Z-scan curves for pristine ZnO nanorod and Zr-doped ZnO nanostructures under an excitation wavelength of 532 nm at 1 input intensity

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Keyword: TPA, Nonlinear optical, ZnO, Nanorod, Z-scan,

Breaking the Te-plate: What Makes Sb₂Te₃ Stand Out?

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Phase Change Materials (PCM) are a class of materials that can reversibly switch between amorphous and crystalline phases. Their pronounced physical properties, such as electrical conductivity, optical reflectivity, and density [1], make them attractive candidates for emerging technologies. Phase transitions are fast and non-volatile, and ability to be triggered by external stimuli such as heat or electric pulses makes these materials intriguing candidates for a wide range applications, including thermal energy storage [2] and optical data storage [3].

Sb-Te based alloys play a central role among PCM because of good cycling performance and compatibility with prevalent semiconductors [3]. Although Ge₂Sb₂Te₅ (GST) and Sb₂Te₃ have been examined both theoretically and experimentally, despite their features such as thermal stability [4] and longer data retention [5], Sb-rich materials has not received as much attention.

In this study, we focused on, one of the Sb-rich compound, Sb₂Te₃ which has limited experimental characterization due to the metastable structure. First-principles calculations based on Density Functional Theory (DFT) provide a powerful and predictive framework for investigating the intrinsic properties of materials. In particular, we aim to evaluate the stability of the material, examine its electronic properties, and explore its potential role in phase-change dynamics by comparing it with other PCM. Our results are expected to contribute to the theoretical understanding of PCMs and to support the identification of new materials with optimized performance for memory and energy storage applications.

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Keyword: *Phase Change Materials, Sb₂Te₃, Density Functional Theory, Structural stability*

Smart Nanomaterials in Concrete: Toward High-Performance and Sustainable Construction Materials

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Concrete remains one of the most commonly used construction materials worldwide. However, the production of cement, the primary binding agent in concrete, significantly contributes to carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, releasing nearly two billion tons annually and accounting for around 7% of total global CO₂ output. It is estimated that by 2050, global cement production could reach six billion tons per year. This alarming projection has prompted widespread efforts to reduce the environmental and climatic consequences associated with cement manufacturing.

One promising strategy involves the incorporation of alternative materials into cementitious systems, particularly pozzolanic materials and nanomaterials. Among these, nanotechnology has gained increasing attention as a means of enhancing the sustainability and performance of concrete. The integration of nanomaterials into cement-based composites enables the development of next-generation concretes that not only deliver superior mechanical properties but also reduce the environmental footprint. These innovations are aligned with the broader goal of advancing sustainable construction practices and emphasize the vital role of nano-engineering in reducing the carbon impact of the construction industry. Various nanomaterials, including nano-silica (SiO₂), nano-alumina (Al₂O₃), nano-ferric oxide (Fe₂O₃), nano-titanium dioxide (TiO₂), graphene oxide (GO), and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have shown considerable potential in this regard. Due to their high surface area and chemical reactivity, these materials can significantly improve the compressive, tensile, and flexural strength of concrete, while also enhancing water resistance and workability. On a microstructural level, nanomaterials enhance the microstructure by occupying microscopic voids, resulting in tighter packing density and a refined interfacial transition zone. This densification reduces porosity and improves durability. Furthermore, nanoparticles accelerate cement hydration, promoting the formation of calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) gel, which is essential for strength development. Nanomaterials can be used alone or in conjunction with other reinforcing materials such as steel fibers, glass, rice husk powder, or fly ash. These combinations have been found to further enhance mechanical performance and decrease water permeability by improving the microstructure and accelerating the hydration process. Additionally, some nanomaterials offer crack-bridging capabilities and contribute to long-term durability by minimizing porosity and strengthening the integrity of the cement matrix.

Overall, nanomaterials present a transformative opportunity for designing high-performance, eco-friendly concretes that support sustainable construction. Their implementation underscores the promising potential of nano-engineering in reducing the carbon footprint of the cement and concrete industry. In the near future, addressing challenges related to scalability and cost-efficiency will be key to facilitating the broader adoption of nanomaterials in cementitious systems.

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Keyword: Nanometaterials, Cementitious Composites, Sustainable Concrete, C-S-H Gel

Production and Characterization of SiN/VO_x Thin Films on Flexible Substrates for Advanced Electronic Applications

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Integrating flexible electronic technologies with thin-film materials to develop functional properties at the nanoscale has become increasingly significant in fundamental science and technological research. Vanadium oxide (VO_x) thin films, due to their remarkable physical and chemical properties, have attracted considerable attention for flexible electronic applications. This study investigates the effect of thin silicon nitride (SiN) buffer layers (0–20 nm), deposited on polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyimide (PI), and polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) substrates, on the structural and electrical properties of VO_x films. The SiN and VO_x thickness range was selected based on preliminary laboratory optimization studies, and deposition was performed by the RF and DC reactive magnetron sputtering techniques. Resistance–temperature measurements exhibited clear substrate-dependent variations in the temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR). Films on PET substrates showed a general decreasing trend in TCR with increasing SiN thickness up to 6 nm (3.1 – 2.75 -%/K). PI-based films showed significant TCR reduction at lower SiN thicknesses (0– 1.5 nm), and at higher thicknesses (9 nm and above), TCR values showed stabilization and convergence toward a consistent value (2.8 – 2.9 -%/K). On the PEN substrate, TCR values increase from 2.43 to 3.1 (-%/K) up to 3 nm thickness and vary between 2.64 – 2.88 (-%/K) in the SiN thickness range of 6 – 12 nm. Highest TCR values have been measured for the SiN/VO_x thin films grown on PEN substrates. Structural analyses indicated that PET and PEN films with and without SiN buffer layers predominantly exhibited a V₂O₅ structure. Grain size determination found that PEN substrates exhibit smaller grain sizes, suggesting the formation of a more metallic vanadium oxide phase. However, X-ray diffraction confirmed that PI-based films were predominantly amorphous. Further structural analyses were performed to clarify the distinct metallic behavior observed in PEN-based films. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy revealed the coexistence of V₂O₅ and VO₂ phases on PEN substrates, with the relative abundance of V⁵⁺ and V⁴⁺ oxidation states significantly varying as a function of the SiN thickness, suggesting buffer-layer-dependent tuning. Analyses of the optical absorbance measurements revealed a dual optical energy gap. These results emphasize the significant role of substrate type and SiN buffer layer thickness in tuning the electrical and structural characteristics of flexible VO_x thin films. This research provides valuable guidelines for designing and optimizing flexible electronic materials, including bioelectronics and thermistor technologies.

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Keyword: Flexible substrates, Silicon nitride buffer layer, V₂O₅ and VO₂ phases, Magnetron Sputtering

Hydrophobic and Oleophobic Surfaces via a Simple and Fluorine-Free Candle Soot-Based Coating Method

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Superhydrophobic and oleophobic surfaces offer critical functionalities such as self-cleaning, anti-fogging, and resistance to contamination by preventing the adhesion of liquids such as water and oil [1]. The methods used to gain these properties, such as electrospinning, plasma etching etc., are often complex, or expensive[2]. In recent years, the candle soot-based coating method has emerged as an innovative and eco-friendly approach. This technique directly deposits nanostructured carbon soot layers, which exhibit low surface energy, onto glass or metal substrates.

Carbon soot, generated in the intermediate zone of a candle flame, adheres to surfaces, forming a highly rough micro/nanostructure. This architecture allows water droplets to roll off easily, achieving water contact angles exceeding 150° and imparting superhydrophobicity to the surface. In recent studies, the potential of candle soot particles has been explored for diverse applications. For example, Huang et al. Modified candle soot with 1H, 1H, 2H, 2H-perfluorooctanol for use as a lubricant additive [3]; Schmäser et al. investigated protein adsorption resistance on tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS)-coated candle soot layers prepared via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [4]; and Qahtan et al. developed a superhydrophobic coating by spraying a candle soot dispersion, demonstrating excellent water resistance and thermal stability [5]. However, these methods often rely on fluorinated materials, which pose significant environmental and health risks and involve high costs and toxic reagents. Therefore, in this study, we developed a simple and time-efficient method for fabricating a candle soot-based hydrophobic and oleophobic coating using the fluorine-free and cost-effective octadecyltrichlorosilane (OTS). To improve the weak adhesion of the soot layer, silica (SiO₂) nanoparticles were deposited onto the surface via CVD. The resulting stable hydrophobic coating acquired oleophobic properties through the hydrolysis of OTS, which chemically bonded to the surface containing both carbon and silica particles. The surface morphology of the coatings was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and wettability properties were evaluated via static contact angle measurements. The results demonstrated that this fluorine-free platform can successfully impart both hydrophobic and oleophobic characteristics in environmentally friendly water and oil-repellent surfaces, showing great potential for practical applications.

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Keyword: *Candle soot coating, SiO₂ particle, hydrophobic and oleophobic surfaces*

Robust CVD-Deposited Thin Films for Protecting QD-Sensor Nanoprobes

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Semiconductor nanoparticles, or quantum dots (QDs), are widely used in various sensor applications due to their wide absorption and narrow emission spectra, high quantum efficiency, photo-bleaching resistance, and high photochemical stability compared to other fluorophores [1-3]. Depending on the application of the sensor, quantum dots (QDs) are exposed to various solvents or physical conditions that can impact their performance and reduce their lifetime [4]. A great deal of interest has arisen in encapsulating QDs against physical damage and corrosion in sensor applications to protect their fluorescence properties. An ideal protective polymer coating for encapsulation should have excellent chemical stability and high mechanical strength. Wet processes are commonly used methods to fabricate polymer coating for surface protection. However, these methods suffer from the degradation of substrate materials due to solvents and catalysts and the generation of impurities. Today, dry processes such as solventless vapor phase deposition methods are most commonly used techniques for protective coating applications. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) is suitable technique to fabricate the thin cross-linked polymer coatings [5]. Here, we present the fabrication of copolymer thin films of glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) and ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA) via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) as protective encapsulation coatings for QD-bonded surfaces. The chemical stability and corrosion resistance of the films were evaluated in various solvents. The fluorescence properties of the quantum dots (QDs) were investigated after exposure to a corrosive medium. The results showed that the cross-linked thin films developed to protect sensor structures exhibited high chemical resistance to strong organic solvents. Furthermore, the encapsulation process used to protect the sensor nanoprobe did not affect the performance of the QD fluorescence in the sensor structure. These results demonstrate that the chemical vapor deposition process can be employed to fabricate cross-linked copolymer conformal coatings to protect QD-based sensor nanoprobes against harsh conditions. Furthermore, it can be concluded that this study is pioneering in the field of sensor structure protection.

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Keyword: *quantum dots (QDs), sensor nanoprobe, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), Protective polymer coating*

Development and Characterization of a UV-Curable Polyurea-Based Hydrogel for 3D Bioprinting of Skeletal Muscle Scaffolds

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Although skeletal muscle possesses a natural capacity for self-repair, recovery is limited in cases of extensive traumatic injury or congenital conditions leading to volumetric muscle loss. In such scenarios, tissue engineering presents a promising therapeutic strategy for muscle regeneration by integrating scaffolds, bioactive molecules, and cells. A major challenge remains in developing constructs that replicate the mechanical and structural properties of native skeletal muscle for 3D bioprinting applications.

Synthetic polymers such as polycaprolactone (PCL) often lack sufficient hydrophilicity, elasticity, and bioactivity, while hydrogels typically fall short in mechanical strength. However, novel biomaterials can bridge this gap by offering tunable properties suitable for skeletal muscle scaffolding [1].

In this study, a novel polyurea-based (PU) biomaterial was developed and characterized for its structural, mechanical, and biological properties. The material was formulated as a bioink and evaluated for UV-curability under a 405 nm light source by varying PU and lithium phenyl-2,4,6-trimethylbenzoylphosphinate (LAP) concentrations and exposure times. Rheological analyses were conducted to assess viscoelastic behavior, and the swelling ratio and weight loss after 7-day hydrolytic degradation were measured. Print fidelity was evaluated using the EnvisionTEC 3D Bioplotter.

Mechanical properties were assessed via uniaxial tensile testing using a 50 N load cell at a rate of 10 mm/min. Scaffolds were seeded with C2C12 myoblast cells at a density of 5,000 cells/ μ L and incubated under standard culture conditions for seven days. Cell viability was assessed, and cytoskeletal organization was visualized using Phalloidin/DAPI staining.

Results confirmed that the PU-based hydrogel containing 25% PU and 0.01% LAP is UV-curable, biodegradable, water-soluble, 3D-printable, and cytocompatible. Tensile testing revealed mechanical properties comparable to those of native skeletal muscle. Furthermore, C2C12 cells remained viable on the scaffold, underscoring the material's suitability for skeletal muscle tissue engineering and its potential for future clinical applications.

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Keyword: 3D bioprinting, Tissue engineering, Polymeric nano-biomaterials

Peptide Encapsulated and 3D Printable Hydrogels as Polymeric Biomaterial Inks and Their *in vitro* Evaluations

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In this project, natural polymers with biocompatible and biomimetic scaffolds were used to give specific shapes using a 3D bioprinter, especially for application in bone tissue engineering. These natural polymers were modified with methacrylic anhydride so that they could be crosslinked under UV light (365 nm) during the 3D printing process. In addition, the methacrylated polymers were mixed with a synthetic biodegradable polymer PEGdiMA (Poly(ethylene glycol)di Methacrylate) to improve the mechanical strength of the hydrogels. These hydrogels were encapsulated with a peptide, specific to bone cell adhesion. This peptide includes 4 aminoacid KRSR motifs in its structure and was synthesized via a solid phase peptide synthesis method. By encapsulating the KRSR (osteoblast adhesive peptide) in the polymers, it was possible to immobilize the peptide into the final hydrogel. The obtained 3D bioprintable hydrogels were characterized for their swelling capacity in water, and chemical integrity via FT-IR Spectroscopy, together with its morphological Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and mechanical (rheometer) properties. Regarding the *in vitro* analysis, the cytotoxic effect of prepared hydrogels has been investigated against mouse fibroblasts (L929 cell line) via CCK-8 assay and it was demonstrated that prepared hydrogels of various combinations of both natural and synthetic polymers provided more than 70 % cell viability, after which the cell adhesion assay was performed against hFOB 1.19 human fetal osteoblast cell line in a time-dependent manner via live/dead fluorescent imaging-based assay and mineralization rate was determined by Alizarin Red S staining.

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Keyword: *Hydrogels, Natural Polymers, 3D Bioprinting, Peptide encapsulated Hydrogels, KRSR, osteoblasts*

Design and Characterization of PVA/H₃PO₄ Hydrogel-Based Triboelectric Nanogenerators for Wearable Energy Harvesting Applications

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With the growing need for sustainable and flexible energy sources in wearable electronics, triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) have emerged as a promising technology for converting mechanical energy into electricity. This work focuses on the development of a flexible TENG composed of a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)/H₃PO₄ hydrogel as the triboelectric layer and a composite of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) with reduced graphene oxide (RGO) as the conductive electrode layer. The analyses on the developed films confirmed the hydrogel structure, strong hydrogen bonding, and a porous network structure favorable for triboelectric interactions. We expect that the incorporation of the PVDF/RGO electrode in future steps will enhance the electrical conductivity and charge transfer within the TENG, contributing to higher energy conversion efficiency. The ionic conductivity and flexibility of the hydrogel, along with its compatibility with human skin, make it suitable for integration into wearable formats. This research aims to contribute to the field of self-powered electronics by demonstrating the potential of hydrogel-based TENGs in energy-autonomous wearable systems. Such devices hold great promise for real-time health and fitness monitoring applications, including motion detection, heart rate sensing, and muscle activity tracking.

Keyword: *Triboelectric nanogenerator (TENG), reduced graphene oxide (RGO), PVA hydrogel, PVDF*

Novel Sulfonated Poly(Ether Ether Ketone) Based Green Nanocomposite As An Alternative Material For Proton Exchange Membrane

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Proton exchange membranes are among the most critical components in energy applications like flow batteries and fuel cell systems. Although commercial Nafion membranes are widely used, their high cost and potential to release environmentally harmful polyfluoroalkyl compounds often limit their broader applicability.

In the present study, a sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone) (SPEEK)-based nanocomposite membrane was developed by incorporating multiwalled carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and the biopolymer lignin, offering a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to commercial Nafion membranes. A specific degree of sulfonation (DS) of the PEEK polymer was optimized. CNTs and wood-derived lignin were uniformly dispersed within the synthesized SPEEK polymer matrix. The resulting blend was used to fabricate a membrane via drop casting, and was subsequently characterized for its physicochemical, thermal, and morphological properties.

The abundant hydroxyl groups in lignin structure facilitated uniform dispersion within the SPEEK matrix, promoted the formation of proton transport pathways. Furthermore, the synergistic effect of these hydroxyl groups and the tubular structure of CNTs contributed to enhanced proton conductivity.

This low-cost, environment-friendly nanocomposite membrane demonstrates strong potential as a next-generation proton exchange membrane for energy applications, providing a viable alternative to Nafion.

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Keyword: *SPEEK, lignin, CNT, proton exchange membrane*

Rapid and Local Photothermal Self-healing of Thermoplastic Polyurethane/BiSn Composites

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The development of intelligent self-healing materials has gained increasing attention in recent years due to their ability to autonomously repair damage, thereby enhancing durability and extending material lifespan. Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) is one of the most promising candidates for self-healing applications, thanks to its tunable chemical structure, favorable mechanical properties, and commercial availability. In this study, a novel approach is presented for developing photothermal self-healing TPU composites by incorporating Bismuth–Tin (BiSn) core–shell particles into the TPU matrix. These BiSn particles exhibit strong broadband light absorption with high absorption rates (75-80%) and can reach temperatures of up to 150 °C within seconds under infrared (IR) irradiation, enabling localized heating for efficient damage repair.

A key advantage of the BiSn core–shell structure is that it allows direct dispersion in TPU solutions without requiring additional surface modifications or stabilizers. This feature not only simplifies the preparation process but also permits the use of BiSn in very low concentrations and minimizing the impact on the transparency and better mechanical properties of the final material. In this study, TPU/BiSn composites with different initial TPU compositions were prepared by solvent cast and hot press. The photothermal response, mechanical performance, and self-healing behavior of the resulting films were systematically evaluated.

The results demonstrate that composites prepared via hot pressing and with higher initial TPU concentrations exhibit enhanced mechanical strength and photothermal efficiency. Notably, the TPU/BiSn films with 20 wt% TPU and only 0.5 wt% BiSn achieved a high tensile strength of approximately 38 MPa and exhibited excellent self-healing performance under IR light (3 W/cm²), with healing times under 5 minutes. These findings highlight the potential of BiSn-based photothermal fillers as efficient and scalable solutions for developing transparent, high-performance self-healing TPU composites for advanced material applications.

Keyword: *photothermal materials, self-healing composites, BiSn core–shell particles*

Photothermal Self-healing of TPU Composites Enabled by BiSn Liquid Metal-Derived Core-Shell Particles

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The development of smart self-healing materials has gained increasing attention in recent years due to their ability to autonomously repair damage, thereby enhancing durability and extending material lifespan. Here, we present a novel approach for developing photothermal self-healing TPU composites by incorporating Bismuth–Tin (BiSn) core-shell particles into the TPU matrix. These BiSn particles were recently reported to exhibit strong broadband light absorption with high absorption rates [1]. Moreover, their core-shell structures possess unique properties when used in composites by strong particle-polymer interactions [2].

Our study revealed a key advantage of the BiSn core-shell structure, which allows for the homogeneous dispersion of particles in TPU solutions without requiring additional surface modifications or stabilizers. This feature not only simplifies the preparation process but also enables the use of BiSn in very low concentrations, resulting in improved mechanical properties and the preservation of transparency at a certain level. TPU/BiSn composite samples were prepared using various compositions and with different techniques. The TPU/BiSn films prepared with a very small amount of BiSn particles showed up to twice the tensile strength of the pure TPU film, and composite film exhibited excellent self-healing performance under IR light with healing times under 5 minutes. These findings highlight the potential of BiSn-based photothermal fillers as efficient and scalable solutions for developing transparent, high-performance self-healing TPU composites for advanced material applications.

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Keyword: *Self-healing composites, Bismuth-Tin Core Shell Particles, Photothermal self healing, Photothermal materials*

Cold Plasma-Assisted Development of a Hybrid Electrochemical Sensor for Ultra-Trace Detection of Ribavirin in Serum and Pharmaceutical Samples

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The precise and sensitive measurement of antiviral agents, including ribavirin (RIBA), is essential for effective therapeutic monitoring and clinical applications, particularly during pandemics such as COVID-19. This study presents the development of a novel electrochemical sensor utilizing molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) technology, achieved through a cold plasma-assisted polymerization technique. Bimetallic magnetic nanoparticles (FeNPs and AuNPs) were used to enhance sensor performance. The MIP@FeNP-AuNP/SPE sensor exhibited high sensitivity and selectivity for RIBA detection, achieving ultra-trace detection limits of 4.92×10^{-15} and 5.23×10^{-14} for standard solutions and serum samples, respectively, in both standard solutions and synthetic serum matrices. Analytical validation demonstrated high reproducibility, stability over six months, and effective application to pharmaceutical formulations. The sensor performance was cross-validated through UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis, and statistical evaluation indicated no significant difference between the two methods. This approach offers a viable alternative to conventional chromatographic techniques, delivering a portable, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable platform for the monitoring of antiviral drugs.

Keyword: *cold plasma, ribavirin, COVID-19, molecularly imprinted polymer*

Organic - Inorganic Collaboration : Borophene meets PEDOT:PSS for X-ray Detection

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Freestanding borophene multilayers (BMLs) were matched with a conducting polymer, PEDOT:PSS, in an acetone medium. It is evident from the results obtained from Hall measurements that the synthesized polymer (PEDOT:PSS) exhibited n-type characteristics. This is conducive to the formation of a structure analogous to a p-n junction with borophene, a p-type material characterised by a high degree of electron deficiency. Current-voltage plots of BML-doped and undoped PEDOT:PSS structures were obtained in the dark. The decline in these graphs, consequent to elevated BML doping, can be interpreted as indicative of this phenomenon. The unbonded orbitals of borophene have been identified as a significant recombination centre for PEDOT:PSS electrons. However, the situation is not as dire as it may appear, as these recombined charges are separated under high-energy photons, such as X-rays, thereby increasing the conductivity of the BML-doped structure. Basic detector parameters, such as sensitivity and noise equivalent dosing, were calculated from the typical current-voltage curves obtained. The results are encouraging for employing such hybrid structures in the presence of high-energy radiation.

Keyword: *hybrid structures, borophene, x-ray detection*

Structurally Engineered PVA-Based Hybrid Coatings with Hierarchical Organic–Inorganic Nanofillers for Enhanced Thermal and Surface Properties

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Polymeric coatings incorporating multifunctional nanofillers have gained increasing attention for their tunable properties and versatile applications in advanced materials engineering.¹ In this study, a series of poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)-based hybrid coatings were fabricated via a dip-coating technique, using a combination of Laponite clay, poly(maleic anhydride-alt-N-vinyl caprolactam) copolymer (H2), and organically modified montmorillonite (H3-Org-MMT) as hierarchical structuring agents. The H2 copolymer was synthesized through bulk polymerization, while H3-Org-MMT nanofillers were incorporated at optimized concentrations to promote interfacial compatibility and nanostructure formation.^{2,3} The coating formulations—ranging from binary (e.g., PVA-Lap, PVA-H2-Lap) to ternary and quaternary hybrids (e.g., PVA-H2-H3, PVA-H2-H3-Lap)—enabled a systematic study of the synergistic effects between organic and inorganic constituents. Comprehensive characterization techniques, including Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), were employed to evaluate the physicochemical interactions, thermal resistance, crystallinity, and surface morphology of the nanocomposite systems. Results demonstrated that the incorporation of H2 and H3-Org-MMT, as well as their combination with Laponite, contributed to enhanced thermal stability and improved surface features. These findings support the applicability of tailored PVA-based nanocomposites in coating technologies where both thermal performance and structural properties are critical.

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Keyword: *nanofiller, nanocomposite, laponite, surface coating*

Tailoring Mechanical Response in Poly(vinyl alcohol)–Bentonite Nanocomposite Films via Spatial Layer Architecture

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Monolithic polymer films often lack the mechanical versatility required for advanced applications, particularly when both high strength and adequate toughness are needed. To address this limitation, standalone poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)–bentonite (BNT) nanocomposite films with spatially varied mechanical properties were fabricated using a cost-effective and reproducible petri-dish casting method. Pre-mixed PVA/BNT stock solutions with clay contents ranging from 0 to 25 wt% were used to construct three-layer films with distinct architectures: uniform (identical BNT content in each layer), sandwich (high–low–high), and gradient (low–high–low). Initial doctor blade casting of films with 0–30 wt% BNT confirmed the successful production of crack-free, homogeneous films, with increasing tensile strength observed as BNT loading increased. These observations laid the foundation for layered designs aiming to optimize strength–toughness balance through architectural control.

To probe the localized mechanical behavior of these multilayered films, cyclic instrumented nanoindentation was applied by incrementally increasing load at the same position, revealing depth-dependent mechanical properties and interlayer interactions. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine BNT platelet orientation and interfacial continuity between layers. In addition, depth-sensing nanoindentation mapping was performed to spatially resolve elastic modulus and hardness distributions across different architectures. This comparative approach enables the evaluation of structure–property relationships in layered polymer nanocomposites and aims to identify configurations that optimize mechanical performance without sacrificing simplicity in fabrication. The outcomes of this study are expected to guide the design of next-generation flexible coatings, barrier membranes, and functional structural films with tunable mechanical responses.

Keyword: *Nanocomposites, Layered films, Nanoindentation mapping*

Dye Removal from Water Using PMMA/PEG-Based Composite Fibers as Adsorbent

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Recognized as one of the most versatile and efficient techniques for the fabrication of fibers with diameters ranging from the micro to nanoscale, electrospinning was employed to fabricate polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)/polyethylene glycol (PEG)-based composite fibers containing inorganic additives such as halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) and boron phosphate (BPO₄). It was aimed to investigate the influence of these additives on the morphological characteristics and dye adsorption capacities of the electrospun fibers. Zeta potential measurements were also applied to analyze the surface charge density of the samples. Furthermore, adsorption test results were evaluated using kinetic models to better understand the adsorption mechanism and rate-controlling steps involved.

SEM analysis revealed that the incorporation of PEG into the PMMA solution led to a reduction in average fiber diameter of neat PMMA, and promoted the formation of a beaded fiber morphology. It was observed that the addition of 5 wt. % HNT or BPO₄ caused an increase in the average diameter of PMMA/PEG fibers. The produced composite fibers were tested for the capability to adsorb methylene blue (MB) from aqueous solutions. Zeta potential analyses demonstrated that the produced composite fibers carried a negative surface charge, thus an enhanced adsorption capacity was observed for MB, being a cationic dye. The incorporation of HNT and BPO₄ to the PMMA/PEG solution significantly improved the dye adsorption capacities of the samples. Among them, PMMA/PEG/BPO₄ composite with 5 wt. % BPO₄ was chosen for detailed kinetic studies. Three well-known kinetic models; pseudo-first-order, pseudo-second-order and intra-particle diffusion models were employed to the experimental data, and the adsorption kinetics were accurately modelled by the pseudo-second-order equation with a strong correlation.

Keyword: Composite Fibers, Electrospinning, Dye Adsorption, PMMA, Additives

Design, Simulation, and Fabrication of MEMS-Based Gas Sensors With Different Sensing Layers

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Metal oxide (MOX)-based chemiresistive gas sensors are widely investigated due to their simplicity, miniaturization potential, and high sensitivity to a broad range of target gases. This work presents the design, thermal simulation, and microfabrication of a MEMS-based gas sensor incorporating TiO_x and WO_x thin films as gas-sensitive layers. The aim is to enhance sensing performance through material selection and optimized heater architecture. All fabrication processes were carried out at METU MEMS Center using cleanroom standard procedures.

The sensor structure features a co-planar layout where both the resistive heater and the interdigitated electrodes (IDTs) are integrated onto the same layer. The heater combines fan-shaped and meander geometries to achieve efficient thermal distribution with reduced power consumption. The device stack includes a silicon substrate, insulating SiO₂, platinum-based heater and electrode lines, and a thin MOX film deposited via reactive DC magnetron sputtering. Although the current structure is substrate-supported, future versions will explore suspended membrane configurations for improved thermal isolation.

Stationary thermal simulations were performed using COMSOL Multiphysics with coupled Heat Transfer in Solids and Electric Currents modules to assess the temperature distribution resulting from Joule heating. Simulations demonstrated uniform thermal profiles at operating voltages compatible with low-power consumption, targeting an effective sensing temperature range of 20–400°C.

Fabrication was completed using standard microfabrication techniques including photolithography, PECVD, sputtering, and wet/dry etching steps. The fabricated structures were characterized using SEM, profilometry, and electrical resistance measurements to evaluate film uniformity, electrode integrity, and heater functionality.

Keyword: *MEMS gas sensor, microfabrication, TiO_x, WO_x*

Alcohol-Free Hand Sanitizer Production via Green Synthesis of Ag@CH NPs

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This project focuses on the green synthesis of core-shell silver-chitosan nanoparticles (Ag@CH NPs) for use in a novel, alcohol-free hand sanitizer with strong antimicrobial performance. The core silver nanoparticles were synthesized using a sustainable route involving orange peel extract (OPE), which acts as both a reducing and stabilizing agent thanks to its high flavonoid and phenolic content. This approach valorizes citrus waste and aligns with principles of the circular economy. Following green reduction, the nanoparticles were encapsulated with chitosan to improve colloidal stability, prevent agglomeration, and enable controlled silver ion release—thereby enhancing safety and antibacterial efficacy. Characterization of the nanoparticles via UV-Vis spectroscopy, particle size analysis, and zeta potential measurements confirmed successful synthesis. AgNPs and Ag@CH NPs exhibited sizes of approximately 11.4 nm and 34.7 nm, respectively, with zeta potentials indicating strong electrostatic stability. In antibacterial assays against *Staphylococcus aureus*, the Ag@CH NPs embedded in a gel matrix exhibited superior inhibition zones compared to silver- or chitosan-only formulations, confirming a synergistic antimicrobial mechanism. The final hand sanitizer is designed to meet the needs of sensitive users, including children, healthcare workers, and populations with religious or dermatological restrictions regarding alcohol. Formulated without parabens or harsh chemicals, the gel is lightly citrus-scented, pH-compatible with skin, and produced using bio-based materials. The study demonstrates how green nanotechnology can enable safe, effective, and sustainable hygiene products, and offers promising directions for scalable, eco-conscious biotechnology applications.

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Keyword: *green synthesis, core-shell nanoparticles, antibacterial activity, core-shell (Ag@CH) nanoparticles*

Optimization of the Slurry Formulation for Direct Ink Writing of High-Density Alumina Ceramics

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Direct ink writing (DIW) is a promising additive manufacturing technique for the cost-effective fabrication of a wide range of materials. Producing high-density alumina ceramics relies on the stability and dispersion of the high solid loading suspensions. In this study, we investigated the use of a dispersant known to effectively stabilize concentrated nano-alumina systems, applying it to submicron alumina powders. The formulation was carefully optimized to minimize the total organic content in the suspension. The relationship between suspension properties and the printing process, as well as the density and microstructure of the sintered parts, was investigated. The optimal formulation resulted in suspensions that could be extruded smoothly through narrow channels, eliminating clogging during extrusion and preventing crack formation in green bodies. Different geometries, including cubes, cylinders, and tubes, were successfully printed, and sintered densities exceeding 97% of the theoretical density were achieved, which demonstrated the effectiveness of the dispersant in achieving high density with low organic content in fine alumina systems.

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Keyword: *ink formulation, ceramic suspension, rheology, additive manufacturing of ceramics*

CsPbBr₃ Perovskite Nanocrystal Scintillators for High-Resolution Medical Imaging

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Scintillators convert ionizing radiation, such as X-rays, into lower-energy photons, making them suitable for various applications, including medical imaging. However, radiation-induced carcinogenesis remains a known risk associated with ionizing radiation in medical contexts. This is a stochastic effect, meaning that the probability of harm increases with radiation dose. Conventional bulk scintillators often have limited radiative recombination efficiency, requiring higher radiation doses to achieve high spatial resolution. This study aims to develop a perovskite-type nanocrystal scintillator that provides high-resolution imaging at lower X-ray doses, enabling safer and more efficient medical imaging. Cesium lead bromide (CsPbBr₃) perovskite nanocrystals are selected for their intrinsic high light yield, fast decay, and large Stokes shift, satisfying key design parameters for medical imaging scintillators. To address the issues of lead leakage and nanocrystal instability, CsPbBr₃ was embedded into a polystyrene (PS) matrix, chosen for its high optical transparency. To improve colloidal stability, CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals were surface-passivated with soy lecithin, a plant-derived, zwitterionic ligand whose long hydrocarbon chains enhance dispersion in nonpolar solvents. Lecithin-capped CsPbBr₃ films were produced via doctor-blade coating on glass substrates under ambient conditions, yielding uniform composites suitable for imaging tests. Furthermore, characterization results of UV–Vis absorption, photoluminescence spectra, zeta-sizer, and X-ray diffraction measurements matched the relevant studies in the literature. Under 30 keV X-ray excitation, an energy in the recommended range for dental imaging and mammography, the lecithin-capped films produced highly resolved images of a dental specimen and an embedded needle in a chicken breast at reduced exposure, while 50 keV tests resolved sub-millimeter features comparable to or better than commercial bulk scintillators. Theoretical light-yield calculations predict ~73,770 photons/MeV, placing this study among the top-performing scintillator materials.

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Keyword: *scintillators, perovskite nanocrystals, optoelectronics, x-ray imaging*

Electrochemical Preparation of Cu/Fe-Ni Microwires and Their Potential as Micromotors

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Micromotors are small-scale devices designed to convert energy into movement at the micro- and nanoscale level, with their design continuously improving due to advancements in materials and fabrication methods [1-2]. In this research, we present the creation of wire-like structures made from segmented copper (Cu) and iron-nickel (Fe-Ni) components. The microwire structures were produced using a template-assisted electrodeposition method within anodic alumina oxide (AAO) membranes. After the deposition process, the wires were separated from the membrane by dissolving and washing steps. The structural characterization was carried out using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), while compositional analysis was performed with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The movement behavior of the microwires when actuated by magnetic forces was examined using video tracking in order to investigate their use as micromotors. Additionally, L-cysteine modification was carried out and surface charges were followed by zeta potential measurements. The findings highlight the potential of segmented Cu/Fe-Ni micromotors as adaptable microdevices suitable for diverse applications.

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Keyword: *Magnetic micromotors, electrochemical fabrication, metallic-based structures*

pH-Responsive Fe₃O₄@Ag Core-Shell Nanowire Hydrogels for In-Body Sensing

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pH-responsive Hydrogels, three-dimensional crosslinked polymeric network systems that are able to absorb large amounts of water, have become the center of attention, especially for biomedical applications, due to their high biocompatibility, water permeability, stimuli responsiveness, self-healing characteristics, flexibility, and soft structure [1]. On the other hand, pH-responsive conductive hydrogels possess all of the benefits of this system together with conductivity, which makes them a very popular alternative in the application of biosensors, bioelectronics, and soft robotics, [2].

In this work, we explore the potential use of magnetoplasmonic Fe₃O₄@Ag core-shell nanowires as pH-responsive resonators for wireless sensing applications in high-frequency bioelectronics. These nanowires offer multifunctionality due to their magnetic and plasmonic characteristics, enabling both signal transduction and mechanical tracking within biological environments. First, the AgNWs bearing 72 nm diameter and 9.5 μm lengths are synthesized according to the polyol method [3]. Afterwards, the magnetoplasmonic Fe₃O₄@Ag core-shell nanowires are synthesized by a facile and effective coprecipitation method in aqueous medium [4]. Finally, the Fe₃O₄@Ag core-shell nanowire-based acrylic acid/acrylamide/polyethylene glycol diacrylate (AgNW/P(AAm-co-AAc-co-PEGDA)) hydrogels are synthesized via free radical polymerization. The 16 nm thick Fe₃O₄ shell enables tracking of the hydrogel's mechanical state in situ through magnetic particle imaging, while plasmonic AgNW ensures the high conductivity. The synthesized hydrogels possess enhanced mechanical and electrical characteristics, which make them a promising material for in-body pH sensing applications.

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Keyword: Fe₃O₄@Ag Core-shell Nanowires, pH-responsive Hydrogels

Functional Group Engineering of Calixarene Fibers for High-Performance TENG Devices

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Triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) have emerged as promising candidates for harvesting ambient mechanical energy to power low-energy devices, particularly in wearable electronics and healthcare monitoring. By eliminating frequent battery changes, these self-powered systems simplify daily life and expand the reach of the Internet of Things (IoT). However, the performance of TENGs heavily depends on the selection and the modification of triboelectric materials, which must be carefully engineered to optimize the charge generating ability of these pairs. Tailoring material combinations allows for the development of efficient, application-specific TENG systems suited for modern self-powered technologies. Herein, we report on the triboelectric effect of various electrospun calixarene fibers, where the calixarene molecules differ in their functional groups either by identity or positional isomerism. Although the base structure remains the same, the subtle variations in the functional groups significantly influenced the triboelectric performance. Triboelectric tests in contact-separation mode against poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) showed that calixarene fibers generated open-circuit voltages (Voc) ranging from 12.5 to 65 V and short-circuit currents (Isc) between 130 to 850 nA, depending on their chemical structures. These findings demonstrate that even small molecular modifications in calixarene compounds can dramatically alter triboelectric output, offering valuable insights into molecular-level design strategies for next-generation TENGs. The functionalized calixarenes provide a versatile platform for efficient energy harvesting and high-performance, self-powered wearable and IoT devices.

Keyword: *Triboelectric Nanogenerators, Calixarene, Energy Harvesting*

Electrochemically Synthesized Polypyrrole/Kaolin Composite for Aqueous Zinc-Ion Battery

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This study involves the electrochemical synthesis of kaolin-doped polypyrrole (PPy/kaolin) on the surface of a graphite disk electrode, the investigation of its electrochemical behavior in Na₂SO₄ solution, and its use as an electrode material in a zinc aqueous ion battery. The synthesis of PPy/kaolin composite as an electrode active material, the determination of its capacitive properties, and its testing within a cell constitute the main originality of this work. Kaolin, a clay mineral with the chemical formula Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄, has a structure consisting of tetrahedral (silica) and octahedral (alumina) layers, is chemically inert, and features low shrinkage-expansion capacity, as well as high-temperature resistance. Due to its fine particle size and layered structure, kaolin increases the mechanical strength of composites and makes them lightweight and robust. When used as an additive in electrodes or electrolytes in batteries, kaolin, being hydrophilic and having high ionic conductivity, large surface area, and porosity, facilitates ion transport, increases efficiency, and improves heat distribution. Thus, it enables the production of high-performance and durable energy storage systems. PPy/kaolin film was coated onto the graphite disk surface using the constant current technique in an acetonitrile solution containing kaolin and pyrrole monomer, and FESEM characterized the coating. The capacitive properties of the coating were determined in a 1 M Na₂SO₄ aqueous solution by recording cyclic voltammograms (CV) at various scan rates. In the final part of the study, PPy/kaolin was synthesized on the graphite disk electrode surface, and its capacitive properties were investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV) at various scan rates in environments containing ZnCl₂, ZnCH₃SO₃, and ZnSO₄ solutions as electrolytes. Subsequently, a zinc aqueous battery cell prepared using zinc foil and graphite paper coated with PPy/kaolin—displaying the best capacitive properties in the selected zinc salt—was tested using CV, galvanostatic charge/discharge, and EIS.

Keyword: *Polypyrrole, kaoline, aqueous zinc ion battery, Electrochemical Synthesis*

VO₂ Doped Nanogenerators For High Temperature Applications

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Light and flexible piezoelectric nanogenerators (PENGs) are regarded as promising power sources for wearable and distributed sensors. The output of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) degrades above 40°C due to the depoling of highly electroactive β -phase. Vanadium dioxide (both VO₂ and V₂O₅) is a promising additive for PVDF to enhance the electrical properties. VO₂ undergoes a reversible semiconductor-to-metal transition around 70°C, evaluated as a thermally responsive filler to bolster PVDF performance at elevated temperatures and is being benchmarked against the more common oxide, V₂O₅. In this study, commercial V₂O₅ and VO₂ powders were integrated in PVDF to form nanocomposite films and fibers. Preliminary data shows that the open-circuit voltage of films was recorded as 8.8 V for pristine PVDF and 19.5 V for V₂O₅ incorporated PVDF films. This doubling effect is attributed to enhanced dipole alignment and interfacial polarisation. Through this preliminary result, a marked enhancement of PVDF-based PENGs by the introduction of vanadium oxides to the system has been demonstrated even before VO₂'s phase transition; therefore, further benefits are expected.

Keyword: *PVDF nanocomposites, piezoelectric nanogenerator, vanadium dioxide (VO₂), flexible energy harvesting*

Development of 3D Carbon Structures: An Additive-Free Solution for Advanced Energy

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Graphene, a fascinating two-dimensional carbon material, exhibits exceptional mechanical strength and electrical conductivity, along with a tunable surface area theoretically reaching $2630 \text{ m}^2\text{-g}^{-1}$. These properties make it a highly promising candidate for the development of high-performance electrochemical supercapacitors (ESCs) [1-3]. Moreover, the residual oxygen-containing functional groups on reduced graphene oxide (RGO) sheets enhance their processability and introduce additional functionalities to the graphene surface [4]. The electrochemical performance of RGO-based supercapacitors largely depends on the electrode microstructure. To achieve optimal device performance, electrodes must possess high electrical conductivity and well-designed micro/nano architectures that facilitate efficient electron and ion transport. Notably, supercapacitors utilizing self-assembled RGO hydrogels with interconnected three-dimensional networks demonstrate both high specific capacitance and excellent rate capability [5]. This study presents a novel electrode architecture, achieved by the successful deposition of three-dimensional (3D) reduced graphene hydrogel (RGH) structures onto a nickel foam (NF) substrate, resulting in outstanding electrochemical performance. Through a meticulously optimized synthesis process, an RGH/NF electrode was fabricated, exhibiting the highest specific surface area ever reported in the literature ($2424.5 \text{ m}^2\text{-g}^{-1}$). This electrode delivers an impressive specific capacitance of $1208 \text{ F}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at a scan rate of $5 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The findings indicate that the direct interface between the RGH and NF enhances electrical conductivity and facilitates more efficient ion transport within the electrode structure. These results suggest that 3D RGH-based electrodes hold significant promise as practical, high-performance candidates for next-generation supercapacitor applications.

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Keyword: Graphene, Hydrogel, Supercapacitor

Dual-Functional Additives Enabling Water Scavenging and Solvation Modulation for High Performance Mg Metal Batteries

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Magnesium (Mg) metal batteries have attracted significant attention as post-lithium batteries owing to their high energy density and crustal abundance. Unfortunately, the insulating passivation layer on Mg electrode such as MgO and MgF₂, along with uneven Mg deposition, not only raises the significant voltage hysteresis but also decreases the cycling lifespan. Furthermore, the presence of trace impurities such as water are inevitably present in the electrolyte, which can adversely affect electrochemical performance, i.e. accelerating passivation and inhibiting Mg cation transport. To address these issues, tuning solvation with a functional additive promotes the formation of a passivation layer favorable for Mg deposition, yet it remains insufficient for removing water. Herein, we employed an imidazole derivative capable of simultaneously regulating the solvation structure and exhibiting an impurity-scavenging effect to enable the construction of a nanoscale interfacial layer. This compound potentially replaces diglyme solvent (G2) in coordination with Mg cation and undergoes hydrolysis upon exposure to trace water, leading to effective impurity removal and enabling passivation-free Mg deposition. Consequently, reversible plating and stripping of Mg is demonstrated with a low overpotential of 0.35V up to 500 cycles at 1.0 mA cm⁻² and 0.2 mAh cm⁻², coupled with a high Coulombic efficiency in Cu||Mg half cells. This work can shed light on the design and control of functional nanointerfaces, contributing to the broader development of nanotechnology-enabled battery systems.

Keyword: *Magnesium metal batteries, additive, impurity-scavenging effect, nanointerfaces*

TPU/PEO/LiTFSI Solid Polymer Electrolytes Coupled with MXene Electrodes for Supercapacitors and Capacitive Sensors

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Solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs) have emerged as transformative materials for electrochemical energy storage and capacitive sensing. SPEs provide superior electrochemical stability and safety for energy storage devices while significantly improving the sensitivity of capacitive sensors. In this study, thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) and polyethylene oxide (PEO) were blended with lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) to provide a unique combination of mechanical robustness and high ionic conductivity that can be used both for energy storage and sensing applications. TPU/PEO/LiTFSI electrolyte achieved an ionic conductivity of $3.62 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, demonstrating its potential as a stable and efficient ion-conducting medium. When integrated with MXene electrodes, renowned for their exceptional conductivity, large active surface area, and mechanical flexibility, the hybrid system demonstrated superior performance in both supercapacitor and capacitive sensor applications. Fabricated symmetric solid-state supercapacitors achieved a maximum specific capacitance of 10.9 F g^{-1} at a scan rate of 1 mV s^{-1} , with significant rate capabilities. Symmetric CV and GCD curves indicate efficient charge storage, low resistance, and stable electrochemical behavior, demonstrating the potential of these devices as flexible solid-state supercapacitors. For the capacitive sensors, the TPU/PEO/LiTFSI electrolyte combined with MXene electrodes delivered a remarkable sensitivity of 727.61 kPa^{-1} at 100 Hz, while lower values were recorded at higher frequencies, indicating that both dielectric and sensing performance decline as frequency increases. These findings underline the synergistic benefits of TPU/PEO/LiTFSI SPEs and the distinctive properties of MXene electrodes, showcasing their promise in advancing solid-state ionics for next-generation energy storage and sensing applications.

Keyword: solid polymer electrolyte (SPE), flexible supercapacitor, capacitive sensing, MXene

Spiral Phase Plate-Based Optical Edge Enhancement

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Edge enhancement plays an important role in image processing, especially in applications such as microscopy, holography, biomedical diagnostics of live cells, and pattern recognition.

One of the well-known methods that has been applied recently in numerous studies is the spiral phase plate (SPP), a phase structure that effectively creates orbital angular momentum from gaussian beams and produces a doughnut-shaped beam (also known as a vortex beam).

The SPP acts like a spatial filter that enhances structural boundaries in the optical domain and reduces the low frequency content by introducing a phase delay that fluctuates throughout the plate in a spiral pattern. This produces a phase gradient that can be utilized to manipulate the light's wavefront. The wavefront that results can be used to produce additional desirable optical effects or it can be focussed to a single point.

The proposed technique was applied to a 4f optical system to improve contrast and resolution in optical imaging and verified through experimental analysis and numerical simulations. The results demonstrate that spiral phase plates offer simplicity and robustness and efficiently enhance edges in real time without the need for computational post-processing.

This work examines how a spiral phase plate (SPP) can be used in a fluorescence microscope using a spatial light modulator (SLM), emphasizing how well it can improve edge detection.

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Keyword: *Spiral phase plate (SPP), edge enhancement, optical imaging, vortex beam*

Design Strategy and Feasibility Analysis of Germanium-Based Avalanche Photodiodes for LiDAR Applications

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Avalanche photodiodes (APDs) represent a critical advancement in photodetection technology, providing internal gain and high-speed response under low-light conditions. This study presents a technical exploration and fabrication-oriented design strategy for germanium-based APDs (Ge-APDs) targeted for near-infrared (NIR) LiDAR applications, particularly within the 900–1550 nm range. Leveraging the superior carrier mobility and low bandgap of germanium, Ge-APDs are projected to exhibit faster response times and extended wavelength sensitivity compared to traditional silicon counterparts, while remaining more cost-effective than InGaAs-based alternatives. However, these advantages come with intrinsic challenges such as elevated dark currents and breakdown instabilities. Our work focuses on evaluating the feasibility of employing germanium as the absorption layer in planar APD structures, while exploring design approaches to mitigate dark current and edge breakdown effects. Strategies under consideration include the use of graded doping profiles, guard ring architectures, and integration of thermoelectric cooling for dark current suppression. We also aim to examine heterostructure-based designs such as separate absorption and multiplication (SAM) and their potential adaptation using Ge/Si or GeSn/SiGe alloys to optimize gain, noise performance, and integration compatibility with CMOS processes. While experimental validation is forthcoming, this study outlines a fabrication roadmap grounded in literature insights and material design simulations. The proposed approach offers a realistic path toward the development of high-gain, low-noise Ge-APDs suitable for compact and efficient LiDAR systems, contributing to the expanding field of high-resolution remote sensing and autonomous navigation.

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Infrared avalanche photodiodes from bulk to 2D materials Piotr Martyniuk, Peng Wang, Antoni Rogalski, Yue Gu, Ruiqi Jiang, Fang Wang & Weida Hu *Light: Science & Applications* volume 12, Article number: 212 (2023)

Keyword: *Avalanche Photodiodes, Near-Infrared Detection, LIDAR Technology, Germanium Photodetectors*

Development of Spray Coated Color-Tunable Photonic Glasses using Metal Oxide Nanoparticles for BIPV Applications

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Recently, the incorporation of building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPVs) into urban architecture has gained significant importance in reducing carbon emission and promoting sustainable communities. This work presents an alternative photovoltaic (PV) coloring strategy aimed at enhancing the aesthetic design of PV panels without much compromising their power conversion efficiency. Our research addresses this challenge by introducing a photonic glass layer colorization method that employs metal oxide nanoparticles, such as V_2O_5 and MoO_3 , to leverage their selective light reflection and absorption properties. Metal oxide materials are favored over conventional dyes for their durability and spectral selectivity. These materials are synthesized as monodisperse nanospheres via a solution-based process and deposited onto the PV panel glass using ultrasonic spray coating. This forms a 2-3 μm thick photonic glass layer that produces angle-independent color through Mie scattering. X-ray diffraction (XRD) method and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are used for the characterization of the synthesized metal oxide nanoparticles and spray coated photonic layers. Mini PV panels with dimensions of 15 cm \times 15 cm were fabricated, and their electrical characterizations are carried out. Efficiency is evaluated using Current-Voltage (IV) measurements. The reference panel (uncoated) has an efficiency of approximately 20.2%. The MoO_3 coated (blue-colored) panel exhibited an efficiency of around 12.1%, while the V_2O_5 coated (green-colored) panel reaches approximately 18.3%. Future advancements in colored BIPV technologies are anticipated to enhance color diversity, thereby facilitating the development of more aesthetically pleasing and architecturally integrable solar energy solutions.

Keyword: photonic glass, metal oxide, building integrated photovoltaics

Development of a Distributed Bragg Reflector (DBR) Simulation Program and Optical Characterization of Si/Si₃N₄ Multilayer Structures

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This study presents the development of a Python-based simulation tool designed for the optical modeling of multilayer dielectric structures, with a particular focus on Distributed Bragg Reflectors (DBRs) composed of Si and Si₃N₄ layers. The simulation environment utilizes the Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) to calculate wavelength-dependent reflection, transmission, absorption spectra, and photonic band structures. Unlike conventional fixed-parameter software, the developed tool supports the use of experimental refractive index and extinction coefficient data, allowing accurate and realistic modeling of dispersive and absorptive materials.

The graphical user interface enables non-programmer users to define layer configurations, thicknesses, and spectral parameters, and to visualize results interactively. Simulations were performed for various layer thicknesses and pair numbers. Results reveal that increasing the optical thickness or the number of layer pairs significantly enhances reflectance and broadens the photonic bandgap. Structures with seven pairs and quarter-wave thickness exhibited near-total reflectivity and sharply defined stopbands centered around ~1050 nm.

This simulation tool serves both as a theoretical investigation platform and as a practical design aid for optical systems such as filters, resonators, and photonic crystals. Its support for wavelength-dependent material properties and its flexible interface make it highly suitable for advanced research and device optimization in the field of nanophotonics.

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Keyword: *Distributed Bragg Reflector (DBR), Optical Simulation, Photonic Bandgap, Si/Si₃N₄ Multilayer Structures*

SERS-Based Detection of Nano plastic Particles Using Plasmonic Substrates

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Plastic pollution has emerged as a major global concern, particularly in the context of marine environments. Various thermal and spectroscopic techniques have been developed for the detection and identification of plastic particles. Spectroscopic techniques used for plastic particle analysis include Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), X-ray-based methods, and Raman Spectroscopy. However the detection efficiency of these methods is limited due to the small size of the plastic particles and complexity of the living environments. On the other hand, given the growing evidence of nanoplastic particles present in diverse environments including marine and freshwater systems, as well as human blood, there is an urgent need to develop and adopt more feasible and precise detection tools. Regarding this, here in this work, we employ surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) to detect polystyrene (PS) nanoplastics, with a diameter of 500 nm, which represent one of the most commonly produced types of nanoplastics found in natural environments. For this purpose, a 100 nm-thick silicon oxynitride (Si_3N_4) substrate is coated with a 5 nm titanium (Ti) adhesion layer, followed by a 30 nm gold (Au) film deposited by sputtering. SERS measurements are carried out with a commercial Renishaw system with an excitation wavelength of 532 nm. A small droplet of PS nanoplastic particles dispersed in water is deposited onto the substrate surface. SERS measurements, performed using a water-immersion objective lens, revealed characteristic Raman peaks of PS nanoplastics at approximately 1000, 1032, and 1600 cm^{-1} . These characteristic peaks are in good agreement with those reported for polystyrene nanoparticles in previously published literature. These findings are preliminary results demonstrating the great potential of SERS-based tools for detecting nanoplastics in aqueous environments, especially at small sizes. Further research is needed to develop and optimize SERS methods for the characterization and screening of nanoplastics in real environmental samples.

Keyword: *Plasmonic, Plastic Particle, SERS Substrate, Raman Measurement*

Implementation of Microfluidic FRAP for Characterization of Nanoparticle Transport in Porous Biopolymer Networks

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Nanomedicine features nanoparticles (NPs) that can be designed in various sizes, shapes and surface functionalities for therapeutic or diagnostic applications. Despite the major promise of nanomedicine for targeted drug delivery and patient-specific treatments, its clinical translation remains limited due to challenges in its effective delivery to the target tissue [1]. Specifically, the extracellular matrix (ECM), a heterogeneous porous network of biopolymers such as collagen, poses a significant barrier against NP transport in the tissue interstitium. Transport of NPs in engineered tissue scaffolds also face similar challenges. Unfortunately, the mechanisms behind hinderance of NP transport within ECM are poorly understood, limiting the design of nanomedicine for delivery. The problem is further complicated by lack of specialized and accessible tools for characterization of diffusive and advective transport properties of NPs. This study addresses this gap by implementing Fluorescence Recovery after Photobleaching (FRAP) [2] for use in shallow (<10-50 μm high) microchannels where ECM mimetic hydrogels are injected in and polymerized. In what we refer to as the microfluidic FRAP technique, containment of specimens in shallow microchannels combined with relatively large length and time scales of interstitial transport enable use of wide-field fluorescence LED illumination rather than the laser illumination, confocal imaging and specialized modules typically required for FRAP. In addition, hydrogels in microchannels can be precisely perfused to characterize and delineate the diffusive and advective transport properties. In this study, we develop and validate this technique by measuring effective diffusivity of fluorescent silica and polymeric NPs up to 400 nm in diameter in nanofibrous collagen type I hydrogels with collagen concentrations varying between 1.5 mg/ml and 6.0 mg/ml. The microfluidic FRAP measurements are compared with those from mean-square displacement analysis of single particle tracking, stochastic simulations based on Brownian dynamics, and measurements from previous studies in the literature. This work provides microfluidic FRAP as an accessible wide-field quantitative microscopy tool for transport characterization and lays the groundwork for investigating the role of other NP design features and ECM components in transport. The insights from this study will ultimately help develop a mechanistic understanding of NP transport for rational design of nanomedicine for optimal delivery.

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Keyword: FRAP, microfluidics, collagen, Brownian dynamics

Formation and Characterization of Protein Corona on Polycaprolactone Nanocarriers

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Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) nanoparticles have emerged as promising platforms for drug delivery due to their ability to provide sustained and controlled release of therapeutic agents. This prolonged release profile enhances drug bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy, while potentially reducing dosing frequency and systemic side effects. Furthermore, biodegradable and biocompatible nature of PCL minimizes toxicity and immunogenicity, making it suitable for clinical use. Despite these advantages, a critical obstacle in the application of PCL-based nanoparticles is the formation of a protein corona. Upon intravenous administration, blood plasma proteins rapidly adsorb onto the nanoparticle surface, forming a layer referred to as the protein corona. This biomolecular coating significantly alters the physicochemical properties and biological identity of the nanoparticles, influencing their biodistribution, cellular uptake, and clearance. Consequently, detailed analysis of the protein composition on the nanoparticle surface is essential to understand and control their in vivo behavior, ultimately contributing to the design of more effective and predictable drug delivery systems.

In this research, we identified the composition and types of proteins in the hard protein corona structure of PCL nanoparticles. The nanoparticles were synthesized via miniemulsion/solvent evaporation technique and characterized by dynamic light scattering, electrophoretic light scattering and electron microscopy. Then, nanoparticles were incubated with either human plasma or fetal bovine serum (FBS) to induce protein corona formation. The tightly bound proteins, termed the hard corona, were analyzed using sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS). LC-MS results revealed a higher prevalence of dysopsonin proteins compared to opsonins within the hard corona composition. These results indicate that the formation of a protein corona may impart stealth characteristics to PCL nanoparticles, potentially extending their circulation time and improving their applicability for systemic drug delivery. Moreover, the cytotoxicity of PCL nanoparticles was investigated through cell viability tests on both L929 mouse fibroblast cells and MCF-7 human breast cancer cells. These evaluations contribute to a deeper understanding of how protein corona formation influences the biological behavior and therapeutic potential of PCL nanoparticles.

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Keyword: *PCL nanoparticles, protein corona, drug delivery systems*

Development of Multiresponsive Hybrid Nanocarriers for Targeted Delivery of Doxorubicin

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Hybrid nanoparticles (HNPs) are promising drug carriers in cancer therapy, offering enhanced loading efficiency, stability, and controlled release. Their tunable structure enables the integration of stimuli-responsive components that trigger drug release under different conditions. The main aim of this study is to design a novel hybrid nanocarrier system with exclusively natural materials for the controlled and targeted delivery of doxorubicin. While lipid core will be examined for its high encapsulation capacity, biopolymeric shell will act as a stabilizer, **eliminating synthetic surfactants**, as demonstrated in our previous studies using albumin in combination with guar gum or dextran [1, 2]. Hence, in this system, Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) and Hyaluronic acid (HA) were used as the shell, while Lauric acid (LA) and Olive Oil formed the lipid core. BSA improves biocompatibility, and HA targets CD44 receptors commonly overexpressed in breast cancer. LA allows temperature-sensitive drug release; additionally, pH and enzyme-sensitive properties of the HNPs will be investigated. In this system, the Maillard reaction was employed to conjugate BSA and HA by preparing them at various BSA: HA weight ratios and incubating for different periods. The successful formation of these complexes was confirmed through SDS-PAGE and FTIR analyses. Following Maillard complex formation, HNPs were synthesized via miniemulsion solvent evaporation method, guided by a Taguchi orthogonal experimental design with varying parameters. Statistical analyses were used to determine the optimal conditions for achieving the ideal size (<200 nm): a BSA: HA ratio of 6:1, shell concentration of 1 mg/mL, incubation time of 96 hours, and a lipid ratio (LA: OO) of 1.5. Doxorubicin was encapsulated into the optimum HNPs using the same method, achieving a high encapsulation efficiency of 76%. Different characterization techniques, including STEM imaging, pH-dependent size and zeta potential analyses, MTT assays, and stability tests were employed to evaluate the optimum HNPs. STEM images confirmed the spherical morphology of the HNPs. In addition, HNPs itself exhibited low toxicity on L929 cells, with cell viability remaining above 80% at 24 hours and above 70% at 48 hours, even at increasing concentrations. Moreover, the cytotoxicity of doxorubicin-loaded HNPs was evaluated on MCF-7 cells. Stability tests conducted in various buffers further supported the stability profiles of both doxorubicin-loaded and empty HNPs. Consequently, the doxorubicin-encapsulated HNPs were optimized to allow for detailed analysis of their release behavior in different physiological environments. Overall, the HNPs possess a multi-responsive system, offering effective and non-toxic delivery for potential cancer therapy.

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Keyword: *hybrid nanoparticles, stimuli responsive system, drug delivery system, doxorubicin*

Development of Light-Responsive and PEGylated Niosomal Formulations for the Delivery of Dexamethasone Against Cancer Treatment

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Cancer remains one of the most prevalent and deadly diseases affecting worldwide. In recent years, various drug delivery strategies have been explored to improve treatment outcomes, particularly by enhancing the stability and responsiveness of carrier systems. In this study, we designed a light-responsive niosomal nanocarrier incorporating PEGylated azobenzene, a photoresponsive molecule that undergoes reversible conformational changes upon UV light exposure[1]. Unlike liposomes, which typically carry a negative surface charge due to phosphate groups, niosomes offer a neutral surface, thereby improving colloidal stability and reducing nonspecific interactions[2]. The chemical structure of the synthesized PEG-azobenzene conjugate was confirmed via FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The resulting niosomes had an average diameter of approximately 200 nm and were further characterized in terms of particle size distribution, zeta potential, and morphology using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Upon UV irradiation (365 nm), the conformational switching of azobenzene was shown to destabilize the niosomal membrane, as evidenced by changes in particle size over time. The niosomal formulation was successfully loaded with the steroidal anti-inflammatory agent Dexamethasone (Dex), and characterized for particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), surface charge, morphology, and drug encapsulation efficiency. The results demonstrate that this niosomal carrier has high potential as a promising candidate for future light-triggered drug delivery applications in cancer therapy.

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Keyword: *Light Responsive, Niosome, Drug Delivery Systems, Pegylated Nanoparticles*

Anti-oxidant Loaded and PEG-based Nanogels for Reducing Oxidative Stress in Atherosclerosis via VCAM1-Targeting

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One of the most important conditions in the world, atherosclerosis causes fatty molecules to build up on the artery walls. Lipid accumulations cause the arteries to thicken and stiffen, which ultimately leads to dangerous consequences including myocardial infarction or ischemia [1]. In addition to being hazardous, current atherosclerosis treatments that do not target damaged locations can have unintended adverse effects on healthy tissues and organs. Therefore, a unique drug monomer containing lipoic acid molecules was designed in this study and utilized for targeting to the atherosclerotic plaques. A nanogel carrier was prepared via PEG polymers and drug-loaded monomer was incorporated to the nanoparticle structure. Later on, covalent conjugation of the anti-VCAM-1 antibody was performed to target the plaques and a fluorescent dye, Cy-5, was attached to the surface as the imaging agent. These nanoparticles were made by utilizing a water-soluble photoinitiator (I2959) and dimethacrylate-functionalized PEG polymers under UV light (365 nm) using a free-radical based gelation process. Three distinct PEG molecular weights (2, 6, 10K) were assessed using the same gelation parameters. The polymer:initiator ratio, gelation temperature and time, solvent type, and dilution factor were all optimized in the nanogel production process. With a high purity (99.58%) and 76% yield, a new monomer with three drug molecules (LA3MA) was successfully synthesized as three lipoic acid drug molecules connected by ester bonds and a reactive methacrylate group in its structure. The dilution factor, temperature, duration, and drug monomer concentration (5, 10, 20% w/v) were assessed for the optimum drug-loaded nanogels. At room temperature in 10mM pH 7.4 PBS solution, it was found that PEGDiMA polymer (6 kDa) produced nanogels with a size of around 100 nm. Nanogels with a monomodal shape and a low PDI value were produced by using polymers at a concentration of 1 mg/300 μ L solvent and a weight ratio of 1:50 polymer:photoinitiator. Cy-5 dye was attached to the surface of amine-functionalized nanogels for in vitro cellular internalization test. Drug-loaded nanogels was investigated for their cytotoxicity behaviour against both L-929 mouse fibroblasts and HUVEC cells at both resting states and in a state that was activated by LPS, an endotoxin to create an inflammation environment. Moreover, drug-loaded nanogels were shown to decrease the amount of reactive-oxygen species almost by half, compared to the free lipoic acid molecule. Overall, this nanogel with novel drug-containing monomer was prepared as an effective nanomedicine for the treatment of oxidative stress-induced inflammation-based atherosclerosis.

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Keyword: Atherosclerosis, Nanogel, Oxidative stress, Controlled drug delivery

Cancelled: Fabricating B6 and QSH- Modified PEG-PLGA Nanoparticles via Double Emulsion for Controlled NAC Release

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Backgrounds: Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) nanoparticles modified with polyethylene glycol (PEG) have gained prominence in the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases due to their ability to carry hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs, and to prolong circulation time. In Alzheimer's Disease, β -amyloid ($A\beta$) accumulation and oxidative stress are among the key pathological processes in disease progression. N-acetyl-L-cysteine (NAC), as a powerful antioxidant, decreases oxidative damage, however, its low bioavailability limits its therapeutic effects. Delivery via PEG-PLGA nanoparticles may enhance the efficacy of NAC; and targeting of the nanoparticle with B6 and QSH peptides facilitates translocation across the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and directs to $A\beta$ plaques, respectively.

Aim: This study aims to design a PEG-PLGA nanoparticle system containing surface modifications with B6 and QSH peptides to provide targeted delivery and to enhance the therapeutic effect of NAC for the use of oxidative stress-based treatment approaches in AD. The developed NAC-loaded NP formulation was evaluated by physicochemical characterization, controlled release analysis, and in vitro cell viability.

Materials and Methods: NAC was quantified using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and the validations were performed according to the ICH Q2(R1) guidelines. PLGA-PEG-B6 and PLGA-PEG-QSH conjugates were synthesized via EDC/NHS chemistry. NAC loaded NPs were prepared using the double emulsion (w/o/w) technique. Characterization of the NPs were performed with Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR), Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC-MALS), and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Drug release profile was monitored via dialysis for 72h. Potential toxicity of the NPs was assessed by cell viability analysis in SH-SY5Y cells using WST-1 assay.

Results: The HPLC method was validated with high accuracy (99–102%), excellent repeatability (%RSD <2), and strong sensitivity (LOD= 0.0172 ± 0.008 µg/mL; LOQ= 0.0521 ± 0.011 µg/mL). The conjugation efficiencies of PLGA-PEG-B6 and PLGA-PEG-QSH reached 70% and 75%, respectively. The optimal NP formulation yielded a particle size of <200 nm, PDI value of 0.15, zeta potential of -24.3 mV, and encapsulation efficiency of 37.82%. DSC analysis showed the successful incorporation of NAC into the polymeric matrix, while SEM imaging supported the spherical morphology. The NP formulation enabled a sustained release profile, achieving 77 ± 4.54% of drug release in 96h. In vitro viability analyses of the cells showed that the NPs were highly biocompatible and preserved cell viability.

Conclusion: The NAC-B6-QSH-PEG-PLGA-NP system, designed with appropriate characteristics to cross the blood-brain barrier, was successfully developed. These results emphasize its use as a promising therapeutic candidate formulation for future studies.

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Keyword: Nanomedicine, N-acetyl cysteine, PEG-PLGA nanoparticles, Double emulsion

Nanomechanical Characterization of Epitaxial Graphene Based Ridges on 6H-SiC using AFM

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As a two-dimensional (2D) material, single atom thick graphene has attracted great attention in the past two decades, not only because of its unique electronic and optical properties but also for its unprecedented mechanical properties. Atomically flat graphene layers can be grown epitaxially on a semiconductor Silicon Carbide (SiC) substrate with a hexagonal crystal lattice structure [1]. Because of the difference between the thermal expansion coefficients of as-grown graphene ($\alpha_G = -8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) and SiC ($\alpha_{\text{SiC}} = 4.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$) substrate, ridge-like protrusions are created throughout the graphene layer during the cooling of SiC from growth temperature to room temperature [2,3].

In this study, atomic force microscopy (AFM) was employed to investigate the nanomechanical behaviour of ridge-like features formed in the epitaxial graphene grown on 6H-SiC. The formation of ridge-like hollow structures in the graphene layer occurs because of anisotropic compressive stress during the cooling process. AFM measurements demonstrated that the height, width, and density of graphene ridge structures depend strongly on the growth temperature. Mechanical characterization was achieved by taking into account the AFM scanning tip behaviour in graphene ridge motion. The spring constants of three different graphene ridges were determined from the change in ridge heights observed in topographies recorded, depending on the applied normal force, which ranged from 4.0 to 16 nN in increments of 4.0 nN. The spring constants (k_r) of three different graphene ridges with varying heights and widths were found as 3.31 N/m, 5.02 N/m, and 5.71 N/m for R1, R2, and R3 ridges, respectively. Upon comparing the height profiles, it was observed that the ridges were vertically displaced by the nanoscale force and subsequently returned to their original height. This study provides a foundation for future research on the nanomechanical properties of graphene and graphene-based nanostructures.

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Keyword: *Epitaxial graphene, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Graphene ridge, Surface morphology*

Capacitive Micromachined Ultrasonic Transducers with Integrated Force Plates (CMUT-FP): Simulation and Fabrication

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Capacitive Micromachined Ultrasonic Transducers (CMUTs) are MEMS-based devices that operate through electrostatic actuation and provide benefits over piezoelectric (PZT) transducers, including broader bandwidth and simpler integration. Nevertheless, PZT transducers typically exhibit higher capacitance and generate greater output pressure.

This study reports the simulation and microfabrication process of a novel CMUT structure featuring two conductive plates: a CMUT plate and a secondary force plate. The thinner force plate is positioned beneath the CMUT plate and is mechanically connected to it via a central shaft. Upon applying a voltage, the force plate deflects and collapses toward the bottom electrode, simultaneously pulling the CMUT plate. This configuration results in a greater capacitance change with applied voltage compared to traditional CMUTs, thereby producing a stronger electrostatic force.

The microfabrication process of the CMUT-FP begins with (1) the lift-off of a 200 nm thick polysilicon layer (gap thickness t_g) patterned at a radius of 16.9 μm on a conductive silicon substrate with 250 nm of thermally grown silicon dioxide (t_i). This initial polysilicon layer acts as a sacrificial layer, eventually defining the vacuum gap. Next (2), the copper force plate, 400 nm thick (t_p), is patterned using lift-off at a radius of 14.9 μm . A second polysilicon layer (3) is then deposited to define the shaft length ($t_s=100$ nm). Anisotropic dry etching at a radius of 3 μm and copper lift-off (4) are used to form the shaft. A copper layer with half the final membrane thickness ($t_m/2$) is lifted off (5) to encapsulate the underlying structures and form the CMUT plate. Both the CMUT and the force plate are released using XeF_2 dry etching of the polysilicon (6). Finally, another $t_m/2$ thick copper layer is deposited via lift-off to seal the etch holes and complete the cell, resulting in a total membrane thickness of 900 nm. For comparison, a conventional CMUT with the same radius a , membrane thickness t_m , and gap thickness t_g is fabricated in parallel to assess deflection performance under identical voltage conditions. The full process utilizes six photolithography masks.

Keyword: MEMS, CMUTs, Ultrasonics, Medical imaging

Modification of Functional Coatings by Intense Pulsed Ion Beam for water purification.

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Intense pulsed ion beam (IPIB) irradiation has become a powerful method for tailoring material properties through its ability to produce ultrafast heating and rapid cooling cycles [1]. This work investigates the impact of IPIB irradiation on different materials, particularly noble metal nanoparticles and metal oxide thin films [2].

In our previous reports, IPIB irradiation was applied to tungsten trioxide (WO₃) thin films to boost their photoelectrochemical (PEC) performance. The treatment created a sponge-like porous surface structure on WO₃, increasing its effective surface area and light absorption capability. Consequently, the photocurrent density rose by approximately 80% compared to untreated films. The rapid thermal process induced by IPIB also facilitated the crystallization of magnetron sputtered amorphous WO₃, further enhancing its PEC properties [3, 4]. However, influence of IPIB on chemically prepared WO₃ thin films shows different nature [5].

Overall, these results demonstrate that IPIB irradiation is a promising approach for precisely modifying material structures at the nanoscale for applications in photoelectrochemical water purification. In this work, IPIB modified WO₃ has shown significant degradation improvement of methylene blue dye which was used as prototype organic waste in water under sunlight compared to not irradiated WO₃.

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Keyword: *water purification, thin films, functional nanomaterials, ion beam modification*

One-Step Bimetallic Nanoparticle Modified SPCE-Based Molecularly Imprinted Sensor for Sensitive Detection of Organophosphorus Pesticides in Environmental Matrices

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Organophosphorus pesticides (OPs), particularly Diazinon, pose serious threats to environmental and public health due to their neurotoxic effects resulting from the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase. Conventional detection methods are often hindered by high costs, extended analysis times, and complex instrumentation. In this study, a novel, sensitive, and selective electrochemical sensing platform based on molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) was developed for the determination of Diazinon in environmental samples. The sensor was constructed by modifying screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) with bimetallic gold-copper (Au@Cu) nanocomposites synthesized via a one-pot chemical reduction method. The bimetallic nanoparticles were optimized in terms of Au:Cu molar ratios (1:1, 1:2, 2:1, 1:4, and 4:1) to maximize electrochemical response. The optimization was validated using cyclic voltammetry (CV), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Morphological and surface characterization was carried out using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR).

The MIP layer was synthesized by electropolymerizing o-phenylenediamine (o-PD) in the presence of Diazinon as the template molecule. Optimal polymerization was achieved at 50 cycles using a 1:0.5 template-to-monomer ratio. The template was removed using methanol (MeOH) over one hour to create specific recognition sites. The sensor's performance was evaluated by comparing the redox peak currents before and after template removal using a 5 mM solution of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ in 0.1 M KCl. The developed sensor exhibited excellent selectivity toward Diazinon even in the presence of structurally similar pesticides such as monocrotophos, propetamphos, buprofezin, and chlorfenvinphos. The sensor showed a linear response to Diazinon concentrations in the range of 2.5 μM to 20 μM , with a limit of detection of 0.7135 μM . Analytical performance was further validated through recovery studies in tap water samples, yielding satisfactory recovery rates.

Recovery experiments using diazinon-spiked tap water samples yielded recoveries ranging from 102.22 % to 112.35 %, validating the sensor's applicability in real-world matrices. In addition, long-term stability was evaluated, with the sensor retaining approximately 75% of its electrochemical signal after 15 days of storage. Moreover, the sensor's environmental sustainability was assessed using the AGREE (Analytical GREENness Metric) tool, confirming its potential as a green analytical technology. The integration of bimetallic nanomaterials not only enhanced the surface area and conductivity but also significantly improved electron transfer efficiency and analytical sensitivity. The proposed sensor offers a rapid, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly alternative for Diazinon detection without the need for complex sample pretreatment.

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Keyword: Diazinon, Molecularly imprinted polymer, Bimetallic nanoparticles, Environmental monitoring

Triply Periodic Minimal Surface Filters for Copper Removal: A Combined Experimental and Computational Study

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Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures composed of CNT/polymer composites were developed and evaluated as advanced porous filters for the removal of copper (Cu^{2+}) ions from aqueous media. Five distinct TPMS geometries were 3D-printed using a CNT-infused photocurable resin, providing highly interconnected pore networks with tunable internal surface areas and topologies. The printed structures were integrated into a flow-through filter holder, and Cu^{2+} ion removal performance was evaluated under continuous flow conditions at a fixed inlet velocity. To quantify copper removal, water samples were collected at the outlet over time and analyzed using Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV), allowing for sensitive and precise measurement of Cu^{2+} concentrations. Results showed a strong dependency of removal efficiency on TPMS geometry, indicating the significant role of flow distribution and contact surface area. To interpret these differences, we conducted computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics using Laminar and Turbulent Flow modules, along with Particle Tracing to simulate transport behavior through each TPMS structure. Seven flow-related descriptors were evaluated, including velocity distribution, wall shear stress, flow uniformity, tortuosity, pressure drop, hydraulic diameter, and residence time distribution. The laminar model failed to capture the observed behavior, while the turbulent model provided more realistic insight into flow dynamics and transport behavior within the TPMS structures. A strong agreement was observed between trends in experimental Cu^{2+} removal and simulated parameters such as residence time and tortuosity. These findings demonstrate the synergy of material design, experimental validation, and modeling for optimizing next-generation CNT-based filtration systems.

Keyword: *Carbon nanotubes, Metal Ion Removal, Differential Pulse Voltammetry, 3D printing*

Droplet-Based Microfluidic Synthesis of Zr-UiO-66 for Efficient PFAS Removal: A Comparison With Conventional Methods

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent, human-made organic compounds widely found in the environment. Recent awareness has drawn attention to the toxicity of these substances. PFAS degrade very slowly in nature and tend to bioaccumulate. PFAS pollutants accumulate in ecosystems and the food chain, leading to long-term harmful effects on human health, such as liver damage, thyroid disease, cancer, and fertility issues. These chemicals, which leak into water from PFAS-containing sources, such as industrial waste and firefighting foams, can reach humans through drinking water. In studies on groundwater and wastewater in Türkiye, perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA) has been identified as the most concentrated pollutant [1]. Metal-organic framework (MOF) structures are porous crystalline materials exhibit high surface area-to-volume ratio, make them effective for water treatment. Their structural stability at high temperatures, flexible structures, and high adsorption capacity render them as advantageous adsorbents. Stability and high thermal durability of zirconium (Zr)-based crystalline structures allow them to remain stable in water and many other solvents. Zr-UiO-66 MOF structures have been used in the treatment of phosphate [2], fluoride [3], dyes, and heavy metals from wastewater [4]. Due to their small pore size and excellent adsorption properties, they have also been used for PFAS removal [5].

In this study, comparative adsorption of PFAS on Zr-UiO-66 nanoparticles, synthesized via the solvothermal method following the conventional macrostatic countertop route and a novel droplet-based microfluidic route, was conducted. MOF particles produced via macro-scale systems exhibit heterogeneous particle and pore size distribution. In droplet-based microfluidic systems, uniform droplets created at the picoliter scale can be used as individual batch reactors. In thousands of uniform microreactors, diffusion rate, heat transfer, and pressure are consistent across all applications and monodispersed MOF nanoparticles can be produced. Zr-UiO-66 structures adsorb PFAS through interactions between the Zr regions and pollutant molecules, form Lewis acid-base complexes, and use hydrophobic interactions to retain pollutants within pores. Therefore, Zr-UiO-66 was chosen as the MOF for use in this research. After the adsorption process, a desorption process was persuaded to clean the particles, and by reusing them, the number of cycles for which the nanoparticles can be used for PFAS adsorption was determined.

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Keyword: *PFAS removal, Water Treatment, Droplet Based Microfluidic Systems, Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs)*

Fast and Scalable Cyclotide Separation Using a Silica Gel-C18 Microfluidic System

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Microfluidic separation technologies have emerged as powerful alternatives to traditional chromatography, addressing issues such as high costs, lengthy processing times, and low efficiency [1, 2]. Cyclotides, which are plant-derived cyclic peptides with a wide range of biological activity from antibacterial to anticancer, require efficient purifying procedures before they can be used in drug development. We provide the first example of a microfluidic device that replicates high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) for cyclotide separation. Silica gel-C18 was produced, analyzed, and incorporated into microchannels to form an HPLC-like stationary phase. Cyclotide extracts from *Viola ignobilis* were prepared using low-voltage electric field extraction, evaluated using HPLC and MALDI-TOF, and then put into the microfluidic system. Using distilled water as the mobile phase, several cyclotides (Vigno 1-5 and Varv A) were successfully separated and collected at varying retention times. These findings demonstrate the promise of silica gel-C18 microfluidic chips as a fast, low-cost, and effective technology for cyclotide separation, with significant implications for accelerating natural product research and drug discovery [3, 4, 5].

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Keyword: *Microfluidic Chip, Separation, Viola Ignobilis, Cyclotides*

Comparative Synthesis and Fluorescence Characterization of Carbon Quantum Dots via Hydrothermal, Solvothermal, and Microwave-Assisted Methods Using Curcumin

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In this research, carbon quantum dots (CQDs) were synthesized using curcumin as a natural carbon source through three different methods: hydrothermal, solvothermal, and microwave-assisted synthesis. The hydrothermal and solvothermal processes were conducted at 120 °C and 180 °C for 2, 4, and 16 h, and the microwave-assisted synthesis was performed using a domestic microwave oven with a 3-minute irradiation time.

Noticeable differences in fluorescence intensity were observed under varying synthesis conditions for each method. In the solvothermal approach, the sample synthesized at 120 °C for 16 h exhibited the highest fluorescence intensity, whereas the one prepared at 180 °C for 2 h showed the lowest, with nearly a threefold difference between them. In the hydrothermal method, the sample obtained at 180 °C for 16 h showed the highest intensity, while the one synthesized at 120 °C for 2 h had the lowest, resulting in approximately a twofold difference. These differences in fluorescence intensity were also reflected in particle size characteristics, as confirmed by dynamic light scattering analysis. The samples with higher fluorescence intensity featured smaller and more uniform particles, approximately 2 nm in size, whereas the other samples contained larger particles around 9.5 nm. These findings demonstrate how variations in synthesis methods and reaction conditions can significantly influence the physical and optical properties of CQDs. Such controllable characteristics enable their promising potential for applications in bioimaging.

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Keyword: *Carbon quantum dots, hydrothermal synthesis, solvothermal synthesis, microwave-assisted synthesis*

Silver Nanoparticle (AgNP)-Based Peptide Conjugates: Antimicrobial Activity and Cytotoxicity

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Today, nanoparticles are not merely passive carriers but active components involved in target recognition, signal transduction, and biomimetic functions. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), known for their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, face limitations in conventional use due to their non-specificity and potential cytotoxicity. This study introduces a peptide-based functionalization strategy to convert AgNP surfaces into specific and versatile interaction platforms for microbial membranes.

Peptides, due to their tunable structures, are widely used in nanotechnology for surface modification, targeted delivery, and biosensing. Their high biochemical specificity and surface interaction capabilities make them ideal candidates for nanobiotechnological applications. Here, AgNPs were conjugated with a cationic peptide derived from Histatin-3 to create molecular adaptors targeting microbial membranes and intracellular pathways. AgNPs enhance membrane permeability via localized field intensification through surface plasmon resonance (SPR), while released Ag⁺ ions disrupt redox balance, boosting the peptide's cytosolic activity and inducing apoptosis through oxidative stress.

AgNPs were synthesized under redox conditions using sodium borohydride and trisodium citrate, and stabilized with a negative surface charge (zeta potential ≤ -35 mV) to ensure colloidal stability. The Histatin-3-derived peptide was designed to carry a +5 charge and possess potential for an amphipathic α -helical conformation optimized for membrane penetration.

Conjugation was carried out under isothermal conditions, considering ligand–surface interaction thermodynamics. A 12–15 nm redshift in the SPR band will confirm peptide binding, while FTIR will identify non-covalent interaction sites. DLS analysis is expected to reveal a ~20–30 nm increase in hydrodynamic size, indicating peptide layer formation. Molecular docking showed strong binding affinities (< -200 kcal/mol) between the peptide and surface proteins of *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* (e.g., ClfA, Als3), with interactions localized to ligand recognition motifs.

Cytotoxicity will be evaluated using the eukaryotic model *Tetrahymena thermophila*, supported by MTT-based assays. Antimicrobial activity will be assessed via CLSI-standardized tests, and the therapeutic index (TI) will be calculated using hemolysis data. The resulting conjugate system combines the physical efficacy of the nanoscale metal core with the specificity of biomolecular recognition, representing a smart bio-nanomaterial.

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Keyword: organik ligand, nanotherapy, silver nanoparticle, antimicrobial

Stress in a Drop: Synergizing Cortisol and Immuno-Nano Approaches

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Cortisol is a key glucocorticoid hormone secreted by the adrenal cortex and regulated via the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, playing a central role in the body's response to stress. Chronic elevation of cortisol levels is associated with significant health issues, including immunosuppression, metabolic disturbances, and mental health disorders such as depression. In this study, a low-cost, portable, and user-friendly paper-based spot test platform for rapid and non-invasive cortisol detection in saliva and sweat was successfully developed. Two parallel strategies were implemented: A chemical method based on the colorimetric response of blue tetrazolium dye and a novel immunochemical approach utilizing gold nanorods (GNRs), and cortisol antibodies. The chemical method leveraged the redox reaction between cortisol and tetrazolium compounds, while the immunochemical method explored the synergistic signal enhancement from GNRs and fuchsin dye conjugates. Both approaches were optimized and validated under synthetic and physiological conditions, with performance compared via colorimetric analysis using RGB quantification software. The final device featured a 3D-printed, handheld format allowing real-time visual assessment and semi-quantitative digital analysis. The project's innovation was reflected in its dual-approach platform, integration with point of care method, and its focus on individualized stress monitoring outside laboratory settings.

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Keyword: *Point of Care testing, Cortisol, Spot Test, Colorimetric Assay*

Freestanding Dot-Blot Platform for Early Detection of Chronic Kidney Disease

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Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is associated with significant healthcare costs and high mortality rates, especially in late-stage cases¹. In this project, we aimed to develop a fast, portable and easy-to-use dot-blot immunosensor for the early detection and monitoring of CKD at the point-of-care (POC). This dot-blot optical biosensor was used to detect two critical CKD biomarkers: Kidney Injury Molecule-1 (KIM-1) and Neutrophil Gelatinase Associated Lipocalin (NGAL)². For the fabrication process, ‘freestanding’ films were first obtained; a water-soluble polymer was coated onto a glass support material by rotary coating/spray coating methods. Subsequently, a newly developed spiro polymer layer was applied on top of the water-soluble polymer. The polymer-coated glass support s then immersed in water to dissolve the water-soluble film while the spiro polymer film is floated as an independent thin film layer³. Spots were formed by marking the glass backing with a writing pen to identify the working areas of the tests. Antibodies were immobilized onto these marked spots using physical adsorption, enabling specific biomolecular recognition. Upon exposure to a UV lamp, fluorescent signals change following antigen-antibody interactions. The resulting spots were photographed using a smartphone camera under UV light, and the images were analyzed in RGB channels using ImageJ software. This process yields quantitative data to develop a smartphone-based, freestanding POC system. In the later stages of the study, it is planned to adapt these spiro polymer-based biosensors to wearable surfaces.

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Keyword: *Chronic Kidney Disease, Point-of-Care, Free-Standing Platforms, Spot Test*

Morphological Engineering of Nanogold Probes for Improved Lateral Flow Assay Performance

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Lateral flow assays (LFAs) are low-cost, rapid and portable platforms for the detection of various analytes. In these platforms, strong visual signals are essential for reliable performance. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are widely utilized in LFAs due to their outstanding optical properties, excellent biocompatibility, structural stability and ease of functionalization. AuNPs can be synthesized in various morphologies, including spheres, rods, prisms, and flowers, which significantly influence the analytical performance of LFAs, particularly in terms of sensitivity, signal intensity, and detection limits significantly¹.

In this study, we synthesized nanospheres and nanoflowers using controlled methodologies. The size, shape, and color of both nanomaterial types were thoroughly characterized to confirm their suitability for LFA applications². For a direct performance comparison of results targeting the same analyte, both types of nanoparticles were conjugated with the same detection antibody³. An evaluation of the assay performance was conducted using quantitative and qualitative methods, focusing on parameters like colloidal stability, dispersibility, signal intensity, and limit of detection (LOD). The results highlighted that both the morphology of AuNPs and the applied stabilization/conjugation strategies significantly affect the sensitivity and reliability of LFAs. This study contributed to a better understanding of nanoparticle morphology selection and optimization for next-generation point-of-care (POC) diagnostics.

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Keyword: *Lateral flow assay, Point-of-care, Gold nanoflower, Gold nanosphere*

A One-Step, Wash-Free Spot Test Prototype Using ITO Substrates to Replace NC Membranes

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Diagnostics and identification represents the foundational steps in controlling and maintaining human health. Traditional laboratory equipment has made it possible to monitor health using a variety of methods for centuries. As a result, point-of-care (POC) testing systems have become increasingly popular for their ability to offer rapid, user-friendly and portable solutions to detect target analytes in biological fluids such as saliva, urine, and blood¹.

It is widely known that lateral flow assays (LFAs) are one of the most widely used POC platforms. However, nitrocellulose (NC) membranes the core material in conventional LFAs, pose several challenges due to their mechanical fragility, inhomogeneity, and limited compatibility with advanced detection systems². To address these limitations, a new diagnostic platform has been proposed, using an indium tin oxide (ITO) glass substrate, replacing the NC membrane. Utilizing the capillary flow principle typical of LFA systems, this platform is designed in a dot-based configuration instead of a traditional line format. Moreover, it eliminates the need for multiple sample processing steps by enabling flow-driven biotransduction directly at multiple functionalized sites, thereby simplifying the overall detection process.

As a result of its high optical transmittance, excellent conductivity, ease of surface functionalization, reusability, and integration with electrochemical/spectroscopic systems, ITO glass is a highly promising material for future diagnostic devices with multi-analysis and advanced readout strategies³. Thus, this work shows the potential of creating an adaptable and innovative basis for next-generation POC testing systems.

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Keyword: *Wash Free System, Spot Test, ITO Substrate, Nanoparticles*

Electrochemical Detection of RAD-140: A Portable and Cost-Effective MIP-Based Sensor Approach

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The increasing prevalence of doping in sports has necessitated the development of advanced detection technologies to uphold ethical competition and safeguard athlete health. Among **Selective Androgen Receptor Modulators (SARMs)**, **RAD-140** has gained popularity, particularly among young athletes and bodybuilders, due to its muscle-enhancing and fat-reducing effects. However, the lack of comprehensive scientific data on its long-term health effects and the spread of misleading information via social media have led to uncontrolled usage and complicated doping control efforts.

In this study, we aimed to develop a low-cost, portable, and highly selective **molecularly imprinted electrochemical sensor (MIECS)** system for the detection of RAD-140. The sensor was designed using **Molecularly Imprinted Polymer (MIP)** technology. A **polymeric nanomaterial** was synthesized via emulsion polymerization and engineered to include selective recognition sites for RAD-140. This imprinted polymer was subsequently applied to a **screen-printed electrode (SPE)** to fabricate the sensing interface.

The performance of the developed MIP-based electrochemical sensor was evaluated using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) techniques. This study represents the first attempt to detect RAD-140 using a MIP-based electrochemical approach, with potential applicability in the analysis of commercial products.

This innovative system provides a novel perspective for doping control in sports, forensic toxicology, and public health applications, and may serve as a model for the detection of similar compounds.

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Keyword: *Biosensor, Polymeric nanomaterial, Molecular imprinting polymer, Electrochemical sensor*

Near Field Communication (NFC)-Assisted Advanced Nanomaterial Based Immunosensor for Point-of-Care Testing in the Early Diagnosis of Chronic Kidney Disease

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Chronic kidney disease (CKD) poses a significant burden on healthcare systems due to its high treatment costs and elevated mortality rates, particularly in advanced stages. Early diagnosis and continuous monitoring are critical for improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare expenditures. [1] Electrochemical immunosensors that incorporate nanomaterials represent a promising class of biosensors, integrating nanotechnology, electrochemical analysis, and immunological techniques. These systems offer several advantages, including ease of use, high sensitivity, fast response times, and excellent selectivity. In particular, carbon-based nanomaterials are widely utilized due to their superior electrical conductivity, biocompatibility, and ability to enhance electrochemical reaction sites. Their large specific surface area facilitates enhanced biomolecule immobilization, making them highly attractive for electrochemical biosensing applications. [2] Herein, we report the development of a portable, rapid, and user-friendly electrochemical immunosensor for point-of-care (POC) applications enabling early stage detection and monitoring of CKD. In this work, a novel electrochemical immunosensor was developed using hollow porous carbon (HPC) and a spiro based conjugated polymer. Subsequently, biofunctional and selective recognition surfaces were fabricated by bioconjugation of specific antibodies of CKD biomarkers, Kidney Injury Molecule-1 (KIM-1) and Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin (NGAL), onto the polymer matrix. Then, the developed immunosensor was integrated with an NFC-based potentiostat, enabling wireless and portable detection of KIM-1 and NGAL for POC use. The biosensors were characterized using analytical techniques to assess their structure and electrochemical performance. The HPC/P1/anti-NGAL and HPC/P1/anti-KIM-1 immunosensors exhibited high sensitivity, stability, and selectivity. The sensors demonstrated a broad detection range of 20–200 ng/mL for NGAL and 10–150 ng/mL for KIM-1, with low limits of detection (LOD) of 13.02 ng/mL and 3.09 ng/mL, respectively. Furthermore, excellent specificity toward target biomarkers was demonstrated. These findings underscore the potential of carbon-based electrochemical immunosensors as reliable, sensitive, and portable platforms for rapid and accurate diagnosis of CKD in clinical settings.

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Keyword: *Chronic Kidney Disease, Point-of-Care Test System, Immunosensor, Carbon based nanomaterials*

PEGylated Gold Nanoparticle-Based Biosensor Platform in a 96-Well Format for High-Specificity Detection in Complex Biological Samples

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Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are highly promising candidates for developing sensitive, label-free biosensors due to their localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) properties. Nanoplasmonic biosensors offer significant advantages, including reduced sample volume, cost-effectiveness, portability, and suitability for point-of-care (POC) applications, all while providing high sensitivity. This study describes the development of a robust nanoplasmonic biosensor platform, specifically optimized for biomolecule detection in complex biological matrices.

AuNPs were synthesized via a seed-mediated approach and characterized by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). These nanoparticles were then immobilized onto a polyethyleneimine (PEI)-coated polystyrene surface, adapted to a 96-well plate format for high-throughput compatibility. To critically address non-specific binding, heterobifunctional polyethylene glycol (Thiol-PEG2K-NHS) was employed as a surface passivating and functionalization agent. Various PEG concentrations were optimized, and the efficacy of surface passivation was rigorously validated using Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) and Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), the latter mimicking complex physiological samples. PEGylation significantly reduced non-specific protein adsorption, evidenced by the absence of LSPR red-shifts in absorbance spectra following BSA or FBS incubation.

The bifunctional nature of PEG, with its thiol group interacting with gold and the NHS terminal group available for biomolecule conjugation, was leveraged. Protein A was successfully conjugated onto the PEGylated surface, and its specific interaction with Anti-GFAP antibody was investigated as a model for antibody-antigen recognition. Parallel optimization experiments included direct conjugation of Anti-GFAP to PEG. Specific molecular recognition was confirmed by distinct LSPR red-shifts observed via spectrophotometric analysis following Protein A – Anti-GFAP interaction. The biosensor's sensitivity to refractive index changes, and by extension, molecular concentration, was further demonstrated through experiments using increasing concentrations of glycerol.

This platform, integrating PEG-based surface engineering within a spectrophotometer-compatible 96-well format, offers a scalable and multiplexable solution well-suited for point-of-care applications. It not only achieves high specificity and minimal background interference in complex biological samples but also establishes a versatile foundation for developing adaptable diagnostic tools through diverse bio-recognition element conjugation.

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Keyword: *Gold nanoparticles, Nanoplasmonic biosensor, PEGylation, Point-of-care devices*

Protein A-Mediated Oriented Antibody Immobilization on PEGylated Gold Nanoparticles for Enhanced LSPR Biosensing

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Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) exhibit unique optical properties due to localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR), making them highly attractive for nanoplasmonic biosensing platforms. The LSPR wavelength is extremely sensitive to changes in the local dielectric environment around the nanoparticle surface, providing a label-free method to monitor molecular binding events. This study focused on developing a stable and functionalized AuNP-based nanoplasmonic platform, optimized for specific antibody binding and sensing applications.

30 nm AuNPs were synthesized via the seed-mediated growth method and characterized by dynamic light scattering (DLS). All functionalization steps and subsequent binding assays were conducted directly in microcentrifuge tubes, thus eliminating the need for complex surface immobilization procedures. The functionalization process involved sequential modification of the AuNP surface. First, a heterobifunctional PEG (Thiol-PEG2k-NHS) was applied at various concentrations to optimize colloidal stability and minimize non-specific binding. Optimal PEGylation conditions were determined through UV-Vis spectrophotometry (monitoring LSPR peak position) and salt-induced aggregation tests. Following successful PEGylation, Protein A was introduced to enable oriented immobilization of immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies through their Fc region, preserving the antibody's antigen-binding sites. Finally, specific antibodies were added to the functionalized nanoparticles.

Successful functionalization and specific antibody binding were confirmed by monitoring the shift in the AuNP LSPR peak wavelength using UV-Vis spectrophotometry. Optimized PEGylation ensured nanoparticle stability with substantial LSPR shift. The subsequent binding of Protein A and antibodies resulted in a distinct and measurable redshift of the LSPR peak, indicative of the increased local refractive index surrounding the nanoparticles. This platform was demonstrated to be stable and ready for subsequent antigen binding studies. The ultimate goal is to utilize this functionalized platform to detect specific antigen-antibody interactions via further LSPR shifts and apply this technology to applications such as cell culture studies.

In conclusion, we have successfully established a robust, solution-phase functionalization protocol for AuNPs using optimized PEGylation and Protein A. This approach enables stable, oriented antibody conjugation, validated by significant LSPR shifts. This modular platform offers a versatile and potentially cost-effective route towards developing sensitive point-of-care diagnostic devices based on nanoplasmonic sensing.

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This study was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Commission of Istanbul Technical University (Grant No: TGA-2022-44113).

Keyword: *Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), Localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR), PEGylation, Protein A immobilization, Nanoplasmonic biosensor, Label-free detection*

Development of an Electrochemical Biosensor for the Detection of Pyocyanin Molecule, One of the Virulence Factors of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Bacteria

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Pseudomonas aeruginosa bacteria cause various diseases with high morbidity and mortality rates in humans, such as wound infections, cystic fibrosis, respiratory tract infections and urinary tract infections [1]. One of the most important factors in the formation of these diseases is a redox active molecule called pyocyanin secreted by the bacteria. Early diagnosis of chronic infections will be possible by using the pyocyanin molecule as a biomarker for *Pseudomonas* infections [2,3]. In this context, our study aimed to produce an electrochemical biosensor that uses the redox active properties of the pyocyanin molecule as a biomarker. Electrochemical methods have several advantages over other methods. Electrochemical methods are highly sensitive and selective in the detection of biomarkers, and detection of even low concentrations (nM or μ M) is possible, and they are much cheaper than other methods. Poly(Aniline-co-Pyrrole)/Au-NP/SPE electrode, which is a surface printed electrode, was obtained by coating Au nanoparticles on the electrode produced by electrocopolymerization of pyrrole and aniline together by chronoamperometric method [4]. An enzyme-free biosensor was designed for the detection of pyocyanin in PBS (pH 7.4) solution by using the prepared Poly(Aniline-co-Pyrrole)/Au-NP/SPE electrode. The electrochemical performance of the hybrid electrode was evaluated using cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analyses. The structural and morphological properties of the prepared electrode were investigated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), scanning electron microscope (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses. As a result of the study, an electrochemical biosensor with high stability was developed that allows the rapid detection of the pyocyanin molecule in PBS (pH 7.4) at very low concentrations. In order to test the applicability of the biosensor in a real sample, a bacterial culture containing the pyocyanin molecule was used. The results obtained from the study show that electrochemical biosensors can be used in the diagnosis of *Pseudomonas* infections. It is also thought that this study will shed light on new studies in the future where clinical samples of patients (blood, saliva, etc.) will be used.

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Keyword: *Pyocyanin, gold nanoparticle, Poly(Aniline-co-Pyrrole), electrochemical biosensor*

Fluorescent Nanosensor for the Detection of Pesticide Atrazine in Real Samples

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Pesticides in food and water sources cause several problems due to their significant threat to human health and the environment. Atrazine, a prevalent herbicide, has the potential to bioaccumulate within the human body via the food chain, thereby inducing neurotoxicity and carcinogenic side effects.

A fluorescence-based biosensor containing superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPION), cadmium selenide/zinc sulfide (CdSe/ZnS), quantum dots (QDs), and aptamers for binding to atrazine (ATZ) pesticide was developed. The nanosensor was characterized by XRD, TEM, UV-vis spectroscopy, zeta sizer, and fluorescence spectroscopy. The fluorescence of the SPION/CdSe/ZnS/Aptamer probe was quenched by atrazine. The Atrazine concentration-based changes in fluorescence values were calculated. The analytical capacity of the developed biosensor at nanogram levels was investigated. The fluorescent sensor exhibited highly sensitive detection of ATZ by fluorescence intensity decreasing with the addition of ATZ in the range of 1–1000 ng/ml and with a detection limit (LOD) of 217 ng/ml and a limit of quantification (LOQ) of 658 ng/ml. The tests were repeated with different pesticides to verify the specificity of the sensor, ensuring its reliability and accuracy. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the biosensor was evaluated in tests on real samples: grape, potato, apple, peach, and water. Primarily, there was a 50% decrease in the fluorescence value of the sensor as ATZ was added to the potato samples.

As a result, the optimized biosensor method, with its unique ability to facilitate chemical residue detection, has the potential to impact food safety significantly. This method is a crucial development in our ongoing efforts to ensure the safety of our food supply.

Keyword: *nanosensor, biosensor, quantum dots, nanobiotechnology*

Electrochemical Sensing of Diazinon via Layer-by-Layer Assembled MIP/MWCNT-TiO₂/Nafion Modified Glassy Carbon Electrode

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Diazinon is a widely used organophosphorus pesticide, and its residues pose considerable risks to environmental and food safety. To address the need for rapid and selective detection of diazinon, a molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP)-based electrochemical sensor was developed on a glassy carbon electrode (GCE). The fabrication involved a layer-by-layer assembly of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) dispersed in DMSO, solvothermally synthesized TiO₂ nanoparticles, and 0.5% Nafion in an EtOH/H₂O (1:1) mixture, forming a stable and conductive nanocomposite film. Subsequently, o-phenylenediamine (o-PD) was electropolymerized in the presence of diazinon as a template molecule using 50 cyclic voltammetry scans in ABS buffer (pH 5.2), resulting in a molecularly imprinted layer. Template extraction was carried out using ethanol under shaking for 30 minutes, and optimal rebinding was achieved in 3 minutes. Electrochemical characterization of the modified electrode (MWCNT/TiO₂/Nafion/MIP/GCE) was conducted using differential pulse voltammetry (DPV), cyclic voltammetry (CV), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in the presence of the [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-} redox couple. A systematic variation in peak current (I_a) was recorded at each modification step: bare GCE (0.456 mA), after nanocomposite modification (1.133 mA), after polymerization (0.035 mA), and after template removal (0.333 mA). The sensor exhibited a linear response within the concentration range of 3.28 × 10⁻⁸ to 6.56 × 10⁻⁷ M. The integration of MWCNTs, TiO₂ nanoparticles, and Nafion provided enhanced electron transfer and film stability, while the molecular imprinting technique ensured high selectivity for diazinon. This study highlights the potential of the proposed sensor as a low-cost, portable, and efficient tool for monitoring organophosphate pesticides in environmental and agricultural samples.

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Keyword: *Molecularly Imprinted Polymer (MIP), Electrochemical Sensor, Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs), TiO₂ Nanoparticles*

pH-Responsive Gold/Carbon Quantum Dot-Embedded Hydrogels for Ferric Ion (Fe³⁺) Sensing Applications

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pH-sensitive hydrogels stand out as advanced smart materials due to their ability to adjust to environmental stimuli. In particular, the selective detection of toxic metal ions in aqueous media enables these materials to offer innovative solutions in environmental monitoring and biosensing applications [1]. This study presents the synthesis and characterization of a new generation of pH-responsive poly(acrylic acid-co-acrylamide) [P(AA-co-AM)] and fluorescent carbon quantum dot (CQD) hybrid hydrogel systems. Acrylic acid segments on the polymer backbone regulate the swelling behavior of the hydrogel by ionizing in response to pH changes, while the acrylamide units maintain the mechanical integrity of the structure and support ion transport [2]. Metal-binding capacity and optical signal response originates from fluorescent carbon quantum dots (CQDs) that are embedded into the hydrogel system and amplified via the gold moiety, i.e. gold-carbon quantum dot nanocouples (Au/CQDs). These nanomaterials exhibit high affinity for heavy metal ions due to surface carboxyl, hydroxyl, and amine groups, and also improve detection sensitivity through the metal-enhanced fluorescence (MEF) mechanism [3][4].

Within the scope of this study, hydrogel samples with varying nanoparticle contents (0%, 0.1%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.5% v/v) were prepared and characterized using rheological analysis, pH-dependent swelling tests, concentration-dependent metal binding assays, UV-Vis spectroscopy, and fluorescence spectroscopy. Furthermore, the metal-binding performance of the hydrogels toward Fe³⁺ ions was evaluated under different pH conditions. The Fe³⁺ ion retention capacities were investigated in FeCl₃ solutions of various concentrations (20 μM, 100 μM, 0.5 mM, and 1 mM).

The study aims to investigate whether the developed system can function as a sensor by exhibiting distinct optical and physical changes in the presence of metal ions. In this context, interplay between the pH responsive nature of the hydrogels and the system's optical response to the presence of metal ions are being evaluated. This approach would pave the way for the development of low-cost, pH-responsive, and portable metal ion sensors through the synergy of polymer chemistry and nanomaterial technology. Based on the findings to be obtained, the potential applicability of the developed hydrogel system in areas such as environmental monitoring, water quality assessment, and biomedical diagnostics will be investigated.

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Keyword: *Carbon Dot, pH-sensitive hydrogels, metal binding capacity*

Effects of Magnetic Field Gradients on SH-SY5Y Cancer Cells and Total RNA

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The increasing need for high-performance micromagnets is attributed to their extensive application in microfluidics, microchannels, magnetic gradient patches, biomedical microelectromechanical systems (Bio-MEMS), and diagnostic biosensors for disease detection [1]. Bio-MEMS is an interdisciplinary field that combines electronics, microfabrication, and biology to create microscale devices and systems for therapeutic applications. The goal of the present study was to investigate the interaction between magnetophoretic systems and living organisms, with a particular emphasis on cancer cells, such as the neuroblastoma cell line (SH-SY5Y), and the retention of their total RNA.

This was achieved through the development of composite micro-magnets composed of Nd-Fe-B and Sr-Fe nano-thin flakes (NFs) using photolithography. The current study developed an innovative and effective technique for developing ordered arrays of Nd-Fe-B and Sr-Fe patterns. The surfactant-assisted ball milling technique yielded Nd-Fe-B and Sr-Fe flakes with a high aspect ratio [1]. Nd-Fe-B and Sr-Fe NFs were mixed at various concentrations, resulting in a homogeneous blend of negative photoresist and Nd-Fe-B/Sr-Fe [2]. The optimal value was determined to be 50 wt.%. The combination underwent a photolithography procedure, incorporating a spin coating approach performed at speeds ranging from 1000 to 1500 rpm. The negative photoresist SU-8 is chosen for its compatibility and chemical stability with Bio-MEMS technology. Nd-Fe-B and Sr-Fe micromagnets are produced according to the specifications provided by the negative photoresist producer. The effective manufacture of grid-patterned micromagnets has led to the successful creation of micromagnets measuring up to 500 µm.

The primary aim was to evaluate the targeted capture efficiency of SH-SY5Y human neuroblastoma cells and their total RNA using the fabricated micromagnets. Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized using the co-precipitation method and subsequently coated with polyethylene glycol (PEG) [3]. SH-SY5Y cells were labeled with PEG-coated Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles, and various concentrations of both nanoparticles and cells were tested [4]. The cell suspension mixtures were then introduced into microfluidic channels containing the patterned micromagnet arrays. Capture efficiency was subsequently analyzed based on the retention of SH-SY5Y cells [5].

Furthermore, for RNA retention analysis, total RNA was first isolated from SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells and then applied to the micromagnet arrays. After exposure to the micromagnetic system, quantitative PCR (qPCR) was performed to assess the retention efficiency based on gene expression levels. These findings indicate a promising approach for magnetic cell sorting, molecular analysis, and the development of precision bio-MEMS platforms for diagnostic and therapeutic applications.

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Keyword: Bio-MEMS, Biosensors, Nanoparticles, Micro-Magnets

Engineering Recognition at the Surface: A Molecularly Imprinted Electrochemical Sensor for Ipratropium

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Ipratropium bromide is a bronchodilator widely used in the treatment of respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma. Despite its therapeutic benefits, monitoring ipratropium levels in biological and environmental samples is of growing interest due to its potential side effects, dose-related efficacy, and emerging concerns over pharmaceutical residues in water systems. Therefore, developing a sensitive, selective, and rapid analytical tool for its detection is essential for both clinical and environmental applications.

In this study, we present an electrochemical sensor platform based on molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) specifically designed for the recognition of ipratropium. The MIP layer was synthesized directly on the electrode surface using a surface imprinting approach, offering enhanced accessibility of the recognition sites and facilitating rapid analyte binding. Unlike traditional bulk or nanoparticle-based MIP systems, the surface-imprinted architecture provides improved sensitivity and selectivity through more efficient analyte diffusion and minimized mass transfer resistance.

Commercially available screen-printed electrodes (Dropsens 11L, featuring carbon working and counter electrodes with a Ag/AgCl reference) were employed for sensor fabrication. Morphological characterizations of the modified electrode surfaces were performed, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and contact angle measurements to confirm successful MIP deposition and surface structuring. Electrochemical performance and analyte interaction were evaluated through voltammetric techniques, providing a versatile and label-free means of ipratropium detection.

The integration of MIPs with screen-printed electrode technology offers a cost-effective, disposable, and portable sensing platform suitable for real-world applications. This work highlights the potential of surface-imprinted electrochemical sensors for selective detection of pharmaceutical compounds, addressing current needs in therapeutic drug monitoring and environmental safety.

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Keyword: *Surface Imprinting, Electrochemical Sensor, Molecularly Imprinted Polymers, Pharmaceutical Emerging Contaminants*

Design of Imprinted Plasmonic Biosensors for Precision Detection of Hereditary Bleeding Disorders

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Biosensors are integral to advancing personalized healthcare through precision diagnosis, treatment, and disease monitoring. In the context of rare diseases and hereditary bleeding disorders, such as hemophilia, traditional treatment frameworks often fall short due to the unique physiological variability among patients. Conventional laboratory diagnostics, requiring high-performance instruments and specialized expertise, limit the accessibility of personalized treatment solutions for the broader population. To address this gap, imprinted polymers with specific binding sites for coagulation proteins—particularly Factor VIII—are being developed to facilitate real-time, spatially independent diagnostics [1-5].

This innovative approach aims to strengthen doctor-patient communication and empower healthcare providers with rapid, actionable insights critical for tailored treatment plans. By preparing plasmonic biosensors integrated with imprinted nanoparticles, we enable the highly selective and sensitive detection of Factor VIII. The imprinted nanoparticles are meticulously synthesized and characterized through size analysis and transmission electron microscopy, setting the foundation for the fabrication of plasmonic biosensors. Comprehensive characterization of the biosensors, including atomic force microscopy and contact angle assessments, is followed by kinetic, selectivity, and reusability analyses, affirming the biosensors' efficacy in real-time Factor VIII detection. This platform holds promise as a transformative tool in personalized medicine, contributing to enhanced patient outcomes and streamlined clinical decision-making.

Acknowledgements

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Keyword: *Molecularly Imprinted Polymers, Plasmonic Biosensor, Factor VIII Detection, Hemophilia Diagnostics.*

Smart Polymeric Patch for Repair of Gastrointestinal System Damages

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Digestion is the primary function of the gastrointestinal system, which consists of a long, tube-like structure that runs between the mouth and the anus as well as other organs connected to it. The mouth, esophagus, stomach, small and large intestines, rectum, and anus are all parts of the system. The system has large number of both benign and malignant disorders. An organ of the gastrointestinal system, the esophagus is a muscular duct that runs between the stomach and the pharynx and is 25 cm long in adults. It facilitates the movement of nutrients or liquids from the pharynx to the stomach. Esophageal diseases are widespread and varied. The most prevalent of these include Barrett's esophagus, eosinophilic esophagus, achalasia, gastroesophageal reflux disease, infections, and esophageal cancer. The aim of this study is to create a smart material by combining natural and synthetic polymers in a hybrid system by tissue engineering methods and to utilize the strengths of these polymers to eliminate tissue damage in the region and to prevent its recurrence.

For this purpose, the bilayer adhesive and biocompatible hybrid patch was developed from modified biopolymers and polycaprolactone. The adhesive layer of the scaffold is composed of chitosan-sodium carboxymethyl cellulose polymers. The chemical, surface, thermal and adhesive properties and swelling behavior were examined in detail. The effect of these properties on biodegradation of gastrointestinal patch was investigated in enzymatic, oxidative, and hydrolytic environments.

Keyword: *polycaprolactone, chitosan, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, patch*

Enhancement of Glass Ionomer Cements via Chitosan and Its Derivatives for Dental Applications

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Glass ionomer cements (GICs) were developed as dental restorative materials due to their biocompatibility, anticariogenic properties, aesthetic appearance, and ability to adhere to tooth, bone, and metal surfaces. Despite these advantages, GICs exhibited several limitations, including low fracture resistance, moisture sensitivity, and inadequate bond strength, which restricted their use in high-stress areas and compromised their long-term performance.

In this study, efforts were made to improve the mechanical properties and degradation resistance of GICs to extend their service life following implantation. For this purpose, glass ionomer liquids were modified using biopolymers such as chitosan, carboxymethyl chitosan (CMC), and β -glycerophosphate-crosslinked chitosan derivatives. These modifications were aimed at enhancing the structural integrity and resistance to hydrolytic and acidic conditions.

The modified GICs were subjected to a comprehensive set of analyses. Chemical interactions were investigated using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, and morphological changes were observed via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Mechanical properties, including compressive and flexural strength, were evaluated to assess structural improvements. Thermal stability was analyzed using Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Additionally, water sorption, solubility, and acid erosion tests were performed to simulate degradation in oral environments.

The results demonstrated that the incorporation of chitosan-based biopolymers led to improved mechanical performance and reduced degradation of GICs. These findings provide a promising foundation for developing next-generation GICs with enhanced durability and clinical applicability.

The aim of future work will be to further optimize the biopolymer composition and assess the in vivo performance of the modified materials in dental applications.

Keyword: *Glass ionomer cement (GIC), Chitosan derivatives, Mechanical enhancement, Biopolymer modification*

Alginate and SBMA Based Antifouling Hydrogels for Tissue Engineering Applications

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Alginate-based biomaterials have attracted considerable interest in tissue engineering due to their advantages, such as biocompatibility, biodegradability and low toxicity [1]. However, they exhibit limited mechanical strength, long-term stability, and weak tissue integration, when they are especially in hydrogel form [2]. To address these limitations, methacrylation of biopolymers including alginate has emerged as a promising approach and has been applied in various tissue engineering applications. In particular, microwave-assisted methacrylation has gained attention for improving reaction efficiency and significantly reducing reaction time [3]. Additionally, anti-fouling surfaces are crucial in certain tissue regeneration applications, such as hernia repair. Zwitterionic polymers have attracted increasing interest for achieving anti-fouling properties [4]. Motivated by these factors, this study focuses on the preparation and characterization of microwave-assisted zwitterionic AlgMA-SBMA hydrogels. The methacrylation of alginate was carried out via an EDC/NHS reaction using 250 W microwave energy [5]. FTIR and ¹H-NMR analyses were conducted to characterize the chemical structure. The degree of methacrylation, determined by ¹H-NMR, was found to be 80%. AlgMA and SBMA, in various ratios, were photo-crosslinked, and the mechanical strength, swelling behavior, rheological properties, and wettability of the resulting hydrogels were analyzed. The AlgMA-SBMA hydrogels demonstrated high swelling capacity, suitable rheological behavior, enhanced mechanical strength, and improved wettability. These findings indicated that microwave-assisted zwitterionic AlgMA-SBMA hydrogels represent a promising biomaterial for tissue engineering applications.

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Keyword: AlgMA, SBMA, Zwitterionic hydrogels, Tissue engineering

Quercetin Incorporated Chitosan Hyaluronic Acid Dermal Wound Dressings

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Many people around the world are affected by the number of injuries that occur every day for various reasons. Wound dressings, which accelerate the processes during wound healing and exhibit bioactive properties by showing a barrier effect, create superiority in the treatment processes. In this study, it is aimed to develop unique dermal wound dressings with biocompatible, bioactive and antioxidant properties.

For this purpose, biocompatible, antibacterial chitosan and biocompatible hyaluronic acid were selected as main biopolymers, where quercetin was incorporated as an antioxidant agent in dermal wound dressing formulations. Chitosan-quercetin and chitosan-quercetin-hyaluronic acid films were prepared with different quercetin ratios. The chemical and thermal characterizations of wound dressings were characterized with FTIR, TGA and DSC. In rheological studies, viscoelastic behaviors of samples were investigated by measuring the shear rate against viscosity at constant temperature. Surface free energy, swelling and biodegradation properties of dermal wound dressings were examined. According to the results of the chemical characterizations, quercetin provided chemical bonding in chitosan and chitosan-hyaluronic acid formulations. Rheological analysis results showed that, quercetin incorporated chitosan and chitosan-hyaluronic acid formulations had non-newtonian fluid properties. Dermal wound dressings showed high swelling capacity in aqueous media and biodegraded in lysozyme containing enzymatic media.

Keyword: *chitosan, quercetin, biomaterial, wound dressing*

Development of Multifunctional Anionic Hydrogel Systems Functionalized with AgNPs and QDs for Biomedical Applications

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Hydrogels have emerged as multifunctional systems in the biomedical field due to their high water retention capacity and biocompatibility [1]. Incorporating natural polymers into the design of these versatile structures offers advantages such as biodegradability, low toxicity, and high compatibility with cells [2, 3]. In this study, an innovative anionic semi-permeable polymer network (semi-IPN) hydrogel system was developed using 3-sulfopropyl acrylate potassium salt (SPA) and the natural polymer pectin. The network structure was synthesized via redox free radical polymerization using N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide (MBA) as a crosslinking agent. The synthesized hydrogels were characterized by SEM, TEM, XRD, FTIR, and TGA analyses to determine their morphological, structural, and thermal properties. The developed semi-IPN nanocomposite hydrogels were evaluated within the scope of two distinct biomedical applications. In the first application, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were synthesized in situ within the hydrogel network using avocado (*Persea americana*) extract due to its antibacterial properties. Subsequently, the semi-IPN@Ag nanocomposite hydrogels were loaded with an antibiotic drug, and their antibacterial activities were assessed against various Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. For the second application, the semi-IPN hydrogel was functionalized with quantum dots (QDs) and designed as a drug delivery system. Doxorubicin (DOX) was loaded as a model anticancer drug. The semi-IPN hydrogels exhibited pH-sensitive swelling behavior, enabling controlled drug release. We tested the cytotoxic effect of the DOX-loaded semi-IPN@QDs system on specific cell lines. The results demonstrated that the developed semi-IPN hydrogel system is a multifunctional and promising biomaterial with potential applications both as an antibacterial wound dressing and as a targeted anticancer drug delivery platform.

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Keyword: *Quantum Dots, AgNps, Drug release, Cancer*

Preparation and Characterization of a Novel Hemostatic Dressing Material

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Hemorrhage is one of the most critical clinical challenges worldwide, accounting for approximately 40% of trauma-related fatalities due to uncontrolled blood loss [1]. The body's natural hemostatic mechanisms may be insufficient to stop bleeding in cases of severe injury or trauma [2]. Therefore, there is a significant need for bioactive hemostatic materials to control external bleeding and accelerate coagulation [3]. In this study, we developed chitosan/gelatin cryogels incorporated with *Verbascum thapsus* (VT) extract to address non-compressible hemorrhage. VT extract was impregnated into 50:50 (w/w) chitosan/gelatin cryogels at concentrations of 1%, 5%, 10%, and 20% (w/v). The VT-loaded cryogels were characterized morphologically by SEM and chemically by FTIR. These cryogels exhibited high water and blood absorption capacities, ranging from 300% to 3600%. Moreover, VT-loaded cryogels showed good antibacterial activity, with inhibition rates up to 89% against *E. coli* and 78% against *S. aureus*. The cryogels demonstrated 94% cell viability with a human fibroblast cell line. Blood compatibility was assessed through hemolysis ratio, which was found to be 1%, indicating good blood compatibility. The hemostatic activity of the cryogels was evaluated using a whole blood clotting assay, which showed an improvement in the blood clotting index (BCI) from 11.9 to 6.5. Furthermore, the clotting time was compared with a commercially available hemostatic dressing, and a reduction from 9.95 minutes to 6.14 minutes was observed. The incorporation of VT into chitosan/gelatin cryogels markedly enhanced their hemostatic performance, enabling rapid blood coagulation within minutes. These findings underscore the innovative application of VT in the development of effective hemostatic biomaterials.

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Keyword: hemostatic, cryogel, chitosan, gelatin

Green Mucilage-Based Hydrogels for Flexible Epidermal Bioelectronic Interfaces

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Epidermal bioelectronics for healthcare monitoring has been an attractive topic in biomedical and materials science. The rapid advancement of wearable bioelectronics has revolutionised real-time health monitoring and personalised medicine. They establish a pioneering research area that integrates advanced material engineering with biomedical applications, addressing challenges in personalised healthcare, remote well-being monitoring, and next-generation diagnostics. Hydrogels, known for their hydrophilic, 3D-network structures and high-water retention capacity, are widely used in bioelectronic applications due to their similarity to human tissue. The integration of hydrogel-based electronic sensors into wearable health monitoring systems allows for the development of stretchable, adhesive, and compatible bioelectronics. The aim of the research is to develop bioelectronic interface films for epidermal electronics using naturally occurring mucilage form. This study develops mucilage-based hydrogels derived from quince seed and linseed, aiming to serve as an interface platform for skin sensors. Agar, a marine-derived gelling agent, enhances hydrogel strength via natural crosslinking through its hydroxyl-rich structure. Unlike alginate or chitosan, it forms a stable, stretchable network without additional crosslinkers, making it ideal for epidermal sensors. PEDOT:PSS, a conductive and biocompatible polymer in this research, makes the bioelectronic interface for sensor applications. In this study, different concentrations of agar were mixed with quince seed mucilage (QSM) and plasticiser. The effect of improved crosslinking network on films was characterised and evaluated.

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Keyword: *Bioelectronic interfaces, Electronic skin, Flexible sensors, Green hydrogels*

Optimization of Mechanical Properties of Porous Gyroid PEEK Scaffolds for Load Bearing Applications

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Bone defects in load-bearing areas require implants that offer both mechanical stability and biological integration. Scaffold porosity and pore size are key design parameters that influence both mechanical performance and biological response. While higher porosity typically enhances nutrient transport and cell infiltration, it also reduces mechanical strength. Conversely, lower porosity structures may offer improved mechanical integrity but impede biological functionality. Literature suggests that pore sizes in the range of 300 to 600 μm are most favorable for osteoblast proliferation, angiogenesis, and mineralized tissue formation. However, balancing these biological requirements with mechanical demands remains a challenge, particularly in load-bearing sites, where scaffolds must resist significant compressive and bending loads. One promising approach to scaffold design involves the use of triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures, which offer highly interconnected porous architectures. Among these, the gyroid geometry has gained substantial attention due to its uniform distribution of material, isotropic mechanical behavior, and high surface area. Gyroid structures can facilitate nutrient diffusion and vascular ingrowth while maintaining sufficient mechanical integrity to support cellular activities and external loads. Their resemblance to trabecular bone also makes them a suitable choice for orthopedic scaffold applications. Polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) has emerged as a strong candidate due to its favorable mechanical properties and biocompatibility. In this context, the present study aims to optimize the mechanical properties of gyroid PEEK scaffolds through a combined computational and experimental methodology. Using nTopology, various gyroid scaffolds were designed with pore sizes ranging from 300 μm to 900 μm and porosities between 60% and 70%. These designs were subjected to finite element analysis (FEA) under displacement-controlled compression to assess their stress distribution and elastic deformation behavior. Two key mechanical metrics were extracted for each design:

1. Maximum von Mises stress ($\sigma_{VM,max}$), to identify critical stress concentrations approaching material yield. Identifies the risk of local failure.
2. Elastic Node Ratio (ENR), calculated as the percentage of nodes where $\sigma_{VM} < 100$ MPa. This metric represents the structural volume remaining within the elastic region and is useful for predicting durability.

Based on these simulations, the most mechanically favorable scaffold geometry was identified. Among the designs, the scaffold with a 450 μm pore size demonstrated the optimal balance: it remained within PEEK's yield strength (≈ 97.9 MPa), while its pore size aligned with the biological window favorable for osteogenesis (300–600 μm).

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Keyword: PEEK, Scaffold, TPMS, Finite Element Analysis

The Effect of Agarose-Gelatin Blend Hydrogels on Spatiotemporal Calcium Phosphate Liesegang Pattern Formation

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Liesegang patterns are periodic non-equilibrium structures, formed by the simultaneous diffusion and reaction of ions, leading to precipitate formation. Since their discovery by Raphael E. Liesegang in 1896, these patterns have been extensively studied to understand and control their formation. Biomineralization, on the other hand, is a process in which organic materials shape the nucleation, growth, and orientation of inorganic minerals. One of the common biomineralization processes in nature is the mineralization of calcium phosphates. That is why their biomineralization processes are studied to understand the fundamentals of crystallization, as well as to design biocomposite ceramic materials. While many studies have focused on the formation of calcium phosphate Liesegang patterns, only a few have investigated their crystal morphology and structure in detail. In this work, agarose-gelatin blend hydrogels were utilized in varying proportions to explore how gel composition influences particle morphology and structure. So far, it has been proven that calcium phosphate patterns form inhomogeneously in terms of particle size and number. Our findings confirmed that the particles also exhibited a diversity of particle shapes in different regions of a single Liesegang band, with very similar ranges of Ca/P ratio. This suggests the coexistence of morphologically distinctive yet structurally similar calcium phosphate phases. Furthermore, studies also showed that the same regions of different generations of bands in the same system consistently displayed the same particle shape, indicating a hierarchical formation of inhomogeneity across different generations. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report to reveal within-band variety of particle shapes. One particle type exhibited a size at least three times smaller than others while retaining a highly porous structure. These results deepen our understanding of the complexity inherent in biomineralization processes and may lead to the development of advanced drug delivery platforms and bone-regenerative materials.

Keyword: Biomineralization, Hydrogels, Liesegang Patterns, Calcium phosphates

In vitro Osteogenic Potential of Decellularized ECM-Based Bioinks

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Three-dimensional (3D) bioprinting enables the precise deposition of cell-laden bioinks to fabricate patient-specific tissue constructs. However, conventional biomaterials often fail to replicate the complex biochemical and structural features of the native extracellular matrix (ECM). Decellularized ECM (dECM)-based bioinks have emerged as promising alternatives, providing inherent biological cues that guide cell behavior and support tissue regeneration [1].

In this study, we developed and 3D bioprinted a novel bioink derived from decellularized bone ECM for applications in bone regeneration. Preliminary in vitro analyses demonstrated that overall cell viability was maintained within the constructs as confirmed by live/dead staining and metabolic activity (Alamar Blue) assays. Microscopical investigation further indicated that cells adhered to and spread within the dECM matrix.

Future work will focus on reinforcing this bioink with hydroxyapatite (HAp) nanoparticles to improve its osteoconductive and mechanical properties, aiming to better mimic the native bone microenvironment [2]. Subsequent studies will evaluate osteogenic differentiation through ALP activity, calcium deposition, and gene expression analyses, along with assessing the mechanical and structural stability of the printed constructs.

These findings highlight the promise of dECM-based bioinks as biomimetic platforms for bone tissue engineering, and ongoing research seeks to enhance their functionality by incorporating HAp.

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Keyword: 3D bioprinting; decellularized ECM; bone regeneration; hydroxyapatite; bioink

(*) Nanoexplosives Production, Characterization, and Performance Tests

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Recent advancements in nanotechnology have opened new avenues in the field of energetic materials, particularly in the production and application of nano-scale explosives. Advantages of nanoexplosives are not limited to significant improvements in reactivity, combustion uniformity, and ignition sensitivity compared to their micro-scale counterparts. Moreover, detonation velocity, brisance, and pressure output of nano explosives have a characteristic dependency to the size and morphology of nanoexplosives. This study presents a guiding way to investigate the production, characterization, and performance evaluation of nanoexplosives. The nanoenergetic compound was characterized using techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and particle size analyzer to assess particle size distribution and morphology. The findings suggest that nano scale energetic materials exhibit moderate size distribution in the variety of ranges from micro- to nanometers with a globular and uniform morphology. Blast experiments exhibited a satisfactory performance that nanoexplosives can be used as buster filling energetics. Performance characteristics of nanoexplosives, thus, are offering potential use in precision applications such as micro thrusters, safe-arm devices, and advanced military systems of the future energetic systems.

Keyword: *Nanoenergetics, explosives, defence*

Plasmon-Enhanced Light Extraction in OLEDs by Silver Nanoparticle Interlayers at Anode-HTL Interfaces

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Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) suffer from limited external quantum efficiency (EQE) due to internal photon losses [1]. This study explores plasmonic enhancement using silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) as an interlayer between the ITO anode and the PEDOT:PSS hole transport layer. Ag NPs were synthesized at six different temperatures; one of them showed optimal spectral overlap (53.6%) with the OLED's electroluminescence [2]. These NPs were dispersed in chlorobenzene at varying concentrations and spin-coated at 1000 or 2000 rpm onto ITO substrates.

Devices fabricated with OMI231BE as the emissive layer and Cs₂CO₃/Al as the cathode revealed that the best performance was achieved with 25% Ag NP content spin-coated at 2000 rpm. This device exhibited 14.7% luminance increase, 13.6% EQE improvement, and reduced turn-on voltage (3.5 V) compared to the reference. In contrast, higher NP contents led to performance degradation, likely due to plasmonic quenching and aggregation-induced scattering losses [3].

The results demonstrate that optimizing Ag NP interlayer parameters can effectively boost OLED performance by enhancing light outcoupling through controlled plasmonic interactions.

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Keyword: *Organic Light Emitting Diodes (OLEDs), Plasmonics, Silver Nanoparticles*

Solvent Vapor Annealing Directed Formation of Needle-like and Flower-like Luminescent Organic Microcrystals

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Organic single crystals are considered ideal candidates for a wide range of advanced technological applications such as flexible electronics, organic transistors, and optoelectronic devices due to their high charge carrier mobilities, directional molecular ordering, and solution processability.¹ However, the fabrication of these crystals with high structural quality and controlled morphology remains a significant technical challenge. Commonly employed methods—such as physical vapor deposition (PVD), solution-phase diffusion, microchannel-guided growth, and slow solvent evaporation—often involve multi-step procedures, require controlled atmospheric conditions, and suffer from limited reproducibility.² These limitations highlight a growing demand for simpler, more scalable, and controllable crystallization techniques.

Solvent vapor annealing (SVA) offers a highly advantageous approach for crystal growth from solution, owing to its compatibility with low-temperature processing, additive-free formulation, and the use of simple equipment. Through controlled interaction between solvent vapor molecules and the surface of the organic film, this method facilitates molecular rearrangement, thereby enabling the formation of diverse crystal morphologies. In this study, two different light-emitting organic molecules with oligo(p-phenylene ethynylene) π -conjugated backbones were deposited onto separate substrates from solution and subsequently subjected to solvent vapor annealing under a controlled environment to induce microcrystal formation. As a result of the annealing process, two distinct crystal morphologies were observed: aligned needle-like structures and flower-like microcrystals. The needle-like crystals exhibited clear directional alignment and formed regions with varying orientations across the surface, indicative of one-dimensional (1D) anisotropic growth. In contrast, the flower-like structures consisted of irregularly extending rod-shaped crystals radiating outward from a central point, displaying a more complex morphology. Owing to their photoluminescent properties, orientation diversity, and random spatial distribution on the surface, these light-emitting organic microcrystals present a unique and robust platform for physically unclonable functions (PUFs).³

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Keyword: Organic Single Crystals,, Solvent Vapor Annealing, Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs)

Understanding the Molecular Architecture of Organic Semiconductors for Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy Applications

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Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) is a powerful analytical technique known for its exceptional sensitivity and molecular specificity. It has found widespread use across diverse fields, including chemical analysis, biosensing, food safety, anti-counterfeiting, and environmental monitoring. Traditionally, SERS relies on plasmonic nanostructures, primarily gold and silver, which can theoretically amplify Raman signals by up to 10^{12} fold. However, these materials often face limitations such as high cost, limited chemical selectivity, small effective surface areas, poor reproducibility, and the potential for photothermal damage to analyte molecules. To address these challenges, researchers have explored inorganic semiconductors for SERS since the 1980s. Despite some promise, these materials often suffer from low enhancement factors and limited tunability of their electronic properties. More recently, attention has shifted toward organic semiconductors, which offer significant advantages such as structural diversity, tunable energy levels, and synthetic flexibility.

In this study, we report the fabrication and evaluation of nanostructured surfaces based on DFH-2T to DFH-6T derivatives varying in conjugation length, as SERS-active platforms. We aim to systematically investigate how π -conjugation length, surface morphology, and optoelectronic properties influence SERS performance, with particular emphasis on the short-chain DFH-2T. The DFH-based molecules were deposited on glass and silicon substrates using a modified physical vapor deposition (PVD) method. The resulting 3D nanostructured films were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and UV-Vis spectroscopy. Their SERS activity was also evaluated using methylene blue as a Raman reporter molecule and a 785 nm confocal Raman microscope. Our results provide promising insights into the design of low-cost, SERS-active semiconducting materials, highlighting the structural versatility of organic semiconductor platforms. By leveraging molecular engineering, this work advances the potential for molecule-specific sensing and paves the way for the development of selective, stable, and scalable SERS technologies.

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Keyword: Organic Semiconductor, Molecular Engineering, Molecular Detection, SERS

Green Synthesis, Characterization, Antibacterial and DNA Cleavage Activities of Silver Nanoparticles Using *Angelica archangelica* L. Root Aqueous Extract

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Nanotechnology has emerged as a revolutionary field with widespread applications in medicine, electronics, and environmental science. Among nanomaterials, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are particularly valued for their unique physicochemical properties and potent antimicrobial effects. Green synthesis methods utilizing plant extracts provide an eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to conventional chemical approaches for nanoparticle production.¹

Angelica archangelica L. is a medicinal plant well known for its rich content of bioactive compounds and has long been used both in folk medicine and in traditional cuisine.² Numerous studies have shown that all parts of the plant possess pharmacological and nutritional value, although the root is considered the primary source for medicinal use.³ Studies in the literature have highlighted various pharmacological activities of the plant, such as anti-asthmatic, antiproliferative, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiallergic, hepatoprotective, and antimicrobial effects, while phytochemical analyses reveal it is particularly rich in volatile oils and coumarins.⁴ The purpose of the study is to synthesize silver nanoparticles using *A. archangelica* root extract as a reducing and stabilizing agent, to perform characterization of the synthesized nanoparticles, and to evaluate their biological activities.

Characterization of the synthesized nanoparticles was performed using UV-Visible spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The UV-Vis spectra showed a characteristic peak between 400–450 nm, confirming the formation of AgNPs. SEM images provided detailed information on the morphology and size distribution of the nanoparticles. The biosynthesized AgNPs' antibacterial activity was evaluated against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria using the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) assay. The results demonstrated effective inhibitory concentrations, indicating significant antibacterial potential. The interaction between the synthesized AgNPs and DNA was investigated with pBR322 plasmid DNA using the agarose gel electrophoresis method. The obtained results showed that silver nanoparticles cleaved the DNA oxidatively.

Our findings demonstrated that *A. archangelica* root extract is an effective bio-reducing agent for the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles with significant antibacterial and DNA cleavage activities, highlighting their potential applications in biomedical fields.

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Keyword: *Angelica archangelica* L., Green Synthesis, Silver Nanoparticles, Biological Activities

Constant and Pulsed Electrodeposited WO₃ Thin Films as a Photoanode of Photoelectrochemical Water Splitting

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With global warming becoming an urgent problem, H₂ has gained importance as an alternative clean fuel. Hydrogen is considered as the fuel of the future because it is clean, renewable, has high energy density and has the potential to meet future energy demands and overcome environmental problems^{1,2}. H₂ is a promising renewable energy source, but 95% of current H₂ production routes require the use of more costly carbon-based fuels for synthesis, making it costly and less sustainable. Photoelectrochemical water splitting, i.e. the decomposition of H₂O molecules into molecular hydrogen and oxygen using solar energy, is considered as one of the most promising renewable energy technologies³. Photoelectrochemical water splitting offers a green approach to hydrogen production, but its efficiency, costs and scarcity of suitable photoelectrode materials for water oxidation and reduction reactions are limited by research. Metal oxides show high stability in aqueous electrolytes; however, they have low photoconversion efficiencies due to their band gap and high production costs. Depending on the crystal structure and quality, WO₃ films are n-type semiconductor materials with an energy band gap in the range of 2.7–3.5 eV, which means a wider photon absorption range than other materials commonly studied for photoelectrochemical applications with higher energy band gaps.

In this work, WO₃ thin films deposited by using electrodeposition with different deposition potential and deposition type (continuous constant voltage electrodeposition (CVE) and single step pulsed voltage electrodeposition (PVE)) for photoelectrochemical water splitting application.

Tungsten trioxide (WO₃) thin films were deposited by electrodeposition using Na₂WO₄·2H₂O with deionized water, H₂O₂ and HClO₄ electrolyte solution. The films were coated at deposition potentials varying from 0.5 to 0.7 V versus Ag/AgCl in order to study the effect of the potential and deposition type (CVE, PVE) on the optical (UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer), morphological (SEM and EDX) and Mott-Schottky (M-S) properties of the films. The films were amorphous phase for CVE and monoclinic phase with PVE. The degree of crystallinity increased with deposition potential. It was observed that the pulsed mode produced thinner films with larger grain sizes compared to the continuous mode due to the shorter reaction time. It was observed that the film surface deposited by continuous mode was denser. The band gaps of the films were decreased from 3.40 eV to 3.10 eV with increasing deposition potential. With the M-S measurement (in 0.5 M H₂SO₄) and UV-Vis spectroscopy their energy band diagrams were analyzed in detail.

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Keyword: *electrodeposition, photoanode, thin film*

Improving Thermal Energy Storage in Nano-enhanced Geopolymer Composites Using Phase Change Materials

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With rising cooling energy demand driven by climate change reducing building energy consumption has become increasingly critical. Thermal energy storage (TES) solutions integrated into building materials have attracted growing attention, with phase change materials (PCMs) offering a promising TES strategy. PCMs are organic or inorganic compounds characterized by their high latent heat capacity, enabling them to store substantial amounts of thermal energy during phase transitions. PCMs can be integrated within a binder matrix using various techniques, including impregnation into porous building materials, macro-encapsulation, shape-stabilized PCMs for direct application, and microencapsulation. Among these approaches, microencapsulated PCMs (μ PCMs) have demonstrated particular effectiveness, as they encapsulate the PCM within a protective shell, preventing direct interaction of the core material with the cementitious matrix. When integrated into building envelopes, PCMs absorb and store excess thermal energy during peak heat periods and subsequently release this stored energy when temperatures decrease. This mechanism effectively shifts peak loads and moderates indoor temperatures, enhancing energy efficiency and thermal comfort. A significant challenge with PCMs, however, is their adverse effect on the mechanical strength of composite systems. This study addresses this by developing nano-silica enhanced geopolymer composites with varying amounts of μ PCM. The inherent high mechanical performance of nanosilica-enhanced geopolymer composites mitigates the strength reduction typically associated with μ PCM inclusion. A comprehensive experimental program was conducted to evaluate the fresh and hardened properties of the developed composites with varying μ PCM content. Workability was assessed using standard flow table tests, microstructural features were examined via scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and thermal behavior was characterized through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and transient plane source (TPS) thermal conductivity measurements. The findings suggest that the proposed composite system offers a viable approach for thermally efficient and structurally robust TES-integrated building materials.

Keyword: Thermal energy storage (TES), Phase change materials (PCMs), Geopolymer composites, nanosilica

Antibacterial Potential of MXene@Curcumin Nanocomposites Against Gram-Negative and Gram-Positive Bacteria

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In recent years, the rising incidence of bacterial infections has resulted in the prolonged and unregulated use of antibiotics. This has contributed significantly to the widespread emergence of antibiotic resistance among bacterial strains, thereby diminishing the efficacy of conventional treatment strategies. In light of this growing global health threat, the development of next-generation antibacterial agents that are both highly effective and long-lasting has become imperative.

Photodynamic Therapy (PDT) / Photothermal Therapy (PTT), which utilized light activation mechanisms, have emerged as promising alternatives in this context. In this study, a synergistic antibacterial platform was designed by integrating the high photothermal conversion efficiency of Ti₃C₂T_x MXene with its function as a photosensitizer, resulting in enhanced antibacterial activity. The resulting MXene@curcumin nanocomposite was evaluated for its light-induced antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* strains.

Experimental findings demonstrated that the Ti₃C₂T_x MXene@curcumin nanocomposite possesses potent antibacterial activity under light irradiation, indicating its potential as an effective alternative to combat antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Nevertheless, further in-depth investigations, particularly concerning biocompatibility and cytotoxicity, are essential prior to biomedical applications.

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Keyword: *Mxene, antibacterial affect, curcumin, photodynamic therapy, photothermal therapy*

Carbon Based Stretchable Electronics Inspired by Undulatory Locomotion

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The concept of biomimicry, which involves the emulation of natural structures, has received significant attention for its potential to foster innovation, sustainability, and efficiency. Biomimicry could provide valuable insights and strategies for the development of stretchable electronics applicable in wearables and sensors. The Kirigami designs, renowned for its ability to create intricate patterns through cutting and folding, serves as a versatile method for crafting flexible electronic devices capable of enduring substantial deformation while maintaining functionality. By drawing inspiration from wave-like motion and integrating concepts from kirigami and biomimicry, engineers can design flexible or stretchable structures that emulate the movements of worms and caterpillars, thereby advancing the creation of durable flexible electronics. A specific manufacturing process, known as laser-induced graphene (LIG), has been developed to facilitate the production and fabrication of graphene, offering potential advantages in scalability and production simplification. This study aims to explore the concept of stretchable electronics by incorporating LIG method and biomimetic kirigami designs into novel design concept. LIG characterization was conducted using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersion X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX), Raman Spectroscopy, and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) to analyze its chemical structure, composition, and defects. Mechanical testing was performed on various kirigami-inspired designs, including a novel arrow design developed for this study, to evaluate their mechanical performance. The unique kirigami design was subsequently tested for electrical performance with two different configurations. The novel design exhibited superior mechanical performance compared to other designs, achieving elongation of 100% before failure, which is the maximum elongation among others, following the serpentine pattern. This suggests that a unique biomimetic kirigami design may be suitable for the further manufacturing. Compared to other examples reported in the literature, the novel design showed a resistance change of up to 5% under a strain of 25%, indicating a greater stability in resistance change under stretching. The study also examined proposals to enhance properties and demonstrated the effects of various geometric improvements on mechanical and electrical performance.

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Keyword: *Graphene, Laser Induced Graphene, Sensors, Polymers*

Time-Dependent Morphological and Structural Evolution of Graphene on Copper via APCVD

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Atmospheric pressure chemical vapor deposition (APCVD) is a scalable and cost-effective method for the synthesis of graphene on metal substrates such as copper. In this study, we systematically investigate the time-dependent morphological and structural evolution of graphene grown on copper foils at 1000 °C under controlled APCVD conditions. Growth durations of 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32 minutes were examined to reveal the influence of growth time on graphene domain size, layer number, and quality.

Optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and Raman spectroscopy were employed to characterize the graphene morphology and layer distribution. Early-stage growth (2–4 min) resulted in sparse, isolated nucleation sites with high single-layer graphene (SLG) coverage. As growth time increased, the lateral domain size expanded, but multilayer graphene (MLG) regions emerged due to domain impingement and vertical stacking. By 32 minutes, significant fractions of few-layer (FLG) and multilayer regions were observed, indicating the onset of overgrowth beyond optimal CVD duration.

Raman mapping provided spatial distributions of SLG, FLG, and MLG, correlating 2D/G intensity ratios with layer number. The study highlights the importance of precise growth duration control for achieving uniform, large-area single-layer graphene. These findings offer valuable insights for optimizing APCVD parameters to tailor graphene structure for electronic and optoelectronic applications. (This study is supported by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK), project no: 1919B012424851)

Keyword: *Chemical Vapor Deposition, Graphene, Surface Characterization, Electrical Characterization*

Lateral Atomic Engineering in Graphene: Tailoring Quantum States and Charge Transport Pathways

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Graphene, as a prototypical two-dimensional (2D) material, has redefined performance benchmarks in nanoscale electronics and energy storage due to its exceptional electrical conductivity, mechanical strength, and tunable electronic properties [1,2]. Meanwhile, conventional battery technologies continue to suffer from limitations such as thermal instability, electrochemical degradation, and capacity fading, which hinder their reliability in advanced applications [3]. The unique characteristics of 2D materials—particularly high surface area, chemical robustness, and superior charge-carrier mobility—position graphene as a promising platform for addressing these challenges.

However, realizing graphene's full potential in energy systems requires precise, site-specific control over electronic and ionic transport at the atomic scale—an unmet challenge in current fabrication techniques. Recent advances in Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)-based nanolithography, specifically local anodic oxidation (LAO) under controlled humidity, enable resist-free, low-damage patterning of graphene with nanometer precision [4]. In this study, we employ LAO to selectively cleave C–C (sp^2) bonds, allowing us to cut graphene into customized geometries and introduce controlled defect sites.

We demonstrate a fabrication strategy in which gate-like nanostructures are defined within monolayer graphene and subsequently functionalized with heteroatoms such as boron and nitrogen (B–N) or integrated with complementary 2D materials. These hybrid junctions exhibit voltage-dependent modulation of local charge carrier dynamics, enabling programmable control of electron and ion transport in a solid-state energy storage environment. By reconfiguring graphene's atomic lattice and bonding orientations, we achieve spatially resolved control of transport phenomena relevant to logic-integrated storage functions.

Our approach introduces a scalable and reproducible pathway for atomic-level engineering of 2D materials, opening new possibilities for next-generation energy storage platforms that couple dynamic electronic tunability with high ionic conductivity. This work underscores the synergy between AFM nanofabrication and 2D material heterostructuring in creating adaptive, atomically precise functional devices.

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Keyword: *graphene, transport, programmable matter, nanolithography*

Spontaneously Sodium-Intercalated Ultra-Thin MnO₂ Nanosheets for Ionic Charge Transport and Neuromorphic Applications

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Layered manganese oxides are promising candidates for applications involving ionic motion, such as neuromorphic devices and ion-based charge transport systems [1, 2]. In this work, we present the synthesis of ultra-thin, single-crystalline MnO₂ nanosheets with intrinsically intercalated Na⁺ ions, achieved through a molten-salt-assisted chemical vapor deposition method. This in situ intercalation approach leads to the formation of a well-ordered δ-MnO₂ phase (birnessite-type) during growth, eliminating the need for post-synthetic ion insertion. Comprehensive structural analysis, including XRD, Raman spectroscopy, and TEM, reveals high crystallinity and confirms Na⁺ incorporation. We demonstrate that ambient humidity significantly influences the ionic mobility, enhancing the electrochemical behavior. Furthermore, two-terminal devices fabricated with these nanosheets exhibit ionic hysteresis and memory effects under an applied electric field, supporting their potential for neuromorphic and ionotronic applications. These findings not only offer a new route to synthesize layered materials with built-in ionic conductivity but also highlight the broader applicability of Na-MnO₂ beyond conventional energy storage.

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Keyword: *Layered materials, Na-MnO₂, Molten-salt-assisted synthesis, Ionic transport*

Enhanced Interlayer Exciton Dynamics in Free-Standing MoSe₂-WSe₂ Heterobilayers

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Atomically thin transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) and their van der Waals (vdW) heterostructures emerged as a new class of two-dimensional semiconductors, owing to their remarkable optical, mechanical, and electronic properties. The reduced dielectric screening and large effective masses in these materials give rise to strong Coulomb interactions between charge carriers. When these monolayers are vertically stacked, the resulting type-II band alignment facilitates the formation of spatially indirect interlayer excitons (IXs) between different monolayers. Nevertheless, fabricating these heterostructures on conventional substrates may introduce undesirable effects, such as defects, strain, unintentional doping, and interfacial traps, which create new non-radiative recombination pathways for excitons, thereby quenching their photoluminescence (PL) intensity, altering their lifetimes, and broadening the excitonic spectral linewidths. To mitigate the substrate-induced effects, we fabricated free-standing heterobilayers of WSe₂-MoSe₂ on microfabricated holes to isolate them from the substrate interactions and probe their intrinsic properties. Low-temperature measurements from the heterobilayer region revealed that, despite the suppressed intralayer exciton emission from both the suspended and supported regions, the IX emission is enhanced in the suspended region, with a fourfold increase. Pump power-dependent studies on IXs further confirmed that suspended heterostructures exhibit higher PL intensity and reduced spectral broadening (FWHM) compared to their supported counterparts. Finally, our time-resolved PL experiments showed slower decay dynamics of IXs from the suspended heterostructures compared to the supported areas, suggesting the suppression of non-radiative recombination channels. In conclusion, isolating TMD heterostructures from substrate-induced effects preserves their intrinsic properties, which is critical for a high-performance quantum photonic application.

Keyword: *Transition Metal Dichalcogenides, Interlayer Excitons, Free-Standing TMD Heterostructures*

Uncovering Reaction Mechanisms And Intermediates: A Metadynamics Study Of Ethylene Glycol Dissociation On Silver (111) Surfaces

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Understanding molecule–surface interactions at the atomistic level is essential for elucidating reaction mechanisms and identifying key intermediates in catalytic systems. However, the heavy computational demand of such calculations present important challenges in mapping the entire reaction mechanism. In this study, we investigate the adsorption behavior and dissociation dynamics of ethylene glycol on Ag(111) surfaces using molecular dynamics simulations. ReaxFF-based [1] simulations were performed in the NVT ensemble at different temperatures and Ag surface sizes to assess the landscape of intermediates. We apply well-tempered metadynamics [2] enables the system to escape local minima and explore rare pathways without having to increase the temperature to unrealistically high values.

In our metadynamics calculations, the collective variables were defined as key internal bond distances (C–H and C–C) within the two CH₂OH groups of ethylene glycol. By positioning the molecule at controlled distances (e.g., ~2-3 Å) from the Ag surface, we observed different dissociation patterns. In one case, a hydrogen atom dissociates and one hydroxyl group binds to the surface while the other remains elevated. Upon applying metadynamics, an additional rare event is captured: a hydrogen atom from the upward-facing hydroxyl group also dissociates, which does not occur in standard dynamics. Once the intermediates are identified, they are then recalculated using higher-accuracy density-functional theory methods.

Overall, our findings reveal distinct binding modes and rare dissociation events that depend on both simulation conditions and collective variable-driven sampling. This work contributes to the understanding of possible reaction intermediates and surface-mediated transformation mechanisms of diol molecules on metal surfaces.

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Keyword: *ethylene glycol, Ag(111), molecular dynamics, metadynamics*

Predicting NEXAFS Spectra Using Machine Learning and TD-DFT Calculations

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Near Edge X-Ray Absorption Fine Structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopy provides critical insights into the electronic structures of materials; however, experimental acquisition using synchrotron radiation is costly and logistically challenging. Numerical simulations using Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) offer an alternative, yet demand extensive computational resources. This project aims to overcome these limitations by developing an efficient machine learning (ML) model trained on TD-DFT-generated spectra.

In this work, we have selected approximately 850 molecules from the Materials Project database, filtering for those containing exactly one diamagnetic metal atom (Mg), with sizes restricted to ≤ 30 atoms. Geometry optimization and subsequent TD-DFT calculations targeting the Mg 1s molecular orbital were executed using ORCA software on the TRUBA supercomputer. Using regression ML algorithms and local descriptors, we were able to devise a way to predict the fundamental aspects of the full spectra without having to perform the full NEXAFS calculations.

Ongoing efforts include expanding the dataset to several thousand spectra to improve the ML model's performance and further optimization of algorithms. Achieving accurate ML predictions will substantially reduce computational costs and broaden the applicability of NEXAFS analyses, benefiting material sciences research and industrial applications.

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Keyword: NEXAFS, quantum-chemistry, TD-DFT, molecular-physics

Modeling Cross-Linked PVA Nanogels Using LAMMPS: Insights into Structure-Property Relationships

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Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) nanogels are cross-linked elastic polymer networks bearing sizes less than 100 nm. These gels are widely used in drug delivery agents and wound dressing applications due to their hydrophilic, biodegradable, and biocompatible properties [1]. It is important to understand the relationship between the molecular structure and nanoscopic properties of these hydrogels for better and more suited applications. These advancements can also be useful for the development of nanogels for biosensing and other advanced biomedical applications. This study introduces a computational approach to simulate the effects of polymer chain length, crosslink density, and changes in the environmental conditions, such as temperature or ionic strength of the solvent, on nanogel properties such as mechanical properties, swelling, and water diffusion. A detailed atomistic model of the cross-linked hydrogel is used to understand the interactions between polymer chains and solvent molecules. For this purpose, borax cross-linked three PVA chains with different number of repeating units, modelled with variable cross-linking density. This mesh structure is used to understand cross-linked PVA behavior under different physical conditions. The molecular dynamic simulations were held with LAMMPS to model the behavior of cross-linked PVA nanogel networks under various conditions. Water molecule dynamics within the nanogel matrix highlight the influence of network architecture on diffusion behavior, which is critical for applications such as drug delivery and tissue scaffolding. This study provides a computational framework for simulating PVA nanogels through molecular-level insights, enabling more efficient design strategies for specialized applications. Future work will focus on validating these results experimentally to further refine hydrogel performance optimization strategies.

Keyword: *polyvinyl alcohol, molecular dynamic simulation, PVA nanogel, cross-linked polymer network*

Investigating the Behavior of Lamina Associated Domains (LADs) in Cell Nucleus

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Genomic organization in the nucleus is highly crucial for a healthy cell as this organization is directly responsible for gene regulation and control of gene expression programs. The dysfunctionality of the cells in most genetic disorders and cancer types has been directly related to the disordered genomic organization by experimental studies. Recently, it has been reported that molecular-scale disorders in the chromatin near the nuclear periphery (i.e., Lamina Associated Domains or LADs) can affect the genomic organization and gene regulation in the nucleus, but underlying mechanisms are poorly understood. LADs are large heterochromatic regions that are positioned near the nuclear lamina (NL). In previous experimental studies, transcriptional proteins functional in gene expressions and RNA Polymerase enzymes have been observed very little in the peripheral chromatin [1,2], suggesting that a non-specific property of LADs can limit the presence of some molecules near the nuclear boundary.

In this work, we model interactions between transcriptional protein and LAD by employing polymer physics concepts and exploring their structural functionality. LADs in human cells can be modeled as random diblock copolymers attracted to a stationary surface that represents the nuclear lamina. [3] The resulting polymer layer hinders the adhesion of large molecules to the surface while allowing smaller molecules to approach the surface. Furthermore, small molecules near the surface can diffuse through dense layers of heterochromatin, albeit with a lower probability, highlighting transcriptional tunneling near the LADs. Overall, our results demonstrate that LADs can act as a steric filter that only allows certain sizes of molecules to diffuse to the nuclear lamina, consistent with experimental studies. [4] This model would enlighten the role and functionality of LADs in genomic organization and would be beneficial in explaining the underlying mechanisms of genetic disorders and most cancer types.

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Keyword: lamina associated domains, nucleus, polymer model, heterochromatin

Design and Characterization of Polydopamine-Coated Halloysite Nanotubes as a Potential Carrier for 5-Fluorouracil

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Cancer remains a serious global health problem, prompting ongoing efforts to develop more effective and targeted treatment strategies. While chemotherapy is still widely used, its lack of selectivity and associated systemic toxicity can lead to severe side effects and reduced patient quality of life. To overcome these limitations, polymer-based drug delivery systems offer promising solutions by enabling controlled and site-specific drug release [1,2].

In this study, a novel drug delivery system was designed using halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) coated with polydopamine (PDA), a biocompatible and multifunctional polymer. The PDA layer was formed through the oxidative self-polymerization of dopamine under alkaline conditions, resulting in a stable and reactive HNT@PDA nanocarrier. Hansen Solubility Parameters, calculated via the HSPiP software, were utilized to predict the compatibility between PDA and various antineoplastic drugs, leading to the selection of 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) as the model compound for conjugation.

The PDA-HNT-5FU conjugate was synthesized and characterized using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and both ^1H and ^{19}F Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. These techniques confirmed the successful surface modification of HNTs with PDA and the subsequent conjugation of 5-FU.

Overall, the results indicate that PDA-coated HNTs may hold promise as a biocompatible and adaptable platform for further exploration in targeted cancer drug delivery applications.

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Keyword: 5-Fluorouracil, halloysite nanotubes, polydopamine, polymer-drug conjugation

Machine Learning-Assisted SERS for the Early Diagnosis of Antimicrobial Resistance

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in bacteria poses a significant global threat to public health, currently contributing to approximately 700,000 deaths annually—a number projected to rise to 10 million by 2050 if effective interventions are not implemented. Among the most concerning organisms are the ESKAPE pathogens: *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* species. To overcome the AMR threat, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) which is based on interaction of nanoparticles and analyte has emerged as a promising analytical method for the rapid and sensitive detection of these resistant microorganisms. The significant molecular similarity of the bacterial strains makes it difficult to distinguish between antibiotic-resistant and susceptible bacteria using SERS spectra. The combination of machine learning algorithms into SERS improves its diagnostic potential[1]. Machine learning methods can assess complex SERS spectra, allowing for more accurate classification of bacterial species and their resistance profiles. In this study, we investigated strains of *E. faecium*, *S. aureus*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *P. Aeruginosa* bacteria among ESKAPE bacteria that are resistant or susceptible to different antibiotics. SERS spectra collected using AgNP-based SERS substrate were classified using machine learning methods such as Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression[2,3,4,5]. Among the ESKAPE bacteria different antibiotic resistant/ susceptible *S. aureus*, we achieve an outstanding classification accuracy of 96.4%, notably with the kNN algorithm. Our findings address the critical need for new approaches to address AMR using SERS-combined machine learning. This study offers light on how to handle the multiple issues presented by AMR, as well as its significant public health implications.

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Keyword: *Antimicrobial Resistance, Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy, Machine Learning, ESKAPE*

Ag and ZnO Nanoparticles Modified Superhydrophobic Activated Carbon Fabrics for Microbial, Chemical and Electromagnetic Protective Clothing with SERS Analysis Capability

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Activated carbon-based materials are frequently used to capture and remove gases, chemicals, and toxic particles due to their high adsorption capacity. Due to these properties, activated carbon fabric protects against chemical hazards in military protective clothing, but it does not provide sufficient protection against biological and electromagnetic attacks. Furthermore, the instantaneous identification of agents used in chemical and biological attacks on military protective clothing is also crucial. In this study, superhydrophobic PDMS modified Ag@ZnO nanocomposite was produced as new multifunctional coating material to coat the activated carbon fabric. The new Ag and ZnO nanoparticles modified superhydrophobic activated carbon fabrics showed 6 different functions including (i) superhydrophobicity to prevent wetting and contamination (ii) photocatalyst for degradation of organic pollutants, enabling a self-cleaning protective mat, (iii) antimicrobial agent for killing of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, (iv) blocking the passage of electromagnetic radiation, (V) chemical adsorption and (vi) reusable surface-enhanced Raman scattering substrate for quantitative analysis of trace pollutants on the surface. This new material has significant potential in military protective clothing applications.

Self-Healing/Injectable Composite Chitosan Hydrogels for Wound Healing Applications

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Development of injectable and self-healing chitosan hydrogels cross-linked with vitamin B6 presents a promising approach for wound healing applications. Chitosan, a biocompatible and biodegradable polysaccharide [1], was dissolved in dilute acetic acid to prepare 3% and 4% (w/v) polymeric solutions. Crosslinking with B6 was achieved at two different chitosan-to-vitamin B6 weight ratios (4:1 and 2:1) to form three hydrogel formulations. Schiff base linkages between the aldehyde group of pyridoxals and the amine groups of chitosan were exploited to establish covalent bonding and promote self-healing capacity [2,3]. The manufactured hydrogels were characterized using FTIR, SEM, UV-Vis spectroscopy, and biological activity assays. FTIR demonstrated the Schiff base formation, confirming B6-induced cross-linking. SEM pictures revealed a porous structure suitable for exudate absorption and cell infiltration. UV-Vis analysis of Xerogels in SBF (pH=7.4) confirmed effective incorporation and controlled release of vitamin B6. Furthermore, antibacterial testing against *Escherichia coli* showed notable inhibition of bacterial growth, indicating the hydrogels' potential as active wound dressings. The findings suggest that the 4% chitosan with a 4:1 vitamin B6 ratio formulation provided optimal structural and functional performance. These chitosan-vitamin B6 hydrogels represent a promising approach for bioactive wound care materials with enhanced healing, antibacterial, and injectable properties.

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Keyword: *chitosan, vitamin B6, hydrogel, self-healing*

Synthesis of SiO₂ Thin Films by RF Magnetron Sputtering and Investigation of Their Anti-Fogging Performance

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In this study, durable and high-performance SiO₂ thin films were produced on soda lime glass (SLG) substrates by reactive magnetron sputtering at various RF powers to provide a permanent solution to the fogging problem. The main objective was to clarify the effects of sputtering parameters on surface morphology, hydrophilicity, anti-fogging characteristics, and to determine the optimal film design. Five different samples (a–e) were comprehensively characterized by SEM for surface features, ATR-FTIR and Raman spectroscopy for molecular and crystal structure, contact angle measurements for wettability, UV-Vis spectroscopy for optical transmittance, and profilometry for accurate film thickness determination.

Profilometry analysis revealed that sputtering conditions strongly affected thickness, ranging from 26 nm to 75 nm. Contact angle measurements demonstrated hydrophilic performance for all samples (20.53° to 34.61°), with the best anti-fog and hydrophilic properties observed for sample (e), featuring a combination of 100W Si buffer and 85W SiO₂ layer, 44 nm thickness, a highly uniform and smooth surface (SEM), and a strong silanol (Si-OH) peak at 917 cm⁻¹ (FTIR). In contrast, higher total RF power (100W Si + 100W SiO₂) resulted in increased film thickness (75 nm, sample c), but also higher contact angle due to internal stress and a decrease in performance. Notably, sample (d) displayed significant surface cracks and defects in SEM, but still showed a low contact angle, suggesting that surface roughness can sometimes enhance hydrophilicity beyond predictions of the classical Wenzel model due to increased capillary action. UV-Vis measurements confirmed over 98% optical transmittance for all films, supporting their suitability for advanced antireflective and optical device applications. Overall, these findings highlight that fine-tuning sputtering power, layer structure, and microstructural parameters is critical to optimizing the anti-fogging and hydrophilic performance of SiO₂ thin films. This work demonstrates that functional layer design and precise process control enable the scalable production of long-lasting, high-transparency, anti-fog coatings for use in optics, photovoltaics, and other high-tech industries.

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Keyword: *Anti-Fogging, SiO₂ Thin Film, Reactive Magnetron Sputtering, Raman Spectroscopy, ATR-FTIR, SEM, Contact Angle Measurement, Profilometry, UV/Vis Spectroscopy*

A Newly Developed Amperometric Immunosensor for the Detection of *Bacillus anthracis* Spores

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Bacillus anthracis is one of the most dangerous biological warfare agents [1]. They are easy to produce and store and are highly resistant to environmental conditions such as sunlight and temperature. It has been discovered that *Bacillus anthracis* spore forms are highly resistant and immobile structures compared with the bacterium forms. Due to its biological warfare importance, the fast and sensitive detection of its spores is crucial [2]. Several biosensor methods are being developed to detect *B. anthracis* spores, except for commercial detection methods. Especially, electrochemical immunosensors take the most significant part of this area [3]. Amperometric biosensors are based on monitoring the current change measured by taking the counter electrode value against the reference electrode of the reduction and oxidation reaction resulting from the direct current applied to the working electrode [4]. Electrochemical immunosensors are techniques that immobilize primary antibodies on the printed electrode surface. After the antigen binds to the primary antibody, the final step is performed with the enzyme-labeled secondary antibody. When the substrate specific to the labeled enzyme is given to the medium, enzymatic activation measurements can be made with the help of the printed electrode [5]. Combining magnetic beads and screen-printed electrodes becomes an indispensable system with electrochemical detection methods. Magnetic beads, which are magnetic nanoparticles, have become essential in biosensors, mainly due to their magnetizability and large surface area [6].

In our study, a newly developed amperometric immunosensor was designed to detect *B. anthracis* spores with magnetic beads and multiplex screen-printed electrodes. In this research, changes in current intensity resulting from oxidation and reduction in the working electrode are directly measured in relation to the spore concentrations. In addition, signals from amperogram curves were used to draw standard graphics in inactive and live spore concentrations. A standard curve was formed in the method by testing the number of inactive and active spores between 5×10^2 - 1×10^5 spores/ml and 2×10^2 - 2×10^4 spores/ml concentrations, respectively. The monoclonal antibody (SA26) conjugated magnetic nanoparticles and the SA27-HRP antibody were used to design the immunosensor. TMB and H_2O_2 were used as HRP substrates. Current changes were taken under an applied potential, and LOD and LOQ values were found as 450 and 722 spores/ml for inactive and 92 and 272 spores/ml for live spores, respectively. *Bacillus anthracis* spore biosensor results against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Bacillus thuringiensis* spores (1×10^4 spores/ml) were also studied under conditions where the Anthrax spore standard curve was obtained. No cross-reactions were seen for these *Bacillus* types.

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Keyword: *Bacillus Anthracis, Magnetic Beads, SPE, Amperometric immunosensor*

A Nanoplasmonic Sensor Array Fabricated with Protein A-Modified Gold Nanoparticles for Label-Free Sensing

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Nanoplasmonic sensors provide high sensitivity and label-free detection, making them ideal for monitoring a wide range of biomolecular interactions. In this study, we report the development of a gold nanoparticle (AuNP)-based nanoplasmonic biosensor within a 96-well plate format. The platform was created by functionalizing AuNPs deposited on the well surfaces with 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) and Protein A. This surface chemistry is designed to enable the specific and oriented immobilization of antibodies for subsequent biodetection.

The fabrication process involved the formation of a self-assembled monolayer (SAM) of MUA on AuNPs, followed by the activation of terminal carboxyl groups. Protein A was then covalently conjugated to the activated surface to facilitate oriented antibody binding. Each step of the surface modification and subsequent molecular binding events was characterized by monitoring the shifts in the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) peak using UV-Vis spectrophotometry.

Our results demonstrate that the functionalized wells exhibit significant and predictable LSPR shifts upon biomolecular recognition, confirming the successful surface modification and the platform's viability for label-free detection. This system offers a cost-effective, scalable, and versatile tool for high-throughput bioanalysis.

Further optimization of key parameters, including incubation times, pH conditions, and blocking steps, is currently in progress to enhance sensor performance. This approach holds significant promise for future applications in diagnostics and advanced biosensing technologies.

Keyword: *Gold nanoparticles, Nanoplasmonic sensor, 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid, Protein A*

Chiral Gold Nanoparticle-Coated Substrates for Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy Analysis of Extracellular Vesicles

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This study focuses on developing a chiral plasmonic platform based on surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) for the sensitive detection and characterization of extracellular vesicles (EVs) isolated from body fluids. EVs are nanoscale particles carrying biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, and proteins, and serve as promising biomarkers for early disease diagnosis due to their role in cellular communication and their reflection of cellular states. Raman spectroscopy allows rapid, label-free, and non-destructive analysis of EV molecular content. However, Raman signals are inherently weak; therefore, this study employs chemically modified glass or silicon substrates coated with chiral gold nanoparticles to significantly enhance signal intensity and enable high-efficiency EV capture. The use of chiral nanoparticles improves diagnostic specificity by distinguishing structural differences in chiral biomolecules such as proteins and lipids between healthy and diseased states. EVs isolated from serum samples will be analyzed using confocal Raman microscopy to obtain detailed molecular fingerprints. Ultimately, this work seeks to establish a non-invasive, label-free, highly specific platform for detecting disease-specific biomarkers, with promising applications in early diagnosis of complex diseases such as cancer. The platform's adaptability to various biological samples and clinical settings is expected to bring new advances to biomedical diagnostics.

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Keyword: *chirality, gold nanoparticles, SERS, Raman*

Antibiofilm Activity of Boron-Doped Biphasic Calcium Phosphates: Role of Boron Content and Synthesis Approach

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Calcium phosphate-based ceramics, especially hydroxyapatite (HA) and tricalcium phosphate (TCP), are widely utilized in biomedical fields due to their excellent performance. When combined, these materials form biphasic calcium phosphates (BCPs), which exhibit superior bioactivity and bone regeneration capabilities compared to either HA or β -TCP alone. Recent studies have demonstrated that the addition of trace elements can further enhance the biological properties of BCPs. Among these elements, boron (B) has attracted attention for its ability to promote bone formation and accelerate tissue repair. In this study, B-doped BCP powders were synthesized using two different approaches: the solid-state method and the wet chemical method. The resulting powders were compacted into pellets (10 mm diameter, 4 mm height) at 80 MPa for 1 minute using a manual universal press, followed by sintering at 1200 °C for 2 hours. The antimicrobial potential of the sintered samples was assessed by investigating their antibiofilm activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Although no significant difference was observed between the two fabrication methods in terms of antibiofilm performance, the incorporation of B notably reduced biofilm formation, indicating that these materials may help mitigate implant-related infections while supporting bone tissue regeneration.

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Keyword: antibiofilm activity, boron, Hydroxyapatite, biphasic calcium phosphate (BCP)

Electrochemical Sensor for Sensitive Detection of the Antiviral Drug Famciclovir via Nanoparticle-Modified Molecularly Imprinted Polymer-Reinforced

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Famciclovir (FCV) is a guanine analog antiviral prodrug that is converted by 1st pass metabolism into the active drug penciclovir. It is successfully used for the treatment of herpes simplex virus (HSV-1), (HSV-2) and varicella zoster virus.¹ This study presents the development of a novel electrochemical sensor utilizing molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) technology obtained by electrochemical polymerization technique. Cu and PEDOT nanoparticles were used to enhance the sensor performance. The FCV@MIP/Cu-PEDOT/GCE sensor exhibited high sensitivity and selectivity for FCV detection, and its working range was determined as 1×10^{-14} M - 1×10^{-13} M. The LOD and LOQ value of developed sensor was 2.4×10^{-15} M and 7.2×10^{-15} M, respectively. The selectivity of the sensor was evaluated using differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) and recovery rates in the presence of these interferences were determined. The recovery values for the FCV@MIP/Cu-PEDOT/GCE sensor ranged from 98.70% to 102.42%, indicating that interferences had little or no effect on the sensor's ability to detect FCV. Also, the results of the study demonstrate that the interfering substances had minimal impact on the sensor's performance, confirming its high selectivity and reliability. The selectivity of the developed sensor surface was evaluated in a competitive solution environment. This confirmed that there was no significant difference between the results of the solution containing only FCV and solutions of molecules with similar structure, and that the developed sensor surface exhibited high selectivity even in a competitive solution environment.

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Keyword: Famciclovir, molecularly imprinted polymer, determination, voltammetry

Prediction of Macroscopic Properties of Nanocomposites from Micrographs Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks

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Understanding the link between nanoscale structure and macroscale behavior is key to advancing nanocomposite materials. In this study, we present ScEMNet, a custom-designed deep convolutional neural network that predicts the macroscopic mechanical properties of aramid nanofiber (ANF) nanocomposites directly from SEM and TEM images. The model is trained to distinguish between samples containing different NaCl molarities (0, 10, 50, 100 mM), which are known to affect fiber interaction and composite performance [1].

ScEMNet features a streamlined architecture with only 1 million parameters across 23 layers, enabling efficient deployment in resource-constrained research settings. Despite its minimal size, it achieves classification accuracy on par with heavier models like ResNet50 and DenseNet201. The training protocol included repeated data splits and cross-validation to ensure robustness and statistical reliability.

Our findings suggest that the model leverages microstructural cues such as void size, node-to-edge ratios, and fiber-void density. These insights point toward potential structure-property relationships that can be further explored using explainable AI techniques. This approach offers a promising path toward data-driven materials characterization, allowing researchers to bridge the gap between nanoscale imaging and bulk property prediction.

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Keyword: *Deep Learning, Nanomaterials, Artificial Intelligence, Transfer Learning*

Europium-Based Rare-Earth Metal Complexes: Promising Emitters for High-Performance Organic Light-Emitting Diodes

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Organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) based on rare-earth complexes have garnered substantial interest due to their unique advantages, including element-specific emissions, enhanced efficiency through the antenna effect, simultaneous emissions enabling white light production, low energy consumption, high thermal stability, and tunable optoelectronic properties. In this work, europium (Eu)-based rare-earth metal complexes incorporating imidazole-based ligands (L1, L2, and L3) were synthesized and used as emissive layer materials for OLED applications. Electrochemical characterization via cyclic voltammetry revealed different energy levels: L1 displayed HOMO and LUMO levels of -5.94 eV and -2.87 eV, respectively, whereas Eu-(L1)₃ exhibited HOMO and LUMO levels of -5.98 eV and -2.91 eV. Similarly, the ligand L2 and its corresponding europium complex, Eu-(L2)₃, showed HOMO/LUMO levels of $-5.81/-2.65$ eV and $-6.07/-2.90$ eV, respectively. Ligand L3 exhibited HOMO/LUMO levels of $-5.96/-2.79$ eV, while Eu-(L3)₃ showed levels at $-5.98/-2.82$ eV.

OLED devices with an architecture of ITO/HAT-CN/TAPC/EML/TPBi/LiF-Al were fabricated, and their electroluminescent properties were systematically investigated. The optimized OLED device demonstrated a turn-on voltage of 3.14 V, a maximum luminance (L_{max}) of 15,378 cd/m², and a maximum current efficiency (CE_{max}) of 5.29 cd/A. The device also achieved chromaticity coordinates (CIE x,y = 0.28,0.41) and a peak external quantum efficiency (EQE_{max}) of 0.99%. These results highlight the potential of europium-based complexes in OLED technology, highlighting the importance of precise molecular engineering for enhanced device performance.

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Keyword: OLED Applications, RARE-EARTH METAL COMPLEXES

Temperature Effects on Phase Evolution and Particle Morphology in Ce-Rich Commercial NdFeB Magnets During High-Pressure Hydrogen Decrepitation

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NdFeB magnets are essential to clean energy and advanced technological applications due to their superior magnetic properties. However, the availability of rare earth elements is susceptible to geopolitical and environmental challenges. The recycling of NdFeB permanent magnets from secondary sources represents a strategic approach to mitigate this supply risks associated with critical raw materials, particularly Neodymium (Nd) and Dysprosium (Dy). Among the available recycling techniques, Hydrogen Decrepitation (HD) has demonstrated significant potential for the efficient recovery of these elements from commercial magnets. This study investigates the effect of temperature during high pressure hydrogen decrepitation on the structural, microstructural, and compositional evolution of a commercial NdFeB magnet with relatively high Ce content, which is confirmed by inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES) analysis provided baseline compositional data for the starting material. Experiments were performed at 9 bar hydrogen pressure under constant conditions of time, with three processing temperatures investigated (25 °C, 50 °C, and 75 °C). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the initial magnet illustrated Ce-rich phases, while X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the presence of CeFe₂. According to XRD results, main RE₂Fe₁₄B phase transformed RE₂Fe₁₄BH_x hydride phase after hydrogenation process. However, the CeFe₂ peaks disappeared, indicating amorph phase transformation. In addition to hydride phase and CeFe₂ phase, the presence Nd₂O₃ phase was detected. LECO elemental analysis was performed to quantify the amount of the oxygen and hydrogen inside hydrogenated powders. These results confirm the presence of oxide and hydrides with different amount. The results demonstrated that powders processed at 75 °C retained higher oxygen levels compared to those treated at 25 °C and 50 °C. This behaviour is attributed to less efficient hydrogen desorption and increased surface oxidation caused by extensive fragmentation. Furthermore, higher processing temperatures produced more agglomerated morphologies with limited cracking, lowering surface reactivity. Overall, the study highlights the effect of temperature on particle morphology, particle fragmentation, and oxidation behaviour during HD. These insights provide valuable guidance for the optimization of NdFeB magnet recycling and reprocessing strategies.

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Keyword: NdFeB magnets, hydrogen decrepitation, recycling

(* Nanotribological Properties of Twisted Bilayer Graphene

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Besides being one of the oldest scientific curiosities for centuries, today we still lack a complete understanding of dry friction. While the characteristics of friction force between two surfaces in macro-scale and nano-scale systems are quite different, there are also some commonly observed scale independent emergent phenomena such as stick-slip behaviour which might guide a complete theoretical understanding. In this poster, we present our experimental and theoretical results on tribological properties of twisted bilayer graphene. Experimental and theoretical studies on friction between Silicon atomic force microscope tips and various twisted bilayer graphene structures have been extensively studied. We study the effect of twisting angle as well as the sliding direction on friction coefficients and try to interpret the results theoretically. This work has been supported by Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK-1001) under 1001-the scientific and technological research projects funding program project number: 122F022

Keyword: twisted bilayer graphene, nanotribology, molecular dynamics

(* Solubility Enhancement of Apixaban via PAMAM Dendrimers

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Apixaban is an oral anticoagulant used to reduce the risk of blood clots and stroke. In this study was to enhance the aqueous solubility of Apixaban, an anticoagulant with poor water solubility, through the formation of complexes with poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimers. Amino-terminated (NH₂) PAMAM dendrimers of various generations were synthesized using the microwave-assisted synthesis (MAS) method and characterized by ATR-FTIR, ¹H-NMR, and ¹³C-NMR spectroscopy.

Apixaban–PAMAM complexes were obtained by solvent evaporation in methanol. The formation of the complexes was investigated using UV-Vis spectroscopy, ATR-FTIR, and differential thermal analysis (DTA). ATR-FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of hydrogen bonding and encapsulation interactions between Apixaban and PAMAM. DTA results indicated a transition of Apixaban from a crystalline to an amorphous structure, demonstrating successful encapsulation.

Solubility studies based on the phase solubility method revealed that PAMAM dendrimers significantly enhanced the aqueous solubility of Apixaban on average by approximately 88.5% compared to its solubility in pure water.

In conclusion, the inclusion complexes formed with PAMAM dendrimers present an effective strategy for improving the aqueous solubility of Apixaban and hold promising potential as drug delivery systems.

Keyword: PAMAM, API, Apixaban, Solubility

(*) Magnetic Properties of Magnetic Nanoparticle (Fe₃O₄)-Filled Polyvinylidene Fluoride Nanofibers

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Magnetic nanoparticles (NPs) are increasingly utilized to functionalize polymer nanocomposites due to their unique physical properties. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) is a leading piezoelectric polymer, prized for its flexibility, mechanical strength, and chemical stability, making it ideal for flexible electronics and energy devices. In this study, we embedded magnetic NPs (50–150 nm) into PVDF nanofibers (NFs) under varying stirring times to optimize their structure and performance

Fe₃O₄-doped PVDF NFs were produced by electrospinning technique. The composite NFs were characterized via XRD, FTIR, and SEM to confirm phase composition and morphology. SEM images demonstrated how diameter of NPs Fe₃O₄ changes, and how solution content stirring times affect the homogeneous distribution of NPs into composite NFs. Vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM) revealed key magnetic behaviors: (i) hysteresis loop squareness decreases near room temperature, and (ii) coercivity (H_c) declines with rising temperature. Importantly, the NPs enhanced the β-phase content of PVDF, critical for piezoelectricity. Fe₃O₄ NPs use their electrostatic property to help PVDF attract electrons in the case of Fe₃O₄ doped-PVDF NFs. These magnetic-PVDF NFs exhibit superior electromechanical coupling, enabling efficient mechanical energy harvesting and self-powered sensing.

These magnetic NPs doped-PVDF NFs exhibit superior electromechanical coupling, enabling efficient mechanical energy harvesting and self-powered sensing. This work highlights the potential of magnetic PVDF NFs for wearable electronics (e.g., motion-sensing textiles and health-monitoring patches), biomechanical energy harvesters (cavenging energy from human motion), and smart textiles, advancing multifunctional nanocomposites for next-generation energy Technologies with embedded sensing capabilities. Furthermore, magnetoelastic coupling effect of the NFs provides adjustable sensitivity in the presence of external magnetic fields, which makes them optimal for self-powered strain and pressure sensors that have a quick reaction time and exceptional endurance. The adoption of them in commercial applications is further supported by the cost-effective production ensured by the scalable electrospinning fabrication technology employed.

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Keyword: PVDF, Fe₃O₄, Electrospinning, Piezoelectric

(*) Room-Temperature Interlayer Excitons of MoS₂/WS₂ Hetero-Bilayers Under Ultimate Metallic Screening**Emine Yegin*, Amir Parsi, Doruk Pehlivanoglu, T. Serkan Kasirga***Bilkent University UNAM – Institute of Materials Science and Nanotechnology, Ankara 06800, Türkiye*

Two-dimensional (2D) transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDC) heterostructures, assembled via van der Waals (vdW) stacking, exhibit unique magnetic, electronic, and optical properties that are not present in their bulk counterparts, offering a highly tunable platform for nanoscale device applications. [1]. Owing to their strong Coulomb interactions and type-II band alignment in heterobilayer form, these materials have emerged as a promising platform for studying interlayer excitons [2]. When interlayer coupling in TMDC monolayers stacked on top of each other, spatially indirect excitons can form across the layers, exhibiting extended lifetimes and distinct out-of-plane dipolar characteristics. The optical response of these excitons is strongly influenced by the underlying substrate, particularly in the presence of metallic substrate, where screening effects can either enhance or quench photoluminescence (PL), depending on interfacial conditions. To systematically explore this substrate-dependent behavior, MoS₂/WS₂ heterobilayers were transferred onto different substrates, either dielectric or metallic, and their interlayer exciton emission was examined at room temperature. Particular attention was given to the effect of nanometer-scale interfacial gaps between the TMDC layers and metallic substrates, which can suppress non-radiative recombination by limiting free charge transfer. To promote effective interlayer exciton formation, post-fabrication thermal annealing was applied to enhance interlayer coupling. The impact of substrate type, interfacial gap presence, and annealing conditions on PL intensity and exciton dynamics was systematically investigated. These results provide insight into the critical role of substrate interactions and interface engineering in tailoring the excitonic properties of 2D TMDC heterostructures for optoelectronic applications.

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Keyword: *Interlayer excitons, metallic screening, photoluminescence, 2D transition metal dichalcogenide*

(*) Engineering Spin, Charge and Photoexcited Carriers in Topological Insulators**Doruk Pehlivanoglu*, Talip Serkan Kasirga***Bilkent University UNAM – Institute of Materials Science and Nanotechnology, Ankara 06800, Turkey*

Bi_2Se_3 is a rhombohedral, quintuple-layered van der Waals material that can be mechanically exfoliated to few- or single-layer thickness. As both a narrow-bandgap semiconductor and the archetypal three-dimensional topological insulator, it combines an insulating bulk with time-reversal-protected, massless Dirac surface states exhibiting spin-momentum locking. This unique electronic structure makes Bi_2Se_3 a straightforward platform for studying spintronic phenomena and quantum transport at accessible temperatures. Its inherently low thermal conductivity and high Seebeck coefficient also confer strong thermoelectric performance. Together, these characteristics position Bi_2Se_3 at the cutting edge of condensed-matter research and emerging device applications. Here we discuss how we can control thermal, spintronic and optoelectronic properties together using scanning photocurrent microscope (SPCM) with suspended crystals. This way we can increase the heating efficiency optically and utilize the interconversion between charge, spin and temperature.

References:J. W. McIver et al., *Nature Nanotech* 7, 96 (2011).S. Pournia et al., *Applied Physics Letters* 120, (2022).**Keyword:** *2D materials, Topological insulator*

(* Synthesis and Analysis of Gold Nanoparticles Incorporating Phytochemicals for Targeted Cancer Therapy**Barış Bilge^{* 1}, Zeliha Cansu Canbek², Kutlu Ülgen¹**¹ *Chemical Engineering Department, Bogazici University*² *Materials Science and Nanotechnology Engineering Department, Yeditepe University*

The gold nanoparticle (AuNP) conjugation of drugs is a highly researched topic, while conjugation of phytochemicals has scarcely been done before. The lack of a standardized method for comparison inhibits the possible actualization of new pharmaceuticals from phytochemicals. Therefore, the development of a method to conjugate gold nanoparticles with phytochemicals and their comparison to other cytotoxic chemicals in a bio-conjugated state warrants further research. Notably, to mimic the natural environment in the body, 3D screening of phytochemicals has yet to be conducted in in vitro settings. 3D scaffolds better replicate the natural extracellular matrix, providing a more accurate representation of how cells behave in living tissues and interact with other neighboring cells. In the present research, a comparative cytotoxic analysis of promising natural compounds and established cytotoxic agents (Doxorubicin, etc) conjugated to AuNPs has been performed using melanoma cells in both 2D and 3D models. The gold nanoparticles are synthesized using the inverse Turkevich method and subsequently pegylated. Pegylation serves as both a spacer arm and a functionalization technique for the nanoparticles. Phytochemical compounds are then bioconjugated onto the functionalized nanoparticles. The conjugates' cytotoxicity is analyzed using cell wells (2D) and cell scaffolds (3D) mimicking the tumor's natural microenvironment. 3D models provide more realistic drug responses, improving the predictive accuracy of drug efficacy and toxicity studies. Overall, this research advances cancer therapy options with the goal of developing safer, more effective, and more focused medicines.

Keyword: *Gold Nanoparticles, Cytotoxic Analysis, Bioconjugation, Targeted Drug Delivery*

(*) Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) sensor for residue-free pesticide detection**Sevda Mert ****İstanbul Okan University, İstanbul, Türkiye*

Pesticide contamination poses a significant threat to environmental safety and human health, particularly due to the persistent residues left on agricultural products. In this study, we present a highly sensitive and residue-free detection method using a Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) sensor. The sensor is engineered with a nanostructured metallic substrate designed to amplify Raman signals of trace-level pesticide molecules without the need for complex sample preparation or chemical treatments. By optimizing surface morphology and using a label-free detection approach, the SERS platform achieves rapid, non-destructive, and ultra-low detection limits for commonly used pesticides. Our results demonstrate high reproducibility, specificity, and real-time applicability, suggesting a powerful tool for food safety monitoring and environmental assessment.

Keyword: *Pesticide, SERS, Raman*

(* Targeted Drug Delivery for Breast Cancer Using Chitosan-Coated SPION Core Shell Nanoparticles**Melek İlayda Barut, Eser Damla Birlik, Mert Güngör, Efe İşsevenler, Bahar Küçükoğlu, Metin Şahin, Murat Alp Şahin ****Middle East Technical University Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Ankara, Türkiye*

The growing demand for precise, responsive, and biocompatible cancer therapies has driven interest in nanoscale drug delivery platforms. This study focuses on the development of multifunctional core-shell magnetic nanoparticles Fe₃O₄@CS designed for targeted drug delivery in breast cancer treatment. The magnetic Fe₃O₄ core was synthesized via the co-precipitation method, selected for its superparamagnetic properties, biocompatibility, and scalability. For the outer shell a Chitosan (CS) coating crosslinked with Sodium Tripolyphosphate (TPP) to achieve pH-responsive behavior was used. Extensive characterization was conducted using XRD, FTIR, VSM, UV-Vis spectroscopy, and SEM to verify the crystalline structure, functional groups, magnetic response, morphology, and release kinetics of the nanoparticles. SEM analysis revealed that the bare Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles had an average diameter of 58 ± 10 nm, while the chitosan-coated Fe₃O₄@CS particles showed an increased size of 78 ± 15 nm. Congo red was employed as a model drug for the Fe₃O₄@CS system due to its anionic nature and electrostatic affinity to positively charged chitosan. Release studies revealed that Fe₃O₄@CS nanoparticles demonstrated a sharp pH-responsive release under acidic conditions, mimicking tumor microenvironments. This dual-nanocarrier approach offers a modular solution that can be tuned for different clinical needs. Overall, this platform provides a robust foundation for the future development of advanced, magnetically guided, and tumor-responsive drug delivery systems.

Keyword: *magnetic nanoparticles, Fe₃O₄@CS, pH-responsive drug delivery, Breast cancer*

(*) Investigation of the Crystallization Kinetics of Barium Titanate/PVDF Nanocomposites**Elif Binici^{* 1}, Hande Çelebi²**¹ *Republic of Turkey Ministry of Trade, Ankara, Turkiye*² *Eskişehir Technical University, Eskişehir, Turkiye*

PVDF is a polymorphic, semi-crystalline polymer that can crystallize in at least four distinct phases. Among these, the β -phase is of primary importance due to its high dielectric constant as well as its piezoelectric and pyroelectric properties, which are essential for electronic applications. The β -phase exhibits spontaneous polarization, thereby demonstrating superior ferroelectric and piezoelectric behavior. In order to promote the development of the β phase, high concentrations of additives are often introduced. Within the scope of this research, barium titanate (BT)/polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) nanocomposites were prepared and their structural, morphological, and crystallization properties were investigated. In order to provide homogeneous distribution of BT in PVDF and to increase the polymer matrix interaction, BT nanoparticles were modified with silane (BT-APS) and further modified by coating with polyaniline (PANI) through in situ polymerization process, resulting in BT@PANI core-shell structures.

The nanoparticles were characterized by XRD (X-Ray Diffractometry), FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy), TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy) and TGA (Thermal Gravimetric Analysis) methods. PVDF based nanocomposites were prepared by solution casting method by adding BT, BT-APS and BT@PANI. The structural, physical and morphological properties of the prepared composite films were investigated by XRD, FTIR and morphological analyses. It was proven that all BT-based additives have a reducing effect on PVDF crystallization. According to Avrami kinetic analysis, the Avrami exponent (n) values ranged between 1 and 2, indicating that both neat PVDF and its composites undergo surface nucleation accompanied by one-dimensional crystal growth. Furthermore, activation energy values, calculated using both the Kissinger and Takhor models, increased proportionally with the additive concentration in the composites. The activation energy of pure PVDF is lower than that of composites, indicating that the composites have lower crystallization ability.

Keyword: *Polymer composite, PVDF, Barium titanate, in-situ, non-isothermal crystallization kinetics*

(*) A Self-Healing SPEEK/PVA Membrane With Nafion-Level Proton Conductivity and Extended Lifetime for Cost-Effective PEM Electrolyzers

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The high cost and limited durability of perfluorosulfonic acid membranes such as Nafion remain critical bottlenecks for large-scale deployment of proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWEs) in green hydrogen production. In this study, we report a novel sulfonated poly(ether etherketone)/poly(vinyl alcohol) (SPEEK/PVA) composite membrane that matches Nafion's proton conductivity while significantly extending service life and reducing cost. The membrane leverages a dynamic, reversible hydrogen-bonding network between sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$) groups in SPEEK and hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) groups in PVA, enabling autonomous healing of microcracks under humid, thermal conditions typical of PEMWE operation. This self-repair mechanism enhances membrane resilience against hydration stress, pressure cycling, and chemical degradation, achieving a longer operational lifetime. In addition to robust mechanical and oxidative stability, the membrane exhibits high water uptake and thermal tolerance, maintaining integrity at up to 80 °C. These results suggest that SPEEK/PVA membranes are a promising hydrocarbon-based alternative to fluorinated membranes for next-generation PEM systems. Future work will focus on long-term performance validation under dynamic operating profiles, scale-up of the membrane fabrication process, and integration with advanced catalyst layers to further enhance overall electrolyzer efficiency and stability.

Keyword: *Self-Healing Membrane, Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM), Proton Conductivity*

(*) Copper Metallization for Sustainable N-Type PV Technologies: Damp Heat Analysis

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In the photovoltaic (PV) sector, reducing cost, improving sustainability, and ensuring secure supply chains are essential for the global energy transition. Silver (Ag) has long been the primary metallization material for solar cells due to its high conductivity and industrial reliability. However, silver presents challenges: it is expensive, has limited availability, and its price is highly volatile. According to the ITRPV 2025 roadmap, silver consumption averages around 9 mg/W for PERC, 13.5 mg/W for TOPCon, and 16.7 mg/W for HJT cells. The IEA estimates that PV-related silver demand could double by 2030, increasing both cost and supply chain risks. Copper (Cu) is seen as the most promising alternative. It is about 80 times cheaper, 850 times more abundant, and offers comparable electrical conductivity (1.68 $\mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ vs. 1.59 $\mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ for Ag). However, integrating copper faces technical challenges: it can diffuse into silicon and cause recombination losses, and it is more prone to oxidation and corrosion, affecting long-term performance. The EU-funded COMET (Copper Metallization for Sustainable n-type PV Technologies) project aims to develop and validate copper-based metallization for n-type crystalline silicon TOPCon cells. Within this project, ingots with different resistivities are processed into wafers and shared with partners for pilot-scale trials. The goal is to reduce silver use while maintaining high efficiency and durability. In this study, copper metallization was used for cell interconnection within modules. Ribbon soldering ensured reliable electrical contacts, with no signs of cracking or delamination in the finger or busbar layers, confirming the feasibility of copper in module production. A key part of this work is the Damp Heat (DH) test, which exposes cells to 85 °C and 85% humidity over time. Copper-metallized minimodules were tested at 200, 500, and 1000 hours, alongside silver-based reference modules. This setup allows direct comparison of degradation due to copper diffusion, corrosion, or contact failure. Initial findings show that with proper barrier design, copper can offer performance and reliability similar to silver. DH results support the commercial potential of copper contacts. Replacing silver with copper enables manufacturers to cut costs and reduce risk—without sacrificing efficiency. COMET thus highlights copper metallization as a viable path toward a more resilient and sustainable PV industry.

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